

D3.18 Fourth periodic report on JRP

WP3 Joint Research Projects

Responsible Partner: Sciansano

Contributing partners: ANSES

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	D3.18 Fourth periodic report on JRP		
WP and task	WP3		
Leader	Sciensano		
Other contributors	ANSES		
Due month of the deliverable	M51		
Actual submission month	M51		
Type	R <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>		
Dissemination level	PU <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>		
Dissemination	<p>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</p> <p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>		

Fourth periodic report on ongoing JRPs

1. INTRODUCTION	9
2. SUMMARY OF THE JOINT RESEARCH PROJECTS PERFORMANCE AND PROGRESS BY THE END OF YEAR 3	9
Project deliverables and milestones	9
Publications.....	11
Relevance of the research projects	28
Critical risks.....	30
3. FINAL REPORTS OF THE FIRST ROUND JRP, YEAR 4	32
JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG	32
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out</i>	32
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results</i>	33
WP1. Comparison of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and antibiotic sales/usage (AMU) data collected through existing surveillance, monitoring and research programs and assessment of risk factors.....	33
WP2. Longitudinal studies of persistence ESBL/AmpC/carbapenem/mcr-1/PMQR producing Enterobacteriaceae on farms or hospitals	37
WP3. AMR characterization, transmission of plasmids and fitness of MDR isolates.	43
WP4. Project coordination and management.	53
3. <i>Project self-assessment</i>	54
4. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	55
Deliverables.....	55
Milestones	61
5. <i>Publications and patents</i>	64
Additional output.....	68
Outcomes	70
6. <i>One Health Impact</i>	71
JRP05-ET1-TOX-Detect	72
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out</i>	72
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results</i>	73
WP0. Coordination, management and communication.....	73
WP1. Constitution of a reference strain collection for <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>B. cereus</i> and <i>C. perfringens</i>	74
WP2: Characterization of toxins/virulence factors	75
WP3: Development of Mass Spectrometry-based proteomics procedures for detection of bacterial toxins and virulence factors.....	78
WP4: Development of new immuno-enzymatic assays for detection of <i>S. aureus</i> and <i>B. cereus</i> toxins and virulence determinants.....	80
WP5: Inter-laboratory ring trial scheme	81
WP6: Dissemination, protection and exploitation of results	82
3. <i>Project self-assessment</i>	83
4. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	85
Deliverables.....	85
Milestones	91
5. <i>Publications and patents</i>	94
Additional output.....	96
Outcomes	96
6. <i>One Health Impact</i>	96
JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA.....	97
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out</i>	97
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results</i>	99
WP0. Coordination and project management	99
WP1. Food chain surveillance mapping.....	100
WP2. Analysis of food purchase data	101

WP3. Syndromic surveillance	106
WP4. Spatial risk mapping.....	107
WP5. Evaluation of surveillance programs & cost efficiency	109
3. <i>Project Self-assessment</i>	112
4. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	114
Deliverables.....	114
Milestones	123
5. <i>Publications and patents</i>	127
Additional output.....	130
Outcomes	131
6. <i>One Health Impact</i>	132
JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT	134
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out</i>	134
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results</i>	134
WP0: Coordination (M1-M30)	134
WP1: Constitution of a strains collection representative of the different reservoirs of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> (M1-M12).....	135
WP2: Whole genome sequencing of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> strains (M2-M16).....	143
WP3 Phenotypic characterisation of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> strains (M1-M29)	144
WP4: Identification of genetic traits in <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> underlying adaptation to the ecological niches (M1-M30).....	148
WP5 : Trainings and dissemination (M1-M30).....	150
3. <i>Project Self-assessment</i>	150
4. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	152
Deliverables.....	152
Milestones	157
5. <i>Publications and patents</i>	161
Additional output.....	163
Outcomes	165
6. <i>One Health Impact</i>	166
JRP010-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC	166
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out</i>	166
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results</i>	168
WP0. Management.....	168
WP1. Risk prediction for Super-shedder animals and human asymptomatic carriers through the use of gut microbiota and immune status analyses (M1-M12)	168
WP2. Prevention of the appearance of Super-shedder animals and asymptomatic carriage in humans and animals by modifying feed and/or microbiota (M1-M12)	172
WP3. Modelling the transmission of zoonotic agents to improve intervention strategies on livestock farms (M1-M12).....	175
WP4. Communication and Dissemination for Impact (M1-M12)	177
3. <i>Project Self-assessment</i>	178
4. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	180
Deliverables.....	180
Milestones	191
5. <i>Publications and patents</i>	197
Additional output.....	199
Outcomes	200
6. <i>One Health Impact</i>	201
4. 12-MONTHS REPORTS OF THE SECOND ROUND JRP, YEAR 4.....	202
JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED.....	202
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out in year 4</i>	202
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	203
WP1 - Assess feasibility of Long-read metagenome sequencing on exemplar matrices. Investigate the use of Hi-C metagenomics.	203
WP2 - Bioinformatics tools to analyse the sequencing data and defining the characteristics within the sample.	206

WP3 - Implementation of on-site protocols for long-read metagenomic DNA sequencing.....	210
WP4 - Project management, coordination, and training workshop.	211
3. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	212
Deliverables.....	212
Milestones	219
4. <i>Publications and patents</i>	223
Additional output.....	224
Outcomes	224
5. <i>Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries</i>	224
6. <i>List of critical risks</i>	225
JRP13-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM.....	225
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out in year 4</i>	225
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	226
WP: 1 Generation of up to date sequence information for selected pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes.....	226
WP2: Assay Development.....	228
WP3: Development of Lateral Flow Diagnostics Detection and Mobile Communication system	230
WP4: Evaluation of on-site tests and other tools developed.....	230
WP5: Project Management.....	231
3. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	232
Deliverables.....	232
Milestones	236
4. <i>Publications and patents</i>	237
Additional output.....	238
Outcomes	238
5. <i>Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries</i>	238
6. <i>List of critical risks</i>	239
JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE	239
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out in year 4</i>	239
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	240
WP0 Project management.....	240
WP1 SMRT implementation	241
WP2 Genome studies.....	242
WP3 : Culture-Independent typing and metagenomics	245
WP4 : Functional characterization of AMR mobile genetic elements (MGE)-carrying AMR genes and bacterial host associations.....	246
WP5 : modelling	246
3. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	248
Deliverables.....	248
Milestones	254
4. <i>Publications and patents</i>	258
Additional output.....	259
Outcomes	259
5. <i>Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries</i>	259
6. <i>List of critical risks</i>	259
JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR	259
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out in year 4</i>	259
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	260
WP1: Project Management and Communication	260
WP2: Field experiments: Determination of the naturally occurring ARG background load and microbial biodiversity in the tested environmental compartments (M25-M60).....	262
WP3- Elucidating the role of Clostridium difficile as an ARG transfer platform over ecosystems boundaries and its linkage between human and non-human (zoonotic) reservoirs (M25-M50)	264
WP4- Determination of the selection pressures in the tested compartments of human, animal and environmental ecosystems (M25-M50).....	266

WP5- Identification of environmental conditions modulating transformation frequencies in soil microcosms and an in vitro porcine gut model (poGutMo) (laboratory studies) (M32-M56).....	268
WP6- Probabilistic and mechanistic models of the links between antimicrobial usage in animals, AMR in the environment, and the risks for public health.	270
3. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	272
Deliverables.....	272
Milestones	279
4. <i>Publications and patents</i>	283
Additional output.....	284
Outcomes	285
5. <i>Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries</i>	285
6. <i>List of critical risks</i>	285
JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir.....	285
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out in year 4</i>	285
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	286
WP1: Coordination and data management.....	286
WP2: Development of a Bioinformatics tool-kit for POI data analysis.....	287
3. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	296
Deliverables.....	296
Milestones	299
4. <i>Publications and patents</i>	301
Additional output.....	302
Outcomes	302
5. <i>Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries</i>	303
6. <i>List of critical risks</i>	303
JRP17-ET2.2-IDEMBRU.....	304
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out in year 4</i>	304
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	305
WP1 Recording the situation of brucellosis in emergent wild and environmental reservoirs (M37-M50) .	305
WP2 Recording the situation of brucellosis in humans.....	306
WP3 Genomic characterisation of Brucella detected from samples and selected isolates.....	307
WP4 Phenotypic characterisation of Brucella detected from samples and selected isolates.....	308
WP5 Zoonotic potential and virulence	311
WP6 Development of a toolkit for emerging Brucellosis infections	313
WP7 Coordination, management and communication.....	313
3. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	315
Deliverables.....	315
Milestones	322
4. <i>Publications and patents</i>	328
Additional output.....	329
Outcomes	329
5. <i>Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries</i>	329
6. <i>List of critical risks</i>	329
JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE	330
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out in year 4</i>	330
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	331
WP1. Sampling strategy	331
WP2. Validation of parasitological and molecular assays.....	332
WP3. Development validation of new tools and production of data relevant for epidemiological assessments.....	334
WP4. Training, dissemination and proficiency testing schemes	337
WP5. Scientific and administrative management.....	338
3. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	339
Deliverables.....	339
Milestones	343

4. <i>Publications and patents</i>	345
Additional output	348
Outcomes	348
5. <i>Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries</i>	349
6. <i>List of critical risks</i>	349
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE	349
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out in year 4</i>	349
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	350
WP1-Coordination and impact.....	350
WP2-NGS-based genomics and metagenomics	351
WP3-Design, implementation and validation of multi-locus typing schemes	352
WP4-Parasite enrichment strategies	353
3. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	355
Deliverables	355
Milestones	359
4. <i>Publications and patents</i>	362
Additional output	363
Outcomes	363
5. <i>Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries</i>	363
6. <i>List of critical risks</i>	363
JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR	364
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out in year 4</i>	364
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	365
WP1: Project coordination and administration (M25-60).....	365
WP2: Data: Coordination of data collection (M25-M50).....	365
WP3: Methods: Assessment/improvement (M25-54)	367
WP4. Results – Quantifying the contribution of various sources of foodborne zoonoses and AMR (M30-56)	369
WP5: Conclusions and policy translation (M32-60)	371
4. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	372
Deliverables	372
Milestones	376
5. <i>Publications and patents</i>	379
Additional output	380
Outcomes	381
6. <i>Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries</i>	381
7. <i>List of critical risks</i>	382
JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE	382
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out in year 4</i>	382
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	383
WP1 Project coordination and integration of results (M25-M54).....	383
WP2 Biosecurity effectiveness studies	384
WP3 Impact of disinfection on persistence of pathogens in biofilm	385
WP4 Modelling of the cost and effectiveness of biosecurity measures	386
WP5 Benchmark of biosecurity practice	387
WP6 Dissemination	389
3. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	391
Deliverables	391
Milestones	396
4. <i>Publications and patents</i>	399
Additional output	400
Outcomes	401
5. <i>Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries</i>	402
6. <i>List of critical risks</i>	403

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES	404
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out in year 4</i>	404
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	405
WP1 Coordination and impact	406
WP2 Multicentre quantitative microbiological risk assessment for <i>T. gondii</i> infections	408
WP3 Multicentre survey to fill the key existing gap: role of fresh produce (i.e. Ready-to-Eat salads).....	410
WP4 Serology method based on novel antigens to discriminate <i>T. gondii</i> infections acquired from oocysts	411
WP5 Novel <i>T. gondii</i> typing method to detect within-genotype variation	413
3. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	415
Deliverables	415
Milestones	417
4. <i>Publications and patents</i>	421
Additional output	428
Outcomes	432
5. <i>Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries</i>	433
6. <i>List of critical risks</i>	434
JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS	435
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out in year 4</i>	435
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	436
WP1 Project management.....	436
WP2 Salmonella controls at the primary production level.....	437
WP3 Surveillance, epidemiology and source attribution	439
WP4 Salmonella Genomics	445
WP5 MCDA model to support priority setting	445
3. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	450
Deliverables.....	450
Milestones	453
4. <i>Publications and patents</i>	455
Additional output	456
5. <i>Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries</i>	456
6. <i>List of critical risks</i>	456
JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE.....	456
1. <i>Summary of the work carried out in year 4</i>	456
2. <i>Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes</i>	457
WP1: Typing comparability and nomenclature	457
WP2: Joining molecular and epidemiological methods.....	459
WP3: Storage, management, and sharing for meta- and molecular data	461
WP4: Development of a user-oriented interface (dashboard) for analysis and sharing of epi and molecular data.....	462
WP5: Dissemination, Testing, Evaluation and Sustainability	463
WP6: Management.....	464
3. <i>Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables</i>	466
Deliverables.....	466
Milestones	468
4. <i>Publications and patents</i>	471
Additional output	472
Outcomes	472
5. <i>Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries</i>	472
6. <i>List of critical risks</i>	472

FOURTH PERIODIC REPORT ON JOINT RESEARCH PROJECTS

1. Introduction

The actual document is complementary to the technical part of the One Health EJP Periodic Report, which describes all the activities within the seven work packages of the project. This JRP-specific document contains more details, and is composed of two major parts: final reports of the projects that have come to an end in 2021, and the 12 months reports of the still ongoing JRP.

All publications and deliverables are available through the specific project pages on the One Health EJP website: <https://onehealthjep.eu/projects/>.

2. Summary of the Joint Research Projects performance and progress by the end of year 3

Project deliverables and milestones

PROJET	Number of deliverables expected at M48	Number of available deliverables at M48	Percentage of available deliverables	Number of delayed deliverables
JRP02-ARDIG	17	16	94%	1*
JRP05-TOX-Detect	19	19	100%	0
JRP06-NOVA	34	34	100%	0
JRP07-LISTADAPT	23	23	100%	0
JRP10-MOMIRPPC	31	31	100%	0
JRP12-FARMED	5	1	20%	4
JRP13-WORLDCOM	5	2	40%	3
JRP14-FULL-FORCE	26	15	58%	11
JRP15-FED-AMR	17	6	35%	11
JRP16-TELE-Vir	7	4	57%	3
JRP17-IDEMBRU	9	6	67%	3
JRP18-MEmE	16	8	50%	8
JRP19-PARADISE	8	5	63%	3
JRP20-DISCOVeR	5	3	60%	2
JRP21-BIOPIGEE	13	9	69%	4
JRP22-TOXOSOURCES	6	6	100%	0
JRP23-ADONIS	11	4	36%	7
JRP24-BEONE	6	3	50%	3
TOTAL	258	195	76%	63

* To be disclosed after publication of the related manuscript

The monitoring of the deliverables gives an indication of the progress that projects make. However, the figures should be evaluated in light of the extensions that the projects were given following the COVID-19 crisis. The large majority of the deliverables have been achieved in time. As a first step, the

deliverable is uploaded to the project group on the [OHEJP website](#). Once approved, it is uploaded to [Zenodo](#) in order to comply with the Open Access requirements. Then the link to the deliverable is made available through the Open Access part of the same OHEJP website, on project page (eg. [NOVA project page](#)).

There is however a significant difference between the first round projects (ARDIG, TOX-Detect, NOVA, LISTADAPT, MOMIR-PPC) for which almost all deliverables are available, and the second round (JRP12 to JRP24) where only 72 out of the expected 134 deliverables were uploaded on the website (achievement rate: 54%). In total, at the end of Y4, about three quarter of the deliverables were handed over.

The project leaders indicated in their report and at the occasion of individual contacts, that delays were mainly due to the COVID-19 situation. All project leaders appreciated the possibility to have their project extended to finalize the work under the best possible conditions. On the other hand, this implies that most deadlines for the expected project deliverables were moved towards the new end date, i.e. December 2022. The same observation was noticed with the first round projects that were extended in 2020 (See figure above).

Another reason for the delays is linked to the confidentiality issue: some project leaders are waiting for the approval of their manuscript before disclosing the contents of the deliverables that are associated to that manuscript. In order to avoid having too many delayed deliverables due to confidentiality reasons, Work Package 3 Team have asked the project leaders to provide a first version of the deliverables with the level of details that they find suitable. The final version will replace this first version once the manuscript will be published.

Work Package 3 Team is in frequent contact with the project leaders to obtain the deliverables as planned. This is not only done by mail, but specific TC are also organized to discuss the final reports (and the accompanying outputs and outcome). WP3 is aware of the risk of delayed outputs and therefore a check point is explicitly included in the templates for the 9M, 12M and final reports.

The impact of COVID-19 and, for some projects, the loss of key personnel, is described under the paragraph “Critical risks”.

PROJET	Number of milestones achieved at M48	Nombre of pending milestones at M48	Percentage of achieved milestones
JRP02-ARDIG	16	15	94%
JRP05-TOX-Detect	25	19	76%
JRP06-NOVA	29	29	100%
JRP07-LISTADAPT	24	23	96%
JRP10-MOMIRPPC	38	34	89%
JRP12-FARMED	10	1	10%
JRP13-WORLDCOM	5	3	60%
JRP14-FULL-FORCE	18	7	39%
JRP15-FED-AMR	19	8	42%
JRP16-TELE-Vir	8	1	13%
JRP17-IDEMBRU	23	16	70%
JRP18-MEmE	4	4	100%
JRP19-PARADISE	8	6	75%
JRP20-DISCOVeR	9	7	78%
JRP21-BIOPIGEE	8	7	88%

JRP22-TOXOSOURCES	11	11	100%
JRP23-ADONIS	6	5	83%
JRP24-BeONE	8	4	50%
TOTAL	269	200	74%

The same observation and explanation as for the deliverables applies for the milestones. Obviously, the rate of achieved milestones is higher for the first round projects than for the second round ones:

- First round projects: 120 milestones reached out of 132. Achievement rate: 91%.
- Second round project: 80 milestones achieved out of 137. Achievement rate : 58%.
- The overall rate is 74% (200 milestones achieved out of 269).

Thanks to the six-months no-cost extension until December 2022, it seems reasonable to expect that the second round projects will be able to complete their tasks before the end of the One Health EJP.

Publications

Since the beginning of the programme in 2017, 128 JRPs manuscripts were published in peer-reviewed scientific journals. The JRP publications are listed below. They are sorted by year and by project.

The publications list is publically available through the [One Health EJP webpage](#). On this webpage, there are individual project pages where project information can be found (mainly links to the project publications and deliverables, eg. [NOVA](#)).

One Health EJP yearly publications lists are also available on Zenodo for years [2018](#), [2019](#) and [2020](#).

2018 – 2 publications

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Analysis of consumer food purchase data used for outbreak investigations, a review. Møller FT, Mølbak K, Ethelberg S.

Eurosurveillance. 2018;23(24). doi:10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2018.23.24.1700503

https://zenodo.org/record/3747633#.XpCQ_sgzZM0

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Identification of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella quasipneumoniae*, *Klebsiella variicola* and Related Phylogroups by MALDI-TOF Mass Spectrometry.

Rodrigues C, Passet V, Rakotondraso A, Brisse S.

Front Microbiol. 2018;9:3000. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2018.03000

<https://zenodo.org/record/3660887#.XkEm5mhKiUk>

2019 – 13 publications

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Antimicrobial Usages and Antimicrobial Resistance in Commensal *Escherichia coli* From Veal Calves in France: Evolution During the Fattening Process.

Gay E, Bour M, Cazeau G, et al.

Front Microbiol. 2019;10:792. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2019.00792

https://zenodo.org/record/4249017#.YAcq_uhKjcc

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: The shufflon of IncI1 plasmids is rearranged constantly during different growth conditions.

Brouwer MSM, Jurgburg SD, Harders F, et al.

Plasmid. 2019;102:51-55. doi:10.1016/j.plasmid.2019.03.003

<https://zenodo.org/record/3730621#.Xn3MyYhKi70>

JRP03-AMR3-RADAR: Attributable sources of community-acquired carriage of *Escherichia coli*

containing β -lactam antibiotic resistance genes: a population-based modelling study. *The Lancet* Mughini-Gras L, Dorado-García A, van Duijkeren E, et al.

Planetary Health. 2019;3(8):e357-e369. doi:10.1016/S2542-5196(19)30130-5

<https://zenodo.org/record/3621285#.XjI8UGhKhPY>

JRP04-ET1-MADVIR: Field samplings of *Ixodes ricinus* ticks from a tick-borne encephalitis virus micro-focus in Northern Zealand, Denmark.

Petersen A, Rosenstjerne MW, Rasmussen M, et al.

Ticks and Tick-borne Diseases. 2019;10(5):1028-1032. doi:10.1016/j.ttbdis.2019.05.005

<https://zenodo.org/record/3634258#.XjI8d2hKhPY>

JRP05-ET1-TOXDETECT: Point-of-Need DNA Testing for Detection of Foodborne Pathogenic Bacteria.

Vidic J, Vizzini P, Manzano M, et al.

Sensors. 2019;19(5):1100. doi:10.3390/s19051100

<https://zenodo.org/record/3935799#.X6Ud-GhKjcc>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: An outbreak of monophasic *Salmonella* Typhimurium associated with raw pork sausage and other pork products, Denmark 2018–19.

Helmuth IG, Espenhain L, Ethelberg S, et al.

Epidemiol Infect. 2019;147:e315. doi:10.1017/S0950268819002073

<https://zenodo.org/record/4249319#.X6UIWmhKjcc>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Non-Typhi, non-Paratyphi *Salmonella*-related hospitalisations in Spain: trends, clinical aspects, risk factors for worse prognosis and hospital costs.

Garrido-Esteba M, Latasa P, Ordóñez-León GY, Martínez-Avilés M, de la Torre A, García-Comas L.

Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis. 2019;38(2):337-346. doi:10.1007/s10096-018-3433-1

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244788#.X6LhGYhKjcc>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: *Salmonella* Surveillance Systems in Swine and Humans in Spain: A Review.

Martínez-Avilés M, Garrido-Esteba M, Álvarez J, de la Torre A.

Veterinary Sciences. 2019;6(1):20. doi:10.3390/vetsci6010020

<https://zenodo.org/record/3635293#.XjIyUGhKhPY>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Whole genome sequencing reveals resemblance between ESBL-producing and carbapenem resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates from Austrian rivers and clinical isolates from hospitals.

Lepuschitz S, Schill S, Stoeger A, et al.

Science of The Total Environment. 2019;662:227-235. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.01.179

<https://zenodo.org/record/4249232#.X6UhA2hKjcc>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Description of *Klebsiella africanensis* sp. nov., *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. *tropicalensis* subsp. nov. and *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. *variicola* subsp. nov.

Rodrigues C, Passet V, Rakotondrasoa A, Diallo TA, Criscuolo A, Brisse S.

Research in Microbiology. 2019;170(3):165-170. doi:10.1016/j.resmic.2019.02.003

<https://zenodo.org/record/3660879#.XkEmO2hKiUk>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Description of *Klebsiella spallanzanii* sp. nov. and of *Klebsiella pasteurii* sp. nov.

Merla C, Rodrigues C, Passet V, et al.

Front Microbiol. 2019;10:2360. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2019.02360

<https://zenodo.org/record/3660875#.XkEICGhKiUk>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Outbreak of Yersiniabactin-producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in a Neonatal Intensive Care Unit:

Wisgrill L, Lepuschitz S, Blaschitz M, et al.
The Pediatric Infectious Disease Journal. 2019;38(6):638-642.
doi:10.1097/INF.0000000000002258
<https://zenodo.org/record/3661013#.XkFq-OSWwj9>

2020 - 60 publications

One Health EJP: The One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP), 2018–2022: An Exemplary One Health Initiative.

Brown, H. L.; Passey, J. L.; Getino, M.; Pursley, I.; Basu, P.; Horton, D. L.; La Ragione, R. M.
Journal of Medical Microbiology 2020, 69 (8), 1037–1039.
<https://doi.org/10.1099/jmm.0.001228>
<https://zenodo.org/record/5541709#.YVXFzZpBy70>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Novel IncFII Plasmid Harboring *Bla* NDM-4 in a Carbapenem-Resistant *Escherichia Coli* of Pig Origin, Italy.

Diaconu, E. L.; Carfora, V.; Alba, P.; Di Matteo, P.; Stravino, F.; Buccella, C.; Dell’Aira, E.; Onorati, R.; Sorbara, L.; Battisti, A.; Franco, A.
Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy 2020, 75 (12), 3475–3479.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkaa374>
<https://zenodo.org/record/4451840#.YAfP RNhKg2w>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Spill-Over from Public Health? First Detection of an OXA-48-Producing *Escherichia Coli* in a German Pig Farm.

Irrgang, A.; Pauly, N.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Grobbel, M.; Kaesbohrer, A.; Hammerl, J. A.
Microorganisms 2020, 8 (6), 855.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8060855>
<https://zenodo.org/record/4447289#.YAWijthKg2w>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: First Detection of GES-5-Producing *Escherichia Coli* from Livestock—An Increasing Diversity of Carbapenemases Recognized from German Pig Production.

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Irrgang, A.; Tausch, S. H.; Pauly, N.; Grobbel, M.; Kaesbohrer, A.; Hammerl, J. A. *Microorganisms* 2020, 8 (10), 1593.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8101593>
<https://zenodo.org/record/4451836#.YAfzdhKg2w>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: ChromID® CARBA Agar Fails to Detect Carbapenem-Resistant Enterobacteriaceae With Slightly Reduced Susceptibility to Carbapenems.

Pauly, N.; Hammerl, J. A.; Grobbel, M.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Käsbohrer, A.; Bisenius, S.; Fuchs, J.; Horlacher, S.; Lingstädt, H.; Mauermann, U.; Mitro, S.; Müller, M.; Rohrmann, S.; Schiffmann, A. P.; Stührenberg, B.; Zimmermann, P.; Schwarz, S.; Meemken, D.; Irrgang, A.
Front. Microbiol. 2020, 11, 1678.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.01678>
<https://zenodo.org/record/4447313#.YA7QnehKjcc>

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Identification of a *Bla*VIM-1-Carrying IncA/C2 Multiresistance Plasmid in an *Escherichia Coli* Isolate Recovered from the German Food Chain.

Pauly, N.; Hammerl, J. A.; Grobbel, M.; Käsbohrer, A.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Malorny, B.; Schwarz, S.; Meemken, D.; Irrgang, A.
Microorganisms 2020, 9 (1), 29.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9010029>
<https://zenodo.org/record/4451858#.YAfqINhKg2w>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Monitoring Antimicrobial Resistance and Drug Usage in the Human and Livestock Sector and Foodborne Antimicrobial Resistance in Six European Countries.

Mesa Varona, O.; Chaintarli, K.; Muller-Pebody, B.; Anjum, M. F.; Eckmanns, T.; Norström, M.; Boone, I.; Tenhagen, B.-A.

IDR 2020, Volume 13, 957–993.

<https://doi.org/10.2147/IDR.S237038>

<https://zenodo.org/record/997236#.XvyQfSgzZM0>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: blaCTX–M–1/IncI1-ly Plasmids Circulating in Escherichia coli From Norwegian Broiler Production Are Related, but Distinguishable.

Mo SS, Telke AA, Osei KO, et al.

Front Microbiol. 2020;11:333.

doi:10.3389/fmicb.2020.00333

<https://zenodo.org/record/3701226#.YAqeSehKjcc>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Temporal dynamics of the fecal microbiota in veal calves in a 6-month field trial.

Massot M, Haenni M, Nguyen TT, Madec J-Y, Mentré F, Denamur E.

anim microbiome. 2020;2(1):32.

doi:10.1186/s42523-020-00052-6

<https://zenodo.org/record/4456718#.YAqfnuhKjcc>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: The importance of using whole genome sequencing and extended spectrum beta-lactamase selective media when monitoring antimicrobial resistance.

Duggett N, AbuOun M, Randall L, et al.

Sci Rep. 2020;10(1):19880.

doi:10.1038/s41598-020-76877-7

<https://zenodo.org/record/4456741#.YAqkH-hKjcc>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Extensive antimicrobial resistance mobilization via multicopy plasmid encapsidation mediated by temperate phages.

Rodríguez-Rubio L, Serna C, Ares-Arroyo M, et al.

Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy. Published online July 28, 2020:dkaa311.

doi:10.1093/jac/dkaa311

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244116#.X6KBDjiWxM0>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Monitoring Antimicrobial Resistance and Drug Usage in the Human and Livestock Sector and Foodborne Antimicrobial Resistance in Six European Countries

Mesa Varona O, Chaintarli K, Muller-Pebody B, et al.

IDR. 2020;Volume 13:957-993.

doi:10.2147/IDR.S237038

<https://zenodo.org/record/997236#.XvyQfSgzZM0>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Stepwise evolution and convergent recombination underlie the global dissemination of carbapenemase-producing Escherichia coli.

Patiño-Navarrete R, Rosinski-Chupin I, Cabanel N, et al.

Genome Med. 2020;12(1):10.

doi:10.1186/s13073-019-0699-6

<https://zenodo.org/record/3730637#.Xn3Pm4hKi70>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Mobile Colistin Resistance Gene Mcr-1 Detected on an IncI1 Plasmid in Escherichia Coli from Meat.

Brouwer, M. S. M.; Goodman, R. N.; Kant, A.; Mevius, D.; Newire, E.; Roberts, A. P.; Veldman, K. T.

Journal of Global Antimicrobial Resistance 2020, 23, 145–148.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgar.2020.08.018>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4475507#.YQJhJTh7mVN>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Phenotypical Antimicrobial Resistance Data of Clinical and Non-Clinical *Escherichia Coli* from Poultry in Germany between 2014 and 2017.

Mesa-Varona, O.; Kaspar, H.; Grobbel, M.; Tenhagen, B.-A.

PLoS ONE 2020, 15 (12), e0243772.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0243772>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4328124#.YKS5sagzbY0>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Colistin-Resistant Enterobacteriaceae Isolated From Process Waters and Wastewater From German Poultry and Pig Slaughterhouses.

Savin, M.; Bierbaum, G.; Blau, K.; Parcina, M.; Sib, E.; Smalla, K.; Schmithausen, R.; Heinemann, C.; Hammerl, J. A.; Kreyenschmidt, J.

Front. Microbiol. 2020, 11, 575391.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.575391>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4981351#.YP7O5Th7m9I>

JRP03-AMR3-RADAR: Analysis of COMPASS, a New Comprehensive Plasmid Database Revealed Prevalence of Multireplicon and Extensive Diversity of IncF Plasmids.

Douarre P-E, Mallet L, Radomski N, Felten A, Mistou M-Y.

Front Microbiol. 2020;11:483.

doi:10.3389/fmicb.2020.00483

<https://zenodo.org/record/3968418#.XyQSQTgUIM2>

JRP04-ET1-MADVIR: Novel enteric viruses in fatal enteritis of grey squirrels.

Dastjerdi A, Benfield C, Everest D, Stidworthy MF, Zell R.

Journal of General Virology. 2020;101(7):746-750.

doi:10.1099/jgv.0.001431

<https://zenodo.org/record/4249097#.X6kclGhKhM0>

JRP05-TOX-Detect: Advanced Methods for Detection of *Bacillus Cereus* and Its Pathogenic Factors.

Ramarao, N.; Tran, S.-L.; Marin, M.; Vidic, J.

Sensors 2020, 20 (9), 2667.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/s20092667>

<https://zenodo.org/record/3933055#.YVcVMJpBy70>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Modelling spread and surveillance of *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. paratuberculosis in the Swedish cattle trade network.

Rosendal T, Widgren S, Ståhl K, Frössling J.

Preventive Veterinary Medicine. 2020;183:105152.

doi:10.1016/j.prevetmed.2020.105152

<https://zenodo.org/record/4450338>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Using stochastic dynamic modelling to estimate the sensitivity of current and alternative surveillance program of *Salmonella* in conventional broiler production.

Apenteng OO, Arnold ME, Vigre H.

Sci Rep. 2020;10(1):19441.

doi:10.1038/s41598-020-76514-3

<https://zenodo.org/record/4271431#.X65ljTiWxPY>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Climatic and topographic tolerance limits of wild boar in Eurasia: implications for their expansion.

Bosch J, Iglesias I, Martínez M, De la Torre A.

GES. 2020;13(1):107-114.

doi:10.24057/2071-9388-2019-52

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244729#.X6LYN4hKjcc>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Identifying emerging trends in antimicrobial resistance using Salmonella surveillance data in poultry in Spain.

Alvarez J, Lopez G, Muellner P, et al.

Transbound Emerg Dis. 2020;67(1):250-262.

doi:10.1111/tbed.13346

<https://zenodo.org/record/3660026#.XvyQnGgzZM0>

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA: Spatial Trends in Salmonella Infection in Pigs in Spain.

Teng KT, Martinez Avilés M, Ugarte-Ruiz M, et al.

Front Vet Sci. 2020;7:345.

doi:10.3389/fvets.2020.00345

https://zenodo.org/record/4244797#.X6Li_lhKjcc

JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT: First Report on the Finding of *Listeria monocytogenes* ST121 Strain in a Dolphin Brain.

Sévellec Y, Torresi M, Félix B, et al.

Pathogens. 2020;9(10):802.

doi:10.3390/pathogens9100802

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244051#.X6J4fziWxM1>

JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT: Genetic Characterization of a *Listeria Monocytogenes* Serotype IVb Variant 1 Strain Isolated from Vegetal Matrix in Italy.

Torresi, M.; Orsini, M.; Acciari, V.; Centorotola, G.; Di Lollo, V.; Di Domenico, M.; Bianchi, D. M.; Ziba, M. W.; Tramuta, C.; Cammà, C.; Pomilio, F.

Microbiol Resour Announc 2020, 9 (33).

<https://doi.org/10.1128/MRA.00782-20>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5472980>

JRP08-FBZ2-METASTAVA: Evaluation of a commercial exogenous internal process control for diagnostic RNA virus metagenomics from different animal clinical samples.

Van Borm S, Fu Q, Winand R, et al.

Journal of Virological Methods. 2020;283:113916.

doi:10.1016/j.jviromet.2020.113916

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244771#.X6Lc5ohKjcc>

JRP08-FBZ2-METASTAVA: COVID-19 in health-care workers in three hospitals in the south of the Netherlands: a cross-sectional study.

Sikkema RS, Pas SD, Nieuwenhuijse DF, et al.

The Lancet Infectious Diseases. 2020;20(11):1273-1280.

doi:10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30527-2

<https://zenodo.org/record/4457341#.YArXXOhKjcc>

JRP08-FBZ2-METASTAVA: Rapid SARS-CoV-2 whole-genome sequencing and analysis for informed public health decision-making in the Netherlands.

The Dutch-COVID-19 response team, Oude Munnink BB, Nieuwenhuijse DF, et al.

Nat Med. 2020;26(9):1405-1410.

doi:10.1038/s41591-020-0997-y

<https://zenodo.org/record/4457379#.YArZ5ehKjcc>

JRP08-FBZ2-METASTAVA: Increased viral read counts and metagenomic full genome characterization of porcine astrovirus 4 and Posavirus 1 in sows in a swine farm with unexplained neonatal piglet diarrhea.

Van Borm S, Vanneste K, Fu Q, et al.

Virus Genes. 2020;56(6):696-704.

doi:10.1007/s11262-020-01791-z

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244782#.X6LfzYhKjcc>

JRP09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE: Prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of Campylobacter isolated from carcasses of chickens slaughtered in Poland – a retrospective study.

Wieczorek K, Bocian Ł, Osek J.

Food Control. 2020;112:107159.

doi:10.1016/j.foodcont.2020.107159

<https://zenodo.org/record/3676306>

JRP09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE: Campylobacter in chicken – Critical parameters for international, multicentre evaluation of air sampling and detection methods.

Johannessen GS, Garofolo G, Di Serafino G, et al.

Food Microbiology. 2020;90:103455.

doi:10.1016/j.fm.2020.103455

<https://zenodo.org/record/3663545#.XkPEvGhKiUk>

JRP09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE: MLST-based genetic relatedness of Campylobacter jejuni isolated from chickens and humans in Poland.

Wieczorek K, Wołkowicz T, Osek J. Biggs PJ, ed.

PLoS ONE. 2020;15(1):e0226238.

doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0226238

<https://zenodo.org/record/3628110#.X6FsFjiWxPY>

JRP09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE: Molecular Characterization and Antimicrobial Susceptibility of C. Jejuni Isolates from Italian Wild Bird Populations.

Marotta, F.; Janowicz, A.; Di Marcantonio, L.; Ercole, C.; Di Donato, G.; Garofolo, G.; Di Giannatale, E. *Pathogens* 2020, 9 (4), 304.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9040304>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5564702#.YVW-g3duLnM>

JRP09-FBZ3-AIRSAMPLE: A multi-center proposal for a fast screening tool in biosecured chicken flocks. Foodborne Campylobacter

Jeffrey Hoorfar, Ivana Koláčková, Gro S. Johannessen, Giuliano Garofolo, Francesca Marotta, Kinga Wieczorek, Jacek Osek, Mona Torp, Bjørn Spilsgberg, Camilla Sekse, Natasia Rebekka Thornval, Renáta Karpíšková

Applied and Environmental Microbiology, Vol.86, N°20

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.01051-20>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244138#.YjHwmzapW3c>

JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC: A multi-scale epidemic model of Salmonella infection with heterogeneous shedding. Labarthe S, Laroche B, Nguyen TNT, et al.

Calvez V, Grandmont C, Lochërbach E, Poignard C, Ribot M, Vauchelet N, eds. *ESAIM: ProcS*. 2020;67:261-284.

doi:10.1051/proc/202067015

doi:10.1051/proc/202067015

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244169#.X6KF4TiWxMO>

JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC: Reduction of Salmonella Typhimurium Cecal Colonisation and Improvement of Intestinal Health in Broilers Supplemented with Fermented Defatted ‘Alperujo’, an Olive Oil By-Product.

Rebollada-Merino A, Ugarte-Ruiz M, Hernández M, et al.

Animals. 2020;10(10):1931.

doi:10.3390/ani10101931

<https://zenodo.org/record/4114070>

JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC: Cost-effectiveness analysis of using probiotics, prebiotics, or synbiotics to control Campylobacter in broilers.

van Wagenberg CPA, van Horne PLM, van Asseldonk MAPM.

Poultry Science. 2020;99(8):4077-4084.

doi:10.1016/j.psj.2020.05.003

<https://zenodo.org/record/4244748#.X6LaalhKjcc>

JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC: Dietary supplementation with fermented defatted “alperujo” induces modifications of the intestinal mucosa and cecal microbiota of broiler chickens.

Rebollada-Merino A, Ugarte-Ruiz M, Hernández M, et al.

Poultry Science. Published online August 2020:S0032579120304843.

doi:10.1016/j.psj.2020.07.015

<https://zenodo.org/record/4017817#.X6LRjYhKjcc>

JRP10-FBZ3-MOMIRPPC: Gut microbiota composition before infection determines the *Salmonella* super- and low-shedder phenotypes in chicken.

Kempf F, Menanteau P, Rychlik I, et al.

Microb Biotechnol. 2020;13(5):1611-1630.

doi:10.1111/1751-7915.13621

<https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Diversity of mucoid to non-mucoid switch among carbapenemase-producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

Chiarelli A, Cabanel N, Rosinski-Chupin I, et al.

BMC Microbiol. 2020;20(1):325.

doi:10.1186/s12866-020-02007-y

<https://zenodo.org/record/4456731#.YAqiMOhKjcc>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Broad-Spectrum Cephalosporin-Resistant *Klebsiella* spp. Isolated from Diseased Horses in Austria.

Loncaric I, Cabal Rosel A, Szostak MP, et al.

Animals. 2020;10(2):332.

doi:10.3390/ani10020332

https://zenodo.org/record/3929408#.Xv8m_ygzZM0

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: *Klebsiella pneumoniae* carriage in low-income countries: antimicrobial resistance, genomic diversity and risk factors.

Huynh B-T, Passet V, Rakotondrasoa A, et al.

Gut Microbes. 2020;11(5):1287-1299.

doi:10.1080/19490976.2020.1748257

<https://zenodo.org/record/3929396#.Xv8lrSgzZM0>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: The ZKIR Assay, a Real-Time PCR Method for the Detection of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and Closely Related Species in Environmental Samples.

Barbier E, Rodrigues C, Depret G, et al.

Dudley EG, ed. *Appl Environ Microbiol*. 2020;86(7):e02711-19,

/aem/86/7/AEM.02711-19.atom.

doi:10.1128/AEM.02711-19

<https://zenodo.org/record/3730608#.Xn3Kk4hKi70>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Community-Acquired Infection Caused by the Uncommon Hypervirulent *Klebsiella Pneumoniae* ST66-K2 Lineage.

Rodrigues, C.; d'Humières, C.; Papin, G.; Passet, V.; Ruppé, E.; Brisse, S.

Microbial Genomics 2020, 6 (8).

<https://doi.org/10.1099/mgen.0.000419>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4436269#.YGLbQ68za70>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: Jousset, A. B.; Bonnin, R. A.; Takissian, J.; Girlich, D.; Mihaila, L.; Cabanel, N.; Dortet, L.; Glaser, P.; Naas, T. Concomitant Carriage of KPC-Producing and Non-KPC-Producing *Klebsiella Pneumoniae* ST512 within a Single Patient.

Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy 2020, dkaa137.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkaa137>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6334276#.YiYSrujML2B>

JRP16-ET2.2-TELEVIR: An alternative workflow for molecular detection of SARS-CoV-2 – escape from the NA extraction kit-shortage, Copenhagen, Denmark, March 2020.

Fomsgaard AS, Rosenstjerne MW.

Eurosurveillance. 2020;25(14). doi:10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2020.25.14.2000398

<https://zenodo.org/record/4247188#.X6QLjWhKjcc>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEME: Cystic Echinococcosis: Clinical, Immunological, and Biomolecular Evaluation of Patients from Sardinia (Italy).

Santucci C, Bonelli P, Peruzzo A, et al.

Pathogens. 2020;9(11):907. doi:10.3390/pathogens9110907

<https://zenodo.org/record/4159681>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEME: Comparison of Two DNA Extraction Methods and Two PCRs for Detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in the Stool Samples of Naturally Infected Red Foxes. Skrzypek K, Karamon J, Samorek-Pieróg M, et al.

Animals. 2020;10(12):2381. doi:10.3390/ani10122381

<https://zenodo.org/record/4384600>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEME: A validated method to identify *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* at species level.

Santolamazza F, Santoro A, Possenti A, Cacciò SM, Casulli A.

Infection, Genetics and Evolution. 2020;85:104575. doi:10.1016/j.meegid.2020.104575

<https://zenodo.org/record/4066416#.X6UQMWhKjcc>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEME: Bayesian Analysis of Three Methods for Diagnosis of Cystic Echinococcosis in Sheep. Bonelli P, Loi F, Cancedda MG, et al.

Pathogens. 2020;9(10):796. doi:10.3390/pathogens9100796

<https://zenodo.org/record/4061823#.X6PZl2hKjcc>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEME: Microsatellite Investigations of Multiple *Echinococcus granulosus Sensu Stricto* Cysts in Single Hosts Reveal Different Patterns of Infection Events between Livestock and Humans.

M'rad S, Oudni-M'rad M, Bastid V, et al.

Pathogens. 2020;9(6):444. doi:10.3390/pathogens9060444

<https://zenodo.org/record/3894117#.XvyQ6ygzZM0>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEME: Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemic cystic and alveolar echinococcosis.

Casulli A. *The Lancet Global Health*. 2020;8(4):e470-e471. doi:10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30066-8
<https://zenodo.org/record/3730559#.Xn3FalhKi70>

JRP18-ET1.1-MEME: Species Detection within the *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* Complex by Novel Probe-Based Real-Time PCRs.

Maksimov P, Bergmann H, Wassermann M, et al.
Pathogens. 2020;9(10):791. doi:10.3390/pathogens9100791
<https://zenodo.org/record/4061718#.X6PY3WhKjcc>

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE: Molecular Characterization of *Giardia duodenalis* in Children and Adults Sampled in Algeria.

Belkessa S, Thomas-Lopez D, Houali K, Ghalmi F, Stensvold CR.
Microorganisms. 2020;9(1):54. doi:10.3390/microorganisms9010054
<https://zenodo.org/record/4422456#.YArbG-hKjcc>

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE: Veterinary Students Have a Higher Risk of Contracting Cryptosporidiosis when Calves with High Fecal *Cryptosporidium* Loads Are Used for Fetotomy Exercises. Schaffner DW, ed. Thomas-Lopez D, Müller L, Vestergaard LS, et al.

Appl Environ Microbiol. 2020;86(19):e01250-20, /aem/86/19/AEM.01250-20.atom.
doi:10.1128/AEM.01250-20
<https://zenodo.org/record/4129990#.X6PX8WhKjcc>

JRP21-FBZSH9-BEONE: Prediction of antimicrobial resistance in clinical *Campylobacter jejuni* isolates from whole-genome sequencing data.

Dahl LG, Joensen KG, Østerlund MT, Kiil K, Nielsen EM.
Eur J Clin Microbiol Infect Dis. Published online September 24, 2020.
doi:10.1007/s10096-020-04043-y
<https://zenodo.org/record/4249355#.X6UnVWhKjcc>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Fluorescent Bead-Based Serological Detection of *Toxoplasma Gondii* Infection in Chickens.

Fabian BT, Hedar F, Koethe M, et al.
In Review; 2020. Accessed August 20, 2020. <https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-34121/v1>
<https://zenodo.org/record/3974390#.X6PV0WhKjcc>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Isolation and genetic characterization of *Toxoplasma gondii* in Spanish sheep flocks. Fernández-Escobar M, Calero-Bernal R, Benavides J, et al.

Parasites Vectors. 2020;13(1):396. doi:10.1186/s13071-020-04275-z
<https://zenodo.org/record/3974417#.X6PWsWhKjcc>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Expression of *in Vivo* Biotinylated Recombinant Antigens SAG1 and SAG2A from *Toxoplasma Gondii* for Improved Seroepidemiological Bead-Based Multiplex Assays.

Klein S, Stern D, Seeber F.
In Review; 2020. Accessed August 20, 2020. <https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-33963/v1>
<https://zenodo.org/record/4129949#.X6Ldr4hKjcc>

2021 - 48 publications

In 2021, 47 manuscripts were published by the JRP (17 by the first round JRP and 30 by the second round JRP). The manuscripts are mentioned below (authors, title, DOI and repository link). A list of all the One Health EJP manuscripts published since 2018 is available on the One Health EJP website:

<https://onehealth.ejp.eu/publications/>.

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Co-Occurrence of the Bla VIM-1 and Bla SHV-12 Genes on an IncHI2 Plasmid of an Escherichia Coli Isolate Recovered from German Livestock.

Pauly, N.; Hammerl, J. A.; Schwarz, S.; Grobbel, M.; Meemken, D.; Malorny, B.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Käsbohrer, A.; Irrgang, A.

Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy 2021, 76 (2), 531–533.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkaa436>

https://zenodo.org/record/4451874#.YgU9vt_MLFU

JRP01-AMR1-IMPART: Isolation Procedure for CP E. Coli from Caeca Samples under Review towards an Increased Sensitivity.

Pauly, N.; Klaar, Y.; Skladnikiewicz-Ziemer, T.; Juraschek, K.; Grobbel, M.; Hammerl, J. A.; Hemmers, L.; Käsbohrer, A.; Schwarz, S.; Meemken, D.; Tenhagen, B.-A.; Irrgang, A.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (5), 1105.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9051105>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4835626#.YVQo9ppBxM0>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Horsing Around: Escherichia Coli ST1250 of Equine Origin Harboring Epidemic IncHI1/ST9 Plasmid with Bla CTX-M-1 and an Operon for Short-Chain Fructooligosaccharide Metabolism.

Valcek, A.; Sismova, P.; Nesporova, K.; Overballe-Petersen, S.; Bitar, I.; Jamborova, I.; Kant, A.; Hrabak, J.; Wagenaar, J. A.; Madec, J.-Y.; Damborg, P.; van Duijkeren, E.; Ewers, C.; Hordijk, J.; Hasman, H.; Brouwer, M. S. M.; Dolejska, M.

Antimicrob Agents Chemother 2021, 65 (5).

<https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.02556-20>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5506463#.YUBKk50zaUk>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Clinically Relevant Escherichia Coli Isolates from Process Waters and Wastewater of Poultry and Pig Slaughterhouses in Germany.

Savin, M.; Bierbaum, G.; Kreyenschmidt, J.; Schmithausen, R.; Sib, E.; Schmogger, S.; Käsbohrer, A.; Hammerl, J.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (4), 698.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9040698>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4981248>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Comparison of Phenotypal Antimicrobial Resistance between Clinical and Non-Clinical E. Coli Isolates from Broilers, Turkeys and Calves in Four European Countries.

Mesa-Varona, O.; Mader, R.; Velasova, M.; Madec, J.-Y.; Granier, S. A.; Perrin-Guyomard, A.; Norstrom, M.; Kaspar, H.; Grobbel, M.; Jouy, E.; Anjum, M. F.; Tenhagen, B.-A.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (4), 678.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9040678>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4704208#.YKS6KKgzby0>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Phenotypic and Genotypic Properties of Fluoroquinolone-Resistant, Qnr-Carrying Escherichia Coli Isolated from the German Food Chain in 2017.

Juraschek, K.; Deneke, C.; Schmogger, S.; Grobbel, M.; Malorny, B.; Käsbohrer, A.; Schwarz, S.; Meemken, D.; Hammerl, J. A.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (6), 1308.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9061308>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4328124#.YKS5sagzbY0>

JRP02-AM2-ARDIG: Outcome of Different Sequencing and Assembly Approaches on the Detection of Plasmids and Localization of Antimicrobial Resistance Genes in Commensal Escherichia Coli.

Juraschek, K.; Borowiak, M.; Tausch, S. H.; Malorny, B.; Käsbohrer, A.; Otani, S.; Schwarz, S.; Meemken, D.; Deneke, C.; Hammerl, J. A.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (3), 598.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9030598>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4964345>

JRP05 ET1-TOX-Detect: The Cytotoxic Potential of *Bacillus Cereus* Strains of Various Origins.

Glasset, B.; Sperry, M.; Dervyn, R.; Herbin, S.; Brisabois, A.; Ramarao, N.

Food Microbiology 2021, 98, 103759.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2021.103759>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5516520#.YgUztzipW3c>

JRP05 ET1-TOX-Detect: DiagnoTop: A Computational Pipeline for Discriminating Bacterial Pathogens without Database Search.

Borges Lima, D.; Dupré, M.; Mariano Santos, M. D.; Carvalho, P. C.; Chamot-Rooke, J.

Am. Soc. Mass Spectrom. 2021, 32 (6), 1295–1299.

<https://doi.org/10.1021/jasms.1c00014>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5516526#.YgUz1TipW3c>

JRP06 FBZ1-NOVA: One Health Glossary to Support Communication and Information Exchange between the Human Health, Animal Health and Food Safety Sectors.

Buschhardt, T.; Günther, T.; Skjerdal, T.; Torpdahl, M.; Gethmann, J.; Filippitzi, M.-E.; Maassen, C.; Jore, S.; Ellis-Iversen, J.; Filter, M.

One Health 2021, 13, 100263.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100263>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4769914#.YT9EEp0za70>

JRP07 FBZ2-LISTADAPT: Chloride Resistance in *Listeria Monocytogenes* of Human, Food, and Environmental Origin.

Gelbicova, T.; Florianova, M.; Hluchanova, L.; Kalova, A.; Korena, K.; Strakova, N.; Karpiskova, R.

Comparative Analysis of Genetic Determinants Encoding Cadmium, Arsenic, and Benzalkonium
Front. Microbiol. 2021, 11, 599882.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.599882>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4456720#.YLDmBzhDtM0>

JRP07 FBZ2-LISTADAPT: Exposure to Quaternary Ammonium Compounds Selects Resistance to Ciprofloxacin in *Listeria Monocytogenes*.

Guérin, A.; Bridier, A.; Le Grandois, P.; Sévellec, Y.; Palma, F.; Félix, B.; LISTADAPT Study Group; Roussel, S.; Soumet, C.

Pathogens 2021, 10 (2), 220.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10020220>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5471681>

JRP07 FBZ2-LISTADAPT: Draft Genome Sequences of Two *Listeria Monocytogenes* Strains Isolated from Invasive Snails (*Arion Vulgaris*) in Austria in 2019. 2021.

Pietzka A; Murer A; Lennkh A; Hauser K; Votsch; Springer B; Allerberger F; Ruppitch W.

American Society for Microbiology, 2021, Vol.10 N°21

<https://doi.org/10.1128/MRA.00375-21>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5472856>

JRP07 FBZ2-LISTADAPT: Comparative analysis of genetic determinants encoding cadmium, arsenic and benzalkonium chloride resistance in *Listeria monocytogenes* of human, food and environmental origin.
Tereza Gelbicova, Martina Florianova, Lucie Hluchanova, Alžběta Kalova, Kristýna Korena, Nicol

Strakova, Renáta Karpiskova

Front. Microbiol., 14 January 2021

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.599882>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4456720#.YLDmBzhDtM0>

JRP08 FBZ2-METASTAVA: Detection of Norovirus Variant GII.4 Hong Kong in Asia and Europe, 2017–2019.

Chan, M. C.-W.; Roy, S.; Bonifacio, J.; Zhang, L.-Y.; Chhabra, P.; Chan, J. C. M.; Celma, C.; Igoy, M. A.; Lau, S.-L.; Mohammad, K. N.; Vinjé, J.; Vennema, H.; Breuer, J.; Koopmans, M.; de Graaf, M.; *Emerg. Infect. Dis.* 2021, 27 (1), 289–293.

<https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2701.203351>

https://zenodo.org/record/4556945#.YgU-E9_MLFU

JRP08 FBZ2-METASTAVA: Monitoring SARS-CoV-2 Circulation and Diversity through Community Wastewater Sequencing, the Netherlands and Belgium.

Izquierdo-Lara, R.; Elsinga, G.; Heijnen, L.; Munnink, B. B. O.; Schapendonk, C. M. E.; Nieuwenhuijse, D.; Kon, M.; Lu, L.; Aarestrup, F. M.; Lycett, S.; Medema, G.; Koopmans, M. P. G.; de Graaf, M. *Emerg. Infect. Dis.* 2021, 27 (5), 1405–1415.

<https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2705.204410>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4457357#.YP7XnTh7m9I>

JRP10 FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC: Effect of Biscuit Flour and Fermented Defatted “Alperujo” Co-Administration on Intestinal Mucosa Morphology and Productive Performance in Laying Hens.

Porras, N.; Rebollada-Merino, A.; Bárcena, C.; Mayoral-Alegre, F. J.; Lomillos, J. M.; Domínguez, L.; Rodríguez-Bertos, A.

Animals 2021, 11 (4), 1075.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11041075>

https://zenodo.org/record/4736117#.Yiht_japVM0

JRP10 FBZ3-MoMIR-PPC: A Large Panel of Chicken Cells Are Invaded in Vivo by Salmonella Typhimurium Even When Depleted of All Known Invasion Factors.

Roche, S. M.; Holbert, S.; Le Vern, Y.; Rossignol, C.; Rossignol, A.; Velge, P.; Virlogeux-Payant, I.

Open Biol. 2021, 11 (11), 210117.

<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsob.210117>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5707381#.Yicr-ejMJM0>

JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED: A Shotgun Metagenomics Approach to Detect and Characterize Unauthorized Genetically Modified Microorganisms in Microbial Fermentation Products.

Buytaers, F. E.; Fraiture, M.-A.; Berbers, B.; Vandermassen, E.; Hoffman, S.; Papazova, N.; Vanneste, K.; Marchal, K.; Roosens, N. H. C.; De Keersmaecker, S. C. J.

Food Chemistry: Molecular Sciences 2021, 2, 100023.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fochms.2021.100023>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5347021#.YS-kSY4zaM8>

JRP13-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM: Population Genomics and Antimicrobial Resistance Dynamics of Escherichia Coli in Wastewater and River Environments.

Delgado-Blas, J. F.; Ovejero, C. M.; David, S.; Montero, N.; Calero-Caceres, W.; Garcillan-Barcia, M. P.; de la Cruz, F.; Muniesa, M.; Aanensen, D. M.; Gonzalez-Zorn, B.

Commun Biol 2021, 4 (1), 457.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-021-01949-x>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5524433#.YcyB25HMJuR>

JRP14 AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE: A Peek into the Plasmidome of Global Sewage.

Kirstahler, P.; Teudt, F.; Otani, S.; Aarestrup, F. M.; Pamp, S. J. *mSystems* 2021, 6 (3).

<https://doi.org/10.1128/mSystems.00283-21>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5543288#.YZPKXmDMJMO>

JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR: Draft Genome Sequence of a Multidrug-Resistant Escherichia Coli Sequence Type 1193 Pandemic Clone Isolated from Wastewater in Austria.

Cabal, A.; Peischl, N.; Rab, G.; Stöger, A.; Springer, B.; Sucher, J.; Allerberger, F.; Ruppitsch, W. *Microbiol Resour Announc* 2021, 10 (37).

<https://doi.org/10.1128/MRA.00762-21>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5770120#.YeZ1rd8xl4F>

JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir: Escape from the NA Extraction Kit-Shortage, Copenhagen, Denmark, March 2020.

Fomsgaard, A. S.; Rosenstjerne, M. W. An Alternative Workflow for Molecular Detection of SARS-CoV-2 – *Eurosurveillance* 2020, 25 (14)

<https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2020.25.14.2000398>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4247188#.X6QLjWhKjcc>

JRP17-ET2.2-IDEMBRU: The Use of Flocked Swabs with a Protective Medium Increases the Recovery of Live Brucella Spp. and DNA Detection.

Freddi, L.; Djokic, V.; Petot-Bottin, F.; Girault, G.; Perrot, L.; Ferreira Vicente, A.; Ponsart, C. *Microbiol Spectr* 2021, 9 (3), e00728-21.

<https://doi.org/10.1128/Spectrum.00728-21>

JRP18 ET1.1-MEmE: Identification of Echinococcus Granulosus Genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs Genotyping Assays. Bonelli, P.; Dei Giudici, S.; Peruzzo, A.; Mura, L.; Santucci, C.; Maestrale, C.; Masala, G.

Pathogens 2021, 10 (2), 125.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10020125>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4471215#.YGLkiq8zZMO>

JRP18 ET1.1-MEmE: New Global Targets for NTDs in the WHO Roadmap 2021–2030.

Casulli, A.

PLoS Negl Trop Dis 2021, 15 (5), e0009373.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0009373>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4771738#.YKTFCqHOogp>

JRP18 ET1.1-MEmE: Molecular Analysis Suggests That Namibian Cheetahs (*Acinonyx Jubatus*) Are Definitive Hosts of a so Far Undescribed *Besnoitia* Species.

Schaes, G.; Joeres, M.; Rachel, F.; Tuschy, M.; Czirják, G. Á.; Maksimov, P.; Conraths, F. J.; Wachter, B. *Parasites Vectors* 2021, 14 (1), 201.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04697-3>

https://zenodo.org/record/4694200#.YTDH7t_OOgo

JRP18 ET1.1-MEmE: Morphological Characteristics of Alveolar and Cystic Echinococcosis Lesions in Human Liver and Bone.

Barth, T. F. E.; Casulli, A.

Pathogens 2021, 10 (10), 1326.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10101326>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5646982#.YicsOujMJMO>

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE: Mining Public Metagenomes for Environmental Surveillance of Parasites: A

Proof of Principle. *Front. Franssen, F. F. J.; Janse, I.; Janssen, D.; Caccio, S. M.; Vatta, P.; van der Giessen, J. W. B.; van Passel, M. W. J.*

Microbiol. 2021, 12, 622356.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.622356>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5494583>

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE: Parasitic Intestinal Protists of Zoonotic Relevance Detected in Pigs by Metabarcoding and Real-Time PCR.

Stensvold, C. R.; Jirků-Pomajbíková, K.; Tams, K. W.; Jokelainen, P.; Berg, R. P. K. D.; Marving, E.; Petersen, R. F.; Andersen, L. O.; Angen, Ø.; Nielsen, H. V.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (6), 1189.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9061189>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4898752#.YTnBA50zaUk>

JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR: Monitoring of Antimicrobial Resistance to Aminoglycosides and Macrolides in *Campylobacter Coli* and *Campylobacter Jejuni* From Healthy Livestock in Spain (2002–2018).

Lopez-Chavarrias, V.; Ugarte-Ruiz, M.; Barcena, C.; Olarra, A.; Garcia, M.; Saez, J. L.; de Frutos, C.; Serrano, T.; Perez, I.; Moreno, M. A.; Dominguez, L.; Alvarez, J.

Front. Microbiol. 2021, 12, 689262.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.689262>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5109549#.YUyflGzZM0>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Identification of Oocyst-Driven *Toxoplasma Gondii* Infections in Humans and Animals through Stage-Specific Serology—Current Status and Future Perspectives.

Álvarez García, G.; Davidson, R.; Jokelainen, P.; Klevar, S.; Spano, F.; Seeber, F.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (11), 2346.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9112346>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5821931#.YdXABWCZOUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Zoonotic Pathogens in Wild Muskoxen (*Ovibos Moschatus*) and Domestic Sheep (*Ovis Aries*) from Greenland.

Berg, R. P. K. D.; Stensvold, C. R.; Jokelainen, P.; Grønlund, A. K.; Nielsen, H. V.; Kutz, S.; Kapel, C. M. O.

Vet Med Sci 2021, vms3.599.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/vms3.599>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5516925#.YUhcMexe70>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Expanding the Known Repertoire of C-Type Lectin Receptors Binding to *Toxoplasma Gondii* Oocysts Using a Modified High-Resolution Immunofluorescence Assay.

Fabian, B. T.; Lepenies, B.; Schares, G.; Dubey, J. P.; Spano, F.; Seeber, F.

mSphere 2021, 6 (2).

<https://doi.org/10.1128/mSphere.01341-20>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4657064#.YGXUY68zaUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: In Vivo and in Vitro Models Show Unexpected Degrees of Virulence among *Toxoplasma Gondii* Type II and III Isolates from Sheep.

Fernández-Escobar, M.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Regidor-Cerrillo, J.; Vallejo, R.; Benavides, J.; Collantes-Fernández, E.; Ortega-Mora, L. M.

Vet Res 2021, 52 (1), 82.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13567-021-00953-7>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5516897#.YUg7QOxe70>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Identification of Molecular Biomarkers Associated with Disease Progression in the Testis of Bulls Infected with *Besnoitia Besnoiti*.

González-Barrio, D.; Diezma-Díaz, C.; Gutiérrez-Expósito, D.; Tabanera, E.; Jiménez-Meléndez, A.; Pizarro, M.; González-Huecas, M.; Ferre, I.; Ortega-Mora, L. M.; Álvarez-García, G.
Vet Res 2021, 52 (1), 106.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13567-021-00974-2>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/5812116#.YdVZo2jMKUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Changes in Serum Biomarkers of Inflammation in Bovine Besnoitiosis.

González-Barrio, D.; Huertas-López, A.; Diezma-Díaz, C.; Ferre, I.; Cerón, J. J.; Ortega-Mora, L. M.; Álvarez-García, G.

Parasites Vectors 2021, 14 (1), 488.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04991-0>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5812119#.YdVZe2jMKUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Veterinarians as a Risk Group for Zoonoses: Exposure, Knowledge and Protective Practices in Finland. Kinnunen, P. M.; Matomäki, A.; Verkola, M.; Heikinheimo, A.; Vapalahti, O.; Kallio-kokko, H.; Virtala, A.-M.; Jokelainen, P.

Safety and Health at Work 2021, S2093791121000871.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2021.10.008>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: The Disease Burden of Ocular Toxoplasmosis in Denmark in 2019: Estimates Based on Laboratory Testing of Ocular Samples and on Publicly Available Register Data.

Marstrand, J.; Kurtzhals, J. A. L.; Fuchs, H. J.; Nielsen, H. V.; Jokelainen, P. *Parasite Epidemiology and Control* 2021, 15, e00229.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parepi.2021.e00229>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5595613#.YXZegxpBy70>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: A Longitudinal Study of Toxoplasma Gondii Seroconversion on Four Large Danish Sow Farms. Olsen, A.; Alban, L.; Denwood, M.; Houe, H.; Birk Jensen, T.; Vedel Nielsen, H. *Veterinary Parasitology* 2021, 295, 109460.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2021.109460>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5516957#.YUhcDexxe70>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: A Real-Time Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction for the Specific Detection of Hammondia Hammondii and Its Differentiation from Toxoplasma Gondii.

Schares, G.; Globokar Vrhovec, M.; Tuschy, M.; Joeres, M.; Bärwald, A.; Koudela, B.; Dubey, J. P.; Maksimov, P.; Conraths, F. J.

Parasites Vectors 2021, 14 (1), 78.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-020-04571-8>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4647866#.YGNbWK8zaUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Molecular Methods for the Detection of Toxoplasma Gondii Oocysts in Fresh Produce: An Extensive Review.

Slana, I.; Bier, N.; Bartosova, B.; Marucci, G.; Possenti, A.; Mayer-Scholl, A.; Jokelainen, P.; Lalle, M.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (1), 167.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9010167>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4647840#.YGNQk68zaUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Comparison of Direct and Indirect Toxoplasma Gondii Detection and Genotyping in Game: Relationship and Challenges.

Stollberg, K. C.; Schares, G.; Mayer-Scholl, A.; Hrushetska, I.; Diescher, S.; Johne, A.; Richter, M. H.; Bier, N. S.

Microorganisms 2021, 9 (8), 1663.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9081663>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5516907#.YUg8qOxxe70>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Infection Prevention and Control Practices of Ambulatory Veterinarians: A Questionnaire Study in Finland.

Verkola, M.; Järvelä, T.; Järvinen, A.; Jokelainen, P.; Virtala, A.; Kinnunen, P. M.; Heikinheimo, A. *Vet Med Sci* 2021, vms3.464.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/vms3.464>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4647937#.YGNfea8zaUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Molecular Analysis Suggests That Namibian Cheetahs (*Acinonyx Jubatus*) Are Definitive Hosts of a so Far Undescribed *Besnoitia* Species.

Schares, G.; Joeres, M.; Rachel, F.; Tuschy, M.; Czirják, G. Á.; Maksimov, P.; Conraths, F. J.; Wachter, B. *Parasites Vectors* 2021, 14 (1), 201.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04697-3>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4694200#.YHg5Z-gzaUk>

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES: Experimental Infection with *Toxoplasma Gondii* in Broiler Chickens (*Gallus Domesticus*): Seroconversion, Tissue Cyst Distribution, and Prophylaxis.

Nedişan, M. E.; Györke, A.; Ştefănuţ, C. L.; Kalmár, Z.; Friss, Z.; Blaga, R.; Blazit, A.; Toma-Naic, A.; Mircean, V.; Schares, G.; Djurković-Djaković, O.; Klun, I.; Villena, I.; Cozma, V. *Parasitol Res* 2021, 120 (2), 593–603.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-020-06984-x>

<https://zenodo.org/record/4647895#.YGNbDT9JGUl>

JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS: Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Human Salmonellosis in the Netherlands.

Mughini-Gras, L.; Chanamé Pinedo, L.; Pijnacker, R.; van den Beld, M.; Wit, B.; Veldman, K.; Bosh, T.; Franz, E.

Epidemiol. Infect. 2021, 149, e254.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0950268821002557>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6090653#.Ygu1fzipW3d>

JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS: Coverage of the National Surveillance System for Human Salmonella Infections, Belgium, 2016-2020.

Van Goethem, N.; Van Den Bossche, A.; Ceysens, P.-J.; Lajot, A.; Coucke, W.; Vernelen, K.; Roosens, N. H. C.; De Keersmaecker, S. C. J.; Van Cauteren, D.; Mattheus, W.

PLoS ONE 2021, 16 (8), e0256820.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256820>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6090759#.Ygu1jzipW3d>

2022 : 5 publications

OHEJP: Participation in One Health Networks and Involvement in the COVID-19 Pandemic Response: A Global Study.

Streichert, L. C.; Sepe, L. P.; Jokelainen, P.; Stroud, C. M.; Berezowski, J.; Del Rio Vilas, V. J. *Front. Public Health* 2022, 10, 830893.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.830893>

<https://zenodo.org/record/6255721#.YiXYeujML2A>

JRPO1-AMR1-IMPART: A European Multicenter Evaluation Study to Investigate the Performance on Commercially Available Selective Agar Plates for the Detection of Carbapenemase Producing Enterobacteriaceae.

Dierikx, C.; Börjesson, S.; Perrin-Guyomard, A.; Haenni, M.; Norström, M.; Divon, H. H.; Ilag, H. K.;

Granier, S. A.; Hammerum, A.; Kjeldgaard, J. S.; Pauly, N.; Randall, L.; Anjum, M. F.; Smialowska, A.; Franco, A.; Veldman, K.; Slette-meås, J. S.

Journal of Microbiological Methods 2022, 193, 106418.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mimet.2022.106418>

JRP05-ET1-TOX-Detect: New Genetic Biomarkers to Differentiate Non-Pathogenic from Clinically Relevant *Bacillus Cereus* Strains.

Kavanaugh, D. W.; Glasset, B.; Dervyn, R.; Guérin, C.; Plancade, S.; Herbin, S.; Brisabois, A.; Nicolas, P.; Ramarao, N.

Clinical Microbiology and Infection 2022, 28 (1), 137.e1-137.e8.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2021.05.035>

<https://zenodo.org/record/5532833#.YVRb8JpBxM0>

JRP11-FBZ4-MedVetKlebs: High Prevalence of *Klebsiella Pneumoniae* in European Food Products: A Multicentric Study Comparing Culture and Molecular Detection Methods.

Rodrigues, C.; Hauser, K.; Cahill, N.; Ligowska-Marzeta, M.; Centorotola, G.; Cornacchia, A.; Garcia Fierro, R.; Haenni, M.; Nielsen, E. M.; Piveteau, P.; Barbier, E.; Morris, D.; Pomilio, F.; Brisse, S.

Microbiol Spectr 2022, 10 (1), e02376-21.

<https://doi.org/10.1128/spectrum.02376-21>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6258025#.YiXWeOjML2A>

JRP18-ET1.1-MemE: A Retrospective Cohort Study on Human Cystic Echinococcosis in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province (Pakistan) Based on 16 Years of Hospital Discharge Records.

Khan, H.; Casulli, A.; Harandi, M. F.; Afzal, M. S.; Saqib, M. A. N.; Ahmed, H.

Pathogens 2022, 11 (2), 194.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens11020194>.

<https://zenodo.org/record/6091472#.YiXX5ejML2A>

Relevance of the research projects

In the final reports, project leaders were requested to expand on the expected One Health impact that their project may have for any national and international stakeholders active in the domains of foodborne zoonoses, AMR and/or emerging threats. Among others, the following expectancies were mentioned:

- ARDIG: the European debate on the data collection systems for antimicrobial use in animals has been supported by the work done in ARDIG; the project added to the JAICRA report by EFSA, EMA and ECDC; close collaboration with other projects dealing with AMR and AMU, and with the network on AMR in animal pathogens, EARS-Vet.
- TOX-Detect: the more performant MALDI-ToF database is an asset for the correct identification of *Bacillus spp.*, *Clostridium spp.* and *Staphylococci spp.* and is of significant use for bacteriology labs; also the harmonized SOP will be valuable in diagnostic and reference labs.
- NOVA: The reporting of barriers and opportunities in food-borne disease surveillance from a One Health point of view is already requested from national authorities; novel approaches to amend and improve existing surveillance programmes (i.e. electronic tracing of food purchases, syndromic surveillance) were proposed.
- LISTADAPT: the detailed characterization of a wide variety of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains will be useful for the tasks of the EURL *Listeria* and will allow the development of new diagnostic tests (interest of the food sector).
- MOMIR-PPC: the project has contributed to the better understanding of the heterogeneity of *Salmonella* infection in humans, pigs and poultry (i.e. super-shedders), and to develop efficient

measures able to either predict the most susceptible animals (or flocks) or to prevent infection by the use of pre- and probiotics; the industry shows some interest in these treatments.

As for the 12 months report, project leaders were explicitly asked to mention on-going and planned cooperation with national and international projects, organizations (e.g. ECDC, EFSA, EMA, EEA, FAO, OIE, WHO), networks, or national ministries. Most frequently, ECDC and/or EFSA were referred to, but also contacts with EU projects (JPIAMR was mentioned several times) and other One Health EJP projects (all JPI and several JRP). Also interactions with relevant EU Reference Laboratories (Brucella, E. coli, parasites, Salmonella, Staphylococci, AMR) were specified. Interestingly, some project leaders described their contacts with national authorities to keep them updated on project outcomes that may be useful for them. Only sporadically, contacts with other international organizations such as OIE and WHO were acknowledged. One projects (BIOPIGEE) listed contacts with private partners.

This overview and the examples clearly illustrate the impact the JRP may have on the work and tasks of national and international stakeholders, be it regarding surveillance programmes, laboratory tasks for diagnosis and characterization, and risk assessors.

Critical risks

The following table summarises the replies on the critical risks as identified by the Project Leaders and their consortium. This question was only integrated in the 12M reports, not in the Final Reports, i.e. only the second round projects are listed.

PROJECT NAME	JRP12-FARMED	JRP13-WORLDCOM	JRP14-FULL-FORCE	JRP15-FED-AMR	JRP16-TELE-Vir	JRP17-IDEMBRU	JRP18-MEmE	JRP19-PARADISE	JRP20-DISCOVER	JRP21-BIOPIGEE	JRP22-TOXOSOURCES	JRP23-ADONIS	JRP24-BeONE	
Description of risk	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes		Yes	See comment*	Yes	No	yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	
Delay in work plan execution	Yes	Yes related with COVID-19 lockdown	Yes		Yes	Yes	yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No		No		No	No	no	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Lack of commitment of partners	Yes, but this has been due to their involvement with COVID-19 pandemic.		No		No	No	no	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes		Yes		Yes	Yes	no	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

PROJECT NAME	JRP12-FARMED	JRP13-WORLDCOM	JRP14-FULL-FORCE	JRP15-FED-AMR	JRP16-TELE-Vir	JRP17-IDEMBRU	JRP18-MEmE	JRP19-PARADISE	JRP20-DISCOVER	JRP21-BIOPIGEE	JRP22-TOXOSOURCES	JRP23-ADONIS	JRP24-BeONE
Description of risk	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No
Poor intra-project relationship	No		No		No	No	no	No	No	No	No	No	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No		No		Yes	No	yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Other risks (please describe)	No		No			Yes	no	Turnover of staff at some partner's Institute	No	Yes	Yes	No	

Replies are copied from the original reports; the answers '+' and '-' were converted in Yes and No, respectively.

*Comment FED-AMR: A risk management table was developed that served as a basis to mitigate the risks (see FED-AMR report in section 3. Reports on the JRP, Year 4).

Eight of the Project Leaders mentioned the risk of losing key persons. As far as was checked in individual teleconferences with WP3 Team, Project Leaders managed to deal with this situation. Not surprisingly, most projects were delayed (11/13), and mentioned delays in duties, tasks and reporting (9/13), all related to the COVID-19 crisis. Minor risks recorded were: Potential entry/exit of partners (4/13) and Other risks (3/13). There does not seem to be any problem related to conflicts, or intra-project relationship.

3. Final Reports of the first round JRP, Year 4

The five remaining JRP of round one (i.e. ARDIG, TOX-Detect, NOVA, LISTADAPT and MOMIR-PPC) were finalized in June 2021 and the Project Leaders submitted their final reports. These were evaluated by independent, external experts as planned, following the instructions in D3.9 (Guidelines for WP3/WP4 on the evaluation of final reports). All final reports of the first round JRP, together with the evaluation reports and scores of the external evaluators, were published as Deliverable D3.17 (Final reports of 1st call JRPs and evaluation reports).

The entire contents of the final reports have been copied below, except for the paragraphs related to the ethics, the data management and the list of dissemination and communication activities, which can be found elsewhere:

- The fourth Ethics report, encompassing Joint Research Projects, Joint Integrative Projects and PhD, has been delivered as D1.26 Ethical review report for Y4 (25 February 2022) on the EC Participant Portal.
- All information on the data management plan can be found in chapter 4 of the One Health EJP Periodic Technical Report Y4.
- The list of dissemination activities: this information has been analysed and reported in the One Health EJP Periodic Technical Report Y4, paragraph 3.1 “Overview of the dissemination activities”.

JRP02-AMR2-ARDIG

1. Summary of the work carried out

The ARDIG project has continued to progress, and after 42 months there have been substantial achievements made by partners, including numerous peer-reviewed publication of papers from the ARDIG consortium. Several project-wide, as well as work package specific, meetings have also taken place by either meeting physically or by tele/videoconference, and there have been regular communication by email. Both oral and poster presentations made by ARDIG partners were well received at the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meetings held during this project.

WP1 (**Comparison of AMR and antibiotic sales/usage data collected through existing national surveillance and research programs and assessment of risk factors**). The ARDIG project has identified that there is a lack of harmonisation on AMU and AMR in the livestock sector and on AMR in the human sector, although there is some overlap between national and international systems. A One-Health approach for AMU and AMR requires harmonisation in various aspects between systems in the human, animal and food sector; suggestions are provided within ARDIG to address this. Differences in AMR between clinical and non-clinical isolates were identified within and between countries for different animal populations. Higher resistance levels in clinical isolates than in non-clinical isolates were found for calves, while the opposite was found in isolates from broilers and turkeys. Decreasing resistance was found in animal isolates between 2014 and 2017. This suggests that measures carried out against AMR including the reduction in AMU in each country have effective results.

A workshop was held with experts in the field, including those from EFSA, EMA and ECDC and other European projects, to make recommendations for improved “One Health” surveillance strategies.

WP2 (Longitudinal studies of AMR persistence). Both Med and Vet partners have been collecting *E. coli* isolates from retrospective as well as prospective longitudinal studies, including *E. coli* isolated from urinary tract infections from local hospitals, as well as livestock (cattle, pigs and poultry). Several partners have also characterised *E. coli* isolated through EU harmonised surveillance for AMR. In addition, all partners who participated in a whole genome sequencing (WGS) AMR workshop have submitted ~50 WGS each (~450 in total) for analysis by five pipelines: APHA SeqFinder/Abricate, PHE GeneFinder, WBVR, Ariba, ResFinder/PointFinder. The AMR genotypes were compared with the corresponding MIC phenotypes for these isolates. WGS of >3000 isolates collected from longitudinal, as well as national surveillance by partners were also compared, and show human isolates generally to be more similar to each other than those from animals, and vice versa.

WP3 (AMR characterization, transmission of plasmids and fitness of MDR isolates). All WP3 partners participated in the AMR pipeline comparison work to help harmonise *in silico* AMR gene prediction and to assess the impact of methodology on AMR gene prediction; a manuscript is currently being prepared for this work. In addition, all WP3 partners have continued AMR gene, plasmid and mobile genetic element characterization of isolates collected in WP2 by WGS (short and long reads), as well as other molecular techniques. Phylogenetic analysis and AMR profiling performed by partners on their dataset, as well as across ARDIG, have helped identify possible transmission events or epidemiological links between different compartments and countries. Also, plasmid characterisation between and across partners, has provided an overview of the types of AMR plasmids commonly circulating which belong to the following types: IncI, IncF and IncX.

2. Work carried out in the JRP. scientific results

WP1. Comparison of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and antibiotic sales/usage (AMU) data collected through existing surveillance, monitoring and research programs and assessment of risk factors.

This WP was led by BfR, with major contributions from APHA, ANSES, NVI, RKI and PHE; other members of the consortium also contributed as and when appropriate. Details of the work performed in WP1 by the consortium is provided below.

WP1-T1 - Exploration and collection of data available on AMR, AMU and potential risk factors

Institut Pasteur

Monitoring of antibiotic consumption and of antibiotic resistance of bacteria responsible for infections has evolved at the start of the project in France with new actors. Monitoring is now under the responsibility of Santé Publique France (SPF) by the CPias nouvelle Aquitaine with a new tool called Consosres for AMU, and by the CPias Pays de la Loire, with also a new tool called Medqual for AMR. In the past, AMR was monitored by ONERBA (Observatoire National de l’Epidémiologie de la Résistance Bactérienne aux Antibiotiques) which is a private association, collecting information on the voluntary basis. Given this situation, despite much efforts we have not been able to collect additional data on *E. coli* infections beyond what is transmitted by the French authorities to the ECDC (ESAC-net and EARS-net).

WP1-T1 - Exploration and collection of data available on AMR, AMU and potential risk factors

Data were collected from six countries represented in ARDIG (UK, NL, DE, FR, NO, ES) and collated in a database. This included data available in the respective institutions involved in ARDIG but also other National and regional systems in animal husbandry and the medical field. A detailed description of current (2019) surveillance and monitoring systems in the animal and the human sector was prepared, submitted as a deliverable and subsequently published in a peer reviewed paper (Mesa-Varona et al. 2020). A substantial diversity of systems and data types was encountered and comparability of data

was largely hampered by this diversity. Metadata collected in the surveillance and monitoring systems were typically limited which further limited the scope of the analyses in task 2.

WP1-T2- Investigation of trends, associations and risk factors

The available data were first descriptively analysed (see deliverable 1.2) and subsequently a framework was developed to compare AMR in *E. coli* from different animal and human populations. A focus was on the comparison of clinical and non-clinical isolates from animals that showed substantial differences which, however, were observed in both directions, depending on the animal population and the antimicrobial considered. One main obstacle to this analysis were differences in the substances included in AMR-testing between countries and populations (clinical vs. non-clinical) that limited the range of substances with comparable data. Another obstacle, the use of different laboratory methods could be partly overcome by the development of harmonized cut offs. The approach used the same methodology to determine the cut offs for different laboratory methods (i.e. broth microdilution vs. disk diffusion).

Analysis of clinical *E. coli* isolates was carried out to describe and compare trends in resistant *E. coli* isolates originating from clinical diagnostic submissions from three livestock species in three European countries. Associations between antimicrobial resistance and year of sampling, species and country were also investigated. The number of isolates tested increased over years 2014 to 2016 in all three countries and decreased in 2017. Similar patterns in resistance were observed between the countries, with cattle isolates having significantly higher odds of being resistant compared to both pigs and chicken isolates. The level of resistance decreased with age in cattle and chicken, younger animals had significantly higher resistance compared to older animals.

Similarly to the analysis of clinical vs. non-clinical isolates, also analysis of clinical isolates from different livestock species and countries faced the same challenges. Although each country monitors resistance levels of a large number of antimicrobials, only a small number of antimicrobials overlapped between different countries and livestock species, highlighting a need for a better harmonization between different countries and production systems. The use of different animal age categories by different countries also had a limiting impact on the scope of analysis. A further finding was that despite the short observation period (2014 -2017, i.e. four years) for several antimicrobials and animal populations a decrease in resistance was observed in the *E. coli* tested. This indicates that efforts taken by countries to control AMR mainly by reducing AMU did foster some progress, although – given the short time period – this was limited. First results have been published in two peer reviewed papers comparing clinical and non-clinical isolates of *E. coli* from three animal populations (broilers, turkeys and calves) (Mesa Varona et al. 2020b, 2021). Two further papers are in preparation that compare clinical isolates from animal populations between countries and isolates from different pig populations and humans in Germany.

WP1-T3- Develop recommendations for improved “One Health” surveillance strategies

Based on the results of tasks 1 and 2 and experiences of other research groups, namely the Aacting consortium and the EU-JAMRAI project, recommendations were drafted and presented to experts in the field in a workshop on March 1 and 2 of 2021. The workshop included experts from the countries involved in ARDIG and the European Agencies (EFSA, ECDC, EMA). One day of the workshop was dedicated to reporting from the different projects (i.e. ARDIG, Aacting and EU-JAMRAI), from EMA and from Norway that has some experiences in presenting AMU and AMR data in a one health approach. The second day was devoted to three discussion groups working on pre-defined questions on surveillance of AMU (Group 1), AMR (Group 2) and the contribution of molecular methods to routine surveillance (Group 3). The workshop gave evidence of different attitudes to the questions that were partly driven by the different roles of the participants. In the AMU workshop the data collection systems currently developed under the new EU-veterinary medical legislation were extensively discussed and EMA clearly elaborated their needs based on the legislation, which are limited to certain tasks. This of course does not constrain the member states in setting up more ambitious collection systems provided that those systems are also fit to cover EMAs needs. While some participants,

including members of the ARDIG consortium, underlined the usefulness of a harmonization process across the systems, others questioned this need with reference to the diversity of the underlying systems of animal production in the different countries.

A report on the workshop is currently in progress and is meant to be shared and discussed with the workshop participants. It will presumably be published after the consultation phase in early autumn 2021.

Main conclusions and recommendations from ARDIG WP1

On AMR

Collection systems on AMR often adopt specific standards and their corresponding evaluation criteria that do not cover all drug and bug combinations. Therefore, different standards and/or evaluation criteria are sometimes used for different drug and bug combinations in the same system. These systems show a lack of harmonisation within and between countries across the human and animal sectors.

Data collecting systems on AMR should collect data:

- applying the same standard (e.g. EUCAST and CLSI)
- using the same evaluation criteria (i.e. epidemiological vs. clinical approach)
- from both isolate types (i.e. clinical and non-clinical isolates)
- applying a similar antimicrobial panel
- from the same sample type
- addressing the same animal categories

These requirements in the same isolate type should be complied in order to compare, evaluate and analyse AMR. Otherwise, data comparisons could not be in most cases directly addressed.

The NRI approach is a statistical method that can be applied, to overcome the lack of harmonisation on laboratory methods and methodologies. These statistical methods require quantitative data across a substantial range of values for the interpretation of data. Therefore, reports on AMR should provide quantitative values rather than data on the SIR level.

Significant dissimilarities were found between data on clinical and non-clinical isolates within animal categories and countries. Higher resistance proportions were mainly encountered in non-clinical isolates of broilers and turkeys and in clinical isolates of calves. Results in calves confirmed previous descriptive data from other studies and were in line with expectations. However, results in poultry were surprising and require further targeted investigations. The results underline that AMR in clinical and non-clinical isolates needs to be evaluated separately and preferably both should be collected.

The lack of AMR harmonisation on further issues such as the lack of harmonisation on antimicrobial panels and animal categories remains. It is necessary to define a harmonised antimicrobial panel in clinical isolates and between clinical and non-clinical isolates.

Our analyses were applied in *E. coli* isolates of livestock between 2014 and 2017. However, this work could be extended in the future to include other bacteria and for longer periods.

On AMU

EU agreed units are not always provided in reports that show data from regional and national monitoring and surveillance systems on antimicrobial consumption in Europe. These units should be always applied.

ESVAC collected sales data in Europe using the agreed unit mg/PCU. However, this measurement only provides a general overview. Farm-level data are required for further analyses. However, there is no AMU usage agreed unit in the animal sector. To overcome this issue reusing the already collected data, two different approaches have been suggested:

- A harmonised AMU usage unit
- Numerator/denominator data to transform one unit into another:
 - a. The name of the active ingredient
 - b. The amount of active ingredient
 - c. The number of treated animals
 - d. The population at risk
 - e. The weight of treated animals
 - f. The time under treatment
 - g. The duration of the therapeutic effect of the active ingredient in the body

The implementation of the Regulation (EU) No. 6/2019 on veterinary products will greatly improve the comparability of AMU usage data in a large number of animal categories.

AMU data collection should be provided by drug, animal species (e.g. broilers and turkeys instead of poultry), type of production (e.g. broiler or laying hens instead of chicken), age categories when the animal production cycle is long (e.g. weaning or fattening pigs instead of pigs) and the mixture of age category and production (e.g. calves instead of cattle).

Reports on AMU should always report on the same drug and antimicrobial drug categories for the same animal category that should likewise be defined in a harmonised way.

It is significantly important to understand the data collection of the health care systems implemented in each country since the data collection procedure may vary. Therefore, data comparisons should be done with care.

On AMU and AMR

Availability of harmonised usage data for animals will allow enhancing the analyses on the association of use and resistance across countries.

In the field of non-clinical AMR, EFSA drove the harmonisation of EU data-collection. However, there is no incentive to harmonise AMU and AMR systems. In the absence of harmonisation, there is no requirement to report to the EU. A large number of AMU and AMR collecting systems were found per country and sector. Some overlap between monitoring and surveillance systems on AMU and AMR was encountered. This overlap may be convenient for system and data validation. However, a better use of the available sources could save resources.

Overlap between reports has been encountered as a logical consequence of the overlap presence between systems. AMU and AMR reports are published in different languages and time ranges. They should be provided annually in one international language to ease published data access.

Antimicrobial use was identified as an influencing factor on AMR. However, AMR prevalence might not necessarily decrease in some drugs addressing only the reduction of AMU due to phenomena such as co-resistance and multidrug resistance. AMR crisis must be addressed from all available angles (e.g. hygienic measures, vaccination, support of scientific studies and reduction of AMU) and as a collaborative action between countries.

During the funding period of ARDIG, the three agencies, EFSA, EMA and ECDC have jointly prepared the JIACRA report based on reported data from all EU-MS and some other EEA countries. As the WP leader of WP1 was member of the JIACRA working group on behalf of EFSA, he was able to consider the perspective of both projects in his work. The JIACRA report is solely based on non-clinical animal isolates as opposed to clinical animal isolates. The JIACRA report demonstrates that where there is a certain degree of harmonization, analysis can be run, keeping in mind the limitations to these analysis. For example the consumption data in animals in the JIACRA report are based on general sales data which limits the analytical potential. In ARDIG we tried to include population based data on AMU as

derived from the national systems, but as pointed out above, this was hampered by differences in the definition of populations and the units used in the description of use. Therefore, both, our work and the work in JIACRA underline the need for more harmonized data. Moreover, in ARDIG we focused on one bacterial species, including data on clinical and non clinical isolates. The differences we observed between clinical and non clinical isolates may indicate that analysis of clinical animal isolates might provide an additional perspective in one health analyses. ARDIG results show that, provided more harmonized data are available, additional analyses can be run. Currently, a lot of collected data have only limited use, as they are difficult to compare with data from other populations/compartments and countries.

WP2. Longitudinal studies of persistence ESBL/AmpC/carbapenem/mcr-1/PMQR producing Enterobacteriaceae on farms or hospitals

WP2-T1- Assessment and selection of longitudinal data from historical studies

UCM

Data from national surveillance projects carried out between 2014 and 2019 focused on antimicrobial resistance surveillance in different animal production sectors have been arranged to be added to the consortium common data for further analyses. From the EFFORT (Ecology from Farm to Fork Of microbial drug Resistance and Transmission) project, up to 10 *E. coli* isolates were collected from faecal samples of 5 pig farms and 5 poultry farms located in different Spanish regions between 2014 and 2015, obtaining a total of 100 *E. coli* isolates. These isolates were not selected under antibiotic pressure and were further characterized by a standard panel of different antimicrobial compounds in order to assess Minimal Inhibitory Concentrations (MICs). All of them were sequenced by Illumina technology. Random-selected *E. coli* isolates (38 from pig samples and 35 from poultry samples) were included in further analyses for AMR detection pipeline comparisons and phylogenetic studies.

From the national surveillance program of antimicrobial resistance carried out by the VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre and the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA), a total of 200 *E. coli* isolates were collected from faecal samples: 100 isolates from swine production in 2017 and 100 isolates from poultry production in 2016 (50 isolates) and 2018 (50 isolates). These isolates were not selected under antibiotic pressure. All isolates were phenotypically characterized according to their antimicrobial resistance profiles to a standardized panel of antimicrobial compounds. Then, all of them were sequenced by Illumina technology and included in posterior analyses for AMR and plasmid characterization and phylogenetic studies. The results of these analyses are described in AMR characterization section.

Institut Pasteur.

In the course of the ARDIG project we have analyzed two set of data from historical studies.

- ESBL producing *E. coli* collected in the course of the i-bird project: The i-bird project coordinated by D. Guillemot (IP) was based on a 4-month study which took place in 2009 in a rehabilitation hospital. It combined weekly rectal swabs and human-human proximities recorded from wireless captors. 3500 rectal swabs have been collected from 329 patients. A total of 4882 bacterial isolates have been analyzed including 425 *E. coli*. Antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed for 30 antibiotics. 604 ESBL-Enterobacterales were isolated from 84 patients including 332 *E. coli* from 75 patients. One to 25 isolates were collected per patient, including patient colonized by ESBL isolates during the whole study. The main aim of the study was to analyze ESBL-bacteria transmission and plasmid acquisition. We selected 204 isolates for WGS (WP3). Selection was based on the patient to sequence at least one isolate per patient and on the week of sampling and taking into account negative samples (one isolate before and after each negative sample). By comparing over time within and between patient genomic diversity of ESBL-producing bacteria together with contact data, we aim to infer transmission routes and the possibility of an environmental reservoir.

- Carbapenemase producing *E. coli* (CPEc) isolates collected by the French National Reference laboratory for carbapenemase producing enterobacteriaceae (Fr-CNR). CPEc represents a major public health threat for two main reasons. First only few therapeutic options remain to treat bacterial infections due to MDR CPEc and second given the ubiquitous nature of *E. coli*, these bacteria contribute to the dissemination of carbapenemase genes and of plasmids carrying those resistance genes. In Europe CPEc from animal origins are extremely rare and none isolates showing this resistance were isolated in the course of the project. However, we have shown that the acquisition of MDR and of carbapenemase genes is a multistep process. A still open question is the contribution of the animal sector in this process. We have focused our study on the four first years of activity of the Fr-NRC from 2012 (year of creation of the NRC) to 2015. During this period, a steady increase of the number of isolates received by the NRC was observed (44 in 2012, 94 in 2013, 250 in 2014 and 388 in 2015). It is likely a consequence of different factors: (i) an increased circulation of CPEc in France; the increased screening of potential carbapenemase carriers at their admission at hospital, as the number of disease associated isolates was found to increase more slowly than the number of samples from screening and (iii) to a raising awareness of hospital and private laboratories to send CPEc isolates to the Fr-NRC. In order to characterize the diversity of these isolates and of the carbapenemase gene, changes during the four years and their evolutionary trajectory related to the acquisition of the carbapenemase gene, we selected for WGS 713 isolates including 22 isolates received by the Bicêtre Hospital laboratory before 2012 (WP3)

NVI

Isolates from a previous study focusing on cephalosporin resistant Enterobacteriaceae have been characterized. All broiler flocks raised on ten broiler farms were sampled during the period from May to October in 2016 and a total of 43 positive isolates were obtained (one isolate per flock). These isolates have been sequenced with Illumina technology in order to study a possible on-farm persistence/transmission between batches of animals on the same farm or broiler house. In total, 11 different *E. coli* Sequence Types were identified. A possible clonal persistence of ESC-resistant *E. coli* at house level was shown for only a minor proportion of the included houses. Isolates from the same house belonging to the same ST could differ by a considerable number of SNPs, shown for ST38 isolates found in three different houses at one farm from several flocks throughout the sampling period. Similar plasmids were detected in different STs, suggesting possible horizontal transfer and/or persistence of plasmids. Seven ESC-resistant *E. coli* of different STs originating from two farms were selected for ONT sequencing and in-depth characterization of *bla*_{CMY-2}/*IncK2* plasmids. We performed hybrid assemblies and SNP analysis. On one farm, highly similar plasmids of approximately 85 kb size were present in three different STs. The plasmids differed by 17 SNPs. On the other farm, two plasmids of 116-117 kb, harboured additional resistance to sulfamethoxazole, tetracycline and aminoglycosides. When compared using Snippy, 0 SNPs were present between these plasmids. The results indicate that highly similar/identical plasmids can exist in *E. coli* of different STs, and possibly persist on broiler farms. Our data show variation at both gene, plasmid and ST level when ESC resistant *E. coli* from consecutive flocks were characterized. It is not possible to determine whether different *E. coli* variants and/or ESC resistance genotypes were present simultaneously in a flock, as only a single isolate was characterized per sample. A manuscript is in preparation and will be submitted later this year.

PHE

PHE collected carbapenemase producing Enterobacteriales, including *E. coli*, isolated from colonisation and infections by hospital laboratories and referred to the PHE reference national reference lab. The isolates were received by the PHE National Reference laboratory in 2014 and 2016 and have been analysed for their genomic and resistance gene diversity (collaborative manuscript with Katie Hopkins submitted).

ANSES

Extended-Spectrum-Cephalosporins (ESC)-resistant Enterobacteriaceae have been isolated from veal calves in France have been included to be studied within ARDIG. Two studies were set up to investigate

the trends in ESBL/AmpC prevalence and antimicrobial usages (AMU) in veal calves during the fattening process.

In a first study, ten fattening farms were selected and visited twice. A total of 50 animals per farm were sampled for ESC-R carriage and other AMR phenotypes upon arrival and 5-6 months later before slaughter.

A second study was then set up to get further insights into the dynamic of ESBL/AmpC spread over the fattening period. Three farms out of the ten from the first study were visited 11 or 12 times at regular intervals of 15 days. A total of 15 calves per farm were sampled and processed as for the first study. In the two studies, the number and types of treatments during fattening were collected.

WP2-T2- Isolation of resistant Enterobacteriaceae on farms

UoS

Task completed. See second annual report, 2019.

UCM

A total of 110 *E. coli* isolates recovered from urinary tract infections were collected from March 2019 to November 2020 in collaboration with a reference hospital located in Madrid. Out of the 110 isolates, 77 were collected from GP patients (community-related infections) and 33 were obtained from inpatient samples (hospital-related infections). We performed the phenotypic characterization according to the antimicrobial resistance profile of all isolates following standard surveillance antimicrobial panels. We sequenced all collected isolates by Illumina technology to carry out the genomic characterization. Illumina data were applied for subsequent AMR, plasmid and phylogenetic analyses.

WBVR

In 2019 and 2020, a group of approximately 700 veal calves in the Netherlands was individually followed from birth to slaughter on 5 to 6 sampling moments. The animals were born on 13 dairy farms spread throughout the country and transported between 14 and 28 days of age to 8 veal farms for fattening. Rectal swabs were taken at each sampling moment for selective culturing on cefotaxime containing media to determine the prevalence of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli*. At the dairy farms the prevalence of *E. coli* ranged from 0-86% (average 26.4%). At all veal farms the prevalence of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli* amongst the animals went up to >50% at least one sampling moment. In 6 farms, prevalence significantly decreased over time.

Extensive records were recorded on farm management, hygiene, antimicrobial usage and health parameters of the animals and analysed using a linear mixed and multivariate regression model to determine risk factors associated with ESBL/AmpC carriage. No association between age of transportation, sex, breed, and presence of ESC-R *E. coli* at the dairy farm was found. At the dairy farm, different management practices for veal calves destined for fattening or replacement heifers, as well as the presence of pets (cats and dogs) and other livestock (horses, sheep and goats) were positively associated with presence of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli*. The presence of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli* at the veal farm was positively associated with presence of these bacteria at consecutive time points. Antibiotic batch treatment of the animals is positively associated with presence of ESBL/AmpC *E. coli* while individual treatment was not. A manuscript describing these results has been prepared and is currently awaiting approval by collaborators before submission.

Short-read WGS data has been generated of > 300 isolates and confirms extensive clonal spread of ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli*, both on dairy farms through the year and on veal farms during a single production cycle. Nonetheless, multiple variants are spread through each farm and animals are colonised by different *E. coli* variants over time. In order to determine the role plasmid spread in the transmission of ESBLs within the farms, ~70 isolates were selected for long-read using Oxford Nanopore Technologies in collaboration with the OH-EJP FULL-FORCE project which is currently under way.

ANSES

In the two studies, ESBL-producing *E. coli* were collected from MacConkey agar for the culture of the dominant flora and onto selective ChromID ESBL agar (bioMérieux) for the specific selection of ESC-resistant isolates from the subdominant flora. After incubation at 37°C for 24 h, one presumptive *E. coli* colony was arbitrarily selected from each plate and isolates were identified using MALDI-TOF.

In the first study, ESBL-producing *E. coli* rates have significantly decreased in all 10 farms (arrival: 67.7%; departure: 20.4%)(Gay et al, *Frontiers in Microbiology* 2019). Feeding milk containing antimicrobial residues to veal calves is hypothesized to explain the high ESBL loads in animals at the entrance on farms. In the dominant flora, proportions of resistances to amoxicillin, tetracyclines, streptomycin and sulfonamides were very high (>60%) at arrival of animals in the farm and had significantly increased at departure. Proportions of resistances to other beta-lactams than amoxicillin were overall low and significantly decreased during the fattening process. Resistance to quinolones also significantly decreased from arrival to departure. A total of 11 isolates were resistant to colistin (MICs ranging between 6 and 16 mg/L) of which 9 were detected in animals upon arrival (originating from 7 different farms), and 2 in animals at departure (both originating from the same farm). The proportion of multi-resistant isolates significantly increased from 60.2% upon arrival to 67.2% at departure of animals. The proportion of isolates susceptible to the seven selected antibiotics was 23.3% upon arrival and 7.3% at departure. Only two isolates displayed co-resistances to all seven antibiotics.

The second study was performed in three veal farms (A, B and C) located in the region of Brittany, France (Massot *et al*, manuscript submitted). Rectal swabs from 15 calves per farm were collected every 15 days until departure to slaughterhouse and screened for intestinal carriage of ESBL-producing *E. coli*. A decrease in ESBL prevalence in calves was observed over the fattening period, although each farm displayed a specific dynamic. In conclusion, we showed that the diffusion of ESBL-encoding genes in calves is a combination of two scenarios encompassing bacterial clone and/or plasmid spread, which highly rely on local features and contexts, including the types and number of antibiotic treatments per farm.

In this second study, we also took the opportunity of the same sampling to characterize the dynamics of the calves' microbiota subjected to antimicrobial pressure (Massot et al., *Animal Microbiome*, 2020). This observational study showed early convergence of the developing microbiota between veal calves and demonstrated associations between the dose of milk powder and composition of the microbiota. It suggested that group treatments of antibiotics resulted in a reduction of microbial diversity and size of the *E. coli* population in the gut and highlighted the need for additional work to fully understand the impact of antibiotherapy in the veal industry.

Finally, we used the three veal calf fattening farms of the second study as a model to investigate and compare the effectiveness of possible interventions to reduce the AMR burden in this sector (Bastardet al, *One Health* 2021). Longitudinal data of ESBL-EC carriage and antimicrobial use (AMU) were used to develop agent-based mechanistic models to assess different hypotheses regarding the main drivers of ESBL-EC dynamics in calves. The models were independently fitted to the longitudinal data using Markov Chain Monte Carlo and the best model was selected. Within-farm transmission between individuals and sporadic events of contamination were found to drive ESBL-EC dynamics on farms. In the absence of AMU, the median carriage duration of ESBL-EC was estimated to be 19.6 days (95% credible interval: [12.7; 33.3]). In the best model, AMU was found to influence ESBL-EC dynamics, by affecting ESBL-EC clearance rather than acquisition. This effect of AMU was estimated to decrease gradually after the end of exposure and to disappear after 62.5 days [50.0; 76.9]. Moreover, using a simulation study, we quantified the efficacy of ESBL-EC mitigation strategies. Decreasing ESBL-EC prevalence by 50% on arrival at the fattening farm reduced prevalence at slaughter age by 33.3%. Completely eliminating the use of selective antibiotics on arrival had a strong effect on average ESBL-EC prevalence (relative reduction of 77.0%), but the effect was mild if this use was only decreased by 50% compared to baseline (relative reduction of 3.3%).

APHA

We have completed the collection of samples for a longitudinal study which focused on two sites of the same UK pig farm which are separated geographically; a non-clinical farm site that houses five age classes of healthy pigs and has ceased group antimicrobial treatments for at least five years, and a clinical farm site that is comprised of three age classes of pigs sent from healthy sites following disease, that have subsequently undergone group and individual antimicrobial treatment. Faecal samples were obtained from both sites from pigs at four time-points at 6 month intervals over 18 months, alongside seagull faecal samples from two time points. Representative *E. coli* were purified from all time points from non-selective and antibiotic selective agar plates (cefotaxime and ciprofloxacin), followed by Illumina whole-genome sequencing (WGS). The WGS data was analysed by reconstructing phylogeny of the *E. coli* isolates, determining presence of AMR genes, plasmid replicon types, in silico Multilocus Sequence Type and mobile genetic elements (WP3).

MIC determination for the isolates collected during visits 4 and 5 has also been completed. An overall analysis of the MIC data across 5 visits has been carried out. Temporal trends were evaluated, as well as a comparison between antibiotic treated and non-antibiotic treated groups of pigs was carried out. A draft publication is in preparation to report these results.

WP2-T3-Isolation of resistant Enterobacteriaceae in hospitals and care facilities

UoS

Task completed. See third annual report, 2020.

Institut Pasteur

The ARDIG project focused on *E. coli*. Following within the consortium discussion, it was decided to focus on *E. coli* isolates responsible for Urinary Tract Infections (UTI) as those isolates are representative of extra intestinal pathogenic *E. coli* and are collected in different countries in a similar way. In addition, it was decided in this prospective study to collect both isolates of community or hospital origins. Community isolates were either from city microbiology laboratories or from outpatients (emergency) in the hospital. Hospital isolates were from hospital clinical microbiology laboratories. As the objective of the study was to analyze the diversity of the isolates, no data on patient were collected. Several studies have been published on isolate collections following selection for either resistance to third generation cephalosporin (3CG) or producing ESBL and we expected, following such selection to retrieve a majority of ST131 isolates, we decided to have a more agnostic approach and not to select for a specific antimicrobial resistance phenotype. In total, we analyzed 1067 isolates collected in 2019 by five partners:

- Institut Pasteur together with the team of Thierry Naas at the Bicêtre hospital collected a total of 251 isolates, including 123 from emergencies (community) and 128 from the hospital wards. These 251 isolates were submitted to WGS (WP3)

NVI

E. coli isolates from humans with UTI in a large centrally located hospital in Norway, and from GP in the same area were collected (the 20 first isolates of each category, from each month in 2019). The isolates have been sequenced (Illumina short read) at NVI and MIC determination have been carried out. The dominating sequence types were ST131, ST73 and ST69. Resistance genes were uncommonly present in ST73 isolates, in contrast to ST131 isolates that usually were resistant to several antimicrobial agents. No particular ST dominated among hospitalized patients. WGS data are included in analyses in WP3.

PHE

PHE have collaborated with UoS (Rob LaRagione, Maria Getino) to short-read WGS sequence a collection of *E. coli* isolated from human urinary tract infections occurring in the community and a hospital setting. Quality checked sequences have been shared for collaborative analysis at IP.

WP2-T4- Data analysis of collected resistant Enterobacteriaceae on national levels

UCM

Within the framework of the ARDIG project, we have characterized and studied the dissemination dynamics of multi-resistant bacterial clonal groups and the genetic determinants that they carry in different settings, including animal production and hospital environments. The isolates were sequenced by Illumina technology and the resulting data were analyzed for AMR and plasmid characterization and phylogenetic studies. The epidemiological metadata and phenotypic resistance profiles of the isolates were integrated with the genotypic data. Thanks to the studies developed during the project, we have identified risky *E. coli* STs that are disseminated in different production types and environments, such as ST1196 and ST10, as well as genes of resistance against antibiotics of clinical importance, such as *mcr* genes and determinants of resistance to cephalosporins, in both pig and poultry farms. Some of them were selected and sequenced by Nanopore technology, based on Illumina genomic analysis and genotypic resistance profiles, in order to study particular antimicrobial resistance gene dynamics. We are working on the manuscript to public the results obtained at national level, but also, we have collaborated with other partners of the project that have similar results in order to analyse international trends and epidemiological dynamics of specific resistance genes and/or STs.

BfR

On request, the BfR had provided sequencing data on *mcr-1*- and *qnr*-carrying isolates for comparative analysis.

APHA

Whole genome sequencing of ESBL/AmpC *E. coli* that have been collected by APHA from national surveillance of livestock (pig and poultry) since 2013 have been analysed for their AMR gene content as well as plasmid diversity. A paper has been published in Science Reports on AMR analysis in *E. coli* from pigs collected between 2013-2017.

WP2-T5: Comparative analysis of collected isolates on a Europe-wide level (M30-M36)

APHA, ANSES, BfR, IP, NVI, PHE, UCM, UoS, WBVR

ARDIG partners have submitted WGS of up to 50 *Escherichia coli* isolates per institute to a repository and five partners (APHA, WBVR, PHE, UCM, and NVI), representing the diversity of pipelines (APHA SeqFinder/Abriicate, PHE GeneFinder, WBVR, Ariba, ResFinder/PointFinder), have analysed ~450 WGS data through the pipelines. All partners have performed MICs on the EFSA panel of antimicrobials on their isolates from this panel of 450 isolates, so phenotypic data could be obtained for comparison with the AMR genotypes resulting from each of the 5 bioinformatic pipelines.

UoS

The UoS has carried out a comparative analysis of swine *E. coli* isolates collected from four different European countries. A total of 1223 WGS assemblies, including 916 from the APHA (UK), 117 from the UoS (UK), 122 from the UCM (Spain), 50 from the BfR (Germany) and 18 from the WBVR (Netherlands) were included in the analysis. Phylogroups and sequence types were determined using ClermonTyping and MLST bioinformatic tools, respectively. Half of the isolates belonged to phylogroup A, 25% to B1 and 13% to C, whereas the common human phylogroup B2 only represented 1% of the swine isolates, reflecting a low degree of transmission between these hosts. At sequence type level, the most common MLST groups found among swine isolates were ST10 (11%), ST744 (11%) and ST88 (7%).

ResFinder and PlasmidFinder databases were used to characterise the acquired AMR genes and plasmid replicons harboured by the isolates. While the most common plasmid types were IncFIB (48%) and IncI1 (36%), the most abundant AMR genes were *tetA* (41%), *aph(6)*-Id (35%), *bla*TEM-1B (34%), *sul2* (30%) and *bla*CTX-M1 (30%). In addition, point mutations were determined using PointFinder, phylogenetic trees were produced with ParSNP, genes were annotated with Prokka and a pangenome analysis was produced with Roary. Out of a total 33797 genes included in the pangenome analysis,

3006 were core genes with an identity between 99 and 100%. An initial representation of the swine collection of isolates based on core genome phylogeny, gene content and country of isolation, showed no specific pattern, possibly due to the bias of the collection towards UK isolates. However, a complete analysis of over 3,000 *E. coli* isolates from humans and different animal species that is being performed by the different ARDIG partners may provide additional insights into host- and country-specific determinants that may be important for AMR transmission.

UCM

We provided the phenotypic resistance data and genomic sequencing data of 50 *E. coli* isolates from poultry and swine farms in order to compare and analyse our results from AMR detection to those obtained by other partners with different pipelines and AMR databases. We performed the AMR genetic detection over the total 450 *E. coli* isolates collected from all partners using the ARIBA (*Antimicrobial Resistance Identification By Assembly*) pipeline and applying the ResFinder database. Regarding the comparative study of certain clonal groups of epidemiological importance, as well as genetic determinants of resistance and plasmid types involved in their dissemination, our group participated with different partners. We provided sequencing data and metadata of *E. coli* isolates belonging to specific STs requested by partners for in depth studies (ST744 and ST38, among others). Likewise, we have focused on the epidemiological study of ST1196 *E. coli* in diverse environments from different countries, for which other partners provided metadata and sequencing data from their project databases. We have integrated these data to perform epidemiological analysis of clonal dissemination at European level. We cooperated with other partners in the study of the epidemiological dynamics of *mcr* genes across Europe, focusing on the mobile genetic elements involved in their dissemination, by providing Illumina-Nanopore hybrid assemblies of *E. coli* isolates carrying these resistance genes from national surveillance studies. The same way, we have facilitated hybrid assemblies and metadata of multiple *E. coli* isolates harbouring resistance plasmids belonging to specific incompatibility groups (IncFII, IncI1 and IncX) to partners of the project that are developing AI tools focused on the rapid prediction and accurate identification of these AMR genetic platforms.

PHE

PHE has shared short read data with partners for *E. coli* belonging to the ST744 and ST1196 lineages in addition to any *E. coli* harbouring CTX-M-1 and IncI1 sequences in order to facilitate the comparisons of isolates across countries and One Health compartments.

APHA

APHA has collected WGS from *E. coli* ST744 isolates from partners in the consortium for further characterisation. Work is progressing to compare the WGS data by reconstructing phylogeny of the *E. coli* isolates, determine presence of AMR genes and mobile genetic elements present in the isolates.

WBVR

Colistin resistance due to *mcr*-encoding *E. coli* have been described in many countries but most reports concern limited numbers of isolates due to the relatively low prevalence in most countries compared to ESBL/AmpC producing *E. coli*. WBVR have collected *mcr*-encoding *E. coli* from livestock, meat and humans from the Netherlands between 2010 and 2020 and sequenced these using Illumina short read sequencing and a selection of isolates also with Long-read sequencing to complete plasmid sequences. Furthermore, partners from the UK, Germany and Spain have submitted WGS data of *mcr*-encoding *E. coli* from livestock in their collections in order to perform a Europe-wide analysis of > 250 isolates. Analysis of this dataset is currently still ongoing.

[WP3. AMR characterization, transmission of plasmids and fitness of MDR isolates.](#)

WP3-T1 - Detailed molecular characterisation of AMR genes present in human, animal, food and environment isolates from WP1 and WP2.

Five partners (APHA/PHE/WBVR/NVI/UCM) have run WGS data from 450 *E. coli* isolates submitted by ARDIG partners (APHA, ANSES, BfR, IP, NVI, PHE, UCM, UoS, WBVR) through their pipelines (APHA

SeqFinder/Abricate, PHE GeneFinder, WBVR, Ariba, ResFinder/PointFinder) to assess the impact of similarities and differences in methodologies commonly used for AMR genotyping within European Institutes on AMR gene predictions. Results from the pipelines analysis have been shared with the consortium, and partners have compared the AMR genotype prediction for each isolate with the corresponding antimicrobial tested by MIC (EFSA panel), using the database/gene catalogue available to them through their Institute. The results of the genotype/ phenotype comparison have been compiled by APHA and analysed further to identify agreements and discrepancies between each approach, as well as the sensitivity and specificity values to aim for between genotype and phenotype correlations. A manuscript of this work is in its final stages and will include recommendations for future use of WGS for surveillance activities. Such comparisons are of extreme importance to EFSA and ECDC as they are moving to reporting of AMR data by genotyping, and we expect our study to make a valuable contribution to harmonisation of current approaches between animal and human sectors in this context of One Health.

UoS

A total of 730 *E. coli* isolated from four different host species have been characterised by whole genome sequencing. Out of 9 sets of isolates, 4 were collected during longitudinal studies over 12-month periods, including 255 from human urinary tract infections, 108 from human bloodstream infections, 85 from healthy poultry faeces and 117 healthy swine faeces. The other 5 collections of isolates are composed of 94 ESBL-harboring *E. coli* from human urinary infections, 15 *E. coli* from healthy human faeces, 16 collected from the caeca of healthy poultry, 26 from avian colibacillosis samples and 14 from healthy cattle faeces.

The genome assemblies, available metadata and molecular characterization results (including assembly quality, MSLT, phylogroups, AMR genes, AMR point mutations and plasmid replicons detected in these isolates) have been uploaded to the ARDIG shared folder for further analysis.

PHE

Analysis of Enterobacteriales producing carbapenemase enzymes revealed that, in addition to isolates producing the OXA-48 carbapenemase associated with a pandemic of self-transferable IncL/M incompatibility group plasmids, other plasmids belonging to this incompatibility grouping have emerged with the NDM carbapenemase. Analysis revealed the NDM gene had been acquired by IncL/M plasmids on multiple occasions occurring in geographically widespread isolates (manuscript submitted to the Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy). To undertake a risk assessment for the threat posed by these emergent NDM encoding plasmids, examples of the most notable 'type' have been shared for fitness comparisons vs. the pandemic OXA-48 plasmid, at the UoS.

APHA

The farm isolates were characterised further by analysis of the WGS data. Levels of AMR genes present within indicator *E. coli* from non-selective media varied significantly between sites, with 84% identified as multi-drug resistant (3 or more AMR genes) on the clinical site in comparison to 4% on the non-clinical, with a corresponding difference in Sequence Types (ST) identified. In contrast, *E. coli* isolated on both sites from antibiotic selective media were mostly identical STs, with ST744 being the dominant *E. coli* isolated from ciprofloxacin containing media and ST88 the dominant from cefotaxime media. Persistence of ST744 clones with <10 SNP differences were identified across time-points, age classes of pigs and seagull samples in both sites. Both STs have previously been reported from animals and humans globally.

The presence of *E. coli* of the same ST with few SNP differences across time points, pigs and gulls indicates persistence and transmission of *E. coli* subtypes on and between sites. Further work is planned to identify factors that may be selecting these clones on site and maintaining AMR in the absence/low use of antimicrobials. A manuscript of this work is currently under review.

BfR

Within the work package 3 of the ARDIG project, we characterized *Escherichia (E.) coli* isolates recovered from livestock and food, provided by the National Reference Laboratory (NRL) for Antimicrobial Resistance (AR) in depth. Selection of isolates for detailed molecular characterization was based on the prevailing phenotypic characteristics (esp. MIC values, resistance profiles) of the (fluoro)quinolone-resistant *E. coli*. By focusing on nalidixic acid (NAL) and ciprofloxacin (CIP)-resistant *E. coli*, all isolates with a MIC of ≥ 8 mg/L for NAL and/or a MIC of ≥ 0.25 mg/L for CIP were further characterized. In total, 452 *E. coli* from the NRL-AR collection of 2017 fulfill the requirements for further investigation. These isolates were screened for six different *qnr*-variants, namely: *qnrA*, *qnrB*, *qnrC*, *qnrD*, *qnrS* and *qnrVC*. The most frequent *qnr*-variant was *qnrS* with 16.1 % among all investigated isolates. Despite of *qnrS*, the occurrence of other *qnr* genes in the isolate collection was rather low. For screening of genomic relation of *qnr*-positive *E. coli*, we conducted XbaI macrorestriction analysis (XbaI-PFGE). The resulting phylogenetic tree revealed certain relations between a few isolates, but overall a broad diversity of XbaI-patterns was observed. For plasmid prediction, the isolates were subjected to S1-nuclease PFGE. This investigation in combination with DNA-DNA hybridization against *qnr*-genes allowed us to derive plasmidal associations with *qnr*-determinants. One-hundred and three *E. coli* were further subjected to Illumina NextSeq sequencing and were analyzed in detail for their genetic types (i.e. cgMLST, MLST, serotype etc.) and specific features (i.e. AMR, virulence, biocides etc.). The sequencing data were further used for predicting associations between the occurrence of *qnr* and isolate- or plasmid-specific features.

UCM

A total of 383 *E. coli* isolates collected and selected in the WP2 of the project were sequenced using Illumina technology, comprising samples from diverse sources: human hospital settings (110 isolates) and swine and poultry production farms (138 and 135 isolates, respectively). All isolates were obtained from non-supplemented culture media, in order to have an extensive and representative *E. coli* population according to AMR profiles. Phenotypic resistance profiles to different antibiotic groups by MIC evaluations were performed, showing a general high prevalence of fluoroquinolone and tetracycline resistance among all collected isolates from animal production sources. With Illumina data we studied the resistance gene content to all antibiotic families, comparing our results to those obtained by other partners with different AMR detection pipelines over the same isolates. This allowed us to identify the similarities and discrepancies between different bioinformatic tools and databases, which will be extremely useful for implementation of national and global AMR surveillance programs. We assembled the reads obtained by Illumina sequencing to perform the detection of antimicrobial resistance genes following different approaches and to identify the different *E. coli* sequence types involved in the dissemination of specific resistance genes at national and international levels. From 100 analyzed isolates from swine and poultry farms, a total of 45 different STs were identified, highlighting a high clonal diversity in the animal production area. However, one of this STs, ST10, was comprised by 23 isolates from both production types, representing the 23% of the isolates, which shows the broad distribution of this clonal group. Other ST, ST1196, also showed a high dissemination in different sources (including human, animal and environmental samples), not only in Spain, but in other several countries around the world. Thus, our group is focused on the epidemiological study of this clonal complex and other ARDIG partners provided sequencing data and metadata of isolates belonging to ST1196, so we are finishing phylogenetic analysis to put in context the epidemiological links of all multi-drug resistant isolates found. We are working on the publication of these results. In addition, one of our main goals was the study of the dissemination dynamics of *mcr* colistin resistance genes on different mobile genetic elements and *E. coli* clones, such as ST1196 and plasmids belonging to IncI and IncX types. We have collaborated with other partners to combine our *mcr*-carrying isolates and we have performed Nanopore WGS to resolve the genomic structure of these isolates and the plasmids involved in the dissemination of these clinically relevant resistance genes. We provided to the project the assemblies and analyses of Illumina data from all human, swine and poultry *E. coli* isolates in order to establish their clonal relationship and common genetic and plasmid contents.

ANSES

In the first study, the ESBL phenotype was largely due to the presence of CTX-M group 1 enzymes, which were identified in 71.5% of the animals upon arrival, and in 61.2% upon departure to the slaughterhouse (Gay et al, *Frontiers in Microbiology* 2019). Of the 241 *bla*_{CTX-M}-group1-carrying *E. coli* upon arrival, 200 harbored *bla*_{CTX-M-1} (200/241, 83.0%), 23 *bla*_{CTX-M-15} (23/241, 9.5%), 12 *bla*_{CTX-M-32} (12/241, 5.0%); 4 *bla*_{CTX-M-55} (4/241, 1.7%) and 2 *bla*_{CTX-M-3} (2/241, 0.8%). PFGE profiles performed on a subset of 10 ESBL-producing isolates per farm upon arrival showed a wide variability without any clustering. At departure, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} was also the most frequently identified gene (51/60, 85%) followed by *bla*_{CTX-M-55} (4/60, 6.7%), *bla*_{CTX-M-15} (3/60, 5.0%), and *bla*_{CTX-M-3} (2/60, 3.3 %). At departure, the PFGE profiles were much more similar than upon arrival so that a high degree of clonality was observed inside each farm. As an example, the PFGE distribution in farm E at departure, where three distinct PFGE profiles were observed, highlights the epidemiological success of certain ESBL *E. coli* clones more than others during the fattening process. Nonetheless, since different CTX-M enzymes were also produced by the same clone, not only a clonal but also a plasmid dissemination has likely occurred, which illustrates the complexity of ESBL spread at farm level. Similarly, the emergence of CTX-M-2 enzymes before slaughter was most likely due to the dissemination of a single clone within farm C since all but one CTX-M-2 enzymes were identified in this farm. Altogether, depending on the farm presenting ESBL-positive isolates, from 1 (farm H, 1 ESBL producing *E. coli* isolate) to 7 (farm B, 26 ESBL-producing *E. coli* isolates), distinct PFGE profiles were observed at the end of the fattening process. Of note, none of the successful clones identified at departure for the slaughterhouse was shared between farms, proving a specific and local evolution. *E. coli* belonged to phylogroups A (n = 134, 39.8%), B1 (n = 78, 23.1%), B2 (n = 9, 2.7%), and D (n = 116, 34.4%) upon arrival, and to phylogroups A (n = 50, 51.0%), B1 (n = 15, 15.3%), B2 (n = 1, 1.0%), and D (n = 32, 32.7%) at departure to slaughterhouse. The *mcr-1* gene was identified in 18 isolates, while one isolate carried both the *mcr-1* and *mcr-3* genes. At departure for slaughterhouse, only 4 animals from 2 different farms still carried a colistin-resistant *E. coli* (MICs ranging between 2 and 4 mg/L). The *mcr-3* gene was detected in all four isolates and was co-harbored with the *bla*_{CTX-M-55} gene.

In the second study, one colony was isolated from the 173 positive samples for further characterization (Massot et al, manuscript submitted). The ESBL-producing *E. coli* isolates carried either *bla*_{CTX-M-1} (112/173 isolates, 64.7%), *bla*_{CTX-M-14} (58/173, 33.5%) or *bla*_{CTX-M-15} (3/173, 1.8%). All of them were resistant to at least two antimicrobials other than β-lactams, the most common resistances being against tetracyclines, sulfonamides, trimethoprim and aminoglycosides. The median number of co-resistances was four.

Institut Pasteur

Study 1. Analysis of CPEc isolates received by the Fr-NRC. We have sequenced 713 isolates received by the Fr-NRC until 2015 by using the Illumina technology. As ST38 represented the most frequent ST

Figure X Phylogeny of 713 CPEc isolates received by the FrNRC. Genome annotation are indicated in outside circles as indicated in the figure key on the left

among those isolates, we sequenced to completion by using the PacBio technology 10 CPEc ST38 isolates. Furthermore, in order to quantify the fitness cost of plasmids carrying carbapenemase genes we similarly fully sequenced six isolates from ST38, ST410 and ST131 closely related to CPEc isolates, but devoid of any carbapenemase genes. We performed whole genome phylogeny of the 713 CPEc isolates together with reference *E. coli*

isolates. For each isolate, we determined the ARG content and the presence of mutations known to contribute to decrease susceptibility in *gyrA*, *parC* and *parE* QRDR regions (fluoroquinolones), in the porin genes *ompC* and *ompF* and in the penicillin binding proteins 3 (PBP3) gene *ftsI* (β -lactams). The most frequent carbapenemase genes were *bla*_{OXA-48}, (65%), *bla*_{OXA-181} (15%), *bla*_{NDM-5} (7%) and *bla*_{NDM-1} (6%). We observed a great diversity of CPEc as the 713 isolates belong to 166 STs from all phylogroups. Nevertheless 57% of the isolates belong to 14 STs with at least 10 isolates. In particular we identified 3 dominant lineages: clonal complex (CC) 10 (including ST10, ST167 and ST617), CC23 including ST410 and ST38 which together gather 50% of the isolates (Figure X). In terms of relation with animal isolates, two CC23 lineages need to retain further attention: ST410 for which closely related ESBL producing bovine isolates have been characterized and ST88 (15 isolates), which was the most frequent lineages among 540 3GC-R *E. coli* isolates from diarrheic veal in Belgium we have analyzed.

Phylogenetic analysis (Figure X) revealed a combination of disperse isolates and of lineages enriched in CPEc isolates. We first focused our analysis on an ST410 clade broadly disseminated and producing OXA181. *bla*_{OXA-181} is carried by a *incX3* plasmid. Analysis of mutations in the branch leading to the ST410 OXA-410 clade revealed candidate loci which might have contributed to the dissemination of this clone. Among those mutations, we focused our analysis on mutation in *ompC*, *ompF* and *ftsI* which lead to decrease susceptibility to some β -lactams including ertapenem. We first extended this analysis to the whole species by retrieving CPEc genome from the NCBI and Enterobase web sites. We combined phylogeny and association study to define three evolutionary trajectories: (i) broadly disseminated MDR lineages mutated in these three genes before the acquisition of the carbapenemase gene and contributing to the “success” of these clones, (ii) ST38 which shows specific properties including an intrinsic reduced susceptibility to certain β -lactams, and (iii) diverse isolates which have likely recently acquired a carbapenemase gene with no sign of dissemination. This last class included isolated from the pandemic lineage ST131 (Patino Navarrete et al. 2020).

We next analyzed data on Fr-NRC isolates considering these observations (Rosinski-Chupin et al. in preparation). Similarly, to what was observed on worldwide collection of isolates, Fr-NRC isolates belong to the same three categories. Sporadic cases were mainly associated with *bla*_{OXA-48}. It could be due to the high conjugation efficiency of the *IncI* pOXA-48 plasmid and its high prevalence in *K. pneumoniae* isolates in France. We also identified and confirmed three clusters of isolates corresponding to hospital outbreaks which all belong to MDR lineages.

Finally, we focused our analysis on ST38 isolates by characterizing the disseminated lineages. Strikingly, the vast majority of isolates belong to three disseminated lineages. In these three lineages, all ARG were inserted into the chromosome and were generally devoid of any plasmid. Combined analysis with publicly available ST38 genomes showed that two of these clades were broadly disseminated, whereas one clade was mostly restricted to France with few isolates from the Netherlands. In order to better characterize the insertion and their dynamic, we fully sequenced 10 isolates belonging to these lineages. In addition to the OXA-48 producing clades, we identified a small cluster of seven isolates carrying *bla*_{VIM-4}. In this case, the carbapenemase gene was not inserted into the chromosome but carried by a new plasmid we characterized. The *bla*_{VIM-4} gene is carried by an integron. Strikingly, it is virtually identical to the non-conjugative plasmid pROUEN1, a plasmid identified in an MDR *Pseudomonas putida* clinical isolate (Eleni Liapis et al. *Frontiers in Microbiology* 2019). pROUEN1 carries a similar integron with five resistance genes including the *bla*_{IMP-63}. Therefore, the only difference between the two plasmids is the gene content of the integron. This observation raised the issue of the evolution from one plasmid to the other one. Our hypothesis is that pVIM-4 derived from pROUEN1 by integration (including *bla*_{VIM-4}) and loss of cassettes (including *bla*_{IMP-63}). It raised also the issue of the acquisition of this plasmid. Analysis of *E. coli* sequences from Enterobase did not reveal any related isolates carrying *bla*_{IMP-63} and BLAST search at the NCBI no similar plasmid. This plasmid does not seem to have disseminated.

Study 2: Analysis of the i-bird collection. The 205 isolates belong to 32 different STs revealing a broad diversity of ESBL-*Ec* carried by the patients. However, 100 belong to ST131, almost 50%. They are carriage isolates recovered from systematic screening and not clinical isolates, showing that, in this environment, ST131 is dominant even among colonizing ESBL isolates. In-depth phylogenetic analysis

of the 205 isolates revealed cases of transmission or of a common source only for ST131 isolates (Fig. 1). ST131 isolates clustered in four groups (Figure 1) with exchanges between patients, as exemplified for group 3 (in blue) identified in seven patients. Furthermore, we observed a within host diversity. A representative isolate of each lineage was fully sequenced by combining long read (PacBio) and short read (Illumina) sequencing to characterize the within- and between host diversity and to infer transmission and directionality. The genomic data will be confronted with temporal and contact data collected during the i-bird project. Therefore, the prolonged carriage of ST131 ESBL-P isolates and their capacity to be transmitted from patient to patient have likely contributed to their predominance among ESBL-P *E. coli*. We also identified three cases of plasmid transmission from *K. pneumoniae* to *E. coli* but no cases of transmission from *E. coli* to *K. pneumoniae*, suggesting that in this context, *E. coli* act mainly as a receiver more than a donor of antibiotic resistance plasmids.

Figure X Phylogenetic tree of 100 ST131 isolates from the i-bird project. The majority of isolates clusters in four different clades that have disseminated in the hospital.

Analysis of UTI isolates from ARDIG

The 250 isolates from UTI collected by ARDIG partners (IP, UCM, NVI, UoS) have been sequenced by the Illumina technology. The isolates belong to 81 different ST revealing a broad diversity (Fig. X). The four most frequent STs are also frequently reported in other studies as responsible for UTI (ST73, 31 isolates; ST131, 20 isolates; ST69, 19 isolates and ST95, 18 isolates). Susceptibility to β -lactams has been determined by disc diffusion assays for the first 120 isolates. MICs of 25 isolates for 14 antibiotics were determined by serial microdilution by ANSES for benchmarking pipelines for ARG identification and for genotype phenotype correlation. Antibiotic resistance genes have been detected using Resfinder and candidate mutations have been investigated by using point finder. 21% of the isolates share a mutation in the FQRD region of *gyrA* and/or *parC* and were predicted to show a reduce susceptibility to fluoroquinolons, whereas 11% express a ESBL of the CTX-M family. Only one isolate, of ST410, carries a carbapenemase gene (*bla*_{OXA181}). These genome sequences are combined to other ARDIG *E. coli* sequences for a global analysis.

NVI

NVI was responsible for phylogenetic analysis of *E. coli* isolates of human and animal origin collected by from partner countries (UCM, IP, NVI, UoS, WBVR, APHA, BfR). A phylogenetic reconstruction of all

Figure X. ST distribution among the 250 UTI isolates

distances between the genomes. After inspecting the phylogenetic tree, subclades were selected for further analysis. The selection of clades was based on the following: To show a possible transmission between food producing animals and humans (demonstrate shared strains between humans/animals), and to demonstrate closely related strains from the same animal species, but originating from different countries (which again can indicate AMR transfer via international animal trade). Each subclade was subjected to another phylogenetic pipeline, using the ALPPACA pipeline (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4452122). Briefly, ParSNP was used to predict the core genome, and Gubbins was used to identify recombinant areas in the alignment. Then, maskrc-svg was used to mask these regions in the alignment, and IQ-Tree reconstructed the phylogeny from that alignment.

WBVR

WBVR have been responsible for determining the AMR gene content of the 3812 *E. coli* isolates of human and animal origin collected by from partner countries (UCM, IP, NVI, UoS, WBVR, APHA, BfR). These isolates were run through the ResFinder pipeline, which performs similar to other pipelines used by consortium members, to determine the isolate AMR genotypes. Differences between host species, geography and management systems that may impact on AMR content and distribution is currently being assessed.

WP3-T2- Characterisation of prevalent circulating plasmids and their transfer in vitro

UoS

The UoS has quantified the transfer of a representative set of broad host range plasmids carrying NDM-1 and OXA-48 carbapenemase genes. Original host species (*E. coli*, *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella oxytoca* and *Citrobacter*) were used as donors in conjugation experiments performed for 1h on LB-agar. A broad range of frequencies was observed when original hosts were used as donors (from no detected transconjugants to high conjugation rates), while more homogeneous results were obtained when the obtained transconjugants (*E. coli* MG1655) were used as donors, reflecting the high sequence similarity between plasmids.

As a general rule, IncL OXA-48 plasmids conjugated at a higher rate than IncM NDM-1 plasmids, likely due to the inactivation of the fertility inhibition gene *tir* in IncL plasmids, and possibly causing the more extensive global spread of OXA-48 plasmids.

UCM

We determined the plasmid content of *E. coli* isolates from WP2, identifying all different plasmid incompatibility groups according to plasmidic replication structures using short-read sequencing data. We focused on the study of dissemination dynamics of *mcr* genes, among others. Out of 35 *mcr-1*-carrying *E. coli* isolates identified in both swine and poultry production farms, we selected 20 belonging to diverse clonal complexes and sources to perform WGS using Nanopore technology. We generated

Illumina-Nanopore hybrid assemblies of the *E. coli* genomes, which allowed the in-depth study of plasmids and mobile genetic elements involved in the dissemination and mobilization of *mcr* genes among these bacteria at farm, regional and national levels, as well as the association of these genes with other genetic resistance mechanisms in the same plasmidic platform. The results showed two different epidemiological routes of *mcr-1* dissemination in animal farms in Spain: i) dissemination via specific bacterial clones, which are present in different farms, even in different animal production types; ii) dissemination via specific plasmid types highly associated with *mcr* genes, which are spread and present in multiple bacterial clones. Among these plasmids, those belonging to the Inc11 type were the most prevalent ones. We are finishing conjugation experiments to assess the capacity of these plasmids to be transferred and maintained at intra and interspecies level. We are currently preparing a manuscript with the aforementioned results. Furthermore, we provided the metadata and Illumina-Nanopore sequencing data of all these *mcr-1*-positive *E. coli* isolates to other partners of the project in order to study the dissemination dynamics of *mcr* colistin resistance genes and their carrying mobile genetic elements and *E. coli* clones at the European level.

BfR

For determination of plasmid-types carrying *qnr*, we focused on *in-silico*-based finishing of the plasmid genomes. For this, the refSNPer tool was used, which elects the closest reference, by mapping the input sample to a chosen reference set and identifies the coverage by using bedtools. With this, we were able to assign several *qnr*-carrying plasmids to reference plasmids and track putative plasmid paths. Moreover, we discovered plasmids, which are yet not described to be associated with *qnr*. In this manner, we detected the most frequently detected plasmid to cluster for the groups of IncY (n=19) and IncX (n=27). It has been emphasized before, that there is a correlation between this IncX plasmids, harboring *bla*_{TEM} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15} genes next to *qnrS*, resulting in ESBL-producing *E. coli*. We could confirm this observation through annotation of our sequences. IncX plasmids are regularly described as a group inhabiting the *qnrS1* gene. Therefore, we decided to determine this plasmid group in detail. We wanted to find out more about the *E. coli*, prone to inhabit this plasmid type and we wanted to describe a proper plasmid backbone. Moreover, our aim was to derive a core genome for the individual *qnr* plasmid types. With this, we wanted to understand their potential in disseminating *qnrS1* and other potential resistance genes. However, the *E. coli* inheriting the IncX-plasmid carrying the *qnrS1* were highly heterogenic. We found diverse ST-types of *E. coli* as well as different matrices, which did hold the respective IncX plasmids. From the XbaI-macrorestriction profile, we confirmed a high diversity of *E. coli*, possibly transmitting this plasmid. Thus, one can conclude that this plasmid, carrying the *qnrS1* gene, is spreading over different *E. coli* types within multiple sources. Further, we screened for their conjugational behavior. First, we determined the conjugational behavior *in silico* with the mob-suit tool. Thus, we found most of the *qnrS* carrying IncX plasmids to hold the respective relaxase and oriT region on the plasmid, suggesting possible transfer. This observation was then validated by laboratory experiments. However, the *in vitro* and *in silico* results for evaluation of the transmissibility of the plasmids mostly showed divergent results.

Next to the *in-silico* detection of plasmid references, we analyzed plasmid structures with long-read sequencing methods. Thus, we were able to generate scaffolds for the most prevalent *qnr*-carrying plasmid types. These basis structures assisted when reconstructing of other *qnr*-plasmid was aimed for characterization of the most prevalent plasmids.

Next to *qnrS* we set our focus on *qnrB*-carrying plasmids in ESBL producing *E. coli*. Therewith, we found some prevailing plasmid types as IncH and Col440I. Further characterization of these plasmids indicates that especially *qnrB19* did mainly exist on small, non-conjugative plasmids. Thus, the spread of these small plasmids remain a mystery. Furthermore, we detected *qnrB2* on IncH plasmid, known for spreading multi-resistance across different matrices. The presence of these *qnrB* resistance determinants in ESBL-producing *E. coli* do pose a particular risk, as it may confer resistance against a “Highest Priority Critically Important Antimicrobials” for human medicine next to the already present genes leading to ESBL producing *E. coli*.

Altogether, with those comprehensive investigations of *qnr*-positiv *E.coli* isolates a thorough and complex picture will be generated for the mobile genetic elements and their dissemination as well as their commonalities in commensal *E. coli*.

NVI

Analysis of circulating ESBL plasmids/strains from broilers in Norway have been performed by using both short and long-read sequencing (isolates with blaCTX-M-1 located on IncI1-ly plasmids). Our data showed that dissemination of blaCTX-M-1 in Norwegian broiler production is due to both clonal expansion and horizontal transfer of plasmids carrying blaCTX-M-1. The genetic diversity at both strain and plasmid level indicates multiple introductions to Norwegian broiler production. The study was published in *Frontiers in Microbiology*.

Comparison studies showed that blaCTX-M-1 plasmids circulating in Norwegian broiler production are highly similar to plasmids previously described from broiler production in other countries. Reconstruction of blaCTX-M-1/ IncI1-ly plasmids from broilers in Norway showed that a plasmids from ST57 isolates harboured IncI1-ly/IncFIB hybrid plasmids with blaCTX-M-1. Conjugation experiments showed that a non-hybrid IncI1-ly blaCTX-M-1 plasmid (sequence similar to the IncI1-ly part on the co-integrated IncI1-ly/IncFIB plasmid) was transferred into more recipient strains, indicating that the non-hybrid plasmid exhibited a greater promiscuity in terms of acceptance and maintenance by various *E. coli* strains.

ANSES

The *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene was carried by five plasmid types disseminated in 16 clones (encompassing 112/173 isolates, 64.7%), while the *bla*_{CTX-M-14} gene was carried by five plasmid types disseminated by 15 clones (encompassing 58/173 isolates, 33.5%) (Massot *et al*, manuscript submitted). The *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-14} genes were carried by distinct plasmids and clones. Of note, the *bla*_{CTX-M-15} gene was detected on the chromosome of the same clone in farms B and C. Four ESBL plasmids were identified in several farms: IncI1/ST312 in farms A and B, IncK in farms A and C, IncF/F2:A-B- in all three farms, and IncF/F2:A-B42 in farms A and C. IncF/F2:A-B42 plasmid was spread by the same *E. coli* clone in different farms, and the others by distinct *E. coli* clones in the different farms. While present in two farms, IncK and IncF/F2:A-B42 plasmids were detected only in one clone per farm, suggesting a limited spread. On the opposite, IncI1/ST312 and IncF/F2:A-B- have spread in several clones in each farm.

APHA

To characterize prevalent plasmids and their dissemination between different systems (D-3.3 and D-3.4), including different host types and geography, APHA has been evaluating a machine learning approach where by presence of some of the most common AMR plasmid types such as those harbouring Inc-I1, Inc-F and Inc-X can be determined. Validation of a test set of isolates harbouring these Inc-types from various partners (APHA, NVI, UCM, and WBVR) with long and short read WGS available, has indicated clearly that the machine learning approach can identify isolates from each Inc-type, as well as separate AMR from non-AMR harbouring plasmids. As part of the next step we are testing all 3812 *E. coli* isolates of human and animal origin collected by partner countries (UCM, IP, NVI, UoS, WBVR, APHA, BfR) to determine what plasmids may be common and disseminating across these regions and host-types.

WP3-T3- Fitness cost of AMR and stability of plasmids in different host strain background

UoS

The UoS has performed *in vitro* growth curves in different media to determine the fitness cost of IncL/M plasmids carrying NDM-1 and OXA-48 genes in *E. coli* MG1655 and other Enterobacterial hosts. In most cases, the tested plasmids had an associated fitness cost to the bacterial host when compared to the growth rate of the same bacteria with no plasmid. In addition, the fitness cost associated with OXA-48 plasmids in *E. coli* MG1655 was slightly lower than the corresponding cost of NDM-1 plasmids, which could also contribute to the increased success of OXA-48 plasmids.

UCM

Fitness and stability experiments of most prevalent *mcr-1*-carrying plasmids from swine and poultry Spanish farms are programmed after completing conjugation assays. Experiments are scheduled to be performed with a broad range of bacterial hosts, including diverse *Enterobacterales* species.

BfR

In this task, selected plasmid types (n=12) were further chosen for fitness and stability tests. Therefore, the *qnr*-carrying isolates were introduced into *E. coli* J53 by transformation or conjugation. The growth performance of the *E. coli* with and without the different *qnr*-plasmid types showed no significant differences. We had also not observed a significant difference in the stability of the plasmids in *E. coli* J53 under selective and non-selective conditions over a time of >150 bacteria generation. Thus, we suppose that the selected *qnr*-carrying plasmids probably had not an influence on the growth of the *E. coli* and will persist without any significant loss over time within its host bacterium. However, up to now we cannot predict any potential influence of the different plasmid types on the fitness and their stability in other Enterobacteriaceae. Based on the results of the conjugation, the majority of the plasmids could be also successfully transferred, but with lower efficacy to other Enterobacteriaceae (i.e. *Klebsiella*, *Morganella*). Further fitness and stability tests need to be done to develop reliable data on this issue.

NVI

Fitness cost and competitive growth of IncI plasmids with ESBL/pAmpC genes from Norwegian broiler production have been performed. We have also investigated the rearrangement of IncI1 shufflons which segment B was interrupted by the transposition unit ISEcp1-blaCTX-M-1-orf477. The study included two IncI1 plasmids (pMLST CC3) harbouring shufflon interrupted by the transposition unit, and a plasmid harbouring uninterrupted, complete shufflon. Plasmids with interrupted shufflons were present in their original hosts and conjugated into an *E. coli* ST162 strain. Liquid single-strain cultures were sampled at four time points during bacterial growth and the shufflon region was PCR amplified and amplicons were subjected to ONT sequencing. The interrupted shufflons generated a lower number of shufflon variants in comparison to the uninterrupted shufflon. Segment-loss frequency of the interrupted shufflons was distinctive in different plasmid hosts. In both uninterrupted and interrupted shufflons, segment A was more favoured to complete partial *pilV* ORF. The study was published in Plasmid.

WP3-T4- Measuring AMR plasmid dissemination in vivo in mouse and Galleria, and chicken and pig in-vitro gut models

UoS

Representative examples of OXA-48 and NDM-1 IncL/M plasmids transferred to *E. coli* MG1655 were used as donors in *Galleria mellonella* conjugation experiments. These studies were performed over a 4h period following injection of 10⁷ CFU of donors and recipients into the *Galleria*, separately. Although the differences in transfer rates between both plasmids were not statistically significant due to high variability rates, the frequencies of the OXA-48 plasmid were slightly higher, reinforcing previous findings *in vitro*. Interestingly, in each case, both transfer rates *in vitro* (1 h in LB-agar) and *in vivo* (4h in *Galleria*) were very similar.

Figure X. *In vivo* conjugation frequency of IncL/M plasmids harbouring NDM-1 (PSAP1756) and OXA-48 (POXA48-1). 10^7 CFU of donors (*E. coli* K12 carrying the plasmid) and 10^7 CFU of recipients (*E. coli* K12) were injected into *Galleria mellonella* larvae. Inoculated larvae were incubated for 4 h at 37 °C, euthanised and homogenised. Donor, recipient and transconjugant CFU/ml were selected in plates containing the corresponding antibiotic combinations. Transfer frequency was calculated as the logarithm of transconjugants per recipient.

The *in vivo* mouse work and *in-vitro* gut models could not be performed due to continued restrictions from Covid19 severely impacting the amount of laboratory activities that could be undertaken for this workpackage; therefore Milestone M-AMR2.ARDIG.16 could not be delivered. The WGS pipeline comparison and analysis of isolates collected from both national and longitudinal farm studies by phylogenetics were additional *in silico*, and the laboratory component (i.e. isolation of *E. coli* and WGS) had already been delivered.

WP4. Project coordination and management.

WP4-T1- Steering committee quarterly meeting

Regular tele- and video-conference meetings, and updates by email, have been made to all members in the steering committee within ARDIG.

WP4-T2- Consortium members annual meeting

Due to COVID19 posing restrictions on travel the ARDIG consortium was unable to meet physically for an annual ARDIG meeting in both 2020 and in 2021, where at least one member from each partner organization was expecting to attend. However, an online meeting via Zoom or MS Teams, was successfully held between partners. It provided an opportunity for partners from all WPs to interact and discuss the work being performed in ARDIG.

Previous to 2020, the ARDIG consortium met physically during the OH-EJP ASMs to discuss and review the project, its objectives and deliverables.

ARDIG partners have used telecommunications and video conferencing facilities, to remain in touch. Regular meeting have been held over the past 42 months of this project to ensure the project is progressing well, and to capture any delay which may have resulted, especially due to the impact of COVID19.

WP4-T3- Reporting and communication

Several work package associated subgroup meetings have been held online to provide time for more in-depth discussion between partners.

All ARDIG 9M and 12M reports were submitted in full and in a timely manner. There have been a number of publications, presentation (both oral and poster) from ARDIG partners which has included work performed within ARDIG.

3. Project self-assessment

The ARDIG project has been highly successful; it has been extremely collaborative, completed all major Milestones and Objectives, and partners have delivered a large number of publications, with several still in preparation or under review, despite the setbacks of COVID19. Assessment of each WP individually is given below.

WP1: Most objectives of ARDIG WP1 were achieved. However, we had hoped to collect and analyse a larger range of variables regarding AMR and AMU. Analysis was substantially hampered by a lack of harmonization across systems and within systems across regions and countries. Based on the collection efforts we are now able to better characterize the shortcomings of the current systems from a one health and transnational perspective. This may inform future efforts for more harmonization and support current efforts such as the EARS-Vet proposal.

WP2: The large number of isolates with WGS data available from both retrospective and prospective studies from partner collections has made it possible to perform AMR trend analysis both within and between countries and compartments. This was a key deliverable for ARDIG and such comparisons will help understand how mobile genetic elements may be disseminating. A possible short fall was that not all “vet” partners were able to access the same livestock farm-type or visit farms at the same frequency, which has made it somewhat challenging to compare across the ARDIG dataset. This shortfall was mainly due to budget constraints which meant partners had to incorporate ARDIG Objectives within existing national and/or research studies, in addition to leveraging national co-funding. Nevertheless, comparison of WGS data collected from both human clinical and veterinary settings, has been performed and analysed, as described in Section 2.

WP3: In general, the main objectives of the WP3 were achieved. The performed analyses had also supported the development of routine sequencing in the NRL-AR and bioinformatics analysis for assessment of AMR dynamics in commensal E. coli. However, sequence comparisons with different interpretation pipelines showed that further harmonization would be necessary to obtain comparable results at the EU level. Furthermore, the interpretation of in silico data without any additional phenotypic or genotypic data can also lead to misinterpretation. In general, the analyses confirmed the suitability of WGS for resistance prediction, but further efforts are necessary to improve interpretation of the observed genes and the genomic association (plasmid vs. chromosome). Studies on the dynamics of plasmids will need further efforts in the future, because of the broad diversity of transmissible plasmid types, which sometimes also differ from region to region and from country to country. Due to the remit of ARDIG being so broad, long read was performed on only a small proportion of isolates with short read data available, so most plasmid genomes remained unresolved. We have therefore developed a machine learning approach to utilise the short read data for plasmid characterisation, which require further testing in future.

4. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
02	D-1.1	A report of AMR and AMU data (and data collection activities) in livestock and humans in the seven participating countries, and with indication to its quality, comparability and purpose.	12			Available on OHEJP Zenodo:Uploaded A publication resulting from this work is available and has already been uploaded to Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/997236#.XvyQfSgzZM0	
02	D-1.2	Description of the specified AMR prevalence/frequency and AMU at population/country/regional level.	24	25		Available on OHEJP Zenodo: Uploaded https://zenodo.org/record/5336876#.YURcObgza70	Report; 9
02	D-1.3	A list of the regions identified for in-depth analysis, and a report including the assessments of parallel trends and estimates of potential associations between AMR and AMU.	24	25		Available on OHEJP Zenodo: Uploaded Two publications resulting from this work is available and has already been uploaded to Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4328124#.YKS5sagzbY0 https://zenodo.org/record/4704208#.YKS6KKgzbY0	Report; 9

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
02	D-1.4	A report of the assessment of risk factors for AMR and AMU	42	42		Available on OHEJP Zenodo: Uploaded https://zenodo.org/record/5336902#.YURcflgza70	
02	D-1.5	Recommendations and target zones for improved “One Health” surveillance	42	42		Available on OHEJP Zenodo: Uploaded https://zenodo.org/record/5416606#.YURcqlgza70	
02	D-JRP2-2.1	Assessment of criteria for inclusion of retrospective and prospective longitudinal studies.	36	42		<p>A questionnaire has been completed by all partners to assess the criteria for inclusion.</p> <p>For both the animal and human isolates that were used from retrospective and prospective studies the criteria was discussed and finalized so comparisons can be made across all datasets available.</p> <p>For the prospective studies for the human isolates the criteria is that the first 20 <i>E. coli</i> isolated from urine from each hospital at each month over a year will be included.</p> <p>There are no criteria for the animal isolates as different livestock and management systems have been sampled. However, we are evaluating differences and similarities in AMR <i>E. coli</i> given the diverse sample types.</p>	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						OHEJP: available Zenodo link: https://zenodo.org/record/5236699#.YSPSruIUmM9	
02	D-2.2	Assessment of retrospective longitudinal studies and collection of necessary data.				OHEJP: available https://zenodo.org/record/5236764#.YSPU1eIUmM8	
02	D-2.3	A project isolates database accessible to all member of the consortium	24			As part of WP2 and WP3, a hub has been created at WBVR for depositing WGS data for analysis across partners, which will also be a database of isolates. The full data set of 3812 <i>E. coli</i> will become accessible on publication, but WGS of many isolates are already available through the publications listed in D-2.4 (below).	
02	D-2.4	Data analysis of all collected isolates on a national level.	42	42		Various national studies have been performed. These have been published in various manuscripts and are available also through Zenodo (see links below). They are: https://zenodo.org/record/3730637#.Xn3Pm4hKi70 https://zenodo.org/record/4249017#.YAqc_uhKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4456741#.YAqkH-hKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4456718#.YAqfnuhKjcc	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
						https://zenodo.org/record/4981248 https://zenodo.org/record/4981351	
02	D-2.5	Comparative analysis of results from the various national studies.	42	42		<p>A manuscript is currently being prepared which compares the individual/country level WGS of isolates from the national studies (D-2.4), as detailed in WP3 T1 and T2.</p> <p>Confidential</p>	
02	D-2.6	Comparative analysis of strains persistence in farms and hospital through longitudinal studies	42	42		<p>This task has been completed and phylogenetic analysis has been performed for comparison across partners or geography, and different compartments (humans/livestock) to detect possible clonal transmission.</p> <p>Details of the work performed by partners for D-2.6 is given in WP2, and in WP3-T1 and T2.</p> <p>Confidential</p>	
02	D-3.1	Prevalent AMR genes and platforms in enterobacteria from humans, animals, food and environment.	20	42		<p>All partners have assessed and are reporting on the AMR gene content of their isolates, especially those already collected in prospective studies and from historical collections. Following a workshop in 2019 to harmonise AMR gene analysis within ARDIG, we</p>	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						<p>have used the ResFinder pipeline to look at AMR content across sectors, although partners have reported used their preferred pipeline on collections from their own dataset.</p> <p>The publications have been uploaded to Zenodo and include those already given for D-2.4:</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/3730637#.Xn3Pm4hKi70 https://zenodo.org/record/4249017#.YAqc_uhKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4456741#.YAqkH-hKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4456718#.YAqfnuhKjcc https://zenodo.org/record/4981248 https://zenodo.org/record/4981351</p>	
02	D-3.2.	Circulating plasmids in humans, animals, food and environment	24	42		<p>Partners have assessed plasmids and mobile elements harbouring AMR genes, including their fitness, as detailed in WP3-T2 and T3.</p> <p>This has resulted in a number of publications, which have already been uploaded to Zenodo. These are:</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/3730621#.Xn3MyYhKi70 https://zenodo.org/record/4475507#.YBKNvOhKhM0 https://zenodo.org/record/3701226#.YAqeSehKjcc</p>	
02	D 3.3.	Predictive modelling of plasmid spread	42	42		<p>Presence and transmission of AMR plasmids are being considered across different compartments.</p>	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						https://zenodo.org/record/4964345 https://zenodo.org/record/4244116#.X6KBDjiWxM0 https://zenodo.org/record/5506463#.YUBKk50zaUk	
02	D-3.4	Validation of plasmid AMR threats in animal models	42	42		<p>Presence of AMR plasmids harbouring OXA-48 and NDM-1 could increase the “threat” of AMR. This theory was tested using a <i>Galleria mellonella</i> model and details are provided in WP3-T4.</p> <p>A study was also performed to look at the association of gut microbiome in calves with antibiotic treatments.</p> <p>https://zenodo.org/record/4456718#.YAqfnuhKjcc</p>	
02	D-4.2	Annual communication to stakeholders	24	42		The stakeholder is aware of the work being performed and will receive a copy of the final report.	
02	D-4.3	Annual communication to stakeholders	42	42		The stakeholder is aware of the work being performed and will receive a copy of the final report.	

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify); 9. This is supportive to an integrative activity; 10. This is not an integrative activity

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
02	M-JRP2-1	Two datasets on (1) AMR and (2) AB usage of the six participating countries.	12	Yes		
02	M-JRP2-2	Assessment of retrospective longitudinal studies and collection of necessary data.	12	Yes		
02	M-JRP2-3	Preliminary molecular characterization of AMR genes from isolates collected in WP1 and WP2.	12	Yes		
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.4	Identification of MDR isolates circulating in humans, animals, food and environment	24	Yes		<p>An assessment has been made by partners of common MDR isolates circulating within the different regions/countries. Based on this assessment partners have agreed to look in more details at the WGS of different <i>E. coli</i> STs collected from partner institutes.</p> <p>In addition, the profiles of >3000 AMR isolates, is being analysed to identify common factors associated with MDR.</p>
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.5	Assessment of AMR genes and platforms in enterobacteria collected from humans, animals, food and environment.	24	Yes		<p>With WP1 AMR phenotypes have been correlated with AMU at regional or country level. Details are provided in D-JRP2-1.2 and 1.3.</p>

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
	M-AMR2.ARDIG.6	Assessment of AMR genes and platforms in enterobacteria collected from humans, animals, food and environment.	18			
	M-AMR2.ARDIG.7	Identification of circulating plasmids in humans, animals, food and environment	24			
	M-AMR2.ARDIG.8	Assessment of ecological and management factors associated with AMR and Antimicrobial usage (from WP1)	42			
	M-AMR2.ARDIG.9	Recommendation for improved One Health surveillance	42			
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.10	Collecting of samples and veterinary data, phenotypical testing of resistant isolates from farms and slaughterhouses.	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see Task 1).
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.11	Collecting of samples and clinical data, phenotypical testing of resistant isolates from hospitals and care homes.	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see WP2)
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.12	Data analysis of all collected isolates on a national level.	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see WP2 and 3)
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.13	Comparative analysis of results from the various national studies (WP2).	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see WP2)

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.14	Identification of plasmid and host chromosome factors that determine plasmid stability, spread, and adaptation to new bacterial hosts and conditions.	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see WP3)
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.15	Identification the host factors that influence plasmid-host adaptation and conjugation rates using animal models	42	Yes		This work has been completed (see WP3)
02	M-AMR2.ARDIG.16	Identification of plasmid-modifications and effects on the resident microbiota through WGS.	42	No		This work was to be completed in WP3 T5 but as laboratory experiments were severely impacted by COVID-19 in 2020 and 2021, when this work was planned.

5. Publications and patents

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Monitoring Antimicrobial Resistance and Drug Usage in the Human and Livestock Sector and Foodborne Antimicrobial Resistance in Six European Countries. 10.2147/IDR.S237038 https://zenodo.org/record/997236#.XvyQfSgzZM0	Yes	Gold	2590 €
Stepwise evolution and convergent recombination underlie the global dissemination of carbapenemase-producing Escherichia coli. https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-019-0699-6 https://zenodo.org/record/3730637#.Xn3Pm4hKi70	Yes	Gold	2656 €
Extensive antimicrobial resistance mobilization via Multicopy Plasmid Encapsidation mediated by temperate phages. https://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkaa311 https://zenodo.org/record/4244116#.X6KBDjiWxM0	Yes	Gold	2590 €
The shufflon of IncI1 plasmids is rearranged constantly during different growth conditions 10.1016/j.plasmid.2019.03.003 https://zenodo.org/record/3730621#.Xn3MyYhKi70	Yes	Gold	2590 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
<p>The importance of using whole genome sequencing and extended spectrum beta-lactamase selective media when monitoring antimicrobial resistance. https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-020-76877-7 https://zenodo.org/record/4456741#.YAqkH-hKjcc</p>	Yes	Gold	1844 €
<p>Antimicrobial Usages and Antimicrobial Resistance in Commensal <i>Escherichia coli</i> From Veal Calves in France: Evolution During the Fattening Process https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.00792 https://zenodo.org/record/4249017#.YAqc_uhKjcc</p>	Yes	Gold	2590 €
<p>Temporal dynamics of the fecal microbiota in veal calves in a 6-month field trial https://doi.org/10.1186/s42523-020-00052-6 https://zenodo.org/record/4456718#.YAqfnuhKjcc</p>	Yes	Gold	1390 €
<p>Mobile colistin resistance gene mcr-1 detected on an IncI1 plasmid in <i>Escherichia coli</i> from meat https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgar.2020.08.018 https://zenodo.org/record/4475507#.YBKNvOhKhM0</p>	Yes	Gold	1660 €
<p>blaCTX-M-1/IncI1-ly Plasmids Circulating in <i>Escherichia coli</i> From Norwegian Broiler Production Are Related, but Distinguishable https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.00333</p>	Yes	Gold	2400 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
https://zenodo.org/record/3701226#.YAqeSehKjcc			
Phenotypical antimicrobial resistance data of clinical and non-clinical Escherichia coli from poultry in Germany between 2014 and 2017 https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0243772 https://zenodo.org/record/4328124#.YKS5sagzbY0	Yes	Gold	1695 €
Comparison of Phenotypical Antimicrobial Resistance between Clinical and Non-Clinical <i>E. coli</i> Isolates from Broilers, Turkeys and Calves in Four European Countries 10.3390/microorganisms9040678 https://zenodo.org/record/4704208#.YKS6KKgzbY0	Yes	Gold	1446 €
Clinically Relevant Escherichia coli Isolates from Process Waters and Wastewater of Poultry and Pig Slaughterhouses in Germany. https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9040698 https://zenodo.org/record/4981248	Yes	Gold	2000 €
Outcome of Different Sequencing and Assembly Approaches on the Detection of Plasmids and Localization of Antimicrobial Resistance Genes in Commensal Escherichia coli https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9030598 https://zenodo.org/record/4964345	Yes	Gold	2000 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Colistin-Resistant Enterobacteriaceae Isolated From Process Waters and Wastewater From German Poultry and Pig Slaughterhouses https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.575391 https://zenodo.org/record/4981351	Yes	Gold	2400 €
Phenotypic and Genotypic Properties of Fluoroquinolone-Resistant, <i>qnr</i> -Carrying <i>Escherichia coli</i> Isolated from the German Food Chain in 2017 https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9061308 https://zenodo.org/record/5501918	Yes	Gold	2000 €
Horsing around: <i>Escherichia coli</i> ST1250 of equine origin harbouring epidemic IncHI1/ST9 plasmid with bla CTX-M-1 and an operon for short-chain fructooligosaccharides metabolism DOI: https://doi.org/10.1128/AAC.02556-20 https://zenodo.org/record/5506463#.YUBKk50zaUk	Yes	Gold	2396 €

Additional output

2018

Posters

- Juraschek, Katharina; Malorny, Burkhard; Kaesbohrer, Annemarie; Hammerl, Jens A (2018). Influence of mobile genetic elements on the dissemination of important resistance determinants in commensal *Escherichia coli*. In: Doktorandensymposium der FU Berlin. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956225>
- Juraschek, Katharina; Shamoun, Dina; Schmogger, Silvia; Irrgang, Alexandra; Grobbel, Mirja; Käsbohrer, Annemarie, Tenhagen, Bernd-Alois; Hammerl, Jens A (2018). A predominant ColE-plasmid prototype is associated with dissemination of the *mcr-4* resistance gene in German *E. coli* isolates from food and livestock. National Symposium on Zoonoses Research. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956247>

Oral presentations

- K. Juraschek, B. Malorny, A. Käsbohrer und J. A. Hammerl (2018). Influence of mobile genetic elements on the dissemination of important resistance determinants in commensal *Escherichia coli*. In: Pre-Doc Symposium des BfR. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956287>

2019

Posters

- Mesa-Varona O. and Tenhagen B-A (2019): Surveillance and monitoring systems for antimicrobial usage in livestock animals in six European countries. In: Quantification, Benchmarking and Stewardship of Veterinary Antimicrobial Usage (AACTING) 2nd International Conference, Bern, Switzerland. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4785050>
- Mesa-Varona O. and Tenhagen B-A (2019): Evidences of overlapping between antimicrobial resistance and drug usage surveillance and monitoring systems in the Human, Animal and Food Sectors in European countries. In: Zoonosen symposium, Berlin, Germany. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4785061>
- K. Juraschek, M. Borowiak, D. Shamoun, S. Schmogger, A. Irrgang, M. Grobbel, A. Käsbohrer, B. Malorny und J.A. Hammerl (2019). Isolation and characterization of a novel *mcr-5* carrying *Escherichia coli* plasmid from chicken feces in Germany. In: 29th European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Disease (ECCMID). Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956484>
- K. Juraschek, C. Jäckel, C. Banyai, K. Nöckler, J. Beutlich, A. Käsbohrer und J.A. Hammerl (2019). Characterization of *qnr*-plasmids from *M. morganii* isolates of various sources. In: 29th European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Disease (ECCMID). Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956584>
- K. Juraschek, M. Grobbel, A. Käsbohrer, B.-A. Tenhagen und J.A. Hammerl. Occurrence and commonalities of plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance in *Escherichia coli* isolates recovered from livestock and food in Germany. In: 29th European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Disease (ECCMID). Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956370>

Oral presentations

- Mesa-Varona O. and Tenhagen B-A (2019): Reviewing antimicrobial resistance and drug usage surveillance and monitoring systems in the Human, Animal and Food Sector in European countries. In: The 1st One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (Dublin, Ireland). Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/4786827>

- Mesa-Varona O. and Tenhagen B-A (2019): Reviewing antimicrobial resistance and drug usage surveillance and monitoring systems in the Human, Animal and Food Sector in European countries. In: The Predoc symposium (Berlin, Germany). Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4944270>
- K. Juraschek, S. Krekow, N. Pauly, M. Grobbel, A. Käsbohrer und J.A. Hammerl (2019). Comparison of Plasmid-Mediated Quinolone Resistance in *Escherichia coli* Isolates from Bovine and Swine Origin Recovered from Livestock and Food in Germany. In: 1st Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Food-Borne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats. Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956663>
- K. Juraschek, B. Malorny, D. Meemken, S. Schwarz, A. Kaesbohrer, J.A. Hammerl (2019). Influence of mobile genetic elements on the dissemination of important resistance determinants in commensale *Escherichia coli*. In: Junior Scientist Zoonose Meeting Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956734>
- K. Juraschek, M. Grobbel, A. Käsbohrer, B.-A. Tenhagen, J.A. Hammerl (2019). Occurrence and commonalities of plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance in *Escherichia coli* isolates recovered from livestock and food in Germany. In: DRS Doktorandensymposium. Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956773>
- K. Juraschek, C. Jäckel, C. Banyai, S. Schmoger, T. Skladnikiewicz-Ziemer, B. Lesniewsky, K. Nöckler, J. Beutlich, A. Käsbohrer and J.A. Hammerl (2019). Dissection of a New *qnrD2 M. morganii* Plasmid Isolated from Systematically Diseased Cold-Blooded Amphibians. In: The International Symposium on Zoonoses Research. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956847>
- Katharina Juraschek (2019). WGS mit der PB SMRT Technologie. In: Abteilungskolloquium. Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956855>
- K. Juraschek, S. Krekow, N. Pauly, M. Grobbel, A. Käsbohrer, J.A. Hammerl (2019). Comparison of Plasmid-Mediated Quinolone Resistance in *Escherichia coli* Isolates from Livestock and Food in Germany. In: BfR-PreDoc Symposium. Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956899>

2020

Posters

Oral presentations

- Mesa-Varona O., Mader, R. Jarrige N., Granier S-A., Perrin A., Jouy E., Chauvin C., Kaspar H., Anjum M., Grobbel M., Velasova M. and Tenhagen B-A (2020): Phenotypic antimicrobial resistance in *Escherichia coli* strains on clinical and non-clinical isolates from broilers in Germany, France and United Kingdom. In: The 2nd One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (Prague, Czech Republic). Virtual. Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/deposit/4787487>
- Velasova M., Smith R., Chaintarli K., Mesa-Varona O., Tenhagen B-A., Kaspar H., Mader R., Amat J-P., Madec J-Y. and Anjum M-A (2020): Antimicrobial resistance of *Escherichia coli* isolates originating from diagnostic submissions from veterinary scanning surveillance in UK, Germany and France from 2014 to 2017. In: The 2nd One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting (Prague, Czech Republic). Virtual. Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/4786343>
- Mesa-Varona O., Mader, R. Granier S-A., Perrin A., Jouy E., Madec J-Y., Kaspar H., Anjum M., Grobbel M., Velasova M. and Tenhagen B-A (2020): Comparison of antibiotic resistance in *Escherichia coli* from clinical diagnostic submissions and isolates of healthy broilers, turkeys and calves from surveillance and monitoring systems in Germany and France. In: the Tenth International Conference on Antimicrobial Agents in Veterinary Medicine (AAVM), Israel. Virtual. Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/4787383>

- Mesa-Varona O. and Tenhagen B-A (2020): Main outputs of the work package 1 from ARDIG (Antibiotic Resistance Dynamics: the influence of geographic origin and management systems on resistance gene flows within humans, animals and the environment) project. In: The workshop on surveillance/monitoring of AMR and AMU in animals and humans, Berlin. Virtual. Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/4944311>
- K. Juraschek, M. Grobbel, A. Käsbohrer, B.-A. Tenhagen, J.A. Hammerl (2020). High heterogeneity of plasmid-mediated quinolone resistance in *Escherichia coli* isolates recovered from livestock and food in Germany. In: 6th Joint Conference of the DGHM & VAAM. Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4956927>

2021

Poster

- Mesa-Varona O, Tenhagen B-A. Comparison of antimicrobial use and resistance data on clinical and non-clinical isolates from livestock in four countries. In: Junior Scientist Zoonoses Meeting 2021. Virtual. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4905583#.YL3gqvkbY0>
- Mesa-Varona O, Kaspar H, Grobbel M, Tenhagen B-A. The influence of the antimicrobial use in the resistance data on clinical and non-clinical isolates from broilers and turkeys in Germany. In: the 5th International Conference on Responsible Use of Antibiotics in Animals. Virtual. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4916495>

Oral presentation

- Mesa-Varona O., Mader, R. Jarrige N., Granier S-A., Perrin A., Jouy E., Chauvin C., Kaspar H., Anjum M., Grobbel M., Velasova M. and Tenhagen B-A (2020): Comparison of antibiotic resistance in *Escherichia coli* from clinical diagnostic submissions and isolates of healthy broilers, turkeys and calves from surveillance and monitoring systems in Germany and France. In: The Predoc symposium (Berlin, Germany). Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/4944150>
- Katharina Juraschek, Carlus Deneke, Silvia Schmogger, Mirjam Grobbel, Burkhard Malorny, Annemarie Käsbohrer, Stefan Schwarz, Diana Meemken and Jens Andre Hammerl (2021). HIGH DIVERSITY OF PLASMIDS CARRYING QNR RESISTANCE GENES IN FLUOROQUINOLONE RESISTANT *ESCHERICHIA COLI* ISOLATED IN GERMANY IN 2017. In: OHEJP ASM. Poster. <https://zenodo.org/record/4957003>
- Katharina Juraschek, Maria Borowiak, Simon H. Tausch, Burkhard Malorny, Annemarie Käsbohrer, Saria Otani, Stefan Schwarz, Diana Meemken, Carlus Deneke and Jens Andre Hammerl (2021). DIFFERENT SEQUENCING AND ASSEMBLY APPROACHES INFLUENCING THE DETECTION OF PLASMIDS AND ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE GENES IN COMMENSAL *ESCHERICHIA COLI*. In: OHEJP ASM. Oral presentation. <https://zenodo.org/record/4957118>

Outcomes

It has been evidenced a lack of harmonisation on AMU and AMR across countries, within animals and, therefore, between humans and animal ([10.2147/IDR.S237038](https://doi.org/10.2147/IDR.S237038)). Higher resistance levels were found in clinical isolates of calves as compared to non-clinical isolates. The opposite was shown in isolates of broilers and turkeys (<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0243772>; <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9040678>). It is required incentives to harmonise AMU and AMR systems as EFSA had driving the harmonisation of EU data-collection in non-clinical isolates. Otherwise, the One Health approach is not straightforwardly achievable.

If sequencing technologies are used for AMR surveillance, it will provide added value by use of AMR gene mechanisms, transmission of clones and the plasmids that contain the AMR genes. Markers of

AMR genes can also be looked at and compared to review prevalence over time, effectively following in the footsteps of Enterobase but expanding upon this. Methods harmonisation of AMR predictions should be considered, as ARDIG has shown some of the common AMR WGS pipelines can vary in their outcomes. Any recommendations made on WGS pipelines should be assessed through the use of EURL.

When performing WGS, ideally all commensal as well as those *E coli* from antibiotic selective plates should be sequenced. However due to the expenses of this work, realistically there needs to be more selective approach which could be that all isolates from antibiotic plates and a subset of commensals are sequenced.

ARDIG WP1

Sales data are collected in Europe providing a general overview on AMU. However, farm-level data are required for further analyses. Some projects, namely ARDIG and AACTING, have provided some suggestions to overcome this issue.

The implementation of the Regulation (EU) No. 6/2019 on veterinary products will allow collecting usage data in a large number of animal categories. This will greatly improve the comparability of data and populations.

Data on non-clinical isolates from livestock is harmonised by the decision 2020/1729/EU. However, except for zoonotic bacteria, there is no harmonisation on clinical isolates. Therefore, there is a lack of harmonisation between clinical and non-clinical isolates from livestock in different aspects. The EU JAMRAI project has proposed to create a European harmonised system on AMR in clinical isolates of animals called EARS-Vet. This project and authors have also suggested antimicrobials panels in clinical isolates.

The outcomes of ARDIG were presented at a workshop (1 and 2 of March 2021) that included experts in the field from EFSA, EMA, ECDC and national governments. Particularly the debate on the data collection systems for antimicrobial use in animals has been supported by the work done in ARDIG.

Bernd-Alois Tenhagen was involved in the preparation of the “3rd Joint Interagency Antimicrobial Consumption and Resistance Analysis (JIACRA) Report” by EFSA, EMA and ECDC and included the findings from ARDIG in his contributions to the report which materialized in ARDIG papers being cited in the report.

Findings were also considered when advising the German Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL) on changes in the antibiotics minimization strategy for Germany and when commenting on the foreseen changes in the EU-legislation with respect to the collection of AMU-data in the European Union.

6. One Health Impact

- The outcomes of ARDIG were presented at a workshop (1 and 2 of March 2021) that included experts in the field from EFSA, EMA, ECDC and national governments. Particularly the debate on the data collection systems for antimicrobial use in animals has been supported by the work done in ARDIG.
- A member of the consortium was involved in the preparation of the “3rd Joint Interagency Antimicrobial Consumption and Resistance Analysis (JIACRA) Report” by EFSA, EMA and ECDC to be published in 2021 and included the findings from ARDIG in his contributions to the report which materialized in ARDIG papers being cited in the report.
- Collaboration between the animal and medical sector in the field of AMR and AMU was fostered including interaction with other projects such as the German One Health Initiative (GOHI) involving BfR and RKI that worked in related areas. Likewise collaboration between different institutions working on AMR in animals in Germany (BfR and BVL) was further strengthened by the exchange of data and the collaborative analysis of the data.

- Recommendations on surveillance of antimicrobial use are also fed into the current German national debate on the further development of the antimicrobial minimization concept.
- ARDIG has strengthened the collaboration between institutes involved in the consortium and the mutual understanding of the challenges each institute is facing. Further, an important collaboration has been set up between ARDIG and EU-JAMRAI in discussions on the EARS-Vet project and was also manifested in a collaborative paper (Mesa-Varona et al 2021).
- The project forces the development and optimization of WGS techniques in the NRL-AR for routine, which will be further used for in silico-based evaluation of the status of isolates from the ESBL-monitoring. Furthermore, the NRL-AR had successfully established in house pipelines, which are focussed on the evaluation of the resistances and the prediction of their genetic localization. Some of the results were further included in an EJP project of the second round, which is focussing on plasmid finishing and assessment of evolution of mobile genetic elements. The provided sequencing data will be used as a reference for a WGS-based ring trial for harmonization of long read sequencing.

JRP05-ET1-TOX-Detect

1. Summary of the work carried out

Bacterial toxins produced by *Staphylococcus spp.*, *Bacillus spp.* and *Clostridium spp.* are responsible for a large number of food-poisoning outbreaks (FPOs) in the European Union. The true incidence of FPOs caused by these toxigenic bacteria is underestimated due to a lack of relevant detection tools and to a common symptomatology that makes outbreak investigation challenging. The OHEJP TOX-Detect project uses three different non-NGS approaches for a better detection of *Staphylococcus spp.*, *Bacillus spp.* and *Clostridium spp.* and characterization of some of their toxins, including emerging threats that remain currently undetectable.

First, collections including strains from various sources (animal, environment, food and human) and different geographical locations in the EU were established under specific criteria selected by the consortium. Strains issued from this “strains collection” were used to analyze the RNAseq, PCR and cytotoxicity data and to study potential correlations between gene presence or expression with strain toxicity and virulence. The growth conditions of the strains, the cytotoxicity assays, the RNA extraction procedures and development of RNAseq assays were defined and optimized. The data were analyzed to allow gene expression and strain toxicity measurement. PCR and RNAseq methods were developed for both *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*. The analysis allowed to propose known as well as new biomarkers to characterize the strains.

A panel of three non-NGS based methods allowing characterization of the three studied pathogens and some of their toxins were developed: (i) MALDI-ToF , (ii) LC-MS and (iii) ELISA methods.

For MALDI-ToF , a new library based on the selected strains collection was developed. Therefore, 152 reference spectra (MSP) from 76 strains were selected after the spectra-processing step. Comparisons and request access with the commercialized database showed high reliable scores that allow to differentiate these three species. The difficulty to differentiate species within the *B. cereus* group was highlighted. Transfer of this database was realized to the European Union Reference network through the organization of an inter-laboratory test.

Staphylococcus enterotoxins types SEM, SEN and SEO and *B. cereus* enterotoxin CytK2, hemolysin HlyII and Sphingomyelinase were selected for methods development, as there is a lack in commercially available methods to detect these toxins. In the absence of toxins standards, procedures for recombinant toxins production and purification were optimized. Stability studies showed that standards produced for *Staphylococcal* enterotoxins SEO and CytK2 are unstable and, consequently, cannot be transferred between partners for method development. Thus, standards for SEN, hemolysin HlyII and Sphingomyelinase have been produced and transferred to partners in charge of LC-MS

methods development. For *Bacillus* enterotoxins, ELISA and LC-MS methods were developed, optimized and transferred to TOX-Detect partners in order to evaluate their transferability. For *Staphylococcal* enterotoxins, LC-MS to target type SEN was developed and transferred to partners for inter-laboratory test.

Results obtained in the TOX-Detect project allowed to enhance acknowledgment on strains producing toxins. Methods developed could be used by reference laboratories (NRLs and EURL) for further development and foodborne outbreak investigation, especially when it comes to non-classical toxins. Selected reference strains for *Staphylococcus* and *Bacillus* have been included in OHEJP CARE project.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results

WP0. Coordination, management and communication

WP0-T1- Coordination, management and communication

The overall purpose of the management structure is to ensure the timely implementation of the tasks and the smooth running of the project as a whole. Its primary goal is to identify arising opportunities and detect the occurrence of obstacles as early as possible, hence maximise the outcome of the project while preventing delays in its implementation. In total, 57 meetings, web conferences and telephone conferences were organised by the coordination team over the 42 months of the project. Objectives were to manage the progress of different tasks and to discuss with partners on technical issues. Discussion and procedure of transfer of the collection of strains between TOX-Detect partners and between TOX-Detect and CARE projects were managed by coordination team. Finally, impact of COVID-19 crisis on TOX-Detect project was also managed by the coordination.

WP0-T2 to T5: Organisation of four face-to-face meetings with all partners

The TOX-Detect kick-off meeting held in Maisons-Alfort (France) from 28th of February to the 1st of March 2018 (M3). 16 participants representing all TOX-Detect partners were present during the kick-off meeting.

The aims were:

- i. to introduce all project members;
- ii. to get information on administrative and financial issues by representatives of EJP coordination team;
- iii. to give an overview of the aims of the project and provide detailed information on all work packages;
- iv. to discuss open questions on the selection of the reference strains that should be used in this project

The first meeting was organized on 20 and 21 March 2019 at Anses (France). 15 participants representing all TOX-Detect partners were present during this meeting. General discussion dealing with EJP projects took place after the presentation of Fanny Baudoin from One Health EJP general coordination. Briefly, she presented guidelines, specific rules, budget, communication tools and spoke about the possible 6-month extension. Special discussion sessions were dedicated to the coordination between WP3 and WP4 in order to transfer the produced enterotoxins in WP4 to WP3 for LC-MS development and protein characterisation.

A second meeting was organized on 15 and 16 January 2020 at Anses (France). 23 participants representing all TOX-Detect partners were present. C. Cordevant and A. Callegari were invited by the coordination of TOX-Detect Project as SSB member and general coordination, respectively. All participants presented their activities and involvement in the TOX-Detect project. A specific discussion was dedicated to the organization of inter-laboratory tests for each technique developed in WP1, WP3 and WP4.

The third meeting was organized as web-meeting on 25 of June 2021. All partners were present. The aim was to discuss on the final report, and to present the restitution of WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4. Remaining tasks of WP5 (MALDI-ToF and ELISA inter-laboratory tests) were also developed.

WP0-T6: mandatory reports on network activities: interim activity report, final report

The coordination drafted and uploaded on OHEJP website the interim and mandatory reports:

Report	Submission period
9 Month report for year 1	September 2018
9 Month report for year 2	September 2019
9 Month report for year 3	September 2020
12 Months report dispatched on	February 2019
Intermediate report (36M)	January 2021
24 Months report	February 2020
36 Months report	December 2020

WP1. Constitution of a reference strain collection for *S. aureus*, *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*

Criteria for selecting the strains have been defined in connection with the needs of other work-packages in order to select the most appropriate strains to be used for the development and harmonization of methods and databases. An inventory of available resources has been done and a list of reference strains with their associated data established with all partners. This collection includes strains from various sources (animal, environment, food and human samples) and different geographical locations.

WP1-T1- Constitution of *S. aureus* strains collection

80 *S. aureus* strains have been proposed by TOX-Detect partners, representing human and food categories. The major part was issued from food poisoning outbreaks. The aim was to develop Ab against SEN and SEO toxins. Therefore, 21 strains encoding for SEN and SEO and a negative control (CIP 53.154) have been selected. Some of these strains have been exchanged between partners under a Material Transfer Agreement.

WP1-T2- Constitution of *B. cereus* strains collection

90 *Bacillus* (Bc) strains have been proposed by TOX-Detect partners, representing human and food categories. The collection includes a total of 21 *B. cereus* strains. Some of these strains have been exchanged between partners under a Material Transfer Agreement.

WP1-T3- Constitution of *C. perfringens* strains collection

As in CPS and BC 54 *C. perfringens* (Cp) strains have been proposed by TOX-Detect partners, representing human and food categories. The collection includes a total of 34 *C. perfringens* strains. Some of these strains have been exchanged between partners under a Material Transfer Agreement.

WP1-T4- Transfer of libraries of MALDI-ToF reference spectra

The MALDI-ToF reference spectra library has been developed using all strains referenced in tasks WP1-T1, T2 and T3. Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) was drafted and uploaded on EJP site. It will be accessible to the scientific community after the publication of this new database.

MALDI-ToF mass spectrometry was performed for bacterial species identification and for verification of purity of stock cultures as well as to establish a library of reference MALDI-ToF spectra. Protocol for protein extraction has been discussed, defined and shared among partners. For each strain, reference spectra (MSP) were generated using 26-32 spectra from total protein extracts spotted onto a target plate in eight replicates, and each spot was analysed four times. Acquisition of raw spectra was done with a laser frequency of 60 Hz, an acceleration voltage of 20 KV and extraction delay of 120 ns. All raw

spectra were analysed according to the established MSP protocol of the MALDI Biotyper[®] V1.1 to remove suboptimal spectra. 152 MSP from 76 strains were selected after the spectra-processing step. 2 MSP have been created for each strain. Comparisons with the commercialized Bruker Daltonic Database: Version 9.0.0 containing 9997 MSP (including 7 MSP for *B. cereus*, 14 MSP for *Staphylococcus* and 10 MSP for *C. perfringens*) were access. The request access with the commercialized Bruker Daltonic database shown high reliable scores that allow to differentiate these three species. A misinterpretation was obtained only for one strain for which a contamination was detected. The difficulty to differentiate species within the *B. cereus* group *sensu lato* was also highlighted. Technical and data processing transfer procedure has been established with partners before organization of a dedicated PT trial (cf WP5). This database was transferred to European Union Reference Laboratory network (11 National reference Laboratories) in June 2021. Technical assistance was provided by WP1 over the inter-laboratory period.

WP2: Characterization of toxins/virulence factors

WP2-T1- Characterization of candidate toxin and/or virulence genes using toxicity tests

This task was launched on M4. The 21 *B. cereus* strains selected in WP1 were tested for cytotoxicity using classical cytotoxicity tests. Among the 40 *C. perfringens* strains selected in WP1, a subset was tested using classical cytotoxicity tests. For those strains, the growth conditions of the strains (vegetative and sporulating) as well as the cytotoxicity assays were defined and optimized.

Following obtention of the strain supernatant of *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*, a suitable analytical method was developed for the determination of the cytotoxic potential of the strains. Potential effects of the supernatants on the pro-inflammatory response in Caco-2 cells (IL-8 secretion) was also investigated. Cellular imaging-based High Content Analysis approaches were developed and used to characterize the mechanisms of toxicity. A subset of strains were chosen based on results from classical cytotoxicity tests, and further evaluated for markers of apoptosis (active-Caspase-3), genotoxicity (γ H2AX, phospho-ATM), pro-inflammatory response (nuclear translocation of NF- κ B), mitochondrial membrane potential (TMRE) and cytotoxicity (Nuclear DAPI staining). The cytotoxic potential varies amongst strains, providing further insight into the complex mechanisms of *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens* pathogenicity.

Figure 1: Cytotoxicity of bacterial culture supernatants from vegetative and sporulating cultures of *C. perfringens* (left) or *B. cereus* (right) in human intestinal Caco-2 cells.

WP2-T2- Assessment of virulence and toxin gene expression using RT-PCR and transcriptomic assays

This task was launched on M5. The aim of this task was to select genes over- or highly expressed in various strains within a panel of candidate genes suspected to play a role during *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens* pathogenesis. In addition, a whole transcriptomic assay was performed (RNAseq technology) in various growth conditions.

WP2-T2-ST1- Optimization of growth conditions to be used for gene expression analysis

For *C. perfringens* different protocols were used: vegetative and sporulating as well as co-incubation with human intestinal Caco-2 cells. Changes were made to the *C. perfringens* sporulation protocol to optimize the production of virulence factors, including CPE. For *B. cereus*, the conditions were chosen based on two parameters, the oxygen level and the pH.

WP2-T2-ST2- Development of RT-PCR assays and transcriptomic analysis

For both organisms, the protocols of bacterial growth, RNA extraction and qRT-PCR were developed and optimized. RNAs were extracted and checked for purity and integrity. The RNA samples were then subjected to RNAseq analysis. Analytical methods were then developed to ensure a proper analysis of the data. These analytical pipelines were then successfully used to provide heat maps and PCA analysis, generating information on up and down regulated genes for each bacterial strain.

For *B. cereus*, 15 strains grown in microaerophilia at pH 7 were sent in triplicate for RNAseq analysis. 9-15 million reads per samples were obtained, with 90% correctly paired. The biological triplicates clustered well together and showed no major differences in the profile of their transcriptomes. 3276 genes were identified in the core transcriptome, which represents approximately 65% of the genes in each strain. 264 genes were found to be differentially expressed (up or down regulated), with p-values less than 0.01.

For *C. perfringens*, 5 strains grown in vegetative and sporulation conditions were selected for the RNAseq analysis. Comparing growth conditions (vegetative vs sporulation), a mean of 677 ± 290 were significantly differentially expressed, of which an average of 444 ± 123 were upregulated and 232 ± 169 genes were downregulated. The majority of differently expressed genes (60 % to 76 %) showed significantly upregulation in all vegetative growth condition compared to sporulation condition.

In conclusion, methods were developed as expected during this task, to 1) optimize growth conditions (subtask 2.1) and 2) develop qRT-PCR and transcriptomic analytical pipelines to successfully analyze and select genes (subtask 2.2).

This allowed to propose a panel of candidate genes to be further characterized during the task 2.3.

WP2-T3- Correlation of specific toxicity profiles with expression patterns of bacterial toxins/virulence factors

The objective of this task was to analyze the RNAseq, PCR and cytotoxicity data and study potential correlations between gene presence or expression with strain toxicity and virulence.

The growth conditions of the strains, the cytotoxicity assays, the RNA extraction procedures as well as the development of RNAseq assays were defined and optimized. The data were analyzed to allow gene expression/presence and strain toxicity and pathogenicity comparison.

First, the *B. cereus* strains were characterized by detecting by PCR the presence of ten genes involved in virulence. According to the presence/absence of the genes, the strains were assigned a genetic signature (GS). The assignment of strains according to their GS shows the genetic diversity of *B. cereus* strains.

Among the strains tested for cytotoxicity, a strong correlation could be identified between *hlyII* presence and high cytotoxicity. Similarly, a strong correlation could be measured between Nhe production and high cytotoxicity.

Figure 2: correlation between cytotoxicity and toxins

As such, it could be concluded that Nhe and HlyII were strong candidates for the development of further detection methods (WP3 and WP4).

For *B. cereus*, the RNAseq data were further analysed to provide correlation with strain pathogenicity. The strains were grouped according to the pathogenicity they induced (non-pathogen vs FBO or clinical strains). We used a penalized conditional logistic regression with the lasso method to select relevant genes for the prediction of pathogenic potential. By applying the prediction model to the 11,179 genes with the selected penalty constant of 0.01, 7 genes were selected as markers to differentiate the strains according to their pathogenicity.

Using this combination of genes, the best results obtained to compare non-pathogenic with FBO strains was an AUC of 0.768, the sensitivity 0.69 and the specificity 0.773.

Remarkably, regarding the clinical strains, the best results were achieved with an AUC of 0.955, sensitivity of 0.9 and specificity of 0.86. Therefore, the analysis concludes that an accurate differentiation between clinical and non-pathogenic strains can be obtained by using these biomarkers.

Figure 3: Best performing biomarker combination for non-pathogenic and clinical strains

Finally, the correlation of the gene expression/presence/absence with the toxicity profiles of the strains have been performed. Thus far, no correlation could be observed between the presence or the expression of the newly identified biomarkers and the cytotoxic potential of the strains.

Further analyses need to be performed to identify other biomarkers, which expression could correlate with cytotoxicity and/or HCA data.

Conclusions

The objective of this task was to analyze the RNAseq, PCR and cytotoxicity data and study potential correlations between gene presence or expression with strain toxicity and virulence.

The growth conditions of the strains, the cytotoxicity assays, the RNA extraction procedures as well as the development of RNAseq assays were defined and optimized. The data were analyzed to allow gene expression and strain toxicity measurement. PCR and RNAseq methods were developed for both *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*. The analysis allowed to propose known as well as new biomarkers to characterize the strains. We thus successfully implemented methods to answer the initial questions, we provided accurate SOP and the deliverables were obtained.

8 SOPs were drafted in this WP2 were uploaded on the OH EJP website.

WP3: Development of Mass Spectrometry-based proteomics procedures for detection of bacterial toxins and virulence factors

WP3-T1- Development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of new enterotoxins (eg SEG, SEH, SEI) from *S. aureus*

In this task, focus is laid on the development of an innovative analytical method for the quantification of three non-classical SEs (SEM, SEN and SEO) suspected to play a role in the notorious pathogenicity of *S. aureus*, specifically in food poisoning outbreaks. To this end, recombinant protein standards expressed in *E. coli* as **part of WP 4 were subjected to a quality control**, a sample preparation technique based on-filter digestion was developed with SEB pure well characterized standard (obtained from H2020 EuroBioTox project, <https://eurobiotox.eu/>) as a model protein and finally a targeted LC-MS² method with the on-filter digestion sample preparation was developed and validated for the quantification of SEN in cultures of *S. aureus*. To assess the quality of the recombinant SEM, SEN and SEO standards, both electrophoresis tools and mass spectrometry were used to verify the purity and amino acid sequence of each standard. The on-filter digestion sample preparation consisted of four major stages namely the filtration of the culture supernatant, the protein denaturation process, enzymatic protein digestion step and finally the elution of the obtained tryptic peptides. Each of the four steps was optimized with *S. aureus* enterotoxin B as a model protein while a standard culture of a *seb* and *sen* negative strain of *S. aureus* was used as blank matrix. Thereafter, the optimized sample preparation was applied and tested with the recombinant SEN standard for quantification by means of an UHPLC system coupled to a Orbitrap mass spectrometer. Separation of the different peptides was performed with a classical C18 column while their subsequent quantification was performed in parallel reaction monitoring mode. Subsequent validation of the obtained method was performed according to FDA guidelines for bioanalytical analyses. Thorough analysis of the three recombinant SE standards demonstrated that only SEN could be seen as a quantitative standard. Hence, only the rSEN standard was used for the development of a targeted LC-MS² method as proof of principle. Ensuing experiments showed that SEN was efficiently retained by the filter and sufficiently digested with the developed on-filter digestion technique. Due to the low expression of SEN, the method was validated in a range of 1 to 7.5 ng/mL, with 1 ng/mL as demonstrated limit of quantification (LOQ). The average recoveries calculated for the concentrations 1, 2.5, 5 and 7.5 ng/mL were respectively 114, 104, 102 and 99%. Calculated coefficients of variance for both repeatability and reproducibility were below 8%, while the calculated measurement uncertainty was below 20% for all nominal concentrations and below 30% for the established LOQ (1 ng/mL).

WP3-T2- Development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of toxins and/or virulence factors from *B. cereus*

Characterizing foodborne toxigenic bacteria and detecting bacterial toxins is a key goal of the project. Here we focused our work on the development of a targeted LC-MS/MS method for the identification of two foodborne *Bacillus* bacteria virulence factors: Sphingomyelinase and Hemolysin-II (HLY-II). These toxins are part of a large number of other toxins that are secreted by the bacterium and responsible for foodborne infections. They were chosen among several other ones because they are present, even if in low amount, in many described strains.

The methods we developed are based on liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) and more specifically on targeted methods.

The first step was the selection of the strain of *Bacillus cereus*. We then first decided to set-up a Top-down proteomics approach to identify toxins from bacterial supernatant. Top-down proteomics, in contrast to the usual bottom-up approach based on protein digestion, relies on the analysis of intact proteins. It allows uniquely addressing the different forms of a protein (proteoforms) present in a sample. However, the first top-down proteomics experiments indicated a very low sensitivity of the approach since no intact toxin could be identified in the bacterial supernatant. This was due to the very low amount of toxins produced by *Bacillus cereus* strains in medium. We should note that this information was not available in the literature. It thus quickly appeared that we had to resort to the

more usual bottom-up approach to set up our analysis. To maximize the sensitivity and thus the chance to identify our toxins of interest, we decided to develop a targeted bottom-up method called PRM (Parallel Reaction Monitoring) on a Q-Exactive mass spectrometer. Even with this sensitive targeted approach, the low amount of endogenous toxins in our samples led us to spike our samples with purified toxins (obtained from WP4, INRAe partner) for both method development and sample preparation. These spiked samples were used to set-up both LC conditions and MS parameters. We used the Pinpoint 1.1 software to achieve the selection of proteotypic peptides.

The full validation of the method was therefore implemented by using a nano-HPLC easy-1200 (ThermoFisher) system coupled to Q-Exactive plus mass spectrometer (ThermoFisher). A SOP has been prepared (see document in annex) in order to allow the transfer of the method to the project partners involved in the inter-laboratories tests.

WP3-T3- Development of Mass Spectrometry-based methods for the detection of toxins and/or virulence factors from *C. perfringens*

A nanoLC-PRM/MS method has been developed for the detection of *C. perfringens* enterotoxin CPE. Mass spectrometry allows the characterization of protein sequence and direct measurement of the toxin, leading to unambiguous identification and unequivocal evidence of its presence, with a sequence coverage up to 86% and at least 20 peptides identified. In parallel, sixteen other virulence factors as well as numerous proteins involved in the sporulation of the bacterium were present in the supernatant, confirming that the presence of CPE is dependent on sporulation. We have developed a method, focused on the detection of CPE, which is based on 6 peptides generated by its tryptic digestion, achieving a sequence coverage of 19.7%. As a protein standard is not commercially available in Europe, a strain from the TOX-Detect collection was selected for its high CPE production under culture conditions developed by ANSES to serve as reference. A homogeneity test was performed on pooled supernatants of this reference strain and 4 out of 6 peptides were found homogenous with a CV of less than 20% and the carryover in the matrix blank was estimated to be less than 0.05%. Serial dilution experiment was performed by diluting the digested reference sample in the digested matrix blank and CPE was detected for dilutions up to 128th. The full validation of the method has been implemented by using nano-HPLC (column Acclaim Pepmap 100 C18, 3 μm 75 μm x 250 mm, ThermoFischer) system coupled to Q-Exactive HF-X mass spectrometer (ThermoFischer). A SOP has been drafted (see document in annex) in order to allow the transfer of the method to the project partners involved in the Inter-Laboratories Comparison tests.

WP3-T4- Transfer of LC-MS/MS methods

The three LC-MS/MS methods, developed in the T3.1, T3.2 and T3.3 and focusing on the detection of toxins and/or virulence factors from *S. aureus*, *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*, respectively, were also implemented in laboratories of several other participants.

First, the new LC-MS/MS methods were developed and in-house validated, when quantitative standard was available (e.g. SEN). Then, for each analytical method, a detailed analytical protocol (and validation report, if done) was written and these protocols were drafted as SOP (see SOPs uploaded on the OH EJP site) before the transfer to the partners for implementation. These methods were transferred to the partners of the WP3 in order to test applicability of the methods before further implementation in WP5. Some adaptations were necessary, given the differences between the instruments used by the partners involved in WP3: Liquid chromatography systems (UHPLC vs nano LC) but also mass spectrometers (ThermoScientific - Q Exactive Focus vs ThermoScientific - Q Exactive HF-X) used for development and implementation were not always the same. Finally, with some modifications, results of the transfer were quite good, with acceptable qualitative results for all the three methods (See WP5). Inter-laboratory comparison tests and the obtained results by participants will be presented in deliverable D5.2 "Final report including results from the eight inter-lab tests".

WP4: Development of new immuno-enzymatic assays for detection of *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* toxins and virulence determinants

WP4-T1- Development of quantitative immunoassays for five known *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* toxins and virulence factors

WP4-T1-ST1- Selection of 5 target genes and construction of genetic tools for proteins overexpression

At the beginning of the project Staphylococcal Enterotoxins (SEs) G, H and I had been chosen as targets for the effort. These choices were changed in month 9 on the wish of the Coordinators to minimize overlap with contemporary projects and maximize the resources allotted to the TOX-Detect Consortium. As of October 2018, the official targets were SEN and SEO. As genetic tool for overexpression of SEs in *E. coli*, the SEN and SEO genes have been cloned in an IPTG (isopropylthiogalactoside) inducible expression vector, with additional N-terminal tags for affinity purification (His6) and protease cleavage (FLAG/Enterokinase recognition site) in place of the wt secretion signal sequences.

WP4-T1-ST2- Proteins production

The necessary SE cloning and production work at the BfR required gaining official approval from the responsible Authority for work with genetically modified organisms; this approval was granted in December 2018, subject to the fulfilling of strict safety requirements. In order to meet these requirements, the SE production procedures and the laboratory organization had to be adjusted, including the purchase of necessary equipment. Due to the need to overcome these problems, the successful production of purified recombinant SEs for both WP3 and WP4 was only possible from March 2020. Although production was successful, the enzymatic removal of the affinity tag after purification (required in order to produce a wildtype N-terminus) was surprisingly ineffective, leading to a further delay in delivering the final protein preparations. Toxin samples for the Partners in WP3 were first delivered in May 2020.

WP4-T1-ST3- Development of specific Ab (poly/monoclonal)

Due to the problems and delays outlined in the above sections, final, purified SE preparations of sufficient quality and quantity were available in June of 2020. Because the production of monoclonal antibodies requires at least 5 – 6 months, there was not sufficient time to allow for the delivery of the hybridoma cultures and characterization of the binders (all of which was necessary for the development of the immunoassays) before the end of 2020 – the original, official end of the TOX-Detect project. The Coordinators therefore requested the contracting of polyclonal sera and the antigens were delivered to the firm Covalab for the production of rabbit immune sera in June of 2020. The polyclonal sera for both SEN and SEO were delivered to the BfR in September 2020.

WP4-T1-ST4- Design of immunoenzymatic assays

The assay development for SEN and SEO began immediately upon delivery of the respective antisera and purified IgGs. While both purified IgG pools effectively and reproducibly recognized their antigens in a simple ELISA (immobilized antigens, respective pAbs and then an anti-rabbit-HRP detection antibody), only the assay for SEO was robust and reproducible in a sandwich format with toxins diluted in BHI culture medium. However, when testing culture supernatants from *S. aureus* strains having no SE genes, it became clear that the pAbs were cross-reactive against other, unknown *S. aureus* components. Although these pAbs against SEN and SEO are not alone suitable for the development of the envisioned immunoenzymatic assays, they will find application in SE affinity enrichment procedures to support other (for example, MS-based) detection methods. In June 2021, these developed Ab were transferred to the European Union Reference Laboratory for Coagulase Positive Staphylococci for development of an LC-MS based Immuno capture extraction method for detection of enterotoxins in food matrices. Results on this application are expected by end of 2021.

WP4-T2- Development of a quantitative immunoassay on a new *B. cereus* toxin or virulence factor

WP4-T2-ST1- Selection of 3 target genes and construction of a genetic tool for protein overexpression

Because WP2 could not deliver data on new *B. cereus* factors possibly involved in the diarrheal strains virulence, this task could not be implemented.

The development of immunoassays against *B. cereus* enterotoxins Nhe and Hbl was discarded because assays (although not quantitative) are already available against these toxins. The BCET-RPLA kit from Oxoid detects HblL2, the BDE-VIA assay from 3M-Tecra detects NheA and NheB, and the DuoPath assay from Merck detects NheB and HblL2. Therefore, in accordance with the coordinators, it was decided to develop assays against the enterotoxin CytK2, the hemolysin HlyII and the Sphingomyelinase.

WP4-T2-ST2- Protein production

For *B. cereus*, the first step was to select, for the three toxins, conserved sequences between reference diarrheal strains. Because these strains were not available at the project start, they were recovered from external laboratories and the toxins were sequenced using Micalis sequencing facilities and funds outside OHEJP TOX-Detect. Due to this preliminary task, cloning of the toxins genes started, after the sequences alignment, with a 6-months delay. The recombinant, His-tagged toxins were successfully produced in an almost pure form and could be delivered to WP3 and used for antibodies production. However, CytK2 was found to be quite unstable (half-life below 20 min.), and the design of an assay against this toxin was dropped.

WP4-T2-ST3- Development of specific Ab (poly/monoclonal)

Polyclonal rabbit antibodies against *B. cereus* toxins were also produced by the subcontractant company Covalab. Western blots with the purified toxin showed that the antibodies had a good affinity, since the serum could be used with dilutions up to 1/30000. Antibodies were purified on Protein A columns. Only the targeted toxins were recognized by the antibodies, meaning that they were quite specific.

WP4-T2-ST4- Design of the immunoenzymatic assay

Because of its ease of use, the development of a lateral flow assay (LFA) similar to the Merck DuoPath, allowing for the simultaneous detection of *B. cereus* Smase and HlyII, was initiated at first. However, despite good results, it appeared that the full design of this assay was not compatible with the project deadlines. Therefore, ST4 of WP4-T2 moved to the design of a simple sandwich ELISA, in which the capture antibody and the detection antibodies are identical. The detection antibody was HRP-tagged. The detection limit was 0.5 ng/ml for Smase and 1 ng/ml for HlyII, and the range of quantification was 0.5 ng/ml to 15 ng/ml for Smase and 1ng/ml to 40 ng/ml for HlyII. Toxins in culture supernatants could be readily quantified and spike-recover assays with these culture supernatants gave good results. SOPs are currently being written and material is being prepared for the interlaboratory trials.

WP5: Inter-laboratory ring trial scheme

The inter-lab tests were organized in order to evaluate the transferability of MALDI-ToF , LC-MS and ELISA methods developed in WP1, WP3, and WP4, respectively. These inter-lab tests have been prepared according to the regulation ISO/IEC 17043. Procedure allowing designing and implementing Inter-lab test was drafted and validated by the consortium. This document presents the objectives and a detailed plan for each ILC (Inter-lab comparison test) organization, see deliverable D5.1.

Training session dedicated to the implementation of ILC according to regulation ISO/IEC 17043, presentation of quality documents, samples preparation and establishment of inter-laboratory tests planning was organized by WP5 leader on 1st of December.

WP5-T1- Inter-lab test on MALDI-ToF for species identification

MALDI-ToF Library developed in the frame of WP1 by partner 1 was successfully transferred and implemented in the laboratory of partner 33 for the three pathogens: *Staphylococcus*, *Bacillus* and *Clostridia*.

EJP TOX-Detect and European Reference Laboratory network were invited to participate to MALDI-ToF ILC. In total 12 participants agreed and received the method for implementation. Samples used in This MALDI-ToF PT were issued from reference collection implemented in the frame of WP1 (Constitution of a reference strain collection). On 1st of June, each participant received 10 codified samples for each pathogen (30 samples in total). Results from participants were expected by end of June 2021.

WP5-T2- Inter-lab test on LC-MS/MS

Three LC-MS based methods have been developed in the WP3. SOP's were drafted and transferred to different EJP TOX-Detect partners in order to test the transferability of these developed methods.

- For *Bacillus* LC-MS method, 3 participants implemented the method, and took part to the Inter-lab exercise. In March 2021, each laboratory received standards, and 2 unknown samples. Results obtained by participants were 100% satisfactory.
- For *Clostridium* LC-MS method, 4 participants implemented the method, and participated to the Inter-lab exercise. Each laboratory received standards and several known samples for implementation of the method. In April 2021, each participant received 2 unknown samples (codified). Participants obtained 7/8 satisfactory results. The ILC report was dispatched to participants on 17th of June 2021.
- For Staphylococcal enterotoxin 'type N' LC-MS method, 3 participants implemented the method, and participated to the Inter-lab exercise. In March 2021, each laboratory received standards and several known samples for implementation of the method. In April 2021, 5 unknown samples (codified) were sent to the three participants. 2/3 participants returned their results to the organizer by end of May. The last participant asked additional time due to a technical problem (device failure). The ILC final report was dispatched to participants on 23th of June 2021. Results obtained by participants were satisfactory at 100% and 93% for qualitative and quantitative results, respectively.

WP5-T3- Inter-lab test on immuno-enzymatic assays

Inter-laboratory test dedicated to ELISA method for staphylococcal enterotoxins was cancelled. See “ WP4 and paragraph 3-Project self-assessment”.

For *Bacillus* ELISA, SOPs were drafted in June 2021. Call for participation is in progress.

WP6: Dissemination, protection and exploitation of results

WP6-T1-Dissemination of information within the partners

Communication and information dissemination between partners was realized through meetings and EJP website or using e-mails. Several face-to-face and web meetings were organized within each WP and between the different WPs. The OHEJP coordination was invited to each general assembly in order to share OHEJP news, recommendations, use of the OHEJP site.

Partners were also invited to join the TOX-Detect group available on the OHEJP website. Deliverables and SOPs have been uploaded to the OHEJP website and are available to all TOX-Detect partners. The interim reports are posted on the OHEJP site and distributed by email to partners.

At OH-EJP level, three posters were presented on work implement in WP and WP2 during the three OH-EJP annual meetings.

WP6-T2- Dissemination of information to the outside.

TOX-Detect project and associated works was presented in:

- Five conferences, in 2019, 2020 and 2021, were presented in France, in Germany, in Spain and in an online meeting, for WP0, WP2 and WP3.
- Five work-shops (European Union Reference Laboratory, Italian reference laboratory, EFSA-ERAM and Astralia group).

Six articles were published in 2019, 2020 and 2021, in the journals Sensors, Food Microbiology, Clinical Microbiology and Infection, and Frontiers in Microbiology, all within the frame of WP2 and WP3.

7 more articles are expected to be published in 2021, for WP1 (1 article), WP2 (2 articles), WP3 (1 article), WP4 (2 articles) and WP5 (1 article).

Therefore, the project will be valorized by at least 10 communications and 13 scientific articles, issued from all WPs.

3. Project self-assessment

As for WP1, the goal to constitute a reference strain collection was achieved without too much difficulty as well as libraries of MALDI-ToF reference spectra of these strains. However, the establishment of MTAs for the exchange of strains took a long time and was a source of delay in the accomplishment of the work package. Moreover, transfer of the MALDI Library was limited to the participant using a Bruker spectrometer.

In WP2, methods were set up to characterize the strain cytotoxicity and the presence/expression of toxins. Known and new virulence markers were identified. However, a specific toxin that would differentiate *B. cereus* FBO strains could not be identified. Thus, a complex analytical pathway had to be implemented to analyse the RNA seq data. This induced some delay in the analysis, but allowed to propose a combination of biomarkers able to accurately differentiate clinical from non-pathogenic strains. For *C. perfringens*, it was confirmed that CPE accounted for the strain cytotoxicity. As this WP contained laboratory work, the COVID-19-crisis led to important delays.

WP4:

- The objective to develop specific antibodies against two SEs (WP4-T1-ST3) was only partially reached and, consequently, the development of quantitative immunoassays for two SEs (WP4-T1-ST4) was not reached. The reason for this is a series of problems and delays primarily regarding the fulfilment of safety requirements for the necessary work with toxin producing GMOs. Thus, sufficient amounts of recombinant toxins were only available at a late project stage, which rendered the production of monoclonal antibodies in time impossible. Therefore, polyclonal antibodies were tested, which, however, turned out to be cross-reactive.
- Task 1 had to produce three already known *B. cereus* toxins and to set up immunoenzymatic assays against them. The three toxins (CytK2, HlyII and Smase) were produced, shipped to WP3, and sandwich ELISA methods against HlyII and Smase were successfully developed. The third immunoassay development was dropped since CytK2 is highly unstable. The objectives of WP4 task 2, which were to set up immunoassays against new toxins, could not be fulfilled because WP2 did not provide toxin names in time; no toxins specific to FBO strains could be identified. This task was highly impacted by COVID-19 crisis (animals immunisation).

For WP5, the objective was to implement interlaboratory tests in order to check the robustness and transferability of methods developed in WP1, WP3 and WP4. The delay observed in these 3 WPs impacted the implementation of interlaboratory tests. Over the 8 expected interlaboratory tests, three were achieved (LC-MS), three were achieved end of June (three pathogens for MALDI-ToF). One interlaboratory test achieved end of July (ELISA for *Bacillus*), and one initially dedicated to staphylococcal enterotoxins was cancelled as the method was not developed (see WP4 comment).

Therefore, deliverable D5.2 (report on interlaboratory tests) cannot be submitted on the expected time.

The coordination team faced several management issues mainly related to the changes of deputy coordinator in 2018, change of WP3 coordination twice (2019 and 2020), absence of coordinator and WP6 leader for 4 months.

For the whole project, tasks managed with personnel recruited under “short contract” were highly impacted by COVID-19 crisis.

4. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
05	D0.1	Report of the kick-off meeting	3			OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5484124#.YTed9I4zZaQ	
05	D0.2	Intermediate report	18			OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516312#.YUdnGLgzZaQ	
05	D0.3	Report of the meeting 1	19			OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5484140#.YTefY44zZaQ	
05	D0.4	Report of the meeting 2	25			OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5484143#.YTef7Y4zZaQ	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
05	D0.5	Report of meeting 3	42		cancelled	Meeting organized on 25 June 2021 Deliverable cancelled as there is no relevant information for scientific community. This is only a management document.	
05	D0.6	Final report	45			Done: OHEJP: available	
05	D1.1	List of well characterized reference strains of <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>B. cereus</i> and <i>C. perfringens</i>	5			OHEJP: available Zenodo: D1.1 TOX-DetectListe of well characterized strains Zenodo	
05	D1.2	Libraries of MALDI-ToF reference spectra	33			Confidential, this concern reference strains under MTA and will be published OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516329#.YVIGPbgzZaQ	3
05	D2.1	Report on results from toxicity assays (classical toxicity tests and High Content Analysis)	42			Confidential, technical data under publication OHEJP: available	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516345#.YUdrGbgzZaQ	
05	D2.2	Report on TR-PCR and RNAseq data analysis	42			Confidential, technical data under publication OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516359#.YUdsV7gzZaQ	8
05	D2.3	Report on correlation between RNAseq data analysis and toxicity assays (incl. toolbox for toxicity prediction)	42			Confidential, technical data under publication OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516372#.YUdtRLgzZaQ	8
05	D3.1	Report on MS-based methods for the detection of new enterotoxins (eg SEG, SEH, SEI) from S. aureus	42			Confidential, new developed method, will be published by the end of the project OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516382#.YUduRLgzZaQ	8

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
05	D3.2	Report on MS-based methods for the detection of cereulide analogs and enterotoxins from <i>B. cereus</i>	42			Confidential, new developed method, will be published by the end of the project OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5484152#.YVIA7gzZaQ	8
05	D3.3	Report on MS-based methods for the detection of CPE and virulence factors from <i>C. perfringens</i>	42			Confidential, new developed method, will be published by the end of the project OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516390#.YUdvgrgzZaQ	8
05	D3.4	Report on the performance criteria for method harmonization	44			Confidential, new developed method, will be published by the end of the project OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5484117#.YVII97gzZaQ	2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
05	D4.1	Report on the immuno-enzymatic assays	45			Confidential, new developed method, will be published by the end of the project. OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5516394#.YUdxP7gzZaQ	8
05	D5.1	Inter-lab tests documents according to ISO/IEC 17043 regulation, adapted to each method	45			OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/4479096#.YBQYXuhKhM0	2
05	D5.2	Final report including results from the eight inter-lab tests	45			OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5532845#.YVIni7gzZaQ	8
05	D6.1	Dispatch of SOPs	45			OHEJP: available Zenodo: OH EJP TOX-Detect projec: Dispatch of SOPs Zenodo	2

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
05	D6.2	Dissemination of results (publications, conferences...)	45			OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5532713#.YVIFrgzZaQ	2

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify); 9. This is supportive to an integrative activity; 10. This is not an integrative activity

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
05	MS0.1	General decision on criteria to select strains	3	Yes		
05	MS0.2	General discussion on interlaboratory trial scheme	3	Yes		
05	M-JRP5-03	Construction of the reference strains of <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>B. cereus</i> and <i>C. perfringens</i>	3	Yes		
05	MS1.1	List of well characterized reference strains of <i>S. aureus</i> , <i>B. cereus</i> and <i>C. perfringens</i>	3	Yes		
05	MS1.2	Exchange of libraries of MALDI-ToF reference spectra	24	Yes		
05	MS2.1	Culture conditions optimized	24	Yes		
05	MS3.1	Reference materials available	5	Yes		Reference strains are available for WPs depending on the availability of MTA and results of M-JRP5-04. Reference materials were transferred after MTA signature when it was requested by the host. Transfer started month 5 and achieved at the end of the project
05	MS2.2	RT-PCR assays developed	14	Yes		
05	MS2.3	High content analysis methods developed	18	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
05	MS2.4	RNAseq data analysed	38	Yes		
05	MS3.2	Methods developed and assessed	24	Yes		
05	MS2.5	Correlation between toxicity profiles and expression patterns assessed.	30	Yes		
05	MS3.3	Methods transferred to partners	39	Yes		
05	MS4.1	Genetic tools constructed for over-expression of known <i>S. aureus</i> and <i>B. cereus</i> toxins	9	Yes		
05	MS4.2	Antibodies produced against known <i>S. aureus</i> and <i>B. cereus</i> toxins	33	Yes		
05	MS4.3	Immuno-enzymatic assays designed for known <i>S. aureus</i> and <i>B. cereus</i> toxins	32	Yes		Milestone not achieved for <i>S. aureus</i> toxins (see explanation in WP4 paragraph).
05	MS4.4	Genetic tools constructed for over-expression of a new <i>B. cereus</i> toxin/virulence factor	/	No		Milestone not achieved (see explanation in WP4 paragraph).
05	MS4.5	Antibodies produced against new <i>B. cereus</i> toxin/virulence factor overproduced	/	No		Milestone not achieved for (see explanation in WP4 paragraph).
05	MS4.6	Immuno-enzymatic assays designed for a new <i>B. cereus</i> toxin/virulence factor	42	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
05	MS4.7	Immuno-enzymatic assays transferred to partners	42	Yes		
05	MS5.1	Dispatch of inter-lab tests documents (according to ISO/IEC 17043 regulation) adapted to each method	M25	Yes		https://zenodo.org/record/4479096#.YBQYXuhKhM0
05	MS5.2	Dispatch of samples and evaluation report to be filled by partners	M44	No	43	Done for LC-MS and MALDI-ToF Expected in M43 for ELISA Bacillus
05	MS5.3	Samples analysed by partners	M42	No	45	Done for LC-MS and MALDI-ToF Expected in M45 for ELISA Bacillus
05	MS5.4	Dispatch of final report	M45	No		Expected in M45 after receivin report on Interlab test for ELISA Bacillus
05	MS6.1	Final report dispatched	M45	No		

5. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Point-of-Need DNA Testing for Detection of Foodborne Pathogenic Bacteria, Vidic et al, 2019, Sensors DOI: 10.3390/s19051100 Uploaded on Zenodo DOI : https://zenodo.org/record/3935799#.YBQaJ-hKhMO	YES	NN	1500\$
Advanced Methods for Detection of Bacillus cereus and Its Pathogenic Factors. Nalini Ramarao, Seav-Ly Tran, Marco Marin, and Jasmina Vidic. Uploaded on Zenodo doi: https://doi.org/10.3390/s20092667	YES	NN	1500\$
Large-Scale Genomic Analyses and Toxinotyping of Clostridium perfringens Implicated in Foodborne Outbreaks in France, Abakabir Mahamat et al, Front Microbiol, 2019. Uploaded on Zenodo https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.00777	YES	No	2655 \$

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
The cytotoxic potential of Bacillus cereus strains of various origins, Glasset et al, Food Microbiology, 2021 Uploaded on Zenodo DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2021.103759	YES	No	No
New genetic biomarkers to differentiate pathogenic and clinically relevant Bacillus cereus strains, Kavanaugh et al., Clin Microbiol Infect, 2021. Uploaded on Zenodo DOI: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmi.2021.05.035	YES	No	No
DiagnoTop: a computational pipeline for discriminating bacterial pathogens without database search. Diogo Borges Lima, Mathieu Dupré, Marlon Dias Mariano Santos, Paulo Costa Carvalho, Julia Chamot-Rooke. Journal of the American Society of Mass Spectrometry. Uploaded on Zenodo https://doi.org/10.1021/jasms.1c00014	YES	No	1227\$

Additional output

This project focused on virulence factors produced by some bacteria producing toxins. Tools developed are complementary with those developed in the frame of the H2020 project EuroBioTox focusing on biothreats. In this one, three partners of the One Health EJP TOX-Detect are present (Anses, Sciensano, Pasteur Institute). Exchanges between the two consortiums and overall presentations of the results will be made during the next meeting of EuroBioTox and during the final meeting of TOX-Detect which will take place in September 2021.

These two projects enhance European networks focusing on bacterial toxins in a One Health context.

Outcomes

In TOX-Detect project, deliverables D1.1 (List of well characterized reference strains of *S. aureus*, *B. cereus* and *C. perfringens*) and D1.2 (Libraries of MALDI-ToF reference spectra) and D5.2 task 1 (Inter-laboratory test on MALDI-ToF method) represent a complete achievement in term of implementation of new databases and methods from implementation of reference collection of strains until the transfer of the method to the European Union Reference Laboratory network. The **MALDI-ToF Library** will complete the commercial database with spectra obtained from strains issued from food born outbreaks occurred in European Union. After publication of the work in open access journals, the scientific community can benefit from this new MALDI-ToF library to improve the MALDI-ToF method in terms of discrimination potential.

WP2 deliverables and D3.3 (Report on MS-based methods for the detection of CPE and virulence factors from *C. perfringens*) propose toxicity and enterotoxins data obtained for *C. perfringens* strains issued from food born outbreaks occurred in European Union. A set of complementary tools developed in this TOX-Detect project can be implemented and used by reference and expert laboratories for food born outbreak investigation, especially RT PCR and LC-MS techniques.

Deliverables dedicated to Staphylococcal enterotoxins study (D3.1 and D4.1) indicate that the enterotoxins SEM, SEN and SEO are produced at very low levels of concentration compared to classical enterotoxins. This information was presented to the EURL for coagulase Positive Staphylococci (EURL for CPS) which will use it for further study and methods development as reported in EURL working program 2019 and 2020. Also, enterotoxins and antibodies produced in WP4 were transferred to EURL for CPS in order to use them to enlarge the scope of detection methods for Staphylococcal enterotoxins.

6. One Health Impact

In this project, we focused on bacterial toxins according to the One Health concept. For this purpose all partners combined isolates coming from food, environmental and clinical samples. All the selected strains have been fully characterized by partners and were used to perform method developments.

The first outcome is the availability of this large and fully characterized collection of strains. A part of this collection has been already used to feed another One Health EJP project, i.e. CARE.

The second outcome is the development of dedicated Maldi-ToF libraries. Robustness of these MSP libraries have been evaluated by a dedicated ILS generating more than 3000 data. We highlighted that the percentage of correct identification of the three pathogens covered by TOX-Detect significantly increased especially for the identification of the isolates of the *B. cereus* group. As results obtained were highly satisfactory, we will dispatch these libraries among partners as well in the EU networks.

Moreover, thanks to this strain collection we were able to design 15 harmonized SOPs for all the targeted virulence factors and 6 dedicated methods. All of these deliverables contributed to the tool box we would like to design at the beginning of the project to enhance characterization of bacteria

producing toxins. These deliverables have been shared and could be used by partners as ILS demonstrated their robustness and efficiency.

JRP06-FBZ1-NOVA

1. Summary of the work carried out

Background

Zoonotic foodborne diseases constitute a serious one health problem throughout the world and are expected to stay high on the infectious diseases risk agenda, fuelled by factors such as globalised trade with food and live animals, modern intensified food production systems, international travel, and the continuous adaptation of known and arising pathogens and hazards, including increased antibiotic resistance. Foodborne diseases, being very prevalent and giving rise to sequelae, pose a serious problem to public health and have significant economic implications in terms of cost of care, loss of productivity and in the agricultural and food industry sectors.

In order to limit the damage and cost caused by zoonotic diseases, it is better to prevent than to cure. Disease surveillance is a crucial prerequisite for prevention; it allows us to be able to analyse and understand trends and patterns of disease occurrence and to choose and evaluate intervention strategies. However, surveillance systems are not always working well and they also come with a price tag. Also digital data sources continues to develop, also within the food chain, and should be utilised if possible for surveillance purposes. It is therefore important that we continuously develop the ways we do surveillance and that we have methods to measure and compare the performance of different surveillance activities. This has been the overall aim of the NOVA project suite.

Methods

NOVA has included project participants from 19 public health and veterinary institutes in 10 countries over a project period of 3½ years. As one of the larger OHEJP projects, it has addressed improvement of disease surveillance through a large number of separate projects, organised into five main themes, as reflected in its overall work package structure. Below, three results from each theme, which we find particularly interesting, are highlighted. Results are summarised in more depths in Section 2 of the Final Report and presented through published and in prep papers and the formal project deliverable reports.

Results

Theme **A. Basic aspects** (and issues in connection with) performing **One Health surveillance** (WP1):

- Surveillance across the foodchain is as yet far from used enough; it holds (and is perceived by actors as holding) much potential.
- Focus group studies highlighted a complex pattern of barriers and opportunities for OH surveillance. In particular relating to data governance.
- A glossary of terms was developed (together with other OHEJP projects) to help overcome barriers between veterinary, food and human surveillance activities.

Theme **B. Use of electronic traces of purchase of food** for surveillance and outbreak investigations (WP2):

- Electronic records of the foods we all buy in shops are a powerful tool in the hands of the disease detectives that investigate foodborne outbreaks. A network to promote use hereof was built.

- Methods of analyses of *big datasets* on supermarket purchases can automatically find vehicles and calculate odds ratio's therefore – tapping into supermarket purchase information should be used regularly in the future for foodborne outbreak investigations.
- Foodborne outbreaks in care institutions – hospitals and elderly homes – occur, are preventable and sometimes traceable via electronic invoices food sales.

Theme **C. One Health** developments of **syndromic surveillance** methods (WP3):

- Individual monitoring of *Campylobacter* detections in major broiler slaughterhouses proved effective for enhancing early detection of *Campylobacter* outbreaks in humans
- Parallel monitoring of indicators on cattle health, *Salmonella* detection in food, and human gastro-intestinal syndromes revealed simultaneous temporal abnormalities. Simultaneous alarms may be used to trigger and orientate field epidemiological investigations.
- Predictions based on models combining veterinary, meteorological and medical data in Norway were used to develop a dashboard to provide stakeholders with predictions of gastrointestinal outbreaks one week ahead of other systems.

Theme **D.** Use and development of **spatial risk mapping** (WP4):

- Development of spatial disease distribution models (for *Salmonella*) have identified provinces in Spain at risk, while taking into account the effect of potential risk factors.
- Risk-based surveillance of *Salmonella*, based on a spatial stochastic disease spread model, was economically favourable -- it relied on only one third of the samples used by traditional surveillance, although the capacity for case detection was also reduced.
- Models and scripts that have been developed for salmonellosis can be applied for other zoonotic diseases and many geographical regions in Europe, depending on data availability.

Theme **E.** Modelling the **cost efficiency** of surveillance programs (WP5):

- By combining models for disease transmission (SIR) simulating emerging food safety issues with models simulating sampling schedules and models of laboratory procedures, we determined the time such systems will need to detect an emerging infection – thereby providing a tool to optimise emerging risk surveillance systems.
- It is possible (by modelling) to make a holistic assessment of how new laboratory technologies can be used to improve the performance of surveillance systems before the technology is actually implemented in a population.
- We've shown that the performance of surveillance programs of foodborne diseases in any part of the food production can (and should) be measured as the effect on the human risk using an QMRA approach, and the cost of surveillance (both monitoring and control) per prevented human case.

Discussion

Overall, NOVA has contributed to the development of several novel methods that can be used to make surveillance and response more efficient and cost-effective. In parallel to strengthening of modelling and data frameworks, we have explored and started the process to incorporate new data sources in the everyday surveillance that our institutes are involved in. We conclude that modelling the full chain from primary production to the consumer, including environmental aspects, is possible but remains a challenge. Our collaboration confirm that a multidisciplinary approach is needed to combine and understand information from the different surveillance components.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results

WPO. Coordination and project management

WPO-T1- Project management

Monthly meetings with WP leaders were held throughout the project, starting already November 2017. For coordination purposes, the coordinator and/or other members from the coordination group attended the official kick-off of meeting of the full OHEJP consortium, and various information meetings within the OHEJP over the years, such as the Project Leaders' Forum. Especially at the start of the OHEJP collaboration meetings with representatives from the ORION and COHESIVE projects were necessary to sort out potential overlap and create synergies between the projects. We have also attended a OHEJP Programme Managers' Committee meeting and a few OHEJP stakeholders' meetings.

Apart from these meetings, project management has included reporting, finding platforms for sharing of information and documents and to summarise information about the project e.g. for the websites of the OHEJP and our institutes. Management has also involved work with the ethics self-assessment and the data management plan (DMP). The DMP work required attendance of educational sessions organised by the OHEJP management, and additional meetings to plan and complete this work process.

A request to extend the project was sent to OHEJP management in May. Due to slow recruiting processes in several partner institutes, we decided already in 2019 that we would ask for an extension. The COVID-19 pandemic also influenced the work in several partner institutes/countries. The request was endorsed and accepted by the PMT and the members of the SSB in June 2020.

WPO-T2- Organise annual assemblies

The first annual assembly was held in Rome, February 28th to March 1st. The meeting was considered a kick-off meeting where we focused on getting to know each other and pick up the planning of tasks and studies included in the project proposal.

A second annual assembly was held in Brussels, March 7-8, 2019. The purpose of the meeting was to meet, plan and discuss ongoing and coming tasks. To focus this work, three specific topics were addressed in the discussions: 1. International aspects and opportunities for international collaboration, 2. Scientific publications, 3. Novelty of methods and approaches used. To share research results across WPs, a scientific webinar was also organised for all project participants in November.

Organisation of a third annual assembly was started at the end of 2019 and was planned to be held in Madrid, 23-24 April 2020. The meeting was cancelled in March due to the COVID-19 pandemic and instead, a shorter online meeting was held on the 23rd of April, with short scientific presentations from the WPs and general information.

In spring 2021 we had a final assembly that again had to be held online. This time we had a two-day meeting, 18-19 May, combining scientific presentations with general information and concluding remarks from the WP leaders.

WPO-T3- Economic reporting and financial management

SVA participated in the start-up financial OHEJP meeting at ANSES 2018 but did not coordinate economic reporting for other partners, as the financial reporting for the joint research project within the OHEJP are performed by each partner institute involved. However, in response to a request by the OHEJP coordination in 2020, the project partners were asked to report any costs that had been wasted due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Only two partner institutes reported such costs. Later, the OHEJP coordination also requested that the budget for the third year of the project were updated by each partner and specific budget files were filled in and sent to OHEJP centrally in June. The conclusion from this update was that partners plan to not underspend but to use potentially remaining resources during the extension period in the fourth year.

WP1. Food chain surveillance mapping

WP1-T1- Definition of a joint food borne zoonosis surveillance terminology

Given the work on a Med-Vet glossary of the participants of ORION WP2 in which members of NOVA WP1 also participated in the first year, in order to complete the deliverable of this WP, a collaboration was established with the ORION team, as well as COHESIVE.

WP1-T1 has collected 274 terms from partners leading all WPs. The NOVA Glossary was delivered to the ORION project leader, BfR, in the second half of June 2019 in order to incorporate the NOVA Glossary into the common OH Glossary. In the period between July and October 2019, there were several exchanges with BfR in order to adjust the NOVA Glossary into the common version. The final result can be found here: <https://aginfra.d4science.org/web/orionknowledgehub/>

The OHEJP Glossary has 3 main functionalities. First, it is a collection of One Health related terms and definitions in the sectors public health, animal health and food safety. Second, it highlights similarities and differences of terms and definitions between the sectors. Finally, it provides an infrastructure to references, search and filter terms, and definitions. As an outcome of this cooperation (of all three projects), a joint article was published in May 2021.

WP1-T2- Mapping of surveillance: data, regulatory framework, key stakeholders, opportunities and barriers

The objective of this task was to identify barriers and opportunities for an integrated One Health surveillance of food-borne diseases in selected EU countries. The task was split into two qualitative research studies: one targeting responsible experts and officials (coordination/administration level) of surveillance activities across the food chain in four different countries, and one targeting veterinary practitioners (field level) in one country. The results from these studies can be used to support revision of existing systems, or development of new systems for food-borne disease surveillance from a One Health (OH) perspective.

Coordination level study

In order to identify barriers and opportunities in food-borne disease surveillance from a One Health perspective, information was collected through interviews with professionals with selected profiles on coordination/administration level and from four countries (Belgium, France, Sweden, and Norway). The study methods and preparations included: 1. Mapping of an existing food chain (used as a visual tool for cueing), 2. Development of an interview guide document, 3. Demographic questionnaire, 4. Excel files for collection of data, 5. Training on performing interviews and qualitative research, 6. Interview try-outs.

The profiles of the professionals interviewed in each of the four countries were the following:

- I. A human medicine epidemiologist (e.g. the head of such a unit or an experienced professional with knowledge of different diseases and managing them)
- II. A person from administration in charge of planning the annual programmed food chain surveillance (expected to be placed at the Min. for Agriculture)
- III. A veterinary medicine epidemiologist (same as for human epidemiologist)
- IV. A transversal coordinator of a national agency, positioned on the link between risk analysis and risk management
- V. Persons from laboratories, ideally the coordinators of the human and veterinary National Reference laboratories (RNL).

The participants selected to be interviewed were identified and contacted by the WP1 members representing each country thanks to their professional network. The 20 interviews were performed by three researchers who received the same training on performing interviews. More detailed information is provided in the respective deliverable report, while a manuscript is being drafted.

According to the analysis, which was performed following the thematic analysis methodology, the barriers and opportunities identified by the interviewees were grouped in the following themes: 1. Data governance, 2. Set-up and operations of the surveillance system, 3. Coordination, 4. Communication, 5. Regulations (political legislations and procedures), 6. Industry's challenges, 7. Funding, 8. Training and education.

For all countries, the barriers and opportunities pointed out as being most important belonged to the themes covering Data governance and Set-up and operations of the surveillance system.

Therefore, the results show that there is room for improvement in food-borne disease surveillance of microbiological pathogens towards a One-Health approach, especially regarding the themes identified as most. An analysis of the collected information is also being performed per identified theme, taking into account the particularities of each country.

Field level study

Early detection of zoonotic and emerging infections is critical for successful handling of outbreaks and control of foodborne diseases. Veterinary practitioners have a key role in the detection of such diseases in livestock. Our objective was to explore how the clinical surveillance and reporting zoonotic and regulated diseases in livestock are perceived and performed by veterinarians in Sweden.

In this study, we conducted in-depth face-to-face interviews with 13 field veterinarians selected based on socio-demographic characteristics. The veterinarians were working in large animal practice. A semi-structured interview guide with open-ended questions and prompts was used to collect qualitative data. The interviews started with general questions to capture the veterinarians' profiles. Thereafter, interviewees were asked to describe their actions in cases of suspected emerging and zoonotic infections under regulation. The discussions followed topics that included their awareness of major disease threats, their perceived role in diseases surveillance, and views on its feasibility. The interviews were transcribed in verbatim followed by thematic analysis of the transcripts using a phenomenological approach.

Themes that commonly appeared were veterinarians, for various reasons, disregarding clinical signs possibly associated with the emerging and zoonotic infections; difficulties to take samples under field circumstances and to send these samples for diagnostic tests; and aspects related to a communication network involving those taking part of the surveillance system.

These results can serve as a baseline for the design of questionnaire-based surveys, also targeting veterinarians in other countries, as a complementary quantitative approach to investigate clinical surveillance. The results provide suggestions for improvements in the reporting chain. The final goal is to increase the likelihood that a veterinary practitioner promptly contacts animal health authorities when they encounter animals showing signs indicative of diseases under national or EU legislation.

WP2. Analysis of food purchase data

Those who like to read detective novels or watch police investigation films, know that the investigators often decide to 'follow the money'. The clever police team follows the electronic trail that money transfer leaves when they investigate and solve complicated criminal cases. When trying to crack the sometimes very complicated epidemiological problems of foodborne diseases and foodborne outbreak investigations, one might wonder if not the same logic may be applied – just for food and not money. In this work package, the overall aim was to explore the possibilities of working with electronic records of food purchase and food movements for obtaining a better understanding of the transmission of foodborne diseases.

Work package 2 (WP2) of NOVA aimed to elucidate whether the surveillance potential of food consumption, as reflected by consumer purchasing patterns, may serve as a digital tool to aid our understanding of both outbreaks and general risk factors of foodborne zoonoses. Understanding food consumption patterns is an important part of understanding foodborne diseases, and modern society opens new possibilities to do this using existing data flows. With recent advents of electronic storage

of purchase receipts, several countries and food business operators have obtained large but currently unused datasets, which can contribute important information. WP2 was divided into five separate tasks, I) Usage & barriers, II) Outbreak investigations, III) Big data analysis, IV) Hospital outbreaks and V) Trace-back and risk mapping. These five subtasks are described individually below.

WP2-T1- Data availability of purchase and consumer data for outbreak investigations (Formerly: Data availability and barriers)

Some EU countries have several years of experience with use of supermarket purchase data or other consumer data for the investigation of foodborne outbreaks, whereas others have never used it. The objective of WP2.1 was to map actors involved in obtaining and using purchase and consumer data, get an overview of the data already used, the context they may have been used in and the experience with these data for outbreak investigations. A second objective was to try to map possible barriers and obstacles when obtaining and/or using these purchase data and other consumer data. This was done through two questionnaire surveys inquiring about purchase data. These comprised data from supermarkets, wholesale, the Internet, fast food chains, and organizations who have access to these data (e.g. market surveys and scanning data companies/apps). Other consumer data comprised catering companies for health care institutions, schools, etc., and in house food preparation in health care institutions, schools, etc. All (public health) partners of EJP-NOVA received an email with the links to questionnaires. Secondly, we approached the institute representatives included in One Health EJP and the members of the ECDC Food- & Waterborne Disease (FWD) network via the Epidemic Intelligence Information System for FWD (EPIS-FWD) to complete one or both questionnaires or to give names of (possible) contacts who could.

Eleven countries completed one or both questionnaires on use of purchase and consumer data in (outbreak) investigations and other research. Seven countries reported to have actually used these data in one or more studies. The two main aims for using purchase and other consumer data are source hypothesis-generation and food trace-back investigation. It is seen as an alternative tool to solve outbreaks with advantages including: that it mitigates issues around the inability of people to remember everything they have eaten one or more weeks ago, especially stealth food products and also that it may provide good data which can lead to strong evidence pointing to a product. Purchase data of supermarket chains could become available for use in almost all countries, often with national coverage. Other purchase and consumer data are less often already available and are more often local or regional. To gather purchase data, member/loyalty, credit and cash cards are crucial, as data could not be extracted for any of the data sources when the purchases are payed cash. The most experience appear to be in the area of the supermarkets, mainly chains, but also consortia and individual supermarkets. Overall, actors needed to obtain and use these data were national public health institute – often together with regional public health institute(s) – and the national food safety authority. Depending on where the purchase or consumer data is obtained from, also the company/institution, chain, consortium or interest group is involved.

Three groups of disadvantages were experienced when using the data, namely obstacles on the level of the supermarket/company/institution, the cases, and the handling of the data. Within all responding countries, eight of 11 countries and six of nine countries saw practical and/or technical obstacles for obtaining and using purchase and other consumer data, respectively, with the main threat being a too high workload. Of all obstacles, privacy legislation was conceived as the most important barrier as it was the only barrier mentioned by more than half of the countries.

WP2-T2- Food purchase data for outbreak investigations

Foodborne outbreaks occur with a high frequency in Europe and constitute a high, although partly preventable, burden to health and economy. Unfortunately, the majority of outbreaks are not fully resolved, in part because outbreak investigations are very time consuming and often rely on patient interviews that can be difficult to perform in sufficient scale and in a timely manner. There is therefore much to gain, if information could be easily gathered in an electronic format on which foods, the patients that are part of outbreaks, have bought in supermarkets or shops prior to becoming ill. Then

it would theoretically be possible to find the foods, which the patients have in common and perhaps even to do a statistical comparison of purchase frequency with a non-patient consumer population. The aim of WP2.2 was to describe this line of investigation as an outbreak methodology, describe its prior use, and map the obstacles that lies in the way of a wider use and to produce recommendations for how it could be applied in EU member states. This was thus to a large degree a review and networking exercise.

As a first step a structured review of the already published literature was done with the purpose of obtaining an overview of the degree to which the method has been used and how it has found application so far. This review was published as Møller et al (2017) in *Eurosurveillance*. For the period 2006–17, scientific articles were found describing 20 outbreak investigations. They were presented and the benefits and shortcomings of the method was discussed in the paper. The term ‘consumer purchase data’ (CPD) was introduced to refer to the method.

As a next step, we invited epidemiologists with experience with CPD to take part in a network. We reached out via the European Public health institutes and the EPIET alumni organisation (EAN) and succeeded in creating a small working group from eight European countries plus Canada. In online consultations, this group has tried to answer the central questions of “When is this method working?” and: “When is it not useful and why?” with the aim of suggesting ways to facilitate its use. It was generally found that perceived obstacles related mostly to lack of guidance in how to use CPD rather than legal issues. A manuscript, which based on these consultations contain a description of a framework for use of CPD as an outbreak investigation method has been submitted. We hope that the work we have so far initiated will lead to a resurgence of use of CPD for outbreak investigations and that this network will keep growing.

WP2-T3- Working with large datasets and novel ways of analysed consumer purchase data (Formerly: Big data analysis of risk factors for sporadic disease)

The previous task dealt with concrete individual outbreak situations. It is conceivable, however, that access to large datasets could lead to conduction of semi-automated outbreak investigations being possible and that CPD could also be used for general analytical purposes. This was the focus of the work conducted in WP2.3. Two paths were followed:

In one path, we aimed to set-up a case-control study of risk factors for sporadic disease using only CPD. *Salmonella* was chosen as the model organism and the project concerned Denmark only. The aim has been to build a digital solution into which Danish residents by invitation (cases of *Salmonella* and comparable persons without known infection selected from the population register) can sign up. This solution includes a way of safely logging in to a secure website where the user is presented with study objectives and information about legal rights and with the possibility of further opening up for investigator access into past purchase records. This is possible if the user is already subscribing to a third party solution (an app) that stores the results of credit card purchases – something about 20% of the Danish population do. This technical solution (which was built with additional support from funding outside of NOVA) is now working and is legally compliant. Construction has involved overcoming a large number of practical, technical and legal challenges. Also, the case-control study is ethically and data-technically approved, a draft of a protocol study has been prepared for submission, and invitational letters have been drafted. However, due to the exceptional COVID-19 situation, the final legal approval of the data collection platform, that were to be used to collect consumer data, was not approved until early June 2021. Thus, running the case control study has been postponed until end of 2021/beginning of 2022 after the end of NOVA. This is in other words a sustainable activity!

A second independent path has involved trying to obtain large real consumer dataset from Scandinavian supermarket chains. Initially work was done using a very large dataset from a major Danish supermarket chain, however, this work had to stop halfway into the project because of GDPR issues. Following a year of negotiations by the FHI, a second large anonymized consumer purchase dataset was offered to our use by a group of Norwegian supermarket chains. It contains individual weekly purchase histories available for analysis (920,834 unique customers from six Norwegian

municipalities in 2019, totalling 222 mill purchases of 30,929 different products). The results of the analysis was presented at the OH_EJP annual meeting 2021 with the title “Simulation and identification of foodborne outbreaks in real consumer purchase data“, and a manuscript is in preparation. The study aimed to use consumer purchase data to simulate outbreaks, identify outbreak vehicles using regression, and examine how performance of selected analytic strategies varied across outbreak parameters.

The simulations generated outbreaks with different attack rates, proportion of background cases (where CPD was not available), and food expiry dates. Further analysis was conducted to evaluate the effect of Item purchase frequency. The proportion of background cases (i.e., those with no available consumer data), was the most important parameter for the number of cases needed to point towards a possible source of the outbreak. Sensitivity analysis was also conducted to address different attack rates (0.01-0.1), expiry length (0-300 days) and incubation time (0-10 days). Not surprisingly, the higher the item detail level (primary product group eg. ‘diary’, secondary product group eg. ‘milk’, and GTIN level: product ID, and brand specific product), the less cases were needed before it was possible to point towards an outbreak source. Thus a logistic regression method can identify outbreak vehicles in a real-world CPD, and is, until further methods are explored, a good consensus candidate. Also, analysis of outbreaks using product groups with a granularity that is comparable to most trawling questionnaires, reduces performance compared to outbreaks analysed on item level. The study also indicated that CPD analysis requires participation from all major grocery chains for optimal performance.

WP2-T4- Foodborne outbreaks within healthcare institutions and use of electronic data of patient meals for their control (Formerly: Food distribution data for hospital outbreaks)

The studies described above targeted illness in the community, however foodborne outbreaks may also take place in hospital and other healthcare settings. For these, individual CPD may not be relevant, but data flows of food purchase by the institutions would be the target of investigation. To explore the possibilities within this area was the focus of WP2.4. It contained two connected but separate paths:

This first aimed to describe the epidemiology of healthcare-associated foodborne outbreaks (HA-FBOs) by conducting a literature review and analysing surveillance data on HA-FBOs. This work has been accepted for publication (Eurosurveillance, 2020, Boone et al). It found 85 HA-FBOs that could be included in an analysis in which the top three associated pathogens were *Salmonella spp.*, norovirus and *Listeria monocytogenes*. High mortality was reported in listeriosis HA-FBOs. The most frequently reported food categories for HA-FBOs were mixed foods, such as ready-to-eat sandwiches, vegetables and fruits, and meat and meat products. Associated risk factors included consumption of contaminated ready-to-eat food including risky foods, unprocessed contaminated foods, inadequate heat treatment, insufficient hygiene of kitchen and equipment and pathogen carriers among food handlers. Based on this analysis, it was concluded that the food supply chain for HCFs must be strictly controlled, HCFs should adhere to food safety measures and hold regular food safety trainings for HCF staff. To increase the early detection of HA-FBOs, surveillance of healthcare associated infections should be integrated with surveillance of foodborne diseases which necessitates interdisciplinary collaboration and exchange of information between hospital hygienists, food safety and public health authorities.

The second path aimed to assess whether electronic data of patient meals served in healthcare facilities (HCF) are available and if these data can be used to prevent HA-FBOs and support outbreak investigations.

The study included electronic data records of meals served to patients in hospitals and nursing homes. To investigate the availability, accessibility and usefulness of patient food menu data for outbreak investigations of HA-FBOs, a survey was conducted jointly among 22 HCFs in Italy and 13 HCFs in Germany. HCFs could directly link food menu data to individual patients in 17/19 hospitals in Italy and 3/7 hospitals in Germany, while in nursing homes this linkage was possible in only 1/3, and 1/7 nursing homes Italy and in Germany, respectively. A large variability was reported in the format and the storage duration of patient food data of HCFs. Searchable databases to store patient menu data were more

frequently reported among Italian hospitals (15/19) than in German hospitals (3/7), whereas such databases were not reported by nursing homes. Both in Italian and German HCFs, food considered as risky for vulnerable persons were offered on the menu. The survey indicated that the availability and usability of patient food data to support HA-FBO investigations were insufficient in German and Italian HCFs, especially in nursing homes. Therefore, standards should be developed to directly link hospital menu data with individual patients, and to harmonise storage duration of patient food data. The survey suggested a need to increase the awareness to avoid high-risk foods on the menu in HCFs.

An online workshop with the healthcare professionals from the Italian HCFs who participated in the survey was organised by the ISS on the 19th of March 2021. In this workshop, HA-FBOs were described, results of the survey in Italy and in Germany were presented, and traceability to support HA-FBO investigations discussed. In addition, focus group discussions were organised with the participants in order to identify strong and weak points for the identification and control of HA-FBOs. Participants highlighted the importance of electronic food traceability data for patient meals instead of paper-based data, and the need for training and information on food safety both for healthcare workers and patients/caregivers. In addition, a contribution was made to a publication on a listeriosis outbreak investigation involving HCFs in Germany. In this outbreak, prospective calculation of disease association was not feasible because of the scarcity of hospital menu data. The likely food vehicle for this outbreak was identified because of the identification of HCFs and the following food supply analysis of the involved HCFs. To fine-tune recommendations on the fitness of patient meal data for HA-FBO investigations, it would be useful to set up additional discussions with members of the OHEJP network.

WP2-T5- Trace back and food risk mapping

Besides data records of food purchases, trace data on a larger geographical scale may also be used to help locate sources of foodborne outbreaks. This was the focus on WP2.5 which centred on the further development of a previously developed risk tool by the BfR: “FoodChain-Lab”. The FoodChain-Lab web application (FCL Web) is an intuitive and user-friendly app that can support public health institutes during foodborne outbreak investigations. It analyses suspicious food items by back- and forward-tracing in the supply chain. The aim of this work was to provide a faster recognition of products potentially involved in foodborne outbreaks. To this end, we implemented the model developed by Kausrud et al. (NVI) that calculates the likelihood of products to be the source of a foodborne-related outbreak based on sales data. This calculation allows investigators to save precious time and resources during outbreaks, since it helps to prioritize food items that should be sampled for laboratory analysis.

Since the calculation of the original model isn’t an easy task especially for users lacking IT-skills, we wanted to provide a user-friendly and intuitive solution to facilitate the access to this method. Therefore, we developed a single page user interface using state of the art technology. We created a step by step guide on how to run the model, how to adjust model parameters for improving accuracy, and how the input data should be structured. The user can grade the results of the calculation by reviewing additional information on the data and results displayed on a map. Using EUROSTAT’s Local Administrative Unit (LAU) data set, we improved the original model by making it available for the whole European Union, since the original model was designed for Norway.

Besides usability, we also invested quite some effort to make the application as sustainable and secure as possible. Therefore, we followed a modular based approach. This means that elements of the web application are reusable, exchangeable and upgradeable. We re-implemented the original model into a module that can be easily integrated into other solutions. At the same time, it increases the calculation performance of the model and provides reproducible results. Another effect of this modular based approach is that we can calculate the model entirely on the user’s machine within the web browser. This increases security, since sensitive data used in the model does not leave the local computer. Hence, the risk of data leakage or hacks of data bases is reduced.

The implementation of the advanced likelihood model into FCL Web increases the availability of this model and provides investigators easy, fast, secure and reliable usage to improve outbreak investigation workflows. It can be accessed at this web address: <https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin>. In

conclusion, integration of a likelihood model for food risk mapping into the state-of-the-art tracing tool FoodChain-Lab allows for open access use in the scientific community.

WP3. Syndromic surveillance

WP3-T1- Identify the opportunities for SyS of FBD

The objective of this task was to identify potential data sources in Member States with partners contributing to WP3, in order to develop specific surveillance components for FBD based on “secondary data” in tasks 3.2 and 3.3. “Secondary data” are already available information, sometimes collected for other purposes than health surveillance that may be of interest for health surveillance.

WP3-T1-ST1- Food chain mapping

The methodology for the inventory of data sources was defined in the NOVA kick-off meeting in March 2018. We drew a comprehensive map of the food chain, from primary production to human consumption (JRP6-WP3-T1-ST1). A general flow chart of the food chain and its environment was drawn, and information flows associated to the material flows were identified.

WP3-T1-ST2- Data source screening: availability, quality and suitability for SyS

In parallel with the food-chain mapping, we worked on a detailed inventory of data sources existing along this food producing continuum. A table was designed to collect data potentially useful and available for data-driven surveillance of FBD. The table was filled in based on expertise of NOVA WP3 members. Forty-nine data sources were identified as relevant for *Salmonella* surveillance along the food chain in the four countries: 28 were dedicated to animal health, 13 to public health, one in feed, one in the environment sector, and six covered at least two sectors. A wide diversity of data sources was observed, from operational surveillance systems producing daily alerts to isolated databases with no centralisation of data. Potential gaps in surveillance coverage were identified. The general flow chart provided a convenient framework to identify existing data sources for inter-sectoral foodborne zoonosis surveillance. This facilitated pinpointing possible but yet unused data sources. As the identified data sources are planned to be used in task 3.2. for the development of univariate surveillance modules, quality of the data for that purpose were critically assessed (JRP6-WP3-T1-ST2).

WP3-T2- Univariate syndromic surveillance development for FBD (and AMR)

Tasks 2 and 3 were launched at the end of Year 1. Task 1 showed that the three countries participating in T2 and T3 do not have the same level of progress in the implementation and use of SyS monitoring tools. We therefore put in place different strategies depending on the degree of progress. However, we chose the same case study in all three countries: the monitoring of *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* from animal and food production to human population. We evaluated univariate syndromic surveillance data of many kinds and origins, from high to very low specificity. For example, we tested datasets of *Campylobacter* isolations on broiler carcasses but also syndromic data (digestive symptoms). Datasets had thus various statistical characteristics like stationarity, trend, seasonality, average number of events, etc. These characteristics influenced the results of detection algorithms, based on their configuration. In this context, we applied a wide range of detection algorithms based on various statistical theories with various sensitivity and specificity in order to highlight diverse statistical anomalies. These algorithms were all effective in different ways, with their performance generally being complementary. In order to enhance sensitivity of detection algorithms and thus to increase relevance of identified events, three main points were raised: the combination of several algorithms, the overlap of multiple datasets and, the use of various temporal and spatial resolutions.

WP3-T3- Evaluation of multivariate syndromic surveillance for FBD

We worked on the methods to integrate signals from different univariate syndromic surveillance systems to improve outbreak detection in humans. In Sweden, an explanatory multivariate SyS was developed, in which the value of evidence (Bayesian likelihood ratio) for an outbreak was assessed for each time point (week), by using a Bayesian statistical model. The model could take multiple time series

data (human *Campylobacter* cases, positive *Campylobacter* tests in broilers, and weather data) together and the outcome was available at national level. The Norwegian veterinary and public health institutes worked on adding veterinary data (*Campylobacter* in poultry) and environmental data (rainfall, temperature) to the current syndromic surveillance system for human gastro-intestinal outbreaks. We compared several methods for outbreak prediction. A real-time pilot study was planned for spring/summer 2020 but had to be postponed due to COVID-19 crisis. A dashboard was developed for evaluating the possible usefulness and benefits of having this system running in real-time. ANSES worked on the development of detection algorithms which processed data from i) bovine sector (cattle mortality, *Salmonella* isolations in cattle, reports on cattle diseases), ii) food sector (*Salmonella* isolations in beef and dairy products) and iii) human health (number of human gastro-intestinal outbreaks).

WP4. Spatial risk mapping

WP4-T1- Identification of spatial relationships and patterns in Salmonella prevalence

WP4-T1-ST1- Surveillance in high prevalence regions to detect introduction and changes in prevalence.

The high prevalence region chosen for studies in this task was Spain. Surveillance data (animal, human and food) from national official sources have been recorded and spatially analysed to identify possible links between the main stakeholders to strength the surveillance efforts under the one health perspective.

Recorded surveillance information on human cases could only be linked to the administrative level NUTS 3. A descriptive analysis of the clinical data (hospital burden including hospitalization rates and case-fatality rates, costs, and risk factors) was performed to evaluate changes in the burden of the disease.

Recorded surveillance information on food could not be properly linked to their geographical location as that information was found missing in most cases. From the exploration of the surveillance sources, we concluded that even if food alerts were mainly in meat (particularly pork and poultry with a positive rate around 7%, *Salmonella*-related food-borne outbreaks were mainly related to eggs.

Recorded surveillance information on pigs (isolation and antimicrobial susceptibility typing of *Salmonella*) have been georeferenced and explored to identify a spatial pattern in the probability of isolation of *Salmonella*. Results suggested a West-East increasing risk of *Salmonella* infection in swine at the province level in Spain, with certain serotype-specific patterns differing (i.e., higher chance of retrieving certain serotypes in certain regions). Association of risk areas with human cases could not be explored because human data does not contain epidemiological information on the possible source of salmonellosis infection.

WP4-T1-ST2- Surveillance in low prevalence regions to reduce prevalence.

The task aimed to develop a disease spread model in the Swedish context (representing a low prevalence region), evaluate different surveillance options, and find direct risks for human salmonellosis using Danish data. *Salmonella* control has already begun since the 1960s in Sweden, including all serotypes and all animal species. The program gradually reduced the prevalence of *Salmonella* in Swedish cattle, with the number of cattle found in control programs since the mid-1990s maintained at a low but steady level. To assess potential surveillance strategies, both the within- and between-herd transmission dynamics of *S. Dublin* infection need to be considered. Within-herd transmission in dairy herds has been extensively studied but approaches to model the between-herd spread of this infection still lack in the literature. In this study, a two-stage transmission model for *S. Dublin* infections in dairy farms has been developed in the SimInf framework, which is suitable for evaluating the effectiveness of different surveillance strategies in a hypoendemic context. Alternative surveillance options (both traditional and risk-based) to detect infected herds have been evaluated deterministically using simulated disease data. Traditional surveillance could detect 25% of the infected herds after one year, while risk-based surveillance detected around 15% of the cases.

However, risk-based surveillance was economically more convenient, as it utilized one-third of the samples used by traditional surveillance. The task of finding direct risks for human salmonellosis using Danish data was delayed due to the difficulty in data sharing (the inability to share sensitive data between SVA and SSI and the inability to share data due to the COVID-19 between SVA and Swedish public health agency). For that reason, the goal of the task was partially modified to develop a method that can measure risks using the Swedish bulk milk screening data instead of human cases. The developed method allows to describe the spatial distribution of *S. Dublin* in Sweden and quantify associations between *S. Dublin*-positive herds and hypothesized risk factors. The spatial scan statistical analysis was adopted to evaluate the spatial clustering of *S. Dublin* and its temporal changes. To evaluate the effect of potential risk factors on the risk of *S. Dublin*, Bayesian regression models using the INLA-SPDE approach were developed. Two positive clustered areas were detected, which means that these areas are more likely to have high numbers of seropositive cattle to *S. Dublin* compared to other regions. These areas are characterized by slightly bigger herd size, high temperature, low precipitation, and fewer contacts with other herds. It remains unclear which factors may be risk factors for spreading *S. Dublin* infections between cattle herds. Human case data were not available to assess the direct risks for human salmonellosis, but the methodologies applicable to human cases have been sufficiently tested using animal data. The models and methods developed in this sub-task can be applied to other similar diseases or other regions.

WP4-T2- Risk of introduction of Salmonella in pig farms through animal feed.

The focus of this deliverable was changed from its original objective due to the decision to ban formaldehyde in the EU, which was the main scenario that was going to be addressed originally. Because of this, an alternative study, based on the assessment of the usefulness of surveillance AMR data for monitoring emergence of *Salmonella* strains of animal origin, was performed. Preliminary studies performed on resistance data determined in *Salmonella* strains from poultry demonstrated the usefulness of multivariate approaches to detect the emergence of AMR profiles ('resistotypes') that could be then used as targets of surveillance projects (Alvarez et al., 2019). These preliminary studies, conducted on isolates of poultry origin since a large strain panel was available, were further extended for the analysis of swine *Salmonella* strains collected between 2001 and 2017 and subjected to serotyping and antimicrobial susceptibility testing in the frame of the surveillance program for antimicrobial resistance in *Salmonella*.

The analysis carried out in a total of 1,318 pig strains belonging to 63 different serotypes included data on AMR to up to 12 different antimicrobials. Resistance data was analyzed using generalized estimating equations in order to assess the existence of trends in the proportion of resistance strain for each of the antimicrobial, and Bayesian network analysis and hierarchical clustering analysis in order to identify links between the presentation of specific patterns of resistance. Furthermore, the spatial distribution of strains presenting specific resistance patterns was analyzed through the use of empirical Bayesian smoothing methods to identify resistance-resistotype specific spatial patterns. The analyses revealed specific groups of phenotypic resistances that were typically presented simultaneously beyond the ones already expected (e.g., antimicrobials belonging to the same class such as nalidixic acid and ciprofloxacin). This suggests the existence of AMR markers that are probably associated in the bacterial genome, such as those found in *Salmonella* Genomic Island 1 (with resistant determinants to beta-lactams, phenicols, aminoglycosides, sulfonamides and tetracyclines). We found that certain serotypes were typically associated with such presentations, and had an uneven spatial distribution over the study period.

In addition, assistance in the development of an IT tool for spatial identification of soil vulnerability areas as regards antibiotic residues and resistances has been done.

WP4-T3- Role of the environment in the occurrence and maintenance of Salmonella infection in extensive farming.

Under this task *Salmonella* data in outdoor pigs and wild boar gathered from official surveillance plans in Spain were explored. Data were analysed and displayed in interactive maps to extend the exploration and interpretation of the *Salmonella* occurrence (story map).

To explore the role of wildlife, a cartographic map of hotspot areas for *Salmonella* transmission between wild boar and outdoor pigs was produced based on the extensive pig farm and wild boar density (updated map from Bosch et al, 2015). Spatial autocorrelation was analysed using the Getis and Ord statistical test. The weight of each variable was quantified through a sensitivity analysis (1,000 iterations, Monte Carlo method). The "Density of extensive pig farms" showed a greater influence (0.79) compared to "Density of wild boar" (0.41). Results did not reveal an association between hot spots and *Salmonella* in wild boar, probably due to the scarcity of *Salmonella* occurrence data in extensive pig farms (<1% of total extensive production in the country).

Machine learning algorithms have been implemented to evaluate whether data of *Salmonella* infected farms could be explained by environmental drivers such as temperature, humidity, precipitation or type of soil and vegetation. By using an existing modelling library ('tidymodels'), we were able to apply several machine learning models in one workflow. In particular, random forests and boosted regression trees were explored. Model outcomes were assessed using cross-validation techniques. The model was first successfully validated on surrogate data, and subsequently applied to intensive and extensive farming data. No clear link was identified between infected farms and environmental variables. In particular wild boar density was not identified as a driver. The likely explanation for the failure to detect risk-factors is that the intensive farming system is not affected by environmental factors, while the data on the extensive farming systems were too scarce. As a second case study, we applied the model to data on *Salmonella* infection in wild boar. Also here, no clear risk-factors could be identified, likely due to the small number of data points. Although the model has not yielded any clearly identified drivers, the developed framework is a valuable outcome that can be readily applied to other settings where there is an interest to correlate spatial absence/presence data on the occurrence of pathogens with environmental and climatic variables.

WP5. Evaluation of surveillance programs & cost efficiency

WP5-T1- Adapt infectious disease models for assessing the effect of surveillance programs in primary animal production on consumer exposure to foodborne pathogens.

This task has been addressed from several different perspectives including a focus on 1. development of model-based approaches to evaluate surveillance in primary production and 2. Models of disease surveillance in primary production that extend to include human exposure.

In the development work on evaluation of surveillance in primary production, methods were established whereby disease spread and surveillance could be simulated simultaneously to efficiently account for both temporally dynamic disease spread and compare various risk-based targeting methods and sampling intensity.

In the task, we worked on three different models:

1) To investigate the utility of these new methods, a model was established of the spread of *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *paratuberculosis* (MAP) in the Swedish cattle population. The model illustrated that the approach allowed to compare surveillance strategies on the standard scale of sensitivity of detection of the disease in the population, but also time to detection, cumulative hazard of detection and the number of herds infected at the time of detection. The method established a foundation to be able to model surveillance strategies and the subsequent downstream effects of interventions and how they could depress the prevalence of disease or the likelihood of disease extinction. In the example of MAP spread in Swedish cattle, the work also illustrated the concept that 'risk based' targeting of herds for surveillance is not always an effective strategy. The results indicate

that for MAP, sampling herds randomly resulted in faster detection compared to targeting herds biased towards those that purchase more animals (high in-degree). This finding may be related to the disease dynamics of MAP which is a very slow spreading disease and it is hypothesized that this form of risk based sampling would be more beneficial for a disease with a faster spread because the nodes with higher network centrality are more likely to become infected whereas with slow spread it is more valuable to utilize a strategy that values sampling of more unique herds (Rosendal et al., 2020). The new modelling methods have been made openly available to the community both through publication and sharing of open source developed tools under the GPL3 licence (<https://github.com/trosendal/paratb>).

2. The same modelling approach was also applied for modelling the *Salmonella* surveillance in Danish broiler production, with focus on the parent flocks. When a parent flock becomes infected, the infection can be transmitted vertically to the broiler flocks, before the parent flock is detected and destroyed, including the eggs at the hatchery. To address this issue, we developed a stochastic dynamic modelling of transmission of *Salmonella* in parent flocks and combined that with the relation between flock prevalence and test sensitivity for environmental samples in the flock. The model was used to investigate the power of the current and alternative sampling schedules. The results show that in the initial phase of spread of infection it is crucial to collect as much sample material as possible in the flocks to detect infection. The model was developed so that it gave parameter estimates relevant for the decision makers. In this case, the decision needs to be taken is that in a situation when a parent flock is detected as *Salmonella* positive, which eggs should be destroyed at the hatchery to avoid that *Salmonella* is transferred from the parent to the broiler flock. The parameter estimated as a response to this was the likelihood of infection of eggs at different ages in relation to the date when the flock was tested positive for *Salmonella* (Apenteng et al., 2020).

3. To explore the potential impact of a national control programme for *Salmonella* in pigs, a previously developed model for transmission of *Salmonella* in a breeder-finisher pig herd (Hill et al. 2016) was adapted to include surveillance. The surveillance consisted of quarterly pooled faecal sampling for *Salmonella* Typhimurium (ST) using a PCR test, and control measures were implemented on farms where the number of positive pools was above a specified threshold. To represent the national population of finisher pigs, the model was run many times, with the prevalence of breeding sows drawn from a probability distribution, this distribution being estimated from a Bayesian model applied to the 2008 EU baseline survey for breeding pigs. The model predicted the impact on the infection prevalence of ST in slaughter pigs for different thresholds of the number of positive pools for control of *Salmonella* on the farm to be implemented. It showed that the prevalence of ST in slaughter pigs in GB would be significantly reduced by targeting control on farms where there were 5 positive pools (out of 5).

WP5-T2- Assessing the effect of using metagenomics in surveillance of foodborne zoonoses.

Traditionally, the surveillance of foodborne zoonotic antimicrobial resistance is based on phenotypic testing of indicator and zoonotic bacteria isolated in the food production chain. The procedure is that samples are collected at different steps in the production line. The presence of antimicrobial resistance has then been investigated both in zoonotic bacteria such as *Salmonella*, and in indicator bacteria such as *E. coli* and *Enterobacter* using different cultivation methods (e.g. MIC).

During the last years, the technological development in sequencing of genetic material directly in the sample matrix, gives the opportunity to investigate the total genetic material of a mixed community of organisms in a sample matrix, such as faecal or environmental samples - metagenomics. Thereby, we can investigate both cultivatable and uncultivatable microorganisms. Metagenomics is a molecular tool used to analyse the mixed genomic materials extracted from environmental samples, which provides quantitative information about presence of genes, including genes coding for antimicrobial resistance (AMR).

In this task we have focused on the surveillance of AMR in the pig production using metagenomics, and how this can be utilised in a national surveillance program with the aim to detect newly introduced AMR and to detect significant increase or decrease in AMR widespread in the pig population.

The modelling approach in this task is similar to the approach in task 1, in the way that we simulate the spread and occurrence of AMR genes in the population. In addition to this, we integrate how pooling of samples and stochastic variation in the sequencing procedure influenced the surveillance data.

The output of the simulation model is counts per million (CPM) of the gene(s) of interest detected per million gene fragment sequenced in a matrix, and the interpretation is on population level. The limit of detection of a gene is 1 count, but because the number of gene fragments sequenced per sample (sequencing depth) is varying, the limit of detection is varying between analyses. The output from the model depends on i) the actual occurrence of the gene(s) in the population (farm prevalence, within farm prevalence), the concentration of the gene(s) in the animal (in the simulation we collect faecal samples), numbers of sample collected at each time of sampling and pooled, and sequence depth used for the pooled sample. The model has a stochastic nature, taking into account variation due to sampling and sequencing depth. To model the increase in the occurrence of the gene(s) in the population by time, we used a Susceptible-Infected (SI) model describing the spread between farms.

The input parameters describing the occurrence of gene(s) were based on existing data from research studies and expert.

The number of samples collected, pooling and sequencing depth are variables we can decide in the design of the surveillance. Different scenarios were simulated mimicking realistic scenarios for these variables.

The output data from the model represents surveillance data. The surveillance data was compared to the true status in the population (given as input parameters describing the occurrence of the gene(s) in the population). The comparison was done both retrospectively, using time-series analysis to calculate the time between true increase of occurrence and detected increase of occurrence, and prospectively, forecasting the occurrence based on surveillance data, and compared that with the true future (given as the input parameter in the model).

The overall results from the modelling, shows that an increased occurrence of AMR gene(s) was difficult to detect during the initial stage of increase (either after introduction or after increase in the occurrence of already present AMR-genes). The major reason for lack of detection in the earlier stage was that the collected samples did not contain the gene(s). An increased number of samples that is pooled and a simultaneously increase in the sequencing depth could partly reduce the time gap. When the increase in occurrence took place in a low rate, were it takes 5-10 years before all farms has the gene, to keep the time gap between introduction and detection short, relatively more samples in the pool and increased sequencing depth are needed compared to a gene with a faster increase in occurrence.

The application of forecasting algorithms shows that it is possible to forecast the occurrence of AMR-genes in the population, but the precision is varying depending on several factors such as the dynamics of the spread and variability due to sampling.

WP5-T3- Modelling the effect of surveillance programs in the food production on human health.

Risk based sampling in the retail phase

The risk-based sampling approach focuses on the question how to subdivide sampling capacity the best in order to monitor as much disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) as possible. The basic idea is that sampling for those pathogen-product combinations is preferred, for which surveillance is cheapest in terms of costs / DALYs monitored. In this study we focus on *Salmonella* in pig meat in the retail phase. Costs per sample refer to microbiological analysis. The number of samples is set using the criterion of a constant relative uncertainty of estimated pathogen prevalence. The number of DALYS is estimated using an overall pathogen-food animal value, which is subdivided over products using exposure assessment estimates. Risk based sampling methodology was applied to France, United Kingdom, Denmark, Sweden and The Netherlands and this led to two improvements in the methodology, so that the number of food product categories and the number of inhabitants of a

country can be taken into account. Ranking of food product groups in terms of costs / DALYs monitored was performed for the respective countries both separately and in combination.

Cost-effectiveness of sampling in the retail phase

We also explored a method to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of product testing in the pre-retail and retail phase, by food industry and the government, respectively, related to food product withdrawal. The criterion is here costs / DALYs evaded. We focused again on *Salmonella* in pig meat. Costs refer to microbiological analysis, and the number of samples taken as reported. The effect includes a positive effect on public health, expressed in DALYs, as batches with a positive test will not reach the consumer, or will be heat-treated first. Cost-effectiveness can be compared with a criterion set by WHO. This comparison indicates that the short-term effect of product testing is not cost-effective, the more since it is suspected that the present calculations give too favourable an estimate. On the other hand, uncertainty of the calculations is large. We did not incorporate the long-term effect of product testing on hygiene performance of food industry, which is difficult to quantify.

Cost-effectiveness of sampling in the farm phase

We explored a method to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of surveillance in the farm phase, focusing on *Salmonella* in pigs, and applying it to The Netherlands and Great Britain. The criterion is costs / DALYs evaded. Costs refer to the number of samples taken, and the costs of microbiological analysis per sample. To calculate DALYs evaded, it is assumed that pig meat from *Salmonella* test-positive farms does not reach the consumer. It is calculated as a decrease in *Salmonella* prevalence at animal level as a result of surveillance, which is carried through the slaughterhouse- and consumer phase to result in a reduction of DALYs.

It is shown that cost-effectiveness is independent of the number of farms sampled, and decreases with the number of samples taken per farm. Cost-effectiveness is more favourable (lower) for GB than for The Netherlands, 4.78E3 and 8.70E3 euros/DALY, respectively, for comparable scenarios. Both the costs and the DALYs evaded are higher for GB, being a larger country, but DALYs evaded with a higher factor than costs. It must be stressed, however, that the calculations have a high uncertainty.

Cost-effectiveness of sampling in the farm phase is much more favourable than in the (pre-)retail phase, being about 8.5E3 euro's/DALY vs 6.08E4 or 2.26E5 euro's/DALY (depending on sampling system)(Evers et al., 2020). The value of 8.5E3 euros/DALY is also lower than 4.6E4 euros/DALY, the standard value set by WHO for cost-effectiveness of an intervention (WHO Europe, 2014).

Additional data collection and conceptual model improvement will increase reliability of the calculation results.

3. Project Self-assessment

Main objectives initially proposed have been accomplished. We have had a collaborative partnership with several new collaborations initiated between veterinary and medicine institutes within countries, as well as between countries. A number of novel tools have been developed, both for research and surveillance (model scripts) and dissemination (story map). Improvement of operational surveillance systems in human health were obtained by adding surveillance components relative to animal health and to environmental conditions.

COVID-19

One of the main problems that occurred during the project period was the COVID-19 pandemic. The project was formed to include partners from both animal and public health and from several member states. We were happy to create such a diverse group, but many experts and researchers in NOVA had never worked together before the start of the project. Therefore, it took some time before all participants understood and agreed on the practical implementation of all tasks and subtasks in the project plan. In the second year, work started to speed up, but when the pandemic hit many tasks slowed down and it was a serious disturbance to the project. Well-established everyday working

routines were altered, face-to-face meetings were not possible, and many experts, especially in the public health institutes, had to prioritise work tasks directly related to COVID-19. The extension of the project into 2021 helped us finish our deliverables but did not fully compensate for the impaired connection in our newly formed network. However, many new links have been created and there are several ideas about how we can capture potential synergies between work that we did and plan for that future, and how we can continue our collaboration.

Data access and quality

Several WPs encountered difficulties to access data and share data between institutions, also within country, due to confidentiality, budget, slow retrieval processes, or data ownership issues. These difficulties were not a surprise, in fact data access was already a focus in our WPs. These obstacles were handled in different ways, for example by aggregating data or changing to another disease of interest. This was not necessarily a problem, as the focus of NOVA has been the epidemiological methods, not one specific disease. However, aggregation of data leads to a loss of information and in a few tasks (in WP4 and WP5), the difficulty or slow process to share human case data resulted in less multidisciplinary outcomes. To compensate for this we have chosen to build tools and models that are general enough to be used for other diseases and data. One approach has been to include synthetic human case data in a model framework, so that the model is fully developed and ready to use once real data are available. In WP2, progress to access large food consumer data was made, but was later withdrawn.

In WP3 problems of data quality were encountered when setting up systems for using secondary data for surveillance. Specific collaborations had to be built with the data owners to improve the usability of their data for an objective of surveillance.

Other deviations and/or problems encountered:

One challenge that appeared already at the start of the project related to the work on one health terminology (WP1, T1). We soon found out that similar work was planned in other OHEJP projects and in the beginning it was unclear how this overlap should be handled. After discussion we concluded that we wanted to avoid any double work, and that it made sense to contribute to one glossary. The ORION project had a glossary with a broader scope in their plan, and in the end, ORION took full lead in this work. The involvement of NOVA and role in the collaborative work was negotiated and focused on terms related specifically to surveillance.

Deliverable 4.6. was replaced because of changes of legislation in the product that was going to be evaluated (formaldehyde). Alternatively, studies on the use of surveillance AMR data for monitoring emergence of *Salmonella* strains in swine were conducted.

In WP5 task 1, the transmission model for *Salmonella* in pigs was originally intended to be a between-herd transmission model. However, **staff departures and delays to recruitment** meant that we had to adapt an existing within herd transmission model. This meant that we had to restrict the evaluation of control measures to finisher pigs, rather than also considering breeding herds.

In WP task 2, **no historical samples were available** that could be re-analysed using new sequencing methods and therefore it was not possible to conduct a comparison based on true emerging health problems in the human population and if it would have been possible to detect it the food production before it became a human health issue. Instead, the task was utilising simulation techniques to estimate how quick an emerging problem can be detected in the primary production.

4. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
06	D-JRP6-0.1	Documentation of consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	3	3		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497264#.YTsQwp0zY-U Available on OHEJP	8 (meeting documentation)
06	D-JRP6-0.2	Documentation of consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	20	20		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497532#.YTsQip0zY-U Available on OHEJP	8 (meeting documentation)
06	D-JRP6-0.3	Documentation of consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	35	35		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497307#.YTsRLZ0zY-U Available on OHEJP	8 (meeting documentation)
06	D-JRP6-0.4	Documentation of consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	42	45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5499696#.YTsPCRIxd3g Available on OHEJP	8 (meeting documentation)
06	D-JRP6-1.1	Glossary of terms based on a common food borne zoonosis surveillance	24	24		Public https://zenodo.org/record/3734079#.XoL5Clgza70 Available on OHEJP	1, 8 (glossary)

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8)</i> <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
		terminology					
06	D-JRP6-1.2	Mapping of food chain surveillance across countries	41	42		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5045224#.YQ5754gzZPY Available on OHEJP	1, 8 (interviews)
06	D-JRP6-2.1	Description by member state of data sources, agreements and organisations (e.g. retailer chains).	10	12		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497406#.YTsoexldPY Available on OHEJP	
06	D-JRP6-2.2	Description by member state of barriers for use: legal, political, economic, practical and technical obstacles.	24	24		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497418#.YTszSJ0zY-U Available on OHEJP	
06	D-JRP6-2.3	Structured review of the field.	5	5		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497396#.YTszhp0zY-U Available on OHEJP	
06	D-JRP6-2.5	Description of data infrastructure module, including an electronic informed consent tool <i>(Original title: Data infrastructure built, electronic informed</i>	12	12		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497425#.YTszCp0zY-U Available on OHEJP	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		consent tool in function.)					
06	D-JRP6-2.6	Case control study of food risk factors for sporadic <i>Salmonella</i> infections. (Formerly: Case control study of food risk factors for sporadic <i>Campylobacter</i> infections)	42	45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5500418#.YTt8-hlxd3g Available on OHEJP Deadline pushed forward as part of extension of the project	
06	D-JRP6-2.4	Simulation analyses to assess the use of consumer purchase data as an analytical tool for outbreak investigations (Formerly: Assessment of the use of the method as an analytical tool, rather than merely hypothesis-generation)	42	45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5500406#.YTt78Rlxd3g Available on OHEJP Due to the COVID-19 outbreak and the impact that has had on the possibilities of the SSI to engage in large population studies, this project may need to be redefined. Also, work has been paused throughout the spring of 2020, because the researchers involved have been moved to work on the COVID-19 response exclusively. We would like to propose to move the deliverable and the corresponding milestone (they are part of the same project) to the end of the new project period, i.e. Month 42	4, 7, 9

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8)</i> <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
06	D-JRP6-2.10	FoodChain-Lab web application: Description and documentation of software, development of tutorials and training material <i>(Formerly: Description and documentation of software, development of tutorials and training material)</i>	42	45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497431#.YTsVWJ0zY-U Available on OHEJP Deadline pushed forward as part of extension of the project	
06	D-JRP6-2.8	Epidemiological analysis of existing surveillance data regarding ha-FBO and foods involved.	10	12		Confidential Available on OHEJP, NOVA private group only	
06	D-JRP6-2.9	Studies using the German results extended to the partner institutes.	24	24		Confidential Available on OHEJP, NOVA private group only	
06	D-JRP6-3.1	Full mapping of the chain process for three main productions in E.U	8	8		Public https://zenodo.org/record/3734082#.XoL5b4gza70 Available on OHEJP	1
06	D-JRP6-3.2	Data inventory with assessment of	10	10		Public https://zenodo.org/record/3734084#.XoL5q4gza70	1

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		availability, quality and fitness for SS				Available on OHEJP	
06	D-JRP-3.3	Description of the SS components implemented and guidelines for their use	24	24		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497514#.YTsXGZ0zY-U Available on OHEJP	1,4
06	D-JRP6-3.4	Recommendations about the quality standardisation of data produced across the food chain for their use in SyS ()	30	30		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497473#.YTsYyp0zY-U Available on OHEJP	1, 4
06	D-JRP6-3.5	Contribution of multiple syndromic surveillance components in the FBD surveillance	42	42		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497483#.YTsUx50zY-U Available on OHEJP Due to the COVID-19 crisis, NIPH employs two-part time workers for working on NOVA since December 2020.	4,5
06	D-JRP6-4.1.	Maps for <i>Salmonella</i> prevalence geographical patterns in intensive livestock and slaughterhouses completed in high prevalence regions	12	12		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497488#.YTsUpZ0zY-U Available on OHEJP	5,6

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
06	D-JRP6-4.2.	Identification of periods with higher probability of detection of infection identified in high prevalence regions and temporal evidences for an association with human cases	24	24		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497506#.YTsuDz0zY-U Available on OHEJP	5,6
06	D-JRP6-4.3.	Assessment of the spatio-temporal infection dynamics model in <i>Salmonella</i> in low prevalence regions.	12	M12		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497494#.YTstA50zY-U Available on OHEJP	5,6
06	D-JRP6-4.4.	Assessment of the spatio-temporal infection dynamics model of <i>Salmonella</i> in low prevalence regions – Evaluation of optimal surveillance strategies	24 (part1), 36 (part2)	24 (part1), 36 (part2)		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5499762#.YTsgjhlxeMp Available on OHEJP	5,6
06	D-JRP6-4.5.	Characterization of the spatial network structure of the pig industry in a Mediterranean scenario	24	36		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497518#.YTstQ50zY-U Available on OHEJP	5,6

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		and <i>Salmonella</i> data mapped and analysed.					
06	D-JRP6-4.6.	Assessment of the potential effect of the withdrawal of the use of formaldehyde-based feed treatments done	42	42		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497496#.YTstAZ0zY-U Focus changed to: Assessment of the usefulness of antimicrobial susceptibility test results for the optimization of surveillance programs for <i>Salmonella</i> of swine origin	5,6
06	D-JRP6-4.7.	<i>Salmonella</i> data in extensive farming in Mediterranean scenario mapped and analysed.	12	12		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497498#.YTstS1J0zY-U Available on OHEJP	5,6
06	D-JRP6-4.8.	Cartographic map of hot spot areas for <i>Salmonella</i> transmission between wild boars and low biosecurity systems.	24	24		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497504#.YTstSLz0zY-U Available on OHEJP	5,6
06	D-JRP6-4.9.	Potential new environmental surveillance indicators identified.	42	42		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497471#.YTstSZJ0zY-U Available on OHEJP	5,6
06	D-JRP6-5.1	Report comparing performance of surveillance strategies	42	45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497957#.YTstSLp0zY-U Available on OHEJP	1, 5, 7, 9

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						D-JRP6-5.1 - Report comparing performance of surveillance strategies” and “D-JRP6-5.2 - Recommendations for metrics to evaluate surveillance performance, will be joined into one deliverable. Deadline after extension of the project is M42 (36+6).	
06	D-JRP6-5.2	Recommendations for metrics to evaluate surveillance performance	42	45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497957#.YTSSLp0zY-U Available on OHEJP D-JRP6-5.1 - Report comparing performance of surveillance strategies” and “D-JRP6-5.2 - Recommendations for metrics to evaluate surveillance performance, will be joined into one deliverable. Deadline after extension of the project is M42 (36+6).	1, 5, 7, 9
06	D-JRP6-5.3	An assessment of the public health effects of very different surveillance strategies to detect emerging foodborne infections in a MS or at European level.	42	45		Due to lag in recruitment this activity started later than first planned	2, 5, 9
06	D-JRP6-5.4	Report assessing the quantitative effect on	42	42		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497485#.YTsrX50zY-U	5, 6

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8)</i> <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
		human health of changing surveillance capacity across different sources in an MS				Available on OHEJP Deadline pushed forward as part of extension of the project.	
06	D-JRP6-5.5	A practical risk based sampling approach that combines exposure to zoonoses with disease burden and costs for sampling at a European level.	42	42		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497451#.YTzRe50zY-U Available on OHEJP Deadline pushed forward as part of extension of the project.	1, 5, 6

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify); 9. This is supportive to an integrative activity; 10. This is not an integrative activity

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.1	Consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	2	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.2	Meeting for information exchange (data, literature, data bases) exchange on exposure assessment, DALY's, consumption data and food handling at home	6	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.3	Food Chain mapping completed, data sources identification advanced, and ready to start developing the SS components	7	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.4	Pilot, data availability.	9	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.5	Case-study choice	9	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.6	Surveillance strategies to implement into the models agreed	12	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.7	Basic model describing models describing spread of emerging zoonoses in immunological naïve animal population established	12	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.8	SOP, best practice description.	16	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.9	Development of method to handle time and GTIN.	17	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.10	Prospectively calculation of disease association measures and retrospective analysis of food consumption patterns in hospitals.	24	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.11	complete specification of the infectious disease models	18	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.12	Submodels to be integrated in the model framework identified and coded in common language	18	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.13	Consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	19	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.14	SS components developed and tested	22	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.15	Glossary of surveillance terminology for foodborne surveillance is disseminated.	24	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.16	Result reporting on the spatio-temporal patterns of infection distribution in intensive pig farms, slaughterhouses and human cases in high prevalence regions and evidences for an association between them.	24	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.17	Result reporting on the spatio-temporal patterns of infection distribution in intensive pig farms, slaughterhouses and human cases in low prevalence regions and evaluation of optimal surveillance strategies.	24	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.18	Result reporting on hot spot areas for <i>Salmonella</i> transmission between wild boars and low biosecurity systems.	30	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.19	The model parts to detect emerging pathogens in the food-chain and detecting human cases, respectively implemented in the model.	24	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.20	Interim report for a practical risk based sampling approach that combines exposure to zoonoses with disease burden and costs for sampling at a European level.	24	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.21	Integration into FoodChain-Lab, release as cloud service.	27	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.22	Case control study of food risk factors for sporadic <i>Salmonella</i> infections.	40	Yes		Due to the COVID-19 outbreak and the impact that has had on the possibilities of the SSI to engage in large population studies, this project may need to be redefined. Also, work has been paused throughout the spring of 2020, because the researchers involved have been moved

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
						to work on the COVID-19 response exclusively. We would like to propose to move the deliverable and the corresponding milestone (they are part of the same project) to the end of the new project period, i.e. Month 40
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.23	surveillance layer added to models	30	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.24	A dynamic modelling layer of surveillance is overlaid the submodels	30	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.25	initial set of results circulated to project team	36	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.26	Consortium assembly and steering committee meeting	34	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.27	Integration of multiple sources developed and tested	36	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.28	Result reporting on risk of <i>Salmonella</i> introduction in pig farms by animal feed and the potential effect of the withdrawal of the use of formaldehyde-based feed treatments.	42	Yes		
06	M-FBZ1.NOVA.29	Result reporting on new environmental surveillance indicators.	42	Yes		

5. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Identifying emerging trends in antimicrobial resistance using <i>Salmonella</i> surveillance data in poultry in Spain. TBDE, 67(1):250-262. DOI: 10.1111/tbed.13346 https://zenodo.org/record/3660026#.XvyQnGzZM0	YES		Yes (processing fees: 3750€)
Climatic and topographic tolerance limits of wild boar in Eurasia: Implications for their expansion. Geography, Environment, Sustainability, 13(1):107-114. https://doi.org/10.24057/2071-9388-2019-52 https://zenodo.org/record/4244729#.X6LYN4hKjcc	YES		YES (no processing fee)
Spatial trends in <i>Salmonella</i> infection in pigs in Spain. Frontiers in veterinary science. In Press. (A). ISSN: 2297-1769. DOI: 10.3389/fvets.2020.00345 https://zenodo.org/record/4244797#.X6Li_lhKjcc	YES		YES, processing fee 2048 € (2490 USD)
An outbreak of monophasic <i>Salmonella</i> Typhimurium associated with raw pork sausage and other pork products, Denmark 2018–19 https://zenodo.org/record/4249319#.X6UIWmhKjcc	YES		YES (no processing fee for this publication)
Analysis of consumer food purchase data used for outbreak investigations, a review https://zenodo.org/record/3747633#.XpCQ_sgzZM0	YES		YES (no processing fee)

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Non-Typhi, non-Paratyphi <i>Salmonella</i> related hospitalisations in Spain: trends, comorbidities, risk factors for worse prognosis and hospital costs. 10.1007/s10096-018-3433-1 https://zenodo.org/record/4244788#.X6LhGYhKjcc	YES	YES Embargo length = 24 months Manuscript release date = 20 November 2018	
<i>Salmonella</i> Surveillance Systems in Swine and Humans in Spain: A Review. 10.3390/vetsci6010020 https://zenodo.org/record/3635293#.XjlyUGhKhPY	YES		YES (no processing fee)
Using stochastic dynamic modelling to estimate the sensitivity of current and alternative surveillance program of <i>Salmonella</i> in conventional broiler production 10.1038/s41598-020-76514-3 https://zenodo.org/record/4271431#.X65ljTiWxPY	YES		YES, processing fee 1570€
Modelling spread and surveillance of Mycobacterium avium subsp. paratuberculosis in the Swedish cattle trade network https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2020.105152 https://zenodo.org/record/4450338	YES		YES, processing fee 2837€ (3450 USD), excluding taxes
A one health glossary to support communication and information exchange between the human health, animal health and food safety sectors. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.onehlt.2021.100263 https://zenodo.org/record/4769914#.YT9EEp0za70	YES		YES (no processing fee)
What motivates and prevents Swedish veterinarians reporting disease suspicions?	YES	Not yet published	Not yet published

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Manuscript in preparation by Oliviera V.H.S., Ågren E.C.C., Frössling J., and Nöremark M. Part of D-JRP6-1.2			

Additional output

The OHEJP glossary is available at the ORION project knowledge hub:

<https://aginfra.d4science.org/web/orionknowledgehub/>

STORY MAP: <https://arcgis.com/1zHSub>. Summary of main outputs, available online.

SCRIPT REPOSITORY: <https://github.com/SVA-SE/NOVA>. Contains code to explore disease surveillance options in a low prevalence setting of *Salmonella* Dublin in cattle.

SCRIPT REPOSITORY: soon available. Contains code to evaluate whether data of *Salmonella* infected farms could be explained by environmental drivers.

Boone I., Wilking H., Eckmanns T., Stark K., Ethelberg S. and Haller S. (2019). Healthcare-associated foodborne outbreaks in OECD countries and a special focus on Germany: current status. 1st Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Foodborne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats (22nd-24th May 2019, Dublin, Ireland). Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/5244658>

Cha, W., Dórea, F., Grøneng, G.M., Rø, G., Hopp, P., Jonsson, M., Dryselius, R. Development of One Health syndromic surveillance for *Campylobacter* in Norway and Sweden. In: Proceedings of the 2nd Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Foodborne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats; May 27-29, 2020; Online meeting.

Gustafsson, W., Andersson, M.G. Designing multivariate syndromic surveillance for animal diseases in Sweden. In: Proceedings of the 2nd Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Foodborne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats; May 27-29, 2020; Online meeting.

De la Torre, A; Rodriguez, A; Álvarez, J; Teng, K; Swart, A; Kim H; Beninca, E. Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost-effective surveillance across the food chain: a story map. ESRI conference. 21-22 october 2020. Madrid, Spain. Online meeting.

Iglesias, M. Martínez, J. Álvarez, K. Teng, A. de la Torre. Spatial distribution and temporal trends for *Salmonella* in pork and humans (2010-2015). I Congreso Virtual de la Sociedad Española de Epidemiología (SEE) y da Associação Portuguesa de Epidemiologia (APE), 21-30 Octubre 2020. Online meeting.

Boone I., D'Errico M. L., Iannetti L., Scavia G., Tozzoli R., Ethelberg S., Eckmanns T., Stark K., Wilking H. and Haller S. (2020). Electronic data on food served in healthcare facilities in Italy and Germany. Feasibility evaluation to support investigations of healthcare associated foodborne outbreaks. 2nd Annual Scientific Meeting of the One Health European Joint Programme on Foodborne Zoonoses, Antimicrobial Resistance and Emerging Threats (Prague, Czech Republic) (27th – 29th May, Online Meeting). Oral communication. <https://zenodo.org/record/5244713>

Iannetti, L., Boone I., D'Errico M.L., D'Orsi F., Ricchiuti L., Centorotola G., Pomilio F. and Cornacchia A. (2021). Foodborne outbreaks surveillance in hospitals and nursery homes: investigation on catering data. 14th European Public Health Conference (Dublin, Republic of Ireland, 20th-21st November 2021, online meeting). Poster. <https://ephconference.eu/programme-at-a-glance-83>. Abstract reference S202100519

Boone I., D'Errico M L., Iannetti L., Ethelberg S., Eckmanns T., Rosner B., Stark K., Haller S., Wilking H. (2021). Training for the Public Health Service in Germany. Healthcare-associated food-borne outbreaks. 24–26 March 2021, Online meeting. Oral communication. <https://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/oegd-2021-programm.pdf>

Boone I., D'Errico M L., Scavia G., Tozzoli R., Iannetti L., Haller S., Wilking H. Nova Project: results of the study in German Hospitals and Nursing homes. Scavia G., D'Errico M.L., Cattaneo C., Anniballi F., Tozzoli R., Boone I., Iannetti L. (2021). Workshop for healthcare practitioners: foodborne outbreak preparedness in healthcare settings. Rome, Online Workshop, 19 March 2021. Oral Presentation

Outcomes

We suggest that project outcomes are shared through the NOVA Story Map. Story maps are ideal for dissemination of main achievements to national and international stakeholders and citizens, providing an interactive interface to bring them knowledge through a user-friendly and easy way. It could be published on the OHEJP twitter account.

Most of the modelling tools (scripts) developed in NOVA are based on freeware and available through open script repositories (see Additional output above).

Deliverables have been and will be shared with **national governments** and **private stakeholder**, specifically with the data owners who shared the data to feed the analysis. In some cases they have been involved in data and results discussion and appears as co-authors of the scientific publications generated.

- Within NOVA, **Anses** explored several data sources regarding *Salmonella* detection in farm animals, food and humans in France. We developed a combination of several algorithms and tools for result visualization that will be transmitted to data owners in order to improve their surveillance systems (2022). The interest of such algorithms is discussed with the **National Platform for Animal Health Surveillance (ESA)** and the Health monitoring platform for the Food Supply Chain (SCA).
- **Swedish Board of Agriculture**. Our models and methods have been used as effective tools for the national surveillance plan that is adopted by the Swedish Board of Agriculture based on recommendations from SVA
- **Animal health organizations**; Växa Sverige and Gård & Djurhälsan (Sweden)
- **Dutch ministry of public health, welfare & sports, Dutch wildlife health center and centre for monitoring of vectors**
- **Spanish Agriculture Ministry**
- **Spanish Health Ministry**
- **Junta de Andalucía, Spain**
- **French surveillance networks on animal health (ESA) and on food safety (SCA)**. Results from NOVA on *Salmonella* surveillance has been transferred to the ESA and SCA networks. Further works will follow.
- **Ministry of Environment and Food of Denmark**. NOVA results used in prediction or the occurrence of AMR in Danish pig production when altering the AMU.
- **Danish National Food Authorities**. As a response to the work done in WP5 task 1 about *Salmonella* in poultry production, the Danish national food authorities have in cooperation with the industry revised the legislation about how to handle *Salmonella* in both the parental and the production part of the production. Three executive orders has been revised based on the output from the research:
 - Control of *Salmonella* in slaughter poultry
 - Control of *Salmonella* in hatching egg production
 - Control of *Salmonella* in the production of eggs for consumption

- **Meat industry and Food Safety Authority, the Netherlands.** The use of the Cost-effectiveness measured as [DALY/Euro] for evaluating the performance of surveillance of foodborne diseases (and other diseases) in the food chain (more precisely the retail phase) was discussed with meat industry and food safety authority in the Netherlands.
- Story map link was shared with **EFSA** after the second annual meeting. We have also had contact with EFSA's Advisory Forum Task Force on Data Collection and Data Modelling

6. One Health Impact

Overall summary of One Health impact

The project contains cultivation of new methods as well as more efficient utilisation of existing data and methods. It offers ideas for direct surveillance tools, but also for tools directed towards evaluation of surveillance systems. The tools and methods are primarily developed with a focus on the currently most important/frequent zoonotic diseases but may also be adapted to control other hazards or emerging agents.

The surveillance of consumer purchase patterns is currently non-existent in Europe. Results from WP2 shows that this genuinely new surveillance approach is potentially valuable and cost-effective. The methods/tools for surveillance of food exposures and trace-back developed, includes tools that presently do not exist anywhere in the world (WP2).

This project's development and combination of syndromic surveillance systems, machine-learning methods, and use of new data sources, is a first bridge across the Med-Vet gap in the syndromic surveillance context (WP3).

Understanding the geographical transmission of diseases is a cornerstone in epidemiology, yet surprisingly rarely used in surveillance practise – the focus on spatial mapping and analysis will provide better possibilities for actual utilisation in the zoonotic disease community (WP4). It will be possible to apply developed models or analytical methods cross-over to other diseases or objects (different animal species or human).

Mathematical modelling is another cornerstone of modern disease transmission understanding that we are now using to find ways to actually measure surveillance performance, and thereby be able to compare the cost-efficiency of different surveillance strategies, considering potential disease spread across the food chain (WP5).

Finally, our mapping of available data sources and identification of surveillance key actors across the food chain, including the underlying reasons for sub-optimal surveillance, should help clarify surveillance structures and challenges across the EU. Moreover, the development of a One Health glossary is useful in promoting communication between different sectors (WP1).

Specific impact points

- The identification and reporting of barriers and opportunities in food-borne disease surveillance from a One Health point of view is the result of a research performed for the first time using a scientific methodology (WP1). This information is already requested from national authorities (e.g. Belgium, Sweden, France), while other projects have contacted WP1 members for collaboration and consultation on similar or following tasks (e.g. Matrix).
- Within NOVA, Anses has explored several data sources regarding *Salmonella* detection in farm animals, food and humans in France. We developed a combination of several algorithms and tools for result visualization that will be transmitted to data owners (National Authorities, National Laboratories and private stakeholders) in order to improve their surveillance systems. Specific detection algorithms that can process temporal signals from correlated time series simultaneously are under development. The interest of such algorithms will be discussed with

the National Platform for Animal Health Surveillance (ESA) and the Health monitoring platform for the Food Supply Chain (SCA) in France.

- Methods developed in NOVA WP3 are also used in a national *Campylobacter* project in Sweden. One of the aims for this project is to assess the temporal correlation between *Campylobacter* surveillance data in broilers and human campylobacteriosis incidence.
- In Norway, we made a One Health surveillance based on the use of gastrointestinal consultations in human (NorSySS) and *Campylobacter* surveillance data from broiler flocks. We combined the data sources with weather data to improve detection and prediction of outbreaks. The NorSySS data was already in daily use for syndromic surveillance for people in Norway and any improvements found can be implemented in the day-to-day surveillance activities. The website and the models will continue to live beyond the OHEJP NOVA project and also be extended further in the OHEJP MATRIX project.
- Analyses carried out in task 4.1 will help to assess the reliability of the current surveillance system to capture the underlying variability in terms of serotypes and antimicrobial resistance for *Salmonella* strains recovered from swine. This can help to assess the power of the sample to describe the spatio-temporal epidemiology of *Salmonella* infection in a high prevalence area (Spain) in swine, and to identify factors associated with the emergence of specific serotypes/strains in specific areas/farms/production systems in the country but not others.
- Defra (UK) have plans to consider a national control programme (NCP) for *Salmonella* in pigs. The models built as part of WP5 for the simulation of surveillance strategies in pigs will be useful for evaluating options for such an NCP. The model and its results have been presented to Defra. Part of the modelling for *Salmonella* in pigs required Bayesian estimates of pig slaughter prevalence, derived from abattoir surveys – these estimates were useful for another EU project (COMPARE), for the source attribution task.
- The Danish Veterinary and Food Administration and the Danish poultry industry has based on the results from the model developed in WP5-task1, decided about strategies for destroying eggs at the hatcheries after detection of *Salmonella* in parent flock, including compensation to the producer. The Danish poultry industry is pioneering industry for controlling *Salmonella* in the poultry sector.
- The work conducted in WP5 T2 is a part of the ongoing revision of surveillance of AMR in the Danish animal and food production (DANMAP). In the future, this surveillance will be based on metagenomics rather than cultivation, that is used today. Thereby the approach and opportunities for collection of samples will be changed. The integration of the surveillance in the animal and food production will increase the opportunity to get the food production more integrated with other sectors of the One Health concept.
- In Sweden, output from NOVA has been used to support the Swedish Board of Agriculture and the animal health organisations in their work to adapt surveillance activities and Swedish legislation to the new Animal Health Law within the EU. The models have been used to support decisions about the target confidence level of future surveillance and to compare surveillance alternatives (e.g. different sample size, sample type, frequency of testing).
- As a response to the work done in WP5 task 1 about *Salmonella* in poultry production, the Danish national food authorities have in cooperation with the industry revised the legislation about the monitoring and management of *Salmonella* in both the parental and the production part of the poultry production.
- Calculations showed that sampling in the veterinary (farm) phase is much more cost-effective (DALY/Euro) than in the retail phase, given that the sampling result has consequences in terms of animal/product withdrawal.

JRP07-FBZ2-LISTADAPT

1. Summary of the work carried out

The LISTADAPT project aims to decipher the molecular mechanisms of adaptation seen in *Listeria monocytogenes* (Lm) to its various ecological niches by comparing both phenotypic and genotypic data from a large, balanced set of strains from human clinical cases, animals, food and environments in several European countries. With 21 partner institutes from public health, veterinary health, food and environment laboratories, the project compiled a dataset of 1575 Lm strains and their genomes. These strains were collected from 20 European countries, which ensured that the dataset was representative of the large number of clonal complexes (i) occurring worldwide (ii) covering many diverse habitats (iii) balanced between ecological niches and geographical regions. The aim of this dataset is to contribute to the understanding of Lm and improve surveillance, therefore it was important to make all of this information available to the scientific community (it has been submitted to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)).

Of the 1575 strains collected, a subset of 200 was selected from 33 clonal complexes known to be the most prevalent in Europe, with a balance between three ecological niches: environment, animal and food. Phenotypic tests were performed on these strains to investigate the strain's ability to survive in soil and subsequently the strains were categorised into three groups depending on survival. No source and no clonal complex were specifically associated to soil fitness. These 200 strains showed the same growth kinetics at pH 7 while there was more variation at pH 5.4. The deviating strains belonged to different CC groups and niches. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing also played a significant role in the LISTADAPT project with 11 antibiotics and 4 biocides being tested against the panel of 200 strains. Overall, results revealed that strains isolated from food had overall higher minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) for the following biocides: quaternary ammonia compounds and peracetic acid compared to strains isolated from animal or the environment. Conversely, no significant differences were observed for MIC of antibiotics from strains from different niches and from different clonal complexes. Interestingly, repeated exposure to quaternary ammonia compounds recurrently led to a decrease of susceptibility toward ciprofloxacin, a fluoroquinolone antibiotic, largely used in human and veterinary medicine and considered as a critically important antimicrobial. Additionally, these lower levels of susceptibility to ciprofloxacin remained stable in most strains even after subculture without biocide selection pressure, suggesting an adaptation involving modifications at the genetic level. Genomic analysis suggested that the accessory genome was associated with biocide tolerance, often linked to prophages and mobile genetic elements, thus demonstrating the adaptability of Lm and the need to further characterise and understand these important organisms.

The 200 strains characterized in detail, both at phenotypic and genotypic level, will help to assess the true importance of these strains as sources of foodborne infections for public health. Genetic mechanisms for the survival and adaptation of Lm (i) in food processing environment (ii) in wild and farming animals (iii) in natural and farming environments are investigated here. The genes could be used as targets for developing rapid monitoring tests. With a view to controlling risks in agricultural and agri-food systems, this project will make it possible to assess the relevance of monitoring plans, for instance in agricultural soils.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results

WPO: Coordination (M1-M30)

The LISTADAPT leader, Laurent Guillier, left the project during the summer of year 2 (Y2) for another position in ANSES. The project lead has been transferred to Sophie Roussel, the successor of Laurent Guillier. Sophie Roussel is a senior scientist that has maintained close relationships with all the

LISTADAPT partners. Indeed, she was a scientist at Anses from 2007 to 2017 working as the head of the molecular typing team of different food-borne bacteria, including *Listeria monocytogenes*. She was closely involved in European projects funded by EFSA and by the European Union (Horizon 2020 PHC7- "COMPARE"). In 2016, with her team, she wrote and set up LISTADAPT. Sophie Roussel worked then during two years (2017-2019) as Research Director at INRAE and was coordinator of the International Centre of Microbial Resources (CIRM) set up by INRAE. In this frame, she was involved in different European programs (H2020 -"CIRCLES" project and H2020 EJP One Health "CARE").

As LISTADAPT leader, Sophie Roussel coordinated and organised two face-to-face meetings (M25): (i) the first – one day -17th January 2020- meeting ANSES-INRAE specifically dedicated to WP3-WP4 (ii) the second - half a day -24th January 2020- with all the partners. Sophie Roussel was invited to present the project (i) during the annual European workshop EURL / NRL *Listeria* in January 2020 (see JRP7-WP5-T4: Dissemination) (ii) during meetings with different scientific partners such as the LIBio, a laboratory of Lorraine University (24th November 2029) and the main professional federations of the French food industry /ADEPALE) (26th November 2020). In addition, Sophie Roussel was invited by the ANSES management team to present the project to the scientific organisation committee of the Anses (26th May 2020 -60 participants).

WP1: Constitution of a strains collection representative of the different reservoirs of Listeria monocytogenes (M1-M12)

WP1-T1: Strain collection (M1-M12)

The LISTADAPT strain collection, unique in Europe, is composed of two compartments, one of which (First compartment C1) very original, as it regroups 847 strains isolated in the environment (soil, river, farm environment) along with strains from wild and farm animals (both healthy and animal presenting clinical symptoms). The second compartment (C2) is composed of 728 strains from five ready-to-eat (RTE) food categories from LISTADAPT partners (Table 1). All the 1575 strains are now centralized, long-term maintained and stored within the ANSES bacterial collection. The future use of some of these strains is protected by MTAs (Material Transfer Agreement). At ANSES, typing data (MLST data and cgMLST data) and associated epidemiological information of all the strains are centralized in a molecular database under the software BioNumerics version 7.6.3. A standardized nomenclature has been established with well-defined categories for all epidata (country, origin, matrix and animal condition) in order to improve the homogeneity of strains IDs.

Table 1: Repartition by compartments and sub-compartments of strains from the whole LISTADAPT collection (1,575)

Animal and environment (C1)				Food products and food production environment (C2)					
Farm animals	Wild animals	Soil and farm environment	Total	Meat	Fish	Dairy	Vegetables	Composite dish	Total
459	194	194	847	246	165	119	95	103	728

WP1-T2: Campaigns to collect additional animal and environmental strains (M1-M10)

WP1-T2-ST1: External collaborations (M1-M2)

To increase the size and representativeness of the collection, the LISTADAPT consortium performed an extensive review of all recent collections of published and unpublished Lm strains and then contacted researchers in charge of these collections. Finally, 14 external partners, food and veterinary laboratories and research institutes, all dealing with Lm hazards in Europe, collaborated with the LISTADAPT consortium (Tables 2 and 3). The initial collection included more strains from animals with listeriosis-associated clinical symptoms than without symptoms. In order to reduce the number of strains originating from animals with listeriosis while maintaining maximum diversity of the dataset, we adopted an original method to select the strains based on metadata (e.g., type of sample, geographic location, isolation time, molecular typing data such as PFGE profiles, animal species and geographic sampling location). This method relies on Gower's coefficient (GC), which is a dissimilarity measure: the "distance" between two units is the sum of all the variable-specific distances (associated with metadata categories). Because this collaborative work, we increased the representativeness and the diversity of animal and environmental Lm strains (strains from more countries at the European Union (EU) level and more partners at a national level). We constructed a large dataset comprising 344 animal and environmental Lm strains from 6 European countries and published collections (Table 2), as well as 373 animal and environmental Lm strains from 15 European countries and non-published collections (Table 3).

Table 2: List of 344 animal and environmental *Listeria monocytogenes* strains from published microbial collections.

Partner	Country (country code)	Category	Origin of isolation	No. of strains	Isolation year	References
Department of Food Hygiene and Environmental Health, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine of Helsinki (n=132)	Finland (FI)	Wild animals	Wild birds, hare, reindeer [NS]	49	1998, 2001	10,14
		Farm animals	Cow, cow milk in bulk tank and pigs [NS]	62	1981–2011	14,43-46
			Cow (aborted fetus) [CS]	4	1984–1987	14,44,45
		Soil and farm environment	Silage ¹ and soil	17	1987–2004	
Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Munich (n=31)	Germany (DE)	Wild animals	Deer and wild boar [NS]	31	2011–2012	6
Norwegian Veterinary Institute (n=29)	Norway (NO)	Wild animals	Slugs	29	2012	11
Department of Applied Microbiology and Human Nutrition ZUT (n=55)	Poland (PL)	Soil and farm environment	Soil from agricultural area	46	2010–2012	26
			Soil from park on city outskirts	9	2015–2016	
Department of Animal Health, NEIKER (n=71)	Spain (ES)	Farm animals	Cow, sheep and poultry feces [NS]	71	2004–2005, 2014–2016	4,47,48
Veterinary Faculty, University of Ljubljana (n=26)	Slovenia (SI)	Farm animals	Cow and sheep [CS]	13	2011–2015	25
		Soil and farm environment	Farm environment, water, pond	2	2008, 2014	
		Wild animals	Fox brain [NS]	11	2014	

CS, Clinical Symptoms. The reported clinical symptoms included rhombencephalitis, abortion, septicemia and mastitis/subclinical mastitis. The type of clinical samples included cerebellum/brain tissue, aborted fetus, fetal membrane, liver, internal organs, feces and milk. NS, No listeriosis-associated Symptoms¹ Strains isolated from silage were considered as originating from the farm environment since silage mainly includes fermented forage crops collected directly from fields.

Table 3: List of 373 animal and environment *Listeria monocytogenes* strains from non-published collections

Partner	Country	Category	Origin of isolation	No. of strains	Isolation year
Not communicated by the authors (n=96)	Belgium (BE)	Farm animals	Cow [NS]	96	2017–2018
		Farm animals	Cow, pig [NS]	6	2013–2014
Veterinary Research Institute (n=14)	Czech Republic (CZ)	Soil and farm environment	Mud, algae from pond, soil from farm, decaying vegetation	8	2010, 2014
		Wild animals	Gerbil, mouflon [NS]	3	Unknown
State veterinary institute (n=7)	Czech Republic (CZ)	Farm animals	Cow, sheep [NS]	4	Unknown
		Farm animals	Cow, sheep, goat [CS]	24	2014–2018
Veterinary and Food Laboratory (n=25)	Estonia (EE)	Wild animals	Deer [CS]	1	2018
		Farm animals	Cow, pork, goat milk, sheep [NS]	7	1987, 1995, 1998
Faculty of Veterinary Medicine/ Department of Food Hygiene and Environmental Health, Helsinki (n=24)	Finland (FI)	Wild animals	Hare, birds feces [NS]	4	1986, 1987
		Soil and farm environment	Silage ¹ and farm environment	13	2003, 2014–2015
		Farm animals	Cow, poultry [NS], horse [CS]	8	2003, 2014, 2015, 2018
Laboratory for Food Safety ANSES (n=25)	France (FR)	Wild animals	Hare [NS]	3	1986, 1996, 2015
		Soil and farm environment	Manure, soil	14	2004, 2006, 2009, 2012
Research Unit OPAALE INRAE (n=6)	France (FR)	Soil and farm environment	Soil, compost, pasture	6	2011, 2012, 2013, 2018
Institute of Food Safety and Food Hygiene, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Freie Universität Berlin (n=15)	Germany (DE)	Farm animals	Pig and sheep at slaughterhouse retention area or immediately after slaughter [NS]	15	2009, 2018–2019

Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment BIOR (n=24)	Latvia (LV)	Farm animals	Cow, goat, sheep, pig [CS]	24	2013–2018
Animal Pathology Laboratory INIAV (n=13)	Portugal (PT)	Farm animals	Cow, goat, sheep, zoo animals [CS]	12	2017–2019
		Soil and farm environment	Corn silage	1	2019
Veterinary Faculty, University of Ljubljana (n=53)	Slovenia (SI)	Farm animals	Cow, sheep, goat [CS]	27	2011–2015, 2018–2019
		Wild animals	Fox [NS]	2	2015
		Soil and farm environment	Cattle farm environment	1	2013
	Croatia (HR)	Farm animals	Cow, sheep, goat [CS]	23	2010, 2016–2017
Department of Biology, Swedish Food Agency (n=16)	Sweden (SE)	Wild animals	Deer, rook, moose, wild boar [NS]	13	Unknown
		Farm animals	Poultry [NS], goat, sheep [CS]	3	Unknown
State Veterinary and Food Institute Dolny Kubin (n=22)	Slovakia (SK)	Farm animals	Sheep, goat [CS]	20	2016–2018
		Soil and farm environment	Feed	2	2015, 2017
Laboratory Feed and Food and Product Safety VWA (n=33)	The Netherlands (NL)	Farm animals	Cow, sheep, goat, poultry [NS]	33	2016–2018

CS, Clinical Symptoms. The reported clinical symptoms included rhombencephalitis, abortion, septicemia and mastitis/subclinical mastitis. The type of clinical samples included cerebellum/brain tissue, aborted fetus, fetal membrane, liver, internal organs, feces and milk; NS, No listeriosis-associated Symptoms; [†] Strains isolated from silage were considered as originating from the farm environment since silage mainly includes fermented forage crops collected directly from fields.

WP1-T2-ST2: Sampling campaigns (M1-M10)

Soil, farm, and wild animal samples were collected in eight European countries (Table 4) in 2018 and in 2019. For the collection of soil samples, the LISTADAPT project members raised awareness and organised crowd-sampling campaigns. All the soil samples were collected from agricultural or wild areas according to a common procedure provided to the samplers based on the existing recommendations reported in the literature. The integration of feedback from samplers enabled a continuous improvement of the sampling protocol. The sampling campaigns were conducted in 17 areas in seven EU member states, Norway and Switzerland, namely AT, CH, CZ, FR, IT, NO, SE, SI and SK, resulting in the isolation of 75 Lm strains. Out of the 1752 available sampling records, the overall prevalence was 3%. We confirm in the present study the low prevalence of Lm in soil reported in the literature (below 1% and up to 6% depending on soil type).

Regarding the subcompartments of farm and wild animal, 55 Lm strains were isolated from sampling campaigns. Three campaigns targeting shelled gastropods sampled in IT, SK and CH resulted in the isolation of six strains. Sampling campaigns were also carried out for wild deer and reindeer feces in Southern Norway, and from cattle, roe deer, wild boar, wolf, bear and fox feces in the Abruzzo and

Molise regions of Italy. Of the 2577 samples collected from vertebrates during the campaign conducted in IT and NO 40 isolates were detected, with an overall prevalence of 1.5%.

Table 4: List of 130 animal and environment strains from sampling campaigns

Partner	Country (country code)	Category	Origin of isolation	No. of strains	Isolation year
Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety AGES (n=1)	Austria (AT)	Soil and farm environment	Meadow	1	2018
Veterinary Research Institute (n=21)	Czech Republic (CZ)	Natural and farm environment	Soil, river bank, pond, decaying vegetation, manure	18	2016– 2018
	Slovakia (SK)	Natural and farm environment	Soil, river bank	3	2016
Research Unit OPAALE INRAE (n=30)	France (FR)	Soil and farm environment	Soil, compost, pasture	30	2018– 2019
Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise G.Caporale (n=59)	Italy (IT)	Farm animals	Cow, goat, sheep [CS]	7	2014– 2018
		Soil and farm environment	Soil and river water	16	2016– 2018
		Wild animals	Fox, wolf, porcupine, badger, bear, snail, crayfish, roe deer, wild boar [NS]	36	2014, 2016– 2018
Norwegian Veterinary Institute (n=10)	Norway (NO)	Wild animals	Deer and reindeer [NS]	10	2017– 2018
Veterinary Faculty, University of Ljubljana (n=3)	Slovenia (SI)	Soil and farm environment	Water pond and soil	3	2018
State Veterinary and Food Institute Dolny Kubin (n=1)	Slovakia (SK)	Wild animal	Snail	1	2019
Department of Microbiology, National Food Agency (n=1)	Sweden (SE)	Soil and farm environment	Pasture	1	2018
Agroscope (n=4)	Switzerland (CH)	Soil and farm environment	Pasture soil	3	2019
		Wild animal	Snail	1	2019

CS, Clinical Symptoms. The reported clinical symptoms included rhombencephalitis, abortion, septicemia and mastitis/subclinical mastitis. The type of clinical samples included cerebellum/brain tissue, aborted fetus, fetal membrane, liver, internal organs, feces and milk. NS, No listeriosis-associated Symptoms

WP1-T3: Strategy for sequencing (M1-M12)

All the strains collected during the Tasks 1 and 2 have been sequenced in WP2.

WP2: Whole genome sequencing of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains (M2-M16)

WP2-T1: Purification of *Lm* DNA from 2000 *Lm* strains (M2-M14)

WP2-T1-ST1: First batch Purification of DNA from *Lm* strains available (M2-M4)

The first batch of 140 strains has been used to purify DNA at month 10. Four additional batches of strains have been used at months 11-12, for a total number of 546 strains

WP2-T1-ST2: Second batch Purification of DNA from additional *Lm* strains (M13-M14)

The second batch of strains has been used to purify DNA at month 24.

WP2-T1-ST3: Purification of DNA from routine surveillance systems at IZSAM, DTU, AGES (M1-M12)

DNA from strains gathered during routine surveillance were also made available by ANSES, IZSAM, DTU and AGES.

WP2-T2: Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) (M3-M14)

WP2-T2-ST1: First batch WGS for available *Lm* strains (M3-M6)

The first batch of 140 strains was sequenced in November 2018.

WP2-T2-ST2: Second batch WGS for additional *Lm* strains (M13-M14)

The second (and last) batch of strains was sequenced in February 2020.

WP2-T2-ST3: Ad hoc WGS (M3-M14)

Completed. Four LISTADAPT partners (AGES, IZSAM, ANSES and DTU) mainly performed the sequencing. All the genomes were centralized in a database at ANSES. (See WP2-T3).

WP2-T3: Genome Assembling and Annotation (M5-M16)

The next generation sequencing (NGS) paired-reads (2 × 150 bp) were generated during the project with Illumina platforms. The genomes were all *de novo* assembled and annotated with a harmonized in-house workflow named ARTwork (Assembly of reads and typing workflow) used in the ANSES Laboratory for Food Safety. In addition to *de novo* assembly, the ARTwork pipeline also performs genome annotation using Prokka. This whole genome sequencing (WGS) workflow has been described in detail in previous publications including the integrated bioinformatics tools and their corresponding versions, enabling repeatability and comparability of the results (Table 5). Assembled genome files will be publicly available in FASTA format through Figshare. Different WGS metrics and quality criteria were employed in the ARTwork pipeline to ensure high-quality WGS data. Reads with an estimated depth of coverage <30× (as estimated by BBmap⁴⁰) as well as contigs and scaffolds with a length of < 200 bp were excluded (n=22). Draft genomes with a total length outside the range of 2.7–3.3 Mb and with a total number of scaffolds > 200 (n=46) were also excluded. In addition, inter- and intra-species contamination of reads was determined using the recently developed ConFindr software (v0.5.1). Since recently demonstrated, inter-and-intra species contamination of 10 single nucleotide variants (SNVs) assessed by ConFindr in the conserved core genes does not significantly impact cluster analysis. We decided to exclude all genomes presenting SNVs lower than this cut-off (n=12) as well as various read- or assembly-related errors (n=34). The employed WGS metrics and quality criteria of the complete LISTADAPT genome dataset were reported (available at <https://figshare.com/s/6582ab54ce4fabfa1fc8>). After quality control of NGS and WGS data, the final LISTADAPT dataset included 1575 genomes. All metadata and WGS data collected herein were centralized and processed with standardized criteria for common nomenclature and NGS/WGS quality control before sharing between project partners. Reads normalized to 100× coverage, draft assemblies and annotated genomes were also centralized at the MongoDB database located at ANSES (Maisons-

Alfort Laboratory for Food Safety). Raw (non-normalized) reads for all the Lm strains sequenced in the LISTADAPT collection (n=1508) were submitted to the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) for sharing with the LISTADAPT project's partners. Raw (non-normalized) reads for 67 Lm food strains obtained from previous publications were submitted to the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) database and were linked to their existing accession numbers (available at <https://figshare.com/s/6582ab54ce4fabfa1fc8>).

Table 5: Bioinformatics tools implemented in the ARTwork pipeline and their versions

Application	Software	Version
Read mapping	BBMap	38.22-0
Read normalization	BBNorm	38.22-0
Quality assessment of reads	FastQC	0.11.8
Trimming of low-quality reads	Trimmomatic	0.38
<i>De novo</i> assembly	SPAdes	3.13.0
MLST prediction	MLST	2.16.1
Retrieval of the closest reference	Mash	2.0
Reference-based scaffolding	MeDuSa	1.3
Gap closing	GapCloser	2.04
Trimming of contigs <200 bp	Biopython	
Quality assessment of the assembly	QUAST	5.0.2
Genome annotation	Prokka	1.13.3

While carrying out a final check on the results obtained during LISTADAPT, we became aware of a correspondence problem between certain strains and their genomes. We are currently fully mobilizing at the level of the ANSES team to resolve as quickly as possible this concern of the integrity of our genome database. Some publications are pending until the problem be solved.

WP3 Phenotypic characterisation of Listeria monocytogenes strains (M1-M29)

WP3-T1: Strategy for selection of strains for phenotyping (M1-M12)

A panel of 200 Lm strains among the 1575 collected and sequenced for the project has been selected on the ground of their reservoirs, sub-reservoirs, sampling area and clonal complex (Figure 1). The three LISTADAPT partners (INRAE, NVI and ANSES) involved in phenotypic characterization (WP3) received the first set of 100 strains (those isolated from food) in May 2018 then the second (those isolated from environment) in April 2019. The selection was done according to the MLST-CC data, using statistical tests. The most prevalent CCs were selected.

Figure 1: Description of the 200 strains selected

WP3-T2: The effects of biocides on Lm strains adaptation (M3-M29)

WP3-T2-ST1: Antibiotics and biocides resistance profiles of Lm strains (M3-M22)

The characterization of MICs (minimal inhibitory concentrations) values for 11 antibiotics and 8 biocides was achieved in August 2019. The results were summarized in a paper (cf point 7).

WP3-T2-ST2: Adaptation to biocides and cross-resistance development to antibiotics of relevant Lm strains (M12-M22)

The impact of exposure to biocides on the antibiotic susceptibilities of Lm was also investigated.. We found that Lm strains isolated from food exhibited overall a lower susceptibility (higher MIC) for ammonium quaternary compounds (QACs) and peracetic acid (PAC) than strains isolated from animals and natural environments. We also showed that repeated exposure to QACs recurrently led to a decrease in susceptibility toward ciprofloxacin (CIP), a fluoroquinolone antibiotic, largely used in human medicine.

WP3-T2-ST3: The effect of biocides on Lm strains in biofilm (M12-M29)

The purpose of the study was to investigate phenotypical differences between the strains in terms of MBC-B (Minimum bactericidal concentration when the strain was in biofilm). Thirty-four isolates from food and twenty-four isolates from animals were cultivated in microtiter plates to form biofilm and then tested for survival after exposure to seven different concentrations of three disinfectants; Didectyl Dimethyl Ammonium Chloride (DDAC), Sodium hypochlorite (HS) and Hydrogen peroxide (Hper). We found the variation to be larger among the strains from wild animals than among the strains from food. The strains from the wild animals also seem to be more tolerant to disinfectants and in several cases the strains from wild animals tolerated twice the concentration of disinfectants compared to isolates from food. This pattern was true for all three disinfectants. The result was unexpected and did not support the hypothesis that exposure to biocides on Lm strains in biofilm is a significant selective pressure that reduces the diversity of strain.

Possible reasons for the results could be that the wild strains may have produced biofilm which is different from the one produced biofilm, that wild strains may be more stable as they are selected for survival by less excess of nutrients, or block variations in the design of experiments.

WP3-T3: Bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation of Lm strains (M3-M29)

The ability of strains to adhere and to form biofilm was evaluated by using two complementary approaches: the BioFilm Ring Test™ (BRT) and crystal violet (CV) methods. These methods allow characterizing early and late/mature states of biofilm development, respectively. The BRT device (Chavant et al., *J. Microbiol. Meth.*, 2007) makes it possible to evaluate the capacity of a bacterial strain to adhere to an abiotic support and start forming cellular aggregates. For each strain, the BRT were carried out after 6, 24 and 48 h of culture in BHI medium, in microplate wells incubated at 20°C, with three replicates for each time. The CV method is directly related to the biomass formed by bacterial cells in biofilm. In this case, the biomass of the biofilms formed by the different strains growing in BHI medium at 20°C in microplate wells was evaluated after 24 and 48 h of incubation. Six replicates were carried out for each of the two times. The results obtained were centralized in a database.

WP3-T4: Survival and persistence of Lm strains in different ecological niches (M3-M29)

WP3-T4-ST1: Survival of Lm in food products and gastro-intestinal environment (M3-M29)

Growth in the presence of preservatives

The primary purpose of the study was to investigate whether the genetic variation had any influence on the responses. The second was to see whether the strains isolated from food responded differently than the strains from nature and animals. An effect was expected as some of the strains from food probably had been isolated from foods with preservatives.

All strains grew well in BHIB at 12 °C. The growth was also significant at 4 °C, but much slower, as expected.

At pH 7, no difference was observed between the 200 strains. The additives had no impact on the growth. The latter was reasonable, as the fraction of undissociated acids at this pH was close to zero at neutral pH. At pH 4.5, the strains responded differently, and a clear effect of the additives was observed. Some strains showed a longer lagphase, some a slower increase in optical density, and some did not reach as high maximum optical density. The inhibiting effect of the additives followed this order: high concentration of acetate, low concentration of acetate, high concentration of lactate and finally low concentration of lactate. This order was the same as the concentration of undissociated acids in the four cases.

A co-variation between CC groups and the phenotypic response of the isolates was however not seen (Figure 2). The more than 200 isolates studied represented 26 CC groups. Isolates with different sensitivity to 2000 ppm of acetate were present in 16 of the CC groups, some of them often found in food. The reasons for the different responses is therefore connected to other characteristics in the genome, which will be further explored in GWAS analyses. The impact of the results is that challenge

studies of foods and development and validation of predictive models should take strain variation into account when targeted to food with low pH.

The impact of CC group, isolation step in the farm-to-fork chain and possible genetic markers for high or low tolerance of preservatives will be systemised and analysed with classical and bioinformatics tools.

Figure 2: Maximum optical density of *Lm* strains after growth at 12°C in Brain heart infusion broth (BHIB) at pH 5.4 supplemented with 2000 ppm of sodium acetate. The results are presented per CC group, and each column represent one strain.

The results were presented in an oral presentation at the EJP conference in May 2020 : Skjerdal T, Fagereng T, Osland AM, Lagesen K, Fiskerbeck E, Nesse L, Sévellec Y, Felix B, Roussel S. 2020. Phenotypical responses to stress of in *Listeria monocytogenes* strains of different Clonal Complexes isolated along the nature-to-farm-to-fork chain. 27-29 May. Second annual meeting EJP (virtual meeting).

Survival during in-vitro digestion

In order to cause foodborne illness, the *Listeria* has to pass the digestion tract and invade the organs. The survival during digestion is therefore essential for the pathogenicity potential of the strain, as a strain that do not pass this hurdle will not cause illness even if it has high virulence genes. The purpose was to study the survival of a fraction of the strain library in an in-vitro digestion model. As the purpose of LISTADAPT was to detect differences between strains, we chose to study more strains and fewer replicates, in order to search for links between responses and DNA sequences in later bioinformatics studies.

The concentration of alive *L. monocytogenes* decreased with app 1 to 5 log₁₀ units cfu/g during the gastric phase. The strains showed some difference also during the intestinal phase, but smaller than in the gastric phase. The model is complex in the sense that enzyme activities and several concentrations have to matched, which in turn makes it challenging to standardise between experiments. There are

indication of a higher tolerance to stomach acid among isolates from some CC-groups, but the data need to be analysed further assessed both with bioinformatic and phenotypical methods before conclusion.

WP3-T4-ST2: Survival of Lm in soil microcosm (M3-M16)

The ability of Lm to survive in soil was strain dependent. Survival ranged from zero to 22% (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Soil survival phenotype of 230 isolates of *Listeria monocytogenes*.

Ascending Hierarchical Clustering clearly identified 3 groups of phenotypes (Figure 4), possibly indicating that some isolates (Phenotype 3) may be better competitors in complex habitats such as soil.

Figure 4 Ascending Hierarchical Clustering of soil survival data.

WP4: Identification of genetic traits in *Listeria monocytogenes* underlying adaptation to the ecological niches (M1-M30)

WP4-T1: Analyze the distribution / prevalence of clonal complexes among the reservoirs (M1-M14)

This characterization helped to determine the two sets of strains for phenotypic studies. The 1575 strains clustered into 109 MLST STs, which belonged to 52 CCs and 23 singleton STs. For 38 strains, the allele profile was unknown (a presumable novel ST) or incomplete (When six out of seven MLST alleles were present, a CC was assigned when possible). We analysed in depth the strains genetic diversity between the three compartments and we showed the obtained results during (i) a 2-days-meeting at

ANSES in April (2019) including all the partners and some external partners and (ii) the EJP general meeting in Dublin (2019) (cf Point 7).

WP4-T2: Literature search of genes or genetic mechanisms responsible for virulence, adaptation and survival (M9-M12)

The list of genes involved in adaptation and survival was produced from research data obtained during the H2020 COMPARE project (2014-2019), coordinated by DTU (DK).

WP4-T3: Biostatistics analysis of annotated genomes (M6-M29)

WP4-T3-ST1: Identification of statistically relevant methods and development of analysis (M6-M16)

During the kick-off meeting of Y1 (March 2018), a list of relevant tools for identifying markers of adaptation to niches (environment, food industry) was established. The LISTADAPT partners has identified two alternative methods (DBGWAS and machine learning method from DTU) (Jaillard et al., 2018). Within the full lists, at least three methods are tested (Machine learning, GWAS based on presence/absence matrix and TreeWAS for SNP) (Brynildsdrud et al., 2016; Collins et al., 2018). For the research of genes identified in JRP7-WP4-T2, the LISTADAPT partners have chosen to use ABRICATE method (<https://github.com/tseemann/abricate>).

- Scoary:<https://genomebiology.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13059-016-1108-8>
- TreeWAS:<https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1005958>
- DBGWAS:<https://journals.plos.org/plosgenetics/article?id=10.1371/journal.pgen.1007758>

WP4-T3-ST2: Processing of all isolates (M22-M27)

Completed

WP4-T4: Comparative analysis of phenotypic data / genotypic data (M24-M29)

The results obtained in tasks WP3-T4-ST1; T3 and T2-ST3 are compiled with all the genomic data for a mixomics approach. All the data are centralized in a database.

Antibiotics and biocides resistance profiles of Lm strains

Genome Wide Association Study revealed that accessory mobile elements including transposon Tn6188 and plasmid pLMST6 were associated with benzalkonium-chloride (BC), a quaternary ammonium compound (QAC) widely used in food processing. The results (genomic and phenotypic data) were summarized in a publication (cf point 7).

Adaptation to biocides and cross-resistance development to antibiotics of relevant Lm strains

Genomic investigations on the strain adapted to biocides revealed important insertions and deletion in the Internalin sequence. Those variations impacted mainly Internalin of unknown function. Several biocide-adapted-strains presented also deletion of transposons or plasmids. An analysis on SNPs revealed that resistance to QACs are likely to be caused by the inactivation of a multidrug resistance efflux pump regulator by the insertion of a stop codon, hence explaining the increased resistance to biocide and to fluoroquinolones. A scientific publication combining the phenotypic and genotypic data is in preparation for the review “Frontiers in Microbiology” (cf Point 7).

Survival in soil

We have investigated the correlation between the phenotypes obtained for survival in soil and the characteristics of the genomes from the 200 isolates. Genome Wide Association Studies (GWAS) analysis did not evidence any link between the origin, the lineage or CC and the fitness in soil. This data suggest that the ability to survive in the soil is linked to multiple small effect genetic factors such as variations of transcriptional regulators, stress resistance proteins and cell wall proteins. However, GWAS applied on smaller and more genetically homogeneous subset (strains from the same CC) successfully identified phage-related- genes associated with soil survival rate. In particular, in the CC6, phenotype 1 was associated with the presence of a lysogenic phage corresponding to LP-030-3 and

with variations in the transcriptional regulator BglG. A scientific publication ANSES/INRAE combining the phenotypic and genotypic data is in preparation for the review “Frontiers in Microbiology” (cf Point 7).

Bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation of Lm strains

A statistical study of all these results is planned in June in order to highlight possible correlations between the origin or clonal complex and the ability to rapidly form a biofilm, and/or a significant biofilm. A publication combining the phenotypic and genotypic data is planned (meeting ANSES/INRAE 12th January 2021).

Survival of Lm in food products and gastro-intestinal environment

Genomic analysis are in progress at NVI. A publication combining the phenotypic and genotypic data is planned.

WP5 : Trainings and dissemination (M1-M30)

WP5-T1: Implementation of a workshop (M1-M2)

Statistical and bio-informatic tools useful for the project were discussed during the Kick-off meeting (March 2018).

WP5-T2: Trainings (M3-M6)

The LISTADAPT coordinator organized a training session, in April 2019, in parallel with the Y2-meeting. It aimed to train 20 participants to R package methods.

WP5-T3: Proficiency Testing Trials (M19-M22)

We decided that there will be no Proficiency testing trial WGS as planned. However, as part of the activities carried out by ANSES as EURL / NRL Listeria, a PT trial WGS was organized in 2018, then in 2019, during which four LISTADAPT partners (AGES, IZSAM, NVI, ANSES) participated.

WP5-T4: Dissémination (M1-M36)

Congresses and Publications –see Point 7

3. Project Self-assessment

As planned, LISTADAPT stimulated Reference laboratories to use WGS for the surveillance of Lm in their countries, as recommended by EFSA and ECDC. LISTADAPT allows continuing stimulation or implementation of WGS as the method of surveillance of Lm in the European countries, as recommended by the EFSA Biohaz panel in 2019 (<https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2019.5898>).

We had originally planned for WP1 to end in December 2018 (M12). However, it was very challenging to collect Lm strains isolated from natural environment. That is why we needed to (i) look for more partners (ii) collaborate with them and (ii) perform additional sampling campaigns. This is the reason why WP1 has been extended until December 2019 (M24). This has led to a substantial delay in the project in particular (i) in obtaining all the genomes assembled and annotated (completed in M28 instead of M16) (ii) in selection of the second batch of strains for WP3 (completed in M16) and (iii) in genomic analysis for WP4.

Last January 2021, we were performing validation tests on an in-house tool, “GenoListeria” which is a high-throughput real-time PCR allowing accurate identification of the most prevalent clonal complexes reported from human cases and food in Europe. Two of the strains analysed with GenoListeria (frozen corn outbreak) were previously sequenced, in the framework of our LRUE Listeria activities, and were included in the LISTADAPT dataset. We observed that the clonal complexes predicted by in silico analysis of these two strains did not match the results obtained by GenoListeria. For the moment, and despite the efforts of our team and those of the ANSES sequencing platform, we do not know the origin

of the problem. These discrepancies led us to verify all the genomes obtained in LISTADAPT-WP2 according to the "historical" data available. A total of 211 strains were sequenced again and for 125 strains, the genomes obtained were not the same and these new genomes corresponded either to historical data or to data obtained by *GenoListeria*.

4. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
07	D-JRP7-0.1	Consortium agreement	1				
07	D-JRP7-0.2	Internal reporting templates	3	3		https://zenodo.org/record/3733303#.X_2-W-hKjcc	
07	D-JRP7-0.3	Plan for dissemination and exploitation of results.	14	16		The dissemination plan was validated during the face-to-face meeting of April 2019. https://zenodo.org/record/3733315#.X_2-d-hKjcc	
07	D-JRP7-1.1	Description of the panel of strains already sequenced	1	1		Sequenced strains were mainly isolated from food industry/ready-to-eat food. These strains were described with metadata https://zenodo.org/record/3733281#.X_2_f-hKjcc	3
07	D-JRP7-1.2	Description of the first panel of strains available to sequence	3	3		https://zenodo.org/record/3686994#.X_2_JuhKjcc	3
07	D-JRP7-1.3	Description of the second panel of strains to sequence.	12	24		The last panel of strains to sequence was sent in December (11 December 2019) Deliverable uploaded on web site on 18 December 2019.	3

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						https://zenodo.org/record/3733232#.X_2-tOhKjcc	
07	D-JRP7-1.4	Report on strain collection and strategy for selection of strains for sequencing.	14	14		The strategy was presented during the OHEJP conference in May 2019 (Dublin). Deliverable uploaded on website on 16 December 2019 https://zenodo.org/record/3734093#.X_2-ZuhKjcc	3, 4
07	D-JRP7-2.1	Annotation of Lm genomes already sequenced (genomes available before the start of the project).	26	31		Confidential until publication in Scientific data is accepted. https://zenodo.org/record/3747482#.XpBuGsgzZM0	3
07	D-JRP7-2.2	Annotation of the Lm assembled genomes from 1st batch sequencing.	26	26		Confidential until publication in Scientific data is accepted. https://zenodo.org/record/3747493#.XpBun8gzZM0	3
07	D-JRP7-2.3	Annotation of the Lm assembled genomes from 2nd batch sequencing.	26	26		https://zenodo.org/record/3747502#.XpBwJMgzZM0	3
07	D-JRP7-2.4	Annotation of the Lm assembled genomes from ad hoc WGS	26	31		https://zenodo.org/record/3747504#.XpB04sgzZM0	2, 3

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
07	D-JRP7-3.1	Resistance profiles to biocide and antibiotics for the 200 Lm strains.	12	20		-Deliverable uploaded on web site on 17 December 2019. Poster presented during the OHEJP conference in May 2019 (Dublin) and during the IAFP's European Symposium on Food safety in April 2019 (Nantes). Confidential until publication in Pathogens is accepted https://zenodo.org/record/3686934#.X_2_NehKjcc	3
07	D-JRP7-3.3	Data on the effect of biocides on Lm strains in biofilm.	29	26		Confidential until publication in Scientific data is accepted. https://zenodo.org/record/3734064#.X_2-BOhKjcc	9
07	D-JRP7-3.4	Biofilms phenotypes for the 200 Lm strains.	33	37		Task completed in December 2020 (meeting Anses/INRAE 12 th January 2020). Confidential until publication is accepted. Public. Deliverable uploaded on web site on 22 January 2021. https://zenodo.org/record/4461726#.YA6j_ehKhM0	9
07	D-JRP7-3.5	Collection of data on survival of Lm as planktonic cells in various ecological niches.	27	27		Confidential until publication in Scientific data is accepted. Public https://zenodo.org/record/3686947#.XoIDllgza70	9

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
07	D-JRP7-3.6	Collection of data on survival of Lm in soil microcosms.	22	20		-Deliverable uploaded on web site on 17 December 2019. -Poster presented at ISOPOL XX in September 2019 (Toronto). https://zenodo.org/record/3686947#.X_2_TOhKjcc	3
07	D-JRP7-4.1	Bibliographic study on catalogues of genes	13	13		https://zenodo.org/record/3733308#.X_2-luhKjcc	3
07	D-JRP7-4.2	Report on prevalence and distribution of clonal complexes among the reservoirs.	26	26		Public https://zenodo.org/record/3734095#.X_2-KOhKjcc	9
07	D-JRP7-4.3	Software chosen for bioinformatics analysis.	16	16		-Validated during the LISTADAPT meeting (April 2019). -Deliverable uploaded on website on 16 December 2019 https://zenodo.org/record/3733311#.X_2_vehKjcc	2
07	D-JRP7-5.1	"LISTADAPT" workshop program.	2			No workshop was organised. Exchanges and discussions were held during the kick off meeting on methodologies and bioinformatics and statistical tools used in LISTADAPT; https://zenodo.org/record/3733319#.X_2-OOhKjcc	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
07	D-JRP7-5.2	Minutes of the training sessions.	10			There has been no minutes on the training sessions. https://zenodo.org/record/3733322#.X_2-hehKjcc	
07	D-JRP7-5.3	Publications and communications	36			Public. Cf point 7	8, 1,3,4

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify); 9. This is supportive to an integrative activity; 10. This is not an integrative activity

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
07	M-JRP7-1	Kick off meeting	2	Yes		6 th March 2018, located at Anses, Maisons-Alfort, France
07	M-JRP7-2	Selection of the 200 Lm strains based on genomic analyses in WP2.	3	Yes		100 strains have been selected based on their genomic characteristics and context of isolation. These strains correspond to samples collected along the food production chain. They were sent to WP3 partners in April 2018; For the remaining 100 strains (from environment and from animals), the selection was based on the prevalence of CCs and chosen to best represent the diversity at the European level. The strains were sent to WP3 partners in May 2019.
07	M-JRP7-3	Workshop done	3	Yes		Discussions on statistical and bioinformatics methods were held during the Kick off meeting.
07	M-JRP7-4	DNA prepared for 1st batch WGS	4	Yes		The first DNA were prepared in September 2018
07	M-JRP7-5	Strategy for selection of strains for sequencing in place	5	Yes		An <u>original</u> algorithm was developed for selecting strain based on meta-data describing the context of isolation of the strains

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
07	M-JRP7-6	WGS raw data produced	6	Yes		The sequencing was reported of many months
07	M-JRP7-7	Face-to-face meeting -2018	8	Yes		Kick off meeting / 6 th March 2018, located at Anses, Maisons-Alfort, France
07	M-JRP7-8	First batch Lm genomes assembly completed	8	Yes		Assembly and annotation with a harmonized in-house workflow named ARTwork. All the genomes are centralized in a database.
07	M-JRP7-9	Identification of Lm strains sequenced to be annotated	10	Yes		Assembly and annotation with a harmonized in-house workflow named ARTwork. All the genomes are centralized in a database.
07	M-JRP7-10	First batch Lm genomes annotation completed	10	Yes		Assembly and annotation with a harmonized in-house workflow named ARTwork. All the genomes are centralized in a database.
07	M-JRP7-11	WGS Training session done	10	Yes		Done
07	M-JRP7-12	All the strain collected and centralized at ANSES	12	Yes		All the 1575 strains are centralized, long-term maintained and stored within the ANSES bacterial collection. The future use of some of these strains is protected by MTAs. Typing data and associated epidemiological information of all the strains are centralized in a molecular database under the software BioNumerics.

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
						A standardized nomenclature has been established. (country, origin, matrix and animal condition...).
07	M-JRP7-13	DNA prepared for 2nd batch WGS	12	Yes		Done
07	M-JRP7-14	Selection of some representative Lm strains for the study of adaptation to biocides.	12	Yes		Thirty-four isolates have been tested on three disinfectants (seven different concentrations). The disinfectants used were Didectyl Dimethyl Ammonium Chloride (DDAC), Sodium hypochlorite (HS) and Hydrogen peroxide (Hper).
07	M-JRP7-15	WGS raw data produced.	25	Yes		Done
07	M-JRP7-16	Second batch Lm genomes assembly completed.	26	Yes		Assembly and annotation with a harmonized in-house workflow named ARTwork. All the genomes are centralized in a database.
07	M-JRP7-17	The database includes MLST data (CC and ST) of all the strains	14	Yes		
07	M-JRP7-18	Second batch of Lm genomes annotation completed.	26	Yes		Assembly and annotation with a harmonized in-house workflow named ARTwork. All the genomes are centralized in a database.
07	M-JRP7-19	Ad hoc batch of Lm genomes assembly completed	25	Yes		Assembly and annotation with a harmonized in-house workflow named ARTwork. All the genomes are centralized in a database.
07	M-JRP7-20	Bioinformatic analysis done for all the strains	28	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
07	M-JRP7-22	Ad hoc batch Lm genomes annotation completed	20	Yes		Assembly and annotation with a harmonized in-house workflow named ARTwork. All the genomes are centralized in a database.
07	M-JRP7-23	Face-to face meeting -2020	25	Yes		
07	M-JRP7-24	WGS Proficiency Testing trial (PTtrial) done	26	No		Given the delay in the project, we decided that there will be no Proficiency testing trial WGS as planned. However, as part of the activities carried out by ANSES as EURL / NRL <i>Listeria</i> , a PT trial WGS was organized in 2018, then in 2019, during which four LISTADAPT NRL partners (AGES, IZSAM, NVI, ANSES) participated.

5. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
First report on the occurrence of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ST121 strain in a dolphin brain. https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7601084/ https://zenodo.org/record/4244051#.X6J4fziWxM1	YES	Gold	1250
Comparative analysis of genetic determinants encoding cadmium, arsenic and benzalkonium chloride resistance in <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> of human, food and environmental origin Front. Microbiol., 14 January 2021 https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2020.599882 https://zenodo.org/record/4456720#.YLDmBzhDtM0	YES	Gold	1000
Exposure to quaternary ammonium compounds selects resistance to ciprofloxacin in <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> . <i>Pathogens</i> . 10, (2) 220. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10020220 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5471681	YES	Gold	1100
Genetic Characterization of a <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> Serotype IVb Variant 1 Strain Isolated from Vegetal Matrix in Italy. <i>Microbiol Resour Announc.</i> 2020 Aug 13;9(33):e00782-20.DOI: 10.1128/MRA.00782-20 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5472980	YES	Gold	500

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
A European-wide dataset to uncover adaptives traits of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> to diverse ecological niches. Accepted in the review Scientific Data in December 2020	YES	Gold	1000
Genomics elements located in the accessory repertoire drive the adaptation to biocides in <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> strains from different ecological niches. Accepted in the review Food Microbiology in December 2020. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2021.103757	YES	Gold	850
Investigation of genome characteristics underlying fitness of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in soil. In preparation for Frontiers in Microbiology.	YES	Gold	1200
Exposure to quaternary ammonium compounds selects resistance to ciprofloxacin in <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> . <i>Pathogens</i> . 10, (2) 220. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10020220 https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5471681	YES	Gold	1100
Assessment of the ability to adapt to biocides and develop cross-resistance to antibiotics for <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> strains. In preparation for Frontiers in Microbiology.	YES	Gold	1200
Genomic diversity of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> strains isolated in Slovakia during 2010-2020. Will be submitted in June 2021 –Frontiers in Microbiology	YES	gold	1200
Draft genomes of two <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> strains isolated from invasive snails <i>Arion vulgaris</i> in Austria. MRA00375-21R1. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5472856	YES	gold	1100

Additional output

Oral communications

2020

- Skjerdal T, Fagereng T, Osland AM, Lagesen K, Fiskerbeck E, Nesse L, Sévellec Y, Felix B, Roussel S. 2020. Phenotypical responses to stress of in *Listeria monocytogenes* strains of different Clonal Complexes isolated along the nature-to-farm-to-fork chain. 27-29 May. Second annual meeting EJP (virtual meeting)
- Sévellec Y, Ascencio Schuttz E, Félix B, Guillier L, Roussel S, Piveteau P. Comparative Analysis of the genomic diversity of *Listeria monocytogenes* in soil and water and food processing through pan Genome Wide Association Study. 27-29 May. Second annual meeting EJP (virtual meeting)
- Palma F, Guérin A, Radomski N, Bridier A, Sévellec Y, Félix B, Soumet c, Guillier L , Roussel S. Deciphering the Biocide-Resistance of *Listeria monocytogenes* Strains from Europe through Genome-Wide Associations at the pangenomic scale. 27-29 May. Second annual meeting EJP (virtual meeting)
- Guérin A, Palma F Le Grandois P, Bridier A, Soumet C, Sevellec Y, Roussel S. Exposure to quaternary ammonium compounds show resistance to ciprofloxacin for *Listeria monocytogenes* from diverse ecological niches. 27-29 May. Second annual meeting EJP (virtual meeting)
- Sept 2020: Food Micro Next Generation Challenges in Food Microbiology –Athènes. Reported in September 2021/Three abstracts submitted (Y. Sévellec, S. Roussel)
- Sévellec, Y. An insight in *Listeria* genomes. Terramo. annual workshop of the ItNRL Lm. 16th September 2020

2019

- Felix B, Feurer C, Maillet A, Guillier L, Boscher E, Kerouanton A, Denis M and Roussel S (2019). Population genetic structure of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains isolated from the pig and pork production chain in France. 26-27 August 2019, Safepork 2019, Berlin.
- Félix B, Feurer C, Maillet A, Desmots M H, Hickey B, Jankuloski D, Karpíšková R, Skjerdal T, Denis M, Gareis M, Zdovc I, Pietzka A and Guillier L (2019). Typing and persistence of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains in food processing environments, prophages identified as major persistence markers. ISOPOL XX 2019, 24 – 27 September 2019, Toronto.
- Guillier L (2019). Assessment of the Genomic Diversity of a Large Collection of *Listeria monocytogenes* Strains Isolated in EU Natural Environments. OHEJP Annual scientific meeting, Dublin, 22-24 May 2019
- Guillier L (2019). Proposal of an Original Method for Selecting Strains to Include in Source Tracking or Source Attribution Based on their Metadata. OHEJP Annual scientific meeting, Dublin, 22-24 May 2019
- Sévellec, Y. 2019. LISTADAPT- Study of the Genetic diversity of *Listeria monocytogenes* from environment to human; Terramo. annual workshop of the ItNRL Lm. 4th July 2019

2018

- Felix, B., 2018. Population genetic structure of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains isolated from the pig and pork production chain in France, presented at Food Micro September 2018, Berlin (Germany).

- S. Antoci, V. A. Acciari, V. Di Marzio, I. Del Matto, G. Centorotola, M. Torresi, C. Marfoglia, G.
- Iannitto, A. Ruolo, G. A. Santarelli, G. Migliorati, F. Pomilio. Preliminary results on prevalence and persistence of *Listeria monocytogenes* in different dairy and meat processing plants in Central Italy, presented at “International meeting on emerging diseases and surveillance” November 2018, Vienna (Austria).

Posters

2021

- Taran Skjerdal#, Tone Fagereng, Eve Fiskebeck, Karin Lagesen, Sophie Rousse. Impact of genetic variation of 200 *Listeria monocytogenes* strains on the growth in presence of preservatives. OH-EJP annual scientific meeting Copenhagen, 9-11 June 2021.
- Toresi M, Rinaldi A, Marzio D et al. Genomic features of two main Clonal Complex groups of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains isolated from European wild animal. 6th World One Health Congress; 30 October - 3 November 2020.

2019

- Torresi M., Rinaldi A., Cammà C., Di Pasquale A., Skjerdal T., Lagesen K., Felix B., Sevellec Y., Guillier L., Leroux A., Ricao M., Boysen M., Lindström M., Castro H., Korkeala H., Gareis M., Frank E., Bulawova H., Brychta M., Amar C., Grant K., Pate M., Zdovc I., Pomilio F (2019). Diversity of *Listeria monocytogenes* associated with wild animals: focusing on CCs with a wide capacity of adaptation. International Symposium on Problems of *Listeria* and Listeriosis ISOPOL XX. 24-27 September 2019 Toronto
- Oevermann A, Hurtado A, Papić B, Karpíšková R, Piveteau P, Wullings B, Bulawova H, Castro H, Lindström M, Korkeala H, Šteingolde Ž, Bērziņš A, Avsejenko J, Kramarenko T, Cabanova L, Szymczak B, Torresi M, Leroux A, Sevellec Y, Guillier L and Félix B (2019). European-wide study reveals high prevalence of hypervirulent *Listeria monocytogenes* clones in farmed ruminants and their environment. ISOPOL XX -24 – 27 September 2019 Toronto
- Skjerdal T, Sevellec Y, Guillier L, , Zdovc I, Pate M, Torresi M, Riacao M, Boysen M, Lindstrøm M, Castro H, Gareis M, Bulawova H, Amar C, Grant K, Leroux A, Pomilio F, Camma C, Di Pasquale A, Lagesen K, Osland Mohr A, Rinaldi A, Karpiskova R, Pietzka A, Ruppitsch W, Szymczak B, Ascencio-Schultz E, Piveteau P and Felix B (2019). Occurrence and diversity of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains in environment and wild life in Europe. ISOPOL XX -24 – 27 September 2019 Toronto
- Ascencio-Schultz E, Gal L, Garmyn D, Szymczak B, Karpiskova R, Pietzka A, Ruppitsch W, Boysen M, Pomilio F, Torresi M, Camma C, Di Pasquale A, Pate M, Skjerdal T, Sevellec, Y., Felix B, Guillier L and Piveteau P (2019). Investigation of genome characteristics underlying fitness of *Listeria monocytogenes* in soil. ISOPOL XX -24 – 27 September 2019 Toronto
- Sévellec Y, Torresi M, Orsini M, Centorotola G, Bilei S, Senese M, Terracciano G, Felix B, Guillier L and Pomilio F (2019). Investigation of a dolphin infection by *Listeria monocytogenes* CC121. ISOPOL XX -24 – 27 September 2019 Toronto
- Vranckx K, Sevellec Y, Deneweth J and Felix B. Phages in *Listeria*: Who are they, what do they do? ISOPOL XX -24 – 27 September 2019 Toronto
- Guérin A, Le Grandois P, Bridier A, Soumet C (2019). Evolution of antibiotics and biocides resistance of *Listeria monocytogenes* from diverse ecological niches following in vitro exposure to biocides disinfectants. ISOPOL XX -24 – 27 September 2019 Toronto
- Guérin A, Le Grandois P, Bridier A, Soumet C (2019). Evolution of antibiotics and biocides resistance of *Listeria monocytogenes* from diverse ecological niches following in vitro exposure to biocides disinfectants. IAFP's European Symposium on Food Safety, Nantes, 24-26 April 2019

- Guérin A, Le Grandois P, Bridier A, Soumet C (2019). Evolution of antibiotics and biocides resistance of *Listeria monocytogenes* from diverse ecological niches following in vitro exposure to biocides disinfectants. OHEJP Annual Scientific meeting, Dublin, 22-24 May 2019

2018

- Felix B, Feurer C, Maillet A, Guillier L, Boscher E, Kerouanton A, Denis M, Roussel S. 2018. Population genetic structure of *Listeria monocytogenes* strains isolated from the pig and pork production chain in France. IAFP EU Stockholm 25-27 April 2018

Outcomes

D-JRP7-1.4 Report on strain collection and strategy for selection of strains for sequencing.

Scientific Paper : "A European-wide dataset to uncover adaptive traits of *Listeria monocytogenes* to diverse ecological niches." Accepted in the review Scientific Data

LISTADAPT made it possible to strengthen the collaboration between the consortium and a team of DTU (Danish Technical University, DK). This team (Research Group for Genomic Epidemiology, expert in machine learning (Njage P et al. 2019. Risk Analysis 39:1397-1413) asked the coordinator to provide them the 1575 genomes and metadata in order to develop a tool predicting the resistance of Lm strains to biocides used in food industry.

D-JRP7-3.1, 3.2, 3. 3, 3. 4, 3.5, 3.6-Phenotypic data of 200 strains isolated from food, animals and environment.

This output included all the phenotypic data obtained (resistance to antibiotics, effects of biocides on Lm strains adaptation; bacterial adhesion and biofilm formation of Lm strains, survival and persistence of Lm strains in different ecological niches). This data is very valuable, as the 200 strains panel has been selected to be balanced between reservoirs, sub-reservoirs, sampling area and CCs with high and low degree of genetic relatedness

All the phenotypic data obtained is centralized in a database. This data will be compiled with all the genomic data for a mixomics approach.

The results obtained on the phenotypic data will be valuable for EURL activities such as selection of strains for challenge testing of low pH foods, and for risk assessments of foods with preservatives. Further, these results can be used to assess the validity of predictive models that have been developed with few strains for strains with other genetic characteristics.

ADEPALE, a professional federation of the French food industry, is very interested in the results. Following the presentation of the project by the coordinator in November 2020, they asked to give them a presentation in May 2021 on all the combined phenotypic/genotypic data obtained. They want to understand the mechanisms of adaptation of the strains in the plant chain from the soil to the finished plant products and wish to set up a research collaborative project with ANSES on this subject.

A large part of the 1575 genomes is used in an important research project (2020-2024) between INRAE and Anses (funded the French Research Agency-ANR). This new project aims to develop tools for the detection and quantification of persistent intracellular Lm, in order to progress in the knowledge of the biology of this phenomenon, on the mechanisms leading to asymptomatic carriage in host, and to propose diagnostic, therapeutic and preventive solutions for at-risk human populations (such as pregnant women and the elderly) and farm animals. This project also aims at studying the variability of this intracellular persistence phenotype according to the genetic and ecological diversity of Lm strains.

The collection of 1575 genomes has been explored using a machine-learning approach recently implemented at DTU-Food (Njage et al., 2019). Complementary to GWAS analyses, this approach allows in silico prediction of phenotypical properties (survival in sol, adhesion, biofilm formation...) for the entire collection, including isolates that will not have been characterized at the phenotypic level.

Several machine-learning methods (gradient-boosting, random forest, support vector machine) will be tested within the SEL Unit, in close collaboration with the DTU-Food.

Some of these strains and genomes are used in the One Health EJP Project “CARE” (2020-2023) (Cross-sectoral framework for quality Assurance Resources for countries in the European Union).

6. One Health Impact

The detailed characterization of these strains at phenotypic and genotypic level will help to assess the true importance of these strains as sources of foodborne infections for public health. Mechanisms for the survival and adaptation of Lm (i) in food processing environment (ii) in wild and farming animals (iii) in natural and farming environments will be identified. The genes identified will be used as targets for developing rapid monitoring tests. With a view to controlling risks in agricultural and agri-food systems, this project will make it possible to assess the relevance of monitoring plans, for instance in agricultural soils.

The results obtained in WP3-T4-ST1 will be valuable for EURL activities such as selection of strains for challenge testing of low pH foods, and for risk assessments of foods with preservatives. Further, these results can be used to assess the validity of predictive models that have been developed with few strains for strains with other genetic characteristics.

With LISTADAPT project, we are looking for molecular markers of interest such as for instance mobile genetic elements harbouring antimicrobial resistance factors as well as provide insight into the population structure and evolutionary history of Lm for epidemiologic investigation. This information could be used for the development of new diagnostic tests to screen food, processing environment and animal reservoirs for contamination by Lm strains. These new tests represent key tools to improve the Lm surveillance system and to assist the food industry decision-making around food processing for improving food safety. For instance, a professional federation of the French food industry is interested in results obtained in W3/WP4. Following the presentation of the project in November 2020, they asked the coordinator to give them a presentation in 2022 on the results obtained in WP4. They want to understand the mechanisms of adaptation of the strains in the plant chain from the soil to the finished plant products and wish to set up a research collaborative project with Sophie’s team on this subject.

The LISTADAPT project makes it possible bridging the gap between “Med” and “Vet”. Listdadapt strengthened the collaboration between Anses and the Institute of Microbiology and Parasitology of the Veterinary Faculty of the University of Ljubljana. A project entitled “Detection of *Listeria monocytogenes* clonal complexes in animal and food samples using real-time PCR” was submitted in April 2021 in response to the call PHC Proteus (Programme Proteus 2022 | Campus France). Moreover a joint paper Anses/ Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment BIOR, Latvia; entitled “Characterization and genetic diversity of *Listeria monocytogenes* isolated of cattle abortions in Latvia, 2013-2018” has been submitted in July 2021 at the Journal Veterinary sciences.

This is the first time a project has focused on such a large and diverse collection of Lm strains isolated from farming/wild animals and farming/wild environment in different European countries. Most of these strains and genomes are very useful for the One Health EJP Project “CARE” (2020-2023) (Cross-sectoral framework for quality Assurance Resources for countries in the European Union).

JRP010-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC

1. Summary of the work carried out

The **MOMIR-PPC project** aimed to develop new approaches to predict, identify and prevent the appearance of animal and human super-shedders based on immune response and gut microbiota

composition. The vast majority of the planned objectives were achieved despite the many problems encountered during the project, and thanks to the time extension granted to us.

This project led to

1. Reproduce the heterogeneity of *Salmonella* infection, characterized by the super- and low-shedder phenotypes in all the species studied (human, pig, chicken mouse), beside the use of different infection models.
2. Original and interesting results, which allow better understanding of the heterogeneity of excretion and to predict and differentiate between these different shedding phenotypes. Moreover, the project allowed the development of original epidemic mathematical models and methods for data analysis.

Among the most important advances, we can highlight:

- **The key role of animal-animal recontaminations** in the spread of *Salmonella* infection at the flock level, which are mainly related to the presence of Super-Shedders, functioning as a reservoir for the pathogen. Our results, have shown that variation in the presence/absence of bacterial virulence cannot explain the super and low shedding phenotypes. However, in contrast, host factors and gut microbiota composition play a crucial role. For example, the gut microbiota composition before infection determines in chicks the super and low shedder phenotypes. Moreover, although the risk of human-to-human transmission of *Salmonella* from asymptomatic carriers is considered low, our study indicates a 10-fold higher rates (24%) of nontyphoidal *Salmonella* shedding than previously suggested.
- **The development of original mathematical models** of epidemics and methods of analyzing intra-animal transmission data. A mathematical model of indirect transmission of bacteria between broilers was also developed. The model can be used for designing and quantitatively assessing candidate bio-security based intervention strategies against indirect transmission of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella*.
- **The identification of several control strategies** based on the importance of the ventilation in farms and the identification of the animals at risk. For that purpose, the MOMIR-PPC project identified several predictive biomarkers, based on gut microbiota composition and immune parameters. The identified biomarkers, which still need to be further confirmed, can either predict the levels of *Salmonella* shedding (in pigs or in chickens) if animals are infected, or can differentiate between the *Salmonella* shedding levels. We also identified the major factors associated with the long term shedding of *Salmonella* in humans.
- **The identification of several preventive measures based on the use of pre- and probiotics.** To prevent salmonellosis, we isolated, characterized and tested the efficacy of probiotics and prebiotics for use in pigs and poultry. The studies were undertaken in experimental infections and in field conditions. For example, we have tested the interventions in 72640 chicks in Bulgaria and 130 000 chicks in Czech Republic. These probiotics and prebiotics can be used as an alternative to antibiotics and may help reduce AMR. Samples were also taken from a number of challenge and intervention studies for metagenomic analysis. Finally, a draft inventory of relevant intervention measures against *Salmonella* in poultry has been developed and the cost effectiveness (utility) of intervention strategies using probiotics against *Campylobacter* has been calculated.
- These results have been or will be disseminated in Joint scientific articles and in congresses.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results

WPO. Management

WPO-T1- Draft and agree Consortium Agreement

As consortium agreement was signed between the EJP coordinator ANSES and the EJP beneficiaries, we considered at the first MOMIR-PPC meeting that it was unnecessary to sign a particular consortium agreement at the MOMIR-PPC level (Deliverable.0.2).

WPO-T2- Produce project-planning, control documentation and Data Management Plan

The project planning has been modified several times due to the left of SAIM from the EJP consortium, and of the Vet-DTU, which has been closed by its Government. The work, which should be performed by these partners, has been taken into account by a new partner (NNDRVMI). We also modified the project planning of the Norwegian Institute of Public Health because Astrid Louise Wester left her institute. The final project planning was decided in June (month 6). The data management plan was updated several times during the project. A final version has been produced in Excel format (Deliverable.0.1 ; D.4.2).

WP3-T3- Control and manage activity progresses, the timely delivery of project tasks and outputs

Numerous exchanges have been performed to coordinate the work performed by the members. This has been done during the intermediate and final meetings and during video-conferences. Informal meeting were organized between few partners to exchange information, to define who will test what (especially concerning the pro and prebiotics, which were tested in farms) and to build joint articles. We discussed also how to store and exchange the bacterial strains developed in the project. Many experiments were postponed due to the COVID-19 crisis, which had an impact on the work of other Partners. This was managed through the extension of the project (Deliverable.0.2).

WPO-T4- Control and manage the project closure and outputs

The final meeting took place in video-conference on 10-11 May 2021. During this meeting, all partners presented their results, but they also provided the necessary information for the final report. All partners read, completed and validated the final report (Deliverable.0.3).

WP1. Risk prediction for Super-shedder animals and human asymptomatic carriers through the use of gut microbiota and immune status analyses (M1-M12)

The goal of this WP was to identify immunological and microbiota markers that are associated to super/low shedding before and/or after infection, which allow us to predict and identify the animals which will be Super shedders. For this WP, we used experimental infection models and also naturally infected animals and humans in "field condition". Taking into account the great adaptability of pathogens for their hosts, the virulence and immunogenicity of *Salmonella* strains originated from Super- and low-shedders were compared.

WP1-T1- Predictive immunological markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and pigs

The goal of the task was to identify immune markers able to identify the super-Shedders and other able to predict the most susceptible animals and/or the animals that will become super-shedders, if infected. The activities focused on the most prevalent serotypes: *S. Typhimurium* for pig, and *S. Enteritidis* for chicken.

Four Partners were involved in this task (ANSES, ISS, IZLER and INRAE), which were done with pigs (ANSES, ISS, IZLER and INRAE), chickens (INRAE) and mice (ISS). A Post doc who, undertook her PhD in the ISS lab, was recruited by INRAE-Tours to manage part of the work devoted to SAIM.

The results obtained by **ISS** and **IZLER** showed in mice and pigs that IFN gamma gene expression (and protein level) correlates to *Salmonella* burden. Moreover, a higher INF-gamma production increases the ability of animals to control infection. In contrast, a specific pro-inflammatory response and stimulation of inflammation pathways is predictive of super-shedder phenotype (**Deliverable.1.1**).

ANSES performed a trial with a total of 45 piglets divided into five groups: one group with five piglets as control and four groups each with 10 piglets (n=40) as inoculated pigs. At 7 weeks of age, piglets were infected with 10^9 CFU/piglets of a monophasic variant of *Salmonella* Typhimurium strain. Pigs were followed during 3 weeks after inoculation before being necropsied. The level of *Salmonella* shedding allowed us to identify three significantly different classes ($p < 0,01$) corresponding to high (n=13), intermediate (n=16) and low shedders (n=11) pigs. Regarding the blood cell number, 12 parameters showed a significant difference ($p\text{-value} < 0,05$) between inoculated pigs and controls, at one or several days after infection, most of them were white cells. The difference was also confirmed to be also significant between super- and low-shedders for 5 parameters, Lymphocytes, basophile, Granulocytes, and Haematocrite). Quantification of TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6 and IFN- γ , showed that a significant difference ($p < 0,01$) was observed on the median production level between super- and low-shedders for IL1- β and IL6 at 1DPI (**Deliverable.1.3 ; D.1.7**). As in part observed in chicks, Low shedders pigs seroconverted earlier than intermediate and high shedders pigs (**Deliverable.2.11**). The results obtained by **ANSES** and **INRAE** suggested that the expression of one immune related gene could be a predictive biomarkers (**Deliverable.1.6**). The expression of several host genes could be biomarkers able to characterize the low- and super-shedder phenotypes. Moreover, a strong pro-inflammatory immune response is correlated to the super-shedder phenotype. This is counter-intuitive but could be explained by the articles describing that *Salmonella* requires intestinal inflammation to sustain its replication in the intestinal tract. Indeed, intestinal inflammation leads to availability of nutrients that are otherwise not accessible in the uninfamed gut and to a better competition with the resident microbiota by creating microaerophilic conditions.

The results obtained from the chick studies performed by **INRAE** showed that the number of blood immune cells circulating in the blood could not be used as a predictive marker for the appearance of the low and super-shedder phenotypes (**Deliverable.1.6**). Moreover, the analysis has shown no differences, after infection, when low and super-shedders are compared with the control group. Similarly, to identify predictive immunological markers associated to high and low shedders, we analysed the differences of the humoral immune response of low and high-shedders and compared their response to non-infected chicks by measuring the production of total (non-specific) IgA, IgY, IgM before and after infection. Generally, the analysis has revealed that the total antibody responses follow a classical pattern with a rise in levels of total IgM preceding the rise in IgY. The total immunoglobulin response was low before infection and increase after infection. Moreover, no significant differences were observed between naïve/low shedders and high shedders. This result shows that level of immunoglobulin cannot be a predictive marker for low shedders and high shedders. Interestingly, a statistically significant increase in IgY level has been observed at 7 days post infection in high-shedders when compared with low-shedders and control groups. Finally, the evaluation of anti-*Salmonella* LPS IgA levels has revealed a lack of response in all the samples analyzed except for two of them, suggesting that anti-*Salmonella* IgA response is not a good candidate to investigate differences between low-shedders and high-shedders in contrast to total IgM response (**Deliverable.1.6 ; D1.7 ; 2.11**). This work had been performed in collaboration with the Bernd Kaspers's lab (U. Munich), **during a short stay, funded by EJP**.

In the same way, the immuno-histological work performed by **VISAVET-UCM** on caecal samples did not show any major histopathological changes between low and super-shedders. In contrast, the inoculation of four commensal bacteria the day of hatch, and which protect chicks from *Salmonella* infection (see WP2), modified both the number of immune cells circulating in the blood during *Salmonella* infection and the host immune response to the pathogen (**Deliverable.2.6**).

WP1-T2- Predictive microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and pigs

The goal of the task was to analyse the gut microbiota composition before and after *Salmonella* infection to identify predictive microbiota markers associated to the super and low shedders in chickens and pigs. Samples from representative pigs and chickens originated from activities of task 1.1 were analyzed based on Illumina sequencing of V3/V4 variable region of 16S rRNA genes. The same experiments were used to analyse both the immune response and the gut microbiota composition.

Four Partners (ANSES, ISS, IZLER and INRAE) were involved in this task for the animal experiments performed with pigs and chicks. UoS sequenced all samples from pigs while VRI sequenced all samples from chicks. Sequencing data were analyzed by UoS, VRI and INRAE.

The work performed by **INRAE** and **VRI** with chicks demonstrated the role of gut microbiota in the susceptibility to *S. Enteritidis* infection and in the appearance of the low and super-shedder phenotypes. We especially demonstrated that (1) axenic and antibiotic-treated chicks are more prone to become super-shedders; (2) super or low-shedder phenotypes can be acquired through microbiota transfer; (3) specific gut microbiota taxonomic features determine whether the chicks develop a low- and super-shedder phenotype after *Salmonella* infection in isolator **Figure 1 (Deliverable.1.8)**. It has been especially described that presence of *Enterococcus* could be a predictive markers of low *Salmonella* susceptibility (**Deliverable.1.9; 1.10**). This study demonstrates the key role plays by gut microbiota composition in the heterogeneity of infection and the possibility to increase resistance to *Salmonella* colonization with pro and prebiotics (see WP2). An article describing this work has been accepted for publication in Microbial Biotechnol.

Figure 1: PCA analysis of the genus frequencies observed before infection (i.e. at 5 and 7 days of age), in order to highlight predictive markers among the three shedding level categories (Low (resistant), intermediate and high (super) shedder phenotypes). Chicks were orally infected at 7 days of age and fecal samples were recovered before and after *Salmonella* infection. Gut microbiota composition was analyzed by 16S rDNA sequencing.

For pigs, **ANSES**, **UoS** and **INRAE** showed that numerous taxa are specific to the low and super-shedder phenotypes (**Deliverable.1.9; 1.10**). A Co-inertia analysis between the immune genes dCt and microbiota features abundances, conducted at **INRAE** did not show a correlation between the gut microbiota composition and immune gene expression (**Deliverable.1.15**). A joint article is in preparation.

Similarly, **ISS** and **IZLER** performed experiments in pigs and sent the samples to **UoS** for microbial community analysis. The samples have been analysed in conjunction with metadata related to the animal's overall health and shedding status, to test the hypotheses regarding the association of the gut microbiome with *Salmonella* shedding status. No clear correlation was observed (**Deliverable.1.9;**

1.10). However, It should be noted that both studies were carried out using pigs with different genetic backgrounds and *Salmonella* strains, therefore this created an opportunity to test the association between the microbiome and *Salmonella* shedding in two different scenarios.

WP1-T3- Risk factors associated with prolonged convalescent *Salmonella* shedding in humans FHI driven this Task.

The goal of the task was to investigate the risks factors associated with chronic *Salmonella* infection in human population. This Task was managed by NIPH. A cohort study was carried out on all nonthypoidal- (NT) salmonellosis cases registered in the Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS). All potential participants were asked to send a stool sample and to respond to an online/paper questionnaire to collect information. Stool samples were processed at NIPH for *Salmonella* growth. Participants with long-term shedding (stool samples positive for *Salmonella* growth by direct culture approximately 5 weeks post infection) were compared to participants with short-term shedding of *Salmonella* (stool samples negative for *Salmonella* growth by direct culture approximately 5 weeks post infection) in order to identify associated factors with long-term shedding. (**Deliverable.1.11**).

Figure 2: Process describing collection of data

Furthermore, all initial *Salmonella* isolates submitted to NRL were serotyped, screened for antibiotic susceptibility and whole genome sequenced (Illumina) (**Deliverable.1.12**). The analysis of host risk factors associated with long-term shedding shows that the percentage of long-term shedders is higher (25%) than previously reported (1-2.2 %) (Gal-Mor O. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2018;32(1):e00088-18). Moreover, NIPH identified the main risk factors to become long term shedders (**Deliverable.1.12**):

- Younger people are *more at risk* (OR 3.5, 95%CI 1.05- 11.56)
- A lactose free diet (OR 5.19, 95%CI 1,21 - 22,31)
- Taking regular medication (OR 2.51, 95%CI 1,42 - 4,41)
- Taking food supplements, vitamins and health foods (OR 2.45, 95% CI 1,09 - 5,49)

No specific pathogen characteristic was identified: no association was found between serotype, sequence or Complex type and long-term shedding. The association with Fosfomycin resistance is tentative due to the small sample size. In conclusion, these results suggested that long term shedding seems more dependent of host factors than pathogen characteristics (**Deliverable.1.5**).

Recent studies indicate that transmission of *Salmonella* is controlled by indigenous intestinal microbiota. We had planned to select pairs of cases (Long-term shedders and Short-term shedders) that shared pathogen or host specific characteristics, with the aim to analyze the host microbiota. However, due to the shortening of the sample collection period, the sample size was considerably reduced and we were unable to perform analytical statistical analysis. The findings are based on univariable and descriptive analysis, and as result, the scientific merit of completing metagenomics is

compromised. As our assessment was that metagenomic analyses of fecal samples would not add weight to our descriptive findings, we have therefore concluded that more data is needed to substantiate the associations that have been uncovered in our study before metagenomics will add scientific value.

WP1-T4- Virulence of Salmonella strains originated from high and low shedders

The goal of the task was to determine whether the super and low-shedder phenotypes could be related to a modification of the virulence level of the *Salmonella* strains during infection.

In vitro virulence of *S. Typhimurium* and *S. Enteritidis* strains collected from super-shedders and low-shedders pigs (ANSES) and chickens (INRAE) were evaluated by INRAE in pig and chicken epithelial and macrophage cell lines.

Salmonella strains from two super-shedders and two low-shedders animals were used in each experiment in comparison with the strain, which was inoculated. INRAE evaluated *Salmonella* adhesion, invasion and intracellular multiplication to an intestinal pig epithelial cell line (IPEC-1) and a pig macrophage cell line (3D4) as well as with a chicken epithelial cell line (LMH). No differences were observed between *Salmonella* strains, whatever the serotype, for any of the parameters evaluated (Deliverable.1.5). In addition, the gene expression of pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory genes was evaluated. No differences were observed in the gene expression of CXCL8, IL8 or TGF β for any of the conditions evaluated. In conclusion, our data do not show any alteration in the *in vitro* virulence of *Salmonella* strains from super-shedder and low-shedder origin (Deliverable.1.14). These results strongly suggested that the super-shedder and low-shedder phenotypes are not related to a modification of the virulence level of the bacterial strains. These results are in line with those obtained in human (Deliverable.1.15).

WP2. Prevention of the appearance of Super-shedder animals and asymptomatic carriage in humans and animals by modifying feed and/or microbiota (M1-M12)

The goal of this WP was focused on the development of preventive and control measures. We tested especially the protective activity of pre-biotics, pro-biotics or nutraceutical formula and assess their effects on immune response, gut microbiota composition, gut physiology and animal performance.

WP2-T1- Development and use of probiotics in chickens and pigs

In this Task, we identified and characterized probiotics and tested their protective effect in pigs and chickens.

Four Partners were involved in this task (**VRI, UoS, NDRVMI and INRAE**), which were done with pigs and chickens in field and experimental conditions.

VRI has developed an extensive library of commensal bacteria from chicken gut, which currently consists of more than 450 isolates with known genomic sequences (https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Traces/study/?acc=SRP101913&o=acc_s%3Aa). These strains were used for oral inoculation of chicks on the day of hatching followed by verification of their presence 7 days later. The conclusion is that in this type of experimental design, bacterial species expressing outer membrane, i.e. Bacteroidetes, Proteobacteria and Veillonellaceae, can efficiently and persistently colonise chicken caeca. Rather unexpectedly, they never succeeded with the colonisation of newly hatched chicks with Gram positive bacteria from phylum Firmicutes and families Lachnospiraceae, Ruminococcaceae or Lactobacillaceae, despite the fact that these species are common microbiota members. Recently **VRI** changed the protocol for culture of gut anaerobes and this seems to provide novel opportunities for culture of yet unculturable species. This modification consisted of culture under microaerophilic conditions and using Karmali agar. Several experiments have been performed to understand 1- why the inoculation of Lachnospiraceae, Ruminococcaceae or Lactobacillaceae which are otherwise common in gut microbiota on chickens 1 to 2 weeks old, were unable to colonise chicks after oral inoculation and 2- the origin of these bacteria in the caeca of chickens.

Other experiments were performed to determine whether the colonisation of chicken intestine with some strains modified on the long term the faecal and/or caecal microbiota composition. For this purpose defined mixtures consisting of bacterial species which can colonise chicken caecum after a single dose on day of hatch were gradually tested in real commercial farms. Altogether, over 130 000 chickens were treated with different mixtures consisting mainly of different *Bacteroides*, *Prevotella* and *Megamonas* species. Due to the financial scopes, these experiments were co-funded also by other projects of **VRI**. Central issue when upscaling from laboratory to field level was the administration of chicken gut anaerobes to flocks consisting of more than 10, 000 chickens. This was done via drinking water, resuspension of liquid cultures to pre-starter feed, jellyfying liquid probiotic cultures before their spread over the pre-starter feed or even feed fermentation by the probiotic strains. The control of gut colonisation showed that tested probiotic strains persist in the caeca of treated broilers till day 35 of life. Moreover, since some of the flocks were formed by reproductive birds, bacterial species were detected in these flocks till week 20 of their life. Thus, the persistence of selected and tested species seemed to be quite long if not permanent (**Deliverable.2.3; D.2.6; D2.5**).

UoS isolated a large panel of potential probiotic candidates from pig faeces. Following identification by 16s and basic *in vitro* characterisation a subpanel was selected for further study. A panel of 30 lactobacilli were phenotypically and genotypically characterised. These studies included growth curves, survival in acid/bile, whole genome sequencing and tissue culture studies (pig cell line) to determine safety and inhibitory ability of whole cells and CFS against *Salmonella* adhesion/invasion (ongoing). To date the studies have indicated that a number of strains are suitable probiotics that meet the EFSA requirements. Four probiotic strains (2 isolated from chicken faeces in a related project) and 2 isolated from pig) were sent to Bulgaria (**NDRVMI**) for efficacy evaluation in chickens and pigs, respectively (**Deliverable.2.3; D.2.6**). If required, strain will also be shared with the EU AVANT H2020 project."

NDRVMI has analysed the effect in field conditions of several probiotics and prebiotics obtained from the **UoS**. They used 4 groups of day-old broilers (18,160 in each group). In groups with probiotics 1 and 2, the birds were raised without antibiotics, as well as any other side effects. Growth rates and food consumption were also excellent and mortality was a little lower than in the control group (where antibiotics were still used). In the third experimental group, where probiotics 1 and 2 were used and a prebiotic was added to stimulate probiotic microorganisms, there were some issues in the middle of the experiment with a sharp increase in mortality observed, this was due to the presence of a pathogenic strain of *E. coli* and for 5 days they were treated with an antibiotic after which the mixture of probiotic 1 and 2 and prebiotic were delivered until the time of slaughter. This group was not a linear hybrid Ross like the other groups, but a linear hybrid Cobb, which appeared to be much more susceptible to disease. The experiment was repeated only with this compromised third group and the control, as the linear hybrid was Ross. Probiotics were used on farms with a long history of *Salmonella* infection and periodic treatment with antibiotics allows the birds to be free of *salmonella* at the time of slaughter. It is noteworthy that *Salmonella* were not detected only in group with probiotic 1, which leads us to think that probiotic 1 has a more pronounced anti-*Salmonella* effect in the gastrointestinal tract. However, the combination of the two probiotics did not result in the elimination of *S. Infantis* throughout the growing period (**Deliverable.2.5; D.2.7**). Moreover, in the group with both probiotics and prebiotic a reduced incidence of intestinal disorders and better food conversion ratios was observed compared to the control group (**Deliverable.2.5; D.2.6 ; D.2.7**).

The experiments with pigs started on September 2020, when 3 experimental groups of weaned pigs were formed, 25 in a group and transferred to individual boxes without a connection between boxes. An additional group of pigs of the same age, reared conventionally (in the same way as those receiving the intervention) on the farm, were used as controls. The pigs in all four experimental groups received the same feed etc., with the only difference being the respective probiotic or a mixture of the two probiotics tested with the addition of prebiotic fed through the drinking water. Particular attention was paid to the safety of supplying a sufficient amount of water containing at least one billion living cells in a milliliter of broth culture dissolved in drinking water. It should be noted that treatment of pigs with *Lactobacillus reuteri* SAP 3319 or a combination of both probiotics and a prebiotic resulted

in a reduced incidence of intestinal disorders and the absence of *Salmonella* in the faeces (**Deliverable.2.5 ; D.2.6 ; D.2.7**).

After completion of the experiment with the broilers and the pigs, all samples were sent to the **UoS** for 16s microbial community analysis, which is ongoing (**Deliverable.2.8 ; D.2.9**).

In WP1 **INRAE** identified *Enterococcus faecium* as a predictive biomarker for the most resistant phenotype. To test the protective activity of this commensal bacteria against *Salmonella* colonization, a candidate *E. faecium* strain was isolated, purified and orally inoculated to a group of 30 chicks reared in a large isolator (CFU=1x10⁹ per chick) at 1 and 6 days of age (i.e. before *Salmonella* infection) (**Deliverable.2.3**). However, no significant difference was observed between the *Salmonella* shedding levels of the *E. faecium*-inoculated and control groups (at any time point). To go further we tested the impact of four commensal bacteria containing *E. Faecium* but also *E. coli*, *Lactobacillus* and *Clostridium* strains. When administrated the day of hatching, this cocktail induced a partial protection against *Salmonella* infection at 7 days of age (**Deliverable.2.5**). The data obtained shows the protective effect of the four commensal bacteria on *Salmonella* excretion and their major impact, on the long term, on gut microbiota composition and immune response. This study paved the way for developing a protective mix of probiotics. An article describing this work has been accepted for publication in Microbial Biotechnol. The impact of the four commensal bacteria on the gut microbiota composition and the immune response was done by **INRAE** with a 16S metabarcoding approach in collaboration with **VRI** and with the Biomark approach. One publication is in preparation (**Deliverable.2.5; D.2.6 ; D.2.10**).

WP2-T2- Use of pre-biotics and nutraceutical already defined by the consortium partners in chicken and pig

The goal of this Task is to measure the effect of several pre-biotics and nutraceuticals on intestinal barrier, gut microbiota composition and protection against pathogens in farms and in experimental conditions.

Mainly three Partners (**VRI, VISAVET-UCM and NDRVMI**) were involved in this task, which was undertaken with pigs and chickens in field and experimental conditions.

To identify bacterial species, which are dependent on particular supplements or growth substrates, **VRI** tested specific supplementation of nutrient broths used for growth of commensal strains. At the beginning of the experiment, caecal contents of adult hen are decimally diluted and inoculated to nutrient broth. Nutrient broths are then anaerobically incubated and after 3 days, microbiota composition is determined by 16S rRNA sequencing. WCHA agar and BHI medium supplemented with lactate, glucose, starch, cellulose, mucin, bile salts, panthenol, biotin, vitamin B12 or whole vitamin B complex were tested. In addition, in the last experiment **VRI** inoculated BHI supplemented with sodium acetate, propionate, lactate, succinate, pyruvate, fumarate, ascorbate, glucose, maltose, saccharose, trehalose, fucose, rhamnose, pectin and inulin. These experiments allowed us to i) determine metabolic potential of individual gut microbiota members, ii) define conditions under which it had been possible to enrich target gut anaerobes and obtain them in pure cultures (see WP2-T1) and iii) map characteristics of different supplements which can be used as prebiotics (**Deliverable.2.6**).

VISAVET-UCM tested the protective effect of fermented defatted “alperujo” against *Salmonella* infection in chickens. The objective of these experiments was to analyze the modification of the microbiota and intestinal mucosa changes before and after the challenging, comparing treated and control groups.

The first experiments performed with laying hens demonstrated the positive effect of fermented defatted “alperujo”. Indeed, a significant increase of duodenal villi height and crypt depth (duodenum and cecum) was observed in the treated group at early life stages. A higher abundance of Actinobacteria, Firmicutes and Proteobacteria was also assessed in the treated group at early life stages as well as decreased number of broken eggs in the treated group (**Deliverable.2.6**).

A second experiment performed with broilers leads to similar conclusion. Significant increase of duodenal villi height was observed in the treated group from 14 to 35 days-old, as well as significant body weight increase at 35 days-old. Fermented defatted “alperujo” consumption also favours microbiota modulation, that may control the spread of pathogenic bacteria by means of competitive exclusion.

Several experiments have demonstrated, *in vitro*, the effect of “alperujo” on *Salmonella*. To test its effect *in vivo*, chicks were divided in two groups: one that was fed with conventional feed and a second one that was fed with “alperujo” since their arrival. After a week of adaptation, animals were challenged with a *Salmonella* strain resistant to colistin. Besides, a subgroup of animals was challenged after 21 days consuming the “alperujo”. The analysis of the data shows a significant reduction of *Salmonella* in the cecum, with both traditional culture and qPCR approaches, at 7 and 14 dpi. However, no significant differences were observed at 21, 28, and 35 dpi (28, 35, and 42 days old, respectively) in the cecal *Salmonella* load among groups by culture ($p > 0.05$) or by qPCR ($p > 0.05$) (see Figure) (**Deliverable.2.7**).

Figure 1. Results of the *Salmonella* spp. count in selective agar in broilers challenged with *Salmonella* Typhimurium at day 7 (purple lines) and day 21 (red lines) of life. Continuous lines represent control groups, whereas discontinuous lines represent treated groups, fed with fermented defatted ‘alperujo’. The *Salmonella* spp. count by culture (CFU/g) is shown on the vertical axis, and samplings (7, 14, 21, 35, or 42) on the horizontal axis.

The intestinal histopathology measures revealed only few differences in the duodenum between the control and the treated group. In the caeca, there was a reduction in the intensity of lamina propria lymphocytic infiltration and GALT hyperplasia in the treated group compared to the control group. In 7-day-old challenged chickens, duodenum villi height was significantly improved in treated chickens on days 7, 14, 28, 35, and 42 ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, the crypts in the duodenum were deeper in all treated samplings ($p < 0.05$). Regarding ceca morphology, crypts were seen to be deeper in 7-, 21- and 42-day-old treated chickens ($p < 0.05$) but not at 28 days of life. Broilers in the treated group challenged at 21 days of age showed a significant improvement in the duodenum villi height at 28, 35, and 42 days of life ($p < 0.05$). The depth of the crypts in the duodenum was significantly improved by the treatment on days 28 and 42 ($p < 0.05$). The cecal crypt was deeper in treated chickens on days 35 and 42 of life ($p < 0.05$).

Treatment with fermented defatted “alperujo” has no significant impact on caecal microbiota (**Deliverable.2.8**). In chickens challenged at 7 or at 21 days of age, there were no statistically-significant differences among the groups established.

[WP3. Modelling the transmission of zoonotic agents to improve intervention strategies on livestock farms \(M1-M12\)](#)

The third WP was focused on the development of multiscale computational models (from within-host to between- host scale) of heterogeneous pathogen transmission by integrating data from WP1 and 2

and already available datasets by consortium partners in order to design and assess intervention strategies. The models was designed to allow assessment of the efficiency and/or cost-effectiveness of different intervention strategies.

WP3-T1- Transmission modelling at within-host and between-host scales

The goal of the task was to develop simplified, but relevant models of the host including key features of the gut microbiota dynamics and key features of the immune system response.

Three partners (NCOH-WU, INRA-Jouy, WUR-WBVR) were involved in this Task with fruitful discussion with the other partners.

WP3-T1-ST1- Within-host scale: modelling individual responses and shedding

INRAE-Jouy designed a generic mathematical model of the dynamic interplay between the gut microbiota, the pathogen and the host's immune response at the within and between-host scale. A paper has been published (**Deliverable.3.1**).

To improve the model with a better representation of the microbiota and pathogen dynamic, **INRAE-Jouy** completed the realization of a C++ software and the corresponding Matlab and R plugins allowing to analyse time series of microbial concentrations. This software implements a non parametric, robust inference approach for fitting Generalized Lotka-Volterra_model on time series data. It will be made publicly available in a near future on INRAE gitlab repository (<https://forgemia.inra.fr/>), a publication is currently being written.

The model was used to analyze a first set of time series of gut microbiota composition in chicken (with **INRAE-Tours** and **VRI**) in order to infer interactions between the pathogen (here *Salmonella*) and the resident microbiota. However, the results were not satisfactory because the time series were very short. In collaboration with **UoS** and **INRAE-Tours** we recently started analysing longer microbiota time series from WP1 (ANSES pig experiment) with this software, together with other data analysis approaches, to better understand and model the interplay between of the immune response and the microbiota. To conclude, this task allowed the development of original epidemic models and methods for data analysis. However, the opportunity to work on the pig data came very late in the course of the project, so we will be able to provide an output on data analysis only close or after the end of the project.

WP3-T1-ST2- Between-host scale: modelling transmission, linked to within-host results

Mathematical modelling analyses were carried out of the outcomes of tailor-made experiments studying the indirect transmission of *Campylobacter* between broilers. In previous research also consisting of a combination of experiments and mathematical modelling, a mathematical model of indirect transmission of bacteria between broilers was developed. This model assumes that bacteria are transferred from inoculated animals (source animals) to spatially separated susceptible animals (recipient animals) through random displacement of infectious material in the environment in combination with a loss of viability of the bacteria in time. Technically this model uses diffusion equations to describe the random displacement of material in the environment between the source and recipient animals. New experiments carried out during the MoMIR –PPC project served to validate and refine this mathematical model by testing predictions in an experimental setting, and to do so consisted of four different spatial setups that were each studied in two repeat animal rooms. . The refined model can be used for designing and quantitatively assessing candidate bio-security based intervention strategies against indirect transmission of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* (**Deliverable.3.2**).

This model not only allows to test biosecurity/hygiene measures, but also offers desired biological insight. In particular it explains the distance-dependence of the indirect transmission rate observed in the experiments, as well as an observed distance-dependent time delay of transmission. The model does so using only three parameters: 1) a 'loss-of-viability' rate describing how fast the pathogen is becoming inactivated in the environment; 2) a diffusion coefficient describing how the spatial distribution of infectious material in the environment changes in time; 3) a transmission parameter

summarizing host-dependent processes (shedding and dose response). As a consequence, the model enables to quantify processes occurring in the environment separately from host-dependent processes.

WP3-T2- Interventions strategies: Identification and evaluation tools.

The goal of the task was to include the different other intervention strategies with those described in WP3-T1. Three partners (WUR-WLR, WUR-WEcR and INRAE) were involved in this Task.

WP3-T2-ST1- Systematic inventory of relevant intervention measures

A systematic inventory of relevant intervention measures against *Salmonella* in broilers and laying hens has been developed.

WP3-T2-ST2- Inclusion of potential interventions into the modelling

At within-host scale, INRAE-Jouy obtained first encouraging results on the use of microbiota and inflammatory response data in ANSES pig experiment to discriminate pigs according to their shedding pattern, in collaboration with UoS and INRAE-Tours. A publication is currently started. The resulting knowledge, as well as knowledge from probiotic strategies in WP2 will be used in the future to include probiotic based strategies in the model developed in WP3-T1-ST1.

WP3-T2-ST3- Development of economic analysis tools

The economic analysis tools allow to evaluate the cost effectiveness (utility) of intervention strategies using probiotics to reduce *Campylobacter* prevalence in broilers. The work performed by WUR WEcR has been done with results of other MOMIR-PPC work packages and model developed in CamCon1 (EU 7th framework programme). The tools determine the cost per averted disease burden (in €/Disability-Adjusted Life Year, DALY), by taking into account the attribution of DALY's to broiler sector, and correcting for import/export. The cost-utility is obtained by calculating the cost per averted disease burden as a function of the on-farm efficacy. The model has been parameterized for four different European countries (Denmark, Netherlands, Poland, Spain) spanning a range of differently structured poultry sectors: taking into account differences in technical and economic farm performance, and scale of poultry production. A scientific paper has been published (**Deliverable.3.3 ; D.3.5 ; D.3.6**). The main results obtained with the model suggested:

- Assuming an efficacy between 10% and 20%, costs per avoided DALY were lowest in Poland and Spain (4,000–30,000 Euro per avoided DALY) and highest in the Netherlands and Denmark (70,000–340,000 Euro per avoided DALY)
- In Poland and Spain, using probiotics is a moderately expensive intervention if efficacy is more than 10%, otherwise it is relatively expensive
- In the Netherlands and Denmark, using probiotics is a relatively expensive intervention irrespective of efficacy
- However, if probiotics were assumed to enhance broiler performance, the intervention would become relatively cost-effective even at low efficacy levels of 1 to 10%.

WP4. Communication and Dissemination for Impact (M1-M12)

WP4-T1- Dissemination of data within the project and management of data

Participation to the OHEJP-ASM conferences in Dublin (2019) and to the virtual conferences (2020 and 2021) with several posters and conferences.

As described in the report, Partners have exchanged for analysis numerous samples and thus the corresponding data from animal experiments. A synthetic Excel file summarized the animal experiments as well as the samples recovered (**Deliverable.4.3**). UoS and VRI have sequenced the samples from pigs and chickens, respectively. UoS, INRAE-Tours and VRI Have analyzed the data and thus the gut microbiota composition of the different samples. VISAVET-UCM has performed

histological analyses, INRAE-Tours has performed virulence assays with strains recovered by other Partners. INRAE-Tours and ISS have performed immune responses analyses. UoS, IZLER and ISS have sequenced and analyzed the data and thus the gut microbiota composition of the different samples. IZLER and NDRVMI have performed field experiments with strains of UoS. Data obtained by other Partners during experimental infections have been sent to INRAE-Jouy and to U. Wageningen. Consequently, an impressive collaboration has made it possible to analyze many parameters of the in vivo experiments performed with pigs and chickens.

WP4-T2- Dissemination of data outside the project and management of data

Participation to several congresses outside the EJP. Several articles have been accepted for publication in open access journals (**Deliverable.4.4**). These articles often involved two or more partners. Several joint articles are in preparation. Due to the COVID-19 crisis the high strategic meeting has been cancelled and the budget devoted to this activity has been reimburse to EJP (INRAE) and (NCOH)). After the international lockdown, we will disseminate our results in international congresses and to stakeholders (**Deliverable.4.5**).

3. Project Self-assessment

The vast majority of the planned objectives are achieved despite the many problems encountered during the project, and thanks to the time extension granted to us.

An **exceptional extension of 12 months** of the project at no extra expense has been indeed obtained by the EJP Project Management Team. This extension was motivated by:

- The withdrawal of SAIM from the EJP consortium after the approval of our project. Part of the work has been performed by INRAE with the help of a Post doctorant.
- Astrid-Louise Webster has left the NIPH, just before the beginning of the project, so that we have adapted the project with Anke-Stüken. These modifications have delayed the ethics committee approvals, resulting of one year delay in the human experiments, but the majority of the aims have been achieved.
- The fact that after the beginning of the project, Vet-DTU has been closed by its Government. To compensate for this loss, we looked for new partners in the EJP consortium and in June 2018 (6 months after the beginning of the project), H. Daskalov (NDRVMI) has joined our consortium. Consequently, part of the work related to WP2 has been delayed by one year.
- Finally, several partners had had difficulties to obtain the ethics committee approval for animal experiments, which has also delayed some experiments.

Moreover, a supplementary **6 months extension**, in addition to our previously 1 year extension has been obtained because some partners have been highly impacted by the COVID-19 crisis. Indeed, several experiments had been cancelled or postponed (especially those with humans and in field conditions) due to the lockdown. Finally, the cancellation of all the meetings has led us to cancel the high strategic meeting with stakeholders (the money was returned). **This project led to:**

- Reproduce the different shedding patterns in all the animal species and with all the models developed.
- Original and interesting results, which allow better understanding of the heterogeneity of excretion and to predict and differentiate between these different shedding phenotypes. These results have been or will be published in international scientific journals and at OHEJP ASM congresses (1st, 2nd, 3rd ed.). The project allowed the development of original epidemic mathematical models and methods for data analysis.
- Important and fruitful exchanges, where one partner analyzed the samples from another partner and which led to joint articles. Moreover, the exchanges between experimental

scientists and mathematicians offers a great opportunity to test our methods on very complete datasets.

Several difficulties have been detected regarding the variability of the gut microbiota composition of chicks from one experiment to another, which raises the question of how can we standardise or normalise the gut microbiota of farm animals? Another observation has been that analysis of immune response in blood of chicks seems less relevant than the mucosal immune response (this is not true for pigs).

Several interesting results have been obtained from a One Health perspective, but as different protocols and methods were used in pigs, chickens and humans, it has been difficult to generalize the results obtained in humans to farm animals and vice versa.

4. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments <i>(Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)</i>	Proposed categories* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
10	D.0.1	Project initiation, Kick off meeting, Project-planning and management documentation	2	2		https://zenodo.org/record/5079519#.YOWoQzNxdPY	
10	D.0.2	Approved and signed Consortium Agreement	6	1		This has been done at the EJP level	
10	D.0.3	Minutes of project meetings (Kick off, midterm and final meeting)	2, 13, 24	2, 24, 41		https://zenodo.org/record/3685528#.XIOVuWhKiUk	report
10	D.0.4	Financial and scientific reports for the EJP Coordinator (Intermediated report)	12, 24	12, 24, 36, 42		https://zenodo.org/record/3685530#.XIOV_WhKiUk	report
10	D-1.1	Panel of immunological markers to assess in pig and chicken	3	6		https://zenodo.org/record/5082034#.YOblwzNxdPY	3

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
10	D-1.2	Development of the immune-signature chips	12			This deliverable has been cancelled due to the left of SAIM at the beginning of the project (see new version of June 2018).	
10	D-1.3	Identification of risk factors for shedding of <i>Salmonella</i> in pigs and poultry farms	12	41		https://zenodo.org/record/5081949#.YObAjjNxdPY Another article is in preparation	5
10	D-1.4	Identification and purification of commensal bacteria present before <i>Salmonella</i> colonization in low shedders (first round)	12	36		https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc	3
10	D-1.4	Identification and purification of commensal bacteria present before <i>Salmonella</i> colonization in low shedders (second round)	20	41		https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc	3
10	In AWP2021 : D-1.04	<i>In vitro</i> virulence levels of different <i>Salmonella</i> strains recovered from	36	41		this deliverable has been merged with D-JRP10-1.5 Confidential	8 report

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		high and low shedders in animals and humans (first round)					
10	D-1.5	<i>In vitro</i> virulence levels of different <i>Salmonella</i> strains recovered from high and low shedders in animals and humans (second round)	36	41		https://zenodo.org/record/5082103#.YObSKTNxdPY CO: until the publication. Only a short version has been uploaded on Zenodo Joint publication is in preparation with ANSES, UoS and INRAE (in AWP2021 : D-1.05)	8 report
10	D-1.6	Definition of predictive immunological markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and in pigs.	20, 34	36		this deliverable has been merged with D-JRP10-1.7	
10	D-1.7	Definition of immunological markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and in pigs.	20, 34	36		https://zenodo.org/record/5079723#.YOWv1zNxdPY CO: until the publication. Only a short version has been uploaded on Zenodo Joint publication is in preparation with ANSES, UoS and INRAE	1 ; 7 ; 8 report
10	D-1.8	Characterization, evolution and comparison of the microbiome of pig and poultry with different shedding status of	18	NO		Delayed due to COVID-19, No clear comparison can be done due to the differences in age between chicks and pigs. No Deliverable	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		<i>Salmonella</i>					
10	D-1.9	Definition of predictive microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and in pigs.	40	36		(in AWP2021 : D-1.09) https://zenodo.org/record/5082178#.YObcrzNxdPY One publication accepted on chicks https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc , others are in preparation	1 ; 7 ; 8 report
10	D-1.10	Definition of microbiota markers associated to the high and low shedders in chickens and in pigs.	40	36		This Deliverable has been merged with D1.9 One publication accepted: https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc , others are in preparation	1 ; 7 ; 8 report
10	D-JRP10-1.11	Recovery of all human samples	42	42		Delayed due to COVID-19, This Deliverable has been merged with D1.12	3
10	D-JRP10-1.12	Antimicrobial susceptibility testing, serotyping and whole genome sequencing of all <i>Salmonella</i> isolates from participants submitted to the	34	42		Delayed due to COVID-19, https://zenodo.org/record/5078733#.YOWeazNxdPY A manuscript is in preparation	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		Norwegian Reference laboratory					
10	D-1.12	Identification risk factors for patients with long term shedding	20	42		Due to change of project leaders at the NIPH,, this Deliverable has been modified and merged with the D-JRP10-1.12 (see version of June 2018).	
10	D-1.13	Description of the differences in immunological, gut-microbiota markers but also in resistome before and after travel to high-risk areas	22		cancelled	Due to change of project leaders at the NIPH, this Deliverable has been cancelled	
10	D-1.14	Identification, from <i>in vitro</i> studies, of immune parameters related to high and low shedders	42	36		This Deliverable has been merged with D1.7 No difference has been detected in chicks. One joint publication is in preparation	8 report
10	D-1.15	Understanding whether high and low shedder phenotypes are mainly related to <i>Salmonella</i> strain variation, immune status, or microbiota composition.	24	42		https://zenodo.org/record/5079547#.YOWqITNxdPY One joint publication is in preparation	report

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
10	D.1.16	A predictor, based on the designed set of mimotopes, using machine learning techniques to discriminate between the diagnostic groups.	24		cancelled	This deliverable has been cancelled due to the left of SAIM at the beginning of the project (see new version of June 2018). The immunoglobulin response cannot be used as a predictive factor	
10	D-2.1	<i>In vitro</i> effect of already characterized probiotics on <i>Salmonella</i> growth and cell invasion	36	42		Delayed due to COVID-19, (in AWP2021 : D2.01) CO: until the publication. Only a short version has been uploaded on Zenodo https://zenodo.org/record/5085459#.YOhVtzNxdPY	8 report
10	D-JRP10-2.11	Evolution of the immune-signature in pig, chicken and/ or human according to the context (infection, treatment...)	34	36		This Deliverable has been merged with D2.10 The immunoglobulin response cannot be used as a predictive factor	report
10	D.2.2	Description of the microbiome and resistome in farms	12, 36	46		The experiment has been delayed due to the COVID-19. The experiments have been completed. The gut microbiota were sequenced, Data analysis is ongoing This Deliverable has been merged with D-2.8	

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
10	D-2.3	Characterization of protective commensal bacteria able to inhibit <i>Salmonella</i> colonization (two rounds)	40	40		https://zenodo.org/record/5082203#.YObhrDNxdPY One article accepted for chicken, https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc One joint publication on pigs is in preparation (in AWP2021 : D2.04)	7,8
10	D-2.4	Determine the influence of defined and undefined probiotics on the microbiome signature, the immune response, gut physiology and welfare of pig and/ or chicken	42	42		This deliverable has been merged with D-JRP10-2.5 (in AWP2021 : D2.05)	7
10	D-2.5	Impact of defined and undefined probiotics on <i>Salmonella</i> colonization in pig and chicken	42	42		https://zenodo.org/record/5082213#.YObjrTNxdPY (in AWP2021 : D2.06) One article accepted https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc One article in preparation.	7
10	D.2.6	Impact of pre-biotics or feed on the immune parameters, the microbiome and resistome, gut	42	42		This Deliverable has been merged with D2.08 (D2.7) (in AWP2021 : D2.07) One article accepted. https://zenodo.org/record/4114070 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.07.015	7

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		physiology and welfare of pig and chicken.				https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics8040215 https://zenodo.org/record/3648214#.XvyTJygZM0	
10	D.2.7	Impact of pre-biotics or feed on <i>Salmonella</i> colonization in pig, chicken and human. Effect on the super-shedders and low-shedders.	42	36		https://zenodo.org/record/5079336#.YOWkYDNxdPY (in AWP2021 : D2.08) One article accepted. https://zenodo.org/record/4114070	7
10	D.2.8	Dynamics of the microbiome and resistome in the different groups and conditions	24	46		The experiments have been delayed due to the COVID-19. They are now completed. The gut microbiota were sequenced, Data analysis is ongoing This Deliverable has been merged with D-2.2	5
10	D.2.9	Validation of immunological and microbiota markers, identified in WP1 and associated to high/low shedding, in the control groups of WP2	24		No done	Delayed due to COVID-19, The great variability in the gut microbiota composition hampered us to conclude.	
10	D.2.10	Evolution of the immune-signature in pig, chicken and/ or	20	42		https://zenodo.org/record/5079202#.YOWilzNxdPY Delayed due to COVID-19, One article in preparation	5

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		human according to the context (infection, treatment...)				Not done for human	
10	D.2.11	Differences in the resistome before and after travel to high-risk areas and after pre-biotic administration	24		cancelled	Due to change of project leaders at the NIPH, this Deliverable has been cancelled (see version of June 2018)	
10	D-3.1	Models at within-host scale taking into account the interactions between infection and microbiota and mechanisms of interventions	22	42		https://doi.org/10.1051/proc/202067015 https://zenodo.org/record/4244169#.X6KF4TiWxM0	5
10	D-3.2	Models at between-host scale, linking to the within-host modelling and taking into account the mechanisms of interventions	22	42		https://doi.org/10.1051/proc/202067015 https://zenodo.org/record/4244169#.X6KF4TiWxM0	5, 7
10	D-3.3	Intervention measures inventory	40		46	(in AWP2021 : D3.03) https://zenodo.org/record/5500249#.YTtd-YgzY2w	5, 7

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
10	D-3.4	Economic analysis tools combined with D-JRP10-3.06	30			(in AWP2021 :D3.04) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.05.003 https://zenodo.org/record/4244748#.X6LaalhKjcc	
10	D-3.5	Definition of intervention measures to target super-shedders	42			(in AWP2021 :D3.05) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.07.015	5, 7
10	D-3.6	Evaluation scheme for cost effectiveness of the intervention strategies combined with D-JRP10-3.04	30			(in AWP2021 :D3.06) https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.05.003 https://zenodo.org/record/4244748#.X6LaalhKjcc	5, 7
10	D-4.1	Development and production of MOMIR-PPC website	4	12		We have used the EJP website	
10	D-4.2	Data management policy and strategies	4	42		The final DMP version has been sent	report
10	D-4.3	Creation of a database of each animal group included in the study (age, conformation, diet, clinical status,	2	36		https://zenodo.org/record/5082319#.YObuYDNxdPY Only a short version has been uploaded on Zenodo	3

JRP/JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Date delivered on Project Group website	If deliverable not submitted: Forecast delivery date	Comments (Please mention: Zenodo reference and other comments)	Proposed categories* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		previous antibiotic treatments, infectious status, etc.)					
10	D-4.4	Publication, and presentation at conferences	24	42		Information included in this report, see paragraph 5: Publication and additional output... Several publications will be finished after the end of the project	5
10	D-4.5	Dissemination to lay-public communities, to policy-makers and regulators, farmers and companies	24	42		Information included in this report, see paragraph 8. Several disseminations will be finished after the end of the project	5

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify); 9. This is supportive to an integrative activity; 10. This is not an integrative activity

Milestones

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.1	Update of the members of the steering committee and of the leader and deputy leader for the WPs and tasks	2	yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.2	Organization of the consortium kick off meeting	1	yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.3	Protocols and ethical committee requests for the different experiments	1	yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.4	Recovery of samples from the first round of experimentally infected animals	8	Yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.5	Identification and selection of farms	4	yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.6	Recovery of samples from selected farms ; Identification of super-shedders and low-shedders in poultry and pig farms	8	yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.7	Comparison of immune response of high and low shedders in chickens and pigs	11	Yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.8	Histological characterization of different intestinal lesions between high and low shedder in chickens and pigs. Immunohistochemical	12	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		studies on intestinal mucosa.				
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.9	Comparison of microbiota composition of high and low shedders in chickens and pigs.	11	Yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.10	Comparison of the predictive markers obtained in pigs with those obtained in chickens.	12	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.11 (or 10?)	In vitro infection of cell lines and organoids with the <i>Salmonella</i> strains recovered from high and low shedders in animals and humans (from the first experiments)	36	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.12	Comparison of the transcriptomic immune response induced in vitro between different strains to identify immunological markers	12	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.13	Four sets of NGS derived 105 mimotope sequences – positively and negatively enriched in IgM and IgA	8	NO		Due to the left of SAIM, this milestone has been cancelled. The role of immunoglobulin levels was investigated, but these levels cannot be used neither as a predictive marker nor as a marker to differentiate between shedding phenotypes
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.14	A selected set of 100 mimotopes for the immune-signature chips.	12	NO		Due to the left of SAIM, this milestone has been cancelled (see version of June 2018). The role of immunoglobulin levels was investigated, but these levels cannot be used

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
						neither as a predictive marker nor as a marker to differentiate between shedding phenotypes
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.15	Inclusion and sampling of volunteers	12	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.16	Selective cultivation of commensal bacteria correlated to low shedding in pig and/ or chicken	10	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.17	Define the panel of probiotics for use in pigs and chickens	2	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.18	Define the panel of pre-biotics and feed for use in pigs, chickens and humans	2	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.19	Recovery of samples from experimentally infected animals and from farms, pretreated with pre-biotics or neutraceuticals	8	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.20	First version of within-host models completed	12	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.21	First version of between-host models completed	12	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.22	First inventory of intervention measures completed	12	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.23 (or 21?)	First version of economic analysis tools completed	12	Yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.23 (or 22)	Organization of consortium meetings (intermediate and closure)	40	Yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.24 (or 12 ?)	Comparison of immune response of high and low shedders in chickens and pigs	36	Yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.25	MALDI ToF Imaging processing and workflow on the paraffin wax slides of intestine wall in high and low shedder from chickens and pigs	18	In part		Only the histological analyses were done on all samples
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.26	Comparison of microbiota composition of high and low shedders in chickens and pigs.	18	yes		
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.27	Comparison of the predictive markers obtained in pigs with those obtained in chickens.	19	yes		Poor correlations have been observed due to the different ages of pigs and chickens
10	M-FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.28	In vitro infection of several cell lines and organoids with the different <i>Salmonella</i> strains recovered from high and low shedders in animals and humans (second round)	18	Yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.29	Comparison of the transcriptomic immune response induced in vitro between different strains to identify immunological markers	20	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.30	Comparison of the immune signature of high and low shedders in chicken and pig.	18	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.31	Inclusion and sampling of volunteers	15	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.32	First selective cultivation of <i>Salmonella</i> from human rectal swabs to be use in WP1	13	NO		The experiment with human was postponed due to the COVID-19. The <i>Salmonella</i> strains were not included in the analysis
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.33	Recovery of samples from experimentally infected animals and from farms, pretreated with probiotics	16	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.34	Updated version of within-host models completed	21	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.35	Updated version of between-host models completed	21	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.22 (or 32?)	Final inventory of intervention measures completed	39	yes		

JRP/JIP Code	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.36	Updated version of economic analysis tools completed	22	Yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.37	Potential interventions included in between-host modelling	22	yes		
10	M-J FBZ3-MOMIR-PPC.38	Organization of the high strategy meeting	24	NO		Due to the lockdown, this meeting has been cancelled and the money returned

5. Publications and patents

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
A Multi-Scale Epidemic Model of <i>Salmonella</i> infection with Heterogeneous Shedding. A first draft was accessible on HAL repository. https://doi.org/10.1051/proc/202067015 https://zenodo.org/record/4244169#.X6KF4TiWxMO	YES	GREEN 0 MONTHS	
Reduction of <i>Salmonella</i> Typhimurium Cecal Colonisation and Improvement of Intestinal Health in Broilers Supplemented with Fermented Defatted 'Alperujo', an Olive Oil By-Product. 10.3390/ani10101931 https://zenodo.org/record/4114070	YES		GOLD – 1,334.20 €
Cost-effectiveness analysis of using probiotics to control <i>Campylobacter</i> in broilers (submitted). https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.05.003 https://zenodo.org/record/4244748#.X6LaalhKjcc https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.07.015	YES		GOLD – 2000 €
Dietary Supplementation with Fermented Defatted 'Alperujo' Induces Modifications of the Intestinal Mucosa and Cecal Microbiota of Broiler Chickens. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.07.015 https://zenodo.org/record/4017817#.X6LRiYhKjcc	YES		GOLD – 1 720 €

Publication title, DOI reference and Zenodo reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing charges (in €)
Effects on Intestinal Mucosal Morphology, Productive Parameters and Microbiota Composition after Supplementation with Fermented Defatted Alperujo (FDA) in Laying Hens. https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics8040215 https://zenodo.org/record/3648214#.XvyTJygZM0	No		GOLD – 435.89 €
Gut microbiota composition before infection determines the <i>Salmonella</i> super- and low-shedder phenotypes in chicken. https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.13621 https://zenodo.org/record/4005830#.X0kCUMgzbcc	YES		GOLD – 2 100 €

Additional output

2018

Oral presentation

A spatially structured model to investigate key drivers of the gut microbiota biogeography" B. Laroche, S. Labarthe et al. Oral presentation MB2 workshop in Besançon, 2018, "Modelling the gut microbiota"

2019

Poster

F. Kempf, P. Menanteau, I. Rychlik, E. Guitton, J. Trotereau, I. Virlogeux-Payant, P. Velge (2019). *Faecal gut microbiota composition of chicks can predict resistance to Salmonella Enteritidis colonization*. Poster communication at Gordon Research Conference "Molecular Mechanisms, Evolution and Treatment of *Salmonella*"

Poster in OHEJP ASM 2019. Rebollada-Merino, A.; Ugarte-Ruiz, M.; Mayoral-Alegre, F.J.; Maasoumi-Nouha, N.; Tomé-Sánchez, I.; Rivero, E.; Porrás-González, N.; García, M.; Domínguez, L.; Rodríguez-Bertos, A. Changes on Caecal Mucosa Morphology and Microbiota in Laying Hens Supplemented with a Nutraceutical Product Obtained from Olive Oil Production.

2020

Poster

Participation to the ASM virtual EJP OneHealth meeting (UoS, INRAE)

Metagenomic Analysis of The Pig Gut Microbiota and association with *Salmonella* status. Poster. Guido Cordoni, Daniel L Horton, Helen Louise Brown, Roberto La Ragione

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342123925> Metagenomic Analysis of The Pig Gut Microbiota and association with *Salmonella* status/stats

Metagenomic Analysis of The Pig Gut Microbiota and Association With *Salmonella* Status. Presentation. RCE 2020 event at UoS. Guido Cordoni, Daniel L Horton, Helen Louise Brown, Roberto La Ragione.

<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346943667> Metagenomic Analysis of The Pig Gut Microbiota and Association With *Salmonella* Status

Velge P. Faecal gut microbiota composition determines susceptibility to *Salmonella* Enteritidis primo-colonization. ." One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting, Virtual, Pragues, 27th-29th May 2020.

Poster in OHEJP ASM 2020. Rebollada-Merino, A.; Ugarte-Ruiz, M.; Miguela-Villoldo, P.; Fernández-Manzano, A.; García, N.; Gómez, S.; Bárcena, C.; de Juan, L.; Domínguez, L.; Rodríguez-Bertos, A. Fermented Defatted Alperujo (FDA) Reduces Histopathological Lesions and Excretion in Laying Hens Naturally Infected with *Brachyspira* spp.

Oral presentation

Porcs artificiellement contaminés par *Salmonella*: liens entre niveau d'excrétion, microbiote et immunité. A. Kerouanton. 2020, Meeting ANSES Ploufragan : Information and exchanges meeting pig farming sector.

2021

Poster

F. Kempf, R. Drumo, Anne Marie Chaussé, T. Kubasova, I. Caballero, S. Roche, P. Menanteau, E. Guitton, I. Rychlik, P. Velge-Immune response, gut microbial composition, *Salmonella* super- and low-shedder phenotypes can be modulated by the inoculation of four commensal bacteria in chicken. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting, Virtual, Copenhagen, 9th-11th June 2021. Poster

16S rRNA MICROBIAL COMMUNITY ANALYSIS AND RELATIONSHIP WITH *SALMONELLA* SUPER SHEDDER STATUS IN PIGS Guido Cordoni One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021 (Poster)

Albena Dimitrova, Gergana Mateva, Gergana Krumova-Valcheva, Eva Gyurova, Mihail Milanov, Helen Brown, Guido Cordoni, Daniel Horton, Roberto La Ragione, Hristo Daskalov. INFLUENCE OF ORAL ADMINISTRATION OF LACTOBACILLUS REUTERI PROBIOTIC STRAINS AND GOS PREBIOTIC ON THE PRESENCE OF *SALMONELLA* SPP. IN FATTENING PIGS. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting, Virtual, Copenhagen, 9th-11th June 2021. Poster

Gergana Mateva, Krasen Penchev, Gergana Krumova-Valcheva, Albena Dimitrova, Eva Gyurova, Mihail Milanov, Helen Brown, Guido Cordoni, Jade Passey, Daniel Horton, Roberto La Ragione, Hristo Daskalov. INFLUENCE OF ORAL ADMINISTRATION OF LACTOBACILLUS REUTERI PROBIOTIC STRAINS AND GOS PREBIOTIC ON THE PRESENCE OF *SALMONELLA* SPP. IN BROILERS. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting, Virtual, Copenhagen, 9th-11th June 2021. Poster

Poster in OHEJP ASM 2021. Rebollada-Merino, A.; Ugarte-Ruiz, M.; Miguela-Villoldo, P.; Domínguez, L.; Rodríguez-Bertos, A. Histomorphological Changes in the Bursa of Fabricius Associated with *Salmonella* Typhimurium Infection in Animals Fed with a Nutraceutical Derived from the Olive Oil Production

Oral presentation

Oral communication in Programa de Doctorado en Veterinaria. Rebollada-Merino, A. Efecto sobre la mucosa intestinal y la microbiota cecal del alperujo fermentado desengrasado en pollos de engorde experimentalmente infectados con *Salmonella* Typhimurium (2020)

Outcomes

- Key role of animal-animal recontaminations in the spread of *Salmonella* infection at the flock level. The high level of *Salmonella* transmission between chicks is related to the presence of super-shedders, functioning as a reservoir for the pathogen. *Salmonella* can be transmitted by air through contaminated dust particles. It is crucial to decrease these transfers (Importance of ventilation on farms) and to identify the animals at risk.
- Identification of predictive biomarkers, based on gut microbiota composition and immune parameters, which can either predict the levels of *Salmonella* shedding (in pigs or in chickens), or which can differentiate the *Salmonella* shedding levels (in pigs or in chickens).
- In humans, long-term *Salmonella* shedder phenotype may be associated to host factors such as young age, disease manifestation, taking food supplements and regular medication. Moreover, although the risk of person-to-person transmission of *Salmonella* from asymptomatic carriers is considered low, our study indicates a 10-fold higher rate (24%) of non-typhoidal *Salmonella* shedding than previously suggested. Our results support current recommended control measures to prevent the occurrence of secondary cases especially in children. Presentation at ECDC Nordic Mini Module.
- Participation to PoC projects COOPERATE funded by stakeholders in Paris-Saclay University (starting 2021). Interest of stakeholders for OTU clustering and for detection method. Design of probiotic consortia based on endogenous microbiota bacteria.
- Development of probiotics for use in pigs and poultry, which can be used as an alternative to antibiotics and which may reduce AMR.

- With approval of national authorities **VRI** tested the developed probiotics in more than a half million broilers in 2020. Farmers are interested in further collaboration as the product may be used instead of antibiotic treatment during first days of life. The probiotic product is being prepared for registration in the Czech Republic though we are still improving its commercial formula – lyophilisation of strict anaerobes without losing viability is quite challenging.
- Collaboration with commercial companies on the use of prebiotics (UoS, UCM-VISAVET). UoS will communicate results to stakeholders FSA, Defra and VMD.

6. One Health Impact

Asymptomatic carrier animals and humans are a serious food safety and health issue resulting in a significant loss to agri- food industry as well as a substantial burden on the healthcare system. The MOMIR-PPC project has led to major advances 1- in the understanding of heterogeneity of *Salmonella* infection, which has been confirmed in all models studied: human, pig and chicken ; 2- in the control measures, which could be used, and in the identifications of the super-shedder animals; 3- in the development of prevention measures able to either predict the most susceptible animals (or flocks) or to prevent infection by the use of pre and probiotics.

- Understanding heterogeneity of *Salmonella* infection. This project has shown the key role of animal-animal recontaminations in the spread of *Salmonella* infection at the flock level. The high level of *Salmonella* transmission is related to the presence of Super-Shedders, functioning as a reservoir for the pathogen. The data have shown that the gut microbiota composition before infection determines in chicks the super and low shedder phenotypes. It is thus possible to prevent infection with pre and probiotics or nutraceuticals. Moreover, although the risk of human-to-human transmission of *Salmonella* from asymptomatic carriers is considered low, our study indicates a 10-fold higher rates (24%) of non-typhoidal *Salmonella* shedding than previously suggested. Our results support current recommended control measures to prevent the occurrence of secondary cases especially in children. The results obtained will have direct applications for the control measures.
- Modelisation of infection. The project allowed the development of original epidemic models and methods for data analysis based on a generic mathematical model of the dynamic interplay between the gut microbiota, the pathogen and the host's immune response at the within and between-host scale. This model will help to decipher the impact of modifications based on gut microbiota and immune response.
- Modelisation of transmission. A mathematical model of indirect transmission of bacteria between broilers was developed. The results showed no transmission at longer distances (above 130 cm), which is consistent with the existence of a threshold distance. The model can be used for designing and quantitatively assessing candidate bio-security based intervention strategies against indirect transmission of *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella*.
- Control strategies. In general, the control of *Salmonella* is based upon the implementation of preventive actions throughout the whole production chain. More specifically, measures should be addressed to (i) the prevention of introduction of *Salmonella* into the herd/ flock, (ii) the prevention of within-herd transmission, and (iii) the increase of the resistance to the infection. Our results have shown at least in chicks, that *Salmonella* can be transmitted by air through contaminated dust particles. It is thus crucial to decrease these transfers with the important ventilation on farms. It is also important to identify the animals at risk. For that purpose, the MOMIR-PPC project identified several predictive biomarkers, based on gut microbiota composition and immune parameters. These biomarkers, which need to be confirmed, can either predict the levels of *Salmonella* shedding (in pigs or in chickens) if animals are infected, or can differentiate the *Salmonella* shedding levels.

- The cost effectiveness (utility) of intervention strategies using probiotics to reduce *Campylobacter* prevalence in broilers was evaluated. Interesting results showed that using probiotics is a moderately expensive intervention in Poland and Spain, if efficacy is more than 10%, otherwise it is relatively expensive. In contrast, in the Netherlands and Denmark, using probiotics is a relatively expensive intervention irrespective of efficacy. However, if probiotics were assumed to enhance broiler performance, the intervention would become relatively cost-effective even at low efficacy levels of 1 to 10%.
- Prevention measures. To prevent salmonellosis, we purified, characterized and tested the efficacy of probiotics and prebiotics for use in pigs and poultry, in experimental infection but also in field conditions. For example they were tested on 72640 chicks in Bulgaria and 130 000 chicks in Czech Republic. These probiotics and prebiotics can be used as an alternative to antibiotics and may reduce AMR.

The benefits of our project for the livestock industries, authorities, veterinarians and medical doctors should be rapid as we have already identified new control measures for risk managers for the prevention and control of salmonellosis. It will also have a short- and long-term impact on the industry, especially with regard to pro and prebiotics. The existence of a market for well characterized and defined probiotics is attested by the success with undefined avian caecal cultures in competitive exclusion, which are now banned by the EU. The results obtained will be disseminated to stakeholders through specialized congresses like the “Animal microbiome congresses” and the “International Conference on Poultry Intestinal Health”.

4. 12-months reports of the second round JRP, Year 4

The projects leaders of the second round projects have filled in 12-months reports. The entire contents of these reports have been copied below, except for the paragraphs related to the ethics and the list of dissemination and communication activities, which can be found elsewhere:

- The third Ethics report, encompassing Joint Research Projects, Joint Integrative Projects and PhD in 2020, has been delivered as D1.26 Ethical review report for Y4 (28 Feb 2022) on the Participant Portal.
- The list of dissemination activities: this information has been analysed and reported in the One HealthEJP Periodic Technical Report Y4, paragraph 3.1 “Overview of the dissemination activities”.

JRP12-AMRSH5-FARMED

1. Summary of the work carried out in year 4

The FARMED project, based on wet laboratory work, continues to be impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic, as many institutes have had restricted access (including lockdowns) to their laboratories for non-essential research work and there have been delays in receiving consumables required for the project. In spite of this we have had progress to the FARMED objectives.

FARMED aims to assess the feasibility of long-read sequencing to rapidly characterise the metagenome and resistome of samples, on-site, in order to provide investigators with the correct information to apply the most appropriate control measures.

Bioinformatics analysis of long read sequencing of a simple (pond water) or complex (animal faeces) matrix spiked with a defined microbial community (DMC) (supplied by BfR), DNA extracted using the preferred method in each institute, highlighted the differences of microbiomes achieved by each institute (WP1). Further work is currently underway to understand why these differences have

occurred even though the 'same' samples were used. The consortium has selected 3 lab-based DNA extraction kits, which were assessed by a minimum of three institutes, in order to determine the usability as well as consistency of these methods. To aid this assessment, the same commercially available defined community was used by all institutes. Institutes have applied one of these lab-based methods on sample matrices most relevant to their institutes. The data analysis is currently ongoing. Further work is still required to optimise as well as automate the DNA sequence analysis methods, such that the analysis can be performed on 'basic' computers by non-bioinformaticians (WP2).

Two instruments capable of on-site DNA extractions are being trialled for their suitability to produce DNA of sufficient quantity and quality for DNA sequencing. Preliminary analysis using these instruments has yielded DNA for single isolates suitable for long read sequencing, but current optimisation is underway to achieve the appropriate quality of metagenomic DNA (WP3). This is being combined with the Voltrax instrument, allowing on site sequence library preparation.

A peer-reviewed publication and a poster have been presented highlighting the use of long read metagenome sequencing to characterise the microbiome as well as identify the presence of genetically modified microorganisms *Bacillus subtilis*, containing AMR genes on the chromosome and on a plasmid, in a feed additive. Two oral presentations have been given at the One Health EJP Dissemination Workshop on Metagenomics, held 27th October 2021.

[2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes](#)

[WP1 - Assess feasibility of Long-read metagenome sequencing on exemplar matrices. Investigate the use of Hi-C metagenomics.](#)

WP1-T1-Assess feasibility /perform long-read metagenomics MinION from 'defined' microbial community.

A thorough evaluation of the short (Illumina) and long (ONT) read sequencing of a defined mock community (DMC) consisting of 6 species (four Gram-negative isolates and two Gram-positive isolates) with known complete genome sequences and different AMR profiles, spiked into water buffalo faeces or pond water at different concentrations, was performed. The sequencing data from six partners were loaded up to the Owncloud repository, where they have been analysed using the KMA pipeline (details of the analysis methods are given in WP2), to allow inter-partner comparison of richness (observed species) and diversity. Analysis showed that long-read sequencing using ONT technology was able to identify some of the bacterial species contained in the DMC, but not all, which appeared to be dependent on the DNA extraction method used.

Regardless of the DNA sequencing method, sequencing comparisons showed that microbial profiles clustered by laboratory (i.e. by project partner) and was likely due to the different DNA extraction method employed by each institute. The AMR profiles appeared to be less affected by institute or DNA extraction method, using the Illumina sequencing compared to the ONT sequencing.

Some additional qPCR analyses have been performed by Sciensano to evaluate the extraction effectiveness, compared to the sequencing reads output. From this, it appeared that the species spiked at the lowest concentration (*Acinetobacter baumannii* and *Escherichia coli*) and not detected by sequencing, could also not be detected by qPCR analysis. On the opposite, all the other species (except one but probably due to technical issues), for which reads were obtained by sequencing, could be detected by qPCR. This allowed to back-up the sequencing results with a more sensitive method. Additionally, the impact of the multiplexing during sequencing (i.e. 3 samples per MinION flow cell) investigated (by Sciensano). When pooling 3 samples on a MinION flow cells, a lot of information was lost because more than half of the sequenced reads were not properly demultiplexed and remained "unclassified". Re-sequencing of the DMC samples with one sample per flow cell allowed to increase the number of produced reads per sample (although the 2 lowest abundant species were still not

detected) and no data was lost. This improved the data analysis, including linking the AMR gene to the corresponding species (cfr WP2).

Based on DMC analysis, the consortium has selected three commercially available DNA extraction kits for further investigation, using real-life ‘simple’ and ‘complex’ matrices (WP1-T2 and WP-T3) of choice for the respective institutes. For evaluation, a commercially available mock community (ZymoBIOMICS Gut Microbiome Standard, GMS, CAT no D6331), has been utilised to identify and achieve a consistent output between different users, and allow comparison of methods between partners in the consortium.

WP1-T2- Assess feasibility /perform long-read metagenomics MinION from ‘simple’ sample matrices.

This task is behind due to the delay in finalisation of the DMC samples (task WP1.1) (caused by the COVID-19 situation), to determine which DNA extraction and bioinformatics analysis methods should be explored further, with institutes starting to analyse their own ‘real’ simple samples, which includes drinking water, river water and sprout spent irrigation water. The Gut Microbiome Standard (GMS) was used to spike ‘simple’ matrices by several institutes to allow comparison of DNA extraction and long read sequencing.

In detail, ISS decided to analyse sprout spent irrigation water, because it is one of the matrices mentioned in Reg. (EU) 209/2013, laying down microbiological criteria for testing the contamination of sprouts with Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*. Tests have been performed extracting DNA with Quick-DNA™ HMW MagBead Kit (Zymo Research) initially following the protocol and starting from 200 ul of sample, which did not produce appropriate yield (total 11 ng of DNA extracted, minimum needed for MinION sequencing is 400ng). The use of a filtration step was excluded, due to the viscosity of the matrix. Concentration of different amount of water was then attempted and finally good results were obtained when concentrating 200 ml of water, obtaining total 1560 ng (52 ng/ul), sufficient for MinION sequencing. The GMS and sprout spent irrigation water spiked with GMS samples were sequenced at ISS in December 2021. Preliminary analyses identified low number of reads: 5,942 reads from clean GMS and 6,946 reads from spiked water were obtained, for 58.8 Mb and 62.7 Mb totally sequenced, respectively (Read length N50 were 18,637 bp and 22,825 bp, respectively). Detailed analysis are currently in progress.

WP1-T3- Assess feasibility/perform long-read metagenomics MinION from ‘complex’ sample matrices.

This task is behind due to the delay in finalisation of the DMC samples (task WP1.1) (caused by the COVID-19 situation), to determine which DNA extraction and bioinformatics analysis methods should be explored further, with each institute starting to analyse their own ‘real’ complex samples, which includes faeces, food/feed, boot socks, and wastewater. The Gut Microbiome Standard (GMS) was used to spike complex matrices by institutes to allow comparison of DNA extraction and long read sequencing. A template table was prepared by APHA, BfR and Sciensano to allow each institute to communicate the settings of the experiments performed (DNA extracted and long-read sequenced) and the obtained results (DNA yield, sequencing statistics, and taxonomic identification), to make comparisons. Six of eight institutes obtained DNA from the three trailed extraction kits, the range of DNA extracted by each institute was comparable between the DNA extraction kits used. The minimum amount of DNA required Nanopore sequencing library prep is either 400ng (rapid) or 1000ng (ligation), so many of the extraction kits the quantities were sufficient to process with long read sequencing. Preliminary analysis of the sequencing results are described in WP2-T1.

Sample	Institute	DNA concentration (ng/ul)		
		Gen Find V3	Pure Link Genomic DNA mini kit	Quick DNA HMW magbead kit
GMS (control)	6 of 8	31 – 39	17.6	24 – 33
Simple WM	2	N/D	N/D	52 – 55.2

Complex matrix (faeces)	4	102 – 139	50.2	102 – 113
-------------------------	---	-----------	------	-----------

ND: Not Determined.

BfR is planning to sequence faecal material containing existing multidrug resistant *Salmonella* and *E. coli* from calves, cattle or pigs (“real life”) as well as faecal material free from *Salmonella*, ESBL and/or carbapenemase producing Enterobacteriaceae inoculated with different multidrug resistant bacteria. Furthermore, other complex matrices such as food will be tested. Here, insect-based foods and sesame-based tahini will be spiked. Both food types are also “real life” matrices, as previous analyses have shown a contamination with *Bacillus* and *Salmonella*, respectively. Matrices for spiking experiments have been collected and microbiologically pretested for suitability. Selected samples have been sequenced using the Illumina technology for screening purposes. Furthermore, adapted mock communities for further spiking experiments are currently being prepared. For all these different matrices, subsequent sequencing will determine to what extent spiked-in bacterial species, “real life” bacterial species and AMR genes can be identified. Additionally, different spiking concentrations will reveal the sensitivity of the method for the different matrices and to what extent strain separation is possible.

Sciensano performed the analysis of the complex feed additive matrix using shotgun metagenomics. Feed additives (e.g. vitamins) are often produced through the use of genetically modified microorganisms (GMMs) to replace chemical synthesis methods, as this is more practical and requires fewer resources. The presence of a genetically modified microorganism (GMM) or its DNA, often harbouring AMR genes, in microbial fermentation products is prohibited by European regulations. If no isolate of the GMM can be obtained, a metagenomics approach is the only way to demonstrate the presence of a GMM in a microbial fermentation product, with characterization based on detection of AMR genes and vectors, species and unnatural associations in the GMM genome. We based the evaluation of the feasibility of this new approach on the investigation of a previously analysed sample containing a GMM *Bacillus subtilis* (rapid alert to the competent authorities (EU): RASFF 2014.1249) overproducing vitamin B2 (riboflavin), isolated and fully characterized at that time. The method was applied to a sample positive for some qPCR markers but for which no isolate could be obtained. The short and long read sequencing technologies were compared for their performances, including the newly released Flongle, as a smaller and cost-effective alternative. The analysis was finalized and the results published in Buytaers et al. 2021 (Food Chemistry: Molecular Sciences, Volume 2, 30 July 2021, 100023). Altogether, our method allowed to predict the presence of a GMM in the sample, based on the simultaneous detection of AMR genes or vectors in species previously described as common GMM producers, and the encounter of unnatural associations in the genome. Generally, this open approach can in the future be applied to other GMM used to produce fermentation products like food enzymes.

DTU has sequenced pig faeces and Danish wastewater samples separately, with and without the addition of the GMS mock community. Both the pig faecal samples and the sewage water samples are part of DTU surveillance programme for pathogen and AMR detection. DTU has a standard operating procedure protocol to run long read sequencing (Oxford Nanopore) where Quick-DNA HMW MagBead kit (Zymo) was used for DNA extraction, and Ligation Sequencing Kit SQK-LSK109 and Native Barcoding Expansion (PCR-free) EXP-NBD104 kits (Oxford Nanopore) were used for library preparation and sample multiplexing. The libraries were run on GridION platform (Oxford Nanopore). Seven Gbp and 4.8 M reads were sequenced, with N50 of 3 kb and 56 Kbp as the longest read. The output was then mapped to our manually curated Genomics Database (for bacterial community identification), and to ResFinder database for AMR predictions.

APHA had access to the REHAB project’s metagenome samples (AbuOun *et. al.* 2020, <https://www.microbiologyresearch.org/content/journal/mgen/10.1099/mgen.0.000630>), faecal samples recovered from pig and cattle. Spiked (ZymoBIOMICS Gut Microbiome Standard added to the sample) and none-spiked faecal samples were processed with GenFind v3 (Beckman) and PureLink (Invitrogen) kits using modified protocols followed by long-read sequencing. It was observed that

GenFind v3 yielded higher DNA concentrations compared to PureLink whether extracting from pure ZymoBIOMICS standard (75ul) or faecal material (200mg). Interestingly, spiked samples yielded even higher DNA concentrations compared to non-spiked samples. Sample analysis is on-going, however the pure GMS and samples spiked with the GMS will be described in the KMA parameter trial (see below).

WP1-T4- Perform Hi-C metagenomics

This task is delayed due to COVID-19 restrictions affecting access to laboratories.

At BfR, initial development of the Hi-C workflow has shown that the ProxiMeta Hi-C Library Prep Kit (PhaseGenomics) requires an already sequenced library as well as ample starting material for library preparation. To establish the method (D-JRP12-WP1.2 and M-JRP12-06), an artificial mixture of bacteria with known genome and plasmid sequences will be used for the preparation of Hi-C libraries. This Hi-C library will then be compared to short-read and long read sequencing data to determine whether it is possible to associate AMR genes to bacterial species as well as the genes' locations on the chromosome or plasmid. Once the feasibility of Hi-C has been evaluated, further testing and optimisation of workflow will be undertaken by task partners, using 'complex' matrices spiked with a mock community. Matrices for spiking experiments have been collected and microbiologically pretested for suitability. Selected samples have been sequenced using the Illumina technology for screening purposes. Furthermore adapted mock communities for further spiking experiments are currently being prepared.

All participating project partners will use the same Hi-C library preparation workflow and sequencing in order to obtain comparable sequencing results. A first discussion on Hi-C sequencing was held on June 7th. For the coordination of participating project partners, the BfR organized an additional (virtual) workshop on October 29th where experiences regarding practical work and data analysis, as well as preliminary results were presented. Sciensano and BfR are currently working on harmonized experimental approaches to produce comparable results of the participating partners as well as on bioinformatics solutions for automated Hi-C data analysis. Currently, BfR is evaluating a commercial workflow provided by PhaseGenomics and an in-house developed mapping-based approach for which different mapper and databases are being tested.

WP2 - Bioinformatics tools to analyse the sequencing data and defining the characteristics within the sample.

WP2-T1- Development/adaptation of a pipeline that can predict species within sample/matrix

To ensure consistency of results, DTU performed preliminary KMA analysis using their manually curated Genomics Database (for bacterial community identification) and the entire DMC dataset of raw short (Illumina) and long (Nanopore) read sequencing data generated by the consortium in WP1.1. The community analysis showed that the species richness of taxa varied between the FARMED consortium, while the diversity of identified bacterial taxa appeared to be consistent between samples. Microbial community analyses showed that bacterial communities that were sequenced by the same institute were more similar to each other, even if they were from different DMC faecal samples, compared to the same sample that were sequenced at another institute. This was observed using both sequencing platform outputs, Illumina and Oxford Nanopore, suggesting the difference were largely influenced by the different DNA extraction and library preparation practices used at each institute. The spiked bacteria were detected from the Nanopore sequencing at a range of different number of reads between the different institutes, only two bacterial taxa were not detected by three institutes when the bacterial communities were identified by Oxford Nanopore sequencing. In the case of the blank samples (FB/WB) we would expect to identify some of the spiked bacteria such as *E. coli* in the samples as these are part of the normal microbiome.

It is important to understand the impact of chosen methodology, such as the different extraction methods, sequencing library preparations, sequence base-calling, as well as the data analysis method, will have on the results obtained.

Sciensano compared the output of different sequence coverages (i.e. 1 or 3 samples pooled on a MinION flow cell) as in to retrieve the expected species and AMR genes. When pooling 3 samples on a MinION flow cells a lot of information was lost due to improper demultiplexing. This was corrected by sequencing one sample per flow cell. Moreover, 2 species not detected with the multiplexed experiments were identified when sequencing one sample per flow cell, and more reads were attributed to the identified species, allowing a more in-depth and sensitive detection. Finally, thanks to this coverage increase, more AMR genes could be detected and more of them could be linked to the species carrying them.

APHA has compared and evaluated the choice of sequencing library preparation kit (slower ligation library kit vs faster rapid library kit) as well as the basecalling (fast vs high accuracy) approach, both can be time-consuming stages thereby impacting timely delivery of results. Using the same DNA extraction method on the same DMC samples from WP1.1, we compared the two options for library preparation and base calling. As expected the ligation library kit and the high accuracy (HAC) base-calling identified more species compared to the rapid library kit and the rapid base calling. However, the ligation kit failed to detect several DMC species which could be down to either the inappropriate size selection step used during library preparation or the choice of KMA parameter thresholds, which are currently being evaluated. If the focus of the investigation is to identify pathogens or bacterial species harbouring AMR genes of interest rather than the exploration of all microbiomes species then the faster and less labour intensive Rapid kit is a suitable option.

The manually curated Genomics Database (for bacterial community identification) from DTU improved bacterial species identification compared to only using the 16S SILVA database. Using the manually curated Genomics Database appears to provide a better coverage of bacterial species identification from metagenomics samples, because it consists of the entire bacterial DNA genomes of the included bacterial taxa (not solely 16S rRNA DNA fragments that are used in SILVA database). This will allow bacterial taxonomical assignment even when the sequenced reads are not or don't contain the 16S rRNA DNA fragment, as limited by SILVA. Using only SILVA database for bacterial species assignments, the sequenced fragment must contain the 16S rRNA genes to produce a hit. However, the DTU Genomics Database (for bacterial community identification) is manually curated, and continuous addition of newly identified bacterial taxa are required. The continuous additions of the new bacterial taxa combined with the large size of this database (as it harbours the entire bacterial genomes, not only fragments or genes) make it bulky and very large in size, which introduce difficulties to share it amongst FARMED partners due to slow transfer speed. However, this manually curated Genomics Database, has been updated to include the five genomes missing from the GMS, and is currently being shared with all the partners. Going forward, FARMED will use the bacterial genomes database.

SSI made an 'read-titration analysis' comparing short- (Illumina) and long- (Nanopore) read sequencing, combined with 'KMA bacterial' database on the Mixed concentration sample from the DMC ring trial. On 2 samples we generated 1.7Gb and 2.9Gb by long-read sequencing and could identify 5 or 6 of the spiked-in genera. Short-read sequencing generated 9.8Gb and 11.2Gb on the 2 samples respectively and only identified 1 or 2 of the genera. Long-read sequence data was then titrated to a level corresponding to the same level of genus identification as in short read data. For the 2 samples, this corresponded to long-read data being ca 200 and 2000 times more efficient in genus identification compared to short- read data. Despite the lower number of reads per total Mb sequence data of long read, the longer Nanopore reads allow a more precise genus/species identification.

We assessed the long-read sequencing output of FARMED consortium GMS alone and samples spiked with GMS (from WP1). The table below summarises the key parameters which were compared, so far. Although a small number of samples have been analysed so far, it appears that the GenFind V3 and the Quick DNA HMW kit produced different results depending on the samples examined. For example,

the Quick DNA HMV kit produced longer N50s and the longest reads in the GMS control compared to the complex matrix, for which longer N50s were produced for GenFind V3 kit. Longer N50 will over the advantage of being able to identify pathogen/AMR combinations. The difference in number of reads per samples was due to the one partner not multiplexing the long-read sequencing so it appears that they achieved more sequence data compared to others.

Sample	DNA extraction kit	GMS (control)	Simple WM	Complex matrix (faeces)
Number of reads per sample	Gen Find V3	191,348 - 363,951	N/D	283,879 - 526,400
	Quick DNA HMW magbead	21,233 - 5,290,000	21,795 - 526,400	526,644 - 3,670,000
Mean fragment length (bp)	Gen Find V3	2,320 – 3,718	N/D	354 – 4,300
	Quick DNA HMW magbead	3718 - 6088	4300.1 - 5309.8	2,643 – 3,200
Read length N50 (bp)	Gen Find V3	4,470 - 11,009	N/D	369 - 21,926
	Quick DNA HMW magbead	11,009 - 17,753	14,749 - 21,926	10,304 – 13,732
Longest read length (bp)	Gen Find V3	100,353 - 423,580	N/D	65,833 - 273,167
	Quick DNA HMW magbead	81,428 – 641,790	145,330 - 273,167	130,552 – 715,993

Preliminary analysis of the metagenome data showed that the 10 of the 12 GMS spiked species were found by all institutes. For two species at the lowest abundances these were only identified by <3 institutes. The range of template identities and coverages varied between the bacterial species and the institutes, and these included bacteria spiked with higher abundance. This data will be further interrogated to optimise the KMA output, as well as to assess the complete microbiome profile in the sample matrices.

Species	Relative abundance (%) by the company	Identified by institution							Template identity range	Template coverage range
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G		
<i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i>	14	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	12.93 – 71.4	14.09 – 85.2
<i>Roseburia hominis</i>	14	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	78.44 – 91.4	80.66 – 95.7
<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	14	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	90.1 – 96.2	92.69 – 99.1
<i>Bifidobacterium adolescentis</i>	6	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	61.5 - 100	64.26 – 100
<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i>	6	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	59.17 - 95	88.67 – 98.8
<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	6	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	51.23 – 95	57.15 – 98
<i>Clostridioides difficile</i>	1.5	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	18.25 – 100	21.87 – 100
<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	1.5	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	91.3 – 98.6	93.95 – 99.6
<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	0.01	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	0.44 – 40.6	0.46 - 42
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	0.001	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	3.8	3.9
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	0.0001	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	0 - 99.3	0 - 99.52
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	14	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	98.99 – 99.8	99.29 - 99.66

Sciensano and APHA are working to compare the effects of parameters on the identification of bacteria, including those spiked in the GMS. When performing KMA analysis, some settings can be modified in order to filter the output results based on the quality of the mapping. If the filtering values indicated in these parameters are too loose, all the mapping results are returned to the user who has to look manually at the strength and robustness of the data. Alternatively, if the filtering values are too strict, less data are returned to the user, who can miss a species present in the sample at low concentration, but these data are more robust and reliable. Several different KMA analysis runs were performed to test how specific parameter choices will influence the output and which are optimal and should be implemented for future work. In total, four commands with varying parameter options were run using the GMS and sample spiked with GMS sequence data. The commands largely differed in a few parameter choices (see table below) affecting whether a species is reported or not.

Besides the specified below parameters, each run also contained the following parameter choices:

- “Default”, “Custom-1” and “Custom-2”: -mem_mode, -bc 0.7, -bcNano, -ef, -proxi 0.9, -na, -nf, -nc, -1t1, -ca.
- “DMC”: -mem_mode -bc 0.7 -bcNano -ef -proxi 0.9 -na -nf

Parameters	Default	DMC	Custom-1	Custom-2
-mrs (minimum alignment score)	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0
-ID (minimum template identity)	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.01
-sasm (skip alignment and assembly)	NO	YES	NO	NO

Future work will focus on the optimization of these parameters, with the aim to keep a balance between good sensitivity of the sequencing analysis and easy interpretation by non-expert users, as well as how to present the results of the microbiome analysis.

WP2-T2- Development/adaptation of a Resfinder-like pipeline for identification of AMR for long-read sequences

Following on from WP2.1, the AMR profiles of the DMC dataset were compared. Unlike the bacterial species, the resistome profiles of the same samples were more similar and this was regardless of the institute. Additional work is needed to define the threshold required. Analysis of AMR in the GMS experiments has not been examined yet.

Furthermore, Sciensano took advantage of the long-read sequencing to make the link between the detected species and AMR genes. The reads first identified by KMA as belonging to a given species were extracted from the whole dataset and subsequently processed a second time by KMA, using the ResFinder database, with the aim to detect AMR genes on those reads. This linking between identified species and AMR genes was successful for the most abundant species of the DMC, but was less straightforward for the other species. Similar work is ongoing for the real samples spiked with the commercial mock community.

WP2-T3- Benchmarking of tools with spiked samples in WP2

The entire DMC dataset, which includes the raw sequencing data files as well as the KMA output files, was compiled for evaluations and comparison, and analysis conducted by DTU (cfr WP1-T1).

DTU has compared their output from the faecal and sewage water samples with and without the GMS mock community (from WP2 T1) by mapping the sequences to bacterial databases using two different aligners/mappers (KMA and KRAKEN). The assigned bacterial species were similar and comparable with no major difference between KMA and KRAKEN, where the same abundant bacteria dominated both outputs (from KMA and KRAKEN). The mapping and alignment jobs were, however, completed more quickly when using KMA.

WP2-T4- Test protocols on site

This task is delayed until an analysis workflow is established.

WP3 - Implementation of on-site protocols for long-read metagenomic DNA sequencing

WP3-T1- Literature search & Harmonisation of on-site DNA isolation

The literature report on DNA extraction was finalised and uploaded Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724557>.

WP3-T2- Investigation of on-site equipment for DNA extraction and sequencing (original title: Investigate the use of Voltrax)

The Voltrax (from ONT) was expected to be able to perform the metagenome DNA extraction as well as the library preparation, which could directly be loaded onto the MinION for sequencing. However, currently the Voltrax is only able to prepare the DNA sequencing library, which is still valuable for on-site metagenome sequencing. The Voltrax is being tested by WBVR and compared to other sequencing library preparation methods in terms of suitability for on-site use and yield per library per time unit. Other partners (e.g. Sciensano) will investigate the use of Voltrax for library preparation in the near future (linked to WP3-T4). However, there are problems for the delivery of the required kits, causing a delay for this task (ONT cannot deliver these, as the instrument is in early access phase and updates are being done).

Additionally, the FARMED consortium has identified potential alternatives which are marketed to produce sequence quality DNA from a metagenomics sample which are being investigated. WBVR has tested the USEB DNA extraction method developed by Wageningen University and Research. While the method would be suitable for on-site diagnostics and is currently used for amplification-based detection methods, the yield of the method was 10 to 100 times below the yield of the Qiagen Puregene kit to which it was compared. Efforts to concentrate the material using DNA binding magnetic beads were unsuccessful and the method is therefore considered unsuitable for on-site usage for Nanopore sequencing.

Sciensano is investigating the Quick-DNA HMW Magbead (ZymoResearch) and DNAExpress (ClaremontBio) kits for on-site DNA extractions. Initial tests using pure bacterial cultures showed that the former produces a higher yield of large (~60 Kbp) DNA fragments of high purity but requires more special equipment to be able to perform this on site, while the latter is specifically designed for on-site

use, but yields lower amounts of fragmented DNA (~18 Kbp), requiring a concentration step to match the input requirement of Nanopore sequencing.

DTU has obtained Bento Lab set up where DNA extraction and library preparation (bench work) could be done remotely in the field by the mean of a transportable power source (battery). DTU is also currently developing an interface-based software where Oxford Nanopore output can be fed to, demultiplexed, basecalled and mapped to small size databases without the use of command lines. The Bento Lab set up and software have been tested in the field in Africa with promising output from bacterial single isolates, and currently being prepared to be tested for metagenomics samples in the field.

WP3-T3- Assess DNA isolation methods for suitability, test on matrices (faeces, blood, dust, (environmental), milk)

At APHA, initial trials of the PDQeX system, using the manufacturer's protocol, to extract DNA from pig faecal samples (collected at APHA) spiked with *E. coli* and MRSA, required further optimisation to increase DNA yields. In partnership with the manufacturer, a new prototype of the extraction tubes, changing sample input amounts and extraction conditions, appear to have increased DNA yield, although still not optimal (~10 ng/μl). While it appears long DNA fragments can be obtained (>12kb on 1% agarose gel) the recovered DNA yields from metagenomic samples using the PDQeX system do not meet the criteria for long-read sequencing. However, several modifications to the protocol have been devised following discussions with the manufacturers. Future work aims to optimise this method to achieve large enough quantity of sequence quality DNA.

At IZSAM, a comparative study was carried out on stool and boot socks collected in poultry farm using Zymo HMW DNA kit and Omega Bio-tek kit. Omega Bio-tek kit showed better results on stool samples in terms of DNA yield, purity, and integrity, while Zymo HMW kit provided higher DNA quantity, quality and integrity for powder collected by boot socks sampling method.

Sciensano is in the process of optimizing the DNAExpress (ClaremontBio) kit for DNA extraction from chicken faecal samples.

WP3-T4- Test protocol on site

This task has not started as we still do not yet have a suitable on-site DNA extraction and sequencing workflow.

WP4 - Project management, coordination, and training workshop.

WP4-T1- Annual physical project meetings

The FARMED consortium has not yet been able to gather together in person since the start of the project, as soon after, the COVID-19 pandemic started. No plans have been made this year to meet in person, as for many countries only essential travel is currently allowed. We will re-assess the travel situation later in 2022.

WP4-T2- Teleconferences will be organised every 3 months, between partners

The FARMED consortium has held teleconferences to discuss project progress and share experiences and results.

- In February 2021, DTU presented preliminary analysis of the WP1 DMC experiments conducted by members of the consortium. This highlighted the application of long read metagenomics to characterize the metagenome and enabled the consortium to decide on DNA extraction methods to pursue in FARMED.
- In April 2021, WBVR presented the WP3 deliverable reviewing the current scientific literature and overview of commercially available methods for on-site DNA isolation. APHA presented

analysis comparing the effects of different sequencing library preparations as well as the sequence base calling approach.

- In June 2021, BfR presented the advantages of the Hi-C sequencing approach and its applicability to the FARMED objectives to associate AMR plasmids to a host with the microbiome.
- In October 2021, BfR provided update on the Hi-C analysis and its practicalities.

WP4-T3- Training dissemination of developed protocols

Not applicable.

WP4-T4- Annual reports

The Y3 2020 annual report was submitted to OH-EJP in February 2021. The Y4 2021 M9 report was submitted to OH-EJP in September 2021.

3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

Impact of COVID-19 on FARMED consortium partners

The COVID-19 pandemic continues to affect many of the FARMED consortium.

- Some countries still remain (20 months since start of FARMED) in lockdown or restricted access to the laboratories to only undertake essential activities, including some scientist involved in COVID-19 activities. For most, all research activities, including the OHEJP projects were considered as non-essential and could not be continued, i.e. no activity in the R&D labs was allowed. This particularly had a big impact and the majority of FARMED involves laboratory based method optimisation.
- The national lockdowns delayed recruitment of staff or students to deliver FARMED objectives, with many new staff / students not in post until summer 2020. For some staff they had to contribute to the COVID-19 related activities.
- Research activities were able to start in summer 2020, however, homework remained the general rule, and social distancing needed to be assured, meaning only a limited number of people can work in the R&D labs. In winter 2020/21, COVID-19 cases were increasing and national lockdowns were re-introduced. The same holds true for winter 2021/22.
- In the last 20 months there has been limited availability or inconsistent delivery, in many countries, of various consumables (such as pipette tips) and scientific kits (such as WGS kits), due to the these items being diverted to COVID-19 testing activities.

As such all the milestones and deliverable have been delayed, and will require additional time to complete.

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
12	D-JRP12-1.1	Report on an initial assessment of long-read sequencing for metagenome (community and AMR) analysis (defined community, spiked and real simple and complex matrices) and comparison to current short-read standard.	47		M53	This has been delayed to the COVID-19 pandemic which has impacted delivery of wet lab experiments (see above).	8 (Method application)
12	D-JRP12-1.2	Report on the feasibility of using Hi-C sequencing for metagenomics to define the context of AMR genes.	46		M52	This has been delayed to the COVID-19 pandemic which has impacted delivery of wet lab experiments (see above).	8 (Method application)
12	D-JRP12-2.1	Optimised long-read sequence bioinformatics tool for the analysis of microbial communities	45		M58		2. Harmonise

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
		made publicly available.					d protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardise d data formats

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
12	D-JRP12-2.2	Optimised long-read sequence bioinformatics tool for analysis of the resistome made publicly available.	M58		M58		2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardise

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
							d data formats
12	D-JRP12-3.1	Review on current scientific literature and overview of commercially available methods for on-site DNA isolation.	M36	M40		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724557	8 (Summary of available methods, not publication)
12	D-JRP12-3.2	Protocol for use of Voltrax on-site for extraction and library preparation from clinical, veterinary and environmental samples, suitable for long-read metagenome sequencing.	M44		M56	Distribution of Voltrax by Oxford Nanopore has been delayed due to instrument up grades.	2. Harmonise d protocols and applied best practice

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
12	D-JRP12-3.3	Protocol for on-site extraction of high-quality DNA from clinical, veterinary, and environmental samples, suitable for long-read metagenome sequencing.	M54		M60		2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice
12	D-JRP12-3.4	Detailed method for on-site long-read sequencing of sample matrix.	M54		M60		2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice
12	D-JRP12-3.5	Report on initial findings of on-site diagnostic tests and IT solutions for human clinical, veterinary and	M54		M60		3. Databases of

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		environmental samples for early warning of emerging resistant pathogens.					reference materials and data, incl. metadata
12	D-JRP12-4.1	Annual communication to stakeholders and OH EJP coordinators	M48, M45		M48, M60		8 (Sharing and communication for application of methods)

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
12	M-JRP16-01	Review on current scientific literature and overview of commercially available methods for on-site DNA isolation presented to FARMED consortium.	M36	Yes	M40	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724557
12	M-JRP16-02	Assessment of long-read sequencing for resolving a 'defined' microbial community and their AMR genes, using current DNA extraction methods; and comparison to current short-read sequencing standard.	M46		M52	This has been delayed to the COVID-19 pandemic which has impacted delivery of wet lab experiments (see above).
12	M-JRP16-03	Assessment of long-read sequencing on spiked metagenome samples, using current DNA extraction methods, and comparison to current short-read sequencing standard for resolving the microbial community and AMR content/context.	M46		M53	This has been delayed to the COVID-19 pandemic which has impacted delivery of wet lab experiments (see above).

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
12	M-JRP16-04	Protocols for on-site high quality DNA extraction using Voltrax and library preparation ready for testing on-site	M43		M54	Distribution of Voltrax by Oxford Nanopore has been delayed due to instrument up grades.
12	M-JRP16-05	Assessment of long-read sequencing for 'simple' metagenome samples, using current DNA extraction methods, and comparison to current short-read sequencing standard for resolving the microbial community and AMR content/context.	M45		M50	
12	M-JRP16-06	Assessment of the feasibility of Hi-C sequencing for metagenomics to define the context of AMR genes.	M46		M51	
12	M-JRP16-07	Protocols for extraction of high-quality DNA (using different methods than Voltrax) from clinical, veterinary and environmental samples (simple and complex), suitable for long-read metagenome sequencing distributed amongst	M44		M58	Distribution of Voltrax by Oxford Nanopore has been delayed due to instrument up grades.

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		FARMED consortium for testing.				
12	M-JRP16-08	Assessment of long-read sequencing for 'complex' metagenome samples, using current DNA extraction methods, and comparison to current short-read sequencing standard for resolving the microbial community and AMR content/context.	M47		M52	
12	M-JRP16-09	Development/adaptation of a pipeline that can predict species within sample/matrix	M45		M51	
12	M-JRP16-10	Finalised protocol for on-site long-read sequencing of sample matrix distributed amongst FARMED consortium for testing.	M45		M53	
12	M-JRP16-11	Development/adaptation of a Resfinder-'like' pipeline for the identification of AMR from long-read sequences	M51		M55	
12	M-JRP16-12	Hands-on laboratory and bioinformatics workshop	M54		M59	

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		organised at DTU and SSI				
12	M-JRP16-13	Benchmarking of bioinformatics tools developed in WP2 with metagenomic sequences gained from T1.1, T1.2 and T1.3	M54		M57	
12	M-JRP16-14	Test the bioinformatics tools that were benchmarked and developed in WP2 on a laptop that is on-site (outside of laboratory conditions)	M54		M60	
12	M-JRP16-15	DNA extraction, library preparation and long-read sequencing tested on-site (outside of laboratory conditions)	M54		M58	
12	M-JRP16-16	Voltrax DNA extraction, Voltrax library preparation and long-read sequencing tested on-site (outside of laboratory conditions)	M54		M58	
12	M-JRP16-17	Complete workflow of DNA extraction (with or without Voltrax), library preparation (with or	M54		M60	

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		without Voltrax), long-read sequencing and bioinformatics analysis tested on-site for early warning of emerging resistant pathogens.				

4. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
A shotgun metagenomics approach to detect and characterize unauthorized genetically modified microorganisms in microbial fermentation products https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fochms.2021.100023 https://zenodo.org/record/5347021#.YS-kSY4zaM8 Food Chemistry: Molecular Sciences	Yes, partial	No	Yes, (0 euros)
D-JRP12-WP3.1 Review on current scientific literature and overview of commercially available methods for on-site DNA isolation. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4724557	Yes	No	Yes, (0 euros)

Additional output

Poster of project “FARMED: Long-read metagenomic sequencing workflow for the identification of pathogens/AMR on-site” presented at the One Health EJP Meeting, hosted in Copenhagen and online between 9-11th June 2021.

Oral presentation ‘JRP12 : FARMED : Fast Antimicrobial Resistance and Mobile-Element Detection using metagenomics for animal and human on-site tests’ presented at ‘OneHealthEJP@Sciensano’ theme day on November 19th 2021.

Outcomes

FARMED colleagues were invited to the organisation of the One Health EJP Dissemination Workshop on Metagenomics, held 27th October 2021, where two presentations were shared:

- Buytaers FE & De Keersmaecker SCJ - Strain-level shotgun metagenomics for the detection and characterization of bacterial foodborne contaminants in the context of outbreak investigation and EU regulatory enforcement.
- Otani, S – Can metagenomics replace the current *E. coli* based monitoring of AMR in livestock, food samples and environment?

Linked to these presentations, a report has been disseminated by the WP5 Science to Policy Translation of the One Health EJP. This report can be used for communication purposes.

5. Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries

Several members of the FARMED consortium are involved in other OHEJP projects. In particular the FULL-FORCE JRP is relevant as the project is utilising long-read sequencing to characterise mobile genetic elements which are associated with driving AMR in commensal and pathogenic Enterobacteriaceae.

Valeria Michelacci (ISS), working at the European Union Reference Laboratory (EURL) for *E. coli* at ISS, is involved in the activities of the steering committee for the development of a joint EFSA-ECDC database for molecular typing data collection, which started working in 2011 on PFGE and MLVA data but is now moving to WGS data collection. The three pathogens object of the surveillance at present are *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella* and Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*, that's why these three EURLs are involved. Moreover, since 2017 EURL *E. coli* on a mandate of the European Commission is coordinating the activities of an Inter EURLs working group on Next Generation Sequencing, involving the following EURLs: *E. coli*, *Listeria*, Staphylococcus (CPS), *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, Parasites, Antimicrobial resistance, and foodborne viruses. The aim is to promote the use of NGS across the EURLs' networks of National Reference Laboratories, build NGS capacity within the EU and ensure liaison between the work of the EURLs and the work of EFSA and ECDC on the NGS mandate sent by the Commission. The working group is meeting twice a year (online since 2020). Deliverables produced by now consist in guidelines for the different steps of NGS data production and analysis, information on reference NGS datasets, trainings modules and proficiency test schemes available for NGS. It has never dealt with metagenomics, yet, but it is among the interests of the Working Group for the future. The presence of Valeria Michelacci, among partners of FARMED, in this Working Group will ensure proper exchange of information about the outcomes of the projects and metagenomics-related documents eventually produced in the working group. EFSA and ECDC are observers of the activities of the group.

DTU is a EURL AMR laboratory as well as being certified WHO laboratory.

Sciensano, as NRL-GMO and also part of the European ENGL (European Network of GMO Laboratories), has contacts with the competent authorities at national (FAVV/AFSCA) and EU level, regarding the notification of the presence of GMM in microbial fermentation products. Sciensano is also member of the ENGL working group on “Sequencing strategies for the traceability of GMOs - methods and related quality aspects” and of the ENGL working group on “Detection of genetically modified microorganisms in food and feed”, where the use of metagenomics for the identification and characterization of GMM in food/feed is being discussed.

6. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	Yes, but this has been due to their involvement with COVID-19 pandemic.
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information

None

JRP13-AMRSH5-WORLDCOM

1. Summary of the work carried out in year 4

One Health EJP WORLDCOM aims to develop diagnostic tools linked with mobile referencing technology for detection of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in zoonotic pathogens. Resulting technologies will enable rapid on-site detection of AMR in pathogens from animal and human populations, facilitating early investigation of emerging resistances and development of machine-learning algorithms for AMR prediction.

Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) enzymes produced by Enterobacteriaceae organisms confer resistance to beta-lactam antimicrobials presenting a major public health concern. Biomarker genes for highly prevalent ESBLs, cefotaximase (CTX-M), oxacillinase (OXA), Klebsiella pneumoniae carbapenemase (KPC) and New Delhi metallo-beta-lactamase (NDM), were selected as assay development targets for AMR marker detection. Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) technology was selected for the detection of the selected AMR genes, due to its rapidity and ease of use. In Loop-primer endonuclease cleavage LAMP (LEC-LAMP) assays, the LAMP primers and reaction are modified to detect multiple targets in one tube. An internally controlled LEC-LAMP assay was developed for differential detection of closely related CTX-M variants, blaCTX-M-1 and blaCTX-M-15, associated with animal and human infection, respectively. A singleplex LEC-LAMP assay was also developed for differential detection of closely related OXA variants, blaOXA-48 and blaOXA-181/232, as a precursor to multiplex assay development. AMR LAMP assays have been developed and validated targeting important AMR genes (MCR-1, KPC, OXA-48, OXA-23 and VIM) that are associated with zoonotic bacterial infections. The assays are able to detect target genes within 10 min, with 100% sensitivity and specificity.

In relation to sample preparation, a rapid protocol for on-site DNA isolation was successfully developed and validated using confirmed CTX-M-1 positive porcine faecal samples. There has also been significant progress with water sample preparation for LAMP detection of pathogens and AMR genes. The method is rapid (30 min), with a detection limit of 10 cfu/mL. The method allowed consistent LAMP detection of all target AMR genes from tap and pond water spiked with different Gram-negative bacterial cultures within 35 min of sample preparation.

Targeted and whole-genome sequencing of AMR strains has progressed. Progress includes NGS data generated from: 24 cephalosporin-resistant *E. coli* strains isolated from alpacas or llamas, and 138 cephalosporin-resistant *E. coli* strains isolated from pigs reared in Germany, containing a range of *bla* AMR genotypes; 390 *E. coli* isolates from diverse sources (110 from human, 144 from swine and 136 from broilers) and 43 *E. coli* isolates from river and wastewater confirming the presence of CTX-M genes and the colistin resistance gene *mcr-1* among these *E. coli* isolates, including isolates co-producing colistin resistance and CTX-M genes. This information will be used for further improvement of LAMP assays.

Significant progress has been made concerning the automated assessment of colorimetric LAMP assays for AMR genes, employing an image processing pipeline combined with a machine learning method. This procedure remains robust against background noise, making it suitable for on-site use as part of a mobile detection kit, and has been implemented as an Android smartphone app for portability. This includes automatically annotating these data and communicating the results with a cloud storage service.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP: 1 Generation of up to date sequence information for selected pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes

WP1-T1- Analysis of publically available sequences for antimicrobial resistance genes associated with Salmonella, Campylobacter and E. coli

This task was completed in Year 3.

WP1-T2- Targeted and whole genome de novo sequencing of phenotypically characterised isolates from various settings

NUIG generated genomic nucleotide sequence data from sequencing locally isolated *E. coli* CTX-M environmental samples and provided this sequence data to a WORLDCOM AMR gene database for use in assay development. This nucleotide sequence information included CTX-M-1 (n=2), CTX-M-4 (n=4), CTX-M-9 (n=1), CTX-M-15 (n=24), CTX-M-27 (n=5) and CTX-M-65 (n=1) *E. coli* isolates.

At the UoS, no whole genome sequencing (WGS) has been performed due to the COVID-19 lock down and difficulty in obtaining samples and publicly available genome databases have been utilised. However, a collaboration with a clinician has been established and the samples collection has been started. The task is still ongoing.

At FLI, 24 cephalosporin-resistant *E. coli* strains isolated from alpacas or llamas in Central Germany were short-read whole genome sequenced. Eighteen isolates contained the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} allele, three the *bla*_{CTX-M-27} allele, two the *bla*_{CMY-2} allele and one each a *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, a *bla*_{CTX-M-65} or a *bla*_{SHV-12} allele. Additionally, 138 cephalosporin-resistant *E. coli* strains isolated from pigs raised in Central Germany were short-read whole genome sequenced. Sequence analysis and gene quantification is still ongoing, but we have identified several isolates with the *bla*_{CTX-M-1}, *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, *bla*_{CTX-M-55} and *bla*_{CTX-M-27} alleles, each. FLI has a manuscript under revision describing the isolation and phenotypic characterisation of the *E. coli* isolates from alpacas and llamas and is currently preparing a manuscript for publication describing their WGS characterization in more detail.

At the UT, *de novo* WGS continued, 96 *E. coli* genomes were *de novo* assembled and AMR genes annotated in December 2021, and additional 106 *E. coli* genomes were sequenced at local sequencing core facility and are currently under processing in bioinformatic pipeline. Long read sequencing protocol using Oxford Nanopore technology is under the development and tested for closing draft genomes successfully. Manuscript about *de novo* WGS of *Campylobacter* spp. has been accepted by Poultry Science (Elsevier).

At UCM, a total of 390 *E. coli* isolates from diverse sources (110 from human, 144 from swine and 136 from broilers) were sequencing using a MiSeq Illumina platform. An *in silico* analysis of acquired antimicrobial resistance was performed, showing the presence of CTX-M genes among the 390 *E. coli* isolates, specifically four isolates contained the *bla*_{CTX-M-15} allele, two the *bla*_{CTX-M-14} allele and one the *bla*_{CTX-M-27} allele. In addition, 10 isolates showed the presence of the colistin resistance gene *mcr-1* (9 from swine and 1 from broiler). Of these 10 isolates, 5 of them co-produced colistin resistance and CTX-M genes. Additionally, 43 *E. coli* isolates from environmental water (river and wastewater) bearing 16S rRNA 16S methyltransferases were sequenced using Illumina and Nanopore technology. The presence of CTX-M genes was observed in the wastewater samples, with 72% (n = 18) were CTX-M-55 producing, while the presence of CTX-M genes was not observed in the river samples. Of the 18 CTX-M-55 positive samples from wastewater, 16 also showed *mcr-1* gene. The results were published in Communications Biology and uploaded to Zenodo repository (DOI: 10.1038/s42003-021-01949-x and <https://zenodo.org/record/5524433#.YcyB25HMJuR>).

During July 2021 a OHEJP Short Term Mission was undertaken by Liam Burke (NUIG) who travelled to Worldcom partner UCM to train in Nanopore sequencing and hybrid sequence analysis for plasmid characterization. The STM resulted in the generation of Nanopore sequence data for a collection of 41 carbapenemase producing (*bla*_{KPC-2}, *bla*_{NDM-5} and *bla*_{OXA-48}) Enterobacterales isolates. All strains were first isolated during 2018-2020 in Galway from natural water environments (rivers, estuaries, sea), hospital and municipal wastewaters, the hospital environment and hospital patients. A cyberattack at NUI Galway greatly impacted project progress between October and December, hampering completion of sequencing. However complete Nanopore data and hybrid assemblies are now available for all strains and annotation and analysis of carbapenemase plasmids and CPE genomes is ongoing. A manuscript will be prepared by the collaborating partners in early 2022.

At INSA a total of 231 *de novo* WGS runs were performed using a MiSeq Illumina platform, namely on 11 *Acinetobacter* genomes from human origin, as well as on other bacteria from different reservoirs such as: 38 *E. coli* from human, 8 from bivalves, 3 from gilthead, 12 from water; 139 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* from human, 2 from gilthead, 10 from hospital environment, 10 from water. Overall, these bacteria have *bla*_{OXA-23}, *bla*_{OXA-48}, *bla*_{NDM}, *bla*_{CTX}, *bla*_{SHV}, *bla*_{TEM}, and/or *mcr*-type genes. Aquaculture bacteria (from bivalves and gilthead) are being included in a PhD thesis with respective manuscript that is in preparation.

Meanwhile, UCM and UT are leading creating and sharing a database draft, with the support of UoS, among the WorldCOM partners to develop a resource of all isolates, their resistance profile and sequences to facilitate sharing of all relevant information. The database draft is currently being further developed and all important and frequently reported ESBL, carbapenem and mobile colistin-mediated resistance genes are included. This task is ongoing.

WP1-T3- Development of machine learning algorithms for the prediction of anti-microbial resistance. (University of Surrey, VISAVET Health Surveillance Centre UCM)

At the UoS, the machine learning algorithm studies have two aims: 1) developing algorithms for automating LAMP detection, reducing personnel biases and the need for expertise to analyse the results, and 2) development of algorithms for the prediction of AMR from WGS.

For the first aim, algorithms have been developed in collaboration with WP2-T1, specifically for the automated detection of AMR genes based on fluorescence and colorimetric LAMP assays image data. For the fluorescence-based detection, amplification and annealing data series were used as the input

for a multi-modal neural network model trained using logistic regression. This model was trained and tested using a total of 56 samples, and leave-one-out cross validation estimated a test accuracy of ~ 98 %. With respect to colorimetric-based detection, images of tested samples (e.g. targeting *mcr-1* and *KPC* genes) were used to train a nearest centroid classifier algorithm to automatically identify colour changes. The images for the samples were pre-processed using colour-based thresholding and contour edge detection to extract representative features for the algorithm. Moreover, a hierarchical clustering technique, agglomerative clustering, has been introduced to provide robustness against background noise. This algorithm has been successfully validated using noisy image data and has since been ported into an Android smartphone app for on-site applications.

Concerning the second aim commitment of this work package task, predicting antimicrobial resistance using WGS, progress has been delayed due to the other commitments for this work package, the delayed employment date alongside COVID-19 related restrictions. To date, a data preparation technique for performing dimensionality reduction on WGS data has been identified from the recent literature, based on forming 'k-mer-based representations' and 'compacted de Bruijn graphs', to reduce the number of input features from ~85 million to ~1 million per sample, in some cases. We plan to pursue this strategy further and identify a suitable supervised learning method for predicting AMR and especially EBSL in zoonotic pathogens. Also, no WGS has been performed, but this task is going to be developed first using publicly available sequences and those from our developed database from WP1-T2 as training for the algorithm. Suitable isolates for WGS have now been identified and will be transferred to the UoS in early 2022.

This task is still ongoing.

WP2: Assay Development

WP2-T1- Development and performance evaluation of singleplex isothermal amplification assays for selected AMR gene targets

NUIG completed the design and development of singleplex Loop-primer endonuclease cleavage - Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LEC-LAMP) assays for the detection of CTX-M Group 1 variants, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, using existing genomic sequence data from *E. coli* isolates collected and processed by NUIG. Sequence alignment analysis was used to identify single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) differences between both variants, which were then used to develop variant specific LEC-LAMP assays for differential target detection. A separate LEC-LAMP assay for the detection of an internal amplification control (IAC) was also developed. Complete analytical specificity for each assay was established. Analytical sensitivity testing for each assay demonstrated rapid low limits-of-detection with 10 genome copies detected in under 20 min. These assays were used in WP2 Task 3 to develop an internally controlled multiplex LEC-LAMP assay. NUIG have completed the design and development of a singleplex LEC-LAMP assay for detection of the OXA variant, *bla*_{OXA-48}. Initial assay evaluation has demonstrated fast low-level detection of 10 genome copies in under 20 min, with specific differential detection from closely related variants *bla*_{OXA-181} and *bla*_{OXA-232}.

At the UoS, five loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) assays had been developed targeting 1) *mcr-1*, 2) *bla*_{OXA-48} and *bla*_{OXA-48-like} genes (OXA-48-, OXA-232-, OXA-181- and OXA-54-encoding genes), 3) *bla*_{OXA-23}, 4) *bla*_{KPC} and 5) *bla*_{VIM}. All five assays had been optimised and validated against a wide range of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains to confirm sensitivity and specificity. All five assays showed 100% sensitivity and specificity, and were detected in less than 10 min. The assays were developed and detected both fluorescently and colorimetric. The LAMP detection limit had also been assessed using *mcr-1* LAMP. The detection limit of *mcr-1* LAMP was assessed using a 10-fold and 2-fold serial dilutions of genomic DNA of *E. coli* NCTC 13846 and shown to be 0.0625 pg of DNA, which was successfully amplified in duplicates in less than 8 min. LAMP primers were also designed targeting *mcr-8*, *mcr-9* and the most frequent alleles of *bla*_{IMP} (imipenem metallo-β-lactamase), and will be validated for *mcr-8*, *mcr-9* and *bla*_{IMP}-encoding resistant strains.

WP2-T2- Evaluation and selection of sample preparation methods for use with laboratory on-site tests

NUIG completed the development and evaluation of a rapid sample preparation protocol, a 15 min Chelex/heat lysis DNA extraction method, for on-site DNA extraction from animal faecal samples. Validation of this method was carried out using porcine faecal samples supplied by FLI. These samples were previously collected and confirmed positive for CTX-M-1 by selecting cultures from Gassner agar plates containing 4 µg/ml Ceftiofur, followed by bacterial DNA extraction and PCR using *bla*_{CTX-M-1}-family-specific primers with Sanger-sequencing. Samples contained varying amounts of coliform strains resistant to Ceftiofur, ranging from 25-100%. 200 mg of each sample was processed using the rapid sample preparation protocol, followed by LEC-LAMP testing. All samples successfully tested positive for CTX-M-1 in under 20 min.

At the UoS, the water sample preparation method has been further developed and validated. The method is advantageous in being rapid (30 min). The detection limit of the method was further assessed using tap water spiked with the *mcr-1* positive *E. coli* NCTC 13846 bacterial culture at different concentrations (10⁷ – 10 cfu/mL). The assay detected up to 10 cfu/mL, as confirmed by culture, of spiked bacterial cells in less than 6 min of the LAMP assay. The water sample preparation method was also validated using tap water spiked with different bacterial cultures of MCR-1 (*E. coli* NCTC 13846), OXA-48 (*E. coli* NCTC 14321), OXA-23 (*A. baumannii* NCTC 13301), KPC (*K. pneumoniae* NCTC 13809 and *E. coli* NCTC 14321) and VIM (*E. cloacae* NCTC 14326) positive strains separately before detection with the AMR LAMP assays. All AMR targets were detected in less than 4 min of the AMR LAMP assays and within 35 min of sample preparation. The method was further validated using pond water samples and we demonstrated successful amplification of bacterial strains used to spike the samples (none of the tested AMR markers were present in the unspiked pond water). All assays were also confirmed using a validated real-time PCR detection assay for the target AMR genes. This task along with WP2-T1 is currently being written as a manuscript for submission in early 2022.

We also implemented the faecal sample preparation method, developed by NUIG, for the direct colorimetric detection of AMR genes from pig faeces. The preliminary results showed successful color change (amplification) with pig faecal samples that were spiked with target bacterial isolates, while un-spiked faecal samples were negative. This method will be further validated using real-time PCR detection and expanded using an extended sample size.

The UoS is currently preparing a manuscript for publication detailing the assay development and evaluations of the five AMR LAMP targets (MCR-1, KPC, OXA-48, OXA-23 and VIM) for the detection of AMR from pathogens and water samples for One Health diagnostic applications.

WP2-T3- Development and performance evaluation of multiplex assays for pathogens and resistance genes

NUIG completed the development and evaluation of an internally controlled multiplex LEC-LAMP assay for the differential detection of CTX-M Group 1 variants, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}. The internally controlled LEC-LAMP assay contains fluorescently labelled primer/probes specific to each target: FAM for *bla*_{CTX-M-1}; HEX for *bla*_{CTX-M-15}; and Cy5 for the IAC. The LEC-LAMP assay demonstrated complete analytical specificity and differential detection of both variants when tested with environmental *E. coli* isolates collected from Ireland and animal *E. coli* isolates from Central Germany: CTX-M-1 (n=15); CTX-M-15 (n=37); and other CTX-Ms (n=12). The LEC-LAMP assay also demonstrated low-level detection for each variant at 10 genome copies per reaction in approximately 20 min. Initial evaluation work to combine the singleplex *bla*_{OXA-48} LEC-LAMP assay with the IAC LEC-LAMP, developing an internally controlled multiplex assay, has been carried out and this work is still on-going. Following this step, simplex and multiplex assays will be evaluated by the remaining partners of this WP (UoS, UT, FLI, INSA) using various sample types, including human, animal and water sources.

To date, FLI has tested the multiplex LEC-LAMP assay on 248 *E. coli* strains isolated from porcine faecal samples and resistant to Ceftiofur. Of these, 157 were positive for *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and 89 for *bla*_{CTX-M-15}. Two

negative strains contain a sequence-verified *bla*_{CTX-M-27} allele. WGS analysis shows that *bla*_{CTX-M-55} positive strains score as *bla*_{CTX-M-15} positive, due to the fact that the SNPs differentiating between *bla*_{CTX-M-55} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15} are located at the 3' end of the gene and, thus, not subject to discrimination by the primers used in the assay. FLI is currently testing faecal samples from pigs and alpacas for resistance to carbapenems or colistin to identify strains for validation of the assays developed by UoS and NUIG.

NUIG is currently preparing a manuscript for publication detailing the development and evaluation of the internally controlled multiplex LEC-LAMP assay for the differential detection of CTX-M Group 1 variants, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, from porcine faecal samples.

WP3: Development of Lateral Flow Diagnostics Detection and Mobile Communication system

WP3-T1- Development of lateral flow diagnostics for AMR detection

At the UoS, AMR LAMP assays have been developed using both fluorescence and colorimetric signals to allow for the immediate detection of the results. With the current developments and the excellent assays performance we are postponing the decision to develop lateral flow detection as it may be redundant and not necessary. However, we plan to expand the current pathogen and AMR LAMP assay targets to further develop a platform that can detect up to ten AMR genes and identify new pathogens of important zoonotic significance. This will significantly improve our developed LAMP platform and enhance its application for the detection of zoonotic pathogens and associated AMR.

WP3-T2- Development of mobile technology for communication of on-site results

At the UoS, a mobile smartphone app targeting Android phones has been developed which can automatically process and categorise captured images of colorimetric LAMP assays targeting AMR genes. This work package task is closely related to JRP13-WP1-T3 for which image processing and machine learning algorithms have been designed for the purposes of automated on-site detection of AMR. The mobile smartphone app developed for this task will be able to communicate results to an online cloud storage service: including captured images and associated metadata. This task is close to completion.

WP4: Evaluation of on-site tests and other tools developed

WP4-T1- Feasibility testing of laboratory and on-site tests for detection of pathogens and resistance genes

NUIG is currently developing a mobile diagnostics workstation for the on-site demonstration and application of the developed rapid sample preparation protocol and internally controlled multiplex LEC-LAMP assay. Portable instrumentation has recently been procured for the development of this unit. Inter-laboratory testing of assays and evaluation of the mobile diagnostics workstation will be carried out on-site using previously confirmed CTX-M-1 positive porcine faecal samples provided by FLI, and bovine faecal sample provided by UT.

FLI has so far acquired 34 composite faecal samples from eight different pig farms representing all stages of a pig fattening cycle and characterized them for cephalosporin (*bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}) and colistin resistance. To validate the sample preparation methods with respect to sensitivity and detection limit, the samples were quantified for total numbers of coliforms and cephalosporin-resistant coliforms. The LEC-LAMP multiplex assay will be used to test both DNA directly isolated from the faecal samples and DNA isolated from enriched cultures. This will allow to estimate the sensitivity and detection limits from field samples with a wide range of coliform counts and percentages of resistant isolates.

WP4-T2- Generation of information for dissemination

Depending on the results of isolation protocol and assay validation and testing, SOPs will be drafted and disseminated among the WorldCOM partners for further validation and optimization.

WP5: Project Management

WP5-T1-Project Management

Regular virtual (ZOOM) consortium meetings were held over the year and a WorldCOM consortium annual review meeting was held on September 20th 2021.

The WorldCOM DMP received positive feedback from the DMP Committee team during July 2021. It was noted that the Worldcom DMP was well developed, with a good understanding about how to use the template. Reviewer's individual comments for improvement were implemented in the online tool. The online tool is now being updated again ahead of the next review on the 24th January. Comments will be answered and DMP finalised by the 21st of February 2022.

3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
13	D-JRP13-1.1	Generation of a sequence database comprising publically available and newly generated sequences for <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Salmonella</i> and <i>Campylobacter</i> spp. and resistance genes CTX-M-15, NDM-5, KPC-2, OXA-48 and MCR-1.	M30	M33		Also shared on relevant WORLDCOM OHEJP website section and with all consortium members during development. public at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4019840	3
13	D-JRP13-1.2	Novel machine learning algorithms for the prediction and detection of AMR from genomic sequences.	M48		M56	This deliverable has been delayed for several reasons: the late employment date in relation to COVID-19 restrictions, and the other commitments of this work package arising	2

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						from collaboration with WP2-T1 – automated detection of LAMP assay data. Moreover, commitments with another OHEJP project and other pressing deliverables have delayed this progress.	
13	D-JRP13-2.1	Multiplex real-time isothermal assays for pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes which will be suitable for use in laboratory and optimised further in WP3 into a format suitable for on-site use	M43	M43		Brief report on deliverable uploaded to ZENODO: Public at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5912015	1
13	D-JPR15-AMR2.1-WP3.1	Lateral flow test for use on-site use together with Smartphone App for collection of data	M48		M50	Full validation of the code is underway. The code is currently only available to	1

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		and transmission of test results to reference laboratory				WORLDCOM or other One Health EJP members.	
13	D-JRP13-5.1	Kick-off meeting organised	M25	M25		Brief report on KOM uploaded to ZENODO : Public via https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5464662	Other -Project management
13	D-JRP13-5.2	DMP reviewed	M30	M33		The OHEJP WP4 team reviewed and approved WORLDCOM's online DMP in the CDP tool in December 2020.	3
13	D-JRP13-5.3	Organisation of project review meeting	M45	M45		WorldCOM consortium review meeting held in September 2021	Other – project management
13	D-JRP13-5.4	Final 12 month technical and financial reports prepared for Year 3	M36	M38		Both technical and financial reports have been uploaded to Zenodo and can be accessed at:	Other – project management

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
						Public at https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5499692	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-01	Generation of sequence information for pathogens and resistance genes of interest.	M30	Y		Deliverable 1: Prevalence of ESBL subtypes in bacterial pathogens and a sequence database of selected alleles, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4019839
13	M-JPR13-AMR2.1-02	Transfer of relevant sequence information for development and training of novel machine learning algorithms.	M48	N	M56	Due to delays in the associated deliverable D-JRP13-1.2 arising from other commitments, the UoS is not yet ready to inform / receive the sequence information for training a machine learning algorithm.
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-07	Performance testing of lateral flow or LAMP detection completed	M48	Y		All developed LAMP assays have been validated.
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-08	Smartphone App for curation of assay results developed	M48	Y		The smartphone app has been successfully validated on example colorimetric LAMP assay results and further experiments have been planned to prepare a manuscript.
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-11	Project review meeting organised	M45	Y		Held in September 2021
13	M-JPR15-AMR2.1-12	Technical and financial reports prepared	M48	N		Technical report completed by M49. Financial reports will be completed by end of M49

4. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
<p>Population genomics and antimicrobial resistance dynamics of Escherichia coli in wastewater and river environments. Delgado-Blas JF, Ovejero CM, David S, Montero N, Calero-Caceres W, Garcillan-Barcia MP, de la Cruz F, Muniesa M, Aanensen DM, Gonzalez-Zorn B. Commun Biol. 2021 Apr 12;4(1):457. doi: 10.1038/s42003-021-01949-x (https://zenodo.org/record/5524433#.YcyB25HMJuR)</p>	YES		YES (2680 euros)

Additional output

PhD-thesis

[Emergence and dissemination of resistance mechanisms to last-resort antibiotics in human, animal and environmental bacteria](#) [Thesis]. Delgado Blas, José Francisco (2021). ID Code: 64821. Director: González Zorn, Bruno

Posters

For WP1-T3 - an abstract entitled 'Automated detection of AMR target genes using loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP)' was submitted by PDRA Brian Gardner at UoS to the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9th-11th June 2021 in Copenhagen. This was selected as an e-Poster presentation.

For WP2-T2 and WP2-T3, poster entitled "Rapid detection and discrimination of closely related Enterobacteriaceae CTX-M group 1 variants, *bla*_{CTX-M-1} and *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, using an internally controlled multiplex loop-primer endonuclease cleavage loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LEC-LAMP) assay" was presented by Owen Higgins at the 2021 Microbiology Society conference, the OHEJP 2021 ASM, and the ECCMID 2021 conference.

For WP2-T1 and WP2-T2, posters entitled "Development of LAMP assays for the detection of key AMR targets in animal faeces and water samples" and "Rapid LAMP detection of key AMR targets for use as bed-side and/or pen-side diagnostics" were presented by Marwa Hassan at the 2021 Microbiology Society conference and the OHEJP 2021 ASM, respectively.

For WP2-T3, a poster entitled "Dynamics of quinolone- and cephalosporin-resistant *Escherichia coli* carriage along the production chain in Thuringian pigsties" was presented by Nicola Pfeifer at the OHEJP 2021 ASM.

For WP2-T1 and WP2-T2 an abstract entitled "Whole-genome sequencing of phenotypically characterized isolates from various settings" was presented by Vera Manageiro at the OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9th-11th June 2021 in Copenhagen (e-Poster).

Outcomes

For WP1-T2, the publication "Population genomics and antimicrobial resistance dynamics of *Escherichia coli* in wastewater and river environments" (DOI: 10.1038/s42003-021-01949-x) developed within the framework of the WorldCOM project was published in *Communications Biology*, showing a global understanding of the AMR by integrating multiple genomic and functional analyses and comparing resistant *E. coli* populations from two distinct ecological niches, wastewater and river environments. The fundamental microbiological knowledge generated with this work contributes to the understanding of the genetic organization of environmental bacteria and establishes the basis for future studies in antimicrobial resistance dynamics.

Albeit not ready yet for dissemination, the LAMP and LEC-LAMP assays developed in WP2 are currently being trialed and publications are being generated. Once these are available and protocols and Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) are developed in WP4, then these are attractive targets for dissemination. This also goes for the lateral flow tests and smartphone detection app developed in WP3.

5. Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries

NUI Galway participates in the MedVetKlebs OHEJP project, and is a member of the Med-Vet-Net association. Prof Morris is part of a JPIAMR network aimed at identifying robust, measurable

surveillance indicators and methodologies for the monitoring of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in the environment.

FLI participates in the JPIAMR consortia HECTOR and OASIS. HECTOR aims to identify determinants of host restriction of *Escherichia coli* strains and their potential association with AMR transmission and prevalence. OASIS aims to develop an AMR surveillance strategy, based on the Lot Quality Assurance Sampling approach, in a One Health context, and applicable in high-, middle-, and low-income countries.

UCM participates in the AVANT EU project, in ARDIG and FARMED, both from OHEJP, as well as in the MSCA CARTNET. Input from these projects will be relevant for WORLDCOM, and active participation between OHEJP projects will be encouraged for the benefit of OHEJP. Further, thanks to the application for Short Term Missions in OHEJP, Dr. Burke from NUI Galway visited the lab at UCM in summer 2021.

INSA is also participating in FED-AMR and FULL-FORCE projects from OHEJP, which outcomes will be important for WORLDCOM and vice-versa.

We are fully convinced that at the end of the project the tool obtained will be very useful, so it will be presented to EFSA and ECDC.

Finally, members of the DISCoVeR OHEJP Project from the Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung (Dr Correia Carreira and Dr Perestrelo) contacted Dr van Vliet from the University of Surrey, for support with using the data from Deliverable D-JRP13-1.1 available from Zenodo. They were provided with additional datasets from public databases and training for accessing and extracting the data of interest.

6. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	
Delay in work plan execution	Yes ¹
Conflicts within the consortium	
Lack of commitment of partners	
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	
Poor intra-project relationship	
Potential entry/exit of partners	
Other risks (please describe)	

Additional information

¹Related with COVID-19 lock down.

JRP14-AMR2.1-FULL-FORCE

1. Summary of the work carried out in year 4

The goal of the FULL-FORCE project is to supply 17 EU partners with a technological toolbox and hands-on training in Single-Molecule Real-Time (SMRT) sequencing, and to apply this knowledge on six study cases and applications in metagenomics and AMR transmission models. Using this state-of-the-art technology, public health and veterinary labs will have the capacity to perform full-length sequencing, and gain detailed insight in mobile genetic elements (MGEs) which carry antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes within and across species.

In Y4, corresponding to the second year of the project, the main focus went to (i) the application of the FULL-FORCE Plasmid Assembly (FFPA) pipeline during an internal proficiency test, (ii) start-up of

the five study cases in WP2, and (iii) applications on metagenomics datasets (WP3). However, the strong laboratory focus which is inherent to the project set-up, continued to suffer from the pandemic. Many consortium members are still reoriented towards COVID-19 surveillance, causing significant delays in deliverables and milestones of the FULL-FORCE project, as elaborated more in detail in the sections below. The physical progress meeting which was planned during ECCMID 2021 in Vienna, was cancelled and postponed to a hybrid meeting on November 22 in Brussels. However, we are still confident that most goals of the FULL-FORCE project are still within reach, also thanks to a six-month extension which was applied for in May 2021.

- The main goal of the FULL-FORCE project is to enable consortium partners to reach a sufficient technical level in plasmid sequencing. To maximize the output from this project, SSI scientists involved in WP1 developed an easy-to-use software package (FULL-FORCE Plasmid Assembler), which will automatically perform hybrid assemblies through the built-in UniCycler program from a combination of short and long sequence reads. A re-evaluation of this tool and possible publication plans will be discussed early January.
- A proficiency test to assess each institute's capacity for SMRT sequencing is currently ongoing. Five multi-drug resistance *E. coli* strains were sent to 16 participating institutes. During the FULL-FORCE meeting, details were discussed (see below).
- Although WP2 (five cases studies implementing long-read sequencing on existing datasets) has suffered some delays, substantial progress has been made. In four of the five study cases, phylogenetic analyses on short-read datasets are ongoing to identify reference strains and plasmids for detailed study by long-read technology.
- WP3 (metagenomics studies using long-read technology) has very well advanced. DTU published a manuscript on the plasmidome of sewage samples using methodology which was optimized during FULL-FORCE.
- In the context of WP4, a protocol for harmonized bacterial conjugation has been established. The robustness of this method will be assessed with selected FULL-FORCE partners in the first half of Y5, and intense collaboration between partners of WP2 and WP4 are foreseen in M42-54.
- The design and parameterisation of a transmission spread model of pAMR in the simulation framework SimInf is currently ongoing in collaboration between the consortium partners of WP5. The second task in WP5 to perform exposure assessment of horizontal and vertical transmitted amr has been initiated and a first report completed.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WPO Project management

WPO-T1-meetings and telcalls

The annual consortium meeting, planned during ECCMID 2021 (Vienna) was **postponed** due to COVID-19 measures. This was replaced by a hybrid meeting in Brussels on November 22, 2021. Regular teleconferences were held to discuss progress and planning of ongoing WPs.

WPO-T2-reporting

In total, 15 new deliverables were uploaded to Zenodo during 2021. The 9 and 12 month reports (Y4) were submitted in due time.

WPO-T3- central data repository

FULL-FORCE is using a centralized data repository to upload sequence- and metadata which are generated during WP1 and WP2. Originally, we planned to use the AMR data hub of the European

A	B
Post-sequencing reporting	strain1 str
Institution: <i>Please insert your institution here!</i>	
DNA purification method (RIVM/other)	RIVM RIV
Flow cell total output	
Total raw output from entire flow cell in gigabasepair?	15.2
Number of barcodes/samples in flow cell?	5
raw ONT output before filtering (NanoPlot on sequencing_summary.txt)	
Guppy version used for basecalling?	v4.0.14
basecalling configuration? (fast, high-accuracy, high-accuracy methylation-aware)	hac_m
number of reads?	200 000
number of bases?	3 000 000 000
median fragment length?	6 200
median quality?	10.1
read length N50?	15 000
longest read?	150 000
ONT after filtering to q≥8 (NanoPlot on filtered barcodeXX.fastq.gz)	
tools used for filtering? (program, version, used options)	NanoFilt
number of reads?	150 000
number of bases?	270 000 000
median fragment length?	6 200
median quality?	10.1
read length N50?	15 000
longest read?	150 000
Short read technology used? (Illumina/Ion Torrent)	Illumina
raw short reads before filtering	
number of reads?	1 500 000
number of bases?	225 000 000
short reads after filtering	
tools used for filtering? (program, version, used options)	rimmomatic_v3.6
adaptor removal? (yes/no)	yes
minimum quality for filtering?	q20 end-trim
minimum length for filtering?	140
number of reads?	800 000
number of bases?	120 000 000
hybrid assembly	
tools used for assembly? (program, version, used options)	FFPA_v1.py
number of contigs? (circular)	4
number of contigs? (linear >10 kb)	1
number of contigs? (linear <10 kb)	3
total length of contigs? (sum of contig lengths)	5.3
identified ESBL/pAmpC gene	CTX-M-15
identified replicon of plasmid ESBL/pAmpC gene	incI1
exact length of contig carrying ESBL/pAmpC gene	112 456
(name, which you choose to give the contig carrying ESBL/pAmpC gene to submit for OwnCloud)	p1_SSI_RIVM_R
ONT coverage calculation	
Short reads coverage calculation	50 943 396
Did you handpolish the plasmid sequence?	yes
Did you run other polishing tools on the plasmid sequence?	no
If yes, which polishing tools and how?	n/a

year of FULL-FORCE.

WP1-T2-SMRT sequencing workshop

This task was completed during the first annual year of FULL-FORCE.

WP1-T3-proficiency test for MGE sequencing

Each institution's proficiency in SMRT sequencing is being assessed afterwards using a proficiency test, organised and coordinated by SSI. Given the delay in the workshop, this EQA is being organised in M37-52. Upon discussion during and after the workshop in October 2020, it was decided to include 5 *Escherichia coli* strains from BfR (GER) as reference strains, since they have been sequenced using Illumina, MinION and PacBIO technologies.

In the PT instructions, it was highlighted that the FULL-FORCE SMRT protocol by RIVM (current version 2) should be followed to produce the ONT sequencing data, so all data can be aggregated into one common method paper. However, as many partners have already established in-house/homemade sequencing protocol (e.g. for DNA purification or hybrid assembly), the option to benchmark these against the FULL-FORCE results was also foreseen.

The strains have been sent out mid-November and at time of writing (M42), six institutes have submitted data.

First analyses and sharing of experiences pointed at difficulties with the elaborate RIVM purification protocol, as it gave highly viscous/concentrated DNA samples which clogged the pores despite producing markedly higher N50s. Therefore, data analysis and the resulting publication will be focused on comparison of DNA extraction methodology and influence of minION 9.4 and 10.3 flow cells on full-length plasmid sequencing.

During the November meeting, it was decided to use the R9.4.1 flow cell, high-accuracy basecaller and in-house extraction methods with a DNA/RNA Shield step added. For those which are unable to

COMPARE Consortium and the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). However, we were not successful in reaching an agreement with ENA, who is still negotiating single-subcontractor model for hubs created during COMPARE. Therefore, we have decided to use a commercial cloud tool (OwnCloud) for temporal data storage during FULL-FORCE.

Currently, this cloud stores over 1.4 Tb of data which is exchanged among partners.

WP0-T4-data management plan

The FULL-FORCE Data Management Plan was constructed in the CDP software and uploaded to <https://apps.lisam.com/app/#Apps/CDP>. As important part of the DMP, a framework agreement on Material Transfer was drafted, circulated and signed among all 18 participating institutions. This agreement covers all transfer of data and strains during FULL-FORCE.

WP1 SMRT implementation

WP1-T1-methodology for MGE sequencing

This task was completed during the first annual

perform the high-accuracy basecaller, it was suggested to buy a computer with powerful graphical card, or to ask a FULL-FORCE member to run the basecaller.

WP2 Genome studies

In WP2, the acquired SMRT toolbox will be applied in the (re-)sequencing of AMR strains from various research and surveillance projects in WP2 including EU projects such as EFFORT, COMPARE, ENGAGE and ARDIG, as well as national and EU surveillance activities for which short read sequences are available. In Y4, the focus in WP2 was on **hypothesis generation based on short-read sequence data** for the five defined studies cases (T2.1-2.5). Short-read Illumina data will allow comparison of total plasmid content and phylogenetic relatedness of isolates and based on those results choose a subset of isolates for MinION runs.

WP2-T1- MGE evolution in longitudinal sample sets (ARDIG, ABRES)

This task focuses on Inc1 plasmids, and focuses on the research question regarding the European diversity in the complete sequences, and whether these plasmids evolve either host-or country specific. Data on Inc1 containing samples from more than 1,000 longitudinal and annual surveillances was collected (see figure and table below), and MLST type of the host was determined. Phylogenetic analysis was performed by Mike Brouwer, showing cross-sectorial and pan-European conservation of certain plasmid lineages. Based on this information, a selection will be made for long-read sequencing (M-JRP19-M12).

Figure 2. cgMLST typing of Inc1 positive E. coli and Salmonella strains from EU monitoring, showing vast diversity in host cell types.

WP2-T2- MGE evolution in cross-sectional data sets (EFFORT, ENGAGE & National Surveillance)

Only preliminary actions have been taken due to the long-term absence of task leader Jens (bFR). The task is now transferred to Joost Hordijk (RIVM), who should be able to complete the set goals by the end of the project.

WP2-T3- Klebsiella pneumoniae: the canary in the coalmine

K. pneumoniae constitute a significant clinical problem and represents a species in which several new AMR genes were first discovered before spreading to other pathogens. *K. pneumoniae* has a wide ecological distribution, diverse DNA composition, AMR gene diversity and high plasmid burden. This is a reason for assuming that the horizontal gene transfer occurs at high frequency in this species. Chromosomal DNA and plasmid DNA will be analysed and information regarding resistance genes and molecular strain typing will be evaluated through SMRT sequencing.

Available strain collections were reported from:

- Human
 - o Denmark = 192 isolates
 - o Sweden = 215 isolates
 - o The Netherlands = 578 isolates
 - o Portugal = 144 isolates
 - Animal/environment
 - o Italy = 15 isolates (cats and dogs)
 - o Norway = 2 isolates (dogs)
 - o France = 105 isolates (cats and dogs)
 - o Germany = 103 isolates (livestock, zoo and environment)
- = 191 isolates (wastewater and slaughterhouse)

PHAS (Alma Brolund) and RIVM performed analyses on this dataset (ST type, and carbapenemase gene content), and found wide variety in sequence types of which some are limited to either human, animal or environment (Figure 2). Likewise, clear association between certain sequence types and carbapenemase genes (e.g., OXA-181 and ST873) was found. More specific phylogenetic analyses are currently (M42) being performed at RIVM (Antoni Hendrickx) to propose a strain selection for long-read sequencing (M-JRP19-M12).

■ = only present in human isolates
■ = only present in non-human isolates

Figure 2. Preliminary analysis of *K. pneumoniae* strains under study.

WP2-T4- AMR in horses: commensals and pathogens

This task objective is to investigate the spread of ESBL-producing Enterobacteriaceae in horses in Europe. The focus will be on blaCTX-M-1 and blaSHV-12 genes. To date, isolates carrying blaCTX-M-1 predominate in horses. This is due to clonal dissemination as well as the spread of closely-related IncHI1 plasmids. The success of this plasmid gene combination might be due to the fact that the IncHI1 plasmid also carries the fos-operon, involved in the metabolism of fructo-oligosaccharides, which could give the plasmid a selective advantage in the gut of the horse. The combination IncHI1+ blaCTX-M-1 appears to be almost exclusively linked to horses. Less is known of the epidemiology of blaSHV-12, which is often associated with IncX3-plasmids.

The inventory of available isolates from horses, both commensals and clinical isolates, among participating partners is completed (n=264). All short-read sequences have been uploaded to owncloud, raw reads are assembled and the plasmidome determined/filtered. The plasmidome is comprised out of 8 clusters.

Based on this information, a selection will be made for long-read sequencing (M-JRP19-M14).

WP2-T5- MGEs in Salmonella Infants and Kentucky

Salmonella Infantis is typically most prevalent *Salmonella* serotype in broilers, and the 4th most prevalent serovar in humans. It is known for increasing drug resistance. In 2007, a first report of megaplasmid pESI (300 kb) was published, while follow-up studies showed that this IncP plasmid contains a *mer* operon, yersiniabactin, toxin-antitoxin systems and AMR genes. Currently it is being reported in Israel, Italy, Switzerland, US, and Hungary¹.

¹ Franco A, et al. PLoS One 2015; 10:e0144802. Aviv G, et al. Environ Microbiol 2014; 16:977–994 ; Hindermann D, et al. Front Microbiol 2017; 8:1322; Tate H, et al. Antimicrob Agents Chemother 2017; 61:e00488-17; Carfora V, et al. Front Microbiol 2018; 9:1880

This task examines the European distribution and evolution of this plasmid, and is led by ISS and IZSLT, who previously published on the phylogeny of *S. Infantis*. During FULL-FORCE, data from their publication will be merged with pESI positive *Salmonella Infantis* strains from contributing partners, to study its diversity and evolution.

Samples were selected among partners, based on the following criteria:

- Phenotypic markers: SMX-TET-SUL resistance (NAL/CIP)
- Genotypic markers: presence of IncFIB(pN55391), tet(A), sul1 and dfrA14
- In case ESBL profile detected, these isolates should be preferably included.

The number of available isolates are listed in the table on the right, and short reads were uploaded to Owncloud. Based on this information and subsequent phylogenetic analyses (IZSLT, see Figure above), a selection has been made for long-read sequencing.

WP2-T6- Evaluation of tools for MGE typing

A benchmark article will be written on current tools, using a search in pubmed/ncbi using a specific string, ie. ((plasmid*[Title]) AND (((software[Title/Abstract] OR (tool*[Title/Abstract])) OR (program[Title/Abstract]))) AND (((((((predict*) OR (sequenc*) OR (identif*)) OR (contig*)) OR (assembl*)) OR (NGS) OR (WGS) OR (HTS)). The article deadline is set on M58.

WP3 : Culture-Independent typing and metagenomics

WP3-T1-MGE analyses in metagenomic datasets

This task has been completed in the first annual year of FULL-FORCE.

WP3-T2-culture-independent methods for plasmid identification

The extraction methodology developed during Y3 was applied on waste water samples in Y4. The results were published in MSystems (<https://journals.asm.org/doi/10.1128/mSystems.00283-21>). This study represents, to the best of our knowledge, the first study to investigate plasmidomes at a global scale using long read sequencing from complex untreated domestic sewage.

WP4 : Functional characterization of AMR mobile genetic elements (MGE)-carrying AMR genes and bacterial host associations

WP4-T1-MGE and host selection

As planned, a complete protocol of conjugation assays in liquid cultures has been drafted. This protocol has the objectives (i) to isolate the plasmid of interest in a plasmid-free recipient strain, (ii) to determine if the plasmid is self-transmissible or only mobilizable, and (iii) to determine the conjugation rate based on the Simonsen model and its derivatives (Simonsen et al., Huisman et al.). This protocol is derived from Huisman et al. that provides all tools to estimate conjugation rates and to simulate population dynamics in an R package and Shiny app (<https://ibz-shiny.ethz.ch/jhuisman/conjugator/>).

An additional protocol for conjugation assays on solid medium is also provided representing a useful alternative protocol for mating assays (see 3.).

In its complete form, the protocol requires 2 conjugation experiments:

- A first one starting from a donor (D) + recipient (R) mating in which D is usually a field strain.
- A second one using transconjugants (T) + R' mating in which R' has a different chromosomal selective marker to the one used in the first experiment.

WP4-T2-In vitro characterization

The protocol developed in WP4-T1 will be applied in (i) a proficiency test, in which conjugation rates of an identical D-R pair will be assessed by five institutes, and (ii) the shufflon regions in Inc11 plasmids studied in task 2.1., i.e. different pilV-Cterm. The latter will be effectuated by constructing plasmid mutants with only one pilV-Cterm, to have all possibilities and compare them also with WT plasmids in mating assays.

WP4-T3-Host association studies

This task has not yet been initiated at the time of writing.

WP5 : modelling

The objectives of WP5 are to address: i) gaps in quantitative knowledge on the spread of pAMR which will be essential to direct future focused research, ii) insight in the uncertainty around the effect of measures reducing pAMR prevalence in the food production chains, and iii) identification of key elements in the production chains to mitigate the risk of human exposure.

WP3-T1-Model design for AMR transmission(M25-M42)

The parameterisation and design of a transmission spread model of pAMR in the simulation framework SimInf is ongoing. SVA (Stefan Widgren) has coordinated two teleconferences with the task participants. The first teleconference was a startup meeting and the second teleconference was a meeting to discuss horizontal vs. vertical AMR transmission. A necessary but challenging step in stochastic modelling is to determine parameters such that the model generates data that are consistent with observations. Parameterization is preferably conducted within a Bayesian framework and in WP5 we are focusing on using Approximate Bayesian computation (ABC), a recent computational approach for simulation-based inference. Development has been completed to add ABC functionality to the open-source SimInf modelling R package (<https://github.com/stewid/SimInf>). The figure below illustrates using ABC in SimInf to fit parameters from data of infected chicken broilers published in Dame-Korevar et al. (2017), and a model with susceptible (S) and infected (I) chicken, showing (for example) that the ageing parameter has a tighter posterior distribution compared to the transmission parameter. Work is ongoing to identify and include other sources of broiler data for parameterisation of more complex models.

WP3-T2 Exposure assessment of horizontal and vertical transmitted AMR (M25-M54)

This task has been initiated. The objective of this task will be on investigating the relative importance of exposure routes from the broiler production chain to humans, as this will indicate where intervention measures to reduce transmission to humans will be most effective, given that an intervention is realistic for the specific exposure route. The terms horizontal and vertical transmission are used in a different way than usual, horizontal transmission meaning AMR transmission from chickens to farmers or slaughterhouse personnel, vertical transmission meaning AMR transmission related to chicken meat consumption. As planned, a report on quantification of horizontal vs. vertical transmission of AMR was completed (D-JRP19-WP5.D2).

3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
14	D-JRP14-0.D1	Start-up meeting report	M27	M27		Confidential due to research updates; 10.5281/zenodo.4275887	8
14	D-JRP14-0.D2	Activity report Y3	M36	M42		Public; 10.5281/zenodo.4896736	8
14	D-JRP14-0.D3	Recorded webinar tutorial ENA AMR data hub	M27	M27		Public; 10.5281/zenodo.4277545	3
14	D-JRP14-WP0.D4	Annual meeting report with (re-)approval of DMP	M48	M48		Public; https://zenodo.org/deposit/5793860	8
14	D-JRP19-WP0.D5	Financial and activity report Y4	M48	M48		Public; https://zenodo.org/deposit/5793868	8

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
14	D-JRP14-1.D7	Delivery of analysis results of proficiency test by partners to SSI	M39	M42		CONFIDENTIAL UNTIL PUBLICATION; 10.5281/zenodo.4896743	8
14	D-JRP14-WP1.D8	Completion of final report of proficiency tests	M48		M54	In progress, some COVID-19 delays & discussion on how to proceed with results	
14	D-JRP14-2.D1	Submission of sequence- and metadata of longitudinal samples at ENA hub	M33	M42		CONFIDENTIAL UNTIL PUBLICATION; https://zenodo.org/record/4905398	8
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D2	Submission of sequence- and metadata of cross-sectional samples at ENA hub	M48		M58	See above, delays due to long-term absence of task lead and deputy lead. Task is now transferred to Joost Hordijk (RIVM)	
14	D-JRP14-2.D3	Submission of sequence- and metadata of <i>K. pneumoniae</i> samples at	M33	M42		CONFIDENTIAL UNTIL PUBLICATION; https://zenodo.org/record/4896755	8

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
		ENA hub					
14	D-JRP14-2.D4	Submission of sequence- and metadata of <i>S. enterica</i> samples at ENA hub	M33	M42		CONFIDENTIAL UNTIL PUBLICATION; https://zenodo.org/record/4896772	8
14	D-JRP14-2.D5	Submission of sequence- and metadata of horse-related samples at ENA hub	M33	M42		CONFIDENTIAL UNTIL PUBLICATION; https://zenodo.org/record/4896789	8
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D6	List of relevant publicly available and in-house developed tools.	M48		M58	Merged with D-JRP14-WP2.D12, a single benchmark article will be prepared in Y5	
14	D-JRP19-WP2.D7	Submission of long-read sequencing data of longitudinal samples to ENA hub	M46		M50	Deadline for long-read sequencing has been set on M50	
14	D-JRP14-WP2.D8	Submission of long-read sequencing data of cross-sectional samples	M46		M50	Deadline for long-read sequencing has been set on M50	

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8)</i> <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
		to ENA hub					
14	D-JRP14- WP2.D9	Submission of long-read sequencing data of <i>S.</i> <i>Infantis</i> and <i>S. Kentucky</i> to ENA hub	M46		M50	Deadline for long-read sequencing has been set on M50	
14	D-JRP14- WP2.D10	Submission of long-read sequencing data of <i>K.</i> <i>pneumoniae</i> samples to ENA hub	M46		M50	Deadline for long-read sequencing has been set on M50	
14	D-JRP14- WP2.D11	Submission of long-read sequencing data AMR horse samples to ENA hub	M46		M50	Deadline for long-read sequencing has been set on M50	
14	D-JRP14- WP2.D12	Report on MGE tool testing for MGE characterization using full-length genomes	M48		M58	Merged with D-JRP14- WP2.D6, a single benchmark article will be prepared in Y5	
14	D-JRP14-3.D1	Database construction tailored at MGEs	M36	M36		Public; 10.5281/zenodo.430571 1	3

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
14	D-JRP14-3.D2	Protocol for plasmid DNA extraction from environmental samples	M34	M42		Public; 10.5281/zenodo.489679 1	2
14	D-JRP14-3.D3	Publication of the validated method for plasmid DNA extraction on environmental samples.	M40	M42		CONFIDENTIAL UNTIL PUBLICATION; 10.5281/zenodo.489672 2	1
14	D-JRP14-WP3.D4	Report on the comparison of available pipelines for metagenome analyses	M48		M58	Merged with D-JRP14-WP2.D6, a single benchmark article will be prepared in Y5	
14	D-JRP14-WP3.D5	Protocols for real time PCR detection of up to 32 ARGs in singleplex format.	M48		-	Due to the departure of task leader Ferando Esperon (INIA, SP) from the FULL-FORCE consortium, this task will not be completed.	
14	D-JRP14-4.D1	First collection of type-materials (MGEs and strains) to be shared between involved partners	M30	M42		CONFIDENTIAL UNTIL PUBLICATION; 10.5281/zenodo.448968 02	3

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
14	D-JRP14- WP4.D2	Refine additional collection of type- materials (MGEs and strains) to be shared between involved partners	M42	M42		Strain collection described in same deliverable report 10.5281/zenodo.448968 02	3
14	D-JRP14- WP4.D3	Set-up of protocols for measuring plasmid persistence in complex microbiota and small- scale testing	M46	M42		Protocol described in same deliverable 10.5281/zenodo.448968 02	2
14	D-JRP14- WP5.D2	A report on quantification of horizontal vs. vertical transmission of AMR	M39	M48		EMBARGO until 30/6/2022 https://zenodo.org/record/4925761	1
14	D-JRP14- WP5.D3	A report on using ABC methodology for parameter inference of a SimInf model designed for pAMR.	M42	M50		Delayed due to pandemic	

* Categories of Integrative activities: 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
14	M-JRP14-M1	Creation of specific data hubs in ENA AMR hub	M27	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M2	A teleconference or physical meeting on horizontal vs. vertical AMR transmission	M27	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M3	Selection of MGEs and host strains to be studied in T4.2	M28	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M4	A teleconference or physical meeting on input/output relationship between SimInf and sQMRA	M29	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M5	Publication of first version of data management plan	M30	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M6	3-days workshop on SMRT sequencing event	M30	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M7	Shipment of proficiency test data and strains	M32	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M8	Sharing of protocols, recipient- and host-strains, molecular tools	M33	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M9	An implementation of a SimInf model designed for pAMR transmission to be	M33	Yes		

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		studied in T5.1				
14	M-JRP14-M10	Final selection of longitudinal samples for SMRT sequencing	M34	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M11	Final selection of cross-sectional samples for SMRT sequencing	M46	No	M55	Long-term absence of task lead – now transferred to RIVM
14	M-JRP14-M12	Final selection of <i>K. pneumoniae</i> samples for SMRT sequencing	M46	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M13	Final selection of <i>S. enterica</i> Infantis and Kentucky samples for SMRT sequencing	M46	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M14	Final selection of horse-related samples for SMRT sequencing	M46	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M15	Analysis of proficiency test data by all partners	M46	No	M52	Delays in lab work due to pandemic
14	M-JRP14-M16	Individual reports of proficiency test sent to partners	M48	No	M54	Delays in lab work due to pandemic
14	M-JRP14-M17	Successful adaptation of plasmid purification protocol to field samples	M36	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M18	Selection of additional MGEs and host strains based on first outcomes of	M40	Yes		

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		WPs-2 and -3.				
14	M-JRP14-M19	Successful implementation of SMRT sequencing of field samples	M42	Yes		
14	M-JRP14-M20	A parameterised SimInf model designed for pAMR transmission to be studied in T5.2	M42	Yes		
14	JRP14-M21	Construction of Isogenic CIPR S. Kentucky ST198 strains carrying different SGI1-related elements	M45	No	-	Shift towards pESI work in S. infantis (M-JRP19-M23)
14	M-JRP14-M22	Transfer frequency data of representative InCHI1-CTX-M1 plasmids	M45	No	M52	Awaiting interlab validation of conjugation protocol (JRP14-WP4-T2)
14	M-JRP14-M23	Data on conjugative transfer of pESI plasmid from S. Infantis to other <i>Salmonella</i> serovars and other microbial species	M45	No	M52	Awaiting interlab validation of conjugation protocol (JRP14-WP4-T2)
14	M-JRP14-M24	Finalised hybrid assemblies of longitudinal samples	M46	No	M50	Delays in lab work due to pandemic
14	M-JRP14-M25	Finalised hybrid assemblies of cross-sectional samples	M46	No	M50	Delays in lab work due to pandemic
14	M-JRP14-M26	Finalised hybrid assemblies of S. Infantis	M46	No	M50	Delays in lab work due to pandemic

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		and S. Kentucky isolates				
14	M-JRP14-M27	Finalised hybrid assemblies of <i>K. pneumoniae</i> isolates	M46	No	M50	Delays in lab work due to pandemic
14	M-JRP14-M28	Finalised hybrid assemblies of AMR horse samples	M46	No	M50	Delays in lab work due to pandemic
14	M-JRP14-M29	Transfer frequency data of mcr plasmids of different incompatibility groups	M48	No	M52	Awaiting interlab validation of conjugation protocol (JRP14-WP4-T2)

4. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Diaconu EL, Carfora V, Alba P, Di Matteo P, Stravino F, Buccella C, Dell'Aira E, Onorati R, Sorbara L, Battisti A, Franco A. Novel IncFII plasmid harbouring blaNDM-4 in a carbapenem-resistant Escherichia coli of pig origin, Italy. J Antimicrob Chemother. 2020 Dec 1;75(12):3475-3479. doi: 10.1093/jac/dkaa374. https://zenodo.org/record/4451840#.YZPKcWDMJMO	YES		YES (processing charges unknown)
Kirstahler P, Teudt F, Otani S, Aarestrup FM, Pamp SJ. A Peek into the Plasmidome of Global Sewage. mSystems. 2021 May 26:e0028321. doi: 10.1128/mSystems.00283-21 https://zenodo.org/record/5543288#.YZPKXmDMJMO	YES		YES (processing charges unknown)

Additional output

None to report.

Outcomes

The FULL-FORCE Plasmid Assembler (FFPA) is a software which can be readily implemented in public health and veterinary labs (as well as in clinical labs), and will provide standardization in plasmid assembly. This is needed to allow comparisons of AMR plasmids across the EU.

5. *Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries*

- The SOLIDNESS network (JPIAMR, 2019-2020) which grouped experts in sequencing, plasmid biology and bioinformatics, and aims to streamline procedures for MGE sequencing. We build on their expertise to organise the PT.
- Cross-sectional and longitudinal bacterial samples of ENGAGE, EFFORT (Horizon 2020, 2013-2018) and ARDIG (OHEJP, JRP2, 2018-2020) projects have been selected for long-read sequencing during WP2.
- The KENTUCKY PhD project (OHEJP, 2020-2022) will use fully sequenced S. Kentucky strains (T2.4) to focus on the cell biology behind MGE transfer.
- Potential collaborations with ECDC and EFSA are envisioned in 2022, for sustainable implementation of long-read sequencing technology in surveillance of AMR in Europe. Therefore, we aim to invite EFSA and ECDC experts to the final meeting of the consortium, planned at the end of 2022.

6. *List of critical risks*

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

Additional information

All items listed “yes” were detailed in the parts above.

JRP15-AMR2.1-FED-AMR

1. *Summary of the work carried out in year 4*

In the FED-AMR project, extracellular DNA (exDNA) is presented as an important environmental reservoir for antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs). Furthermore, bacterial transformation contributes to the horizontal gene transfer (HGT) of antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs). However, empirical

data on the impact of bacterial transformation in the environment are lacking, this project aims to rectify this.

In the second year of the FED-AMR project WP1 has been able to coordinate the scientific and administrative matters between the partners including the scientific meetings and scientific webinars, budgeting and overall coordination as discussed in the 9M report.

In WP2, all samples have been collected. Sample cultivation, antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) and genomic characterization of the collected bacterial isolates is in progress. The FED-AMR bacterial collection is a diverse set of relevant bacteria, from several distinct reservoirs that will overall contribute to understand the dissemination of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) within the compartments, reinforcing the One Health approach. In addition, extracellular and total DNA have been analysed through 16S metagenomics (measurement of bacterial diversity) and through gene enrichment [characterization of AMR genes, including the resistome but also the mobilome, and heavy metal resistance genes (MRGs)]. Results derived from those analysis are now being interpreted through statistical comparisons. The first results from WP2 were already presented at the OHEJP ASM2021 and other works were submitted to ECCMID 2021 and accepted for poster presentation.

WP3 has finished the epidemiological survey of zoonotic *C. difficile* ribotypes across participant countries and evaluated their dissemination, including those resistant to antimicrobials, between humans, animals and the environment using the pig farm as proof of concept. Also, several sampling campaigns were conducted to enrich the collection of *C. difficile* isolates targeting several animal species including previously uncharacterized for *C. difficile*, such as llamas and alpacas, and food, like strawberries. All these sampling campaigns are concluded and WGS and AMR characterization of *C. difficile* isolates is ongoing. The obtained genomes from important ribotypes are being gathered for a genomic study. The first results were presented in the OHEJP ASM2021 as posters. A scientific manuscript with the results from the Portuguese HOAL is being prepared.

The analysis of antibiotics, elements and herbicides for all regions tested in WP4 is still in progress. It is being performed by the three specialized laboratories in WP4 (Austria, UK and Poland). preliminary results have been already obtained and their integration with other WPs will occur soon after.

WP5 has finalised all risk assessments for the *in vitro* gut model and set up of the model has begun. We prepared the *E. coli* strain and DNA amplicon, encoding rifampicin resistance, to be used in the gut model and confirmed the ability of the *E. coli* strain to acquire antimicrobial resistance from the DNA amplicon, which completed the first WP5 deliverable. We are currently optimising the *in vitro* pig gut fermentation model conditions to demonstrate optimum growth of the recipient strain and demonstrate the transfer of AMR using amplicons.

WP6 has focused on finalizing the protocol for a systematic review on factors influencing the prevalence of antibiotic resistance in the environment and on formulating and validating a mathematical model for the dynamics of microbial communities. The protocol was submitted to *Environment International* and following extensive feedback from the two editors, it has been changed to a “systematic evidence map”. We are currently addressing the editors comments and resubmit a revised version (deadline mid February 2022). The protocol has also been registered to OSF (<https://osf.io/a8gv6/>). With respect to the task on modelling microbial communities, we have formulated a new model for this and explored other models for comparison purposes to refine our research questions. We are also developing *in silico* data to validate our approach.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1: Project Management and Communication

While the ongoing pandemic still has effects on the progress in our project, the continuous exchange through the monthly online teleconferences has played a large role in the management of the FED-AMR project.

Due to issues arising from recruitment delays in both this and last year, the pandemic, equipment issues and other obstacles, we have had to slightly adjust our timetable this year and shift some tasks to Y5. The 6 month extension has and will aid us considerably to achieve our goals.

WP1-T1- Scientific Management (M25-M60)

This task is **ongoing** for the whole project duration (M25 to M60). The experts of the FED-AMR Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) have participated in decision-making processes affecting the FED-AMR project.

WP1-T1-ST1- Coordination of sampling, laboratory experiments and building a database (M25-M33)

This subtask was already **completed** in year 3. Check the 12-months report 2020.

WP1-T1-ST2- Webinar forum and Skype meetings for instant scientific interactions (M30-M58)

This subtask is continuing from Y3. Four webinars were already held in year 3. In the year 4 of the project we continued with the scientific webinars. Up to now, Dr. Maja Rupnik held a webinar on “*Clostridioides difficile* – an environmental perspective” and Dr Ana Sofia Ribierto Duarte talked to us on her experience with “Metagenomics and analysis of metagenomics data”. All webinar presentations were recorded as previously indicated with permission of speakers and participants. The recordings were made available to the consortium and are confidential, as they are only meant for the consortium members that could not take part or would like to revisit the webinar. As a general rule, the dissemination outside of the FED-AMR project is not permitted.

The management team at AGES is also organizing monthly online meetings. Minutes of these meetings are registered and shared with the project partners for approval. A definitive version incorporating all suggestions received is distributed and published in the AGES website (<https://FED-AMR.ages.at>). In addition, regular calls occur between the deputy leader of WP1 and the leader of WP1-T1.1 to discuss the evolution of the different WPs and tasks. Such meetings will continue for the duration of the project as necessary in addition to the monthly TCs for progress report.

WP1-T1-ST3- Project Meetings (M25-M52)

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the next project meeting is postponed to April 2022 (Y5) will be held in Lisbon. This subtask is **ongoing**.

An online interim meeting took place on the 14th of December 2021. This meeting was held to exchange more in-depth status updates and discuss overarching themes and questions in our project.

WP1-T2- Administrative Management (M25-M60)

As described in past reports the administrative management (AM) at 2-AGES coordinates the joint activities in the frame of the FED-AMR project. Additionally, each partner had appointed an Administrative Representative who is and will be in direct contact with the AGES AM whenever necessary.

As indicated before, considerable effort was put in the assistance with budgetary issues for the entire project and specific partners, which was conducted in close cooperation with the project lead, the scientific manager and the partners in question.

A risk management on a daily basis is also taken care of by the administrative team, in coordination with the leading staff. The overarching risk management strategy initiated in year 3 of the project was put in place by the AM and the Scientific Manager (SM), in consultation with the FED-AMR Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) to ensure that adverse situations are properly handled along the course of the project, which is being highlighted in the Data Management Plan. This task is **ongoing**.

WP1-T3- Data and Protocol Management (M25-M58)

A first version of the Data and Protocol Management Plan was already delivered on M34. In year 4, the DMP has been updated in the new OHEJP data management platform CDP, with details of FED-AMR data throughout the project, with information provided to the leader and deputy leader by task leaders on their datasets. In addition, the task leader and deputy leader have generated a metadata file for all samples collected in WP2. This file will facilitate the introduction of metadata in the CPD platform and data analysis. This task is **ongoing**.

WP2: Field experiments: Determination of the naturally occurring ARG background load and microbial biodiversity in the tested environmental compartments (M25-M60)

WP2 takes place over the first, second and third year of the project (Y3, Y4 and Y5). The end of this WP has been postponed to M54. In Y4 a postdoc was recruited by INSA, Daniel Olivença, who is dedicated to statistical analysis and (bio) informatics, namely harmonizing the consortium's WP2 data and correlating them with other WPs.

WP2-T1- Assemble list of sampling compartments and points. Determination of test areas representative for the European regions (North, West, East, South) (M25-M30)

This task was already **completed** in year 3. Check the 12-months report 2020.

WP2-T2- Establish common protocol for sampling and data analyses to facilitate comparability of the results between European test areas (North, West, East, South) and local sampling locations (M25-M33)

This task was already **completed** in year 3. Check the 12-months report 2020.

WP2-T3- Assess microbial and ARG diversity with NGS in the selected test environments (metagenomics). Compare microbial and ARG diversity between ecosystems and over ecosystem boundaries. Characterization of cultivable environmental bacteria on complete nutrient and minimal media (M27-M50)

Due to the situation caused by the COVID-19 pandemic and the tight budget available for genomic analysis, the FED-AMR consortium decided in Year 3 to introduce changes with respect to this task, as also indicated in task [JRP15-WP2-T2](#) (see 12-months report 2020). Up to now, most samples have been collected and cultivated by the FED-AMR partners. The last sampling was finalized in early June 2021.

As explained in the culture protocol, **isolates** from six bacterial species that may be resistant to one or more critically important antimicrobials (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Salmonella spp*, *Staphylococcus aureus* methicillin resistant, *Enterococcus faecium* and *Enterococcus faecalis* vancomycin resistant) have been obtained along the sample cultivation process. These bacterial species selected from the WHO Global priority list of antibiotic-resistant bacteria to favour their identification in our human, animal and environmental compartments and to search for equal or similar genetic traits than human pathogenic bacteria. AMR is now being evaluated or even completed in some countries through diverse AST, for a selection of **isolates** gathered in each country. The methodology followed depends on the availability of each test in the participant countries and includes determination of the minimum inhibitory concentration (MICs) by broth microdilution or E-test and/or disc diffusion as preliminary screening. Countries have already started to whole genome sequence (WGS) for a selection of their isolates and started or even finalized the phylogenetic analysis.

In addition, the microbial diversity has been evaluated by characterising all 16S variable regions (V1-V9) through 16S rRNA metagenomics in the **DNA samples** (extracellular and total DNA), which is more sensitive than the conventional 16S amplicon sequencing. In parallel, the same samples have been analysed through gene enrichment to detect ARGs (see task WP2-T2 and subtask WP2-T3.2). As explained in Year 3, gene enrichment allows us to dispense with both shotgun metagenomics (WP2-

T3.1 task) and qPCR (WP2-T4). All countries shipped to the Austrian company their DNA up to June of Year 4 and both analysis finalized in December 2021. In addition, an “analysis group” composed by three consortium members was created to be able to interpret the target enrichment and the 16S results in a harmonized way. This analytical work consist mostly of statistical and bioinformatics analysis that involve data cleaning and processing using diverse R packages like Phyloseq or Vegan, among others, to determine which microbial groups and ARG genes are associated with the different environmental compartments studied.

As for the six clinically relevant species isolated from the collected samples, WGS analysis (task WP2.6) is being performed. This task is **ongoing**.

WP2-T3-ST1- Shotgun sequencing and bioinformatic analyses of AMR genes and MGEs (M37-M48)

The FED-AMR partners agreed on the evaluation and comparison of ARGs using a novel methodology based on gene capture probes or gene enrichment (see task WP2-T2 and subtask WP2-T3.2). This novel methodology allowed us to analyse the AMR genes and MGEs, and dispense with both conventional shotgun metagenomics (this subtask) and qPCR (task WP2-T4) for the collected samples. So, this subtask does no longer exist in a methodological point of view, but the aim will persist, and **results will come from WP2-T3.ST2**.

WP2-T3-ST2- Gene enrichment with gene capture probes (M31-M48)

After confirming in Year 3 the better performance of the gene enrichment methodology over the conventional shotgun metagenomics for detection of the resistome, project partners started sending their DNA samples (both extracellular and total DNAs) to a third party that has performed the gene enrichment and the 16S shotgun metagenomics for all samples in WP2. Last samples arrived to the facilities of the Austrian company by M43 and all the target enrichment results for all countries have been received. These include the ARGs diversity in each of the samples, DNA type (extracellular vs. total) tested, and the raw FASTQ files generated in the target enrichment process for each of the samples, which are being stored both locally and on a cloud server. The former are been currently analysed with statistical software. This task is **ongoing**.

WP2-T4- Quantify clinically relevant ARGs in the tested compartments (qPCR; qPCR arrays) (M34-M42)

As explained in the 12M report of Year 3, the detection of ARG through qPCRs was eliminated from the project. The FED-AMR Scientific Supervisory Board (SSB) contributed to this decision-making process. However, the quantification of relevant ARGs in the analysed compartments will be performed, as it will be inferred from the number or reads that cover each detected ARG.

WP2-T5- Identify naturally transformable bacterial species in the tested compartments (NGS) (M42-M52)

This task is **ongoing** and relies on the results from previous tasks.

WP2-T6- Assess clonal/lineage diversity in selected ARB species (M43-M52)

Phylogenetic trees will be established between bacterial species present in different but interconnected compartments using data obtained in **WP2-T3**.

WP2-T7- Isolate and assess quantity, diversity and stability of free extracellular ARG encoding DNA in the tested environments. Sequence comparisons (M34-M52)

Following the available DNA extraction protocol, WP2 participants have extracted the exDNA and total DNA from all samples immediately after their collection. Since the sampling campaign finished in Spring 2021, the target enrichment and 16S metagenomics assays started previously in M36 for the first batch of DNA samples.

E. coli, *K. pneumoniae*, *Salmonella spp*, *S. aureus* methicillin resistant, *E. faecium* and *E. faecalis* vancomycin resistant strains have been retrieved from the collected samples. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing and WGS is being performed for each partner in a selection of strains, where the characterization of the ARGs harboured by those strains is also being investigated.

The start and end of this task was delayed to M34 (year 3) and M50 (year 5), respectively.

[WP3- Elucidating the role of *Clostridium difficile* as an ARG transfer platform over ecosystems boundaries and its linkage between human and non-human \(zoonotic\) reservoirs \(M25-M50\)](#)

WP3-T1- Epidemiological survey of zoonotic ribotypes across participant countries (M25-M40)

This task was already **completed** in Year 3. Check the 12-months report 2020.

WP3-T2- WGS and AMR characterization of human and non-human *C. difficile* isolates (M34-M52)

At the moment, all the new *C. difficile* strains collected by WP3 participants are being tested to identify their AMR profiles and WGS to identify sequence types (STs) and resistance genes. In addition, ribotyping is also being conducted. This task is **ongoing**. The activities are described in more detail per partner below.

At 36-INSA, the new isolates were collected from pets and from food chain animals; in 2021, there were 8 different campaigns of sampling. Regarding pets: 1) 271 samples were collected from a kennel, with a prevalence of *C. difficile* of 3.4%; 2) 293 samples were prospectively collected from two veterinary hospitals (Lisbon and Porto), July-September 2021, with a prevalence of *C. difficile* of ~20%. Genetic characterization of the isolates showed the presence of diverse toxigenic and non-toxic ribotypes, also found in human samples. AMR evaluation showed resistance to clindamycin (25%), metronidazole (15%), moxifloxacin (9%) and rifampicin (2%). WGS of isolates of particular ribotypes and also of human isolates of the same types is being conducted. As an output, a scientific manuscript is being prepared.

Regarding food chain animals, the main findings were: 1) 56 samples from cattle were collected, with a prevalence of 10.7%; different zoonotic and toxigenic RTs were found, again overlapping human strains; resistance was found to moxifloxacin; 2) pig intensive culture, a total of 141 samples were collected, the most common zoonotic types were found, as well as resistance to moxifloxacin. WGS of animal isolates, as well as isolates from human cases with zoonotic ribotypes, distributed from 2016-2020 from different Portuguese hospitals, in a total of around 100 isolates, is being carried out, in order to evaluate the extent of genetic overlap between human and non-human *C. difficile* lineages (JRP15-WP3-T3). To support all the WP3 activities involving partner 36-INSA, a DVM (Frederico Alves) was recruited for 6 months (March to August 2021).

At partner institute 9-BfR, the second batch of samples originating from partner 25-NUIG (wastewater collected within WP2) was started to be analysed in June 2021. All of the four samples received are positive for one or more *C. difficile* strains. The characterization of the isolates is ongoing.

Furthermore, strains isolated in Y3 were whole genome sequenced and are being compared with WGS of other partners in JRP15-WP3-T3.

For Q2 and Q3 2021 a sampling study with strawberries was conducted between June and September 2021 and preliminary experiments to validate the isolation method were conducted. For this, strawberries from retail were spiked with *C. difficile* spores of three different test strains at two spiking levels and analysed regarding the recovery rate. Different variants of the sampling procedure were compared. A continuation of the sampling study involving other WP3 partners in summer 2022 is being now discussed.

At the institute of partner 10-FLI, samples from WP2 (14-UT and 25-NUIG, human and animal fecal samples, and manure) are analysed for *C. difficile* and isolates are characterized. Strains from the FLI *C. difficile* collection were revived and WGS were generated for approximately 100 isolates. 48 animal

RT 033 strains, all from cattle, were identified and sequenced. To identify unusual, previously uncharacterized *C. difficile* compartments, a collection of 94 fecal samples from llamas and alpacas was examined: 8 *C. difficile* isolates were obtained and characterized. Phenotypic and genotypic AMR characterization of the *C. difficile* isolates was initiated.

WP3-T3- Evaluation of the extent of genetic overlap between human and non-human *C. difficile* lineages (M41-M52)

At 13-SSI: As part of WP3-T3 where we compare human and veterinary *C. difficile* isolates, we did WGS of 12 porcine bacteria and 579 human clinical isolates. Porcine bacteria were retrieved from 330 fecal samples (4% positives) collected at farms from different locations in Denmark. The most striking similarities between human and porcine strains were three ST6 and four ST11, three of the ST11 with 2-3 cgMLST allelic differences to closest human isolate. Several different AMR genes were found, both complete and partial, which is being explored as part of the resistance gene pool prone for extracellular exchange WP3-T4.

36-INSA and 9-BfR are still sequencing the genome of the isolates. The analysis of the remaining WGS data will be performed in the first half of 2021.

At partner 9-BfR: Human RT033 strains were delivered from an external project partner and whole genome sequenced at the BfR. The WGS will be used for a comparison with RT033 strains from 36-INSA isolated in JRP15-WP3-T4.

At partner 10-FLI: The WGS will be used for comparison with RT033 strains from 36-INSA and strains collected from 9-BfR.

WP3-T4- *C. difficile* / AMR dissemination between the human, animal and the environment: pig farm as a proof of concept (M34-M48)

This task started on M34 although it was planned to start on M37. Two sampling campaigns have been undertaken, one in the summer and the other in autumn, in the HOALs from Austria and Portugal. For *C. difficile* study, samples were taken from pig barn, pig manure, farmers, wastewater treatment plant, groundwater and superficial water according to the sampling scheme from WP2.3. The partners that could not perform *C. difficile* isolation sent their samples to other partners. Several *C. difficile* strains have already been isolated and currently under study. This task **was completed on M48**.

Again, a more detailed summary of activities per partner is described below:

2-AGES: In this task, we aimed to assess the genetic relatedness, genetic and phenotypic resistances of *C. difficile* strains obtained from human, animal and environmental sources to monitor the dissemination of resistant RT 078 /ST 11 *C. difficile* across the human animal wildlife interface. For that, we collected 85 samples from geographically interconnected environmental compartments in an open air laboratory in Austria in 2020. After sample cultivation, the obtained *C. difficile* strains were all whole genome sequenced, ribotyped and tested for antimicrobial susceptibility. In addition, isolates were compared with human and pig isolates gathered between 2016 and 2019.

We recovered seven toxinogenic *C. difficile* RT 078 /ST 11 isolates (manure n= 3, wastewater n= 3, wildlife n=1) from the 85 samples. Five strains were phenotypically resistant to moxifloxacin and one also to clindamycin. All were susceptible to vancomycin, metronidazole and rifampicin and carried *cdeA* (n= 7), *tet40* (n=3) and *efpA* (n=1) as resistance genes (ARGs). A comparison of the genetic and phenotypic features of the RT 078 /ST 11 Austrian FED AMR *C. difficile* strains with the human (n= 20) and pig (n= 20) strains of RT 078 /ST 11 from the external collection was made. Human isolates were toxinogenic (n=20) and resistant to moxifloxacin (n=9), clindamycin (n= 7) and rifampicin (n=1), but no resistances were detected against metronidazole or vancomycin. However, they presented more diversity of ARGs than the environmental isolates.

Core genome MLST based typing revealed that four FED-AMR strains clustered with four human isolates from 2018 and 2019. All were resistant to moxifloxacin and/or clindamycin.

cgMLST revealed a cluster of antimicrobial resistant RT 78 /ST 11 *C. difficile* strains from human, animal and environmental sources, and therefore it suggests again its zoonotic traits despite lacking epidemiological links.

26-INSA: Samples were obtained from a Portuguese zootechnical station, and collected from different compartments of animal (pigs and others), human and environmental origin. All samples were broth enriched and cultured on selective medium in aerobic atmosphere. For each isolate, around five colonies were taken and evaluated for the toxins profile by multiplex-PCR and genetic diversity by PCR-ribotyping. WGS followed by core-genome single nucleotide variant (SNV)-based analysis was performed in a subset of isolates. A total of 188 samples were collected between July 2020-March 2021. The overall *C. difficile* positivity rate was 37.2% (70/188), and included samples from environmental (58.3%, 35/60) and animal (31.5%, 35/111) compartments. Ribotype (RT) 033, from ST-11/clade-5, was found in 90% of the positive samples, including samples from compartments linked with the pig barn (pigs, swine cesspool/manure, agricultural soil, control soil and wastewater treatment plant). All the isolates from this RT were positive for all toxin genes (tcdA+tcdB+cdt+). The phylogenetic positioning of the PT RT033 isolates in the context of other ST-11/clade-5 isolates showed a unique clonal origin of our isolates, clearly distinct from the remaining ST-11/clade 5 lineages/clusters, including the classical RT033 cluster. This new PT RT033 clone shares genomic features with several RTs from the ST-11/clade-5. The presence of PT RT033 clone in all compartments associated with the pig barn suggests a transmission cycle originated in these animals. These findings reveal the potential role these reservoirs can hold in the transmission network of *C. difficile*, including to humans. This study comes as a valuable contribution to the overall knowledge on the diversity of the ST11 clade 5, shedding a light on the evolutionary path not only of this clade but of *C. difficile* as a species. The PT RT033 shows a unique combination of genetic features found in other clade 5 RTs but never before described in a RT033, being the first report of a toxigenic RT033 strain. Based on these results, a scientific publication is being prepared.

WP4- Determination of the selection pressures in the tested compartments of human, animal and environmental ecosystems (M25-M50)

At this stage, almost all samples have been dispatched to 34-PIWET (antibiotics), UBA Vienna (herbicides) and 23-UoS (trace element analysis). The analysis of the samples for antibiotics, herbicides and trace elements is still **ongoing**.

WP4-T1- Selection of essential antimicrobials to be quantified in the tested compartments (published antibiotic consumption data, farmers' questionnaire, personal experience, expert interviews (veterinarians) (M25-M30)

This task was already **completed** in year 3. Check the 12-months report 2020.

WP4-T2- Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in aqueous matrices (water) (M31-M50)

29 antibiotics are in the analytical scope of the LC-MSMS method used in WP4-T2, T3, T4 and T5: 4 tetracyclines, 7 sulphonamides, 10 fluoroquinolones, 7 macrolides and trimethoprim. Results of 35 water samples are available: antibiotics from 3 antimicrobial classes (macrolides, tetracyclines and sulphonamides) were detected in 23% of the samples (maximum values are 4.65 µg/L azithromycin, 3.66 µg/L oxytetracycline and 0.23 µg/L sulfadimidine).

This task is **ongoing**.

WP4-T3- Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in manure (M31-M50)

Results of 17 manure samples are available: antibiotics from 2 antimicrobial classes (fluoroquinolones and tetracyclines) were detected in 59% of the samples (maximum values are 41 µg/kg marbofloxacin,

10 µg/kg enrofloxacin; 124 µg/kg oxytetracycline; 768 µg/kg doxycycline). The concentrations of all 4 antibiotics exceed the minimum selective concentrations. This means that under the given circumstances the detected antimicrobials are likely to select bacteria resistant to these compounds.

This task is **ongoing**.

WP4-T4- Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in faeces (M35-M50)

Results of 16 samples are available: no antibiotics were detected. This task is **ongoing**.

WP4-T5- Quantification of four antimicrobial classes (tetracyclines, macrolides, sulphonamides and fluoroquinolones) in soil (M31-M50)

Results of 92 soil samples are available: the tetracycline doxycycline was detected in 8 samples (8.7%) in the range between 9 µg/kg and 20 µg/kg. The highest concentration could be at the minimum selective concentration.

This task is **ongoing**.

WP4-T6- Quantification of herbicides in agricultural soil (M31-M50)

The following substances are in the analytical scope of the LC-MSMS method: **Glyphosate** and its more stable degradation product **AMPA** (Aminomethylphosphonic acid), **Glufosinate**, **2,4-D** (2,4-Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid), **Metolachlor** and its degradation products **Metolachlor ESA** and **Metolachlor OA**, **Bentazon** and **Metazachlor** and its degradation products **Metazachlor ESA** and **Metazachlor OA**.

Results of 114 soil samples, 30 water samples and 7 manure samples are available: herbicides were detected in 58% of the soil samples (maximum values are 200 µg/kg AMPA and 74 µg/kg Glyphosate), 83% of the water samples (maximum values are 4.3 µg/L AMPA and 0.7 µg/L Metolachlor ESA) and 86% of the manure samples (maximum values are 91 µg/kg AMPA and 41 µg/kg Glyphosate).

The observed glyphosate levels in the tested compartments are below the MICs and sub-inhibitory concentrations as analysed for *Salmonella* sp. strains. It is likely that the observed glyphosate concentrations (wet weight) do not select for resistant bacteria or perturb bacterial populations.

This task is **ongoing**.

WP4-T7- Measurement of the concentration of trace elements in environmental samples gathered across participants countries (M31-M50)

The analyses by ICP-MS focus on most relevant trace elements for co-selection (Cd, Cr, Cu, Co, Hg, Ni, Pb, Zn).

Results of 36 soil samples, 20 water samples and 21 plant samples are available. The maximum concentrations of bioavailable trace elements in the soil samples are: Cr: 0.257 mg/kg; Co: 0.638 mg/kg; Ni: 1.721 mg/kg; Cu: 0.985 mg/kg; Zn: 28.472 mg/kg; Cd: 0.065 mg/kg; Pb: 1.822 mg/kg.

The concentrations of the 8 trace elements are within the usual range for these compartments.

The task leader Monica Felipe-Sotelo is on maternity leave. As an intermediate responsible person Neil Ward and Cameron Wallin have agreed to oversee analysis of FED-AMR samples and Mark Chambers has been of great help in coordinating the communication for this task. Work had been delayed due to an issue in equipment, but analysis of samples is as of now in progress. Results of 36 soil samples, 20 water samples and 21 plant samples are available for analysis.

This task is **ongoing**.

WP5- Identification of environmental conditions modulating transformation frequencies in soil microcosms and an *in vitro* porcine gut model (poGutMo) (laboratory studies) (M32-M56)

WP5-T1 Establish baseline levels of HGT in the model organism (*E. coli*) arising from transformation in the poGutMo (M32-M49).

WP5-T1-ST1 Ability of *E. coli* to acquire AMR to serve as a donor DNA (M36-M38).

E. coli is generally known to be naturally transformable; however, standard laboratory strains are also known to be naturally competent in rapidly acquiring new genetic material at a relatively high rate. Thus, *E. coli* is commonly selected and used a model bacterial species to study bacterial transformation. *E. coli* K12 is a standard transformation strain that is often used in studying antimicrobial resistance gene transfer. *E. coli* K12-J53 is a derivative strain of K12 that is sodium azide resistant, which is often used as a selection marker. Thus, *E. coli* K12-J53 has been obtained from AGES and is used as a reference strain in the transformation experiments in both the *in vitro* and in the gut fermentation model where sodium azide is used as the first selection marker.

Under antibiotic stress, *E. coli* can undergo spontaneous mutation in the RNA polymerase β subunit (*rpoB*) gene conferring resistance to rifampicin. Using the spontaneous mutant generation method, *E. coli* J53 was used to generate rifampicin resistant mutants so rifampicin can be used as a second selection marker for transformation conjugates. Six rifampicin resistant mutants were generated and named *E. coli* J53-RifR1-6 and a growth curve was performed for both rifampicin resistant strains and the parental J53 strain to confirm the growth rate of mutant strains and ensures the lack of intrinsic fitness burden associated with the mutations. All rifampicin mutant strains grew successfully with minimum or no effect on the growth rate. *E. coli* J53-RifR1 was chosen, cultured and its DNA was extracted to be used as a donor DNA. PCR primers were designed targeting part of the *rpoB* gene (~2250 bp) including all RNA polymerase β subunit clusters where mutation frequently occur. Targeted *rpoB* sequence of both *E. coli* J53 and *E. coli* J53-RifR1 were successfully amplified, purified, and quantified.

Preliminary natural transformation experiments were performed using *E. coli* J53 strain as the recipient strain (rifampicin sensitive) and the *rpoB* DNA amplicon (0.2-0.5 μ g) from *E. coli* J53-RifR1 as the donor DNA (rifampicin resistant) in LB broth. Our results showed the successful recovery of *E. coli* J53 that is both sodium azide and rifampicin resistant with controls showing colonies only on sodium azide/MacConkey no.3 agar plates. The transformation experiment was also shown to be dependent on time and DNA concentration as demonstrated in the literature. The transformation frequency was calculated and showed to be about 10^{-6} - 10^{-7} . This demonstrates the success of the generation of the rifampicin mutant strain, PCR primer design, amplification of the target sequence and transformation of the *E. coli* J53-RifS with rifampicin resistance containing amplicon, which confirms the suitability of the strains used to be utilised for transformation experiments in the *in vitro* gut model. In the future, we shall setup the *in vitro* fermentation pig gut model and inoculate it with *E. coli* J53 as the recipient strain (rifampicin sensitive) and the *rpoB* DNA amplicon from *E. coli* J53-RifR1 as the donor DNA (rifampicin resistant) to assess the transformation frequency at different time points and experimental conditions.

This task and the corresponding deliverable D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.1 have been completed.

WP5-T1-ST2 Determine the optimal growth parameters for cultivating *E. coli* strains within the gut model (M40-M50).

The *in vitro* pig gut model is a continuous flow model with controlled temperature, pH, flow rate and under anaerobic gas conditions. The model is formed of six vessels, each can contain a total volume of 20 mL. Each three vessels are connected to a media feeder through a multichannel pump to control the flow rate. Each vessel is also connected to pH pump through a pH probe to measure and control the pH as adjusted from the acid and base provided. The vessels and media feeders are connected to anaerobic gas to maintain fermentation conditions. The extra media are discharged from the vessels through the waste tubings. The system does not allow the build up of pressure as it contains gas outlets

and media waste tubings. The vessels are contained in a glass chamber that is connected to a temperature-controlled water bath. The system has been chosen and set up to allow testing of different conditions with the ability to prepare and test molecularly relevant concentrations of AMR-encoding DNA.

To represent the pig gut microbiome communities, equal weight of five pig faeces samples were pooled, mixed and aliquoted as a source for faecal microbiome in the pig gut model. The *rpoB* amplicons are used as AMR-encoding eDNA and *E. coli* J53 as the recipient strain. In D5.1, we demonstrated that all amplicon concentrations showed successful transformation at a different efficiency rate. Thus, 30-50 µg of DNA were chosen as demonstrating rapid AMR transfer within the *in vitro* gut model. The concentration range also represents the eDNA concentrations extracted in WP2 and is naturally present.

We standardised the gut model conditions so it represents the large intestine in terms of pH, temperature, etc., to allow for the optimal growth of the recipient strain, the faecal microbiome and subsequent fermentation. Initial experiments demonstrated decrease in the microbial concentration of the recipient strain. Therefore, the flow rate, in particular, was optimised and increased to control the supply of enough nutrients and minimise the outflow of eDNA, to allow transformation events to occur. We are currently optimising further experimental conditions such as the concentration of the microbial faecal content along with testing of the chosen DNA concentration to demonstrate optimal growth conditions and *in vitro* pig gut model conditions that are suitable to demonstrate transformation.

The task has started and is still **ongoing**.

Start date delayed to M40. New end month: 50 (Year 5).

WP5-T1-ST3 Rates of transformation calculated by taking samples from the gut model and plating on agar plates supplemented with the appropriate antibiotics (M46-M50).

Start date delayed to M46. New end month: 50 (Year 4).

The preliminary rate of transformation has been calculated using different concentrations of amplicons and at different timepoints, without the addition of gut microflora. The transformation frequency within the first 48 hours ranged from 1.67E-02 - 1.20E-06. Once all conditions in D5.2 are optimised and we demonstrate transformation in the presence of gut microbiome we will determine the baseline rate of transformation in the final tested conditions.

The task has started and is still **ongoing**.

WP5-T1-ST4 DNA transfer rates via bacterial conjugation will be calculated using the endpoint method (M45-M50).

Start date delayed to M45. New end month: 50 (Year 4).

WP5-T2- Evaluate conditions that drive HGT and the emergence of AMR via transformation (M49-M56)

WP5-T2-ST1- Iterative evaluation of candidate drivers (antibiotic, herbicide, cation) of HGT evaluated in the gut model – round 1 (M49-M53)

Start date delayed to M49 (Year 5).

WP5-T2-ST2- Iterative evaluation of candidate drivers (antibiotic, herbicide, cation) of HGT evaluated in the gut model – round 2 (M53-M56)

Start date delayed to M53 (Year 5).

WP5-T3- Effect of different environmental conditions on the expression of competence genes in E.coli determined using soil microcosms (M44-M52)

This task started in M44 and is being performed with *A. baylyi* as it is more suitable to show the effects on soil microcosms.

WP6- Probabilistic and mechanistic models of the links between antimicrobial usage in animals, AMR in the environment, and the risks for public health.

WP6-T1 Build a probabilistic mathematical model of the emergence of AMR in target bacteria and the relative contribution of transformation and conjugation to ARG acquisition (afterwards: Factors influencing the prevalence of antibiotic resistance in the environment) (M32-M60)

As said in the previous report, due to challenges in obtaining the data required for setting up a machine learning model (in part related to COVID-19 restrictions), we have decided to carry out a systematic review of the literature regarding environmental factors of AMR prevalence. The data extracted as part of this systematic review will be used to inform the design of a future machine learning model, which will be completed outside FED-AMR and will be based on the results from the systematic evidence map.

WP6-T1-ST1 Data Integration, Annotation and Association Analysis (afterwards: Systematic review: environmental factors associated with AMR) (M32-M60)

Start date delayed to M32.

We have received all comments from the co-authors for the protocol for the systematic review and we are incorporating them. This has resulted in an extensive 9-pages document with many sections (e.g. Introduction, material and methods, appendixes) that can be transferred/adapted to the final manuscript. We have contacted PROSPERO to register the protocol, but since the feedback was that this review is not within the scope of PROSPERO we are exploring other options (e.g. Cochrane) or register the protocol with a journal (e.g. like PLoS One or BMC Open).

In-line with the goal of this WP6.1, a key outcome is to identify the relative importance of HGT mechanisms associated with the spread of antibiotic resistance, i.e. transformation vs. conjugation. The searched databases, specific search strategy, plans for data management and categories of extracted data types are specified in the linked protocol. This deliverable provides this protocol documentation on the UoS GitLab website at the following link: <https://gitlab.eps.surrey.ac.uk/bg0013/systematic-review-protocol-amr>. This is a private repository, and will remain confidential until publication of the systematic review or registration of the protocol. The protocol can be shared with all members of the FED-AMR or other One-Health EJP members and they can access to the GIT repository if requested. We have also secured a machine-learning based software tool that will aid the leading authors with screening 1000's of potentially relevant articles. We haven't started screening the titles/abstract due to other commitments with WP6-T2. This task is ongoing.

WP6-T2 Develop mechanistic models to address key questions regarding the spatio-temporal changes observed in microbiological communities (M34-M60)

We are continuing to review the literature to keep updated with state-of-the-art techniques. We have developed and formulated a mathematical model for microbial communities as well as explored published models and used an existing dataset of time-series bacterial abundances to validate our approach. We have also tested different approaches to infer relevant parameters for published models and we are now focusing on how to adapt these techniques to our model. We now aim to link *in-silico* data with our model to validate our approach. Once this is done, we will start to use the model to address a few conceptual questions. This task is ongoing.

WP6-T2-ST1 - Modelling microbial communities I (M34-M60)

Start date was delayed to M34.

In a preliminary analysis performed on the dynamics of microbial community, we showed that these can critically switch from one state to another depending on how antibiotics are administered.

We aim to use our model with novel data (from UoS or from other FED-AMR partners) rather than the ones in the literature. Discussion with our partners on potentially available data is on-going. As discussed above, in-silico data is being generated based on individual-based modelling (i.e., Gillespie algorithm) with parameters matched to experimentally obtained values, including background noise, for increased biological realism. This data shall be used to test our generalised Lotka-Volterra model with a carrying capacity term.

WP6-T2-ST2- Modelling microbial communities II (M46-M54)

Start delayed to M46. Subtask is **ongoing**.

3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
15	D-JRP15- FED-AMR -WP1.5	Annual project report	M36	M38		Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5078024	8
15	D-JRP15- FED-AMR -WP1.6	Interim project report (T1.3.)	M47		M52	Public. Delay associated with the in person meeting in Lisbon that has been postponed to April 2022 (M52) due to COVID-19.	8
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.2	Preliminary data collection on ARG prevalence and ARG background load in the compartments analysed so far (T2.4)	M36	M37		Public OHEJP: available Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5078064	8

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.3	Annual report Y3 (WP2)	M39	M38		Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5078149	8
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.4	Determination of naturally transformable bacteria in tested environmental compartments (T2.5)	M44		M52	Public This deliverable depends on the results of task 2.3 and therefore it has been delayed.	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.5	Shotgun sequencing: ARG diversity in tested environmental compartments (T2.3.1)	M46	M47		Public Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5726732	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.6	16S metagenomics results: Microbial biodiversity and phylogenetic relationships of ARBs over ecosystem boundaries (T2.3, T2.6)	M46		M52	Public Since not all partners got their sequencing results at the same time, we could only start in December 2021 to work on a harmonized statistical and	10

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						bioinformatics analysis workflow that integrates all samples (>400) and comparisons across countries.	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.7	Quantity and stability of free extracellular DNA observed in environmental compartments tested so far (T2.7)	M50		M52	Public Target enrichment (= antimicrobial resistance genes profiling) in free extracellular DNA is finished for all the samples (>400), but data are still being analysed.	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.8	Annual report for Y4 (WP2)	M48		M49	Public.	8
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.1	<i>E. coli</i> strains demonstrated to be suitable for transformation	M26	M38		Deliverable will be made public, but elements of the data included in the deliverable may be embargoed or kept confidential, in line with the OHEJP guidelines.	10

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						Zenodo: deliverable description https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5121159	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.2	Optimal growth parameters for cultivating <i>E. coli</i> within the porcine gut model and the time after inoculation at which its concentration is maximal determined	M45		M50	Public The delay in achieving this deliverable is due to COVID-19 and troubleshooting the growth of <i>E. coli</i> in the presence of gut microbiota.	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.3	Pilot experiments using PCR amplicons as ARG donors	M46		M50	Public The delay in achieving this deliverable is due to COVID-19 and troubleshooting the growth of <i>E. coli</i> in the presence of gut microbiota.	10

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 <i>(month)</i>	Date delivered on Project Group <i>(month)</i>	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date <i>(month)</i>	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.4	Optimal growth parameters for cultivating the clostridial strains within the gut model determined	M47		M52	Public The delay in achieving this deliverable is due to COVID-19 and delays in WP5.	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.5	Conjugation-mediated HGT between the clostridial donor and recipient strains within the gut model determined	M47		M52	Public The delay in achieving this deliverable is due to COVID-19 and delays in WP5.	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.6	Clostridial transconjugates characterised by whole-genome sequencing	M48		M54	Public The delay in achieving this deliverable is due to COVID-19 and delays in WP5.	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.9	Results from pig gut model regarding HGT by transformation and conjugation in presence of selected antibiotics, herbicides and heavy metals	M49		M52	Public The delay in achieving this deliverable is due to COVID-19 and delays in WP5.	10

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP5.11	First results from soil microcosm experiments on effects of environmental conditions on transformation	M47		M51	Public Delayed due to unavailability of an agreed soil microcosm SOP, which is developed for synergistic effects in the frame of a different project suffering from COVID-19 postponements.	10
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.1	Main code for the mathematical modelling made available in public repository (e.g. GitHub) with associated documentation (which can be used as “Material and Method” section of the forthcoming publications).	M30	M37		This is now a protocol for systematic review (not a code for mathematical modelling). Confidential until publication or registration of the protocol for the systematic review, except for FED-AMR or other One-Health EJP members.	3

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 <i>(month)</i>	Date delivered on Project Group <i>(month)</i>	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date <i>(month)</i>	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
						Zenodo: deliverable description https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5139307	
15	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.3	Update of codes and documentations in public repository (e.g. GitHub).	M43	M47		Confidential until published by WP6, therefore not on Zenodo yet (but available to the consortium on request)	10

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-04	Interim meeting	M41	Yes	M48	Had to be moved online and scheduled for convenience, date was decided in the TCs and through an online meeting on Zoom
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-14	Starting preparations for shotgun sequencing (T2.3.1)	M37	Not applicable		Shotgun Metagenomics was replaced for target enrichment (see Task 2.3.1)
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-15	Stop: field sampling campaign (T2.3), DNA isolations (T2.7)	M40	Yes		
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-16	Starting 16S metagenome analysis of obtained DNA isolates. Batch format (T2.3)	M40	Yes		
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-17	Start: Determination of naturally transformable bacteria (T2.5)	M41	Yes		
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-18	Finalizing ARG qPCRs (T2.4)	M42	Not applicable		qPCRs were replaced by target enrichment
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-19	Finalizing determination of transformable bacteria (T2.5)	M44	No	M52	This milestone is in progress and depends on the results of task 2.3 and therefore it has been delayed.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-20	Start: Assessment of clonal/lineage diversity of ARB (T2.6)	M43	Yes		

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-21	Finalizing 16S metagenome analysis of obtained DNA isolates (T2.3)	M46	No	M52	This milestone is in progress due to the high amount of sequence data to be analysed.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-22	Finalizing assessment of clonal/lineage diversity of ARB (T2.6)	M46	No	M52	This milestone is in progress due to the high amount of sequence data to be analysed.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-23	Finalizing shot gun sequencing and bioinformatics and statistical analysis of NGS data (T2.3.1, T3.2.2, T2.3)	M48	No	M52	Statistical analysis ongoing. Target enrichment and 16S sequencing have already finished.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-26	Complete WGS on all included isolates	M46	No	M52	This milestone is in progress due to the high amount of sequence data to be analysed.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-27	Complete AMR profiles on all included isolates	M46	No	M52	This milestone is in progress since not all countries have completed the susceptibility tests.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-38	Porcine gut model set up using faecal samples obtained through WP2, samples stored for trace element analysis (WP4) – experiments can start	M44	Yes		
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-39	Samples from gut model experiments stored for trace element analysis (WP4)	M41	Yes		All samples are stored with every experiment.

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-43	Antibiotics, herbicides and heavy metals most likely to drive HGT through transformation supplied to UoS.	M47	M51		
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-42	DNA sent for whole-genome sequencing	M43	No	M57	The delay is due to delay in the whole WP5 due to COVID-19 and troubleshooting experiments.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-45	Deliver results from 1st round of gut model experiments to WP6 leader for further modelling	M45	No	M55	The delay is due to delay in the whole WP5 due to COVID-19 and troubleshooting experiments.
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-46	Results from modelling in WP6 communicated to inform parameters for use in 2nd round of gut model experiments	M46	No	M55	There has been a delay in the progress of this WP6 task due to pressing commitments to another OHEJP project 'WorldCOM'. Also, by the nature of the mathematical model we are exploring and difficulty in obtaining absolute abundance counts from experiments, we are working on first generating our own in-silico dataset to validate our model. To mitigate some of these issues, we have ongoing contacts with other FED-AMR members to try to use novel data generated by our partners.

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-56	Literature review on fluctuating ecological systems and gut model approach.	M45	Yes		
15	M-JRP15-FED-AMR-57	Analysis of data produced from the 1st round of gut model experiments. Formulation and implementation of the model to identify how natural fluctuations depend on the drivers. Results communicated to WP5 leader.	M46	No		The review of the literature is an ongoing task to ensure we are updated with the state of the art.

4. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Draft Genome Sequence of a Multidrug-Resistant Escherichia coli Sequence Type 1193 Pandemic Clone Isolated from Wastewater in Austria DOI: 10.1128/MRA.00762-21 https://zenodo.org/record/5770120#.YeZ1rd8xl4F	Yes	No	1.050,00 \$ 929,38 €

Additional output

Poster

- Abstract in ECCMID **2021** (e-poster): Antimicrobial resistance and genetic relatedness of environmental bacteria across the animal-human-wildlife interface in Austria (WP2, 2-AGES)
<https://zenodo.org/record/5499916#.YTs2z-dCR4E>
- Abstract presented in Annual Scientific Meeting **2021** (e-poster): Diversity of bacterial communities and genes encoding AMR in different environmental compartments along the food/feed chain (WP2, 36-INSA)
<https://zenodo.org/record/4916135#.YTsqrudCR4E>
- Abstract presented in Annual Scientific Meeting **2021** (e-poster): Dissemination of antimicrobial resistant *Clostridium difficile* RT078/ST11 in Austria across the human-animal-wildlife interface (WP3, 2-AGES)
<https://zenodo.org/record/4915872#.YTsrnOdCR4E>
- Abstract presented in Annual Scientific Meeting **2021** (e-poster): Zoonotic spread of multi-resistant *C. difficile* (WP3, 13-SSI)
<https://zenodo.org/record/4915901#.YTsqsOdCR4E>
- Abstract presented in Annual Scientific Meeting **2021** (e-poster): Diversity and Dynamics of *Clostridioides difficile* in a farm environment PT (WP3, 36-INSA)
<https://zenodo.org/record/4916135#.YTs1O-dCR4E>
- Abstract presented in Annual Scientific Meeting **2021** (e-poster): FED-AMR: Determination of selection pressures for AMR in environmental samples (WP4)
<https://zenodo.org/record/4916158#.YTs1CudCR4E>
- Abstract presented in Annual Scientific Meeting **2021** (e-poster): Ecological modelling of microbial communities subject to perturbation (WP6, 23-UoS)
<https://zenodo.org/record/4915941#.YTsqs-dCR4E>
- Presentation by SZU in the Ekomonitor Seminar on Waste Analytics in **2021**: English title: International project to map the potential for horizontal transfer of antibiotic resistance genes across different ecosystems, original language: Czech.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5770033>
- Abstract accepted to ONE – Health, Environment, Society – Conference , 21-24 June 2022. "Modelling the dynamics and long-term stability of perturbed gut microbiota" (WP6, 23-UoS).

Other

- Brian Gardner, Francesca Contadini, Davide Messina, Martha Betson, Mark Chambers, Alexandre De Menezes, Laura C. Gonzalez Villeta, Marwa M. Hassan, Roberto M. La Ragione, Joaquin M. Prada, Arnoud H. M. van Vliet, Lorenzo A. Santorelli, Nick Selemetas, Mukunthan Tharmakulasingam, Gordon Nichols, Revati Phalkey, Adriana Cabal, Werner Ruppitsch, Markus Woegerbauer, Manuela Canica, Inaki Deza-Cruz, Giovanni Lo Iacono. *Factors associated with the prevalence of antibiotic resistance in the environment from a One Health perspective: Protocol for a systematic evidence map* (Protocol Manuscript in preparation for submission to "Environment International" by WP6).
- Gajda, M. Gbylik-Sikorska, T. Błądek, E. Nowacka-Kozak, M. Bilecka, A. Kuśmierz, I. Szymanek-Bany, M. Brandtner, G. Rab, M. Hassan, M. Chambers, R. La Ragione, V. Kisand, K.Arbo, T.

Tenson, M. Korinkova, Z. Drahosova, O. Moreira, A. Sequeira, V. Manageiro, M. Caniça, Ch. Nikolaidou, A. De Menezes. *Analysis of antimicrobials in environmental samples as a part of determination of selection pressures for antimicrobial resistance*. Euroresidue conference: 23rd-25th May 2022, Egmond aan Zee, The Netherlands (abstract sent by WP4).

Outcomes

Not yet at this stage.

5. *Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries*

- On April 6 2021 partner 2-AGES presented our project to **MediPIET** (Mediterranean and Black Sea Field Epidemiology Training Programme Network), at the Training of Trainers on One Health.
- In the context of WP2, we have established a small collaboration with the **University of Delft** for comparison of our different extracellular DNA extraction methodologies and further analysis with target enrichment were performed for two water samples that University of Delft.
- Presentation of the FED-AMR project at the One Health Session, Project Review Module 2021 and facilitation at the Introductory course and Phylogeny Sessions 2021, as part of the **ECDC Fellowship Program**.
- **EFSA** is being updated (in)directly on the progress of the FED-AMR project through a stakeholder that belongs to the FED-AMR Advisory Board (Beatriz Guerra).

6. *List of critical risks*

As mentioned in last year 12M report, we acknowledge the existence of some risks derived from such a large and diverse project, both in terms of interpersonal relations and scientific matters. We have therefore set up a dedicated risk management table for the FED-AMR project last year, which was documented in all reports. Please refer to the **risk management table attached below**.

FED_AMR_Risk
Management Table.xl

JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir

1. *Summary of the work carried out in year 4*

TELE-Vir is a 2.5 year (now 3.0 with an extension of six months) Joint Research Project of the One Health EJP that focusses on developing a fast point-of-evidence (poi) toolbox for identification and characterization of emerging virus threats for human and/or domestic and wildlife animals.

In the TELE-Vir project we are combining a suitable field-deployable point-of-care approach, and a direct upload of genomic, phenotypic and epidemiological data into a user-friendly bioinformatics toolkit for fast identification and characterization of new emerging virus threats. We are developing and adapting existing point-of care methods and tools and expand these to a harmonized poi protocol for field analysis. The poi protocol requires only a minimum of laboratory equipment and is designed

to be compatible with MinION sequencing technology. Moreover, we are combining and integrating in the poi toolbox phenotypic and epidemiological data to aid risk assessment and management. The poi toolbox is available to other interested national and international parties for example shared with established networks.

The worldwide SARS-CoV-2 pandemic has a great impact on the TELE-Vir project. There have been national lockdowns, laboratories have been closed or allocated for SARS-CoV-2 diagnostics. There has been a worldwide shortage of basic laboratory reagents and equipment, which has influenced the ability to perform elementary laboratory experiments. However, the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic has also had a positive influence on the project, as we demonstrated that we can inactivate the SARS-CoV-2, other RNA viruses being non-infectious and we developed alternative methods for NA extraction (WP3), which is in line with the development of a field-based protocol for MinION sequencing using a minimum of laboratory equipment (the poi tool box). Moreover, we used successfully SARS-CoV-2 as model virus in our metagenomics tool box. This approach will now be adapted and applied for DNA viruses (in progress).

Our first annual meeting from the TELE-Vir project was held online at the end of January 2021, due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. We agreed on that, we will keep our strategy and will focus on RNA viruses, as the newly emerged SARS-CoV-2, but also on DNA viruses to apply our metagenomics approach. WP2 supports this approach by providing proof of concept for bioinformatic platforms using coronaviruses, and influenza viruses as main models. The pandemic has both given new opportunities in this area with overwhelming volumes of data becoming available as well as challenges caused by data quality, and logistical constraints and restrictions. In this context, the TELE-Vir platform has been built to enhance genome-based viral surveillance, by facilitating both sequencing data analysis and output navigation and interpretation.

Challenged by the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, the TELE-Vir consortium has shown impressive resourcefulness and adaptability. Deliverables and reports were reached and submitted. The TELE-Vir consortium meets regularly to exchange, to discuss problems and to find solutions to guarantee the best possible progress and success of the project. Results are disseminated as scientific publications and presentation at workshops, webinars and conferences including OneHealth EJP conferences.

Overall, the COVID-19 pandemic has also had a positive impact on the TELE-Vir project and many of the experiences and problems encountered during the crisis will be further used or translated to the development of the TELE-Vir poi-tool box, which will help to control outbreaks of new emerging viruses in the future, at national, regional, European and even global levels.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1: Coordination and data management

WP1-T1- Coordination and project management

Project management and coordination of the project is proceeding according to the plan. The WP1 leaders organize regular meetings for the whole TELE-Vir consortium to guarantee the best outcome of the project. This is ongoing.

WP1-T2- Data management

Data management plan (DMP) was submitted in the first year of the project (December 2020). It is and will be continuously updated accordingly to the newest results generated.

WP1-T3- Kick-off-meeting at IZSAM, Italy

The kick off meeting of the TELE-Vir project was held on January 21st – 22nd 2020 at the International Centre for Veterinary Training and Information "F. Gramenzi" (CIFIV) of Istituto Zooprofilattico

Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise "G. Caporale" (Via G. Caporale, Teramo, Italy). All partners were present. This task is completed.

WP1-T4-1st TELE-Vir meeting online, organized by SSI

The first meeting of the TELE-Vir project was held on January 25th 2021 as an online meeting. All partners were present. This task is completed.

WP1-T5- 2nd TELE-Vir meeting at SSI, DK

This meeting will be postponed to July/August 2022, as we want to have the project parts completed before having the 2nd TELE-Vir meeting to discuss the outcome. This is possible as we applied for an extension of the project for six months (extension approved).

WP1-T6- Workshop in the use of the POI toolbox at SSI, DK

This workshop will be postponed from January – to July/August 2022, as we want to have the project parts almost completed before we will hold the workshop. This is possible as we applied for an extension of the project for six months (extension approved).

WP2: Development of a Bioinformatics tool-kit for POI data analysis

WP2-T1- Survey and collection of databases for genotype-phenotype associations

At the kick-off meeting it was agreed that the first stage was selection of important phenotypic characteristics for the chosen model virus (influenza and coronaviruses), followed by assessment of the amount and quality of data available. During M25-M36, a literature review was performed to identify coronavirus phenotypes of relevance to tropism, emergence, and clinical disease, and any data available for their prediction based on genotype. A summary was circulated to partner institutes and associated virologists, together with a survey. The aims of the survey were two-fold: (1) to obtain the views of virologists (potential end users of the TELE-Vir toolkit) on coronavirus phenotype prediction and variant monitoring activities that they would like to see in a genomic surveillance toolkit; and (2) to obtain test datasets for further development of the toolkit.

During M37-M48, progress covered several fronts. The results of the coronavirus survey were reviewed and discussed in TELE-Vir internal meetings, and presented as a poster at the OHEJP ASM 2021. Additionally, a scoping review to identify relevant phenotypes and their feasibility of prediction was performed for influenza A virus. Finally, data linking genotypes (lineages and mutations) with phenotypic changes for both SARS-CoV-2 and influenza A virus were collected from available literature.

For SARS-CoV-2, genotype-phenotype data are expanding rapidly, and data collection will have to continue to keep the database up-to-date and relevant. A decision was reached by the WP2 team to investigate making use of curated online databases for this purpose. Suitable databases will be reviewed, and a strategy elaborated, in the first half of next year.

WP2-T2- Development of bioinformatics modules for third-generation sequencing analysis and pathogen identification

In the context of pathogen detection and field genome sequencing, there are multiple advantages in either using online bioinformatics tools or running the platforms locally. As such, a Docker version of the online INSaFLU platform has been built and distributed publicly (<https://github.com/INSAFLU/docker>) in order to facilitate the local installation process. INSaFLU users, TELE-Vir partners and other stakeholders (e.g., ECDC) were notified of this novel feature. INSaFLU has been successfully installed and run locally 'offline' on partner computer servers including at UoS.

As a response to COVID-19 pandemic, both the locally installed INSaFLU version and original website (<https://insaflu.insa.pt/>) were adapted to better accommodate the identification and genome-based analyses of the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2), as follows:

- a new module for rapid assignment of Human Betacoronavirus (BetaCoV), including the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2), has been developed and implemented, and the rationale behind the classification and outputs was documented (https://insaflu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/data_analysis.html#influenza-type-and-sub-type-identification-and-human-betacoronavirus-classification-as-of-march-2020; check more details in the list of current INSaFLU genetic markers used for Influenza type and sub-type identification and Human Betacoronavirus classification);
- the publicly available SARS-CoV-2 reference genome sequence (NCBI accession number MN908947) was inserted as default in the INSaFLU reference database;
- multitasking configurations were changed, considerably speeding up the analyses, and the maximum upload file size was made more flexible;
- a new tab “Settings” was created making software parameterization more flexible and tailored to SARS-CoV-2 NGS analyses, with emphasis on including user-defined parameters for reads quality analysis, mapping and consensus generation.
- automatic masking of low coverage regions was incorporated in the platform, i.e., automatic generation of consensus sequences for incomplete locus, i.e., undefined nucleotides (“N”) are automatically introduced in low coverage regions at a user-selected coverage thresholds
- an automate pipeline for Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) data analysis was optimized and implemented in INSaFLU, from raw reads to quality analysis, reference-based generation/curation of consensus sequences, mutation annotation, gene/protein/genome alignments, phylogenetic tree, metadata visualization, etc (details about the pipeline, including software version, default settings, etc, can be found in: https://insaflu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/data_analysis.html#). By automatically detecting the sequencing technologies (e.g., Illumina, or ONT) and subsequently allocating the technology-specific pipeline, the platform allows flexible data analysis and sample comparison regardless the technology used. This flexibility is particularly useful, for instance, in the context of genomic epidemiology consortia with centralized data analysis, but decentralized sequencing. Partner Sciensano shared ONT data on animal influenza A viruses, SARS-CoV-2, and locally implemented the INSaFLU pipeline, and, in a joined effort with partner INSA evaluated the assembly approach for animal DNA viruses (LSDV). Read data was also shared by partner SSI in order to evaluate the pipeline performance on ONT data.
- Automatic SARS-CoV-2 Pango lineages (<https://pangolin.cog-uk.io/>) assignment using Pangolin (<https://github.com/cov-lineages/pangolin>), as described by Rambaut and colleagues (Nat Microbiol; 5:1403-1407), was integrated in both the locally installable and website versions of the platform. Whenever a new Pangolin / Pangolearn version is released, a button “Update Pango lineage” is automatically made available, so that users can re-assign all samples in the project using the latest software/database versions.
- Direct links for consensus sequences analysis using Nextclade (<https://clades.nextstrain.org/>) were also included in the INSaFLU online, allowing an easy and rapid SARS-CoV-2 clade classification, mutation exploration and other analyses available at the Nextclade framework.
- A first version of the module for the rapid mapping-free influenza type and subtype/lineage identification, as well as Human Betacoronavirus (BetaCoV) identification, using ONT read data was also released in both platform versions (locally installable and online).
- With the emergence of Omicron variant, the database for rapid assignment of Human Betacoronavirus (BetaCoV) was updated to enable a rapid and automated mapping-free detection of Omicron reads from both Illumina and ONT data.

These and other updates were documented and are available at full INSaFLU documentation webpage: (<https://insaflu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>) and Github (<https://github.com/INSaFLU/>)

One of the main goals of this task is also to upgrade the platform for automatic pathogen identification in order to support both human and veterinary clinical practice and disease outbreak investigations. After reviewing the current state-of-the-art of the field of bioinformatic pipelines for metagenomic virus diagnostics, a modular pipeline is being developed, incorporating the key steps of metagenomics taxonomic classification, namely: read quality control, host-depletion, genome assembly, and reads/contig classification. Specifically, we are testing software (such as Centrifuge, Diamond, Kaiju, Kraken2, KrakenUnique, BLAST) and databases (such as NCBI, RVDB, Uniprot, Virosaurus) commonly used in virological diagnostic laboratories on clinical metagenomics using datasets that have been well characterized by RT-PCR. This will allow us to benchmark the different workflows (i.e., test combinations of different components, reference databases and/or parameters) in order to finely explore how these different tools behave and, ultimately, to determine the best approach(es) to be implemented in the TELE-Vir toolbox. Work on this task is ongoing. Independent of the workflow(s) that we ultimately decide to integrate into the platform, each classification run is to report a list of most-likely suspected viruses, each accompanied by several robust and the diagnostic-oriented metrics. In fact, we place particular emphasis on the usefulness and accessibility of end-user reports, as it is our intention that this toolbox will serve to strengthen output interpretation and decision-making on the part of users.

WP2-T3- Development of bioinformatics modules for sequence curation and phenotypic association

This task is highly dependent on the collected databases for genotype-phenotype associations, and the design of the bioinformatics approach cannot be fully drawn at this stage.

During M37-48, the basis for a genotype-phenotype association module was developed. The module takes as input a protein alignment (as generated by the existing INSaFLU pipeline), and detects mutations in each of the component sequences. It then rapidly screens these mutations against a database of known genotype-phenotype associations (such as, amino acid site changes already linked to: antiviral resistance, resistance to neutralizing antibodies, enhanced affinity to host-receptors antibodies or enhanced transmissibility), and generates a user-friendly overview of phenotypes predicted for each sequence. Testing of the module is currently ongoing.

Incorporation into the INSaFLU pipeline is foreseen for the first half of next year (M54), but this will be dependent upon the adaptations required for the module to be compatible with external genotype-phenotype databases.

Additionally, we continue to investigate the feasibility of inferring biochemical and immunological properties, using existing models and machine learning approaches being tested at UoS. In this context (and in work aligned with JIP COVRIN), we have been exploring SARS-CoV-2 antigenic variation and its genetic determinants, using antigenic cartography analysis of published datasets as well as data received from partner SSI. Antigenic cartography offers a robust and reliable way to measure immunological properties using serological data and multidimensional scaling. The result is quantified antigenic distances between viruses, which can then be compared with genetic distances derived from sequence data. Proof of principle has previously been demonstrated for influenza virus where the antigenic effect of individual mutations has been inferred, allowing prediction of antigenic variation (phenotype) from genetic data (genotype). Antigenic distances between key SARS-CoV-2 variants are currently being measured using rabbit sera in collaboration with SSI, for comparison with genetic data.

WP2-T4- Development of bioinformatics modules for genomic and metadata integration towards enhanced surveillance

Following the kick-off meeting a strategic approach has been agreed to achieve this task. First, Nextstrain (<https://nextstrain.org>) tools will be implemented for temporal and phylogeographical analysis. Then, we implement novel functionalities focused on fitting the needs of labs working in different sectors (vet, PH, etc.) and that can be handled by users from multidisciplinary fields. In this context, INSaFLU was also upgraded to easily display metadata on phylogenetic trees (through user-defined node colouring and metadata blocks), thus facilitating integration of relevant epidemiological

and/or clinical data and pathogen genomic data (https://insaflu.readthedocs.io/en/latest/change_log.html). Other functionalities for better data navigation and interpretation were also implemented, namely two novel interactive and dynamic “expand-and-collapse” panels for enhanced report of: 1) all detected mutations (including detailed information about genome position, nucleotide change, coverage evidence, frequency, impact at protein level, etc); and, ii) the mean depth of coverage and horizontal coverage per locus for all samples using interactive color-coded buttons. Still, further developments are ongoing, dependent on tasks 2 and 3.

WP2-T5- Development of a user and surveillance oriented web-based interface

During M25-M36, an application for an STM in 2021 was successful, for UoS and INSA to align bioinformatic approaches and share knowledge of the existing INSAFLU bioinformatics pipeline, in the context of WP2-T2 and WP2-T3 and to facilitate the eventual design of the user interface. The STM has been delayed by current travel restrictions but researchers are coordinating virtually and aim to complete the STM when possible (a option to postpone to 2022 has been granted). Work on this task is ongoing. In particular, we are investigating approaches to: i) synchronize local and web instances of the platform, allowing an easier integration and sharing of data, i.e., results of local analysis (“offline”) can be “communicated” to a centralized repository with web access; ii) facilitate data flow and sharing with external resources (GISAID/NCBI/ENA...).

WP3-T1- Development and validation of a S.O.P for sample handling & pre-treatment

1) Protocol to verify the inactivation of animal viruses using three different lysis buffers.

For propagation of selected animal viruses (myxoma virus, MYXV; canine adenovirus type-2, CAV-2; canine coronavirus, CCoV; hepatitis A virus, HAV) representing different virus families, the following cell lines were used: rabbit kidney (RK13), madin-darby canine kidney (MDCK), A-72 and Rhesus kidney, FrP-3. The prepared virus stock suspensions were used for subsequent inactivation studies. The virucidal activity of MagNA Pure lysis / binding buffer (MPLB, Roche), AL (Qiagen) and AVL (Qiagen) were assessed under various temperature-time conditions. The inactivation efficiency of viruses was evaluated on the basis of a CPE appearing in the infected cells. The cytotoxicity of the cells caused by buffers used was assessed by a MTT assay. All buffers in the concentrations recommended by producers and the tested temperature-time profiles were effective in virus inactivation. Likewise, the minimal virus inactivating concentration of MPLB was assessed.

3) A protocol to verify the inactivation activity of two buffers for Bovine Beta-CoV (model virus for SARS-CoV-2).

MPLB (Roche) and eNAT™ (Copan) against a Bovine Beta-CoV (Bov-CoV strain 9WBL77) was developed. The eNAT buffer is a Guanidine-thiocyanate based medium that stabilizes the RNA and DNA of Viruses. Bov-CoV strain belongs to the same genus as SARS-CoV-2 but can be propagated in BSL2 facilities and thus was used as a model to validate virus inactivation using different inactivating buffers. The protocol is based on the ultracentrifugation of the virus-inactivating buffer compound in order to remove the toxic effect of the inactivating buffer on cell cultures. For inactivation protocols using MPLB and eNAT buffers, one virus titer (10^5 TCID₅₀/ml) and one contact time (30min) were used. After 30 min of contact, the three samples: 1) Virus control (Virus + MEM), 2) virus + MPLB and 3) virus + eNAT were ultracentrifuged to remove the toxic supernatant. The pellet of samples 1, 2 and 3 was resuspended in the same volume of PBS and then titrated in HRT-18 cells: Sample 1: 10^5 TCID₅₀/ml, sample 2: < 10 TCID₅₀/ml and sample 3: < 10 TCID₅₀/ml. In conclusion, the inactivating power of the MPLB and eNAT buffers against a beta-CoV under test conditions was highlighted.

4) Heat inactivation protocols for Bov Beta-CoV 9WBL77 as model virus.

One ml of virus suspension with an infectious titer of 10^5 TCID₅₀/ml was heated at two different temperatures. In the first protocol the virus suspension was heated at 56°C for 30 min and 60 min. In the second it was heated at 60°C for 60 min. After heat treatment, the viral suspensions were

inoculated into HRT18 cells for three blind passages and viral growth was tested using a Mab-based virological ELISA. Heat treatment at 56°C was shown not to completely inactivate the virus for both 30 and 60 min as evidenced by viral growth after three passages. The viral suspension was instead completely inactivated at 60°C for 60 min.

5) Fast and easy field-deployable inactivation method for SARS-CoV-2 (and other viruses) using MPLB-buffer.

Reducing transmission risk during sample handling is paramount. Previous studies have shown virus inactivation abilities of the highly cytotoxic MagNA Pure Lysis Binding (MPLB) buffer used for nucleic acid extraction and purification (Rosenstjerne et al. *Journal of clinical microbiology*. 2016 Oct;54(10):2521-9 ; Vinner. and Fomsgaard., 2007. *Journal of virological methods*, 146(1-2), pp.401-404.). In this study, we show how 20 minutes of incubation in MPLB-buffer at room-temperature produce rapid inactivation of the SARS-CoV-2 using a modified published protocol by Rosenstjerne et al (2016).

Two human SARS-CoV-2 isolates of 10^5 and 10^6 Tissue Culture Infectious Dose₅₀/ml were incubated with MPLB-buffer or PBS (positive controls). The mixture was diluted to non-cytotoxic MPLB-buffer concentrations and incubated on tissue cultures. Supernatant and cells were harvested at multiple time-points and reverse transcription quantitative-PCR (RT-qPCR) was performed for quantification.

Results. We show that MPLB-buffer can reduce SARS-CoV-2 titers at least 2-log units. With this protocol, we can facilitate POI-diagnosis and promote field research without risk of infection.

This workpackage has been finalized and we could base on all experiments performed, agree on one methods for the final SOP, using a hand extraction method described by Rosenstjerne et al. and MPLB buffer (see above under point 5). The protocol for the SOP has been adapted including the input from all TELE-Vir partners, based on their experimental results.

WP3-T2- Development and validation of a S.O.P for sample NA purification

N/A extraction of RNA and DNA viruses infecting fish

To detect RNA and DNA viruses applying the metagenomics approach work is also ongoing on extracting nucleic acids from surface liquids (mucus) of fish infected by a DNA virus, using an rapid approach. Field samples were obtained after an outbreak and tested positive using conventional methods (extraction by columns and test by PCR). Starting with these samples, a simplified extraction procedure with a specific lysis buffer and magnetic beads was tested in 2021, both in lab. and field.

Three researchers spent one day in a fish farm affected by a severe viral disease due to a mimivirus (mortality > 70 %). Early in the morning, samples were collected from 2 sick fishes and extracted using a simplified protocol based on magnetic beads (kit Macherey-nagel, without centrifuge and columns). The presence of viral DNA in the total nucleic acids was tested using a portable PCR platform performing rapid cycles (MIC). Three successive different PCR assays were performed during the day: one for diagnostics (taqman-based), and two for genotyping the virus using High Resolution Melting targeting two distinct genes. Both samples were highly positive for the targeted virus indicating the efficiency of the extraction method for detecting the virus in clinical cases. The genotyping by HRM indicated the presence of two variants in co-infection in fish. However, the melting temperatures of each variant were slightly different (1°C) to those of controls and to those usually obtained by performing traditional - column based - extractions methods, suggesting the presence of contaminants having an effect on the stability of the double-stranded DNA when heated. The suspicion of contaminants is important since it may have an impact on the use of MinION, which is a sequencing method rather sensitive to the purity of DNA.

N/A extraction SARS-CoV-2 and peste des petits ruminant virus (PPRV)

In order to facilitate sample testing in field settings, a new evaluation study to circumvent NA extraction was accomplished. To this end, a panel of 71 nasopharyngeal swabs and 19 saliva samples, previously analysed for SARS-CoV-2 by the regular PCR method, were initially selected. Briefly, the so-called method “Saliva Direct” (Vogels et al, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.medj.2020.12.010) was followed and samples were heated at 95°C for 5 minutes in the presence of proteinase K, to be afterwards directly incorporated to the standard PCR mix. All samples with an initial Ct value <35 were detected using the “saliva direct” protocol. The Ct values reported by the two procedures compared, standard NA extraction and “saliva direct”, were mostly similar for samples with Ct<33. Even more, the “saliva direct” protocol allowed the SARS-CoV-2 detection by conventional RT-PCR and the subsequent Sanger sequencing was also successful. Whether these heated & treated samples could serve as template for NGS analysis using the MinION device still requires investigation.

Considering these promising results, additional studies were planned to evaluate the convenience of this system for the detection of other relevant viral pathogens. An initial panel of 10 samples (swabs, blood and faeces), collected at different days from a sheep experimentally infected with peste des petits ruminant virus (PPRV), was analysed. Samples were processed as mentioned above and tested with the real-time RT-PCR established in the lab for PPRV detection (using the same reagents as for SARS-CoV-2 PCR). Unfortunately, only samples with an initial Ct<30 could be detected, although reporting a Ct value much higher than using the standard NA extraction. Besides, samples with an initial Ct>30 were not detected. This preliminary study indicates that this “Saliva Direct” alternative could not be a reliable procedure for PPRV detection, at least under the assayed conditions.

Enrichment or depletion can be necessary to detect the RNA or DNA of interest in a metagenomics approach. Additional experiments with SARS-CoV-2 as model virus, with two pre-treatment steps were performed to delete cellular DNA, before nucleic acid discovery (Fomsgaard et al., 2022, MedXriv; /doi.org/10.1101/2021.12.31.21268552). Briefly, pooled SARS-CoV-2 patient samples were incubated with DNAase I Set (Zymo Research) in final volume of 1ml of PBS. After DNase treatment and additional filter step was performed using a 5ml syringe attached to a 0.22µm filter device, to process 1 ml of the sample material after DNase treatment. Nucleic acid extraction was performed using MagNA Pure LC Total Nucleic Acid Isolation Kit (Roche Life Sciences) by adding the 1 ml sample material (400µl DNase I treated sample material then diluted with 600µl PBS) directly into 1 ml of MagNA Pure Lysis and Binding-buffer (MPLB-buffer) following the field extraction method of Rosenstierne et al (2018). Briefly, sample and MPLB-buffer were mixed for lysis, before the magnetic glass particles (MGPs) were added and the contents mixed by gently flipping the tube. Using a small magnet, the MGPs were captured within the tube and washed three times in order to release bound nucleic acids. The same approach were used for both RNA and DNA pathogen detection.

Additional methods for N/A extraction were tested

Selected nasopharyngeal swabs have been processed with different lysis/inactivation buffers trying to circumvent the NA extraction. The first trials resulted in a lesser viral RNA detection by real-time PCR when compared to the established diagnostic procedure, resulting in the ultimate loss of the weak positive samples. Preliminary assays using samples collected on FTA cards have also led to lower detection of viral RNA. Experiments incorporating simple washing steps of FTA cards, with no need of NA extraction, combined with different RT-PCR reagents allowed to detect positive samples with Ct<30.

Heating of nasopharyngeal swabs has also been tested in order to circumvent NA extraction (Fomsgaard and Rosenstjerne, Euro Surveill. 2020 Apr;25(14):2000398. doi: 10.2807/1560-7917). The use of MagNA Pure Lysis Binding (MPLB) buffer as a field-deployable method for viral NA extraction and purification has been proven useful for targeted diagnostics of EBOV using RT-qPCR (Rosenstjerne et al. 2018. *Journal of visualized experiments: JoVE*, (136)).

Total Nucleic Acids (NA) extraction is performed by High Pure Viral Nucleic Acid kit (Roche). SISPA protocol is used to obtain cDNA by a random-tagged primer (FR26RV-N) consisting of six random nucleotides and a 20 nucleotides (nt) tag, synthesis of the second strand of cDNA will be achieved by 3'-5' Klenow Polymerase and PCR amplification step of ds cDNA is accomplished by a single primer (FR-20RV) complementary to the 20 nt tag.

We already has successfully established protocols for N/A extraction and we will agree on methods for the final SOP. The protocol for the SOP will be adapted including the input from all TELE-Vir partners, based on their experimental results.

WP3-T3- Development and validation of a S.O.P for NGS library preparation & MinION sequencing (DNA & RNA)

An SOP for two different MinION library preparation kits has been tested: PCR Barcoding kit (SQK-PBK004) and Rapid Barcoding Kit 96 (SQK-RBK110.96) that are able to prepare barcoded sequencing libraries for both gDNA and amplicons sequencing.

The PCR Barcoding kit (SQK-PBK004) is designed to prepare barcoded sequencing libraries when there is a limited amount of starting gDNA available from multiple samples. End-repair and dA-Tailing are performed using the NEBNext End Repair/dA-tailing module and then, adapters which contain primer binding sites, are ligated to the prepared ends. The kit contains 12x primer pairs, which are then used to amplify each sample: each primer pair contains a barcode and 5' tags which facilitate the ligase-free attachment of Rapid Sequencing Adapters. Amplified and barcoded samples are then pooled together and Rapid Sequencing Adapters are added to the pooled mix. The kit involves ~50 mins pre-PCR work. The PCR step is variable (depends on the number of cycles, polymerase speed and template length). The standard protocol requires starting with 100 ng of gDNA. The post-PCR work is about 10 mins.

Rapid Barcoding Kit 96 (SQK-RBK110.96) is a PCR-free method and therefore removes PCR bias and retains base modification information which can be analysed using tools developed in the Nanopore Community.

Deconvolution of barcoded sequencing data is supported by MinKNOW and Guppy software, which classify the barcode sequence and sort reads into corresponding folders.

The Rapid Barcoding Kit recommends an input of 50 ng of DNA in a total volume of 9 ul per sample.

MinION sequencing Avian influenza virus (AIV)

A SOP for MinION sequencing of Avian influenza virus (AIV) has been tested. Four primer PCR protocol and the PCR Barcoding Kit (SQK-PBK004) from Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT, Oxford,UK) was used to sequence and typing of avian influenza virus. Preliminary amplification of RNA was conducted prior to sequencing on MinION utilizing SuperScript IV One-Step RT-PCR System with Platinum Taq (Invitrogen/ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA) and universal Influenza A primers designed for the

conservative ends of all AIV segments (Zhou et al., 2009, J Virol 83:10309-10313). Spot on Flow Cell, R9 version (FLO MIN 106D; ONT) and basecaller Guppy (v3.29; ONT) was used for the real-time basecalling to produce sequencing data and monitor the run. Sequencing data from two samples were analyzed using CLC Genomics Workbench (Qiagen-CLCBio). Study is ongoing.

Similar efforts were done at Sciensano with targeted MinION applications for Avian influenza, as well as the ARTIC nCOV-2019 amplicon sequencing panel. Data were shared with Insa in the frame of task WP2T2 for evaluation in the InsaFlu pipeline in comparison to other analysis options.

MinION sequencing bovine coronavirus (BCoV)

A SOP for MinION sequencing of bovine coronavirus (BCoV) as a model has been tested. The SOP is based on Sequence-Independent Single-Primer Amplification (SISPA) and Native barcoding genomic DNA protocol (with EXP-NBD104, EXP-NBD114, and SQK-LSK109) available from the Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT, Oxford, UK). SISPA approach allows to amplify total RNA in ca 9 hours, however the protocol time can be shortened by reducing the number of PCR amplification cycles. The process involved the following steps: I. Reverse transcription of RNA utilizing SuperScript IV (Invitrogen/ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA) with tag-labelled primer (Allander et al., 2005); II. Second strand synthesis using 3'-5' exo- Klenow DNA polymerase (New England Biolabs, Ipswich, MA); III. Whole Genome Amplification of double-stranded cDNA by PCR. The study is ongoing.

The other SOP which also tested on BCoV as a model was based on Complete Whole Transcriptome Amplification Kit (WTA2-10RXN, Merk, Sigma-Aldrich) and Native barcoding genomic DNA protocol (with EXP-NBD104, EXP-NBD114, and SQK-LSK109) available from the Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT, Oxford, UK). WTA2 kit allows to amplify total RNA in less than 4 hours. The process involved two steps: I. Reverse transcription of RNA with non-self-complementary primers which resulted in cDNA library, comprised of random, overlapping 100 - 1000 base fragments flanked by universal end sequence; II. Amplification of cDNA by PCR using WTA2 polymerase and a universal end primer to produce WTA2 product. The study is ongoing.

MinION sequencing African swine fever (ASFV)

A SOP for MinION sequencing of African swine fever virus (ASFV) without DNA preamplification was tested. The SOP is Genomic DNA by ligation (SQK-LSK109) which can be used in combination with Native barcoding genomic DNA protocol (with EXP-NBD104, EXP-NBD114) available from the Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT, Oxford, UK). The process involved DNA repair, adapter ligation and clean-up, followed by priming and loading the flow cell and sequencing. Time for the MinION library preparation from high molecular weight genomic DNA (1.5 µg input) can be shortened to 3-3,5 hours. The study is ongoing.

Metagenomics approaches

Animal viruses

Several random amplification and library prep methods with readout on Oxford Nanopore Technologies and Illumina platforms for several cases were evaluated: (1) on a farmed seabass sample from partner ANSES (Laurent Bigarré) (cluster of cases with hemorrhagic skin lesions); (2) massive mortality of EMCV infected piglets in Belgium with suspicion of an additional viral cofactor and (3) massive mortality of piglets in Spain where EMCV was already excluded using targeted diagnostic assays. Without identification of a clear etiology in the seabass case. In Belgian pig case: near full genome of EMCV was recovered + co-infecting Torque teno sus virus and Gokushoviruses. In the Spain pig case no etiology could be identified. The 3 cases highlight the need of analysing proper control samples and of the development of good metagenomic analysis workflows.

Swabs (from lymph node and spleen) from 2 cows tested positive for malignant catarrhal fever were used to evaluate a protocol comparing 2 high-molecular weight DNA extraction methods (Monarch vs Puregene) and different amplification protocols (REPLig vs Picoplex vs no amplification) prior to MinION sequencing. Metagenomic analysis identified for 5 out of 8 conditions tested 1 or more Ovine

Gammaherpesvirus 2 read(s) that covered at most 6.4% of the viral genome. The results highlighted that more investigations were needed using this approach.

Human viruses – exemplified by SARS-CoV-2

SARS-CoV-2 samples with two pretreatment steps and N/A as describe above (see also Fomsgaard et al., 2022, MedXriv; /doi.org/10.1101/2021.12.31.21268552) and further cDNA synthesis and random amplification were performed for subsequently library preparation and nanopore sequencing. Briefly as also described in Fomsgaard et al., 2022, MedXriv; /doi.org/10.1101/2021.12.31.21268552 , the Whole Transcription (WTA) system in the REPLI-g Cell WGA and WTA Kit (Qiagen) was used for additional genomic DNA removal, reverse transcription, ligation and random amplification. Two modifications were incorporated into the protocol: firstly, the NA from the 10 µl input material remained bound to the MGPs from the NA extraction step (Rosenstjerne et al., 2018). Secondly, instead of using the oligo dT primers provided in the kit for the reverse-transcription step, we used 20 µM 5'-phosphorylated random hexamers as described earlier (Rosenstjerne et al., 2014). For the library preparation samples were multiplexed using the Rapid Barcoding Kit (Oxford Nanopore Technology). The DNA concentrations of the samples were determined using a Qubit Fluorimeter (Life Technologies) and used to normalize the input material for sequencing libraries. Here, sample concentrations were standardized to contain 400 ng DNA (in 7.5 µl) , incubated with 2.5 µl of the individual barcodes for 1 minute at 30°C and then 80°C, before 10 µl of multiplexed samples were incubated for another 5 minutes at room temperature with the rapid adaptor enzyme. For faster library preparation, bead purification was omitted. The libraries were loaded and sequenced on R9.4.1 flowcells on the MK1C device (Oxford Nanopore Technology) with default settings, fast base calling enabled and a run length of 20 hours. DNase/RNase free water was included as a negative control. By reducing the non viral RNA components in the samples using a DNase pretreatment, as well by establishing the whole protocol from N/A extraction to library preparation we could successfully established a protocol that allows fast (within six hours) metagenomics detection of RNA viruses in biological samples. This is an important step for our WP4, where we want to detect RNA- and DNA viruses in samples collected in the field.

A similar approach has been tested for the detection of DNA viruses. Here 8 HPV positive samples 1 and a negative control were subjected to the two pretreatment steps as described above. REPLI-G were used for cDNA synthesis and for Whole Genome amplification (WGA) and sequencing libraries were prepared with the Rapid Barcoding Kit (Oxford Nanopore Technology). The study is ongoing and further optimization of the protocol and metagenomics analysis are needed.

3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
16	D-JRP14-1.1	Kick-off meeting in Italy (IZSAM)	M25	M25		Public https://zenodo.org/record/3734134#.Xwbj0Sgza70 Milestone reached by M25 on time	
16	D-JRP14-1.2	1st version of the DMP	M30	M30		Milestone reached by M30 on time	
16	D-JRP14-WP1.3	1st TELE-Vir meeting (online)	M37	M37		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5506645#.YUSEcLgza70 Milestone reached by M37 on time	

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
16	D-JRP14-WP1.4	2nd version of the DMP	M42	M46		Work is ongoing	
16	D-JRP14-WP2.1	Open-sourced bioinformatics platform that allows the user-friendly handling of high-throughput sequencing data (second and third generation) for detection and monitoring of viral emerging threats	M48	Ongoing	M57	Multiple functionalities were already developed and implemented in the platform. Due to the several circumstances (pandemic, difficulty in post-doc hiring, the extension of the project...), work is still ongoing and will be delivered on M57.	
16	D-JRP14-3.1	1st version of a poi S.O.P for sample handling & pre-treatment	M36	M39		Deliverable reached and published https://zenodo.org/record/5506816#.YUSElbgza70	
16	D-JRP14-3.2	1st version of a poi S.O.P for sample NA	M36	M39		Deliverable reached and published	

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		purification				https://zenodo.org/record/5506848#.YUSFD7gza70	
16	D-JRP14-3.3	1st version of a poi S.O.P for NGS library preparation & MinION sequencing	M36	M46	M51	Protocol found for RNA viruses, different sample material needs to be tested in WP4. For DNA viruses experiments are in process. First SOP can be written in M50/51	
16	D-JRP14-WP3.4	Report on the validation of MinION sequencing mimicking the field scenario in lab conditions	M48		M54	The report will be written in M54, as the field studies are ongoing from M48 to M54 based on the six months extension of the project	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
16	M-JRP14-01	Collected and curated databases for genotype-phenotype associations	M36	Yes		Initial database for CoV genotype phenotype associations complete. The rapidly developing available data for SARS-CoV-2 mean that this database will need to be continuously reviewed, throughout the remaining project time.
16	M-JRP14-02	Software modules for third-generation sequencing data handling	M39	Yes		Modules for automate quality control and analysis of ONT data were developed and implemented.
16	M-JRP14-03	Software modules for viral rapid detection and classification	M42	Ongoing		Modules for automate classification of Beta-coronaviruses, and further lineage classification of SARS-CoV-2 were implemented. Work is ongoing to implement module for pathogen identification.
16	M-JRP14-04	Software module for rapid screening of genetic features potentially linked to specific phenotypes (e.g., antigenicity, tropism, anti-viral drug resistance)	M45	Ongoing	M54	Automated add-on to existing INSaFlu modules developed and undergoing testing. The rapidly developing Sars-CoV2 available data mean delaying this milestone to ensure the resulting module is fit for purpose is strategically important
16	M-JRP14-05	Advertisement of the poi-toolbox workshop finished	M47		M53	Workshop postponed due to the six month extension of the project
16	M-JRP14-06	Detailed plans and scheme for training of TELE-Vir and	M48		M54	Postponed due to the six month extension of the project

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		OHEJP participants in the POI protocol for MinION sequencing performed incl. training materials, manuals & lectures and personal				
16	M-JRP14-07	Detailed plans and scheme for training of TELE-Vir and OHEJP participants in the POI data analysis performed incl. training materials, manuals & lectures and personal	M48		M54	Postponed due to the six month extension of the project
16	M-JRP14-08	Registration of participants for training in the POI-toolbox finished (max. 30 participants)	M48		M54	Postponed due to the six month extension of the project
16	M-JRP14-09	Software module for locus- and genome-based comparative phylogenomics	M48	ongoing	M54	Novel functionalities for better phylogenetic/metadata data navigation and interpretation were implemented. Work is ongoing to implement a module for enhanced temporal and phylogeographical analysis

4. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
An alternative workflow for molecular detection of SARS-CoV-2 – escape from the NA extraction kits shortage, Copenhagen, Denmark, March 2020 https://doi.org/10.2807/1560-7917.ES.2020.25.14.2000398 https://zenodo.org/record/4247188#.X6QLjWhKjcc	No		
Improvement of field deployable metagenomics virus detection by a simple pretreatment method doi.org/10.1101/2021.12.31.21268552	yes		

Additional output

Posters

- Borges V. 2020. INSaFLU: open web-based bioinformatics suite for genome-based surveillance of influenza virus and other pathogens, such as SARS-CoV-2. European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) COVID-19 Laboratory Networks Influenza (online), 20 de Maio, 2020 (**invited communication**)
- Borges V. 2020. INSaFLU: open web-based bioinformatics suite for genome-based surveillance of influenza virus and other pathogens, such as SARS-CoV-2. **World Health Organization (WHO) Europe Laboratory Workshop** (online). 1 de Junho, 2020. (**invited communication**)
- C. Bogaardt, V. Borges, J. P. Gomes, J. Isidro, M. Pinheiro, J. M. Prada, D. L. Horton. Assessing coronavirus risks: feasibility of predicting traits of clinical and epidemiological relevance from sequence data. OHEJP Copenhagen June 9-11th 2021 (**poster**)
- Borges V. 2020. INSaFLU: open web-based bioinformatics suite for genome-based surveillance of influenza virus and other pathogens, such as SARS-CoV-2. **INASA (National Institute of Health from Guinea-Bissau) (27 August 2021)**. (**invited communication**)
- Pinheiro M, Pais RJ, Isidro J, Pinto M, Bogaardt C, Prada JM, Horton DL, Gomes JP, Borges V (2021) INSaFLU-TELE-Vir: an open web-based bioinformatics suite for influenza and SARS-CoV-2 genome-based surveillance. **ARPHA Conference Abstracts** 4:e68845. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.4.e68845>
- Vítor Borges, Miguel Pinheiro, Ricardo J. Pais, Joana Isidro, Miguel Pinto, Carlijn Bogaardt, Joaquin M. Prada, Daniel L. Horton, João Paulo Gomes. INSaFLU-TELE-Vir: an open web-based bioinformatics suite for genome-based surveillance of influenza, SARS-CoV-2 and other pathogens. ISIRV-WHO Virtual Conference, COVID-19, Influenza and RSV: Surveillance-Informed Prevention and Treatment, 19-21 October 2021 (**e-poster and recorded flash talk**)

Poster presentation at One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting:

Fast and easy field-deployable Sars-CoV-2 virus inactivation for downstream analysis. Anna S. Fomsgaard^{1,2}, Graham J. Belsham², Ria M. Lassaunière¹, Jannik Fonager¹, Katja Spiess¹ 1. Virus Research & Development Laboratory, Statens Serum Institute, Copenhagen, Denmark 2. Department of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

Outcomes

- Delevelopment of field deployable inactivation of viruses (DNA and RNA)
- Development of a pretreatment strategy to increase non-target virus detection applying metagenomics
- Development of an open web-based bioinformatics suite for virus genome-based surveillance

5. *Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries*

As the national member of the ECDC EVD-LabNet (Anders Fomsgaard) we are sharing methods and results from our TELE-Vir methods in detection of emerging virus.

The Statens Serum Intitute (SSI) in CHP Denmark is a one health institute and thus all findings and methods and mututal surveillence testings are shared with Veterinary networks and ECDC.

The National Institute of Health (INSA) Dr Ricardo Jorge, Portugal, has presented the INSaFLU-TELE-Vir open web-based bioinformatics suite for virus genome-based surveillence on behalf of several international initiatives and networks, e.g., ECDC COVID-19 Laboratory Networks Influenza, WHO Europe Laboratory Workshop. INSA also maintains several cooperative actions at national and international levels to enhance the capacity building of other national and international laboratories (e.g., National Institute of Health from Guinea-Bissau) in pathogen genome-based surveillence.

Medilabsecure (<https://www.medilabsecure.com/>) is an international project aiming to reinforce the preparedness and surveillence of relevant zoonotic pathogens in 22 beneficiary non-EU countries through a one health consortium. Human virology, animal virology, entomology, public health, veterinary services, and epidemiology sectors join their knowledge in specialized networks. CISA-INIA is leading the veterinary virology network, and will transfer the technology and methods emanated from the TELE-Vir project, which are specifically relevant tools for the human and animal virology components of Medilabsecure. Nextthreat is a recently launched Spanish project aiming to explore the viral pool in selected matrices from different environmental settings to finally identify and prioritise potential emerging pathogens. The consortium is leaded by CISA-INIA and include a multidisciplinary expert panel working under a one health approach. Protocols produced within the TELE-Vir project could be further validated during the progress of Nextthreat.

6. *List of critical risks*

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	Yes
Other risks (please describe)	

Additional information

The project leader Maiken Rosenstjerne left the project, but was immediately replaced be a new project leader for the TELE-Vir project Katja Spiess. We lost one project member, but the task could be covered by other partners of the TELE-Vir project. Due to the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic tasks and reporting got delayed, but with the six months extension, the project can be finished with a good result outcome.

JRP17-ET2.2-IDEMBRU

1. Summary of the work carried out in year 4

Project IDEMBRU aims to develop a toolkit for diagnostics, characterization and assessment of zoonotic potential of newly discovered species and strains of worldwide present and dangerous bacteria from genus *Brucella*. In the same time, the project examines the possibilities for existence of new unexplored wildlife and environmental reservoirs of classical *Brucella* species, which have been characterised Worldwide as tools for bioterrorism. The toolkit will be able to assess the risks for new sources and newly discovered strains of *Brucella* species in order to greatly improve the public health protection from this highly contagious disease.

In the second year of the project, the consortium reorganised and prioritized the tasks of genetic, phenotypic comparisons and characterisation of zoonotic potential of newly discovered species and isolated strains. All partners continued sample collections from wildlife, environment and humans in order to assess the levels of contamination and provide scenarios to test the final toolkit within the One Health approach concept.

The sample collection for WP1 started throughout Europe mainly from wildlife species from forest, fresh water and marine coastal habitats. The sampling is now ongoing in all partners' laboratories participating in WP-1. To be able to complete this task, the consortium organised sample collections with the wildlife protection networks and hunting organisations in each country. To optimise the usage of wildlife carcasses, from these organisations the existing tissue samples already collected for other research projects are exploited. Already more than 1500 samples have been processed and analysed at least by molecular or bacteriological methods. Several environmental strains of bacteria similar to *Brucella* (such as *Ochrobactrum* spp.) have been isolated, but further genetic typing is needed to establish the links.

Currently, many European countries are experiencing the surge in cases of canine brucellosis primarily in dogs with few human cases described as well. Within WP-2, the network with another One Health EJP project – COHESIVE has been established regarding the evaluation of presence of *Brucella canis* in dogs and humans and to determine its pathogenic characteristics. The professional exposure groups have been identified and WP-2 concentrated the sera testing on samples coming from individuals who are professionally more likely exposed to *Brucellae*. The members of two projects organised the first European workshop on *B. canis* in May 2021, and it made foundation for the joint White paper initiative on current epidemiological situation in Europe and recommendations to EU commission for further necessary actions. Therefore, IDEMBRU project decided to focus a part of its work on *B. canis* as one of the evident emerging zoonoses from *Brucella* genus. Since the project saw many setbacks last year, the evaluation of DNA extraction methods from complex matrices (water, soil and faeces) was finalized at the end of 2021. Additionally, the DNA extraction from canine faeces has been analysed as important source of data. The harmonised whole genome sequencing protocols have been prepared and first ring trials finished. This year the environmental root commensal bacteria *Ochrobactrum* spp. have been added to the *Brucella* genus since several species are considered opportunistic pathogens. During our project, many isolated strains, especially from environmental samples, similar to *Brucella* morphologically, have been isolated, but molecular methods did not detect them. Therefore, we constructed the primers specific for *Ochrobactrum* spp. in order to distinguish between the two genera. The next step is to validate a microfluidics PCR plate, so that the diagnostic and typing of *Brucella* and *Brucella*-like bacteria can be performed even from a few organisms on a large number of samples. The big advantage of microfluidics system is that it can perform up to 96 primer pairs PCR on up to 96 samples at the time, and the total volume of the sample is 1µl. The protocols for RNA extraction, RNA sequencing and antimicrobial resistance have been validated. The only manufacturer of plates for micronaut analysis stopped the production because of the economic value. Therefore, the IDEMBRU consortium decided to replace micronaut analysis with MALDI-TOF MS high resolution and include the lipopolysaccharides in the MALDI-TOF libraries. This means the

proteomic profiling of already known, highly virulent strains, low virulent and non zoonotic strains from bacterial media, as well as upon cell culture infections. This will create complete proteomic profile and help identify the virulence factors which can then be used in new diagnostic and/or characterisation tests. The results obtained will be confirmed with other employed methods in WP3, WP4 and WP5 before adding any conclusions to the final toolkit. The cell cultures for *in vitro* infection have been chosen, and pipeline for pathogenicity classification established so that first experiments in WP-5 can start as planned this year.

The regular monthly online meetings are held within consortium, and WP communication

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1 Recording the situation of brucellosis in emergent wild and environmental reservoirs (M37-M50)

WP1 takes place throughout the first, second, and third year of the project. Task 2 and task 3 have been developed during 2021.

WP1-T2 Sampling and analytical strategy according to previous epidemiological information from the different partners (M37-M50)

Task 2 is being developed since November 2020 and will last until February 2022. At the time of this report, a total of 1584 samples from different hosts and from the three different biotopes (coastal regions, forest and fresh water) has been analysed. Table 1 summarizes the variety of samples obtained and processed to map existing atypical or emerging *Brucella* strains. Depending on the host species, collected samples included blood, and tissues such as brain, thymus, lung, muscles, parts of internal organs, and lymph nodes.

Guidelines for sample treatment and bacteriological diagnosis procedures were harmonized and distributed among partners. The harmonization of complementary molecular and serological methods are in the final stages. Most of the tissue samples have been initially tested by bacteriological and molecular diagnostic methods. Blood samples, when available, were tested using rose Bengal test (RBT), complement fixation test (CFT) and specific ELISAs, to characterise serological responses. All isolated strains (*Brucella* spp. or *Ochrobactrum* spp.) were characterized according conventional microbiological and molecular methods. First results of these analyses, combined with epidemiological data were presented at annual OH EJP Conference and at the international Brucellosis conference in Chicago (December 2021).

WP1-T3 Synthesis and analysis of data (M37-M50)

Data obtained in task 1 and task 2 is being integrated for further analysis to improve knowledge regarding emergent *Brucella* species infections.

Table 1. Existing collection of samples, hosts and Countries of origin.

Biotope	Host	No. samples	Origin
Coastal Region	Cetaceans	59	United Kingdom, France
	Pinnipeds	2	United Kingdom
	Turtle	50	Italy
Forest	Foxes	660	Bulgaria, France, Germany, Portugal
	Hares	45	Portugal
	Jackals	42	Bulgaria
	Wild ruminants	262	Bulgaria, France, Germany, Portugal
	Wildboar	457	Bulgaria, France, Portugal
Freshwater	Frog	7	Germany

WP2 Recording the situation of brucellosis in humans

WP2-T1 Creation of a surveillance network dedicated to human brucellosis

A brucellosis laboratory surveillance network was developed in collaboration with Bruce-list and Portuguese network of medical laboratories (hospitals and private laboratories). The epidemiological questionnaire was developed and distributed in order to obtain as many data as possible, and in the same time respect the personal data protection and privacies of each patient. Since 2020, several outbreaks of *Brucella canis* were recorded throughout European kennels. In collaboration with COHESIVE project, we decided to focus on patients who have professional exposure, primarily to *Brucella canis*, but also to other sources of atypical *Brucella* species (veterinary workers, kennel and shelter staff, fisherman...). From already existing sera bank and tissue collections, samples were obtained from same population as described above, in order to establish the strains collection and/or the biological samples from human populations suspected of *Brucella* infections.

WP2-T2 Sampling and analytical strategy according to epidemiological information from the surveillance network

The human tissue samples in Portugal were processed by direct bacteriological and molecular diagnostic methods (isolation and real time PCR) in the biosafety level 3 facility. At this moment 44 human samples (21 blood, 13 cerebro-spinal fluids, 4 biopsies and 6 already isolated strains-confirmation analysis) were processed.

According to the agreement with COHESIVE project, we started to check already existing sera banks with targeted populations. We tested 200 sera belonging to the biobank of the National Institute of Health Dr Ricardo Jorge (previously no *Brucella* suspicions) using Rose-Bengal test. All serologically positive sera were tested by real time PCR for *Brucella* targeting IS711.

In the lights of newly identified strain *B. inopinata* –like BO3 isolated from a pet frog, which does not agglutinate with any of known mono specific sera (anti A, anti M, anti R), deliverables 2 and 3 have to be postponed. In the next four months, ANSES partner (also EURL for brucellosis) will produce the specific antigens for BO3 strain for diagnostic purposes. *B. inopinata* and *inopinata*-like strains are genetically atypical representatives of *Brucella* genus, with proven zoonotic potential. No reaction with known *Brucella* specific sera, demonstrates existence of strains/species that cannot be detected by current diagnostic tools, which still represents significant threats for public health. The production of a specific antigen will allow validation of existing banks on choosen (see above) human sera for the presence of specific antibodies for newly discovered atypical *Brucella* strains, probably even beyond BO3 strain.

In the same time, we noticed that there is no known test for humans for rough *Brucella* species (such as *B. ovis* and *B. canis*). This means that there are no test (validated or in development), except direct bacteriological and molecular diagnostics tools, for newly emerging *B. canis* infections in humans. Therefore, we propose to use the existing *B. ovis* antigen for complement fixation (FC) test and try to validate it on a sera from confirmed human brucellosis cases, as well as dog owners from which *B. canis* or *B. suis* have been diagnosed.

We can do all additional tests and shine more light on human brucellosis risks as well as public health protection strategies if we obtain additional six months for the WP2-Del2 which will impact WP2-Del3 as well. This extension will also contribute greatly to the completeness of the final toolkit from human medicine side and improve the decision making trees the toolkit will provide.

WP3 Genomic characterisation of *Brucella* detected from samples and selected isolates

WP3-T1 Optimisation of methods for generating molecular typing data from complex samples

Consortium members previously contributed to an informal survey describing DNA extraction protocols currently applied to animal tissue and environmental samples in partner laboratories. Through this we identified where methodological discrepancies existed, and areas where further optimisation work was required. Consequently, we have focused optimization work on a number of complex matrices of particular significance to the current project, such as swabs and soil.

Evaluation of methods for DNA extraction from soil has been performed at APHA. Comparison of DNA extraction methods has been undertaken using soil types relevant to the distinct ecosystems identified in IDEMBRU WP1 and biologically relevant concentrations of target organism DNA.

Swabs are used for sampling animal and human tissues as well as environment. Evaluation of different types of swabs has been performed at ANSES. This work has identified optimal swab materials and recovery protocols. Optimisation of protocols for swabs has focused on both DNA extraction and culture of viable organisms. This work has now been published (Freddi et al., 2021 [<https://doi.org/10.1128/Spectrum.00728-21>]).

WP3-T2 Harmonisation and standardisation of protocols for whole genome sequencing

This task aims to compare the performance of whole genome sequencing procedures undertaken in partner institutes. This incorporates both the practical aspects (DNA extraction, library preparation, whole genome sequencing) and bioinformatics (de novo assembly and reference-based alignment) protocols.

A survey was conducted amongst partner institutes engaged in WP3, in order to identify common practices and ensure results are comparable between partner institutes. A relevant panel of *Brucella* spp. isolates was identified, and prepared for distribution to partner institutes engaged in WP3. Prior to distribution (as heat-inactivated cultures) these strains were tested to confirm the identify and suitability of the material.

Whole genome sequencing of the material shared was undertaken by partner institutes, using existing locally established protocols. Not all partner institutes engaged in this task have been able to return results within the required time-frame (three of seven). Delays have arisen from involvement of partners laboratories in the on-going COVID-19 response in their respective countries, and other competing demands on staff time and resources (e.g. avian influenza outbreaks). Consequently, the deliverable report for this task will be up-dated as soon as further results are received (within the next two months).

Results concerning the performance of library preparation and whole genome sequencing undertaken in partner institutes (e.g. quality metrics; number of reads etc.) have been collated, to assess comparability between partner institutes. Additionally, reference-based alignment and de novo assembly metrics have been compared. Where possible, sequencing results returned by partner institutes have been compared with curated reference sequences available via publically available

genome databases (e.g. NCBI RefSeq) to benchmark results. Participating laboratories employed a number of different methods for DNA extraction, though in all cases a commercially produced column based kit was used. Similarly, several different methods were used for quantification and quality assessment of the resulting DNA, with both micro-volume spectrophotometry and DNA-binding fluorescent dye approaches applied. There were significant differences between participants in the concentration of DNA recovered from the strains (2-way ANOVA; $P < 0.01$). However, all DNA concentrations were sufficient for the library preparation kit in use at participating laboratories. As would be expected, there was a significant positive association between the number of reads and the percentage of reads identified as duplicates. Participants employed a number of different tools for short-read reference based alignment and variant calling at their respective laboratories. Outliers in this relationship (i.e. those samples with the largest residuals in linear regression) were all *B. inopinata* BO1. Similarly, there was a highly significant positive association between the total number of reads and the average depth of coverage of the reference genome (linear regression $R^2 = 0.6636$; $P < 0.0001$). The number of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) identified by participants, relative to the selected reference strain, was largely comparable. As expected, both *B. inopinata* and *B. vulpis* exhibited a markedly higher number of SNPs than the three core *Brucella* species included in the panel of strains.

In conclusion: A number of significant differences were observed between institutes in results of both sequencing performance and subsequent and bioinformatics analysis. However, in all cases differences between laboratories had very minor impact on the conclusions which could be drawn, relative to differences between the strains themselves. The high degree of genetic divergence of atypical *Brucella* strains (both relative to core *Brucella* spp. and amongst atypical strains) emphasises the need to select appropriate reference genomes for reference-based mapping and variant calling analyses. Additionally, this work has also identified a need for improved reference genomes for a number of recently described *Brucella* sp. strains.

WP3-T3 Identification of emerging Brucella species: adaptation of molecular tools

This task aims to utilise conventional methods and whole genome sequencing to generate molecular typing data from emerging *Brucella* spp. isolates, to ensure that existing schemes remain applicable to the full diversity of the genus.

Initial work for this task has involved the collation of existing data from atypical strains from publically available databases of WGS (e.g. NCBI SRA), MLVA and MLST data. Where strains are not represented in databases of existing conventional typing methods (MLVA and MLST), these results will be extracted from available whole genome sequence data, using available pipelines.

Also under WP3, methods for generating long-read sequencing data using the Oxford Nanopore Minlon platform have been evaluated and optimized. Application of these protocols for generating long-read sequencing data have enabled complete, or nearly complete, genomes to be generated for a panel of atypical *Brucella* spp. isolates.

WP3-T4 Integrative analysis of genomic and epidemiological data collected in WP1 and WP2

This task will utilise results from other tasks within WP3, and has not yet been started.

WP4 Phenotypic characterisation of Brucella detected from samples and selected isolates

WP4-T1 Phenotyping of novel emerging Brucella spp.

WP4-T1-ST1

The subtask has started. Strains from FLI were phenotyped and sent to BfR for RNA Sequencing. A phenotyping scheme specifically for novel emerging *Brucella* spp. is currently being developed together with the project partners.

WP4-T1-ST2

Initial motility tests have been carried out. Suitable *Brucella* candidates are selected for electron microscopy studies. Electron microscopic investigations are currently being carried out.

WP4-T1-ST3

Unfortunately, production of the commercial test system for phenotyping *Brucella* has been discontinued. Therefore, the work with this particular system in this subtask can not be performed and further characterisation will be replaced with MALDI-TOF library analysis and library creation.

WP4-T2 Antimicrobial resistance testing of emerging *Brucella* spp.

WP4-T2-ST1

A microdilution antibiotic test scheme has been tested with novel emerging *Brucella* to adapt the procedure. A suitable antibiotic pattern has been selected. Based on this pattern, the antimicrobial test plates have been ordered from the manufacturer and have already been delivered to all project partners involved in these experiments. Currently, the corresponding working protocols are being discussed and implemented in the partner laboratories.

Table 2. Layout of the antimicrobial test plate

Abs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
GEN	8	4	2	1	0,5	0,25	0,125	0,0625	0,031	0,016	0,008	0,004
STR	16	8	4	2	1	0,5	0,25	0,125	0,0625	0,031	0,016	0,008
DOX	8	4	2	1	0,5	0,25	0,125	0,0625	0,031	0,016	0,008	0,004
TET	8	4	2	1	0,5	0,25	0,125	0,0625	0,031	0,016	0,008	0,004
CMP/ RAM	CMP 8	CMP 4	CMP 2	CMP 1	CMP 0,5	RAM 8	RAM 4	RAM 2	RAM 1	RAM 0,5	RAM 0,25	RAM 0,125
T/S	4/76	2/38	1/19	0,5/ 9,5	0,25/ 4,76	0,125/ 2,375	0,0625 / 1,187	0,031/ 0,594	0,016/ 0,297	0,0078 / 0,148	0,0039/ 0,074	0,00195/ 0,037
CIP	4	2	1	0,5	0,25	0,125	0,0625	0,031	0,016	0,008	0,004	0,002
LEV	4	2	1	0,5	0,25	0,125	0,0625	0,031	0,016	0,008	0,004	GC

CMP: Chloramphenicol; CIP: Ciprofloxacin; DOX: Doxycyclin; GEN: Gentamycin; LEV: Levofloxacin; RAM: Rifampicin; STR: Streptomycin; TET: Tetracyclin; T/S: Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole; GC: Growth Control

AMR testing of a *brucella*-like frog isolate using micronaut plate is presented. Upper table: plate measured in a commercial ELISA reader at 450 nm. Lower table: reading by eye. Orange marked areal=result; green marked areal=growth control. Values between reading by eye and measurement with ELISA reader are in good agreement if you choose 0.1 (ELISA reader result) as cut off value.

Abs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A -GEN	0,065	0,065	0,063	0,064	0,064	0,065	1,197	1,345	1,351	1,341	1,348	1,343
B -STR	0,064	0,066	0,064	0,065	0,673	1,166	1,291	1,331	1,335	1,366	1,352	1,338
C -DOX	0,069	0,067	0,068	0,067	0,067	0,069	0,123	0,742	0,964	1,119	1,260	1,317
D -TET	0,077	0,068	0,068	0,067	0,068	0,071	0,284	0,746	0,930	1,137	1,264	1,291
E - CMP/RAM	0,065	0,064	0,065	0,070	0,937	0,091	0,641	1,169	1,328	1,334	1,324	1,325
F - T/S	0,082	0,092	0,109	0,297	0,860	1,114	1,281	1,321	1,338	1,348	1,344	1,377
G -CIP	0,065	0,064	0,064	0,332	0,874	1,287	1,277	1,322	1,306	1,303	1,296	1,310
H -LEV	0,064	0,067	0,063	0,131	0,624	1,166	1,333	1,331	1,322	1,338	1,327	1,336

Abs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12

A - GEN	8	4	2	1	0,5	0,25	0,125	0,063	0,031	0,016	0,008	0,004
B - STR	16	8	4	2	1	0,5	0,25	0,125	0,063	0,031	0,016	0,008
C - DOX	8	4	2	1	0,5	0,25	0,125	0,063	0,031	0,016	0,008	0,004
D - TET	8	4	2	1	0,5	0,25	0,125	0,063	0,031	0,016	0,008	0,004
E - CMP/RAM	8	4	2	1	0,5	8	4	2	1	0,5	0,25	0,125
F - T/S	4/76	2/38	1/19	0,5/9,5	0,25/4,76	0,125 / 2,375	0,0625 / 1,187	0,031 / 0,594	0,016 / 0,297	0,0078 / 0,148	0,0039 / 0,074	0,00195 / 0,037
G - CIP	4	2	1	0,5	0,25	0,125	0,063	0,031	0,016	0,008	0,004	0,002
H - LEV	4	2	1	0,5	0,25	0,125	0,063	0,031	0,016	0,008	0,004	GC

For comparison: photo of scanned plate:

WP4-T3 RNA sequencing of a representative panel of classical and novel *Brucella* spp.

WP4-T3-ST1

Evaluation of RNA seq kits for different *Brucella* species identification has been done. A suitable protocol has been developed. However, based on further work, this will also be adapted in the future, if necessary.

WP4-T3-ST2

Currently optimization of the RNA-Seq protocol is underway.

WP4-T3-ST3

Clinical isolates from one project partner (FLI) have arrived and the respective MALDI ToF MS spectra have been generated. In addition strains from the in-house strain collection that had not yet been integrated into the existing peptide profile database have been analyzed with MALDI ToF MS. Integration of these MALDI ToF MS spectra into the peptide profile database is underway. MALDI ToF MS spectra generation and subsequent integration will be continued when isolates from the other project partners are available.

WP4-T3-ST4

To identify active metabolic pathways in different *Brucella* spp. an integrative bioinformatic analysis of genomic, transcriptomic and metabolic data will be done. However, metabolic phenotyping of *Brucella* isolates cannot be carried out as planned since the Micronout™ system is not available anymore. Therefore, a new metabolic phenotyping approach has been designed and will be implemented to enable generation of the required metabolic data.

WP5 Zoonotic potential and virulence

WP5-T1-ST1 Creation of *Brucella* genomes database from publicly available and emerging isolates

Creation of the database was slightly delayed as emerging isolates are still mostly lacking. Therefore, we decided to focus more on a test-set based on publicly available isolates and isolates we had in our own collection. As the final goal is to be able to give an indication of the zoonotic potential of the isolates, we first gathered information on this classification. Good classifications could be found for *B. melitensis*, *B. abortus*, *B. suis*, *B. canis*, *B. ovis*, *B. neotomae*, *B. ceti*, *B. pinnipedialis* and *B. microti* (Table 1). Reference assemblies of these species were collected from NCBI. Next to these near perfect assemblies, draft assemblies based solely on Illumina reads from our own database were collected for all species and the serovars except *B. microti*, which was lacking in our collection. These draft assemblies are probably more similar to the data we will obtain from new isolates from WP1, WP2 and WP3 in the first stage of genomic characterization. Combining both sets gave a test-set of 30 genomes to be used to examine differences between zoonotic and non-zoonotic species and robustness of tools to assembly quality.

Table 3: Predicted zoonotic potential

Species	Host preference	Predicted zoonotic potential
<i>B. melitensis</i>	sheep, goat	high
<i>B. abortus</i>	cattle	moderate
<i>B. suis</i>	pig	moderate
<i>B. canis</i>	dog	mild
<i>B. pinnipedialis</i>	seals	mild
<i>B. ceti</i>	cetaceans	mild
<i>B. microti</i>	common voles	no reported infections
<i>B. neotomae</i>	dessert wood rat	mild
<i>B. ovis</i>	sheep	no reported infections

Based on Atluri et al. 2011, Xavier et al. 2010 and a survey within the IDEMBRU consortium.

WP5-T1-ST2 Selection of bioinformatics tools for identification and comparison of virulence factors

A literature search revealed a diverse array of tools to identify virulence genes in bacterial assemblies, of which a subset was selected as possible candidates (VFanalyzer, PathoFact, BrucellaBase, PathogenFinder, and ABRicate), and only one widely used virulence gene database, namely VFDB (<http://www.mgc.ac.cn/VFs/main.htm>). This database contains detailed information on a core set of 3,620 genes linked to virulence and a non-redundant set of 32,903 genes. It is linked to their webtool VFanalyzer, this tool was tested and could detect 49 virulence genes in the set of *Brucella* bacteria. However, similar species with different assembly qualities would sometimes end up having different numbers of genes, the input menu over-complicates the process and it only searches on the protein level, meaning that most assemblies need to be translated first.

PathoFact (Nies et al. 2021) is a recently developed tool to detect virulence factors, toxin genes, AMR, plasmids and phages. It uses both HMM profiles as well as random forest classifiers to detect virulence genes. Unfortunately, the output only display whether a self-annotated gene is virulent, but does not give any info about where this match was based on or annotation of the specific gene. Furthermore, it seems to classify more than half of all *Brucella* genes as at least potential virulence factors (e.g. 1832/3152 of *B. melitensis* GCF000007125.1 and 1828/3219 of *B. ovis* GCF000016845.1). This seems to be a bit of an overestimation and considering the small difference between *B. ovis* and *B. melitensis* also leaves little room to use this output for classification of zoonotic potential.

Table 2: PathogenFinder output summary of NCBI assemblies.

<i>Species</i>	<i>ID</i>	<i>Predicted zoonotic potential</i>	<i>Pathogenic Families Matched</i>	<i>Non-Pathogenic Families Matched</i>	<i>The organisms is predicted as human pathogenic</i>
B.melitensis	GCF000007125.1	high	972	74	Yes
B.abortus	GCF000054005.1	moderate	1022	62	Yes
B.suis	GCF000007505.1	moderate	1016	46	Yes
B.canis	GCF000018525.1	mild	1020	48	Yes
B.pinnipedialis	GCF000740275.1	mild	865	49	Yes
B.ceti	GCF000590795.1	mild	701	31	Yes
B.microti	GCF000022745.1	no reported infections	1026	55	Yes
B.neotomae	GCF900446125.1	mild	673	43	Yes
B.ovis	GCF000016845.1	no reported infections	509	33	Yes

BrucellaBase (Sankarasubramanian et al. 2016) seemed promising on paper, as it was dedicated to *Brucella* spp. alone. Regrettably, this service seems to be discontinued as the server is no longer available (<http://www.dbtbrucellosis.in/brucellabase.html>).

For PathogenFinder (Cosentino et al. 2013) the builders created a database of genes that are linked to known pathogenic bacteria and a set of genes linked to non-pathogenic bacteria based on which genes could be found exclusively in either sets. This web tool can be run on an assembly and puts out the amount of hits to both sets (Table 2). These results largely matched the expected differences in pathogenicity and it is possible to find back the underlying matches. However, no stand-alone version is available making it difficult to integrate into a pipeline.

Last, we looked into ABRicate (<https://github.com/tseemann/abricate>) this is a tool that can assist in blasting assemblies to databases, under which also VFDB, producing easy usable output in the form of a presence absence matrix. With this tool we could blast our test assemblies to the VFDB database as with VFAnalyzer only now on nucleotide level, which gave more robust results over different assembly levels. Surprisingly, it found a max of 43 genes instead of the 49 that VFAnalyzer found. And the selective power between zoonotic and non-zoonotic is quite small with this select set of genes.

WP5-T1-ST3 Creation of an automatic/semi-automatic pipeline for virulence assessment of novel isolates based on their genomes

We decided to make a pipeline on the basis of ABRicate. This package also includes the option to build a custom database. In this way we can add the genes that VFAnalyzer found extra and include 10 other potential *Brucella* spp. virulence genes selected in a recent paper on virulence factors in *B. melitensis* (Rabinowitz et al. 2021) to the core VFDB set. Due to delays during the building of the database and the necessity to build our own database for the pipeline, this task is slightly delayed by approximately two months and will thus most likely be completed in February 2022.

WP5-T2

WP5-T2-ST1 Assembly of macrophage cell lines collection derived from human and animals

A table has been created and put on the SharePoint WP5 folder in which all participating consortium members can add their cell collections. Until now, three partners have filled out which relevant cell lines are in their collections. Besides, WBVR has ordered cell lines that are used in the in vitro infection assays: A dog macrophage cell line (DH82), a human monocyte cell line (THP1) and a human

trophoblast cell line (HTR8-SVneo). These cell lines have arrived and have been cultured successfully. This task is completed, although it is possible that more participating partners will fill out the table on the SharePoint .

WP5-T2-ST2 Development of in vitro infection protocol

For the optimization and development of an *in vitro* infection protocol several infection experiments have been performed with different cell lines, including macrophages from animal origin and human cell lines. Besides, five different *Brucella* species with different zoonotic potential were used in order to standardize the protocol and optimize parameters like MOI, time of incubation etc. Readout parameters include CFU count and PCR to quantify the infection rate. *Brucella* species will be exchanged from ANSES to WBVR for the next Subtask 5.3. The developed protocols will be shared by putting the SOPs on the SharePoint, so participating partners can use these protocols for the next milestone. This task was completed at the end of 2021.

WP5-T2-ST3 Harmonization of analytical methods for investigation of pathogen – host-cell cross talk

The deadline of this project is in April 2022. In vitro protocols have now been created so the investigation of pathogen – host cell cross talk can start in January 2022.

WP6 Development of a toolkit for emerging Brucellosis infections

Since this Work package depends on results and final conclusions provided by previous five WPs, the strategy and choice of methods has been left for consortium's decision during the annual Workshop which will take place in March 2022.

WP7 Coordination, management and communication

WP7-T1 Management, integration and delivery of the project, coordination and effective reporting and communications between project partners

The project partners organize regular monthly meeting where the results, problems and further steps of each WP are discussed. WP leaders and deputies make sure that all milestones and deliverables have been met, and with the project coordinators prepare reports, scientific and public communications. When necessary, additional WP meetings are organized (this year 12 in total) where specific issues which need more research or confidentiality are discussed. Because of ongoing pandemic, all meetings are organized online. This year, one training session, financed by OHEJP mobility grants, has been organized at ANSES for one partner institution in order to assure proper treatment of samples and analyses for this project as well as for their needs of National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis in their respective country.

In collaboration with COHESIVE project in May 2021 the first *B. canis* workshop was organized. More than 70 people from the whole world participated in identifying this bacteria as a new potential threat. It was decided that major initiative is necessary to curtail the outbreaks that started happening in Europe since 2020. The members of two OHEJP projects volunteered to write up the Whitepaper on threats the *B. canis* represent for public health and animal welfare in Europe. Since then the regular two months meetings have been organized (video conferences only). Final version of the White paper is expected to be finished in the first part of 2022.

WP7-T2 A data management plan

Data management plan has evolved with the needs of the project. Mainly the documents, data bases are up to date. There are several documents, specifically for WP3 and WP4 which will be discussed first among the partners and added as soon as possible.

WP7-T3 Milestones management

Necessary changes in order to deliver milestones on time as well as delays and problems in achieving them are reported in advance or during monthly meetings by work package leaders and/or deputies. Modifications to the project made possible by newly available materials and techniques are discussed among all partners, evaluated and, if considered appropriate, implemented in a coordinated manner. All possible changes are made with the emphasis on developments in perceived threats and newly published work appearing in the literature.

WP7-T4 Toolkit components communication

Since the work on final components of the toolkit has not started yet, this task will be performed accordingly in real time during Y5 – 2022.

3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
17	D-JRP17-WP1.Del1	Creation of a common database to share information about emerging <i>Brucella</i> and reservoirs among the consortium partners	M31	M33		Public: OHEJP_JRP17_IDEMBRU_Data_management_datasheet Zenodo https://zenodo.org/record/4572555#.YUC5OzhDtN0	4
17	D-JRP17-WP2.Del1	Set-up of a human Brucellosis network	M42	M38		Public: OHEJP_JRP-17_IDEMBRU_Work_package_2_Deliverable_1 Zenodo https://zenodo.org/record/4569910#.YUC5RjhDtM1 Brucella canis workshop Zenodo	5

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
17	D-JRP17- WP3.Del1	Standard operating procedures for the extraction of <i>Brucella</i> DNA from complex matrices	M42		M49	The WP3 leaders (APHA) have experienced a number of delays to the completion of this deliverable, which relies to a significant degree on the distribution of strains to partner institutes. These arise from the on-going impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic at the work-package lead institute (APHA), as well as other local factors, such as staff availability. A revised work-plan has been established, which allowed the deliverable to be completed by December 2021. Final reports are being validated by consortium members	

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8)</i> <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
						and will soon be published on Zenodo	
17	D-JRP17-WP3.Del2	Harmonised whole genome sequencing and bioinformatic protocols	M42		M48	The WP3 leaders (APHA) have experienced a number of delays to the completion of this deliverable, which relies to a significant degree on the distribution of strains to partner institutes. These arise from the on-going impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic at the work-package lead institute (APHA), as well as other local factors, such as staff availability. A revised work-plan has been established, which allowed the deliverable to be completed by December 2021.	

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						Final reports are being validated by consortium members and will soon be published on Zenodo	
17	D-JRP17-WP5.Del1	Bioinformatics pipeline for detection and classification of <i>Brucella</i> virulence factors in context of zoonotic potential	M48		M50	A delay of 2 M is expected for finishing the pipeline. This is mainly due to a delay in the creation of a genome database (M17): we wanted to include <i>Brucella</i> 's that were sequenced within the project to make a representative dataset. No new strains have yet been identified, and therefore, assemblies of recently sequenced reference strains present in local collections have been included. The	

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
						quality of the assembly impacts the settings of the bioinformatic tools significantly, and the integration of this variable takes 2 months additional time.	
17	D-JRP17-WP6.Del1	Review of toolkits for infectious diseases	M48		M51	Several toolkits have been presented during the last years workshop. During the annual workshop in March, consortium will do the final revision and decide on strategies, based on available toolkits for infectious diseases and validated results of five previous Work Packages.	
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del1	First draft of data management plan	M36	M40			8

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del2	Creation of a data sharing common platform	M48	M48		Confidential A part of ANSES server has been opened for the members of IDEMBRU consortium. This will serve to store large data files – DNA sequences, data bases, epidemiological questionnaires and results provided by WP3, WP4, and WP5. The data storage space is divided according to the workpackage needs. All data have been stripped of any identifications, both personal identifiers or institutuinal.	4
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del3	Final draft of data management plan	M36	M40		Sent to OH EJP for publication	8
17	D-JRP17-WP7.Del4	Report of the first annual workshop	M40	M42	M42	Public:	8

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		including exchanges between partners and inputs from external stakeholders				One Health EJP JRP17 WP7, Del4 Annual Workshop Report Zenodo https://zenodo.org/record/5389832#.YUC5fDhDtM1	

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
17	M-JRP17-M2	Conference call of the steering committee regrouping WP leaders + deputy leaders on data management	M42	M34		
17	M-JRP17-M3	Definition of type of data generated for each WP and structure of the data sharing platform	M36	M34		
17	M-JRP17-M4	Conference call of the steering committee regrouping WP leaders and deputy leaders	N/A	M34		
17	M-JRP17-M5	Creation of an epidemiological questionnaire	M37	M36		
17	M-JRP17-M6	Information on worldwide emerging <i>Brucellae</i> (shared database)	M34	M33		
17	M-JRP17-M7	Definition of sampling and testing protocols (molecular, bacteriology and serology)	M36	M42		
17	M-JRP17-M8	Definition of sampling and testing protocols (serology, bacteriology and molecular biology)	M38	M41		

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
17	M-JRP17-M9	Drafted RNASeq protocols to identify regulatory differences between classical species and emerging <i>Brucella</i> strains	M40	M36		
17	M-JRP17-M10	Definition of the programme of the annual workshop	N/A	M36		
17	M-JRP17-M11	Organisation of accommodation and logistic aspects	N/A	N/A		
17	M-JRP19-M12	Implementation of first annual workshop	M38	M40		
17	M-JRP17-M14	Choice of the informatic system to implement the notification system	M38	M40		
17	M-JRP17-M15	Harmonisation of protocols for whole genome sequencing	M35	M48		The WP3 leader (APHA) has experienced a number of delays to the completion of this deliverable, which relies to a significant degree on the distribution of strains to partner institutes. These arise from the on-going impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic at the work-package lead institute (APHA), as well as other local factors, such as staff availability. Therefore, the milestone was completed at M48.

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
17	M-JRP17-M16	Optimised protocols for the extraction of <i>Brucella</i> DNA from complex matrices	M42	M48		The WP3 leader (APHA) has experienced a number of delays to the completion of this deliverable, which relies to a significant degree on the distribution of strains to partner institutes. These arise from the on-going impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic at the work-package lead institute (APHA), as well as other local factors, such as staff availability. Therefore, the milestone was completed at M48.
17	M-JRP17-M17	Creation of <i>Brucella</i> genomes database from publicly available and emerging isolates (WP 2)	44	M44		
17	M-JRP17-M18	Conference call of the steering committee regrouping WP leaders and deputy leaders	42	M42		
17	M-JRP17-M19	Characterisation of serological responses and identification of isolated emerging <i>Brucella</i> species	46		56	So far few strains have been isolated from any samples and project has to rely on existing collections. Secondly, the blood or sera is not the tissue usually collected from wildlife and is especially difficult to obtain outside the hunting season. Therefore, the scarcity of the available sera alone postponed this milestone. Secondly,

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
						the already the numbers of secondary antibodies or kits validated for wild animals is very low. With the ongoing pandemic situation, their availability is impeded and sometimes the waiting time is counted in months.
17	M-JRP17-M20	Characterisation of serological responses and identification of isolated emerging <i>Brucella</i> species	46		56	Currently there are no means to distinguish between classical and atypical <i>Brucella</i> infections based on human serology alone. Moreover, certain non clinical infections go undetected as the strains at hand do not represent <i>Brucella</i> like epitopes. Recently isolated <i>Brucella</i> strain which has no classical immunogenic determinants (but has been characterized by classical bacteriological and molecular methods as <i>Brucella</i> spp.) provides a chance for development of more precise and robust serological test which will be validated by our partners from human medical laboratories.
17	M-JRP17-M21	Selection of bioinformatics tools for identification and comparison of virulence factors	46	47		

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
17	M-JRP17-M22	Assembly of macrophage cell lines collection derived from human and animals	46	48		
17	M-JRP17-M23	Definition of the programme of the annual workshop	44	M49		
17	M-JRP17-M24	Creation of an automatic/semi-automatic pipeline for virulence assessment of novel isolates based on their genomes	48		56	A delay of 2 M is expected for finishing the pipeline. This is mainly due to a delay in the creation of a genome database (M17): we wanted to include <i>Brucella's</i> that were sequenced within the project to make a representative dataset. No new strains have yet been identified, and therefore, assemblies of recently sequenced reference strains present in local collections have been included. The quality of the assembly impacts the settings of the bioinformatic tools significantly, and the integration of this variable takes 2 months additional time.
17	M-JRP17-M25	Development of in vitro infection protocol	48	49		
17	M-JRP17-M26	Organisation of accommodation and	46	49		

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
		logistic aspects				
17	M-JRP17-M27	List of toolkits available from previous experience	47		51	Several toolkits have been presented during the last years workshop. During the annual workshop in March, consortium will do the final revision and decide on strategies, based on available toolkits for infectious diseases and validated results of five previous Work Packages.
17	M-JRP17-M28	Literature reviewing	47			
17	M-JRP17-M32	Implementation of 2nd annual workshop	48			
17	M-JRP17-M33	Mailing list of people / institutes receiving notifications	48			

4. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
The use of flocked swab with protective media increases the recovery of live <i>Brucella</i> spp. and DNA detection. Microbiol Spectr. 2021 Dec 22;9(3):e0072821. doi: 10.1128/Spectrum.00728-21. Epub 2021 Nov 17.	Yes		Luca Freddi, Vitomir Djokic, Fathia Petot-Bottin, Guillaume Girault, Ludivine Perrot, Acacia Ferreira Vicente, Claire Ponsart

Additional output

International Brucellosis conference – Chicago Dec 2021:

Brucella spp and *Ochrobactrum* spp DNA in French foxes, wild boars and deer. V. Djokic, G. Girault, L. Freddi, L. Perrot, L. Laboutiere, A.Ferreira Vicente, M. Ribeiro, F. Petot-Bottin, C. Ponsart.

Comparison of five serological methods in non-infected, suspect, exposed and brucellosis infected dogs: impacts on diagnostic strategies. A.F. Vicente, V. Djokic, M. Ribeiro, F. Petot-Bottin, L. Perrot, L. Laboutiere, L. Freddi, G. Girault, C. Ponsart.

OHEJP Annual conference:

Natural habitats for detection of emerging *Brucella* species: a new strategy to identify putative threats (IDEMBRU) Ponsart Clairea, Ferreira A.C.i, Daskalov H.d, Garofolo G.e, Melzer F.f, Freddi L.a, Girault G.a, Ferreira Vicente A.a, Ashford R.c, Whatmore A.c, Al Dahouk S.b, Prasse D.b, Kydyshov K.f, Cavaco Gonçalves S.i, De Massis F.e, Sacchini F.e, Milanov M.d, Pelerito A.h, van den Esker M.h, Kampfraath D.h, Djokic Vitomir

Molecular detection and differentiation within Brucellaceae family in urban and rural wildlife. Djokic Vitomir, Michelet Lorraine, Girault Guillaume, Lecu Alexis, Freddi Luca, Ferreira Vincente Acacia¹, Perrot Ludivine, Laboutiere Lisa, Boschiroli Maria Laura, Ponsart Claire

An innovative microfluidic qPCR platform for high throughput testing of *Brucella* sp. and *Ochrobactrum* in environmental samples. Guillaume Girault, Vitomir Djokic, Luca Freddi, Acacia Ferreira Vicente, Sabine Delannoy, Patrick Fach and Claire Ponsart

Outcomes

New developed methods and protocols will be shared and used by the MS reference laboratories involved in brucellosis surveillance and diagnostics. The toolkit will be available on the EU reference laboratory website, leading to a wide dissemination among stakeholders. The link to the toolkit will be also shared with FAO/OIE networks.

5. *Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries*

Fol ECDC - EFSA Charter on Brucellosis – *Brucella* (Epidemiological survey of the Brucellosis cases in Europe) [The European Union One Health 2020 Zoonoses Report \(europa.eu\)](http://The European Union One Health 2020 Zoonoses Report (europa.eu))

6. *List of critical risks*

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe) – parental leaves of several consortium members	Yes

Additional information

Delays appeared principally from COVID-19 situation, but also from new developments with *Brucella canis* emergence and spread in Europe. Work package 3 tasks have been done with the proposed delay of six months, while other Work packages advance more or less on the schedule. The new developments, realisation that there are no available tests for rough *Brucellae* in humans and discovery of a new strain that has no known *Brucella* antigens urges us to reconsider human part of One health concept and develop more in that direction in order to provide more comursome results.

Certain delays appeard because of COVID-19 infections and parental leaves key partners had to take. These delays have been minimalised by communication between partners, regular meetings and the fact that each work package has leader and deputy who can step in and fill in the gaps specifically with project coordinators.

JRP18-ET1.1-MEmE

1. Summary of the work carried out in year 4

MEmE is an international multicentre collaborative project that aims to fill research gaps highlighted by international agencies for the detection and control of zoonotic parasites *Echinococcus multilocularis* (Em) and *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* (Eg), causing alveolar echinococcosis (AE) and cystic echinococcosis (CE), respectively. MEmE focuses on standardization, harmonization and validation of existing parasitological and molecular methods, and the development and comparative assessment of innovative molecular tools to detect Em and Eg in the food chain. Production of epidemiological data on the presence of Em/Eg eggs in the food chain focuses on vegetables for human consumption and on canine faeces in selected endemic countries. MEmE provides a comprehensive set of integrative activities to harmonize procedures, improve the detection and produce epidemiological data on potential pathways of transmission of Em and Eg.

MEmE current achievements:

- Production of Standard Operating Procedures and sampling of different matrices from naturally or experimentally infected definitive and intermediate animal hosts.
- Validation of the parasitological (Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique, SSCT) and molecular diagnostic (multiplex-PCRs and MC-RT-PCR assay) procedures to detect Em and Eg in different matrices along the food chain.
- Publications on the development and validation of new tools: a) Comparison of two DNA extraction methods and two PCRs for the detection of Em in stool samples; b) Bayesian Analysis of three methods for diagnosis of CE in sheep; c) Microsatellite investigations of Eg cysts; d) Species detection of Eg by novel probe-based real-time PCRs; e) Validated method based on PCR-RFLP and multiplex PCR assay for the identification of Eg species; f) Identification of Eg G1/G3 by SNPs assays.
- Ongoing multicentre studies for the production of data relevant for epidemiological assessments (contamination of vegetables for human consumption by eggs of Em/Eg; prevalence of Em/Eg in dog faeces).
- Dissemination of project results at different levels (general public, scientific community, experts, health authorities and media).

MEmE scientific papers published on peer-review journals:

- [Morphological Characteristics of Alveolar and Cystic Echinococcosis Lesions in Human Liver and Bone](#). *Pathogens*. 2021;10(10):1326.
- [New global targets for NTDs in the WHO roadmap 2021–2030](#). *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*.

- 2021;15(5):e0009373.
- [Identification of *Echinococcus granulosus* genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs genotyping assays.](#) *Pathogens*. 2021;10(2):125.
 - [Molecular analysis suggests that Namibian cheetahs \(*Acinonyx jubatus*\) are definitive hosts of a so far undescribed *Besnoitia* species.](#) *Parasit Vectors*. 2021;14(1):201.
 - [Comparison of two DNA extraction methods and two PCRs for detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in the stool samples of naturally Infected red foxes.](#) *Animals (Basel)*. 2020;10(12):2381.
 - [Cystic echinococcosis: clinical, immunological, and biomolecular evaluation of patients from Sardinia \(Italy\).](#) *Pathogens*. 2020;9(6):907.
 - [A validated method to identify *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* at species level.](#) *Infection, Genetics and Evolution*. 2020;85:104575.
 - [Bayesian analysis of three methods for diagnosis of cystic echinococcosis in sheep.](#) *Pathogens*. 2020;9(10):796.
 - [Species detection within the *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* complex by novel probe-based real-time PCRs.](#) *Pathogens*. 2020;9(10):791.
 - [Microsatellite investigations of multiple *Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto* cysts in single hosts reveal different patterns of infection events between livestock and humans.](#) *Pathogens*. 2020;9(6):444.
 - [Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis.](#) *The Lancet Global Health*. 2020;8(4):e470-e471.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1. Sampling strategy

WP1-T1. SOPs for sampling in matrices

The following Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) were generated:

- Sampling of faecal material in dog faeces collected from the environment (WP1-T2) and their processing for molecular analysis.
- Sampling of *E. granulosus* cysts from naturally infected sheep and pigs at abattoirs (WP1-T2) and experimentally infected sheep (WP1-T3) and their processing for molecular analyses.
- Sampling of faeces and small/large intestines from experimentally infected foxes (WP1-T3) and their processing for parasitological and molecular analyses.
- Sampling of vegetables for human consumption (WP3-T6) and their processing for molecular analysis.

Task accomplished.

WP1-T2. Matrices collection in the field from intermediate and definitive hosts

The aim of this task was to collect different parasitic matrices from naturally infected definitive and intermediate hosts for their use in other WPs. Involved participants organized sampling from definitive and intermediate animal hosts. Totally, 590 intestines of red foxes, 181 intestines of arctic foxes, 100 intestines of raccoon dogs from endemic areas were collected; most of them were examined with SCT/SSCT. From positive intestines, Em worms were isolated. Intestines and isolated worms will be used for tasks connected with new PCRs and SSCT validation, and PTs organization. Additionally, faeces from distal part of large intestine were collected. A total of 63 red fox intestines from areas supposed to be free of Em were collected and 300 intestines of red foxes from Em free areas (Ireland) were collected. Other parasites (*Mesocestoides* spp., *Taenia* spp.) were isolated from the intestines of red foxes for specificity controls. A total of 210 samples of pigs' livers and 200 sheep's livers with suggestive

lesions of *Echinococcus* spp. larvae were collected and prepared for identification. Additionally, few *Em* and *Taenia hydatigena* lesions isolated from *Arvicola terrestris* and *Eg* cysts isolated from sheep and pigs were collected. A total of 70 sibling voles were examined for *Em* with only one showing parasitic liver cysts (probably *Taenia* spp). A total of 1,304 faecal samples from dogs for epidemiological study were collected. Additionally, hundreds of dog faecal samples from environment were collected as a potential matrix for validation. Task accomplished.

WP1-T3. Matrices collection from experimental animal models

Concerning the fox model, four infections were realized with two foxes euthanized and the two others were dewormed after 90 dpi. Worms (training on SSCT, WP4-T1), eggs (lettuce investigations, WP3-T6) and faeces were obtained. Interruptions due to COVID-19 disrupted the production of protoscoleces in the mouse model currently delaying the possibility of infecting foxes. The experimental material currently available consists of 5,000 *Em* eggs, 50 faeces and 100 microtubes of frozen protoscoleces. Ethical authorisation on "Experimental infection of carnivores with *Echinococcus multilocularis*" (Decree n° 21_105#33541 November 16 2021, APAFIS #33541-202110081648536 v11) has been renewed for five years.

Task accomplished.

WP2. Validation of parasitological and molecular assays

WP2-T1. Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique, SSCT

Among the 603 red and arctic fox intestines collected by five partners (NVI, PIWET, FLI, ANSES and BIOR), 568 were independently analysed for each of the four segments of intestines resulting in 139 positive samples. The remaining 35 red fox intestines collected by FLI will be analysed in February 2022 (M50) with the aim of obtaining more positive intestines for the estimate of the sensitivity of SSCT method. The protocol of validation for SSCT was also applied to raccoon dogs from Poland and Latvia in order to determine a potential combination of a pair of segments which may result in a high sensitivity of the method. Among 70 racoon dog intestines which were analysed, five were infected by *Em*. Data from racoon dogs will be combined with those from experimental results previously obtained in red foxes.

Task almost accomplished.

WP2-T2. Comparison of multiplex PCRs

This task focused on the validation of two molecular assays widely used for the detection of *Echinococcus* spp. in definitive and intermediate hosts, targeting mitochondrial and nuclear markers:

- Assay 1: Boubaker et al. (PLoS Negl Trop Dis, 2013): a single-tube multiplex PCR allowing discrimination of *Echinococcus* at species/genotypes level.
- Assay 2: Trachsel et al. (Parasitology, 2007): a single-tube multiplex PCR targeting the definitive host for the identification of eggs belonging to *Eg*, *Em* and *Taenia* genus.

Assay 1. Validation process was developed as follows: first, a collection of reference parasitic material (worms, cysts and genomic DNA), provided by the [WHO Collaborating Centre for the Epidemiology, Detection and Control of Cystic and Alveolar Echinococcosis](#) (Rome, Italy), was selected for the experiments. The collection included at least two or more parasitic materials for each species of the *Eg* complex, for *Em* and for members of genus *Taenia* (*T. saginata*, *T. hydatigena* and *T. multiceps*). As validating requirements, results were considered valid when they resulted in an unequivocal species identification and were confirmed by three independent repeated experiments performed by two different technicians. Once experiment conditions were settled, the analytical sensitivity of the assay have been evaluated testing serial dilution of reference DNA. The assay was initially carried out with the original conditions described by the authors, resulting in the lack of six over 11 PCR targets needed for proper species identification. Thus, results were evaluated again under several modified conditions

(i.e. using equimolar primer mix, running a gradient PCR to identify a better annealing temperature, testing different Taq polymerases, increasing reaction volumes and annealing time). Last, single primer pairs were tested independently to evaluate their performance and, when their working conditions were found proper, they were combined with other primer pairs to achieve a balanced amplification. In conclusion, lack of specific PCR bands or the appearance of aspecific PCR bands made impossible to execute the multiplex PCR and to get simultaneously all the targeted markers amplified, neither with the original conditions nor with the modifications tried. The high number of PCR markers targeted (n=11) by Assay 1 probably had a negative impact on the overall performance of this method.

Assay 2. The original paper describes a Multiplex PCR, which amplifies fragments of different sizes of DNA encoding portions of the mitochondrial genes (Subunit I of NADH dehydrogenase (ND1) for Em (PCR fragment 395 bp), and portions of ribosomal genes, subunit *rrnS* for Eg complex (117 bp), *Taenia* spp. (267 bp) and *Diphyllobotrium* spp. (267 bp). The original multiplex PCR was developed to identify eggs of the taeniid tapeworms from carnivores. In this validation process genomic DNA extracted from worms (Em and *Taenia* spp.) and cyst material (Eg) served as template for the multiplex PCR assay.

The validation process was developed as reported in assay 1. First, a collection of reference DNA, provided by the [WHO Collaborating Centre for the Epidemiology, Detection and Control of Cystic and Alveolar Echinococcosis](#) (Rome, Italy), was selected for the experiments. The collection included DNA for the species of Eg, Em and members of genus *Taenia* (*T. saginata*, *T. hydatigena* and *T. multiceps*, *T. polyacanta*, *T. hydatigena*, *Diphyllobotrium latum* and *Diphyllobotrium dendriticum*). As validating requirements, results were considered valid when they were specific (unequivocal species identification) and confirmed by three independent repeated experiments performed by two different technicians. Once experiment conditions were settled, the analytical sensitivity of the assay has been evaluated testing serial dilution of reference DNA. The multiplex-PCR was initially carried out with the original conditions described by the authors. Gel electrophoresis resulted in the following results: Em amplicon showed the characteristic band of *Taenia* (267 bp), *Taenia* spp. amplicon always showed a non-specific band (around 200 bp), and the amplicon of Eg was often weak. Mixed infections were excluded by the nature of the matrices used, therefore the results were evaluated again under several modified conditions (i.e. using equimolar primer mix, running a gradient PCR to identify a better annealing temperature, testing different Taq polymerases, increasing reaction volumes and annealing time). After several tests, the concentration of the primers was changed to an equimolar primer mix (final concentration 0.2 μ M), which resulted in a correct identification of all species. Expanding the number of Em DNA tested (n=82) from different countries it was observed that 10 out of 82 samples showed the typical band of Em but also a light band typical of Eg (117 bp).

In conclusion, the single-tube multiplex PCR by Trachsel and colleagues (2007) has been proved to be a robust and reliable assay that can be used not only for the identification of taeniid eggs but extended to DNA extracted from different matrices. Nonetheless, problems with specificity of the PCR products can be eventually observed and the optimization of the primer concentration must be achieved. In this validation process an equimolar (0.2 μ M) primer mix showed the highest efficiency for the PCR reaction. Task accomplished.

WP2-T3. Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay

Two magnetic capture protocols, published by Isaksson et al., 2014 (10.1186/s13071-014-0583-6), and Maas et al., 2016 (10.1016/j.vetpar.2016.10.016), respectively, were performed in parallel in two laboratories (FLI and RIVM) using the artificially spiked fox faecal samples. The reproducibility of the methods and their analytical sensitivity were tested and compared in the two laboratories. In addition, these two methods were tested with a set of field faecal samples from foxes naturally infected with Em. Thus, diagnostic sensitivity of the two methods was also tested and compared. The data obtained are currently being analysed and written up in a manuscript.

SOP for validation of Magnetic capture – real-time PCR assay. There was a delay with the milestone in this task and the lead on the task was transferred from SVA (SVA withdrew from MEME in 2021) to NVI in M37. The methods (DNA extraction with automatic washing and manual washing protocols, as well

as three real-time PCR protocols) and accompanying training video (for magnetic capture DNA extraction with manual washing) were published on Zenodo as project restricted technical notes in M42 (DOIs: 10.5281/zenodo.4897969; 10.5281/zenodo.4746190; 10.5281/zenodo.4746181; 10.5281/zenodo.4746141). If needed additional guidance, via digital meeting platforms, has been offered to the seven laboratories (BIOR, CVRL, INIAV, ISS, PIWET, SSI and VFL) that have registered for the training. So far, only one has requested this. The verification and ring test material has been distributed to all partners that have registered for participation in the ring test (FLI, INIAV, ISS, NVI, SSI and RIVM). So far only one of the partners has provided their ring test results whilst three others have requested a delay to reporting due to supply chain issues for the reagents used or request for additional training (ISS) in 2022. The ring test consists of a sample set of 10 faecal samples that have potentially been spiked with *Em* worm segments for each laboratory to analyse. This task is anticipated to be completed during the first half of 2022.

WP3. Development validation of new tools and production of data relevant for epidemiological assessments

WP3-T1. New molecular markers for *Em* and *Eg* s.l.: from rapid diagnostics to source attribution

ST1: new mitochondrial markers. Recent studies have revealed an unexpectedly high genetic diversity at mitochondrial genome level for *Eg* (*E. granulosus sensu stricto* and *E. canadensis* - genotypes G6/G7). However, these studies covered only part of the genetic diversity since many important endemic regions were missing (e.g. China and Russia). Moreover, for several species including *Em*, the mitogenomes data are scarce. In order to develop species/genotype specific diagnostic assays, additional mitogenomes data are required for all *Echinococcus* spp. using a larger worldwide panel of different *Eg* (*E. granulosus sensu stricto*) species and genotypes (n=300), and *Em* (n=200). Toehold Exchange Probes based diagnostic tool will be developed to provide a reliable and rapid identification of species/genotypes of *Eg* (*E. granulosus sensu lato*) and *Em*. The complete mitogenomes of 48 samples of the *Eg* genotypes G6/G7 from various countries of the World were sequenced. These sequences will be included to the total dataset of mitogenomes.

ST2: New microsatellite markers. The screening of the *Eg* genome resulted in the identification of 15 new microsatellites targets, which are currently evaluated for their polymorphism, reproducibility, limit of detection, quality of the electrophoretic profiles and their specificity. The selected targets will be coupled with *EgSca6* microsatellite previously described by MEmE (M'Rad et al., 2020) in order to obtain a panel with a high discriminatory power. The possibility to use these microsatellites for large phylogenetic studies was initiated for the validation of the clustering method. *Eg* DNA samples from North Africa (Morocco and Tunisia) and Europe (France and Moldova) were collected and testing of microsatellites polymorphism is ongoing. Four new microsatellite targets were identified and are currently under evaluation.

ST3: NGS-based method. The very high variability of *Eg* (*E. granulosus sensu stricto*) at the mitogenome level provides a possibility to perform source attribution analysis. Using the mitogenome data together with microsatellite fingerprinting may constitute reliable means to track the source of infection. Previous studies have shown that samples collected from the same area can be distinguished from samples from other areas based on complete or near-complete mitogenome data. At first, a method will be developed to sequence 96 mitogenomes with a single sequencing run. For this, we have already developed primers that enable PCR-amplification of the entire mitogenome in a single PCR. We aim to use 96 different barcodes and the PacBio's Single Molecule, Real-Time (SMRT) Sequencing in the Sequel System, which allows easy and cost effective generation of highly accurate long reads (>99% single-molecule read accuracy) for DNA amplicons, such as the complete mitochondrial genomes. However, this assay requires samples of good quality. As the quality of parasite samples varies and often important samples are of low quality, we started to develop primers for such samples that consists of several primer pairs. Testing of these primers is in progress and task will be accomplished in due time.

WP3-T2. New multiplex TaqMan qPCR for detection and genotyping of Eg s.l. and Em

We established six TaqMan[®] probe-based qPCRs that can be used for the diagnosis of Em and Eg genotypes in five epidemiologically relevant species and subgroups, i.e. *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (G1, G3), *E. equinus* (G4), *E. ortleppi* (G5), the *E. canadensis* cluster (G6 to G8 and G10), a single genotype (G8) of the *E. canadensis* cluster as a single-step genotyping technique. It also allows differentiating Eg and Em samples from other *Echinococcus* spp. or *Taenia* spp. in samples derived from cystic or faecal material. The qPCRs show high efficiency (ranging between 99% and 106%), high analytical specificity (100%) and sensitivity (ranging between 0.6 and 1.4 copies/ μ l), when used with DNA obtained from cysts or from cloned PCR products. Therefore, they are suitable for a PCR-based diagnosis of CE in intermediate hosts, including humans as dead-end hosts. To parallelize the detection and typing of members of the Eg complex, two variants of a TaqMan[®] probe-based five-plex real-time qPCR assay were developed and validated. The first variant of these assays can simultaneously detect and genotype *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (G1, G3), *E. equinus* (G4), *E. ortleppi* (G5), and the *E. canadensis* complex (G6 to G8 and G10). The second variant of the test is capable of detecting and distinguishing *E. granulosus sensu stricto* (G1, G3), *E. ortleppi* (G5), the *E. canadensis* genotype G8, and the remaining two members of the *E. canadensis* cluster (G6 and G10). For simultaneous diagnosis and typing of Eg complex and Em infections, further variants of a TaqMan[®] probe-based multiplex real-time qPCR are currently being developed. Task accomplished.

WP3-T3. Detection of Em/Eg in complex samples: sequencing using Regions Specific Extraction (RSE) and NGS

First step was to establish a pipeline for nanopore mtDNA sequencing and to allow sufficient data generation and for testing data analysis tools. Work started using DNA from positive controls included from the MC-DNA EmNok surveillance method, as these were spiked faecal samples isolated using magnetic capture of mtDNA from Em. The processed samples contained lower number of targets compared with pure Em-controls. Having enough material to allow sequencing, in order to get nanopore protocols working, call for some modifications of the material. As an alternative enrichment step, Illustra TempliPhi, was considered as a means to generate more template DNA for nanopore sequencing. A few dilutions were carried out to accommodate for faint samples. In addition to the positive Em control from MC method, a standard prepared DNA samples from *Taenia* spp. were also included as controls. Samples were cleaned and DNA was measured. Further, they were prepared according to the selected nanopore sequence kit and some runs on Minion flongle flowcell was attempted on the products. All runs failed to generate data, and experiments were suspended until replacement chemicals arrived. As an alternative approach which would help solve the potential issue of not having enough parasite DNA molecules available in the sample to allow for full characterisation, and learning from recent method development for Sars-Cov2, a similar approach to the nanopore Midnight protocol (Freed et al., 2020) which is in use for full characterisation of virus genomes. We are exploring a similar long PCR-tiling approach for *Echinococcus* spp. mtDNA characterisation, using a panel of primers generating eight overlapping segments. This protocol will be tested on positive samples (native parasites, and fish-DNA) and PCR-optimisation and testing suitable nanopore kit protocols (ligation vs. rapid) is ongoing.

WP3-T4. Proteomic study on biomarker discovery in exosomes from animal plasma

We encounter technical difficulties regarding the proteomic study (at ISS, Italy) from plasma of experimentally infected (and controlled) sheep in Portugal (at INIAV, Portugal). Because of COVID-19, we were late in obtaining ethics committee approval at INIAV. Afterwards, in November 2020 we made two attempts with parasite protoscoleces collected from sheep in Sardinia (IZSS, Italy) to infect foxes in Nancy, France (ANSES) where ethics committee approval was also obtained for foxes. Unfortunately, in January 2021 we did not obtain Eg worms from fox experimental model (neither at flotation of faecal samples nor at PCR examination). During February/August 2021, we mobilized the international community to provide Eg eggs from experimentally or naturally infected canids. We received positive feedback from Australia, Iraqi Kurdistan, Kazakhstan and China, willing to collect and subsequently

provide eggs. National lockdowns and national restrictions due to COVID-19 affected such field-collaboration since all these participants have retired. These eggs would have been used to infect sheep (animals are still housed in Portugal) and collect plasma for proteomic analyses searching for biomarkers of infection. We also discussed to modify ethical clearance at INIAV and try to infect sheep with Eg protoscoleces, instead of Em egg. Since intraperitoneal injection of protoscoleces does not mimic natural infection, this may affect molecular pathways and therefore proteomic analysis outcome. Even if we found another solution, there would be no time to implement it before the end of MEmE because of the long time (at least 1 year) it takes for the parasite to develop in sheep. We confirm that COVID-19-pandemic has definitively discontinued task 4 of WP3. To replace this activity, a new subtask was inserted in WP3: “Contamination of berries for human consumption by Em/Eg” (WP3-T6-ST2).

WP3-T5. Assessment of newly developed molecular methods against the existing techniques

The different molecular methods developed in MEmE (RFLP and qPCR for Eg; see MEmE publications) will be compared with already available methods regarding limit of detection of each assay but also by evaluating sensitivity and specificity using DNA samples obtained from field samples but also from experimental infection. Furthermore, faecal samples obtained during SSCT will be used to be compared with results obtained by processing the available Em copro-qPCR. This evaluation will be realized using the same DNA samples in different laboratories. Task will be accomplished in due time.

WP3-T6. Contamination of vegetables for human consumption by Em/Eg

The filtration method (Guggisberg et al., 2020) combined with real-time PCR in lettuces was validated at ANSES with 95% probability of detection for three Em eggs (75% probability of detection for two eggs and 50% for one egg). A first survey conducted in 2020 in France collected 106 lettuce samples (grouped in 35 pooled samples; each pool constituted from two to five lettuces from the same geographical origin). Seventeen pooled samples were from private kitchen gardens (n=44), while 18 from local markets (n=62). Em was detected in two pooled samples from local markets and one from kitchen gardens. Hydatigera spp. (cat tapeworm) was detected in four and two pooled samples from kitchen gardens and local markets, respectively. In the summer of 2021, a survey was conducted in Europe, including 15 MEmE partners from 12 endemic countries for Em and/or Eg. Around 1,200 lettuce samples were collected from local markets and supermarkets with around 50/100 lettuces collected by each partner which realized the first washing step of the filtration method. In order to minimize bias, these frozen pellets were sent to ANSES where filtration and molecular detection methods are undergoing. One Em positive pooled sample out of 60 tested (n=120 lettuces) was identified in France, one positive pooled sample out of 44 (n=88 lettuces) was identified in Switzerland and two positive pooled samples out of 25 were identified in Denmark (n=50 lettuces). No positive Em samples were detected in pooled samples from Portugal (n=100 lettuces), Germany (n=62 lettuces) and The Netherlands (n=6 lettuces). A new additional subtask on the detection of Echinococcus spp. eggs in strawberries and blueberries was inserted in MEmE (WP3-T6-ST2). The filtration method was validated on strawberries with 95% probability of detection of three eggs in 200g sample (88% probability of detection for both two and one egg) and will be validated for blueberries in 2022. A survey started in France in 2021 with 34 samples of strawberries collected from local markets, which resulted negative to Em. This study is planned to be extended in 2022 by including samples of blueberries from other countries. Task will be accomplished in due time.

WP3-T7. Prevalence of Em/Eg in dog (faecal samples) from selected geographical areas

Eight MEmE partners were involved in this task (one of them left the task because of COVID-19 pandemic). Until now 1,304 samples of dog faeces were collected, most of them together with filled questionnaires. About 380 more samples are planned to be collected before the end of this study. DNA was extracted from 1,056 samples. Overall, 355 samples have already been examined in France, Italy, Poland using multiplex PCR (Trachsel et al., 2007) and no Echinococcus spp. positive were detected. In France, 1 Taenia krabbei, 1 Taenia serialis and 1 Mesocestoides spp. positive samples were recorded.

In Italy, 60 samples were additionally examined with the new qPCRs (Maksimov et al., 2020) for Eg complex developed within MEmE framework; 15% positive results were obtained. Additionally, in France, 109 samples were examined using qPCR (Knapp et al., 2016) for Em but without positive results. The expected end of the task is M54.

WP3-T8. Potential human risk factors by means of questionnaires

Due to COVID-19 impact on hospitals, we replaced this task with "Human source attribution of cerebral CE by molecular approach and its quantitative assessment in the literature". This task focuses on the first source attribution based on molecular methods of a rare case of cerebral CE in a child from Roman campagna. A literature search was also conducted on 6 databases with Boolean terms for the clinical and epidemiological quantification of cerebral CE at global level. No limitation of year of publication was envisaged. Inclusion criteria were: clinical reports including case reports, case series, clinical trials, retrospective and prospective cases of confirmed human cerebral CE. Exclusion criteria were: animal cases, AE cases and no confirmed cases of cerebral CE. The search identified 1,776 relevant articles which were selected by title and abstract. Relevant data from full text of 422 papers were currently extracted. Task will be accomplished on M54.

WP4. Training, dissemination and proficiency testing schemes

WP4-T1. Trainings

This WP focuses on establishing the most effective methods for training scientists from institutions participating to MEmE in the parasitological and molecular identification of *Echinococcus* spp. Due to COVID-19 pandemic, no physical training was conducted until now. For this reason, NVI generated online training on "Magnetic capture of *Echinococcus multilocularis* DNA from red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faecal samples: DNA extraction with manual washing steps". A training movie showing each of the steps can be viewed on YouTube at: <https://www.youtube.com/embed/hdo3mE8oMKE?rel=0>. One of the partners (ISS) has requested physical training for the magnetic capture method at NVI and this has been planned for spring/summer 2022.

WP4-T2. Dissemination of project results

This task focuses on establishing the most effective methods for disseminating project results at different levels. Due to COVID-19 pandemic non-participation to physical events prevent the dissemination, while it was done during online events ("One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021", "Annual meeting of the European Reference Laboratory for Parasites 2020" and "13th European Multicollloquium of Parasitology") and publishing scientific papers for a wide scientific audience (see papers on Lancet Global Health and PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases).

WP4-T3. Organization of selected PTs from WP2 and WP3

A Proficiency Testing scheme (PT) on "Segmental Sedimentation and Counting Technique (SSCT)" for the detection of Em was launched in October 2021 (M46). Such PT involved 12 participants from MEmE and two additional European national reference laboratories out of MEmE. The participants have received five segments of intestines (three negative and two positive) in order to perform SSCT. A discordant result was obtained by two participants (one false negative and one false positive). These results can be considered as very encouraging as any laboratory realized SSCT in routine diagnostic intestinal analysis (excepting organizer Anses) and many don't even use intestinal diagnostic as a routine method for detection in definitive host. A second PT on "Verification of *Echinococcus multilocularis* magnetic capture method in red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faeces and proficiency test" is planned and this task will be completed during the first half of 2022.

WP5. Scientific and administrative management

WP5-T1. Setup of the project

Task accomplished.

WP5-T2. Administrative and scientific management

Activities are ongoing throughout the lifespan of MEmE to accomplish its administrative and scientific management.

WP5-T3. Ethics management

All ethic needs of MEmE accomplished.

3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
18	D-JRP18-WP1.1	SOPs for sampling in matrices shared within the Consortium	M28	M31		Public https://zenodo.org/record/4455196#.YAmIsxbSKg_o	2
18	D-JRP18-WP1.2	Collection of samples in the field finalized	M36	M45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5499866#.YTsvmc_OM_zk	8
18	D-JRP18-WP1.3	Collection of samples from experimental animal model finalized	M48		M50	Small delay (1-2 mth) due to COVID-19 crisis	8
18	D-JRP18-WP2.1	Validation of SSCT	M36	M48		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5499551#.YTr8sM_OM_zk	8
18	D-JRP18-WP2.2	Validation of multiplex PCRs	M44	M49		Public	8

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						https://zenodo.org/record/5499864#.YdwvolnSKgo	
18	D-JRP18-WP2.3	Validation of Magnetic Capture Real-time PCR assay	M44	M45		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5500594#.YTusOaTOMzk	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.1	New molecular markers	M48		M54	Delay (6 mth) due to COVID-19 crisis	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.2	New multiplex TaqMan qPCR	M48	M48		Public https://zenodo.org/record/4061718#.YdwY6FnSKgo	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.3	New NGS method for the detection in complex samples	M48		M54	Delay (6 mth) due to COVID-19 crisis	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.6	Contamination of vegetables by Em/Eg	M48		M54	Delay (6 mth) due to COVID-19 crisis	8
18	D-JRP18-WP3.7	Prevalence of Em/Eg in dog from selected geographical areas	M48		M54	Delay (6 mth) due to COVID-19 crisis	8

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
18	D-JRP18-WP3.8	Potential human risk factors by means of questionnaires	M48		M54	Task replaced with "Human source attribution of cerebral CE by molecular approach and its quantitative assessment in the literature". Delay (6 mth) due to COVID-19 crisis	8
18	D-JRP18-WP4.1	Analysis and evaluation of training activities	M48		M54	Delay (6 mth) due to COVID-19 crisis	8
18	D-JRP18-WP4.3	Final report of PT SSCT	M48	M49		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5816663#.YdQlv1njLmE	8
18	D-JRP18-WP5.1	Data Management Plan (DMP)	M30	M45	M49	Public M45: https://zenodo.org/record/5415292#.YTITD9_OOgo Update in M49:	8
18	D-JRP18-WP5.2	Periodic technical and financial reports to	M36	M45		Public	8

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		EJP/Commission				https://zenodo.org/record/5413157#.YTH66d_OOgo	
18	D-JRP18-WP5.3	Periodic technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M48	M49		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5833427#.YdwWF1nSKgo	8
18	D-JRP18-WP5.5	Kick-off annual meeting in Malzéville (France) by ANSES	M27	M28		Public https://zenodo.org/record/4455256#.YAmKvxbSKgo	8

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
18	M-JRP18-01	Tasks and responsibility allocation	M25	Yes		Kick off meeting in France used for the allocation of the tasks and responsibilities
18	M-JRP18-02	Organization of Kick-off annual meeting by ANSES	M26	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-03	Ethics approvals for the use of animal model	M28	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-04	SOP for validation of SSCT	M30	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-05	SOP for validation of multiplex PCRs	M30	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-06	SOP for Validation of Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay	M41	Yes		Distributed along with verification material and ring test in M46.
18	M-JRP18-07	Protocols for New molecular methods, NGS included	M30	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-08	Protocol for proteomic analysis in animals plasma	M30	No		COVID-19 disrupted this task. See WP3-T4. New task on the detection in berries was inserted (WP3-T6-ST2).
18	M-JRP18-09	Protocol for contamination of vegetables by Em/Eg	M30	Yes		

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
18	M-JRP18-10	Protocol for prevalence of Em/Eg in dog	M30	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-11	(Questionnaire scheme for potential human risk factors) Task replaced with literature search for "Human source attribution of cerebral CE".	M30	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-12	Interim evaluation of collection of samples in the field	M32	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-13	Preparation of technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M35	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-15	Interim evaluation of collection of samples from experimental animal model	M42	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-16	Selection of new/old methods to be compared	M44	Yes		
18	M-JRP18-18	Preparation of technical and financial reports to EJP/Commission	M47	Yes		

4. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Morphological Characteristics of Alveolar and Cystic Echinococcosis Lesions in Human Liver and Bone. https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0817/10/10/1326 https://zenodo.org/record/5646982#.Ydr55ybSlzk	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge)
New global targets for NTDs in the WHO roadmap 2021–2030. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.0009373 https://zenodo.org/record/4771738#.YKTFCqHOOgp	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge; invited editorial)
Cystic echinococcosis: clinical, immunological, and biomolecular evaluation of patients from Sardinia (Italy). https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9110907 https://zenodo.org/record/4159681	YES		Yes, 1.389 €
Molecular analysis suggests that Namibian cheetahs (<i>Acinonyx jubatus</i>) are definitive hosts of a so far undescribed <i>Besnoitia</i> species. https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04697-3 https://zenodo.org/record/4694200#.YTDH7t_OOgo	YES		Yes, 2.190 €
Comparison of two DNA extraction methods and two PCRs for detection of <i>Echinococcus multilocularis</i> in the stool samples of naturally infected red foxes. https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10122381 https://zenodo.org/record/4384600	YES		Yes, 1.481 €

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Species detection within the <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato</i> complex by novel probe based Real-Time PCRs. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9100791 https://zenodo.org/record/4061718#.X6PY3WhKjcc	YES		Yes, 1.258,81 €
A validated method to identify <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato</i> at species level. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meegid.2020.104575 https://zenodo.org/record/4066416#.X6UQMWhKjcc	YES		Yes, 2.300 €
Morphological Characteristics of Alveolar and Cystic Echinococcosis Lesions in Human Liver and Bone. https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0817/10/10/1326 https://zenodo.org/record/5646982#.Ydr55ybSizk	YES		Yes, 0 € (free of charge)
Identification of <i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs Genotyping Assays. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens10020125 https://zenodo.org/record/4471215#.YGLkiq8zZM0	YES		Yes, 696,38 €
Bayesian analysis to evaluate three diagnostic methods for cystic echinococcosis in sheep. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9100796 https://zenodo.org/record/4061823#.X6PZl2hKjcc	YES		Yes, 1.389,79 €
Microsatellite Investigations of Multiple <i>Echinococcus granulosus sensu stricto</i> cysts in single hosts reveal different patterns of infection events between livestock and humans. https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens9060444 https://zenodo.org/record/3894117#.XvyQ6ygzZM0	YES		Yes, 654,56 €
Recognising the substantial burden of neglected pandemics cystic and alveolar echinococcosis.	YES		Yes, 0 €

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(20)30066-8 https://zenodo.org/record/3730559#.Xn3FalhKi70			(free of charge; invited comment)

Additional output

Presentation of MEmE project at:

- “Do we know the real burden of human cystic and alveolar echinococcosis in Europe?”. 13th European Multicolloquium of Parasitology. October 12-16, 2021. Held online. Belgrade, Serbia.
- “Multi-centre study on *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* in Europe: development and harmonization of diagnostic methods in the food chain (MEmE project)”. 13th European Multicolloquium of Parasitology. October 12-16, 2021. Held online. Belgrade, Serbia.
- “From feed to fork: contamination of lettuces by eggs of *Echinococcus multilocularis* and other taenidae species”. 13th European Multicolloquium of Parasitology. October 12-16, 2021. Held online. Belgrade, Serbia.
- “The neglected zoonoses cystic and alveolar echinococcosis”. OH-EJP Summer School 2021. 26 July - 6 August 2021. Held online. Rome, Italy.
- “Species detection within the *Echinococcus granulosus sensu lato* complex by novel probe-based Real-Time PCRs”. 16th Workshop of the National Reference Laboratories for Parasites. 24 November 2021. Held online. Rome, Italy.
- “*Echinococcus* parasites: from correct identification to global phylogeography”. Keynote Lecture. 9th Conference of the Scandinavian-Baltic Society for Parasitology: Parasites in a Changing World. 21-23 April 2021. Virtual conference; Organised by Nature Research Centre and Young Academy of the Lithuanian Academy of Sciences. Vilnius, Lithuania.
- “Multi-centre study on *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* in Europe: development and harmonization of diagnostic methods in the food chain. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting”. Held online. 9-11 June 2021. Copenhagen, Denmark.
- “Internal dissemination online event ‘OHEJP at SSI’”. 4 May 2021. Copenhagen, Denmark.
- “Multi-centre study on *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* in Europe: development and harmonization of diagnostic methods in the food chain”. 15th Workshop of the National Reference Laboratories for Parasites. 15 December 2020. Rome, Italy.
- “Multi-centre study on *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* in Europe: development and harmonization of diagnostic methods in the food chain”. One Health EJP Annual Scientific meeting, held online. 27-29 May 2020. Prague, Czech Republic.
- “Kick off meeting of MEmE”. 5-6 February 2020. Nancy, France.
- “Multi-centre study on *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Echinococcus granulosus s.l.* in Europe: development and harmonization of diagnostic methods in the food chain”. XXVIII World Congress on Echinococcosis. 29-31 October 2019. Lima, Peru.

Outcomes

Expected achievements of MEmE are:

- Production of Standard Operating Procedures for sampling different matrices from naturally or experimentally infected definitive and intermediate animal hosts for Em and Eg.
- Validation of the parasitological and molecular diagnostic procedures to detect Em and Eg in different matrices along the food chain.
- Development and validation of new molecular tools to detect Em and Eg in different matrices along the food chain.

- Production of data relevant for epidemiological and risk assessments on the contamination of vegetables and berries by parasite eggs and on the prevalence of Em/Eg in dog faeces in selected endemic countries.
- Dissemination of project results at different levels.

5. *Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries*

Ongoing and planned collaborations with the following entities:

- The other parasitology-JRPs: PARADISE and TOXOSOURCES.
- The European Reference Laboratory for Parasites (EURLP).
- The WHO Collaborating Centre WHO Collaborating Centre for the Epidemiology, Detection and Control of Cystic and Alveolar Echinococcosis (in humans and animals).
- PERITAS project (molecular ePIdemiological studiEs on pathways of tRansmission and long lasTing cApacity building to prevent cyStic echinococcosis infection). 2018-2021. Funded by the EC under EULAC-Health.

6. *List of critical risks*

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders) *	yes
Delay in work plan execution **	yes
Conflicts within the consortium	no
Lack of commitment of partners	no
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	no
Poor intra-project relationship	no
Potential entry/exit of partners *	yes
Other risks (please describe)	no

Additional information

* See “JRP18-WP2-T3. Magnetic Capture - Real Time PCR assay”. Task was transferred from SVA (SVA withdrew from MEmE in 2021) to NVI. Problem solved.

** Generally due to COVID-19 crisis.

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE

1. *Summary of the work carried out in year 4*

Cryptosporidium and *Giardia* are important intestinal pathogens of humans and young animals, with a global distribution. They are transmitted through direct and indirect routes, and have caused large outbreaks linked to contaminated water and food. The PARADISE project aims at delivering informative genotyping schemes and innovative detection strategies applicable to food matrices for both parasites. This will allow better investigations of outbreaks and the obtention of prevalence data needed for improved risk assessment.

The most relevant progresses for the research-orientated activities are summarized below:

- WP2: A large effort from the Consortium allowed collection of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* isolates across Europe for whole genome sequencing experiments. This generated >100 *C. parvum* genomes from humans and ruminants, and of >40 *G. duodenalis* assemblage B genomes, mostly from humans. The *in silico* metagenomics approach demonstrated the presence of parasite sequences in metagenomes from various matrices. A manuscript has been published, with a focus on *Cryptosporidium* and a description of workflows that increase the specificity of detection. The amplicon-based platform was further tested, and a manuscript describing its application to zoonotic protozoa in pig faeces has been published. Detection of flagellates (including *Giardia*) remained problematic. Parasite reference material has been used to spike plant DNA at different concentrations to mimic natural contamination. After NGS sequencing, the limit of detection of amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics approaches will be assessed.
- WP3: The first selection of 28 *C. parvum* regions endowed with high genetic variability was completed based by comparing >140 genomes. In the case of *G. duodenalis* assemblage B, 20 regions with high genetic variability were identified by comparing 18 available genomes with a newly developed analytical pipeline. Laboratory tests by PCR and Sanger sequencing have been performed for all candidates and each parasite, with design of protocols for single and nested PCR. Based on the observed genetic variability and additional criteria, eight markers have been selected for *C. parvum* and seven for *G. duodenalis* assemblage B. Further testing and validation is ongoing, based on a large collection of parasite samples (about 500) made available from the Consortium. The discriminatory power of the typing scheme for *C. parvum* will be compared to that achievable through the use of markers containing Variable Number of Tandem Repeats, developed by an associated partner (CRU).
- WP4: After immunization of two new-world camelids with extracts from *G. duodenalis* cysts or *C. parvum* oocysts, peripheral blood mononuclear cells were isolated and stored in TRIZOL. Reactivity of the animal immune sera against the respective antigens was verified by ELISA and IFA. RNA from PBMCs was extracted, and cDNA libraries of variable domains of heavy-chain only antibodies (VHH) were produced. Subsequent screening of the *G. duodenalis* library identified several VHH clones reacting against cysts. Screening of the cDNA library against *C. parvum* oocysts is still in progress. For the aptamers, a new strategy based on high-throughput sequencing of DNA sequences from each SELEX round and each replica was applied. A core of sequences progressively enriched throughout the SELEX process was identified for both *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*. Experiments to evaluate the binding properties and affinity of potential binders are under way. For DNA fishing, two capture systems were designed for *Cryptosporidium* (18S rDNA and gp60 loci), and one was designed for *Giardia* (beta giardin locus). Validation of *Cryptosporidium* capture systems is ongoing in two laboratories.

In short, delay in some activities has occurred, but the project is proceeding largely as planned.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1-Coordination and impact

WP-1-T1- Management, coordination and communication

In Year 4, the restrictions caused by the COVID-19 pandemics have continued, and communication has mostly relied upon virtual platforms. WP and Task leaders did meet regularly to follow the project's activities, plan experiments and discuss new strategies. All partners have been kept informed of the project's progress by e-mail and have been consulted before important deadlines (e.g., at the time of reports). The members of the Steering committee have been nominated, while the composition of the Advisory Board needs to be completed.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is updated regularly. Outcomes are made available following the FAIR principle. Dissemination of the outcomes has included presentations at national and international conferences, workshops and scientific publications.

The Annual meeting of Year 4, originally scheduled for M42, has been organized as a virtual meeting on the 26 of October, as the ongoing pandemics did not allow a meeting in person. During Year 4, the Consortium has published two manuscripts.

WP2-NGS-based genomics and metagenomics

WP2-T1- NGS-based genome study of selected isolates of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*

The goal of this task is to generate new whole genome data of isolates of *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis* assemblage B, and to ensure that isolates from different European countries and different hosts are included. Many partner institutes (ANSES, INIAV, ISS, NVI, OKI, PIWET, RKI, SLV, SSI and SVA) and associated partners (BIOR, CRU) have been able to collect faecal samples positive for *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia*. Samples were shipped to SVA, RKI and ISS, where high-quality genomic DNA was prepared, checked for the presence of bacterial contaminants by PCR, submitted (in the case of *Cryptosporidium*) to whole genome amplification (WGA), purified and finally sent to ANSES for NGS-based whole genome sequencing experiments. All NGS experiments were based on Illumina technology (short reads, 2x150 paired ends), and scaled to achieve an average 50X coverage.

For *C. parvum*, >100 genomes of isolates from humans and ruminants, collected in Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Norway, Poland, Portugal and Sweden, have been sequenced. To this dataset, 40 additional genomes from previous projects and collaborations, mostly from isolates collected in Italy and the UK, have been made available and included in downstream analyses.

For *Giardia*, 40 genomes of isolates of Assemblage B have been sequenced, mostly of human origin and after isolation of the parasite by *in-vitro* culturing. Many additional genomes generated during previous projects and collaborations were included in downstream analyses, also representing isolates of Assemblage A, which also infects humans and non-human hosts. A cloud storage space for sharing raw sequence data has been set up by SVA, and a password-protected access has been granted to all partners involved in the bioinformatics analyses. SVA has implemented the *Cryptosporidium* pipeline developed by a previous EU Horizon 2020 project (COMPARE), whereas RKI has developed a new analytical pipeline to process *Giardia* NGS sequence data.

WP2-T2- In silico analyses of metagenomes for detection of foodborne parasites (protozoa and helminths)

The goal of this task is to demonstrate that parasite sequences present in complex metagenomics datasets can be detected with high specificity and to evaluate the limit of detection. Indeed, specificity and sensitivity are essential parameters to consider when exploring the applicability of metagenomics as a platform for foodborne parasites detection. Genome information is available for many protozoa and helminths, and a reference database can be constructed, against which metagenomics reads can be queried. Such a reference database is close to being completed, but the deadline for the associated milestone (M-JRP-PARADISE-5, Referenced database of foodborne parasite genomes established) has been moved to M48.

During Year 4, the pipeline code has been optimized to speed up the processing time. Moreover, the scalability of the pipeline was investigated in view of the huge size of the metagenomics datasets to interrogate. A manuscript presenting several test cases and focusing on bioinformatics strategies to increase the specificity of detection of parasite sequences in complex datasets has been published in *Frontiers in Microbiology*.

A test case of particular interest was a very large metagenome dataset (2.5 billion reads) derived from lettuce; the lettuce was a suspected vehicle of infection in an outbreak of human cryptosporidiosis. Using kraken2 for classification of the reads, 4090 reads of *Cryptosporidium* were identified, of which

3436 classified as *C. parvum*. Other parasites were also identified, including *Toxoplasma* (1932 reads), *Plasmodium yoelli* (2877 reads) and *Theileria* spp. (75 reads). However, using more stringent pipeline settings, no reads from these latter parasite species were retrieved. This suggests that alignment-based tools, such as Kma and/or BWA-MEM, are best suited for taxonomical classification of the reads, but are more demanding in terms of computing time. In order to speed up the process with alignment-based tools, target-specific signature sequences can be used. A set of such signature sequences has been created for *C. parvum* by comparing its whole genome sequence with those of *C. hominis*, *C. muris*, *C. ubiquitum*, *C. andersoni*, *C. baylei*, *C. meleagridis* and the chipmunk genotype. Finally, a metagenomics dataset containing 210,000 reads, free of target parasites, has been spiked *in silico* with 10 highly specific reads from *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*, respectively. The 10 spiked reads for the two parasite species were correctly identified using the metagenomics pipeline with kraken2 as classification tool.

WP2-T3- Experimental amplicon-based and shotgun metagenomics for detection of foodborne parasites

One goal of this task is to optimise a platform based on amplicon-based Next Generation Sequencing for detecting parasites, with special emphasis on foodborne parasites. The principle of the method relies on amplification of the 18S ribosomal DNA gene (18S rRNA) from eukaryotic organisms. The method is part of a 16S/18S platform developed at SSI. The method has already been used in various studies and has been applied to genomic DNA extracted from various matrices such as faeces, other clinical sample types (EDTA blood, spinal fluid, skin/cornea biopsies/scrapings, etc), food products and environmental samples. The deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP2.1 (Protocol for 18S rDNA-based amplicon sequencing for detection of relevant FBPs) was submitted at M37. A manuscript describing the application of this platform to the detection of various zoonotic protozoa in pig faeces has been published. The platform still shows low sensitivity for the detection of microsporidia and some flagellates, including *Giardia*, and this may be due to problems of the Illumina sequencing technology with very GC-rich stretches (i.e., the nuclear ribosomal DNA sequence of *Giardia*). To overcome this problem, the possibility to add additional primers will be first explored, including primers targeting the ribosomal ITS for improved detection of parasitic nematodes. In parallel, alternative markers will be identified based on the FLUIDIGM technology.

A second goal is to compare the performance of the amplicon-based Next Generation Sequencing with that of shotgun metagenomics, an untargeted sequencing approach used to profile the taxonomic composition of communities. In particular, we intend to compare the limit of detection (LOD) of the two methodologies. To this end, genomic DNA from a plant matrix (ready-to-eat mixed salad) has been extracted at VRI and spiked with different amounts of genomic DNA from three parasites (*Cryptosporidium*, *Giardia* and *Toxoplasma*), provided by ISS. This will simulate the presence of 10, 50 and 100 (oo)cysts in a large excess of plant genomic DNA, mimicking the low contamination level observed in naturally contaminated foodstuff. The anonymized spiked samples have been sent to SSI and ISS for amplicon-based and shotgun experiments, respectively, which will be shortly completed. Bioinformatics analyses will be performed to identify parasite-specific sequences, and the samples will be also tested by in-house *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* real-time PCR assays for comparison.

WP3-Design, implementation and validation of multi-locus typing schemes

WP3-T1- In silico selection of informative loci from comparative genomics data

The goal of this task is to compare whole-genome data for the identification of regions of high genetic variability in both *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (Assemblage B). The following selection criteria were used: (i) the variable regions should be located on all chromosomes or (ii) at a sufficient physical distance to minimize genetic linkage; (iii) a high genetic variability across the isolates should be present; and (iv) specificity for *C. parvum* or *G. duodenalis*, determined *in silico*, should be demonstrated.

Whole-genome comparison of >100 *C. parvum* isolates revealed a relatively low genetic diversity, with about 24.000 SNPs identified. To identify regions with high genetic variability, two approaches were used. First, the number of SNPs was calculated in each gene, and then in 500 bp windows. Candidates (n=28) were further selected after calculation of Simpson's diversity index. In the second approach, physical intervals containing a predefined number of SNPs (e.g., 10) were identified in the genome. Next, intervals of approximately 500-700 bp were selected and ranked in terms of their information content. Candidates from both approaches were retained for laboratory validation.

For the Assemblage B isolates of *G. duodenalis*, whole-genome comparison revealed greater variability compared to *C. parvum*. A dedicated analytical pipeline developed at RKI was used to identify variable regions. At present, 20 candidates have been selected, having high genetic variability among the tested isolates and being located on the five different chromosomes.

More details on the selection procedures can be found in the report on the deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.1 (Report on the *in silico* selection of highly polymorphic sequences in *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* genomes).

WP3-T2- Development of MLST schemes for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*

During Year 4, primers were designed for all *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* assemblage B marker candidates, and for both single and nested PCR reactions. Reference genomic DNA and DNA from faecal samples were used for PCR and Sanger sequencing experiments. Different combination of candidates have been systematically evaluated for their discriminatory power before inclusion in the final typing schemes. For *C. parvum*, eight different markers (one per chromosome) have been selected, while for *G. duodenalis*, which has 5 chromosomes, seven markers have been selected.

When developing new typing schemes, it is of paramount importance to test candidate markers on a large collection of samples from different hosts and geographical origin. These tests are under way at the four partner Institutes in charge (ISS, RKI, SVA and UoS). Besides samples already available in these Institutes, additional *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* DNA sample from the Consortium have been shipped during spring 2021. This includes 124 samples now available at ISS, 47 samples at RKI, 187 samples at SVA and 247 samples at UoS.

In parallel to the selection and testing of SNP-based markers, a different typing scheme for *C. parvum* developed by the associate partner CRU is being evaluated. This system is based on seven markers containing Variable Number of Tandem Repeats (VNTR), which are amplified in two multiplex PCR reactions and analyzed on a capillary sequencer to determine fragment size. SVA already applied the VNTR typing scheme to all 187 *C. parvum* samples available, which originated from Denmark, Latvia, Norway, Netherlands and Sweden. Data will be analysed in collaboration with UoS.

The associated deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.2 (Report on the identification of markers for multi-locus sequence typing of *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis*) has been completed.

WP3-T3-Interlaboratory comparison of typing schemes

During Year 4, collection of information on the parasite isolates and the associated metadata available at each partner Institute has been completed. Part of these samples were shipped and used for laboratory validation of candidate markers. The inter-laboratory comparison aimed at assessing the robustness and reproducibility of the typing schemes will be organized in Year 5 (spring 2022).

WP4-Parasite enrichment strategies

The objectives of WP4 are the development and evaluation by inter-laboratory comparison of: i) two pre-DNA extraction protocols based on two alternative affinity reagents, nanobodies (single-chain variable fragment antibodies) and aptamers (oligonucleotides that bind to a specific target molecule), and their application for magnetic capture of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts in different matrices; ii) a protocol for post-DNA enrichment to concentrate parasite DNA based on hybridization of target-specific biotinylated probes.

WP4-T1- Development of pre-DNA extraction enrichment strategies

Nanobodies: Two new world camelids were immunized with extracts from *Giardia duodenalis* cysts or *Cryptosporidium parvum* oocysts, respectively, and peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were isolated and stored in TRIZOL for later RNA preparation. Immune sera of the animals were tested by ELISA and IFA to ensure sufficient antibody production, and thus reactive B cells, against *Giardia* and *Cryptosporidium* antigens. The results showed that both animals react to the respective antigens. RNA from PBMCs was extracted and cDNA libraries of variable domains of heavy-chain only antibodies (VHH) were produced. Subsequent screening of *G. duodenalis* library identified several VHH clones reacting against cysts. Screening of cDNA library against *C. parvum* oocysts is still in progress. Positively selected VHH clones will be used for expression and purification by affinity chromatography for further characterization. The associated deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.2 (Report on the selection of highly affine nanobodies specific for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*) has been completed.

Aptamers: ANSES accomplished ten rounds of SELEX for five aptamer pools for both *C. parvum* (IOWA strain) and *G. duodenalis* (assemblage B). The PCR products of each round and each replica were subjected to high-throughput sequencing (HTS) and the data analysed by bioinformatics tools (Patternity suite). A core of sequences progressively enriched throughout the SELEX process were identified for both *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*. Similarly, but using a different SELEX protocol, ISS has completed 14 round of selection (in triplicate) against *G. duodenalis* assemblage B cysts. Sequence pools were also analyzed by HTS and Patternity suite, and enriched sequences selected. Screening of the candidates is in progress to assess if they are true “binders” and evaluate their binding properties and affinity. The associated deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.1 (Report on the cloning and sequencing of aptamers specific for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*) has been completed.

WP4-T2- Development of post-DNA extraction enrichment strategies

In Year 3, SVA designed a magnetic capture (MC) system for *Cryptosporidium* (18S ribosomal DNA gene) and one for *Giardia* (beta-giardin gene), whereas RIVM designed a different capture probe for *Cryptosporidium* (gp60 gene). Rigorous testing of these capture systems on FACS-purified sorted oocysts (SVA) and on fecal samples (RIVM) demonstrated high sensitivity (10 purified oocysts and 125 oocysts in 2 g fecal samples, respectively). Further testing to better define the detection limit in different matrices are under way. This will be based on a series of test panels, including purified oocysts sorted by FACS (5, 10, 50 and 100), fecal samples spiked with 5, 10, 50 or 100 oocysts, clinical samples with different Cq values, and dilution series of clinical samples. These panels will be tested in eight replicates at both SVA and RIVM.

In Year 5, novel capture systems will be designed based on the new, informative markers selected for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* by WP2/WP3, but priority is given to a robust validation of the existing capture systems, as detailed above. The associated D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.3 deliverable (Report on the probes designed to targets developed in WP3 for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*) has been completed.

3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP1.1	Report of the kickoff meeting	M26	M30		Public OHEJP: available https://zenodo.org/record/4452807#.YAhQRDmg9dg	8 (Meeting report)
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP1.2	Report of Annual meeting	M42		M46	Organization of a physical meeting still impossible. Due to some delays in research-oriented WPs, the virtual Annual meeting was held on the 26 of October 2021.	8
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP2.1	Protocol for 18S rDNA-based amplicon sequencing for detection of relevant FBPs	M30	M37		Public OHEJP: available https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4478998	2

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP2.2	Report on the FBPs detected in metagenomics datasets by in silico analysis	M48		M52	The work has been delayed due to limited access to some partner's Institute caused by COVID-19. Nevertheless, several analyses have been performed on metaganomes from wastewater and from calf gut. The deadline has been moved to include additional data and provide a more consistent picture	2
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.1	Report on the in silico selection of highly polymorphic sequences in <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i> genomes	M30	M36		Public OHEJP: available https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4452771	2
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.2	Report on the identification of markers for MLST of <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M42		M45	Public OHEJP: available https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5494475	2

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.3	SOPs for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i> MLST schemes	M48		M50	Most of the work has been completed, but the final evaluation of two alternative <i>C. parvum</i> schemes is still ongoing	2
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.1	Report on the cloning and sequencing of aptamers specific for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M36		M45	Public OHEJP: available https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5495542	2
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.2	Report on the selection of highly affine nanobodies specific for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M36		M45	Public OHEJP: available https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5495560	2
19	D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.3	Report on the probes designed to targets developed in WP3 for <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i>	M44		M45	Public OHEJP: available https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5495592	2

** Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);*

Milestones

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-1	Kick-off Meeting (WP1)	M26	Yes		
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-2	Study visit (ISS-ANSES) for optimizing aptamer selection strategy	M28	No	No longer planned	Study visit impossible due to the COVID-19 epidemics
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-3	Key isolates of <i>C. parvum</i> collected	M30	Yes	M45	Collection now completed. Delays in this activity were due to the COVID-19 epidemics
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-4	Key isolates of <i>G. duodenalis</i> collected	M30	Yes	M45	Collection now completed. Delays in this activity were due to the COVID-19 epidemics
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-5	Referenced database of foodborne parasite genomes established	M30	Yes	M48	Database completed. Delays in this activity were due to the COVID-19 epidemics
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-6	Pipeline for metagenome data analysis for FBPs optimized	M30	Yes	M48	Pipeline completed. Delays in this activity were due to the COVID-19 epidemics
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-7	First set of candidate markers for MLST development available	M30	Yes		
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-8	Animal immunization and cDNA library of nanobody sequences for <i>C. parvum</i> and for <i>G. duodenalis</i> completed	M36	Yes		

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-9	Submission of genome sequences of <i>C. parvum</i> and <i>G. duodenalis</i> to public repository	M36	No	M50	The last round of genome sequencing has been completed, and data will then be submitted to a public repository
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-11	Highly affine nanobodies selected	M36	No	M45	Laboratory work delayed due to COVID-19 restrictions in Year 3. Technical challenges to solve for <i>Cryptosporidium</i>
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-12	Pre-evaluation of probes directed towards markers commonly used for <i>C. parvum</i>	M36	Yes		
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-13	Pre-evaluation of probes directed towards markers commonly used for <i>G. duodenalis</i> .	M36	Yes		
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-14	Annual meeting (WP1)	M42	No	M46	The Annual meeting has been held, virtually, on the 26 October 2021.
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-15	Technical Workshop on on enrichment strategies (WP4)	M42	No	M54	Organization of the technical workshop not possible due to the COVID-19 pandemics. Possibility to produce a video tutorial and/or to organize a dedicated session duering the last project meeting (June 2022, M54)
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-16	Final set of markers for MLST of <i>C. parvum</i> available	M42	No	M45	

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-17	Final set of markers for MLST of <i>G. duodenalis</i> available	M42	No	M45	
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-18	Technical Workshop for training on MLST (WP3)	M48	No	M54	Organization of the technical workshop not possible due to the COVID-19 pandemics. Possibility to produce a video tutorial and/or to organize a dedicated session duering the last project meeting (June 2022, M54)
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-19	Validation of marker for typability and resolution accomplished	M48	No	M50	
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-20	Magnetic bead coupled nanobodies suitable for the enrichment of (oo)cysts available	M48	No	M52	
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-21	Magnetic bead coupled aptamers suitable for the enrichment of (oo)cysts available	M48	No	M52	
19	M-JRP-PARADISE-22	Hybridization probes tested for robustness and sensitivity available	M48	No	M52	

4. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Molecular Characterization of <i>Giardia duodenalis</i> in Children and Adults Sampled in Algeria https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9010054 https://zenodo.org/record/4422456#.YArbG-hKjcc	YES		Yes 2730.00 \$ = 2437.96 €
Veterinary Students Have a Higher Risk of Contracting Cryptosporidiosis when Calves with High Fecal <i>Cryptosporidium</i> Loads Are Used for Fetotomy Exercises 10.1128/AEM.01250-20 https://zenodo.org/record/4129990#.X6PX8WhKjcc	YES		Yes 1475.33 €
Parasitic Intestinal Protists of Zoonotic Relevance Detected in Pigs by Metabarcoding and Real-Time PCR https://www.mdpi.com/2076-2607/9/6/1189 https://zenodo.org/record/4898752#.YTnBA50zaUk	Yes		Yes Free of cost
Mining public metagenomes for environmental surveillance of parasites: a proof of principle. https://zenodo.org/record/5494583	Yes		Yes 1580.00 \$ = 2176.47 €

Additional output

A general description of the project has been published (in Danish) by partner 13 (SSI) in the Danish Veterinary Journal (<https://ipaper.ipapercms.dk/fsek/dvt/2020/dvt102020/?Page=36>)

A presentation on the metagenomics work in WP2 was given at the meeting of the Dutch Society for Parasitology on 26th of May, 2021 ([NVP - Evenementen \(parasitologie.nl\)](http://NVP-Evenementen.parasitologie.nl))

Outcomes

A major outcome of the project is the generation of a large number of whole genome data for both *Cryptosporidium parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis*. Exploitation of these data will provide an unprecedented opportunity to study the biology of these parasites and to shed light on the mechanisms that have influenced their evolution, virulence, host adaptation, and population genetic structure. Remarkably, the One Health EJP will be at the forefront of genomic research for these two pathogens.

5. Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries

- Complementarities with the OHEJP research project “Toxosources”. Specifically, collaboration on bioinformatics approaches for genome comparison and development of new typing schemes. Further interactions foreseen in relation to new methodologies for enrichment and detection of parasites in specific food matrices (ready-to-eat salads).
- Complementarities with the OHEJP integrative project “OH-Harmony-CAP”, in which *Cryptosporidium* has been selected as a model organism for evaluation of the current and best practices and the development of harmonised protocols.
- Link with the objectives of the **European Union Reference Laboratory for Parasites** in terms of new typing schemes for FBPs that, in perspective, may become official, validated methods.
- Complementarities with the **EFSA-funded research project “IMPACT”** for the definition of optimized protocols for the molecular detection and characterization of FBPs on selected food matrices.

6. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	Turnover of staff at some partner’s Institute

JRP20-FBZSH3-DISCoVeR

1. Summary of the work carried out in year 4

This DISCoVeR project brings together experts from different disciplines (microbiology, bioinformatics and epidemiology) and sectors (veterinary science, food safety, public health and environmental health) from 19 institutions in 13 European countries into a unique consortium to address the challenges of source attribution in an interdisciplinary manner. As there is no gold standard for source attribution, we take a comprehensive approach applying several different methodologies and models in a comparative fashion.

In the first year, we mapped the existing knowledge gaps and recommend new studies and/or methods that are needed to fill them. We then mapped existing data by creating data inventories for all DISCoVeR target pathogens. Data collection is ongoing, as some partners met delays in collecting new data from non-livestock and non-food sources. We have, therefore, extended the completion of project datasets to February 2022. We have included data from a broad range of reservoirs and sources, including those that are not traditionally part of existing monitoring and surveillance activities, e.g. pets (incl. reptiles), wildlife, and environmental sources.

The work focus on cataloguing, evaluating and advancing existing methods for source attribution and develop methods for the critical assessment of source attribution models. Novel approaches for source attribution are explored, developed and assessed. Existing approaches that are investigated include the microbial subtyping, meta-analysis of case-control studies and outbreak data, and risk-assessment based methods. The source attribution estimates focus on three pathogens (*Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, and STEC) and AMR.

For *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*, several partners are developing WGS-based attribution models. Preliminary results indicate that the outputs are very much in line with previous subtyping approaches (phenotypic and MLST based), although the WGS-based models appear to have a higher predicting accuracies due to the increased discriminatory power. Conventional subtyping approaches are also being applied for all the target pathogens, and we expect at least for *Salmonella* to be able to make a multi-country model. A systematic literature review of recently published (2011-2021) case-control studies of sporadic *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* infections has been completed and will together with data from previous reviews form the basis for an overall meta-analysis using Bayesian evidence synthesis methods. Multi-Country Comparative Exposure Assessments (CEA) of target pathogens in pets have been completed. The output is the relative exposure of humans to pathogenic and antimicrobial resistant bacteria due to (in)direct contact with cats or dogs.

An online stakeholder workshop was held on January 22, 2021. Around 20 participants from EFSA, ECDC, EURLs, other relevant EJP projects, as well as DISCoVeR WP-leads met to discuss how DISCoVeR results could support the work of the stakeholders and vice versa. A mapping of the currently existing control programmes of the target pathogens and AMR in humans, animals and the environment at the EU and national level is also completed. This task was addressed by i) a scientific literature review, ii) a review of grey literature, and iii) a survey aimed at relevant national experts.

On the project management side, we have since the project start had one face-to-face meeting and six webmeeting for all partners, and 11 web meetings for the project management team. We have created a share-site for partners to share documents and data. For sharing of genomic sequences, we have set up a secure space on the data platform sciencedata.dk. Finally, all partners have signed a Material Transfer Agreement.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1: Project coordination and administration (M25-60)

WP1-T1- Project management (M25-60) - ongoing

Since the start of the project, we have had one face-to-face kick-off meeting hosted by DTU on February 10-12, 2020, and six web meetings for all partners and 11 webmeetings for the project management team (PMT) consisting of all work package leaders, their deputies and task leaders.

A share-site hosted by DTU has been set up, where project partners can share documents and data, including minutes of meetings and the developed data inventories.

Partners have agreed on a Material Transfer Agreement (MTA), which is being signed by all partners.

WP1-T2- Mapping of existing knowledge gaps (M25-28) - completed

For the mapping of existing knowledge gaps a systematic literature search by means of a rapid review was performed. Based on predefined search queries publications relevant for source attribution of the bacterial species *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, VTEC/STEC and for antimicrobial resistant (AMR) bacteria (*Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, *E. coli*) were identified in the two databases Scopus and Web of Science. Each identified publication was tagged according to categories like the organisms and sources they considered or the methods they employed. Using the data of the tagged publications knowledge maps were created, which showed how much publications were found for each method-source combination for each of the above-mentioned bacterial species and AMR. The methodology and results of this mapping together with suggestions how to fill the identified knowledge gaps were put together in a report and submitted as deliverable D-JRP FBZ-1-WP1.1 to the project coordination. The results were also presented at the OHEJP ASM in Copenhagen June 9-11, 2021. A short summary is uploaded at Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/record/5825542#.YdcJyWjMKUk>

WP1-T3- Data Management Plan (DMP) (M25-60) - ongoing

The first draft of the DMP was prepared in Nov 20, but its development is a continuing process. Considering the structure of the new DMP tool, we plan to upload information about our selected datasets, whenever we have a 'finalised' dataset ready for data analysis. Next update was done in M49, where almost all WGS data were uploaded to sciencedata.dk.

WP2: Data: Coordination of data collection (M25-M50)

WP2-T1- Mapping of existing data/database est. (M25-36) - completed

A data inventory form in Excel was adapted to each pathogen subgroup. The purpose of the inventory was to get a quick overview of strains and sequences available in order to pinpoint areas with limited data availability to i) direct further sampling, and ii) identify for which pathogens and models we can expect to have sufficient data for source attribution. The data inventories have been filled-in by partners and hazard-specific webmeetings have been organized to present the data available and agree on further sampling of mainly non-animal food reservoirs and/or isolate characterization (mainly sequencing) and transmission to the other WPs for source attribution analysis. A short description and the hazard-specific data sheets have been uploaded to Zenodo as D-JRPFZ-1-WP2.6.

The data inventories and expected new data have provided the basis for selection of appropriate datasets for source attribution for the focus hazard and attribution approaches (see WP4 description for the source attribution approaches selected for each organism).

For sharing WGS data among participants, we created a space on the data platform sciencedata.dk and made a plan for uploading data. A meeting to demonstrate the sciencedata platform was held May 27, 2021. Most sequence data have been uploaded, but due to delays in sample collection, a few are still pending.

Partners are either uploading i) raw sequence data, which are then run through the FoodQC pipeline at DTU, or ii) assembled sequences, which should then adhere to a set of agreed quality criteria, which are uploaded to the share-site.

WP2-T2- Data collection: Salmonella (M25-48) - ongoing

Overall, ten participants from nine countries (Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Ireland, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Spain and UK) delivered data about *Salmonella* serovars in their collections. Seven institutes showed data from animals, food and environment, five concerning humans.

Overall, the most numerous *Salmonella* serovars are *S. Enteritidis* (>19100 isolates/> 800 sequences), Typhimurium (>9600 isolates/> 270 sequences), monophasic variant of *S. Typhimurium* (>6500 isolates/> 300 sequences) and *S. Infantis* (>2560 isolates/ 190 sequences). Those serovars occur in all main sources. SE and ST were found as a top 1 and 2 in humans and animals. In food *S. Infantis* and *S. Typhimurium* are dominant. The environment is represented by the least number of isolates of different *Salmonella* serovars (>300 isolates/ 0 sequences). Some countries declared ongoing sampling or being ready to sequence selected isolates if needed.

For WGS-based source attribution, focus is on the following serovars: Typhimurium, monophasic Typhimurium, Enteritidis, Infantis, Derby, and Newport. For these serovars it was possible for a handful of countries to contribute with 25 sequences per source per serovar and country during the past 5-10 years.

For a multi-country attribution model based on phenotypic information only, available subtyping data for *Salmonella* were submitted from several partners and formatted for source attribution analyses in WP4.

WP2-T3- Data collection: Campylobacter (M25-48) - ongoing

The *Campylobacter* specific questionnaire was filled-in by 10 institutes from 7 countries. A total of >5000 whole genome sequenced strains were reported to be available for the project. This includes genomes of human clinical strains, food, animal and environmental strains.

Fairly good data sets are available already and the modelers expect to be able to use the data, despite the incompleteness when it comes to full coverage of countries, sources, years. New sampling should primarily focus on environmental samples and other sources that are not well covered already. Focus is on *C. jejuni* and *C. coli*.

For WGS-based source attribution, focus is on collecting data from recent years, 2015-2020, with around 100 human genomes and 50 genomes from each source. To increase the amount of available data, 7-loci MLST data were also collected to construct a 'conventional' multi-country source attribution model as well. For the modeling work, see WP3 and WP4.

WP2-T4- Data collection: VTEC (M25-50) - ongoing

A more detailed isolate inventory was created and filled in by 16 partners from 11 countries. More than 3000 human STEC isolates with WGS data will be available for the project. For the animal, food and environmental STEC isolates almost 1000 isolates with WGS data will be available. This is one of the more comprehensive datasets for STEC available. ISS has developed a WGS pipeline, which most partners have been running using the Galaxy platform, and sequences are uploaded to sciencedata.dk.

The need for further sampling of other sources than food-producing animals has been highlighted and sampling is planned. Some sampling have been performed, however, due to COVID-19 the some sampling has been postponed or cancelled for several partners.

WP2-T5- Data collection: AMR (M25-48) - ongoing

Overall, eight countries (Czech Republic, Denmark, Germany, Ireland, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal and Spain) have in their strain collections clinical/indicator *E. coli* (including ESBL-*E. coli*) gathered for

task 4. Number of available isolates/sequences ranges from less than 100 (Ireland) to 500-700 (Czech Republic, Poland) to > 1.000 (remaining countries). Most of the isolates, however, come from animals/food products, so that only Denmark and the Netherlands report a large number (>100) of isolates of human origin.

It was decided to focus on ESBL-EC from years with overlapping data from multiple reservoirs, and thus the period 2013-2020 was considered the best period. It was proposed to collect additional information for countries with available strains/sequences (possibly at the strain level), including: 1) availability of phenotypic AMR information, and 2) specifics on the genotypic information available (for non-sequenced strains): gene families/specific genes. A strain-level database has been built containing currently information on ~5,600 ESBL-EC (pending addition of strain-level data from Germany and Denmark), with most isolates up to now originating from the Netherlands (~2,700 isolates) and Spain (~2,200), mostly from animal sources.

WP3: Methods: Assessment/improvement (M25-54)

In this WP, monthly webmeetings are held to discuss progress and preliminary results.

Deliverable (D-JRPFZ-1-WP3.2) on evaluation of SA methods is ongoing and is expected to be finalised M50. We are applying the so-called TRACE framework to evaluate the various models identified through a scoping review.

WP3-T1- Assessing and developing source attribution methods based on microbial subtyping (M25-54)

Ongoing

WP3-T2- Assessing and developing source attribution methods based on phylogenetic data (M25-54)-Ongoing

As it turned out, there is a considerably overlap between the objectives and activities of T1 and T2, and we have consequently merged the two task, which will therefore be reported together below.

A working group has been assembled and is meeting bi-monthly. The research objectives has been defined: Using WGS/phylogeny of surveillance data to apply weights in source attribution models to move from reservoir attribution towards source attribution that is directly actionable by public health and food authorities, by better reflecting exposure evidence. Focus are on *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella*.

A Danish dataset of *Campylobacter* sequences collected from humans, animals incl. pets, foods and environments from 2015-2017 has been processed through different bioinformatics pipelines to obtain MLST, cgMLST, wgMLST, SNPs and Kmer data. All these genomic output data have been explored in different source attribution models using machine learning (ML) to identify any host-associated genetic (groups of) markers. The different models were assessed with regard to accuracy and number of human cases that they would be able to predict. The best method will be applied to other partners' *Campylobacter* data as well as to more recent data from Denmark (2019-2020). A MSc student at DTU contributing to the development of the above-mentioned bioinformatics and machine-learning approaches for *Campylobacter*, handed in her thesis in June 2021.

A comparison of source attribution methods is ongoing using a sample of 280 *Campylobacter* isolates from human cases and animal/environmental sources in the Netherlands using STRUCTURE, BEAST and a Random Forest methods on core-genome SNPs, gene presence absence data and cgMLST data. The three methods show slightly different attribution estimates, with the Random Forest method showing a noticeable lower attribution to the environment using both genetic sources, cgMLST representing the core genome and gene presence absence representing the accessory genome. Although there is no golden standard, the output of each method was compared with the majority vote. In this dataset, it seems that STRUCTURE based on cgMLST data slightly outperforms the other

methods as it most often agrees with the majority vote. More analyses will be done to confirm this finding.

A ML approach using random forest (RF) to perform source attribution of 420 human UK and DK sequences of *S. Typhimurium* and monophasic variants of *S. Typhimurium* was applied. 482 animal sequences from nine primary source classes were used for model training and testing. The cgMLST profiles (3002 core genomes) and accessory genome (1230 genomes incl. plasmids, phages) of all 902 sequences were retrieved and used as model inputs (features) after imputing missing data. Preliminary data of the RF model using cgMLST as input suggest that the major source of human *S. Typhimurium* infections in UK and DK is pig meat ($\approx 66\%$ of cases) followed by 'other non-livestock cases' ($\approx 10\%$). However, further refinement of the models are ongoing. The same dataset were also analysed using a Bayesian model and using the accessory genes present/absence as input.

Deliverable D-JRPFZ-1-WP3.1 "Describe novel approaches for source attribution using microbial subtyping" summarises the different WGS-based approaches developed. It is currently being reviewed by partners and will be uploaded eminently.

WP3-T3- Evaluation of microbial subtyping source attribution by infectious disease modelling (M25-54) - ongoing

This task sets out to develop a method for measuring the quality of source attribution based on subtyping. The work was planned to result in a milestone in M33, but this has been postponed to allow for evaluating also the models coming out of T1 and T2. The approach taken is based on simulating bacterial population using the software: Bacmita <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty093>

WP3-T4- Assessing and developing approaches for source attribution of antimicrobial resistance based on metagenomics (M25-54) - ongoing

Nothing to report specifically for the project, as we are still identifying and collecting relevant metagenomic data. In particular, we are in need of data from the general population to further develop the approach. So far, such data seems only available in the Netherlands. A paper ([Duarte et al., 2021](#)) describing the methodology was recently published by one of the partners (but related to another EU financed project). INIAV and DTU have been granted a STM addressing the use of metagenomics for source tracking in aquaculture. The STM will take place in January 2022.

WP3-T5- Assessing and developing source attribution approaches based on case-control study results (M25-48) - ongoing

A systematic literature review of recently published (2011-2021) case-control studies of sporadic *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter* infections has been conducted. The merging of the this new systematic review with previous reviews is also done. Next step is to conduct an overall meta-analysis using Bayesian evidence synthesis methods to obtain updated source attribution estimates for WP4.

A methodological paper "Combining attribution estimates from empirical studies and expert opinions", presenting the approach used in WP4 to combine attribution estimates from different sources, will be submitted soon for publication by one of the partners.

WP3-T6- Assessing and developing source attribution approaches based on data from reported outbreak investigations (M25-48) - ongoing

Milestone in M33 (M-JRPFZ-1-06): Methods for source attribution based on outbreak data evaluated was met. Outbreak data for this task was requested from EFSA, which released the data in M40. Modeling for *Salmonella* is completed and results will soon be shared with the wider project group and applied in WP4.

WP3-T7- Assessing and developing source attribution approaches based on Risk-assessment (M25-45) - ongoing

A review of existing comparative exposure assessment (CEA) models was completed in M38 (M-JRPFZ-1-18).

For the CEA approach, data for all DISCoVeR partner countries are incomplete or non-existent. A comparative exposure assessment, to be “comparative” needs to include different sources or to be performed in different regions/countries, which would also be in line with the spirit of OHEJP projects. It was therefore decided that a reasonable approach would be to perform an exposure assessment for a specific source for which we expected to find only few typing data, i.e. pets like dogs and cats. The pet-CEA were performed for all three target pathogens and AMR in different countries that have the necessary data. The resulting exposure estimates were compared between the countries, and it was investigated whether possible differences are also reflected in the attribution estimates obtained by the other methods. The models are including available data on national pathogen prevalences in dogs and cats received from partners.

WP4. Results – Quantifying the contribution of various sources of foodborne zoonoses and AMR (M30-56)

In WP4, data collected in WP2 and the methods assessed/developed in WP3 are used to quantify the contributions of the main sources of the three target pathogens and AMR. Results will be presented per pathogen, attribution method, type of data and, when/if applicable, geographical region/country. Particular attention will be given to environmental and non-livestock (pets and wildlife) sources besides the ‘traditional’ livestock/food sources. The results of applied methods for each pathogen will be compared in the light of data availability and robustness, underlying uncertainties, the point in the food production chain where source attribution takes place, and the usefulness of different methods to answer different One Health questions. Before performing any attribution, it has become evident in the past months that it is necessary to compare the typing data between countries using, e.g. PCA and/or similarity metrics like PSI. In this way, geographical regions could be identified as the “epidemiological units” for the attribution analyses. Moreover, such an analysis would already be very informative in itself as it would provide information on the distribution of relevant subtypes among the DISCoVeR partner countries and it would also offer the opportunity to identify potential sources of surrogate data for the attribution analysis.

Overall, a plan for which models to apply for each pathogens was agreed upon at a meeting on February 15, 2021. At the same meeting, persons/groups responsible for data management and modeling, respectively, for each pathogen-model combination were identified.

As an activity of interest for all tasks within WP4 and in collaboration with WP2 and WP3, we worked together to define a minimum set of (meta)data to be collected to perform source attribution in a meaningful way. A document was prepared and shared with all partners. This document was integrated in the milestone M-JRP FBZ-1-07 (Format for results presentation (standard structure) for all pathogens and AMR).

WP4-T1- Salmonella source attribution and comparison of results from different approaches (M30-54) - ongoing

The specific activities of this task are structured as follows:

- 1) Attributions based on microbial subtyping, which will include frequency-based models based on phenotypic subtyping data and machine-learning approaches based on WGS data. The data for running the frequency-based models are made available and analyses are ongoing: this specific analysis based on serotyping data will target four countries (the Netherlands, Portugal, Czech Republic and Denmark, as examples of respectively Western, Southern, Eastern and Northern Europe). The analyses based on the genomic data will start as soon as the data are made available by WP2.

2) Analysis of *Salmonella* outbreak data based on national data reported to EFSA's outbreak database. The database has been cleaned and an overall preliminary analysis has been performed, in which it appears that eggs are the main source of the salmonellosis outbreaks observed in Europe between 2015 and 2019. Further analyses are ongoing to stratify the results by geographical region (Western, Southern, Eastern and Northern Europe) and serotype. A trend analysis will also be attempted.

3) Meta-analysis of case control data to update previous systematic reviews. The systematic review of articles published between 2011 and 2021 has been performed using a standardized process to review literature and selecting relevant articles using the key-terms: *Campylobacter* (campylobacteriosis) or *Salmonella* (salmonellosis), Case-control, Sporadic and Risk Factors. Studies were included when passing the relevance screening, quality assessment and criteria for eligibility. From a total of 2084 identified references, 9 articles (5 on campylobacteriosis and 4 on salmonellosis) were deemed fit for data-extraction and were included in this review. Information on the frequency of mentioning and estimated odds ratios were collected. The most often mentioned risk factors for campylobacteriosis were: the consumption of chicken (5-times), owning a dog and/or cat (4-times), consumption of raw/undercooked meat (2-times) and contact with live poultry and/or birds (2-times). For Salmonellosis these were: the consumption of raw pork (4-times) and chicken (2-times), owning a cat and/or dog (2-times) and travelling abroad (2-times). The previous use of gastric anti-acidic drugs was mentioned often for both campylobacteriosis and salmonellosis, as well. The next step will be to perform a meta-analysis of these studies together with those already meta-analyzed in the period prior 2011.

4) Exposure assessment (pets only, but all target pathogens). The goal of this analysis was to estimate the relative exposure of humans to pathogenic and antimicrobial resistant bacteria due to (in)direct contact with cats or dogs, as compared between countries, using two approaches. The General Exposure Indicator, which is the ratio of the number of dogs or cats and the number of humans in a country, gives a relative, bacterium a-specific, quantitative exposure estimate which proves to show clear variation and differences between countries. The Bacterium Exposure Indicator is the ratio of the number of bacterium-specific infected dogs or cats and the number of humans in a country, and this gives a relative, bacterium-specific, quantitative exposure estimate. The uncertainty introduced by the dog/cat prevalence data, and its availability, implies that only a limited number of differences between countries could be found for the Bacterium Exposure Indicator.

WP4-T2- *Campylobacter* source attribution and comparison of results from different approaches (M30-54) - ongoing

Like in the previous task, specific activities have been defined:

1. Attribution based on microbial subtyping, which will include frequency-based models based on 7-loci MLST data, machine-learning approaches based on WGS data, and population genetic models. These analyses will start as soon as the data will be made available by WP2.
2. Meta-analysis of case-control data to update systematic reviews (please see corresponding point in task JRP20-WP4-T1)
3. Exposure assessment (pets only). (Please, see corresponding point in task JRP20-WP4-T1)

Analysis of outbreak data is not included because the scarcity of documented *Campylobacteriosis* outbreaks would make such an analysis not very useful.

WP4-T3- *VTEC* source attribution and comparison of results from different approaches (M30-56) - ongoing

Specific activities include:

1. Attribution based on microbial subtyping, which will include frequency-based models based on phenotypic data (virulence genes, etc.), machine-learning approaches based on WGS data

(if data allows), and population genetic models. These analyses will start as soon as the data will be made available by WP2.

2. Exposure assessment (pets only). (Please, see corresponding point in task JRP20-WP4-T1)

Meta-analysis of case-control studies and outbreak is not included, because there are already recent work available through a piece of WHO work led by one of the partners.

WP4-T4- AMR source attribution results presented regionally and by region/country, for each applied method and integrated (M30-56) – ongoing

Specific activities include:

1. Attributions based on microbial subtyping, more specifically frequency-based models of ESBL based on the distribution of AMR determinants. The database including ESBL data for source attribution using the frequency-based models is completed and analyses are ongoing.
2. Attribution based on a ML approach comparing the resistomes in human and various sources based on available metagenomic data.
3. A conceptual model for bidirectionality of ESBL transmission has been developed and is currently being parameterized with data for the Netherlands.

The task is awaiting results from WP3.

WP5: Conclusions and policy translation (M32-60)

WP5-T1- Technical expert evaluation (M41-57) - ongoing

It is considered as part of this task to turn the deliverable (D-JRPFZ-1-WP3.2) into a document/report for decision makers/risk managers for an overview of the advantages, limitation, and data requirements for the various attribution models.

WP5-T2- Translating source attribution estimates into options for control policies (M33-58) - ongoing

An online stakeholder workshop was held on January 22, 2021. Around 20 participants from EFSA, ECDC, EURLs, other relevant EJP projects, as well as DISCoVeR WP-leads joined the meeting.

A Master student enrolled at DTU has in collaboration with ISS addressed the deliverable D-JRPFZ-1-WP5.1: Map of the current existing control programme and intervention strategies to mitigate the risk of transmission of *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, VTEC, and antimicrobial resistance to human at the EU and national level. This task was addressed by i) a scientific literature review (completed), ii) a review of grey literature (completed), and iii) a survey aimed at relevant national experts (completed, being reviewed). The survey was distributed through the OHEJP network and EFSA's zoonosis network. DG SANTÈ and EFSA have been informed about the survey and provided their endorsement as well as their help to distribute the survey. The MSc student handed in her thesis on June 7. Finally, one abstract was selected for oral presentation at the OHEJP ASM on June 9-11 in Copenhagen.

A summary of the literature review and the overall results of the survey was submitted as deliverable D-JRPFZ-1-WP5.1 in M48.

WP5-T3- Final recommendations in a OH frame (M49-60) –

Not started yet.

4. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
20	D-JRP16-1.1	Mapping of knowledge gaps and recommendations for new data generation and method development	M28	M33		Uploaded to Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5825542#.YdcJyWjMKUk	1/5
20	D-JRP16-1.2	Data Management Plan	M30	M35		The DMP can be found here	3
20	D-JRP20-2.5	Database/sharing platform solution established	M36	M42/M48		Confidential – only partners has access to the WGS data selected for the project. By the end of the project, all data used for peer-review papers will be uploaded to publicly available genomic	5

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						<p>archives such as ENA. Some of the data used are already at ENA. A short document describing the data-sharing platform is uploaded to Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/record/5828337#.Ydh0XGjMKUk</p> <p>This deliverable was compiled in December 2021, but the data-sharing platform was available from June 2021.</p>	
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP2.6	Description of data generated for <i>Salmonella</i> , <i>Campylobacter</i> , Shigatoxin-producing <i>E. coli</i> (STEC) and their AMR determinants	M48		M49	<p>Public. https://zenodo.org/record/5828412#.YdmekGjMKUk</p>	3/5

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP3.1	Describe novel approaches for source attribution using microbial subtyping	M48		M49	Deliverable being reviewed by partners. Will be uploaded imminently.	7
20	D-JRPFZ-1-WP3.2	Report on the critical and quantitative evaluation of existing and novel source attribution methods	M48		M51	Delayed as the task lead has been involved in COVID-19 management.	
20	D-JRP20-5.1	Map of the current existing control programme and intervention strategies to mitigate the risk of transmission of <i>Salmonella</i> , <i>Campylobacter</i> , VTEC, and antimicrobial resistance to human at the EU and national level.	M42	M48		Public. Delayed due to COVID-19. https://zenodo.org/record/5812282#.YdhU42jMJPY	1

** Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities ; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);*

Milestones

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
20	M-JRP20-01	Identification of Project Management Team	M25	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-02	First annual project meeting	M27	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-03	Completion of mapping of knowledge gaps and recommendations for new data generation and method development	M28	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-04	Identification of types of samples to investigate and for which species to include in the sampling	M29	Yes		Achieved M32
20	M-JRP20-05	Framework for evaluation of Microbial subtyping methods	M33	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-06	Methods for source attribution based on outbreak data evaluated	M33	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-07	Format for results presentation (standard structure) for all pathogens and AMR	M33	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-08	Mapping of data available for <i>Salmonella</i>	M34	Yes		

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
20	M-JRP20-09	Mapping of data available for <i>Campylobacter</i>	M34	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-10	Mapping of data available for VTEC	M34	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-11	Mapping of data available for AMR	M34	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-12	Protocol for presentation of results for <i>Salmonella</i> , <i>Campylobacter</i> , VTEC and AMR	M34	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-13	Framework for using phylogenetic data for source attribution	M36	No	M51	The milestone more difficult to achieve than expected. Need other WGS modelling tasks to be completed first, as the results will feed into the phylogenetic approach.
20	M-JRP20-14	Comparison of data and methods for each pathogen and AMR	M36	Yes		Achieved M38
20	M-JRP20-15	Framework for using metagenomic data for attribution of antimicrobial resistant	M39	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-16	Results from evaluation of microbial subtyping methods using artificial data	M40	No	M54	Task has been delayed due to prioritisation of other activities.

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
20	M-JRP20-17	Description of method of source attribution using existing case-control	M42	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-18	Method for source attribution by risk assessment evaluated	M42	Yes		
20	M-JRP20-19	Second annual project meeting hosted by ANSES	M41	No	Cancelled	No physical meeting due to COVID-19
20	M-JRP20-20	Completion of control programme and intervention strategies mapping	M41	Yes		Achieved M48
20	M-JRP20-21	Update of Data Management Plan	M41	Yes		Achieved M49
20	M-JRP20-22	Completion of data collection	M42	Yes		Data collection has been delayed due to COVID-19. Almost all expected data were uploaded to our data-sharing platform by M48, although a few additional data may still roll in in the beginning of Y5.
20	M-JRPFZ-1-23	Completion of dataset for all species	M48	Yes		

5. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
V. Lopez-Chavarrias, M. Ugarte-Ruiz, M. C. B. Asensio, A. Olarra, M. Garcia, J.L. Saez, C. De Frutos, T. Serrano, I. Perez, M.A. Moreno, L. Domínguez, J. Alvarez Monitoring of Antimicrobial Resistance to Aminoglycosides and Macrolides in <i>Campylobacter coli</i> and <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> from healthy livestock in Spain (2002-2018) doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2021.689262 https://zenodo.org/record/5109549#.YUyifLgzZM0	Yes		Yes

Additional output

Abstracts from the ASM One Health EJP 2021, 9-11 June, 2021:

- Sara Perestrelo, Guido Correia Carreira, Lars Valentin, Jennie Fischer, Yvonne Pfeifer, Guido Werner, Judith Schmiedel, Linda Falgenhauer, Annemarie Käsbohrer. "Source Attribution of ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* in Germany" Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP 2021, 9-11 June, Denmark and online.
- Guido Correia Carreira, Annemarie Käsbohrer. "Mapping knowledge gaps of source attribution methods and sources for zoonoses and resistant bacteria using a rapid review approach". Oral presentation held at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Rebekka Sørensen, Tine Hald, Gaia Scavia, Michele Luca D'errico. "MAPPING THE CURRENT EXISTING HAZARDS' CONTROL PROGRAM AND STRATEGIES IN THE VARIOUS SECTORS AND TRACTS OF THE ANIMAL-ENVIRONMENTFOOD-HUMAN CHAIN IN EU". Oral presentation held at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Mónica Oleastro, Maria Leonor Lemos, Alexandra Nunes, Paulo Martins da Costa. "A PRELIMINARY STUDY OF *CAMPYLOBACTER* SPP. IN DOGS IN PORTUGAL – A ONE HEALTH PERSPECTIVE". Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Ana Amaro, Célia Leão, Patrícia Themudo, Lurdes Clemente. "EMERGENCE OF MULTIDRUG RESISTANT *SALMONELLA* INFANTIS ST32 IN THE POULTRY INDUSTRY, PORTUGAL 2016-2020". Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Leonor Silveira, Sofia Ribeiro, Iúri Lopes, Mariana Fontes, Rita Castro, Frederico Lemos, Angela Pista. "Prevalence and characterization of *Salmonella* spp. and pathogenic *Escherichia coli* in food-producing animals in Portugal". Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.
- Pista A., Ribeiro S., Fontes M., Batista R., Coelho A., Furtado R., Lopes T., Moura I., Saraiva M., Maia C., Belo-Correia C., Lopes I., Silveira L. "Prevalence and characterization of pathogenic *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* spp. in wild animals in mainland Portugal". Poster presentation at the ASM One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting 2021, 9-11 June in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.

Other abstracts:

- Sara Perestrelo, Guido Correia Carreira, Lars Valentin, Jennie Fischer, Yvonne Pfeifer, Guido Werner, Judith Schmiedel, Linda Falgenhauer, Annemarie Käsbohrer. "To which extend do humans and animals share the same reservoirs of ESBL producing *Escherichia coli*?" Poster presentation at the Junior Scientific Zoonosis Meeting 2021, 3-4 June, online.
- Célia Leão, Ana Amaro, Patrícia Themudo, Lurdes Clemente. Insights into pESI like megaplasmid of *Salmonella* Infantis ST32 spreading in the poultry industry. Poster presentation at the MICROBIOTEC 2021, 23-26 November.
- Angela Pista, Sofia Ribeiro, Mariana Fontes, Iúri Lopes, Rita Castro, Leonor Silveira. Detection and characterization of Enteropathogenic *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella* spp. in cats and dogs from a Lisbon area kennel - A ONE HEALTH perspective. Poster presentation at the XVII Congresso Internacional Veterinário 2021, 22-23 October, Santa Maria da Feira, Portugal.

Scientific reports:

- Eric Evers (RIVM, The Netherlands), Annemarie Käsbohrer (BfR, Germany). “Assessing and developing source attribution approaches based on risk assessment”, OHEJP DISCoVeR WP3-T7, milestone M-JRPFZ-1-18, 10 February 2021.
- Mayu Horie. “Application of Machine Learning in source attribution of foodborne bacteria”, special MSc student project report, Utrecht University and RIVM, The Netherlands.

Master theses:

- Brinch, M. L. Development of a WGS-based source attribution model for *Campylobacter*. MSc Thesis, June 2021, National Food Institute, Research group for Genomic Epidemiology, Technical University of Denmark.
- Sørensen, R. A. Mapping the currently existing hazards’ control programmes and strategies in the various sectors and tracts of the animal-environment-food-human chain in EU/EFTA/EEA. MSc Thesis, June 2021, National Food Institute, Research group for Genomic Epidemiology, Technical University of Denmark.
- Wang, B. Development of a WGS-based source attribution model for *Salmonella*. MSc Thesis, September 2021, National Food Institute, Research group for Genomic Epidemiology, Technical University of Denmark.

Outcomes

We expect by the end of the project to have identified and filled important knowledge, methodological and data gaps for source attribution of zoonotic pathogens and AMR determinants through systematic collection and analysis of existing and new data and by applying existing, modified and novel approaches.

Besides scientific publications describing the developed methods, we will also produce publications that in detail document the project’s datasets that we have collected. This will, hopefully, be useful for other researchers that will find it interesting to explore our data and models. In particular, we believe that the multi-country dataset compiled on STEC isolates and sequences from humans and different animal and food sources is quite unique and could provide novel insights to the epidemiology of STEC in EU MS. In addition, we plan to make models available, primarily as R-scripts. Each script will link to the exact dataset used in the model.

Finally, in an overall report, we will make recommendations on how source attribution estimates can be translated to policy action to support the surveillance, control and prevention of foodborne infections in EU. The report will be aimed at stakeholders such as ECDC and EFSA, and farmer and consumer organisations.

6. [Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries](#)

As part of WP5, we held a stakeholder web meeting on January 22, 2021 inviting EFSA, ECDC and the relevant EURLs to discuss how DISCoVeR results can contribute the work of the stakeholders and vice versa.

In addition, one of our partners is also part of OHEJP WP5, and she will inform about DISCoVeR’s activities in relevant fora (Stakeholder committee, Scientific Steering Board (SSB) and Program Owner Committee (POC)), and potentially asking DISCoVeR to give a presentation at a later stage. We are also linking in with projects ADONIS, ORION and MATRIX to coordinate potentially overlapping activities.

7. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	+
Delay in work plan execution	+
Conflicts within the consortium	-
Lack of commitment of partners	+
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	++
Poor intra-project relationship	-
Potential entry/exit of partners	+
Other risks (please describe)	-

JRP21-FBZ3.1-BIOPIGEE

1. Summary of the work carried out in year 4

The OHEJP BIOPIGEE project aims to identify effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures to control hepatitis E virus (HEV) and *Salmonella* occurrence in European pig farming. These two pathogens represent important zoonotic organisms that are difficult to detect and control on a pig farm. To achieve this, nineteen partner institutes from 12 countries are carrying out together comprehensive literature reviews, field and experimental studies, expert surveys and risk modelling (organised in Workpackages, WP). The collated information will be disseminated to stakeholders (farmers, veterinarians, advisors) in illustrations, a support tool and workshops. BIOPIGEE has been successfully running since January 1st 2020:

WP1: The BIOPIGEE Mid-term meeting took place as a virtual 2-day-event in March 2021. Collaborations with other projects were initiated and realised. A new task defined ‘biosecurity measures’ to harmonise understanding across project tasks. The data management plan was updated following advice from the DMP group. Several changes in the project plan were coordinated to cope with consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic. A 6-month-extension of the project was requested in agreement with all partner institutes.

WP2: A BIOPIGEE biosecurity questionnaire was applied in farms of several partner countries. This task was half a year delayed due to the pandemic situation but is now complete with questionnaires collected from 262 farms. A slaughterhouse online survey on best biosecurity practice was designed and carried out in seven participating countries (DE, CZ, EE, IT, AT, UK and NL). Sampling methods for slaughterhouses were agreed and bacteriological samples collected from two slaughterhouses (in CZ, IT). Longitudinal field studies are heavily affected by the pandemic but were initiated (in UK, IT, NL).

WP3: A HEV infectivity assay was developed successfully to be used to detect infectious HEV in samples of different origin. It may be included in a method for assessing the persistence of infectious HEV in surface samples. A method on how to test effectivity of disinfectants using the HEV infectivity assay and the method for testing persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers were established. *Salmonella* isolates for testing were selected. The comparison of methods and planning of how to test effectiveness of disinfectants is ongoing.

WP4: Pig movement data were obtained from UK and France, but considerable work was needed to work around data privacy issues with the UK data and they could not be fully integrated in the time available. It was not possible to obtain movement data from Italy or Germany in time. Draft results of the network model with the French data have been produced, including simulations of some on-farm biosecurity interventions. Despite delays due to staff resourcing and COVID-19, work is underway to adapt the previous *Salmonella* QMRA for HEV and integrate the network model with the QMRA.

WP5: The catalogue of biosecurity measures to reduce HEV and *Salmonella* prevalence was revised to ensure consistent data and safe updates. A systematic literature review and meta-analysis on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures against *Salmonella* and HEV in pig farms were carried out. In addition, literature on pathogenic *E. coli* was studied to complement knowledge about *Salmonella* based on the similarity of the pathogens. An expert panel from T2.1 (scientists) was expanded to incorporate knowledge of also e.g. practitioners, advisors. The panel assessed relevance of biosecurity measures to reduce *Salmonella* and/or HEV in pig herds in an online survey (T5.4). Results were analysed.

WP6: Illustrations of examples for good biosecurity were collected at our web group from WP2. Planning of workshops was amended due to the pandemic, physical conferences were cancelled. For the first workshop, national events serve to report and discuss project results with stakeholders. The second workshop was a web meeting between the project group and the expert panel from T5.4. A relevant conference for hosting the third workshop was identified and its organisation is ongoing. A BIOPIGEE glossary was developed.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1 Project coordination and integration of results (M25-M54)

The project management, development of data management and provision of project deliverables and reports are ongoing tasks until the end of the project.

WP1-T1- Project management and meeting organisation (M25-60)

The BIOPIGEE Mid-term meeting took place virtually on 2nd/3rd March 2021 (organised with APHA) where all WPs and Tasks presented their work, results, challenges and further plans which were discussed with the group. Four quarterly WP leader meetings and collaborations with other projects and institutions were arranged. An online glossary of relevant terms in BIOPIGEE has been developed between task groups in cooperation with the MATRIX project. The BIOPIGEE website, shared documents (uploaded to the BfR Knime server) and data reports from a survey-tool for T2.2 have been continuously managed. The change of leadership in WP4 was accompanied to guarantee a smooth hand over of coordinating tasks. Since several tasks of the project are affected by the pandemic situation (farm visits, lab work, workshops), changes in the timeline of tasks and consequences for links between Tasks/WPs were coordinated. The Gantt Chart and list of due dates for deliverables and milestones was modified accordingly. In agreement with all project partners, despite budgetary consequences, a 6-month-extension of the project was requested (April '21) in order to enable fulfilment of planned tasks. The work plans of all WPs for Y5, 2022, have been modified together with WP-leaders taking a 6 months extension into consideration. The deputy project leader, Veit Zoche-Golob left BfR and the BIOPIGEE project and his support with the publication management was transferred to the project leader Elke Burow for transitional supervision.

WP1-T1-ST1 Definition of biosecurity measure (M39-50)

The new subtask "Definition of 'biosecurity measure' across WPs/Tasks in BIOPIGEE" (T1.1.1) was identified and initiated. The group developed a common understanding of 'biosecurity measure' across project tasks based on applied inclusion/exclusion criteria from five BIOPIGEE task groups and a literature scoping review including four scientific databases. The definition proposal will be presented via a poster at the ONE-Health, Environment, society-2022 conference. In addition, an article manuscript presenting and discussing the definition in detail is in preparation.

WP1-T2-Development of data management plan (M25-60)

A draft of the data management plan (DMP) was developed with WP leaders and entered into the CDP-tool in 2020. From the CDP-tool, an excel sheet of the DMP was downloaded, uploaded to the BIOPIGEE website and transferred to a shared document hosted at the BfR-server (link in FORUM at the BIOPIGEE

website). Updates made by WP leaders in the shared document in June, August, October and December 2021 were transferred to CDP.

New options to describe complex datasets with multiple choice for species and matrices were considered together with the option to split data sets as was informed in a training session by the DMP group in March 2021. Also contact information, keywords, description and kind of file were updated for each data set as suggested by DMP group during 2021. The DMP will be updated repeatedly until the end of the project.

The DMP includes 21 different kinds of datasets which are closely related to deliverables of the project. It is research data and methodologies, mainly related to pigs as focused in the project. Most of the data are intended to be published in scientific journals and are therefore confidential until publication. Location, where to find the data (e.g. website, Zenodo) is listed together with information whom to contact for each dataset (names, institutions and email addresses), which have a unique identifier in the plan. There is little to consider for ethical aspects as data will be anonymised and no personal or identifiable data will be included. Data related keywords from ORION were selected on a drop down list in the CDP tool and included. Thereby, the plan takes into account the following aspects: data summary, making data findable, making data openly accessible, making data interoperable, increase data re-use (FAIR data principles), data dissemination, data security and ethical aspects.

WP1-T3-Provision of project deliverables and reports (M25-60)

The publication plan for the project, arranged in a shared document, was modified to indicate the status of publications (intended, in work, submitted, accepted, published) for WP2-5 and is being continuously managed. Here also references and links of finalised publications are collated. Deliverables are getting continuously collected and distributed (uploaded to the private web-group and to Zenodo). Reporting is a repeated task. The AWP-Y5 was amended together with the WP leaders, considering a 6-months-extension, was submitted to OHEJP coordination team (9th June 2021) and was silently accepted (without any comments) by the OHEJP coordination. The 9M-report 2021 was prepared together with the WP leaders.

WP2 Biosecurity effectiveness studies

WP2-T2- Application of the biosecurity protocol (M27-M48)

Although COVID-19 restrictions had a large impact on the progress of the task, as of 1st December 2021, all of the planned farm visits (262) had taken place and questionnaires uploaded onto the electronic data capture system from nine countries (DE, NL, CZ, PL, BG, UK, AT, IT, EE) with additional data provided by two other countries (SE and FR). Almost 4,000 samples were collected from field visits and tested for *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus (HEV), with additional data provided from national *Salmonella* monitoring, to help categorise farms as being at high or low risk for these pathogens. Analysis is being completed to determine the significant associations between biosecurity measures and pathogen risk category. Photos were collected from farm visits to show case examples of good and bad biosecurity practice, to add to project documentation in work package 6.

The deliverable WP2.9 “Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at farm” was submitted in December 2021.

WP2-T3 Slaughterhouse biosecurity practices (M37-48)

An online survey was designed to collect information on best biosecurity practice in slaughterhouses. The survey took place in seven countries (DE, CZ, EE, IT, AT, UK and NL) with 32 responses. The survey included 20 questions organised into the sections general, transportation, lairage (waiting area at the slaughterhouse where arriving pigs are kept until slaughter), scalding, singeing, evisceration, carcass splitter, decontamination and chilling. The content was based on information about biosecurity measures’ effectiveness presented in peer-reviewed literature and on opinions from slaughterhouse experts within the partner institutes.

Sampling methods for visits to slaughterhouses were agreed within the team. Bacteriological samples were collected from three slaughterhouses, one in CZ and two in IT. The samples were collected along the slaughter line to help validate information on the effectiveness of biosecurity practices. The evidence from the studies are being collated into a report on the effectiveness of slaughterhouse biosecurity.

The deliverable WP2.8 “Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at slaughterhouses” was submitted in December 2021.

WP2-T4 Field studies (M25-M54)

This task has been largely affected by COVID-19 lockdowns in the participating counties. However, longitudinal studies are planned to start soon in the UK and in IT. In NL, the research focus for this task has been updated and will now focus on internal biosecurity and spread of HEV between pens. A pilot study on four farms has been completed, the results of which were analysed and informed the final study protocol (choice of farm and age groups to sample) for the longitudinal study. Unfortunately, recruitment in NL has been delayed due to farmers withdrawing participation or being found to be HEV negative.

WP3 Impact of disinfection on persistence of pathogens in biofilm

WP3 and its lab work is partly delayed due to COVID-19 pandemic and consequences.

WP3-T1 Comparison of methods for testing the effect of disinfectants (M25-46)

Parameters to compare methods for testing disinfectants effectivity were described. Reference strains to be used by all participating laboratories have been defined. Comparison of biofilm methods between labs is ongoing. Methods to continue with in Task 2-ST2 have been defined.

The deliverable WP3.7 “Assessed methods for testing disinfectants on *Salmonella* in biofilm” was produced and submitted in August 2021.

WP3-T2 Effect of disinfectants on biofilm-associated wild type *Salmonella* (M25-50)

This task is ongoing. Disinfectants and conditions and biofilm methods to be used have been defined. Wild type strains have been selected and sent to all participating laboratories.

WP3-T2-ST1: Selection of wild type *Salmonella* isolates (M25-M36)

A panel of *Salmonella* isolated from UK pig farms have been screened for their biofilm abilities using two methodologies. From this panel, six biofilm-forming *Salmonella* isolates, from serovars Derby and Typhimurium, have been selected for the use in Task 2-ST2.

WP3-T2-ST2 Assessing the effect of disinfectants (M37-M56)

Each lab will use the already locally established biofilm model for testing the effectiveness of disinfectants. Lab work has been started, initial testing is ongoing.

WP3-T3- Study of HEV stability in relation to disinfection approaches (M25-M56)

HEV stability in microfilms will be studied using appropriate HEV infectivity assays which have been developed in WP3-T3-ST1, and will be further implemented in year 2 (and 3) of the project.

WP3-T3-ST1 Adaptation and implementation of HEV infectivity assay for testing biofilms (M25-M36)

The HEV infectivity assay was completed (deliverable 3.6). In this assay, primary hepatocytes are isolated from liver tissue of (HEV free) piglets using a collagenase treatment. The obtained primary hepatocytes are aliquoted and stored at -180°C until use. For the actual assay, the hepatocytes are seeded onto plates and inoculated with different samples potentially contaminated with HEV. A second method for testing of HEV infectivity, precision-cut liver slices (PCLS) has been developed also

and will be used further for validation of the hepatocytes assay (see above). Adaptations of the bioassay will be made as appropriate, to make it suitable for testing biofilms.

The deliverable WP3.6 “HEV infectivity assay is available” (M36) is implemented further. It has been tested on field samples and will be further validated using other HEV bioassays.

The deliverable WP3.5 “Method for testing persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers” was completed in June 2021.

WP3-T3-ST2 (M37- 48)

We investigated whether there was a correlation between the presence of HEV and *Salmonella* in faecal samples of pigs. No significant correlation had been seen, however more samples need to be tested to obtain reliable outcomes. Farm samples taken in biofilm areas need to be tested for the presence of infectious HEV. This part is still ongoing and can take place in the first months of 2022 depending on when we are allowed to sample the farms. The method how to sample the environment/biofilms has been developed and tested. Electrostatic Dust Collectors (EDC) are used to swab the environment/ biofilm. The virus has been eluted, which means adsorbed material was removed from the adsorbent, EDC, by means of a solvent, 5ml of cell culture medium in this case and tested for the presence of HEV with the use of real time PCR. In case of a positive result the sample will be grown in the HEV infectivity assay.

The deliverable WP3.14 “Information on the persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayer/biofilm” is depending on the results of deliverable WP3.20 due at the end of 2021.

WP3-T3-ST3 (M49-M56)

The deliverable WP3.20 “HEV infectivity test adapted for testing of HEV in biofilms” was delivered in December 2021.

WP4 Modelling of the cost and effectiveness of biosecurity measures

The lead of WP4 changed. The former leader Beate Pinior left AGES/Vetmeduni Vienna and the BIOPIGEE project. The former deputy Robin Simons (APHA) overtook the lead and Mathieu Andraud (ANSES) is new deputy.

WP4-T2- Stochastic simulations on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures (M33-M56)

WP4-T2-ST1- Data collection for the transmission models

The data collection phase for the network model was completed, but there were issues with obtaining pig movement data for some of the proposed case study countries. Data were obtained and successfully integrated into the model from France. Data were obtained from the UK, but due to data privacy issues, some data (e.g. information to identify individual farms) could not be shared. Considerable effort was put in to developing methods to allow geographical data to be used instead, but unfortunately this did not leave enough funding to fully integrate the UK data into the model and validate the results. The method is developed to allow this in the future, but the resource is unlikely to be available within BIOPIGEE. It was not possible to obtain movement data from Italy and while a potential source for similar data from Germany was identified, it was not possible to obtain the data in time.

Data collection for the QMRA is underway and has identified a number of potential gaps, particularly in relation to inactivation rates and dose-response for HEV, which we will look to resolve over the next year of the project.

WP4-T3- Merge of models into one QMRA (M33-M56)

WP4-T3-ST1- Different transmission models will be matched to one QMRA zoonotic pathogen model

Draft results of the farm-to-slaughter network transmission model with the French data have been produced, including simulations of some on-farm biosecurity interventions. This work is currently in publication process.

Despite delays due to staff resourcing, COVID-19 and outbreak response work related to avian influenza, work is underway to adapt the previous *Salmonella* QMRA for HEV. This includes developing methodology for consumption of liver as a route of human HEV infection and a methodology to simulate the inactivation of HEV during cooking of liver. Data collection has identified a number of potential gaps, particularly in relation to cross-contamination rates at the slaughterhouse, inactivation rates and dose-response for HEV, which we will look to resolve over the next year of the project.

Discussions have taken place to ensure successful integration of the network model with the QMRA at the slaughterhouse stage. A poster on this process has been presented at the 2021 OHEJP annual meeting.

WP4-T4- Economic model of biosecurity measures across Europe

This task has not yet worked on until M46 as the initial task leader, Beate Pinior/Conrady, left the project. A new member, Clara Bester took over this task in M47. Initial work concentrates on analysing the cost-related data collected within WP2 Task2 during the farm visits in several countries. Furthermore, a concept for the cost-benefit analysis is being developed taking into account outcomes from a literature review conducted within the COHESIVE project.

WP5 Benchmark of biosecurity practice

This work package was led by Veit Zoche-Golob from M35 until M47. Task T5.1, T5.2 and T5.4 have been intensively worked on and a first publication is in preparation, further publications are planned. The WP5 lead is currently being vacant and the recruitment process is ongoing at BfR. Delays in this WP are possible depending on the duration of the replacement.

WP5-T1- Data integration from WP2-4 in catalogue of biosecurity measures (M27-56)

The catalogue of biosecurity measures to reduce HEV and/or *Salmonella* prevalence was revised to consider all relevant data from the project, to ensure consistent data and safe updates. Procedures for inputs and updates as well as backups were defined. Data was updated by the first results from T5.2 and T5.4. All BIOPIGEE participants were invited to supplement the BIOPIGEE catalogue of biosecurity measures. The catalogue is getting updated continuously with identified biosecurity measures and estimates of their effectiveness. This task is ongoing.

WP5-T2- Literature review/meta-analysis (M27-50)

Ongoing. A first round of a systematic literature review about the effectiveness of biosecurity measures specifically against *Salmonella* and HEV in pigs farms is finished with the help of 10 reviewers from 7 countries, who evaluated about 1650 articles found in literature databases and according to a harmonised scheme. Relevant data were extracted and estimates of the effectiveness of the identified biosecurity measures were summarised by meta-analyses. The risk of bias of the included articles was assessed. First effect estimates were offered to WP4 at the end of M38 and entered in the catalogue of biosecurity measures (T5.1). The systematic literature and meta-analyses was then updated and expanded, including biosecurity measures to reduce the occurrence of pathogenic *E. coli* in pig herds. In this round, a total of 11 reviewers overall participated from 7 different countries. Tutorials on literature screening, data extraction and risk of bias analysis were held to instruct participants. In this updating turn, a software-based machine learning tool, ASReview was applied alongside the manual screening by reviewers, with thanks to the collaboration from the University of Utrecht. In total for the manual screening, 5130 article titles were initially included and 1185 abstracts were screened in

duplicate. For ASReview, 4068 articles were uploaded onto the software and 536 abstracts were screened. After further full text screening, 82 articles moved to data extraction and finally risk of bias analysis, with a final sample of 54 papers deemed to have sufficient primary data to be extracted for the analysis. Data cleaning of the extracted estimates has not been finished yet and is ongoing by four partners throughout December and January. Work can be delayed due to a lack of staff at BfR and elsewhere to conduct the analysis of the extracted effect estimates.

WP5-T3-Machine learning approaches (M53-58)

This task has not started yet and conduction is unclear as the task leader left the project and replacement is unclear. Partly, the additional use of ASReview replaced this task.

WP5-T4- Expert panel to add estimations on effectiveness/ weights (M33-52)

The questionnaire about biosecurity measures in primary pig production, developed in T2.1 and applied on farms in T2.2, was adapted for an expert survey to assess the importance of biosecurity measures to reduce *Salmonella* and HEV occurrence in different pig production systems.

For this, questions were reworded to best practice statements, considering results from T5.2 literature review, and the initial expert panel from T2.1 (scientists) was expanded to additionally incorporate knowledge of other stakeholders like practitioners, advisors, etc.. We found marked differences between the veterinary and consulting systems within the pig sectors of the different partner states. These differences in the systems considerably influence the understanding of the roles within the pig sector of different professions. We finally identified and agreed on superior grouping of expertise and representatives from participating countries were recruited for the panel. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the interviews were carried out with an online questionnaire.

The experts were asked to: 1) rate their own expertise for the pathogens HEV and *Salmonella*, for the husbandry systems and for biosecurity; 2) select the setting(s) they wanted to answer questions for (settings: HEV*indoor keeping, HEV*outdoor keeping, *Salmonella**indoor keeping, *Salmonella**outdoor keeping); 3) rank the effectiveness of eight biosecurity measure categories, scoring them between 1-80 based on their importance for pathogen prevention/control, and 4) within each category, score each specific measure, based on its relevance to control within each setting, between 1 (least relevant) and 5 (most relevant). Responses from 46 experts (from PL, UK, DE, BG, AT, IT, SE, NL, BE, EE, NO) could be included in the analysis. The experts' answers to the questionnaire were analysed.

Preliminary results indicate that, no biosecurity category stood out, with all category contributing to some extent. The experts also demonstrated the high importance of the majority of the biosecurity measures within the categories, nonetheless activities related to animal movement/mixing as well as cleaning/disinfection practices were consistently ranked high for all settings. Additionally, gaps relating to outdoor farming and HEV in pigs were identified and should be targeted in future research.

A manuscript for this study is intended to be submitted to a scientific journal and is currently in the internal review process.

This task is ongoing.

WP5-T5 Benchmark system for effectiveness of biosecurity (M51-58)

This task has not started yet.

WP6 Dissemination

WP6-T1- Assembly and development of biosecurity information (M27-60)

WP6-T1-ST1- Identification of appropriate websites or other online channels

So far, 21 web sites in 6 countries have been identified for dissemination and are listed in a shared document. The link is accessible for the consortium via the OHEJP BIOPIGEE website. This task is carried out on an ongoing basis and the list is amended and updated throughout the project.

WP6-T1-ST2a Provision of information for farming schools and websites

Illustrations of examples for good biosecurity (pictures), which are planned to be used in this task, have been collected in WP2. Pictures from different partner countries' farms have been uploaded to an assembly at our website. Ideas about the content of this material have been exchanged with an advisory service in Germany as well as at the online workshop between the BIOPIGEE project group and the T5.4 expert panel. At the beginning of 2022, a meeting with a German farming education centre is planned to find out how the material should be set up to address farming pupils. This task is ongoing.

WP6-T1-ST2b Provision of slaughterhouse protocol to slaughter industry/related associations

A slaughterhouse biosecurity protocol/questionnaire has been developed and sent to slaughterhouses in seven countries (DE, CZ, EE, IT, AT, UK and NL).

The deliverable WP6.15 "Biosecurity protocol on slaughterhouse provided" was completed in December 2021.

WP6-T2- Development of a support tool to calculate cost effectiveness (M55-60)

This task has not started yet.

WP6-T3- Organisation of a workshop-series (M25-58)

WP6-T3-ST1 Identification of relevant stakeholders

Ongoing. For the second workshop, an expert panel, recruited for T5.4, was invited for a web-meeting to discuss BIOPIGEE results.

WP6-T3-ST2 Identification of relevant conferences

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, physical conferences have been cancelled. Relevant conferences for hosting the third workshop in conjunction with a conference, were listed in our publication list, options have been discussed in the WP leader meeting in June and September 2021. The ESPHM has been identified for hosting the Workshop. The organisation is ongoing and the task group is in discussion with the conference team to open the arrangement for not only in person but also a hybrid, or even full online version. This will be re-assessed with consideration of the pandemic situation at the beginning of 2022.

WP6-T3-ST3 Organisation of Workshop 1 (M25-54)

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the first workshop was cancelled. National information events are planned instead. In Germany, participation in information days of and with animal health services took place to inform and discuss results from BIOPIGEE (25th Nov 2021). Here, contacts and exchange with a German consultancy service for biosecurity practice in pig farming and with a German training centre for farming apprenticeship were initiated. This exchange may be beneficial with testing and giving feedback when designing the information material in T6.1.2a and the support tool in T6.2.

WP6-T3-ST4 Organisation of Workshop 2 (M40-48)

An online workshop was held on 14th December 2021. Listed experts for JRP21-WP5-T4 were invited to this half-day-workshop where preliminary results from the BIOPIGEE project were presented and

discussed. There were in total 62 participants from 11 countries, 35 project members and 27 externals. The panel was represented by 17 participants.

The presentations gave a good overview about first findings. Main points in the discussions were how we define and delimit biosecurity measures in pig production and what has been so far learned about transmission of HEV between pigs. Moreover, a focus of this workshop was the exchange of ideas about how and where to disseminate outcome of the project to spread knowledge on best biosecurity practice in pig production.

WP6-T5- Press release (M36-39)

Additionally, a press release about activities in the project has been drafted between partners (DE, UK, AT, SE) and published at the beginning of 2021.

WP6-T6- Glossary of terms used in BIOPIGEE (M46-48)

A glossary of terms used in BIOPIGEE has been developed between tasks and is hosted in the infrastructure of the OHEJP MATRIX project. The BIOPIGEE Glossary can be accessed via a link on the OHEJP BIOPIGEE website since 17th December 2021.

3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
21	D-JRP21-WP1.13	Project report 2nd year submitted	48	48, pending		Has been uploaded to the project web group and submitted as first version to OHEJP WP3. Based on the comments, it was revised and is planned to submit in M49	8 (reporting)
21	D-JRP21-WP1.19	Revised data management plan submitted	48	48 (49 last update in CDP)	Next 50/final 60	According to OHEJP DMP group end of the project; repeated updates in CDP/Project Group; next delivery is in M49/50	8 (reporting)
21	D-JRP21-WP1.2	First draft of data management plan finished	30	34 (website)		The DMP is uploaded to the project website, is entered and public in the CDP tool, gets repeatedly updated in a shared	8 (reporting)

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
						document and changes transferred to CDP; OHEJP DMP group recommends to upload only the final DMP to Zenodo.	
21	D-JRP21-WP1.4	Project report 1st year submitted	36	36		Public, 10.5281/zenodo.4361090 https://zenodo.org/record/4361090	8 (reporting)
21	D-JRP21-WP2.1	Biosecurity protocol (addressing measures to control <i>Salmonella</i> and HEV) designed for data collection in the field	28	29 (44 zenodo)		Public as short version since 31.08.2021, 10.5281/zenodo.5336900 https://zenodo.org/record/5336900	2
21	D-JRP21-WP2.12	Produce report on evidence gathered by field studies	48		54	Delayed by six months due to problems with capability to conduct longitudinal trials during COVID-19 lockdowns and	

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
						related issues with farmer recruitment.	
21	D-JRP21-WP2.8	Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at slaughterhouses	42	48		Uploaded to the website, public as short version, 10.5281/zenodo.5774876 https://zenodo.org/record/5774876	4
21	D-JRP21-WP2.9	Quantified biosecurity effectiveness from applied biosecurity protocol at farm	42	48		Uploaded to the website, public as short version, 10.5281/zenodo.5792859 https://zenodo.org/record/5792859	4
21	D-JRP21-WP3.20	HEV infectivity test adapted for testing of HEVs in biofilm	48	48		Uploaded to the website, public as short version, 10.5281/zenodo.5793040 https://zenodo.org/record/5793040	1

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
21	D-JRP21-WP3.5	Method for testing persistence of infectious HEV in surface microlayers	36	42		Public, 10.5281/zenodo.4940091 https://zenodo.org/record/4940091 ; was delayed due to COVID-19 pandemic and consequences	2
21	D-JRP21-WP3.6	HEV infectivity assay available	36	36		Public as short version, 10.5281/zenodo.5242819 https://zenodo.org/record/5242819	2
21	D-JRP21-WP3.7	Assessed methods for testing disinfectants on <i>Salmonella</i> in biofilm	40	44		Public as short version, 10.5281/zenodo.5211242 https://zenodo.org/record/5211242	2
21	D-JRP21-WP4.11	Model Output: Number of animal cases with and without biosecurity measures	47		55	Delayed due to staff resourcing and COVI-19 issues.	

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
21	D-JRP21-WP6.10	Workshop 2 completed	42	48		Took place as virtual workshop on 14 th Dec, between project group and expert panel, report: 10.5281/zenodo.5806257 https://zenodo.org/record/5806257	5
21	D-JRP21-WP6.15	Biosecurity protocol on slaughterhouse provided	48	48		Uploaded to the website, public as short version, 10.5281/zenodo.5772529 https://zenodo.org/record/5772529	2
21	D-JRP21-WP6.3	Workshop 1 completed	30		54	Cancelled due to pandemic situation. It may be replaced by local national workshops to disseminate results.	5

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
21	M-JRP21-03	Relevant conferences for workshops to be held are identified	26	Yes (46)		Was delayed due to pandemic situation. It is planned to disseminate more findings in pre-conference-Workshop at the ESPHM on 11th March 2022
21	M-JRP21-05	Relevant stakeholders identified	28	Yes (36)		Was postponed due to the current COVID-19 situation (no workshops took place yet); Instead of stakeholders, a list of experts for a panel in T5.4 has been expanded (online table, link in BIOPIGEE private webgroup). These experts were finally invited for an online workshop to be hold in December 2021.
21	M-JRP21-06	Appropriate websites or other online channels for dissemination identified	30	Yes		List of web sites is being filled in an online table (link in BIOPIGEE private webgroup); Content will be continuously updated throughout the project
21	M-JRP21-07	Workshop 1 completed	30	Yes (47)		WP-leader decision: The workshop was cancelled due to COVID-19-outbreak, instead national information events in 2021/22 are planned (in Germany, animal health services were informed about our findings and discussed with at their conference in Nov 2021)

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
21	M-JRP21-09	First part of meta-analysis finished	36	Yes (38)		A literature review and meta-analysis was carried out. Was delayed due to partners involved in COVID-19-testing and missing personnel for 4 months at BfR
21	M-JRP21-12	Mid-term meeting successfully organized	39	Yes		
21	M-JRP21-13	Application of protocols across countries	40	Yes (46)		Was delayed and sample size slightly reduced in a few countries due to pandemic situation and restrictions for visiting farms.
21	M-JRP21-14	Relevant stakeholders re-identified	36	Yes (41)		As stated for M-JRP21-05, an expert panel is addressed instead. This was re-identified in M41.
21	M-JRP21-15	Transmission model adaptation based on available data	39	No (45)		Draft results for France complete, including some biosecurity interventions.
21	M-JRP21-16	Test methods to be used in JRP21-WP3-T2-ST2 are selected	40	No (46)		Milestone completed. Each lab will use the already locally established biofilm testing method for T2-ST2.
21	M-JRP21-18	Workshop 2 completed	40	Yes (48)		Was postponed to the second half of 2021, due to pandemic situation, changed to a virtual workshop with the expert panel from T5.4.
21	M-JRP21-19	Completion of farm visits and lab work	44	No	54	Postponed, due to pandemic situation and restrictions on visiting farms in some countries.

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
21	M-JRP21-20	Application of appropriate economic methods based on available data	45		51	Postponed to beginning of 2022 as this task is depending on delayed tasks.

4. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Propagation du virus de l'hépatite E de la case à la filière: analyse de réseaux complexes et modélisation, JRP conference/paper (accepted)	Yes	Yes	No
Complex network analysis to understand trading partnership in French swine production, PlosOne (revision in process)	Yes	No	Yes

Several publications, intended as peer-reviewed articles, are planned:

- In work: manuscripts in T1.1.1 on the definition of biosecurity measures (working title “What is a biosecurity measure? A definition proposal for farms and linked processing operations”) and in T5.4 on the expert opinion about relevance of biosecurity measures (working title “Prioritization of pig farm biosecurity for control of *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus infections, results of a survey among European experts”)
- Ideas/intended: manuscripts dealing with results (data evaluation is still in work) e.g. from T2.2/T2.3 on the application of biosecurity questionnaires in farms/slaughterhouses and effectiveness of measures to control *Salmonella* and HEV; from T2.4 on longitudinal studies about specific biosecurity measures in farms; from WP3 on test methods for disinfectants and biofilms/ for HEV stability; from T5.2 on literature review/meta-analysis about biosecurity measures in pig farming to reduce prevalence of HEV/*Salmonella*/pathogenic E.coli.

Additional output

Flyer

The Flyer describing briefly the BIOPIGEE project (D-JRP21-WP6.4) has been repeatedly used to e.g. inform participating farms in T2.2.

Posters/ Talks

- Catherine M^cCarthy, Robin Simons, Pachka Hammami, Mathieu Andraud, Stefan Widgren, Beate Conrady (2021). BIOPIGEE: Modelling of the cost and effectiveness of biosecurity measures. Poster at OHEJP ASM 2021. Copenhagen/Online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4911566>
- Claire Oastler, Mardjan Arvand, Katharina Konrat, Ane M. Osland, Vanessa Pfiffer, Lene Vestby, Becky Gosling (2021). Assessment of the biofilm forming capability of *Salmonella* isolates sourced from pig farms in Great Britain. Poster at OHEJP ASM 2021. Copenhagen/Online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5497688>
- Elke Burow (2021). Biosicherheitspraktiken für die Schweinehaltung in Europa / BIOPIGEE – Biosecurity practices for pig farming in Europe. Talk at the SGD conference 2021. Bad Sassendorf/online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5797014>
- Gergana Krumova-Valcheva, Albena Dimitrova, Eva Gyurova, Gergana Mateva, Mihail Milanov, Hristo Daskalov (2021). Hepatitis E in humans and pigs in Bulgaria (REVIEW). Poster at OHEJP ASM. Copenhagen/Online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4926180>
- Ivana Koláčková, Renáta Karpíšková, Tereza Gelbíčová, Zdenka Vacková, Jonaáš Vaňhara, Daniel Sperling (2021). *Salmonella* spp. in pig farms – still an issue?. Poster at ESPHM. Online.
- Nikolaus Huber, Elena L. Sassu, Gergana Krumova-Valcheva, Marina Meester, Ivana Kolackova, Petra Vasickova, Elisabeth Waller, Giuseppe Aprea, Annemarie Käsbohrer, Veit Zoche-Golob, Elke Burow (2021). Biosecurity measures reducing *Salmonell*ssp. and hepatitis E virus prevalence in pig farms: A systematic Review and Meta-analysis. Poster at OHEJP ASM 2021. Copenhagen/Online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4905616>
- Pachka Hammami, Nicolas Rose, Vladimir Grosbois, Stefan Widgren, Andrea Apolloni and Mathieu Andraud (2021). Live animal movements - Understand trade partners choices to predict chains of contact. Poster at SVEPM. Online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5005733>
- Pachka Hammami, Stefan Widgren, Vladimir Grosbois, Andrea Apolloni, Nicolas Rose, Mathieu Andraud (2021). Complex network analysis and Exponential Random Graph Models: Epidemiological implications of network structures. Talk at the Modah conference 2021. Online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5512130>
- Pachka Hammami, Stefan Widgren, Vladimir Grosbois, Andrea Apolloni, Nicolas Rose, Mathieu Andraud (2021). Multi-levels Hepatitis E Virus Spread In Various Epidemiological Contexts: Combining Complex Network Analysis & Disease Transmission Model. Talk at the CCS conference 2021. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5638730>
- Renate W. Hakze - van der honing; Sophie van Oort; Wim H.M. van der Poel (2021). Development of an ex vivo infectivity assay for Hepatitis E Virus. Poster at OHEJP ASM2021 Copenhagen/Online. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4946490>
- Richard P. Smith, M. J. Vilar, Hannah Jones, Elke Burow (2021). Preliminary description of biosecurity practices related to importing pig and semen onto European pig farms. Poster at OHEJP ASM 2021. Copenhagen. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4906860>

- Tarmo Niine, Arvo Viltrop, Imbi Nurmoja, Richard Smith, Elke Burow (2021). *Salmonella* in slaughterhouse!? What would be the right questions in that situation?. Society for Veterinary Epidemiology and Preventive Medicine (SVEPM) annual conference 2021. Online. Zenodo.<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5496890>
- Tarmo Niine, Arvo Viltrop, Imbi Nurmoja, Richard Smith, Elke Burow (2021). Identification of the best biosecurity practices in slaughterhouse in regards to *Salmonella* and hepatitis E virus. The One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting. OHEJP ASM 2021. Copenhagen/Online. Zenodo.<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5496902>

Press release

A press release about the project has been developed for creating awareness. Partners have translated it to local languages. It has been used as a template to spread information in Sweden, Austria and Germany (<https://www.sva.se/forskning/internationellt-samarbete/europeisk-samverkan-kring-livsmedelsburna-smittor/biopigee-ett-one-health-ejp-projekt>/<https://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/gefahr-im-schweinstall-ein-forschungsvorhaben-soll-die-ausbreitung-von-salmonellen-und-hepatitis-e-viren-begrenzen.pdf>). German farming magazines like topagrar and Rind&Schwein published a project description as well.

Social media

The annual BIOPIGEE progress meeting was advertised on the OHEJP twitter feed.

Websites

- The BfR website and BfR Twitter account informed about the project to increase its awareness - https://www.bfr.bund.de/en/biosecurity_practises_for_pig_farming_across_europe_ejp_biopigee_-252636.html
- <https://twitter.com/bfrde/status/1356619760625201152?lang=bq>
- The cross-sectional study within work package 2 task 2 was advertised on the British National Pig Association website - http://www.npa-uk.org.uk/Participants_wanted_for_biosecurity_study.html

Glossary

An online glossary of terms used in BIOPIGEE has been developed between task partners in collaboration with the MATRIX project. It is findable and accessible via the BIOPIGEE website, and directly

https://knime.bfr.berlin/knime/webportal/space/EJP_ORION/BIOPIGEE/BiopigeeGlossary?exec=abaebb77-0905-40f1-918c-2bfff0d1ab9

Outcomes

In the BIOPIGEE project, **biosecurity protocols** and **questionnaires**, tailored to identify measures against the specific and different pathogens *Salmonella* and **HEV on farm (indoor and outdoor system)** and at **slaughterhouse**, have been developed and harmonised among European countries. This is an important base for controlling occurrence of these zoonotic pathogens in the food chain. The listed measures will be available for use beyond the project period. The protocol development approach could serve as orientation for the adaptation of protocols to target other pathogens.

A common and deeper understanding of the meaning of biosecurity practice through the **definition of 'biosecurity measure'** was developed between the partners through a scope review and discussion

sessions in the project group. The definition can facilitate future communication on best biosecurity practice.

The **approach** for a **literature review** on the **complex** topic of effective **biosecurity measures** against different pathogens in the pig production has been developed for the use with an **international group** of several reviewers. Competences among partners were expanded. The approach, incl. produced tutorials, could be used further after the project.

Within the framework of work package 3 (impact of disinfection on persistence of pathogens in biofilm), harmonisation of methods among the participating laboratories was achieved with regard to the definition of reference strains and the selection of **test methods** for the effect of disinfectants on **Salmonella and HEV in biofilms**, and is still being in progress. This is new and important basic knowledge for the control of HEV and *Salmonella* occurrence.

5. *Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries*

A **collaboration** between BIOPIGEE and the **OHEJP MATRIX** was initiated. A number of relevant terms related to biosecurity practice in primary pig production were identified, defined and thereby common understanding developed within and between BIOPIGEE task groups and its partner institutes. It was agreed between Matrix and BIOPIGEE to implement an **online glossary** and to place its link on the OHEJP BIOPIGEE website. For this, the glossary was transferred and implemented in the infrastructure developed by MATRIX, which allows filtering and searching for terms and makes them easily accessible. The glossary is hosted on an BfR server. The OHEJP Communication Team supported this initiative by including a link towards the glossary at the BIOPIGEE website. Hereby, terms and definitions used in BIOPIGEE were made findable, accessible and reusable.

Dr Carla Gomes of **Animal Health Ireland** was engaged to see if there is potential for collaboration with a study that she is conducting on the effectiveness of biosecurity measures in Irish pig herds. There is the potential to add their data into the analyses of this project, although the Irish data will only be available towards the end of the project.

BIOPIGEE is in contact with the EU/global project **HealthyLivestock**. In a web-meeting between both projects on May 4th 2021, overlap between several parts in the projects was identified and we agreed that sharing insights is valuable. In particular, the key factors associated with disease prevention to be identified in HealthyLivestock and the key biosecurity measures associated with reduction of *Salmonella*/HEV prevalence to be identified in BIOPIGEE appear valuable to compare. It is intended to present this comparison in a joint paper. A next meeting between both projects is planned for spring 2022 when relevant tasks are further along in their process.

The **German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture** indicated interest in the T2.3 survey on biosecurity measures in the pig slaughter line. We forwarded a link to the German version of the questionnaire to the Ministry.

A **software-based machine learning tool, ASReview**, could be applied alongside and thereby supplement the extensive manual screening by reviewers in WP5 T5.2, with thanks to a collaboration from the **University of Utrecht (library, Felix Wejdema)**.

Thanks to a collaboration with the **German Meat Industry Association** (Verband der Fleischwirtschaft e.V.) and its support of our study, the survey on biosecurity measures at slaughter was sent out to more than 90 German slaughterhouses via the association's newsletter.

The Food Standards Agency in the UK are collaborating in the study, assisting with recruiting slaughterhouses into the study of slaughterhouse biosecurity effectiveness and also participating in reviewing and informing on relevant guidance documents. The project clearly benefits from **national collaborations with animal health services/veterinary services and practicing veterinarians**, which

partly have already existed before (in Germany, we could build on a proven cooperation with animal health services after the project ORRES) and partly are being built during the BIOPIGEE project, are of high importance and support for the project. These services/vets can recruit farms based on their client pool and are less restricted in accessing farms for sample collection/survey in the COVID-19 situation. They are also involved in our expert panel and will play an important role in the dissemination part as having a special interest in our findings and to disseminate them. In the expert panel, also staff with agricultural and teaching background (chambers of agriculture), scientists from different national (research) institutes (e.g. FLI in Germany) and universities (e.g. Vetmeduni Vienna/Leipzig, University of Rostock, Utrecht University), quality controllers of the pig production chain are included. Additionally, the cooperation with universities also makes it possible to obtain data and information from on-going national projects to fill any data gaps in our WPs. For instance, cooperation with Austrian swine clinics enables to recruit farms to participate in questionnaires and to obtain information about existing data sources. Thanks to these collaborations, we can build on a strong network of varied experts between practice and science in Europe.

To enable consideration of **pig movement information** for simulation studies in WP4, we intensified a contact to the **Chamber of Agriculture** in the **German federal state North Rhine-Westphalia** and initiated their collaboration with ANSES and AGES. The Chamber and institutes are exchanging information and ideas.

For a target group orientated preparation of dissemination material and tool (WP6), contacts were initiated between BfR and a **German public consultation service on biosecurity in pig farming** (Biosicherheitsberatung Schweinehaltung, Tiergesundheitsdienste der **Tierseuchenkasse Baden-Württemberg**). An additional contact was made with a **German training centre for farming apprenticeship** (Chamber of Agriculture North Rhine-Westphalia). Ideas are getting exchanged on how material and a tool can be designed to address the needs and interest of pig farmers. It was agreed to send draft material for feedback to the consultancy service and to keep them updated about new outcome from the project. A meeting with the training centre took place January 2022.

6. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	(Yes)
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	Yes

Additional information

Due to the pandemic, the project is delayed. Therefore an extension was requested and work plans were modified (for several tasks and links between them) in 2021, to enable the fulfilment of the project as much as possible. Many parts of the work have already been done. Still, important studies need to be carried out and finalised in 2022. As several partners are still or again involved in COVID-19 related tasks and as the dynamic pandemic situation can lead to a hardly plannable workload, this could lead to additional delays in the project because of conflicting tasks and change of contact partners when forwarding tasks to colleagues. However, the partners and the group have gained experience in this situation, trained handling of changes/ sharing of work even though there have only been virtual meetings for a long time. In addition to bilateral, WP-/Task-group and WP-leader

meetings, a Midterm meeting (2nd/3rd March) and a Workshop (14th December) enabled intensive exchange about current topics, strengthening the team and finding solutions in dialogues together. We hope to be able to also physically meet for Workshop 3 and the final project meeting in 2022.

Uncertainties in the budget planning in OHEJP at this stage and the currently advised caution with expenses and extension of employment contracts of temporary staff (with contracts until previous end of the project) can lead to questions at the partner institutes and in the project about how this can be handled. There is a risk that there will be too few staff available for the entire planned work.

BfR:

The WP5 leader and project deputy Veit Zoche-Golob has left the project (mid of November 2021). The position is currently vacant at BfR. A competent and fast replacement is important for the fulfilment of the planned work, even though much could already be implemented or finalised. Staff is also needed to organize and support within tasks.

AGES/VetMedUni:

The WP4 leader left the project (spring 2021). A replacement has been found in November 2021 and is currently getting introduced to the task.

AGES:

Due to the epidemiological situation in Austria and the related lock-downs, farm visits could not take place in full number as planned (fulfilled 2/3). Concerning the lab work, HEV investigations were delayed. This was initially due to difficulties in trying to harmonize the protocol to the one used in the project (finding reagents and establishing protocols to ensure standardization). Technical difficulties have been solved, but investigations were delayed as most of the staff has been busy with COVID-19 diagnostics.

APHA:

We are finding that farmers are less willing to engage with research during the COVID-19 pandemic, and this is slowing recruitment. However, this has improved during 2021.

WBVR:

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic work on this project was delayed at least 6 months. We aim to catch up as soon as possible. However, it remains unsure what delays in the end will be.

JRP22-FBZ4.1-TOXOSOURCES

1. Summary of the work carried out in year 4

TOXOSOURCES is a Joint Research Project of the One Health EJP that focuses on *Toxoplasma gondii* at the interface between humans, animals, food, and the environment.

Toxoplasma gondii is a foodborne parasite that causes a high disease burden. The infection can be acquired by ingesting oocysts (environmental pathway) or tissue cysts (meatborne pathway). The relative contributions of the two pathways to the infection and disease in humans remain unknown, partly due to a lack of appropriate methods. Environmental contamination with *T. gondii* oocysts is understudied and likely underestimated due to the lack of suitable harmonised sampling approaches and detection methods.

TOXOSOURCES investigates the relative contributions of the different transmission routes and sources of *T. gondii* infection using multidisciplinary approaches. The project is developing new methods and yielding new knowledge, and it has both ambition and potential to advance science in the field.

The TOXOSOURCES consortium has collected data for a multicentre quantitative microbiological risk assessment for *T. gondii*: a multicentre quantitative exposure survey was conducted, and systematic literature reviews yielded estimates of prevalence of the infection in a high number of animal host species as well as in fresh produce and the environment. After an extensive literature review to support the selection of a method to detect *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce, a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) was developed, implemented and validated, and is being applied in a multicentre pilot survey on ready-to-eat salads. The project has selected promising antigens for exploring serology for detecting *T. gondii* infections caused by oocysts, and an unprecedented effort of whole genome sequencing of *T. gondii* isolates was used to identify polymorphic marker regions for the establishment of a new typing method to detect within-genotype variation. The developed SOPs for these methods will be applied in 2022.

The outcomes of TOXOSOURCES will include quantitative and comparable estimates of the contribution of the main sources and transmission routes to *T. gondii* infections across Europe. The project fills several relevant data gaps. A major outcome already reached is the collection and whole genome sequencing of a large number of *T. gondii* isolates across Europe. Moreover, the consortium itself is a major achievement - exemplifying a successful cross-sectoral, international One Health collaboration, which is needed to address this zoonotic parasite.

The TOXOSOURCES Consortium comprises 21 One Health EJP partners and several external partners. The TOXOSOURCES Consortium has shown impressive resourcefulness and adaptability, and while timelines have needed adapting, all Milestones have been reached on time and all Deliverables and reports have been submitted by their planned deadlines. Dissemination of outcomes has been active and included scientific publications and presentations at conferences, workshops and webinars, and several collaborations with other projects and networks have been established.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

Progress made in TOXOSOURCES during Y4 (2021) followed the planned timeline, and all Milestones and Deliverables were reached by their deadlines.

Due to the COVID-19-pandemic there was a need to considerably adapt internal timelines, in particular those related to laboratory work due to lockdowns. TOXOSOURCES applied for a 6-month extension until the end of the year 2022, to ensure 1) that the project can fully achieve all the planned aims; 2) that all partners have the opportunity to benefit from implementation of the new methods and knowledge; 3) that the studies are able to cover all the aspects planned; 4) that the outputs scheduled for 2022 will be of high quality and we have time for their efficient dissemination; and as a result of all the previous points: 5) that TOXOSOURCES will have the impact it has the potential to have.

The work is organized into 5 work packages (WPs) with tasks (T) and some subtasks (sT). The project spans over three Annual Periods (Y3-Y5, 2020-2022).

Key outputs are available via the project homepage: <https://onehealthejp.eu/jrp-toxosources/> and via Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=keywords:%22TOXOSOURCES%22&sort=-publication_date.

Kick-off Meeting of TOXOSOURCES, February 2020, at Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark.

WP1 Coordination and impact

TOXOSOURCES-WP1 manages the project and is responsible for its progress, and integrates all the results of the project to achieve the common goals. TOXOSOURCES-WP1 ensures the project adheres to H2020 rules regarding e.g. ethics, IRP, dissemination and publication. Moreover, TOXOSOURCES-WP1 is responsible for the Data Management Plan of the project. TOXOSOURCES-WP1 coordinates the compiling of deliverables and reports and their timely submission, as well as the organization of project meetings and communication. Science-to-policy translation and efficient dissemination are emphasized to maximize the impact. Interest Group with representatives from e.g. industry will facilitate targeted dissemination to stakeholders.

The main focus of TOXOSOURCES-WP1 during Y4 was ensuring project progress as planned, and organizing the Annual Meeting (divided into two parts, Part I, held online in June, and Part II, held online in November). These aims were reached. All Milestones were reached on time and all Deliverables and reports were submitted by their deadlines. The Annual Meeting was organised in two parts to benefit from synergies with both the Annual Scientific Meeting of One Health EJP and events organised in the autumn, including a major event in parasitology in Europe, EMOP. Dissemination was active and included scientific publications and presentations at conferences, workshops and webinars - including several invited presentations. TOXOSOURCES was invited to present its results at the Stakeholders Committee Meeting of One Health EJP on June 11, 2021, and was highlighted in a Thematic Report focusing on environmental aspects addressed by One Health EJP projects. Several collaborations with other projects and networks have been established and were strengthened in 2021. Of specific note is the collaboration with SafeConsume project in benefiting from Horizon Results Booster services. TOXOSOURCES-WP1 integrates all the results of the project to make them useful, in particular to contribute to developing interventions.

The impact of the COVID-19 situation is followed closely, and challenges have been managed well by planning and resourcefulness, deputies and replacements. The effect of delays caused by the COVID-19-pandemic is evident, and there has been a need to considerably adapt internal timelines, in particular those related to laboratory work due to lockdowns. The project applied for a 6-month extension until the end of the year 2022; the extension request was solely due to the challenges caused by the COVID-19-pandemic.

WP1-T1- Management, coordination and communication

The Kick-off Meeting was held February 3–4, 2020, at SSI, Copenhagen, Denmark, with a possibility to participate remotely. Online meetings with the whole consortium have been held on October 20, 2020, on June 8, 2021 (Annual Meeting 2021, Part I), and on November 15, 2021 (Annual Meeting 2021, Part II).

The established key structures for management of the project include monthly online meeting with TOXOSOURCES WP-Leaders and Co-Leaders, Consortium emails, use of the online group for sharing and storage of relevant documents, and WP-level online meetings.

Screenshot from an online meeting of TOXOSOURCES-WP-Leaders and WP-Deputy-Leaders.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is updated regularly, and the project leader participates in the work of the One Health EJP DMP Committee. Outcomes are made available following FAIR principle. Dissemination of the outcomes has been active, and included presentations to relevant audiences at conferences, workshops and webinars, and scientific publications.

The collaborations with the Interest Group and other collaborators have started by establishing key contacts. Invited by SafeConsume, TOXOSOURCES joined a Horizon Results Booster project group called “DISH - Towards healthy and safe diet” that includes SafeConsume, TOXOSOURCES, Stance4Health, EAT2beNICE and FOODSAFETY4EU. TOXOSOURCES suggested a OHEJP Cogwheel Workshop with SafeConsume, and it was organized on November 25, 2020.

Challenged by the COVID-19-pandemic, the TOXOSOURCES Consortium has showed impressive resourcefulness and adaptability, and the careful risks-and-dependencies planning has proved useful. All Milestones, Deliverables and reports have been reached and submitted by their planned deadlines throughout the timeline of the project. The consortium is highly motivated and the general atmosphere is positive and supportive.

WP1-T2 Integration of all results to contribute to developing interventions, dissemination

Efficient dissemination and science-to-policy activities at national, European and global levels include facilitating the use of the new knowledge, linking the providers and users of the knowledge, and advocating multidisciplinary approaches.

TOXOSOURCES is part of a Horizon Results Booster project group “DISH - Towards healthy and safe diet” that includes SafeConsume, TOXOSOURCES, Stance4Health, EAT2beNICE and FOODSAFETY4EU. Module A was finished at the end of 2020, and module B services were launched in 2021. A factsheet and video about the DISH collaboration were produced; these will be made public in 2022.

Welcome to the DISH table towards healthy and safe diets

This factsheet has been produced by iCONS in the context of the Horizon Results Booster services delivered to SafeConsume (GA N. 727580), Stance4Health (GA N. 816303), One Health EJP TOXOSOURCES (GA N. 773830), FOODSAFETY4EU (GA N. 101000613) and Eat2beNICE (GA N. 728018). This product does not reflect the views of the European Commission.

horizonresultsbooster.eu

A page from factsheet produced for DISH collaboration.

TOXOSOURCES was invited to present its results at the Stakeholders Committee Meeting of One Health EJP on June 11, 2021, and was highlighted in a Thematic Report focusing on environmental aspects addressed by One Health EJP projects.

Outcomes of TOXOSOURCES are made available following FAIR principle. Dissemination of the outcomes has been active, and included presentations to relevant audiences at conferences, workshops and webinars, and scientific publications. Early-career colleagues involved in the work are particularly encouraged to present the results. Another special focus in the dissemination is integration of results from the different TOXOSOURCES-WPs.

*WP2 Multicentre quantitative microbiological risk assessment for *T. gondii* infections*

TOXOSOURCES-WP2 aims to quantify the relative contribution of sources of *T. gondii* infection, including meat products, fresh produce and environmental pathways, in all EU regions by quantitative microbiological risk assessment (QMRA). TOXOSOURCES-WP2 develops QMRA models for infection via tissue cysts (meat) and oocysts (environmental pathways), and applies the models in a multi-country study covering all four EU regions. Input data for the QMRA have been collected with contributions/support by all partners and TOXOSOURCES-WP3. An overview of the prevalence of *T. gondii* infection in humans and animals used for human consumption as well as cats was obtained by review of available literature, including grey literature. Exposure data were collected in a harmonised way using a survey specifically designed for QMRA purposes. Region- or country-specific products, dishes or eating habits were identified and the associated key processing parameters collected by the partners. The literature review of human infections also covers risk factor studies, to compare QMRA outcomes and epidemiological data.

During Y4, the main focus was finalising the data collection for running the QMRA model. The exposure survey was conducted. Meat processing information was collected and literature reviews were finalized and conducted.

The work progressed following the plans. All milestones were reached on time, and Deliverables were submitted on time.

*WP2-T1- QMRA modelling for human *T. gondii* infections*

The Consortium members involved in QMRA modelling met at RIVM, The Netherlands, to discuss plans in 2020. The development of the structure for the QMRA model for environmental transmission of *T. gondii* was finished, and expansion of both the meatborne and environmental QMRA models to include multiple countries was started. The work builds on previous work, in particular on an existing

meatborne QMRA model, as well as on environmental QMRA model developed in a PhD project of Huifang Deng, which was successfully defended on December 08, 2020.

During Y4, the main focus was checking input data as preparation for running the QMRA model. In addition, sensitivity analyses (to identify the most influential input parameters) and scenario analyses (in case of large uncertainty regarding input parameters) that will be initiated were planned.

WP2-T2- Review of prevalence of *T. gondii* infection in animals

A list of European countries and a list of key animal species raised or hunted for human consumption in Europe were collated. These were used to develop a search strategy for data on prevalence of *T. gondii* in animals. Earlier experiences from systematic reviews performed by EFSA and in the Baltic-Nordic region were taken into account in the process.

The search, screening of retrieved records, and data extraction were finished in 2020, and the data were checked and cleaned. The process and general results were summarised in a Deliverable. Selected primary results were submitted as abstracts and selected for presentation at scientific events. The results are being prepared for scientific publication.

This task is an example of a task that has included collaboration with early-career colleagues, and cross-project collaboration with OHEJP PhD project.

Related to this task, TOXOSOURCES members are also participating in another review together with the OHEJP-ORION project, focusing on risk factors for *T. gondii* infections in animals. While that information is not directly needed for the QMRA, together with the prevalence estimates it will provide important input for planning interventions.

WP2-T3- Quantitative exposure survey

In 2020 a general questionnaire was developed by expanding an existing questionnaire and taking into account experiences from the Dutch National Food Consumption Survey, risk factor information from a prospective case-control study in the Netherlands, and applying categorisation of the EFSA FoodEx system, which enables comparison with existing surveys. The questions were adapted to the different countries by including region/country-specific products. Decisions on sample size (respondents per each country) were finalized.

In 2021, the questionnaires were distributed via a market research agency to collect harmonised data on food consumption and handling and exposure to oocysts from the countries included in the QMRA. The data were provided for the QMRA, and plans for making the data publically available in connection to their publication, so that they can be used for QMRA modelling of other foodborne pathogens, were initiated.

WP2-T4- Overview of processing parameters for relevant meat products

Information on food consumption in the different countries was collected from the EFSA FoodEx2 database. Information on region/country-specific relevant products was also collected from consortium members. The list of products that need to be included in the exposure survey was harmonised across the countries. Product-specific processing parameters were discussed in the process of planning the survey questions, in particular regarding local products.

The data from the exposure survey inform which meat products are included in the QMRA model. Next, product-specific parameter values for freezing, salting and heating (e.g. time, temperature, concentration) were collated. The information were obtained using meat processing handbooks, communication with meat producers, or from package information in retail, and will be used as input data to the QMRA. Further discussions about the parameters include contacts with the industry.

WP2-T5- Review of prevalence and risk factors for human *T. gondii* infection

This task has been among those most affected by COVID-19 pandemic due to involvement of several key consortium members in the COVID-19 response. Efficient replacements and synergy with

TOXOSOURCES-WP2-T2 ensured that this task has also progressed well. The experiences from TOXOSOURCES-WP2-T2 work were incorporated into the planning of the systematic review protocol under this task. During 2021, the main focus was to finalize the searches, screening and main data extraction, analyse the results for their usefulness for the QMRA and prepare to deliver data for the QMRA modelling team. The data will be analysed by Bayesian hierarchical modelling to estimate the prevalence by country.

Results from the literature review on *T. gondii* source attribution (including risk factor analyses) for COST-action Euro-FBP were presented at OHEJPASM2020, emphasizing the continuation of the work in TOXOSOURCES. The screening and extraction protocol was aligned with that of a review done in collaboration with OHEJP-ORION project.

WP3 Multicentre survey to fill the key existing gap: role of fresh produce (i.e. Ready-to-Eat salads)

TOXOSOURCES-WP3 aims to fill the knowledge gap concerning the relevance of fresh produce contamination by *T. gondii* oocysts as an infection source for humans. TOXOSOURCES-WP3 selected the most reliable methods for the molecular detection of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce using a literature review, expert experiences, experimental evaluation and inter-laboratory comparison. Harmonised detection is implemented among the partners. TOXOSOURCES-WP3 collected existing data on *T. gondii* oocyst prevalence in fresh produce and the environment, together with information on fresh produce (e.g. RTE production, trading and consumption) in Europe. The data were used to design a risk-based sampling strategy for a multicentre pilot survey to detect *T. gondii* in fresh produce, applying the defined SOP. The ongoing multicentre pilot study, spanning all four European regions, is the first of its kind and will deliver valuable input for the TOXOSOURCES-WP2 and future QMRAs.

In 2021, the focus was to: i) implement the molecular detection method(s) among partners and perform a ring trial to assess the implementation and complete SOP validation; ii) to complete the collection through a literature review of existing data on *T. gondii* oocyst contamination in the environment to be provided to WP2; iii) to start sampling and testing for the multicentre survey.

All these aims were reached. The work progressed according to plan. The ring trial timeline was adjusted to allow all interested laboratories to implement the method. The final sampling strategy was presented to the consortium at the Annual Meeting 2021, Part I. Milestones and Deliverables were achieved on time.

WP3-T1- Selection, evaluation and implementation of detection procedure for *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce

An extensive literature review and multi-attribute assessment of the different steps in molecular detection of *T. gondii* (DNA) (oocyst recovery, DNA extraction and DNA amplification) was performed and complemented by a survey of expert opinions, current practices and experiences, to select the most suitable molecular method for *T. gondii* oocyst detection in fresh produce. The Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.1 summarizes this process, which provided a good starting point for developing a standard operating procedure (SOP) for the multicentre survey of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce. The results were published as a scientific article in early 2021.

The comparative experimental work was completed in 2020, and instead of the planned physical technical workshops, video tutorials were produced. The work towards the SOP was reported in Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.2 and presented to relevant audiences in 2021.

The deliverable describing the organisation of the ring trial was submitted on time. The ring trial timeline was adjusted to allow all interested laboratories (larger number of laboratories than originally planned) to implement the method, and thus this task will continue some months longer than originally planned. The main work was finished on time and all the outcomes (Deliverables and in addition a scientific article) were delivered on time.

WP3-T2- Design of a risk-based sampling strategy

An extensive review of peer-reviewed literature on the prevalence of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce was performed, as well as a review of the literature on *T. gondii* prevalence in the environment (soil and water) and bivalves. These were complemented by an online questionnaire to consortium partners to collate grey literature on the topic. A data summary on literature-based prevalence of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce was provided to TOXOSOURCES-WP2, and the results have been prepared for scientific publication, and the manuscript has been submitted. The key aspects of the work and results from grey literature search were reported in Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.4. Moreover, selected primary results were submitted as abstracts and selected for presentation at scientific events.

The design of a risk-based sampling strategy for the multicentre survey of *T. gondii* oocysts in fresh produce was started by preparing an online questionnaire to gather relevant information on trade and consumption of ready-to-eat salads from local and international industry. In addition, a request for information was sent via the EFSA focal point and a simple survey on RTE salads sold locally at supermarkets across Europe was conducted. Data were combined to design a sampling plan, taking into account sample size calculations, feasibility and costs, and the sampling strategy for WP3-T3 was defined.

The milestone of finalizing the sampling strategy was reached. The final sampling strategy was presented to the consortium at the Annual Meeting 2021, Part I.

WP3-T3- Multicentre pilot survey on *T. gondii* in fresh produce in Europe

The sampling strategy and plan for the multicentre pilot survey was finalized. A multicentre pilot survey for the molecular detection of *T. gondii* in selected fresh produce in Europe is being performed based on outputs of WP3-T1 and WP3-T2. Samples are being collected, over one year, in countries representative of the four European regions according to the strategy developed in WP3-T2. Fresh produce samples are obtained from local supermarkets and analysed the SOP defined in WP3-T1. Some partners perform only the oocyst recovery step of the SOP, store frozen the processed samples and deliver them to partners that have implemented the full SOP for the molecular testing. This approach ensures faster processing of the perishable fresh produce thus increasing the overall number of tested samples.

WP4 Serology method based on novel antigens to discriminate *T. gondii* infections acquired from oocysts

TOXOSOURCES-WP4 aims to develop a source-attributing serological method. TOXOSOURCES-WP4 identifies novel oocyst/sporozoite-specific antigens of *T. gondii* that have source-attributing potential and explores serological methods able to discriminate between oocyst- versus tissue cyst-driven infections. Finally, the methodology is applied to estimate the proportion of oocyst-driven infections in humans and animals used for human consumption.

The bioinformatic selection of promising protein candidates was finalized in 2020, and although laboratory work has been strongly affected by the COVID-19-related restrictions, the work progressed following the overall plans in 2021. The recombinant expression of proteins of interest is followed by assessing them using suitable sera.

WP4-T1- Identification and production of *T. gondii* stage-specific antigens for source attribution

The predicted proteome of the *T. gondii* oocyst/sporozoite was analysed bioinformatically to identify the best stage-specific and antigenically relevant protein candidates. A list of 96 proteins with source-attributing potential was defined. The main selection criteria were exclusive expression in oocysts, evidence of secretion, and a high score in linear epitope prediction.

The bioinformatic selection of promising protein candidates was finalized in 2020, and the work on the next steps continued in 2021 and continues further in 2022. The recombinant expression of proteins

of interest is followed by assessing them using suitable sera. A selection of known stage-specific proteins are tested in parallel to the novel candidates.

WP4-T2- Development of a novel stage-specific antigen-based ELISA to diagnose oocyst- and bradyzoite-driven *T. gondii* infections

Key sera have been characterized using a selection of widely employed serological tests, yielding interesting comparative data. The results obtained in the comparative study were presented in an international scientific meeting. The results are prepared for scientific publication.

The plan and experimental design for the development work were finalized in 2020 for the screening of the proteins using a step-by-step validation process. A detailed workflow for protein screening and development of a serological test was formulated and followed, reported in Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4.1 and published in international scientific publication. Candidate proteins were selected out of a panel of 15 initial candidates for further ELISA development.

Key aspects of the work done as well as key achievements of the process were reported in Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4.1.

WP4-T2-sT1 Standardization of a POI-based ELISA to diagnose oocyst- and/or bradyzoite driven *T. gondii* infections using reference pig sera

A suitable panel of sera from pigs experimentally infected with either oocysts or tissue cysts, first characterized using commercially available and routinely used serological tests for the selection of the best secondary antibody for the novel stage-specific antigen-based ELISA, is then tested using the approaches developed. Appropriate control sera were selected for the protein screening and assay development. The development of a source attribution serological assay is in progress following different strategies.

WP4-T2-sT2 Validation of a novel stage-specific antigen based ELISA to diagnose oocysts-and/or bradyzoite-driven *T. gondii* infections using reference sera from several relevant host species including humans

A suitable panel of sera from sheep experimentally infected with oocysts was characterized using commercially available and routinely used serological tests and the best secondary antibody for the novel stage-specific antigen-based ELISA was selected. International collaboration identified suitable sera from humans that would be useful for the work. The reference sera are then tested using the approaches developed.

WP4-T3- Exploring the prevalence of oocyst-derived *T. gondii* infections in animals and in humans

Using the POI-ELISA validated in WP4-T2, an inter-laboratory ring trial will be conducted, followed by pilot studies. The method will also be offered to other Consortium partners for testing existing collections of positive sera. The planning of this work was started.

WP4-T3-sT1 Inter-laboratory validation of the POI-based ELISA

POI-based ELISA will be adapted to the participating laboratories to obtain comparable results. Inter-laboratory reproducibility and analytical sensitivity will be evaluated using positive and negative reference sera (experimental *T. gondii* infection) identified in WP4-T2-sT1. The planning of this work was started.

WP4-T3-sT2 Exploring the prevalence of oocyst-driven infections in domestic animals (pigs, small ruminants) and wildlife (wild-boar, wild ungulates) used for human consumption

To reveal differences in the relative prevalence of oocyst-driven infections between animal species, regions and management systems, positive sera from naturally infected animals from different European regions will be tested using the POI-based ELISA. The planning of this work was started.

WP4-T3-sT3 Exploring the prevalence of oocyst-driven infections in humans

Well-defined positive sera from *T. gondii*-infected humans available from different European regions will be tested using the POI-based ELISA by pilot studies, that may include, based on availability, sera from congenitally-infected children aged <13 months and from older children >2 years; sera from recently infected adults; as well as sera from any suspected *T. gondii* outbreaks in Europe. The planning of this work was started.

WP5 Novel *T. gondii* typing method to detect within-genotype variation

TOXOSOURCES-WP5 aims to identify highly polymorphic regions in genomes of very closely related *T. gondii* strains across Europe, which are made available by partners and collaborators. Preliminary NGS data on European clonal type II *T. gondii* isolates has revealed substantial variation between isolates and relative to reference strains. Using the panel of strains from various parts of Europe, regions in the genome with an optimal SNP density are identified and used to establish a novel typing method.

The work in year 2020 was successful in both retrieval of relevant isolates and their whole genome sequencing (WGS). The work progressed following the plans in 2021, with focus on disseminating the results by presentations to relevant audiences.

WP5-T1- Retrieval of relevant *T. gondii* isolates or NGS-quality DNAs for NGS and NGS-MST

T. gondii isolates, WGS-quality DNAs or WGS-data on isolates were collected from across Europe. Isolates were expanded *in vitro*, and DNA was extracted for WGS. The focus was on *T. gondii* Type II isolates, while other isolates were included as well. This retrieval of key *T. gondii* isolates or DNAs was successful and the total number of isolates retrieved for the work is markedly higher than the original target. Isolates from northern and eastern European regions were first underrepresented on the list, but further efforts were successful in gathering more isolates from these regions.

During 2021, further isolates were collected to establish a panel for inter-laboratory comparison and pilot studies (WP5-T3). A request for contributions was sent out to networks including the NRL network. For particular regions, we included a larger number of isolates to show that resolution of typing is high enough to trace differences of local isolates.

All DNAs are also characterised based on polymorphism of fewer markers using existing standard techniques (PCR-RFLP and microsatellite (MS) typing).

WP5-T2- Novel, standardized high-throughput direct NGS-MLST *T. gondii* genotyping method

Based on sequence information obtained by WP5-T1 a novel, standardized high-throughput targeted NGS-MLST genotyping method is being established and validated to distinguish between closely related *T. gondii* strains. Timely dissemination is emphasized, and progress and results of this work have been presented to relevant audiences.

WP5-T2-sT1 Whole genome sequencing (WGS) of key *T. gondii* isolates and WGS-quality DNAs

A large number of whole genome sequences have been generated. The sequences of key *T. gondii* isolates have been provided to TOXOSOURCES-WP5-T2-sT2.

WP5-T2-sT2 Establishment, validation and refinement of a novel, standardized high-throughput targeted NGS-MLST *T. gondii* genotyping method

Based on the sequences from WP5-T2-sT1, highly polymorphic marker regions (partially focusing on introns and/or particular gene regions of e.g. virulence associated genes) were identified and are being evaluated for suitability for the establishment of a new typing method. The higher number of sequences than originally planned has proven highly beneficial for the work.

For validation, the novel NGS-MLST results were compared with results of conventional techniques (PCR-RFLP, MS typing) (i). Similarities and differences in the capability of the novel NGS-MLST method and the PCR-RFLP- and MS-based techniques for the *T. gondii* differentiation are established. (ii) The

analytical sensitivity will be determined using different sample matrices, spiked with different levels of parasites. Plans were made for this work.

A standardized workflow for the collection and preliminary analysis of NGS-MLST data on *T. gondii* is established. The Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5.1 summarized the key steps of the NGS-MLST *T. gondii* genotyping method and its establishment. This deliverable provides the base for its further validation by an Inter-laboratory comparison and its application by NGS-MLST pilot studies. Finally, the new technology will be distributed to interested partners, if possible by a workshop at FLI, prior to inter-laboratory comparison and pilot studies (WP5-T3).

WP5-T3- Inter-laboratory comparison and NGS-MLST pilot studies

The plans for this work were made. Using a panel of reference samples, an inter-laboratory comparison of the established novel NGS-MLST genotyping method will be performed. Then, the method will be applied to “real/unknown“ *T. gondii* positive samples from the field, i.e. samples from intermediate hosts (including humans), definitive hosts and environment by laboratories that implemented the method.

Plans are being made for pilot studies, based on availability of suitable isolates/DNA/samples. Aim is to conduct three studies, and apply the method to different types of samples.

WP5-T3-sT1 Inter-laboratory comparison on the novel NGS-MLST method

The plans for this work were made and a panel of reference samples was prepared. An inter-laboratory comparison of the established novel NGS-MLST genotyping method will be based on this defined set of samples sent out to participating laboratories across Europe, to confirm that typing results are in agreement between different laboratories and to obtain information about the robustness and applicability of the method.

Additionally, as a need for inter-laboratory comparison of one of the conventional *T. gondii* typing techniques, the MS-based technique, was identified, such comparison is being organized, in a synergistic manner with the inter-laboratory comparison of the novel method.

3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP1.1	Data Management Plan	M30	M30		Public. 10.5281/zenodo.3924450 OHEJP: available	8
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2.1	Report on prevalence of <i>T. gondii</i> infection in animals for human consumption and cats within Europe	M40	M40		Public. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4730705 OHEJP: available	5
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP2.2	Report on quantitative exposure data from survey of WP2	M48	M48		Public. https://zenodo.org/record/5812060#.YdVbAWjMKUk OHEJP: available	3
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.1	Report on available analytical procedures for detection of <i>T. gondii</i> in fresh produce and list of promising analytical procedures	M28	M28		Public. 10.5281/zenodo.3778719 OHEJP: available	2
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.2	SOP on detection of <i>T. gondii</i> in selected fresh produce matrix	M36	M36		Public. 10.5281/zenodo.4405242 OHEJP: available	2

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.3	Report on the ring trial of WP3	M40	M40		Public. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4730717 OHEJP: available	2
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.4	Report on literature review on the prevalence of T. gondii oocysts in fresh produce and environment	M48	M48		Public. https://zenodo.org/record/5812067#.YdVaomjMKUk OHEJP: available	5
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP4.1 [numbering corrected, this is 4.1, there will be 4.2 in 2022]	SOP for a novel source-attributing serological method	M48	M48		Public. https://zenodo.org/record/5812071#.YdVay2jMKUk OHEJP: available	2
22	D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP5.1	SOP for a novel NGS-MLST genotyping method of WP5	M48	M48		Public. https://zenodo.org/record/5812077#.YdVa22jMKUk OHEJP: available	2

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities); 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-01	Kick-off Meeting held by WP1	M26	Yes		Kick-off Meeting held on 3.-4.2.2020 at SSI, Copenhagen, Denmark, with possibility to attend online. Milestone reached by M26 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-02	Bioinformatic selection of oocyst/sporozoite-specific antigens completed in WP4	M28	Yes		Selection done. Milestone reached by M28 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOXOURCES-03	Key isolates summarized in WP5	M30	Yes		Summary list of key isolates compiled. Milestone reached by M28 (ahead of time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-04	List of meat products or dishes that need to be included in exposure survey is provided by WP2-T4 to WP2-T3	M34	Yes		List provided. Milestone reached by M34 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-05	Experimental selection of the appropriate methods for samples analysis in WP3	M36	Yes		Experimental selection done. Milestone reached by M36 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-06	Delivery of data summary on literature-based prevalence of T. gondii oocysts in fresh produce from WP3 to WP2	M36	Yes		Data summary delivered. Milestone reached by M36 (on time).

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-07	Production of the first sets of purified soluble recombinant proteins (up to 100) for WP4-T2 serological assays	M36	Yes		Production started. Milestone reached by M36 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-08	Evaluation of the source attributing ability of the first sets of stage-specific antigens produced in WP4-T1	M36	Yes		Evaluation started. Milestone reached by M36 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-09	Finalization of risk-based sampling strategy of WP3	M38	Yes		Strategy ready by the deadline of the milestone. The sampling plan was presented to the consortium at Annual Meeting 2021, Part I. Milestone reached by M38 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-10	Country-specific estimates of prevalence in animals provided as input for QMRA	M38	Yes		Input data provided. Milestone reached by M38 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-11	Questionnaires for exposure survey ready to be rolled out by WP2	M38	Yes		Questionnaires finalised. Milestone reached by M38 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-12	List of meat products for which processing parameters need to be collected is provided to WP2-T4	M40	Yes		Information provided, with focus on local products included in the survey. Milestone reached by M40 (on time).

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-13	Exposure data from survey are provided as input for QMRA	M43	Yes		Data available in M41. Milestone reached by M41 (ahead of time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-14	Processing parameters for relevant meat products are provided as input for QMRA	M45	Yes		Reaching this milestone was supported by the work done to identify relevant local products (synergy). Milestone reached by M45 (on time). This milestone was a startingpoint for discussions with industry.
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-15	Country-specific estimates for prevalence of human T. gondii infection provided as input data for QMRA	M45	Yes		Reaching this milestone was supported by the work done in animal prevalence review (synergy). The papers included in systematic review contain the information. Milestone reached by M45 (on time). After reaching the milestone, the information is formatted for the purpose, based on experiences from the animal prevalence review.
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-16	Delivery of data summary on fresh produce consumption in EU from WP3 to WP2	M45	Yes		Data delivered. Milestone reached by M45 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-17	Delivery of data summary on literature-based prevalence of T. gondii oocysts in environment from WP3 to WP2	M45	Yes		Data delivered. Milestone reached by M45 (on time).

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-18	Antigens for serological assays	M48	Yes		The key antigens have been delivered in batches. Milestone reached by M48 (on time).
22	M-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-19	Annual Meeting held by WP1	M48	Yes		Part I held in M42, part II in M47. Milestone reached by M47 (ahead of time).

4. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
<p>A real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction for the specific detection of <i>Hammondia hammondi</i> and its differentiation from <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i></p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-020-04571-8 https://zenodo.org/record/4647866#.YGNbWK8zaUk</p>	YES	NO	YES, 2190 €
<p>Expanding the Known Repertoire of C-Type Lectin Receptors Binding to <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> Oocysts Using a Modified High-Resolution Immunofluorescence Assay</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1128/mSphere.01341-20 https://zenodo.org/record/4657064#.YGXUY68zaUk</p>	YES	NO	YES, 2130 €
<p>Experimental infection with <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> in broiler chickens (<i>Gallus domesticus</i>): seroconversion, tissue cyst distribution, and prophylaxis</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-020-06984-x https://zenodo.org/record/4647895#.YGNbDT9JGUI</p> <p>Shareable link: https://rdcu.be/chKFi</p>	<p>YES</p> <p>OHEJP is not mentioned under 'Funding', as the main authors are from external partners, participating at their own funding.</p> <p>OHEJP is acknowledged under</p>	NO	<p>NO</p> <p>But as FAIR as possible: a "shareable link" is provided by the Springer Nature SharedIt content-sharing initiative: https://rdcu.be/chKFi</p> <p>"Authors of original research articles: // Can post shareable links to view-only versions of their peer-reviewed research</p>

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
	<p>'Acknowledgments', stating: "AG, RB and GS are part of the TOXOSOURCES consortium, supported by funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 773830: One Health European Joint Programme."</p>		<p>paper anywhere, including via social channels, institutional repositories and authors' own websites as well as scholarly collaborative networks" The metadata are available via Zenodo, together with the shareable link.</p>
<p>Expression of in vivo biotinylated recombinant antigens SAG1 and SAG2A from <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> for improved seroepidemiological bead-based multiplex assays 10.1186/s12896-020-00646-7 https://zenodo.org/record/4129949#.X6Ldr4hKjcc</p>	YES	NO	YES, 1.890 €
<p>Fluorescent bead-based serological detection of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> infection in chickens https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-020-04244-6 https://zenodo.org/record/3974390#.X6PV0WhKjcc</p>	YES	NO	YES, 1990 €
<p>Infection prevention and control practices of ambulatory veterinarians: A questionnaire study in Finland https://doi.org/10.1002/vms3.464</p>	YES	NO	YES, 0 €

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
https://zenodo.org/record/4647937#.YGNfea8zaUk			
Isolation and genetic characterization of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> in Spanish sheep flocks https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-020-04275-z https://zenodo.org/record/3974417#.X6PWsWhKjcc	YES	NO	YES, 1990 €
Molecular Methods for the Detection of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> Oocysts in Fresh Produce: An Extensive Review https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9010167 https://zenodo.org/record/4647840#.YGNQk68zaUk	YES	NO	YES, 738.89 €
Molecular analysis suggests that Namibian cheetahs (<i>Acinonyx jubatus</i>) are definitive hosts of a so far undescribed <i>Besnoitia</i> species https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04697-3 https://zenodo.org/record/4694200#.YHg5Z-gzaUk	YES, both TOXOSOURCES and MEmE	NO	YES, 2190 € Open Access funding enabled and organized by project DEAL.
Isolation, Genotyping, and Mouse Virulence Characterization of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> From Free Ranging Iberian Pigs. https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2020.604782 https://zenodo.org/record/5516873#.YUg5qOxxe70	YES	NO	YES, ND (= no data on fee)
In vivo and in vitro models show unexpected degrees of virulence among <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> type II and III isolates from sheep. https://doi.org/10.1186/s13567-021-00953-7 https://zenodo.org/record/5516897#.YUg7QOxxe70	YES	NO	YES, ND

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Comparison of Direct and Indirect <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> Detection and Genotyping in Game: Relationship and Challenges. https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9081663 https://zenodo.org/record/5516907#.YUg8qOxxe70	YES	NO	YES, ND
Zoonotic pathogens in wild muskoxen (<i>Ovibos moschatus</i>) and domestic sheep (<i>Ovis aries</i>) from Greenland https://doi.org/10.1002/vms3.599 https://zenodo.org/record/5516925#.YUhCMexxe70	YES	NO	YES, 1600 €
A longitudinal study of <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> seroconversion on four large Danish sow farms. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2021.109460 https://zenodo.org/record/5516957#.YUhCDexxe70	YES	NO	YES, ND
Veterinarians as a risk group for zoonoses: exposure, knowledge and protective practices in Finland https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shaw.2021.10.008 To be added to ZENODO and project website when a final version is available, currently [in press, corrected proof]	YES	NO	YES, 0 EUR
The disease burden of ocular toxoplasmosis in Denmark in 2019: Estimates based on laboratory testing of ocular samples and on publicly available register data https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parepi.2021.e00229	YES	NO	YES, 1580 €

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
https://zenodo.org/record/5595613#.YXZegxpBy70			
Identification of Oocyst-Driven Toxoplasma gondii Infections in Humans and Animals through Stage-Specific Serology—Current Status and Future Perspectives https://zenodo.org/record/5821931#.YdXABWCZOUk https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms9112346	YES	NO	YES, 1647 €
Development and validation of a time-resolved fluorescence immunoassay for the detection of anti-Toxoplasma gondii antibodies in goats https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2021.109432 https://zenodo.org/record/5812135#.YdVYmmjMKUk	YES	NO	NO Reasoning: not directly from the work plan of TOXOSOURCES, but co-authored by TOXOSOURCES co-funded colleagues, and the work supports and contributes to TOXOSOURCES (synergies). The authors have considered that using TOXOSOURCES funding for open-access publishing fee of this papers is not applicable, and other funding supporting the work did not cover Open Access publishing fees.
Seroprevalence of Toxoplasma gondii in outdoor dogs and cats in Bangkok, Thailand https://doi.org/10.1017/S0031182021000421 https://zenodo.org/record/5812133#.YdVZOGjMKUk	YES	NO	NO Reasoning: not directly from the work plan of TOXOSOURCES, but co-authored by TOXOSOURCES

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
			co-funded colleagues, and the work supports and contributes to TOXOSOURCES (synergies). The authors have considered that using TOXOSOURCES funding for open-access publishing fee of this papers is not applicable, and other funding supporting the work did not cover Open Access publishing fees.
Molecular survey of Besnoitia spp. (Apicomplexa) in faeces from European wild mesocarnivores in Spain https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.14206 https://zenodo.org/record/5812123#.YdVZXWjMKUk	YES	NO	NO Reasoning: not directly from the work plan of TOXOSOURCES, but co-authored by TOXOSOURCES co-funded colleagues, and the work supports and contributes to TOXOSOURCES (synergies). The authors have considered that using TOXOSOURCES funding for open-access publishing fee of this papers is not applicable, and other funding supporting the work did not cover Open Access publishing fees.

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Changes in serum biomarkers of inflammation in bovine besnoitiosis https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-021-04991-0 https://zenodo.org/record/5812119#.YdVZe2jMKUk	YES	NO	YES, 1555 €, covered from other funding
Identification of molecular biomarkers associated with disease progression in the testis of bulls infected with Besnoitia besnoiti https://doi.org/10.1186/s13567-021-00974-2 https://zenodo.org/record/5812116#.YdVZo2jMKUk	YES	NO	YES, 2245 €, covered from other funding

Additional output

TOXOSOURCES is active in disseminating its outputs, with presentations to relevant audiences.

Invited talk at Mandagsmøde, Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology & Prevention, SSI, March 2, 2020:

How and why to prevent *Toxoplasma gondii* infections
Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark

Oral presentation at OHEJPASM2020, May 27-29, 2020:

Source attribution for *Toxoplasma gondii* infections in Europe

Marieke Opsteegh (1), Hannah Morgan (1), Huifang Deng (1), Gereon Schares (2), Sandra Stelzer (2), Sara Monteiro Pires (3), Helga Waap (5), Jacek Sroka (6), Heidi Enemark (7), Jelena Srbljanovic (8), Olgica Djurkovic-Djakovic (8), Chiara Trevisan (9), Agnetha Hofhuis (1), Lasse S. Vestergaard (4), Pikka Jokelainen (4), Joke van der Giessen (1), Euro-FBP (COST Action FA1408), TOXOSOURCES Consortium RIVM, The Netherlands (1); FLI, Germany (2); DTU, Denmark (3); SSI, Denmark (4); INIAV, Portugal (5); PIWET, Poland (6); NVI, Norway (7); UoB, Serbia (8); ITG, Belgium (9)

Poster at OHEJPASM2020, May 27-29, 2020:

TOXOSOURCES – *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

Pikka Jokelainen (1), Marieke Opsteegh (2), Marco Lalle (3), Furio Spano (3), Gereon Schares (4), Sara Monteiro Pires (5), Anne Mayer-Scholl (6), Frank Seeber (7), Simone M. Cacciò (3), Joke van der Giessen (2), TOXOSOURCES Consortium (Joint Research Project of the One Health European Joint Programme)

SSI, Denmark (1); RIVM, The Netherlands (2); ISS, Italy (3); FLI, Germany (4); DTU Food, Denmark (5); BfR, Germany (6); RKI, Germany (7)
[10.5281/zenodo.3924467](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3924467)

Poster and talk at 3-Minute-Thesis competition at OHEJPASM2020, May 27-29, 2020:

Tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to sausage and dry ham, a quantitative risk assessment

Filip DAMEK¹, Bastien FREMAUX², Dominique AUBERT³, Marieke OPSTEEGH⁴, Sandra VUILLERMET¹, Pikka JOKELAINEN⁵, Joke VAN DER GIESSEN⁴, Pascal BOIREAU¹, Isabelle VILLENA³, Radu BLAGA¹
¹ UMR BIPAR, Ecole Nationale Vétérinaire d'Alfort, ANSES, France ² IFIP - Institut du Porc, France ³ National Reference Center on Toxoplasmosis, Toxoplasma Biological Resources Center, CHU Reims and EA7510, SFR CAP-Santé, University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne, USC EpiToxo ANSES, France ⁴ National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, The Netherlands ⁵ Statens Serum Institut, Denmark

Short oral presentation at One Health EJP Cogwheel workshop with JPIAMR, April 28, 2020:

#TOXOSOURCES *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified
Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark

Poster and short oral presentation in a webinar 'Toxoplasma gondii e toxoplasmosis in una prorspettiva One Health' organized by Italian Society of Parasitology (SOIPA), June 30, 2020:

TOXOSOURCES – TOXOpasma gondii SOURCES quantified

P JOKELAINEN¹, M OPSTEEGH², M LALLE³, F SPANO³, G SCHARS⁴, S MONTEIRO PIRES⁵, A MAYER-SCHOLL⁶, F SEEBER⁷, S M CACCIÒ³, J VAN DER GIESSEN², TOXOSOURCES CONSORTIUM (JOINT RESEARCH PROJECT OF THE ONE HEALTH EUROPEAN JOINT PROGRAMME)

¹ Statens Serum Institut, Copenhagen, Denmark, ² National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, Bilthoven, The Netherlands, ³ Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Rome, Italy, ⁴ Friedrich Loeffler Institute, Insel Riems, Germany, ⁵ Technical University of Denmark, Kongens Lyngby, Denmark, ⁶ German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment, Berlin, Germany, ⁷ Robert Koch Institute,

Berlin, Germany

Two lectures at One Health EJP Summer School August 17-28, 2020:

Parasites in the food chain: global One Health risks

Wildlife and Public Health

Joke van der Giessen, RIVM, The Netherlands

Oral presentation at PhDay, October 14, 2020:

Desarrollo de un nuevo ELISA para la detección de anticuerpos frente a *Toxoplasma gondii* en el ganado porcino

Nadia María López Ureña, UCM, Spain

Invited talk at International One Health Webinar Series of School of Public Health and Zoonoses, Guru Angad Dev Veterinary and Animal Sciences University, India, November 5, 2020:

Relative contributions of the different sources of *Toxoplasma gondii*, a globally important pathogen of major public health concern

Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark

Oral presentation at International Pathology Day, November 11, 2020:

Endemic pathogens and international research projects during a pandemic: *Toxoplasma gondii* and international research project TOXOSOURCES as an example

Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark and Martha Betson, UoS, UK

Roundtable, International Pathology Day, November 11, 2020:

Discussion topic: Why international knowledge sharing is a winner

Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark

Oral presentation at ApicoWplexa virtual meeting series, November 12, 2020:

Toxoplasma gondii in Spanish farm animals: opening new avenues from genotype to phenotype

Mercedes Fernández-Escobar, UCM, Spain

Short oral presentation at One Health EJP Cogwheel workshop with SafeConsume, November 25, 2020:

TOXOSOURCES - *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark

Short oral presentation at 15th Workshop of the National Reference Laboratories for Parasites, December 15, 2020:

#TOXOSOURCES *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark

Oral presentations at TOXO-21 webinar, 2021

by Rafael Calero-Bernal and Pikka Jokelainen

Oral presentations at ApicoWplexa virtual meeting series, February 18, 2021:

Selection, validation and SOP development of a molecular detection method for identification of *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts in leafy-green vegetables

Iva Slana¹, Nadja Bier², Borbara Bartosova¹, Gianluca Marucci³, Anne Mayer-Scholl², Pikka Jokelainen⁴, Marco Lalle³

A comparative study of the most widely used serological tests in the diagnosis of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in small ruminants

López-Ureña, Nadia María¹; Calero-Bernal, Rafael¹; Pazmiño-Bonilla, Elvis Daniel¹; Vázquez-Calvo,

Ángela 2; Sánchez-Sánchez, Roberto¹; Ortega-Mora, Luis Miguel¹; Álvarez-García, Gema¹

Invited oral presentation at RSU conference, virtually in Riga, Latvia, 2021

Pikka Jokelainen

Poster presentation at CSBSP conference, virtually in Vilnius, Lithuania, 2021

Pikka Jokelainen

Presentation at internal dissemination events 'OHEJP at SSI' 4.5.2021 and 3.11.2021

Pikka Jokelainen

OHEJPASM 2021, June 9-11, 2021

Two oral presentations and several posters, including:

Fernández-Escobar, M.; Maksimov P.; Joeres, M.; Álvarez-García, G.; Jokelainen, P.; Schares, G.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Calero-Bernal, R. Lights and shades in genotyping: European *Toxoplasma gondii* needs a closer look using harmonised approaches. *Annual Scientific 2021 OneHealthEJP*. 9th-11th June 2021. Poster.

Joeres, M.; Maksimov, P.; Tuschy, M.; Bärwald, A.; Conraths, F.J.; Koudela, B.; Blaga, R.; Cacciò, S.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Jokelainen, P.; Schares, G. Unprecedented Whole Genome Sequencing effort reveals highly polymorphic regions in the genome of European *Toxoplasma gondii* strains. *Annual Scientific 2021 OneHealthEJP*. 9th-11th June 2021. Poster.

Maksimov, P.; Cacciò, S.; Joeres, M.; Conraths, F.J.; Koudela, B.; Blaga, R.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Jokelainen, P.; Schares, G. Development of a Next-Generation Sequencing-based typing method for *Toxoplasma gondii* for European needs. *Annual Scientific 2021 OneHealthEJP*. 9th-11th June 2021. Oral.

Poster presentation at conference 'Responsible Use of Antibiotics in Animals'

Infection prevention and control practices among ambulatory livestock and equine veterinarians Marie Verkola¹, Terhi Järvelä¹, Asko Järvinen², Pikka Jokelainen^{3,4}, Anna-Maija Virtala⁴, Paula M. Kinnunen⁴, Annamari Heikinheimo^{1,5}

Keynote presentation at ApicoWplexa virtual meeting series, June 24, 2021

Pikka Jokelainen

Oral presentation at ApicoWplexa virtual meeting series, June 24, 2021

Environmental contamination with *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts: a systematic review

López-Ureña, Nadia María¹; Chaudhry, Umer²; Calero-Bernal, Rafael¹; Messina, Davide²; Evangelista, Francisco²; Betson, Martha²; Lalle, Marco³; Jokelainen, Pikka⁴; Ortega-Mora, Luis Miguel¹; Álvarez-García, Gema¹

Poster presentation at annual conference of the German Veterinary Medical Society, section "Parasitology and Parasitic Diseases", 28th to 30th June 2021

Development of a next-generation sequencing-based typing method to detect within-genotype variation in *Toxoplasma gondii*

M. Joeres¹, P. Maksimov¹, M. Tuschy¹, A. Bärwald¹, F. J. Conraths¹, B. Koudela^{2,3}, R. Blaga⁴, S. Cacciò⁵, M. Fernández-Escobar⁶, R. Calero-Bernal⁶, L. M. Ortega-Mora⁶, P. Jokelainen⁷, G. Schares¹

Poster presentations at WAAVP, Dublin, Ireland, July 2021

Tropism and persistence of *Toxoplasma gondii*: from pork carcass to dry sausage

Filip Dámek¹, Bastien Fremaux², Dominique Aubert³, Marieke Opsteegh⁴, Sandra Thoumire¹,

Sandra Vuillermet¹, Pikka Jokelainen⁵, Joke van der Giessen⁴, Pascal Boireau⁶, Isabelle Villena³, Radu Blaga¹

Toxoplasma gondii prevalence in animals in Europe: a systematic review

Filip Dámek¹, Helga Waap², Marieke Opsteegh³, Pikka Jokelainen⁴, Delphine Le Roux¹, Gunita Deksné⁵, Huifang Deng³, Gereon Schares⁶, Arno Swart³, Anna Lundén⁷, Gema Álvarez-García⁸, Martha Betson⁹, Rebecca Davidson¹⁰, Adriana Gyorke¹¹, Sanne Stokman³, Daniela Antolová¹², Zuzana Hurníková¹², Henk Wisselink¹³, Jacek Sroka¹⁴, Siv Klevar¹⁵, Rob van Spronsen³, Radu Blaga¹

Endoparasites of feral cats in Denmark

Stine Thorsø Nielsen¹, Ida Sofie Thuesen¹, Søren Saxmose Nielsen¹, Peter Sandøe¹, Pikka Jokelainen², Christen Rune Stensvold², Michelle Bitsch Hardy¹, Nikoline Johansson¹, Heidi Huus Petersen³, Stig Milan Tamsborg¹, Helena Mejer¹

International workshop on molecular methods for *T. gondii* during summer 2021

teachers and participation from TOXOSOURCES.

One Health session of Project Review Module of ECDC's EPIET and EUPHEM programmes, August 25, 2021

Project presentation, chairing, participation in round table.

Poster presentation Zoonoses 2021 – International Symposium on Zoonoses Research “From Disease Ecology to SARS-CoV-2; Berlin, October 13-15, 2021

Identification of oocyst-driven *Toxoplasma gondii* infections through stage-specific serology – concepts and challenges

Gema Álvarez García ¹; Rebecca Davidson ²; Siv Klevar ²; Pikka Jokelainen ³
Luis Miguel Ortega Mora ¹; Furio Spano ⁴; Frank Seeber ⁵

EMOP 12-16 October

Several presentations, including:

Pikka Jokelainen TOXOSOURCES: *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified

Pikka Jokelainen (invited duo-talk with Karen Shapiro) Wildlife as sentinels and indicators for transmission of *Toxoplasma gondii*

Joke van der Giessen Risk ranking and evaluation of surveillance systems for foodborne parasites in Europe.

Joke van der Giessen Public Health impact of foodborne parasite in a One Health approach

Filip Dámek *Toxoplasma gondii* seroprevalence in European wildlife: a systematic review

Filip Dámek Tropism of *Toxoplasma gondii* in the tissues of experimentally infected pigs

Nadia María LÓPEZ UREÑA^{1†}, Umer CHAUDHRY^{2†}, Rafael CALERO BERNAL¹, Davide MESSINA², Francisco EVANGELISTA², Martha BETSON², Marco LALLE³, Pikka JOKELAINEN⁴, Luis Miguel ORTEGA MORA¹, Gema ÁLVAREZ GARCÍA¹

Environmental contamination with *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts: a systematic review

Nadia María LÓPEZ UREÑA^{1†}, Rafael CALERO BERNAL¹, Ángela VÁZQUEZ CALVO², Patricia VÁZQUEZ ARBAIZAR², Nuria GONZÁLEZ FERNÁNDEZ¹, Radu BLAGA³, Bretislav KOUDELA^{4,5}, Luis Miguel ORTEGA MORA¹, Gema ÁLVAREZ GARCÍA¹

Comparative study of the serological tests used for the diagnosis of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection in domestic pigs

Maksimov, P.; Caccio, S.; Joeres, M.; Conraths, F.J.; Koudela, B.; Blaga, R.; Fernández-Escobar, M.; Calero-Bernal, R.; Ortega-Mora, L.M.; Jokelainen, P.; Schares, G. Genome-wide single nucleotide variation in *Toxoplasma gondii* type II isolates from Europe. *13th European Multicolloquium of Parasitology*. Belgrade, Serbia, October (12-16), 2021. Oral.

DISCONTTOOLS seminar 20 October 2021

Gereon Schares et al.: DISCONTTOOLS expert group on zoonotic toxoplasmosis: many gaps identified, new diagnostics developments and vaccines are necessary for effective intervention

V SIMBRATOX -Brazilian Symposium of Toxoplasmosis and II SINTOX -International Symposium of Toxoplasmosis. Universidade Federal Rural de Rio de Janeiro. November, 2021.

Calero-Bernal, R. Invited speech: Methodologies for the study of *Toxoplasma gondii* genetic population structure: future perspectives.

Examples of other activities:

#TOXOSOURCES has been used on social media:

<https://twitter.com/hashtag/toxosources?f=live>

Participation in WomenInScience tweet of OHEJP 11.2.2021

Pikka Jokelainen, Joke van der Giessen

Interviewed to Pathologist-journal

Pikka Jokelainen

Interview for article in Finnish Cat Association on feline toxoplasmosis

Pikka Jokelainen

Artistic collaboration:

Pikka Jokelainen

Anni Puolakka: From the Heart (2021)

Single channel video, duration 14:14

The work has been / will be shown at Jyväskylä Art Museum, Tampere Film Festival, Baltic Triennial (Vilnius), HAM gallery / Helsinki Art Museum

<http://annipuolakka.com/fromtheheart/>

TOXOSOURCES partner institutes have also mentioned TOXOSOURCES in their communications, e.g.:

<https://www.ssi.dk/aktuelt/nyhedsbreve/epi-nyt/2020/uge-4---2020>

https://www.rki.de/DE/Content/Forsch/EJP_OH2020.html

<https://www.sva.se/forskning/internationellt-samarbete/europeisk-samverkan-kring-livsmedelsburna-smittor/toxosources-ett-one-health-ejp-projekt/>

https://www.bfr.bund.de/en/toxoplasma_gondii_sources_quantified__ejp_toxosource_-249310.html

<https://www.iss.it/en/web/iss-en/-/news-1>

Outcomes

- SOPs (final versions will be made available in 2022)
- Data from exposure survey (will be made available in connection to publication in 2022)

- Whole genome sequences of high number of *T. gondii* strains from Europe (will be made available in connection to publications in 2022)
- Video and factsheet from DISH collaboration (will be made available in early 2022)

5. *Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries*

TOXOSOURCES builds largely on previous work and is actively looking for collaborations and synergies.

- An example of building on previous work is the building on the work performed within **COST-Action Euro-FBP**.
- Another example of building on previous work is that the TOXOSOURCES-WP3 work builds on work done in **project IMPACT** (Standardising molecular detection methods to IMprove risk assessment capacity for foodborne protozoan Parasites, using *Cryptosporidium* in ready-to-eat salad as a model organism”; Partnering Grant Project Grant Agreement Number GP/EFSA/ENCO/2018/03 – GA03).
- TOXOSOURCES addresses several key gaps identified in **DISCONTTOOLS** work - <https://www.discontools.eu/database/110-toxoplasmosis.html> and collaborates in the updating of the database. In 2021, TOXOSOURCES contributed to a poster presentation at DISCONTTOOLS Seminar.
- TOXOSOURCES collaborates with **SafeConsume project** (<http://safeconsume.eu/>). Both projects are interested in the relevance of *Toxoplasma gondii* contamination in fresh produce, with different focus: SafeConsume focuses on consumer behaviour on safe handling of fresh produce at home, whereas TOXOSOURCES WP3 focuses on fresh produce from harvest to packaging. TOXOSOURCES suggested OHEJP Cogwheel Workshop with SafeConsume, and it was organized on November 25, 2020. SafeConsume invited TOXOSOURCES to join a Horizon Results Booster group. Via this collaboration, TOXOSOURCES also established links with projects **Stance4Health**, **EAT2beNICE**, and **FOODSAFETY4EU**. In 2021, the collaboration was named ‘DISH’ and it produced a factsheet and video that will be made public in 2022.
- Collaboration with **International network for environmental Toxoplasma studies (INETS)** is another important established collaboration. INETS is a global network that organizes e.g. workshops. TOXOSOURCES will be presented at INETS workshop 2022.
- Collaboration with international colleagues on workshop on molecular methods during summer 2021.
- TOXOSOURCES has links to several PhD projects. For example, work in WP2 builds on the PhD work by Dr. Huifang Deng ‘Source attribution of human toxoplasmosis, A quantitative microbiological risk assessment approach’. **One Health EJP PhD project ToxSauQMRA** (PhD candidate Filip Damek) is closely linked to TOXOSOURCES. At RKI a recently started PhD project (David Warschkau) aims at establishing an *in vitro* model of oocyst generation in intestinal organoids by which antigens identified in WP4 will be further analysed for function/localization.
- There are collaborations with **other One Health EJP projects**, including **MEME**, **PARADISE**, **OH-Harmony-CAP**, **MATRIX**, **COHESIVE** and **ORION**. Synergies and complementary approaches have been identified.
- To enable and encourage collaborations, the QMRA models will be made available via a repository (<https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/rakip/>)

- **European Reference Laboratory of Parasites** and network of **National Reference Laboratories** are well represented in the consortium, and used for e.g. distributing request for sample collaboration. TOXOSOURCES work was presented at the annual workshop of 2021.
- The German EFSA Focal Point encouraged TOXOSOURCES to reach out to the **Focal Point network** to distribute the link to the survey gathering information on production and trade of fresh produce in Europe (TOXOSOURCES-WP3). Consumption of fresh produce is one of the possible routes of *Toxoplasma gondii* transmission to humans, which has been little explored to date. Thus, one aspect of the project is to investigate the presence of *T. gondii* in ready-to-eat fresh produce. The data will be used to evaluate the possible role of fresh produce as a source of *T. gondii* infection (quantitative microbiological risk assessment), and to design a sampling strategy for a multi-centre study investigating selected fresh produce for presence of *T. gondii* oocysts. Action on this was taken in early 2021, and the EFSA-contact of OHEJP was informed via OHEJP-WP5.
- WP5 development work for genotyping approach is suggested to be mentioned in 2021 report of OIE Collaborating Centre ‘Zoonoses in Europe’, FLI.
- TOXOSOURCES collaborates with and builds on the results of several national and regional projects.

6. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	No
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	Yes

Additional information

The challenges due to COVID-19 pandemic have been managed well by planning and resourcefulness, deputies and replacements. More challenges due to the pandemic are expected also in 2022, in particular due to limitations to perform laboratory work, and the situation is followed closely.

There are no critical dependencies between the WPs and Tasks in TOXOSOURCES. Each TOXOSOURCES-WP has identified specific risks and minimized their likelihood and impact by careful planning. The identified points are followed up closely.

TOXOSOURCES-WP1: Delays in work execution or reporting are avoided by setting internal deadlines so that any unexpected minor delays will not delay the deliverables and other key output. Loss of key persons can happen but will have minimal impact on the project, because excellent deputy leaders are assigned for all the key roles. Entry of new partners (e.g. previously external partner, now joining OHEJP as partner following the enlargement campaign) is considered a strength, not a risk. Lack of commitment of partners is considered unlikely, the consortium is motivated and committed. Conflicts within the consortium are avoided by transparent coordination and agreements. Not being able to meet physically is a challenge, but TOXOSOURCES has adapted well.

TOXOSOURCES-WP2: The QMRA models require a range of input data, and assumptions are needed. The uncertainty is reduced as much as possible, e.g., by covering all of Europe in the literature reviews

and using Bayesian hierarchical modelling. Sensitivity analyses will be run to identify the influential input parameters, and scenario analyses will be performed in case of large uncertainty. Potential effects of uncertain data on the outcomes will be clearly presented. Evaluation of data gaps helps identify priorities for future research. QMRA modelling depends on timely delivery of input data, and this is why reaching the milestones has been important. It is acknowledged that the time for running final models and interpreting and reporting the results is limited. The work on human prevalence data has been affected by the COVID-19 pandemic because several task participants have been involved in the pandemic response. The workplan is flexible and the human prevalence data are only used as a correction factor on the predicted number of infections from the QMRA model and will not influence the relative contributions.

TOXOSOURCES-WP3: Limited data are available on the prevalence of *T. gondii* in fresh produce in Europe and a representative sampling design for the survey was not possible. This was solved by applying a risk-based approach. The SOP proved robust and suitable for a multi-centre study.

TOXOSOURCES-WP4: This is high-risk/high-gain ambitious research. Using the selected robust approach, we explore the source-attributing potential of a number of protein candidates that were identified bioinformatically. Well-defined sera from animals experimentally infected with oocysts or tissue cysts was available. Well-defined human sera derived from oocyst-caused infections are scarce, but identified as available in the consortium or via collaborators.

TOXOSOURCES-WP5: A sufficient number of isolates was retrieved and sequenced for the work. Preliminary results regarding the novel method are promising, we can expect that the method will have useful discriminative power. If the discriminative power is lower than expected, the method will nevertheless be a valuable addition to the currently available methods.

JRP23-FBZSH5-ADONIS

1. Summary of the work carried out in year 4

Salmonellosis remains the second most common zoonosis in humans in the EU and failed recent years to decrease further, or even increased, in some EU MSs despite a significantly long-term decreasing trend in human cases since 2008. The ADONIS project investigates at different levels (primary production, epidemiology, and the pathogen) possible underlying drivers for the change in *Salmonella* epidemiology.

On the primary production level measures implemented in the frame of the national control programs (NCPs) and information generated through these measures was evaluated using data from member states where partners in WP2 were located. Audit reports of the NCPs were extensively analysed in order to rank the type of flaws identified and type of recommendations made. Then, data on detection of *Salmonella* in poultry farms from one MS was used to identify factors associated with positive results in routine samplings, suggesting that farm (location, production type), animal (age) and sampling (season, sampler)-associated factors are associated with increased chance of detection of *Salmonella*. The framework developed will be used to analyze data from another country in 2022.

On the epidemiology level

- A detailed statistical analysis for the Netherlands and Belgium revealed that the incidence of *S. Enteritidis*, which is the dominant serotype, decreased significantly in both countries until 2015, followed by an upward trend, which was particularly pronounced in the Netherlands. Potential *S. Enteritidis* outbreaks in both countries and the fraction of invasive infections in the Netherlands also increased after 2015. From this we concluded that SE incidence in both the Netherlands and Belgium stopped decreasing as from 2015 onwards, when an increasing trend started. The increased occurrence of potential outbreaks and invasive infections since 2015 might partially explain the observed reversal of the trend.

- We evaluated the performance of the surveillance programs in Belgium and the Netherlands (that could maybe explain the observed changes in epidemiology). Both surveillance systems are characterized by a relatively high population coverage which changed only marginally between the time-periods 2006-2012 and 2013-2020. The observed change in *Salmonella* epidemiology can therefore not (or only partially) be explained from a change in surveillance systems.
- An exposure assessment regarding *S. Enteritidis* contamination of eggs, based on data from especially Spain, revealed the absence of a correlation of total exposure (product of prevalence and microbiological load) with clinical incidence, indicating that changes in exposure are unlikely to explain observed changes in the *S. Enteritidis* epidemiology.
- We performed an analysis on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the incidence of salmonellosis in The Netherlands which decreased significantly after March 2020 by roughly half of the incidence in the years 2016-2019. We noticed higher fractions of invasive infections and increased relative proportion of serotype Typhimurium and decreased proportion of Enteritidis. This led to decreased contributions of laying hens and increased contributions of pigs and cattle as sources of human infections. The observed changes probably reflect a combination of reduced exposure to *Salmonella* due to restrictions on international travels and gatherings, closure of dine-in restaurants, catering and hospitality sectors at large, and changes in healthcare-seeking and diagnostic behaviours.
- We conducted a source attribution study for *Salmonella* in the EU based on outbreak data using EFSA data. Overall, the most important food source was eggs (48%) followed by pork (10%), and (other) meat products (9%). Outbreaks caused by *S. Enteritidis* and other less common serotypes were mostly attributed to eggs (58% and 20% resp.) whereas outbreaks caused by *S. Typhimurium* and its monophasic variant were mainly attributed to pork (37%). There was a significant increase in the number of outbreaks, by 5% on average per year (IRR: 1.05, 95% CI: 1.01-1.09), between 2015 and 2019, which was mainly caused by an increase in Eastern Europe related to *S. Enteritidis* (and eggs).

On the pathogen level the project made a start with the genomics part by constructing a sequence inventory and a shared database from which analysis will be performed in order to assess potential changes in the population biology of *S. Enteritidis* on EU scale. Preliminary results suggests a role of plasmid content. We also started with the analysis of the population structure of *Salmonella* in the EU which will involve a population-genetic description (diversity, clonality, etc) as well as a phylodynamic analysis to identify recent clones that emerged.

Finally, a framework for the multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) has been made, the criteria for the assessment of the possible explaining determinants for the changing *Salmonella* epidemiology have been defined. Two surveys regarding the weighting of criteria according to their importance and for scoring the different possible drivers according to the (weighted) criteria has been completed by the panel of experts. The MCDA modelling with this data will be performed in 2022.

2. Work carried out in the JRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1 Project management

WP1-T1- Coordination

Although challenging due to the COVID-19 situation the project is running so far without major problems. Regular TCs within the project management team and within WPs were/are conducted.

WP1-T2- Aligning and communication

WP1-T2-ST1 Reporting

Draft 9M report over 2021 has been delivered, and current document is the updated 12M report 2021.

WP1-T2-ST2 Alignment and communication

The ADONIS project was shortly discussed at the ECDC food-and waterborne disease disease group coordination meeting (Nov. 2021) .

WP2 Salmonella controls at the primary production level

WP2-T1- Comparative analysis of Salmonella controls and management measures at MSs level

Comparative analysis of *Salmonella* national control programs (NCP) and management measures at MS level has been based on three activities: 1) an evaluation of historic data from controls performed by competent authorities and food business operators in laying hen flocks in one MS (Spain), 2) a questionnaire assessing differences in the NCPs performed at the country level filled in by partners participating in this task (France, the Netherlands, Poland, Spain and United Kingdom), and 3) a review of the audit reports on NCPs performed by the European Commission. An update on the status of each of these activities is provided below:

1. **Analysis of historic data from NCP:** Data on the surveillance activities carried out in laying hen flocks as part of the NCP in Spain between 2013 and 2019 were shared by the national veterinary official services (Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Fisheries). The database included information on the date, type and number of samples collected in all laying hen flocks, the agent conducting the sampling (Competent Authorities – CA – or Food Business Operators – FBO) and the result regarding *Salmonella* detection (negative, positive for a target serovar – Enteritidis or Typhimurium – or positive for other serovars). Overall, approximately 66,000 samples were collected during 48,000 sampling events over the seven-year period, with only 4% of the samplings resulting in the detection of *Salmonella* (and 0.8% positive for a target serovar). Significant variations in the proportion of positive events were observed in terms of the location of the farm, year, time of the year, sampler (CA or FBO), type of sample (dust, feces, boot swabs), flock type (cage, barn, free-range and organic) and age of the animals. Results were analyzed using a Bayesian hierarchical mixed logistic regression model using the result in the sampling (positive or negative to *Salmonella* isolation) as the response variable and the available covariables at the farm (location), flock (flock size, production type) and sampling (date of sampling, age of the animals, sample type, sampler) levels as potential explanatory variables.

Results revealed a major effect of the sampler (FBO vs. CA) even after the effect of all the other known predictors was considered. Furthermore, a significant effect of the year and the time of sampling were also found. Additional details will be provided in the deliverable report.

2. **Questionnaire on NCP at the country level:** a questionnaire with open and closed questions (multiple-choice and dichotomous) was generated to be filled in by interested partners in WP2. The document was divided into four main sections scope of the program and population assessed, auto control checks performed by FBO, official controls performed by CA, and biosecurity measures. Questionnaires were filled in by partner members/associated institutions with experience on the NCP in each country.

The answers revealed many similarities between countries (as expected since all NCPs are based on European Regulation (EC) No 1177/2006) but some differences were found in all four sections. The laying hen populations assessed differed largely on predominant production systems, and small farms (outside of the scope of the NCPs) were defined differently depending on the country. Target serotypes included in NCPs also differed in certain cases, and funding mechanisms for compensation to producers were also different (public vs. private

insurance systems). Similarly, NCPs differend slightly in terms of biosecurity requirements/vaccination policies, although lack of precise information on vaccination was in fact identified as a limitation in several countries. Additional details will be provided in the deliverable report.

The main conclusions from reviewing of audit reports:

- a) Member States put quite some effort and resources on the implementation of NSCP, so does the EC to verify it
- b) Although the quality and precision of recommendations seem to improve, the key for auditing countries is unclear. It is neither
 - human population since Bulgaria was audited 3 times, France – 1, and Sweden – 0
 - nor animal production (Germany and Malta – 2 each)
- c) Numerous legislation quoted in the recommendations shows multiplicity and complexity of requirements
- d) As a result, although NSCPs have been implemented more than a decade ago, and they are being improved ever since, almost none NSCP is prefect.
- e) Deficiencies concern sampling, laboratory testing, reporting, restrictions and measures taken along the food chain (including outbreak analyses), as well as evaluation of NSCPs progress.

Anses contributed to the development of the questionnaire on *Salmonella* controls at MSs level. We provided data for France, along with the National Laboratory for *Salmonella* in poultry production and the French Ministry of Agriculture. Regarding analysis on temporal trends of *Salmonella* in poultry, we are presently in discussion with the Ministry of Agriculture to obtain data on the results of the national control programs from 2013 to 2020 in France.

WP2-T2- Comparative analysis of Salmonella controls and management measures at farm level

WP2-T2-ST1 Field studies during outbreaks and sensitivity testing

A harmonized protocol for the investigation of *Salmonella* outbreaks in laying farms was developed by APHA and Anses in 2020. Shortly, the protocol includes a study to assess the sensitivity of several sampling methods to detect *Salmonella* in the environment of a positive flock (swabs, boot swabs, dust samples) and to estimate the intra-flock prevalence of birds excreting *Salmonella* in droppings. The results obtained in the sensitivity study will make possible to update the sensitivity models previously developed in the UK and France in 2000's. The field investigation also includes a study on the efficacy of cleaning and disinfection (C&D) measures taken in *Salmonella* positive layer farms. More than thirty environmental samples are performed before C&D for *Salmonella* detection in order to identify the most contaminated surfaces in the farm. Samples are taken at the same points after C&D to evaluate the efficacy of C&D practices. We focus on the study of outbreaks occurring on aviary or barn laying hen farms, as those types of housing systems are less studied than the furnished cage system. Field studies were planned to begin during spring 2020. The objective was to study five outbreaks in the UK and five outbreaks in France. We had to postpone the study due to the COVID-19 crisis (no farm visit was allowed in 2020). The first visit was carried in April 2021 in France.

As mentioned above, opportunities for field work were severely curtailed by the pandemic. APHA managed to visit two farms in 2020 in between national lock-downs. Four post- cleaning and disinfection visits were carried out on layer farms linked with ongoing human outbreaks of *Salmonella* Enteritidis. Sampling followed the agreed protocol (see above). At one premises, no *S. Enteritidis* was found within the bird area of the sampled poultry houses, but it was isolated from a sample collected in an adjoining service area and from two dead mice. Multiple samples collected outside one of the houses were positive, primarily from puddles in various locations. At the second premises, samples collected from both inside and outside of the poultry houses had *S. Enteritidis* isolated from them. No positive samples were found after cleaning and disinfection a further two follow-up visits. Advice was

given to farms on *Salmonella* control, which included recommendations for cleaning and disinfection, egg handling, and enhanced biosecurity. No *S. Enteritidis* has been reported in subsequent flocks from any of the farms.

WBVR works on a review that aims at checking the scientific literature on available data on sampling protocols. In this review information is collected to answer two questions. First one aims at reviewing what is the lowest prevalence (limit of detection) of *Salmonella* Enteritidis in laying hens, which can be detected in the environmental samples with a high confidentiality. This is a comparison of the prevalence in laying hens with the prevalence in environmental samples. The requirements here are that it is known what is the *S. Enteritidis* prevalence in laying hens as detected with culture on samples of individual laying hens.

The second research question aims at reviewing the diagnostic sensitivity of environmental sampling methods to detect *S. Enteritidis* in laying hens. It is a comparison of the detection ability of different environmental sample procedures. It does not matter what the *S. Enteritidis* prevalence is. The only requirement is that the flock is infected with *S. Enteritidis*. The databased searches resulted in identifying 1175 publications. Following removal of duplicates and screening of title and abstract resulted in determination of 118 full texts. They are currently assessed for eligibility by two researchers. This screening will be followed by extraction of data from identified publications, its analysis and reporting.

WP2-T2-ST2 On farm surveys

PIWet is involved in the development of questionnaires on welfare, biosecurity, and other preventive vaccinations carried out on farms concerning other pathogens and in the context of *Salmonella spp.* infections on poultry farms located throughout the country. The questionnaires were prepared and sent almost all over the country. We are currently awaiting the results of the sent out questionnaires containing detailed information on the poultry flocks under management. Unfortunately, the collection of the survey is significantly delayed than previously thought.

We are still waiting for the results of the farm surveys.

WP3 Surveillance, epidemiology and source attribution

WP3-T1- Evaluation of surveillance systems in humans

In the previous 12M report of 2020, we described that key elements and attributes were identified for evaluation, as well as the countries of which the *Salmonella* surveillance system would be evaluated. These countries were Spain, UK, Netherlands, Belgium, and Norway. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, resources were limited and we decided first to focus on the Netherlands and Belgium.

Currently, the key elements for the surveillance system of the Netherlands and Belgium have been described, including e.g. objectives of the surveillance system, case definition etc. All key attributes, such as internal completeness and geographic coverage of the surveillance system, have also been described. These results are currently being collated in a single deliverable, that we expect to finalize in January/February 2022, which is 2 months after the initially planned submission date. Due to time constraints, and because they are not part of the ADONIS project, the Spanish surveillance system could not be evaluated.

WP3-T2- Assessment of changes in the epidemiology of human *S. Enteritidis* (SE) cases and other relevant serovars

Time series analyses to identify factors that might explain the stagnating trend of *S. Enteritidis* have been finalized for the Netherlands and Belgium. Data on culture-confirmed SE human infections from national surveillance registries in the Netherlands and Belgium between 2006 and 2019 were analyzed using multivariable negative-binomial regression models with restricted cubic splines. SE incidence was significantly higher in summer and autumn versus winter, as well as in persons aged 0-4 and 5-14 versus ≥ 60 years, and increased with increasing proportions of travel-related and resistant SE

infections. SE incidence decreased significantly in both countries until 2015, followed by an upward trend, which was particularly pronounced in the Netherlands (Fig. 1). Potential SE outbreaks in both countries and invasive infections in the Netherlands also increased after 2015. From this we concluded that SE incidence in both the Netherlands and Belgium stopped decreasing as from 2015 onwards, when an increasing trend started. The increased occurrence of potential outbreaks and invasive infections since 2015 might partially explain the observed reversal of the trend. While these factors provide insights into the possible causes of the stagnating trend, attention should also be given to factors influencing SE epidemiology at primary (animal) production and pathogen genomic levels.

[A manuscript describing these analyses has been submitted in December 2021 to Eurosurveillance for publication]

Fig. 1 Changes over time in the incidence of *Salmonella* Enteritidis human infection based on the multivariable negative binomial model using restricted cubic splines on the long-term incidence with four knots equally distributed (2006, 2010, 2015, 2019). Reference year: 2015.

- A. We evaluated the national *Salmonella* surveillance systems in Belgium. The surveillance of human salmonellosis in Belgium is dependent on the referral of human *Salmonella* isolates to the National Reference Center (NRC). Knowledge of current diagnostic practices and the coverage of the national *Salmonella* surveillance system are important to correctly interpret surveillance data and trends over time, to estimate the true burden of salmonellosis in Belgium, and to evaluate the appropriateness of implementing wholegenome sequencing (WGS) at this central level. The coverage of the NRC was defined as the proportion of all diagnosed human *Salmonella* cases in Belgium reported to the NRC and was assessed for 2019 via a survey among all licensed Belgian medical laboratories in 2019, and for 2016–2020 via a capture-recapture study using the Sentinel Network of Laboratories (SNL) as the external source. In addition, the survey was used to assess the impact of the implementation of culture-independent diagnostic tests (CIDTs) at the level of peripheral laboratory sites, as a potential threat to national public health surveillance programs. The coverage of the NRC surveillance system was estimated to be 83% and 85%, based on the results of the survey and on the two-source capture-recapture study, respectively. Further, the results of the survey indicated a limited use of CIDTs by peripheral laboratories in 2019. Given the high coverage and the limited impact of CIDTs on the referral of isolates, we may conclude that the NRC can confidently monitor the epidemiological situation and identify outbreaks throughout the country. These

findings may guide the decision to implement WGS at the level of the NRC and may improve estimates of the true burden of salmonellosis in Belgium. We obtained similar results for The Netherlands and conclude that the observed change in *Salmonella* epidemiology can therefore not (or only partially) be explained from a change in surveillance systems.

[this work has been published as: Nina Van Goethem, An Van Den Bossche, Pieter-Jan Ceysens, Adrien Lajot, Wim Coucke, Kris Vernelen, Nancy H. C. Roosens, Sigrid C. J. De Keersmaecker, Dieter Van Cauteren, Wesley Mattheus. Coverage of the national surveillance system for human Salmonella infections, Belgium, 2016-2020. PLOS ONE: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256820>]

- B. We determined the main food sources and recent trends of salmonellosis outbreaks in Europe. Although harmonized *Salmonella* control programmes are implemented at primary production, *Salmonella* remains a major cause of foodborne outbreaks in Europe. Outbreak data are observed at the public health endpoint and provide a picture of the most important sources of *Salmonella* infection at the level of exposure. To prioritize interventions, it is important to keep abreast of the sources and trends of salmonellosis outbreaks. Salmonellosis outbreak data for 34 European countries in 2015-2019 were obtained from the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). For source attribution, food products implicated were categorized according to EFSA's zoonosis catalogue classification scheme. An established probabilistic attribution model was then applied using the information on the implicated foods, overall and by region and serotype. To assess significant trends in outbreak occurrence, overall and by region and serotype, Poisson mixed-effects models were used. Results: Overall, the most important food source was eggs (48%, 95% Uncertainty Interval(UI): 45-51%), followed by pork (10%, 95% UI: 8-12%), and more generally, meat products (9%, 95% UI: 7-11%) (Fig. 2). While eggs were the first most important food source in all regions, pork was the second most common food source in Northern and Western Europe and meat products in Eastern and Southern Europe (Fig. 3). Outbreaks caused by *S. Enteritidis* and other less common serotypes were mostly attributed to eggs (58%, 95% UI: 54-62% and 20%, 95% UI: 13-27%, respectively), whereas, outbreaks caused by *S. Typhimurium* and its monophasic variant were mainly attributed to pork (37%, 95% UI: 29-45%) (Fig. 4). There was a significant increase in the number of outbreaks, by 5% on average per year (IRR: 1.05, 95% CI: 1.01-1.09), between 2015 and 2019. Particularly, the number of outbreaks increased significantly in Eastern Europe and was mainly caused by *S. Enteritidis* (IRR: 1.15, 95% CI: 1.09-1.22), whereas in Northern and Southern Europe, outbreaks caused by *S. Enteritidis* decreased significantly from 2015 to 2019 (IRR: 0.72, 95% CI: 0.61-0.85; IRR: 0.71, 95% CI: 0.63-0.80, respectively). In conclusion: In Europe, eggs remain the primary source of reported salmonellosis outbreaks, which increased significantly in occurrence from 2015 to 2019, particularly outbreaks caused by *S. Enteritidis* in Eastern European countries. Regional, temporal and serotype-associated differences in the relative contributions of the different sources were also observed.

[A manuscript describing these analyses is in preparation for In. J. Food. Microb.]

Fig. 2. Proportions of human salmonellosis outbreaks attributed to simple and unknown food sources by year with their respective 95% uncertainty intervals in Europe, 2015-2019.

Fig. 3. Proportions of human salmonellosis outbreaks attributed to simple and unknown food sources by EU region with their respective 95% uncertainty intervals, 2015-2019

Fig. 4. Proportions of human salmonellosis outbreaks attributed to simple and unknown food sources by the most common serotypes reported with their respective 95% uncertainty intervals in Europe, 2015-2019

- C. In addition, we performed an analysis on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the incidence of Salmonellosis in The Netherlands. The public health measures implemented to control COVID-19 may influence also other infectious diseases. Using national laboratory surveillance data, we assessed the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on human salmonellosis in the Netherlands until March 2021. Salmonellosis incidence decreased significantly after March 2020: in the 2nd, 3rd and 4th quarters of 2020, and in the 1st quarter of 2021, incidence decreased by 55%, 57%, 47% and 37%, respectively, compared to the same quarters of 2016-2019 (Fig. 5). The decrease was strongest among travel-related cases (94%, 84%, 79% and 93% in the aforementioned quarters, respectively). Other significant changes were: increased proportion of cases among older adults and increased proportion of invasive infections, decreased proportion of trimethoprim resistance, and increased proportion of serovar Typhimurium monophasic variant vs. Enteritidis. This led to decreased contributions of laying hens and increased contributions of pigs and cattle as sources of human infections. The observed changes probably reflect a combination of reduced exposure to *Salmonella* due to restrictions on international travels and gatherings, closure of dine-in restaurants, catering and hospitality sectors at large, and changes in healthcare-seeking and diagnostic behaviours.

[a paper has been published: Mughini Gras et al 2021, Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on human salmonellosis in the Netherlands; *Epidemiology & Infection*, DOI: 10.1017/S0950268821002557]

Fig. 5. Quarterly proportions of salmonellosis cases according to travel history (A), invasiveness (B), infecting serovar (C)

WP3-T3- Assessment of human exposure to S. Enteritidis

The exposure assessment has been performed and finalized. For the exposure assessment the simplified approach of the pre-treatment load was used, which was calculated as the product of egg SE prevalence and egg consumption rate. The main challenge was data availability, because data on S. Enteritidis in eggs (used as input for the exposure assessment model) was only available for Spain. For the other countries for which the exposure assessment would be performed, namely the Netherlands, Belgium and the UK, these data were not available or could not be obtained.

Results for Spain suggest a poor correlation between the number of human S. Enteritidis and the pre-treatment S. Enteritidis cases was poor. This indicates that changes in human exposure to S. Enteritidis through consumption of eggs, which is the most important source of human S. Enteritidis infections, cannot explain the stagnating S. Enteritidis trend. Furthermore, the significance of import of eggs played a minor role in Spain. However, it is important to note that these conclusions are based on data from Spain only.

WP4 Salmonella Genomics

WP4-T1- Collection overview

All partners are involved in WP4, especially in the generation and centralisation of sequences. An inventory was created to get an overview of the available strains and sequences at each partner institution. The inventories were collated and presented at a teleconference held on 17 February 2020, where a decision was made on the final selection of strains to be sequenced for the genomic analyses. The whole dataset is being shared within the consortium for analysis.

Working groups are made to jointly tackle the different objectives.

WP4-T2- Population structure and comparative genomics

A first rough analysis on the population structure of *Salmonella* enteritidis has been made. It clearly shows a mixture of seemingly clonal expansion over Europe as well as clones that are very different (Fig. 6). Currently we are analyzing plasmid contents, AMR profiles, virulence profiles, phage content etc.

Fig. 6 NJ-tree of the *Salmonella enteritidis* database of the ADNOIS project.

WP4-T3- Phylodynamics and Phylogeography

The work is in preparatory phase. It will reconstruct the recent (10-years) evolutionary developments within the *Salmonella* Enteritidis population in EU (as captured by the ADONIS dataset).

WP4-T4- Mutant creation and testing including GWAS studies

A pilot GWAS study was performed on a limited dataset of 120 genomes. The study detected 6 plasmid related genes slightly associated with the *S. Enteritidis* increase since 2014. More analysis is needed to confirm this pilot study.

WP5 MCDA model to support priority setting

WP5-T1- Framework building

This task is completed and deliverable 5.1 completed.

A schematic overview of the MCDA process is summarized in the figure below (Fig. 7). This process has been completed up to the MCDA modelling part.

Fig. 7. Schematic overview of the MCDA process.

Identify determinants/interventions (the 'alternatives')

The determinants possibly associated with the reversal of the decreasing trend were identified based on the (hierarchical) structure of the transmission chain and all possible interrelation between primary production, exposure and pathogen characteristics. A literature review was conducted to assist this process in addition to experts' input.

Two MCDA models will be built, one for the determinants and one for the interventions, using the criteria listed here below:

- **Determinants** (factors that may have causal relations with the stagnation of the declining trend):
 - **Primary production**
 - **Premature relaxation of *Salmonella* control measures and/or changes in husbandry practices in laying hen flocks** (e.g. laxer biosecurity measures - incl. those implicitly linked to improved animal welfare like free-range hen farms and farms with outdoor access, changes in vaccination schemes, as this has become voluntary/forbidden in some countries, changes farm size, group size and stock density, etc).
 - **Deficiencies in the enforcement of existing regulations by competent authorities and/or producers in laying hen flocks** (e.g. authorities fail to fully comply with regulations due to lack of resources, high workload, and/or possible negligence/malpractice of those involved in control activities, etc.)
 - **Inadequacies of statutory sampling programs in laying hen flocks** (e.g. insufficient sensitivity of current protocols, sampling protocols are prone to misinterpretation or misuse, etc.)
 - **Public health and epidemiology**
 - **Changes in national *Salmonella* surveillance programs and/or diagnostics** (e.g. more sensitive in diagnostics or increased geographical surveillance coverage)
 - **Increased exposure to *S. Enteritidis* through eggs or changes in risk factors for infection (i.e. transmission routes)**
 - **Pathogen**

- **Emergence and spread of specific *S. Enteritidis* strains with increased fitness**, e.g. increased replication, virulence and/or antimicrobial resistance.
- **Interventions** (measures that can be implemented to reverse the stagnating trend):
 - **Primary production**
 - Implementing stricter biosecurity measures and/or change husbandry practices
 - Increasing vaccination (with currently available vaccines)
 - Improving/increasing sampling schemes
 - **Public health and epidemiology**
 - Changing case reporting and/or case ascertainment procedures
 - Reduce exposure to specific sources
 - **Pathogen**
 - Set strain-specific targets for surveillance
 - Develop new vaccines for specific strains

Produce list of criteria

- **Criteria for the determinants** (to define which has the strongest “causal relationship”) were:
 - Strength of evidence (based on rigor, type and quality of research outcomes supporting a given determinant)
 - Plausibility (based on the general credibility/acceptability of the research outcomes and underlying assumptions supporting a given determinant)
 - Consistency of findings (based on the amount of concordant research outcomes supporting a given determinant)
 - Effect size (based on the magnitude of the effect: The larger the effect size in the research outcomes the stronger the causal relationship of a given determinant)
- **Criteria for the interventions** (to define which is the “most promising” for prioritization)
 - Feasibility (based on the degree for the intervention to be easily or conveniently implemented, both financially and logistically)
 - Public health impact (based on the expected impact that the intervention would have on the human disease burden)
 - Cost-effectiveness (based on the expected impact that the intervention would have on the cost of illness, after considering the costs of the intervention itself)
 - Novelty/originality (based on the degree of innovation of the intervention: something that has been experienced/tried before and has not worked well could be less promising of something that has never been tried before)

These criteria were determined by the WP5 research team using input from the *Salmonella* experts working in the project. It is assumed that that decision criteria are independent of one another.

Weight criteria according to relative importance by a panel of experts: survey I

Different approaches exist to assign weights to the different criteria according to their relative importance [1]. In ADONIS, we use the AHP method, in which the criteria weights are established based on pairwise comparisons. Pairwise comparisons are used on each level, to provide estimations of the weights for the criteria and for the alternatives as well, resulting in a preference matrix. The criteria weights are determined by the mathematical method of finding the principal eigenvector of this matrix [2], and then a consistency ratio is defined to assess the consistency of judgements. The eigenvector is the positive vector that changes by only a scalar factor when that linear transformation (expressed as the matrix in question) is applied to it. As a disadvantage, seeing that all criteria have to be compared with each other, stakeholders have to make $n*(n-1)/2$ decisions. The weights of the criteria will be determined by the panel of experts (see Section 4 later on) by filling out a survey.

Score determinants/interventions against the criteria by a panel of experts: survey II

Also the alternatives will be scored using Saaty’s weighting method (AHP method) based on pairwise evaluations: the advantage of AHP pairwise comparisons is that there is no need to convert all valuations into one unit, e.g. costs, rates, etc. One just needs to specify what is judged to be more important (pairwise) at the level of alternative criteria inside the criterion structure. The scores of the determinants and interventions will also be determined by the panel of experts (see Section 4 later on) by filling out a second survey. Survey 2 will be administered separately from Survey 1.

The scale for the pair-wise comparisons for both the weighting of criteria and scoring of alternatives is summarized here below.

The Fundamental Scale for Pairwise Comparisons		
Intensity of Importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two elements contribute equally to the objective
3	Moderate importance	Experience and judgment slightly favor one element over another
5	Strong importance	Experience and judgment strongly favor one element over another
7	Very strong importance	One element is favored very strongly over another; its dominance is demonstrated in practice
9	Extreme importance	The evidence favoring one element over another is of the highest possible order of affirmation
Intensities of 2, 4, 6, and 8 can be used to express intermediate values. Intensities 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, etc. can be used for elements that are very close in importance.		

We follow the general advice for the pairwise comparisons to score alternatives that are no more than about 9, as it time-consuming, there can arise problems with inconsistency and fatigue, and it can lead to small differences in final scores. Same rule of thumb goes for the number of criteria. This will be tested during data analysis by comparing variation in scores in the first vs. second half of the surveys to check whether within the same respondent, this has changed (as an indication of potential bias).

Construct the final ranking of the determinants/interventions according to relative importance

Following the AHP approach, we will compute the priority vector, as follows: (<https://people.revoledu.com/kardi/tutorial/AHP/Priority%20Vector.htm>)

1. Paired comparison matrix level 1 with respect to the goal (aggregated pairwise comparisons of the criteria, i.e. weighting) → the priority vector is obtained from normalized Eigen vector of the matrix.
2. Paired comparison matrix level 2 with respect to each criteria (aggregated pairwise comparisons of the alternatives against each of the criteria, i.e. scoring) → calculate priority vector for each of the criteria
3. Compute the overall composite weight of each alternative choice based on the weight of level 1 and level 2 → overall weight is the normalization of linear combination of multiplication between weight and priority vector.

WPS-T2- T2 MCDA modelling

Data analysis will be performed over the first half of 2022 in R using the following packages:

- MCDA package (<http://eprints.whiterose.ac.uk/112838/1/mcda-r-package.pdf>)
- AHP using ahp package (<https://www.r-bloggers.com/analytic-hierarchy-process-ahp-with-the-ahp-package/>,

<https://bioconductor.org/packages/devel/bioc/vignettes/Prize/inst/doc/Prize.pdf>,
<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/ahp/vignettes/examples.html>

- AHP for survey data using ahpsurvey package (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/ahpsurvey/vignettes/my-vignette.html>)

3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
23	D-JRP#-1.2	Y3 report delivered	M39	M39		P	
23	D-JRP#-2.1	Report on the evaluation of the questionnaires	M30	M47		P Deliverable to be uploaded soon	
23	D-JRP26- WP2.3	MS's specific analysis of temporal trend of <i>Salmonella</i> in poultry flocks	43		50	Delay in getting authorization from national veterinary authorities to share final outcomes	
23	D-JRP26- WP2.4	Recommendations for improving <i>Salmonella</i> surveillance in poultry flocks	48		58	Moved to the end of the project (incl. 6M extension)	
23	D-JRP#-3.1	Description of surveillance systems regarding their key	36		50	3.1 and 3.2 will reported in one report. Delays due	

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number (Original number, if different from the actual one)	Deliverable name (Original name, if different from the actual one)	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* (1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)
		elements				to COVID-19 but draft ready	
23	D-JRP#-3.2	Description of basic epidemiological characteristics of human S. Enteritidis cases and other relevant serovars	36		50	3.2 and 3.4 will reported in one report. Delays due to COVID-19 but draft ready	
23	D-JRP26-WP3.3	Report on the evaluation of the surveillance systems' attributes	48		50	3.1 and 3.2 will reported in one report. Delays due to COVID-19 but draft ready	
23	D-JRP#-3.4	Extended the report on epidemiological characteristics with results from the rarefaction analysis the refined source attribution models, but also with data on food consumption patterns	45		50	3.2 and 3.4 will reported in one report. Delays due to COVID-19 but draft ready	
23	D-JRP#-3.5	Report on human S. enteritidis exposure in	42		50	Finished and draft deliverable ready.	

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
		different countries and time periods				Finalisation for submission M50.	
23	D-JRP#-4.1	Sequence inventory report	31	38			
23	D-JRP#-5.1	Final assessment frameworks of MCDA	48	48			

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
23	M-JRP26-1	Kick-off meeting organised	M26	Y		
23	M-JRP26-2	Communication partners mapped	M28	Y		EFSA and ECDC participate in the MCDA
23	M-JRP26-3	Inventory of documents available for the comparative analyses	M30	Y		
23	M-JRP26-4	Farm survey planed and questionnaires developed	M30	partly		COVID-19 delayed field work
23	M-JRP26-5	Selection of three countries of which their national S. Enteritidis surveillance systems will be evaluated	M27	Y		
23	M-JRP26-6	Obtained national surveillance data on S. Enteritidis and other relevant serovars	M30	Y		
23	M-JRP26-7	Sequence collection to be shared amongst partners	M31	dealyed	M44	One partner missing in MTA signature and 2 partners sequence sharing. Brexit and COVID-19 have significantly affected the sequence sharing.
23	M-JRP26-8	Phylogenetic trees describing the sequence collection (D-JRP#-WP4.1)	M32	Delayed	M44	One partner missing in MTA signature and 2 partners sequence sharing. Brexit and COVID-19 have

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
						significantly affected the sequence sharing.
23	M-JRP26-9	Inventory of MCDA methods suited to the data being collected.	M30	Y		
23	M-JRP26-10	Annual meeting organised	M40	Y		
23	M-JRP26-11	Outline of the assessment framework (transmission chain)	M42	Y		
23	M-JRP26-12	Meeting on aligning epidemiological and QMRA approach	M45	Y		
23	M-JRP26-13	List of candidate strains for phenotype testing	M37	delayed	M60	We expect to have the complete sequence collection in Month 44, before the first genomic analyses suggest a list of candidates for phenotypic testing
23	M-JRP26-14	Identification of the experts to participate in the weighting exercise of the MCDA	M42	Y		
23	M-JRP26-15	Data finalized for manuscript on Population of <i>Salmonella</i> collection	M48	Y		

4. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Mughini Gras et al 2021, Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on human salmonellosis in the Netherlands; <i>Epidemiology & Infection</i> , DOI: 10.1017/S0950268821002557	Yes		Y (2500 euros)
Nina Van Goethem, An Van Den Bossche, Pieter-Jan Ceysens, Adrien Lajot, Wim Coucke, Kris Vernelen, Nancy H. C. Roosens, Sigrid C. J. De Keersmaecker, Dieter Van Cauteren, Wesley Mattheus. Coverage of the national surveillance system for human <i>Salmonella</i> infections, Belgium, 2016-2020. <i>PLOS ONE</i> : https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256820	Yes		Y

Additional output

- Linda Chanamé Pinedo et al. 2021. Trend reversal in human infections with *Salmonella* Enteritidis in The Netherlands (2005-2019). Abstract and oral presentation at OHEJP ASM June 2021.
- Linda Chanamé Pinedo et al. 2021. Temporal trends and epidemiological patterns of antimicrobial resistance in human *Salmonella enterica* isolates in the Netherlands, 2008 to 2019. Abstract submitted to I3S conference (June 2022, France).

5. Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries

Given our co-financing structure we perform this research in agreement with the Dutch Ministry of Health. We report the results of ADONIS in our half-yearly reporting.

We are in contact with ECDC en EFSA to present our results on source attribution of *Salmonella* based on outbreak data (EFSA data), which gave some potential interesting research for these stakeholders.

6. List of critical risks

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	No
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	No
Other risks (please describe)	No

JRP24-FBZSH9-BeONE

1. Summary of the work carried out in year 4

In BeONE we have composed a test dataset consisting of whole genome sequences (WGS) and related metadata across four target pathogens (*Salmonella*, *Listeria*, STEC and *Campylobacter*). This dataset has been collected from the 12 partner institutes involved in BeONE, and is used to test different approaches of analysing and clustering bacterial genomes for surveillance and outbreak detection. For this purpose a standardization of ontologies and metadata is also provided. Furthermore, we are creating a common platform to share this type of data (WGS, allele profiles and metadata) between institutions, both national and international, and as part of this platform, a dashboard for visualising data is being developed.

The work has been significantly delayed during the last year, due to COVID-19 and large personnel changes. However, there has still been significant progress in the project.

The State of the art delivery (D1.1) was completed in collaboration with the ORION project, and the BeONE Dataset collection and curation was completed, with a total of 3,439 isolates. Quality control

and assembly of the genomes is ongoing. Furthermore, an automated system for congruence analysis has been set up, and the pipelines to evaluate have been identified among the 12 BeONE partners.

Likewise, a draft manuscript for a conceptual model on genomic epidemiology has been written (D2.1). The outbreak detection algorithm (D2.2) has been finalized and tested on *Listeria*, and is now to be tested on the remaining target pathogens.

The standardization using ontologies has been completed. The core of a database model has been developed, that supports comparison of data from different data supplying components. Domain specific areas are still under development, and crucially epidemiological data (person/animal) is still missing. The collected metadata (M3.4) will help the finalization of this last stage of the data model development. The form of data sharing has been changed due to change of personnel and will be encrypted JSON files for now, with the possibility of further development.

The dashboard and backend development has been closely linked to a Danish project (SOFI), where the food authorities, DTU (as expert data processor of food and livestock samples) and SSI (public health Institute), collaborate on a common platform for integrated analysis of food and patient samples for outbreak detection. The dashboard in its current state is focused on a searchable and sortable data table. It can merge and display data from multiple sources, however, development is still ongoing. cgMLST and clustering are still being investigated. The actual visualization of epi-curves and phylogenetic trees for the dashboard are ongoing and we will have a meeting to discuss this in January.

A new plan for testing has been made and many partners are/will be involved. Some components have already been tested within the SOFI pipeline. From the second annual meeting Mirko Rossi was invited as keynote speaker and presented the EFSA pipeline, BeONE and this pipeline are fairly streamlined. Finally, the monthly meetings have been reintroduced to enable more communication between partners and across WPs.

2. Work carried out in the IRP, scientific results and integrative outcomes

WP1: Typing comparability and nomenclature

WP1-T1 Establishment of state of the art

Status: Completed

As reported in the 9M report, this task was completed in collaboration with the ORION project (deliverable available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5155570>). In particular, the BeONE contributions were mainly focused on describing start-to-end workflows for routine genome-based surveillance of the four foodborne bacterial species under study (*Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Escherichia coli* and *Campylobacter jejuni*), with emphasis on identifying challenges and opportunities for harnessing WGS as a key tool for One Health Surveillance. The final output is an online handbook covering the main technical and practical aspects associated with the application of WGS for foodborne diseases surveillance. By following a simple and straightforward writing and structure, this document can be easily understandable by laboratory staff starting in the field, thus helping national and local labs to build capacity and competence on the use of NGS methods for surveillance purposes. The One Health Sequencing for Surveillance HandBook is available at <https://oh-sfs-handbook.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>.

WP1-T2 Dataset selection and curation

WP1-T2-ST1 Dataset selection and collection

Status: Completed

This task had the objective of compiling a dataset (including sequencing reads and respective metadata) that captures the genomic diversity within the populations of the four foodborne pathogens

(*Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Escherichia coli* and *Campylobacter jejuni*), including samples from human, food and veterinary sources and sets of epidemiologically verified outbreak isolates. In particular, this dataset is intended to be used for: i) cluster congruence analysis between the different partner's pipelines (WP1); ii) testing novel algorithms (combining genomic and epidemiological data) for outbreak detection (WP2); iii) testing metadata structures and the compliance and viability of the metadata combination from different sectors and regions (WP3); iv) testing both the dashboard and the database, and analysis of the backend (WP3/4); and v) testing the behaviour of the system to handle epi-data from different countries in a user-oriented manner (WP4). Therefore, it required a close collaboration with all the BeONE partners, which were requested to share anonymized data under the compliance of a signed Material Transfer Agreement (MTA). The MTA was circulated a priori for revision and final acceptance. This task also involved that everything was set up at NVI's server SAGA for data upload, storage and analysis. Data submission was performed following guidelines for data upload (account login, anonymization, and transfer of data), which included specific instructions to fill a metadata submission form elaborated using EFSA Data Collection Framework for Controlled Vocabularies in collaboration with WP3. A final step for read anonymization including rename of sequencing reads and shuffling their order in the file was performed. The BeONE dataset comprises a total of 3,439 isolates [*L. monocytogenes* (n=1,305), *S. enterica* (n=1,169), *E. coli* (n=244) and *C. jejuni* (n=721)]. Although the submission of additional data by the partners is still possible (if needed), the BeONE dataset is considered as complete, being open for usage within the frame of BeONE activities (and in compliance with the MTA). The WP1-T2-ST1 deliverable is available at ZENODO link (available later this month).

WP1-T2-ST2 Quality check and assurance, and genome assembly

Status: Ongoing

As mentioned in the previous annual report, this subtask was redefined and inserted within WP1-T3 activities. In particular, it will involve reads' quality control/filtering, confirmation of species identification (and contamination checking), genome assembly and in silico typing, possibly with <https://github.com/tseemann/mlst>. In order to optimize this task, an additional effort was made (in collaboration with WP3) to refine the assembly process not only regarding the running time and resources' allocation, but also to decrease the amount of unnecessary temporary data generated by the assembler. The delay associated with this additional work is expected to be compensated by its consequent increase in the assembly efficiency.

WP1-T3 Clustering congruence and thresholds

WP1-T3-ST1 Selection of WGS-based typing methods to be evaluated

Status: Ongoing

The selection of WGS-based typing methods to be evaluated started at the BeONE Kick Off Meeting where a survey was performed to assess which institutions would be available to participate in the analysis, i.e. include their routine pipeline for genomic surveillance and outbreak investigation of the four foodborne pathogens. All partners (12 institutions, because PHE has left the project) confirmed their availability to participate in this exercise and each partner will be responsible for pipeline installation and running on SAGA (or locally), with full support of WP1/WP3 teams. Additional details regarding each of the pipelines, such as its nature (assembly-based or mapping-based), clustering method, cluster definition and output format were requested. This information was used to i) identify overlap between the different pipelines and establish a strategy to increase the efficiency of the analysis; and ii) develop the necessary bioinformatics strategies to deal with the output heterogeneity and obtain a desired typing data to pursue with the subsequent sub-task. Furthermore, information regarding the partner's availability to run the pipeline locally or on SAGA was assessed. This information was also crucial to determine the list of pipelines that require installation on SAGA, and estimate the computational and storage needs. After this assessment, additional resources were requested. In summary, the clustering congruence analysis will count on the participation of all the

BeONE partners, and will include eight assembly-based pipelines and four SNP-based pipelines, among which there are widely used commercial and non-commercial software.

WP1-T3-ST2 Assessing clustering congruence between different methods at different hierarchical levels

Status: Ongoing

The completion of this task depends on the setup of the different pipelines and on the completion of the “Cluster congruence” dataset (which will include the BeONE dataset and publicly available data). The setup of the different pipelines is currently ongoing. For the “Cluster congruence” dataset collection, an assessment of the sequencing data available at ENA/SRA was performed. Moreover, isolate typing data from public databases, such as Enterobase or PubMLST, as well as from major scientific publications of the field was collected and used to build “Cluster congruence” dataset with a proper representativeness of the diversity within each species. The selected public dataset is under construction and will be curated following the same procedure as described for the BEONE dataset (see WP1-T2-ST2). As mentioned in the previous 9M report, meanwhile, we have already developed bioinformatics pipelines to automatize the clustering congruence analysis. The developed scripts are able to obtain clusters at every partition threshold for each method, which is the basis to: i) identify threshold levels of clustering stability for each method; ii) compare the congruence between methods and ultimately define threshold ranges showing clustering convergence.

WP1-T3-ST3 Correlating clustering congruence with existing nomenclature schemes

Status: Ongoing

The completion of this sub-task depends on the completion of the dataset collection and curation that is currently ongoing in WP1-T3-ST2. As described in WP1-T3-ST2, the developed scripts are adjusted to allow a rapid comparison of the clustering profiles obtained at different threshold levels and the strains grouping defined by existing nomenclatures.

WP2: Joining molecular and epidemiological methods

WP2-T1: Conceptualization of epidemiological and biological factors impacting on fine resolution clustering and outbreak detection

Status: Completed

A conceptual model of the factors impacting fine resolution clustering and outbreak detection has been made and explained in detail in a draft manuscript which is now undergoing the last revision round with the co-authors. The abstract hereof was submitted as deliverable to Zenodo and the OHEJP online platform.

WP2-T2: Integrating genomics with epidemiology

Status: Ongoing

Cluster detection based on WGS often assumes that the various isolates come from a common source and that the source is clonal in nature i.e. the population of the bacterial pathogen at the source is genetically homogeneous. Thus, all the isolates pertaining to a cluster can be traced back to a most recent common ancestor, which, in epidemiological terms, means that patients that share highly similar strains are likely to have contracted these from a common source. Challenges still remain regarding the epidemiological interpretation of WGS. A major point of uncertainty is the definition of clusters. To this end we have developed a multitier algorithm that incorporates concepts of evolutionary biology. For compatibility with the currently used molecular typing system – cgMLST, Hamming distance, and single-linkage hierarchical clustering (sl) – the first step follows this procedure. The use of single linkage combined with a variable number of missing loci for each isolate allows, however, for allelic distances within a cluster much exceeding the predefined threshold of allelic

dissimilarities. Furthermore, the structural unit of DNA is not the gene but the nucleotide, which means that allelic distances may be in fact an underestimation of the dissimilarity among isolates. We thus use a second step involving SNP-calling, pairwise Hamming distances, and Gaussian mixture models to split potential multimodal distributions of pairwise dissimilarities, which are often indicative of multiple clusters. Additionally, in a third step we calculate the expected SNP distances between any two or n (multiple coalescent) isolates based on Kingman's coalescent model of shared ancestry. In a fourth step, the comparison of the distribution of observed dissimilarities with the expected one is expressed as the probability that the two or n selected isolates come from a common ancestor in a given timespan. The summarized WP2-T2 deliverable (D2.2) will soon be available at ZENODO. The testing of the algorithm is still ongoing and expected to be finalized by M50. A draft manuscript (D2.3) describing the algorithm and its testing is expected to be delivered by M52.

WP2-T2-ST1 Comparison of the epidemiologic clusters with the phylogenetic tree of the Campylobacter jejuni isolates

Status: Ongoing

Progress has been made in this task by partner SSI (13) with identification of several clusters/outbreaks and evidence that a successful surveillance programme can be based on sampling a relatively small fraction (10%) of the cases (DOI: 10.3201/eid2603.190947). Testing of the developed algorithm is expected to be finalized by M50.

WP2-T2-ST2 Comparison of the epidemiologic clusters with the phylogenetic tree of the Shiga toxin producing Escherichia coli (STEC) isolates

Status: Ongoing

We have assembled the dataset of epidemiologically validated outbreak isolates with available WGS and detailed epidemiological metadata; this is expected to be used in testing the algorithm by M50.

WP2-T2-ST3 Comparison of the epidemiologic clusters with the phylogenetic tree of the Salmonella enterica isolates

Status: Ongoing

We have assembled several datasets, corresponding to outbreaks of various *Salmonella enterica* serovars: *Salmonella enterica* serovars Enteritidis, Thompson, Typhimurium, and Heidelberg, that will be used in the validation process.

WP2-T2-ST4 Comparison of the epidemiologic clusters with the phylogenetic tree of the Listeria monocytogenes isolates

Status: Completed

We have applied the above mentioned algorithm to a dataset of *Listeria monocytogenes* CC6, containing isolates epidemiologically validated as part of an outbreak in The Netherlands. In our example, the cluster defined with the broad threshold of ten alleles dissimilarity (often used in practice) is subsetted in the second step to a cluster corresponding to seven alleles and in a third step to one corresponding to four alleles difference. Additionally, our analyses indicate that inclusion of WG sequences from other sectors (i.e. food safety) is highly desirable if not mandatory for accurate cluster identification. The results will soon be available in the deliverable document at ZENODO.

WP2-T3: Definition of guidelines for cluster investigation

Status: Ongoing

In developing the algorithm at WP2-T2 (D2.2) we have used various data sources (e.g. cgMLST and SNP) and methods (e.g. hierarchical clustering, maximum likelihood), and have identified strengths and weaknesses of their usage in daily practice. A comparison of the respective methods as well as

prospective improvements to cluster detection are being compiled into a document expected to be delivered by M52.

WP3: Storage, management, and sharing for meta- and molecular data

WP3-T1: Evaluate national level data sharing

Status: Completed (see 12M REPORT 2020)

WP3-T2: Metadata acquisition and standardisation

WP3-T2-ST1 Metadata acquisition

Status: Completed (see 9M REPORT 2021)

WP3-T2-ST2 Standardization using ontologies

Status: Completed

Epidemiological metadata fields are structured using predefined fields. To allow interoperability between institutions, a selection of suitable EFSA Data Collection Framework (DCF) catalogues is used. The included hierarchical connections between terms suffice to use the vocabulary as an ontology system for the purposes of the BeONE system.

The ontology system has been tested when collecting the metadata from WP1-T2-ST1 using the epidemiological metadata collection excel sheet. This concludes Milestone 3.8.

WP3-T3: Database design and implementation

WP3-T3-ST1 Determine and implement data structure for database

Status: Ongoing

Database schemas have been established for WGS data. Mandatory fields narrow down to cgMLST profile allele hashes, species names, country of origin and year of sampling. Additionally, it is strongly advised to fill a number of optional data fields, including results from Quality Control, computational steps and Epidata at a higher spatiotemporal resolution within the limits of an MTA. Database design regarding epidata has also been finalized. The epidata structure is based on the EFSA Data Collection Framework (DCF) catalogues using preselected fields (see JRP24- WP3-T2-ST2). The metadata implementation allows to combine the hierarchical terms of the DCF catalogues in a tag-like fashion to improve their joint descriptive accuracy. Each hierarchical term is stored as a term lineage within the data model including hierarchical level information to improve automated filtering and annotation of phylogenetic models. The existing Bifrost database still needs to be adjusted to the BeONE data schema.

WP3-T3-ST2 Implement API for import of data

Status: Delayed

Due to personnel changes at SSI, where the API was to be developed as part of the Bifrost system, we redesigned the data import structure, as also mentioned in WP4-T3. As a proof of concept, data from local partners will be transformed into json files following the data structure determined in JRP24-WP3-T3-ST1. Data will then be exported, asymmetrically encrypted and signed, sent to partners and then decrypted on their end to add it to their local database. The implementation of this system is pending and expected to be finished by M50.

WP3-T3-ST3 Data porting from an existing pipeline

Status: Completed

The WGS assembly and quality control pipeline AQUAMIS (<https://doi.org/10.3390/genes12050644>) as well as the cgMLST-based clustering pipeline chewieSnake

(<https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2021.649517>) were adapted to output analysis results in a BeONE compatible JSON data structure. The outputs from these pipelines can be imported into the BeONE MongoDB database without further changes.

WP3-T3-ST4 Data porting from further pipelines

Status: Delayed

The data structures and schemas are being designed with compatibility to a number of different pipelines in mind. As a second compatible example pipeline, the outputs of Bifrost will be ported into the BeONE system. Development has not yet started.

WP3-T3-ST5 Expansion of the API for referencing/exporting of entries in other reference databases

Status: Delayed

Looking into the possibility of using the API of ENA to upload samples, however ENA changed their submission interface which might cause difficulties.

WP3-T3-ST6 Expansion of the API for queries from the dashboard WP4

Status: Delayed

A web application developed internally at SSI will form the basis of the dashboard application (both front- and backend). In the context of this web application several API's for querying the database have been developed in the second half of 2021. Further expansion of these API's is expected to take place in the first half of 2022. This activity will be closely synchronized with the development of the dashboard frontend which will take place in the same period.

WP3-T4: National data sharing pilot

Since the development of the BeONE data exchange system, the national data sharing pilot was preferred and slightly readjusted. In collaboration with FLI, isolates of *Salmonella* enterica serotype Dublin were exchanged between the BfR and the FLI, responsible for Food Safety and Animal Health respectively. Data was clustered using cgMLST based on ChewieSnake and SNP-Clustering and cluster congruency was determined. A publication on this work is planned.

WP4: Development of a user-oriented interface (dashboard) for analysis and sharing of epi and molecular data

The work in WP4 has been strongly affected by COVID-19 as well as changes in personnel at SSI, where the WP leader and two developers found other employment during the last year, and the following WP lead is now on paternity leave the next year. The positions have been filled with new competent staff, however, some rescoping is necessary. Additionally, significant work has gone into making the system GDPR compliant.

WP4-T1 Dashboard

Status: Ongoing

At present, metadata and (some) typing results can be viewed in table format (as part of the SOFI platform). NVI and SSI have initiated the development of epigenetic visualizations for the dashboard, which is expected to be finished and testable by BeONE partners before summer.

WP4-T1-ST1 Core display components

Status: Ongoing

Currently a data display table of data.

Visualization of phylogenetic trees is under development and will be based on cgMLST data and displayed by phylocanvas, which is an interactive tree visualization software for the web.

WP4-T1-ST2 Component integration

Status: Delayed

This subtask is awaiting further development in JRP24- WP4-T1-ST1.

WP4-T2 Back end analysis implementation

Status: Ongoing

Back end analysis implementation is based on the Bifrost framework being developed at SSI, as well as tools from the Center for Genomic Epidemiology at DTU (<https://cge.cbs.dtu.dk/services/>). The BeONE framework employs Dockerized Snakemake workflow management pipelines, the non-relational database MongoDB (<https://www.mongodb.com/>) and a Python-based set of tools to handle data flow from bioinformatic tools to database storage. This is complete except for the cgMLST implementation based on chewBBACA, which is still ongoing. The best way to do version control is still researched.

WP4-T3 Cluster analysis and collaboration tool

Status: Ongoing

We're still looking into the best cluster analysis methods and how to implement them.

Other projects that we have recently been working on have revealed that data sharing and collaboration in the area of genetic data is extremely complicated, even within the EU, due to GDPR and other regulatives. This means that systems that handle personally identifiable health data need to be designed from the ground up to be 'aware' of these regulatives. Thus, as a part of WP4, a security model has to be developed that deals with these issues, meaning that the scope of WP4 will grow, and as a consequence the scope of other areas will have to be adjusted. SSI and BfR have a plan for sharing the data, but it will need to be updated with more security when Kristoffer Kiil is back from leave (mid-end 2022).

WP4-T4 Data sharing front end

Status: Delayed, but ongoing

Due to personnel changes, as well as the experiences described above, we are rescoping the data sharing system.

WP5: Dissemination, Testing, Evaluation and Sustainability

WP5-T1 Dissemination

Status: Ongoing

A documentation effort of the backend system has been prioritized. Code organization, containerization and strict observation of separate development, testing and production environments, has the goal of stable and in turn portable code.

Later on, detailed instruction manuals will be provided. Specifically: local installation of the BeONE system, user instructions for data input and output, as well as guidelines for data interpretation, sharing etc. (much of this will be output provided by the respective WPs).

WP5-T2 Continuous Testing and Feedback

Status: Ongoing

The initial testing plan has been revised and discussed among WP4 (development) and WP5 (testing).

Although the BeONE system itself is not ready for user tests by the BeONE partners (other than SSI) until spring 2022, continuous testing is ongoing through the SOFI platform. This platform is the National data sharing platform in Denmark, which is being developed as a collaboration between the

Danish public health and Food authorities. This platform is the basis for the BeONE platform, and thus much of the testing is performed in parallel.

The testing that has been performed so far on the platform includes continuous user interface testing, which has been performed on more than 500 sequences, and associated metadata, between the two Danish authorities. Continuous debugging has been performed with regards to mapping of QC results, typing results (e.g. species, subspecies, MLST, serotype), metadata etc., personalized views (table format), filtering of results and metadata, searchability within data (metadata and results), export of results (metadata and analysis results).

For now, the testing of upload to the system (automatic and manual) is still pending as well as some analysis features are pending development (for instance cgMLST and visualizations such as trees and epicurves). All of this is expected to be developed and tested during spring/summer 2022.

WP5-T3 Final evaluation

Status: Delayed

The final evaluation is postponed to autumn 2022, as the project has been extended.

WP5-T4 Sustainability

Status: Ongoing

Key requirements for sustainability of the dashboard and analysis system have been identified as good documentation of the system, and an open source organization around the system to carry on the collaborative work after the project ends.

At the end of the project a sustainability document will be created, describing the possibilities.

WP6: Management

WP6-T1 Management

Status: Ongoing

We have started monthly meetings for all involved in BeONE. Meetings to discuss particular parts of the project where all interested are invited and also smaller meetings for discussion specific tasks in WPs.

The leadership has changed again as Kristoffer Kiil is on paternity leave the next year. Two colleagues from SSI have taken over his part as project lead and WP lead.

WP6-T2 Communication

WP6-T2-ST1 Kickoff meeting

Status: Completed

WP6-T2-ST2 2nd Annual Meeting

Status: Completed

The second annual meeting was initially postponed due to the COVID-19 situation and with high hopes that it could be held as a physical meeting in the fall. As it was realized this was not an option, the meeting was instead held as a teams meeting on October 28th. The Meeting included a thorough review on all WPs, as well as a keynote from Mirko Rossi on the EFSA platform.

WP6-T2-ST3 3rd Annual Meeting

Status: Pending

The third annual meeting will be postponed until early autumn 2022 as the project has been extended.

WP6-T2-ST4 Development hackathon

Status: Canceled due to COVID-19 crisis and the difficulties in meeting face-to-face.

WP6-T3 Data Management

Status: Ongoing

The shared data used for WP1-2 and for testing in WP5 is placed at the NVI server SAGA and where the BeONE pipeline also is being set up.

Other data has also been shared between institutes for different tasks.

3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8) (several categories may be applicable)</i>
24	D-BeONE.1.1	Report on the state-of-art	M30	M39		Public D-BeONE.1.1 Report on the state of the art Zenodo https://zenodo.org/record/5155571#.YUC8GzhDtM3 Scope changed to avoid duplication of work with ORION, and mitigate delays due to COVID-19. Delivery date changed to wait for ORION delivery fall 2020.	10
24	D-BeONE.1.2	Finalized BeONE dataset	M32	M48		Delays due to COVID-19	3

JRP/ JIP code	Project deliverable number <i>(Original number, if different from the actual one)</i>	Deliverable name <i>(Original name, if different from the actual one)</i>	Delivery date from AWP 2021 (month)	Date delivered on Project Group (month)	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date (month)	Comments <i>Please mention: public or confidential, the Zenodo reference, reason and justification of delay (for instance COVID-19), other comments</i>	Proposed category* <i>(1 to 8)</i> <i>(several categories may be applicable)</i>
24	D-BeONE.2.2	Final Outbreak detection algorithm	M46	M48		Public (link available later this month)	4
24	D-BeONE.4.1	Back-end analysis pipeline	M36		M53	Delayed due to COVID-19	4
24	D-BeONE.4.2	Web input system	M36		M54	Delayed due to COVID-19	4
24	D-BeONE.6.1	Initial data management plan	M30	M33		Public https://zenodo.org/record/5497853#.YToRjxlxdaQ	8

* Categories of Integrative activities : 1. Design and implementation of surveillance and control activities; 2. Harmonised protocols and applied best practice; 3. Databases of reference materials and data, incl. metadata; 4. Standardised data formats, aligned data analysis for interpretation of surveillance data; 5. Sharing and communication of surveillance data; 6. Sharing of best intervention activities; 7. Prevention: aligned use of facilities and models; 8. Other (please specify);

Milestones

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
24	M-BeONE.1.1	State-of-the-art completed	M30	Yes		
24	M-BeONE.1.2	Collected dataset	M30	Yes		
24	M-BeONE.1.3	Curated WGS dataset completed	M32	No	M51	Delayed due to COVID-19 crisis and constraints in hiring personnel
24	M-BeONE.1.5	Clustering congruence analysis completed	M48	No	M54	Plan adjusted and delayed due to COVID-19 crisis and constraints in hiring personnel
24	M-BeONE.2.2	Outbreak detection algorithm -provisional version	M42	Yes		
24	M-BeONE.3.1	Agreement on minimal and optimal set of metadata	M28	Yes		
24	M-BeONE.3.2	Finalized evaluation of data sharing experiences	M34	Yes		
24	M-BeONE.3.3	Implementation of data structure	M34	No	M52	Delayed due to database development
24	M-BeONE.3.4	Finished implementation of controlled data entry	M36	Yes		

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
24	M-BeONE.3.5	Plan for ontology implementation	M36	Yes		
24	M-BeONE.3.6	Implementation of API for import of data	M36	No	M52	Plan adjusted, still delayed due to personnel changes at SSI
24	M-BeONE.3.7	Data porting from an existing pipeline	M42	Yes		
24	M-BeONE.3.8	Application of the selected ontology system(s)	M48	Yes		
24	M-BeONE.3.9	Data porting from at least one further pipeline	M48	No	M52	COVID-19 and personnel changes
24	M-BeONE.3.10	Expansion of the API for export functionality	M48	No	M54	Delayed due to personnel changes
24	M-BeONE.4.1	Initial requirement list from workshop at kick-off meeting	M26	Yes		
24	M-BeONE.4.2	Implementation plan	M28	Yes		
24	M-BeONE.4.3	Prototype dashboard	M32	No	M53	Being redone due to personnel changes
24	M-BeONE.4.4	Plan for data sharing system	M34	Yes		

JRP/JIPCode	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP 2020	Achieved (Yes/No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
24	M-BeONE.5.2	Yearly sustainability document	M36	No	M60	Will be combined with yearly sustainability document for Y6. Not prioritized due to delays in other activities.
24	M-BeONE.5.3	Initial test plan	M28	Yes		
24	M-BeONE.5.4	Overall evaluation at 2nd annual meeting (workshop)	M40	Yes		
24	M-BeONE.6.1	2nd annual meeting	M40	Yes		

4. Publications and patents

Publication title and DOI reference	Is OHEJP acknowledged?	Is it a Green Open Access? If yes please provide the embargo length and the manuscript release date	Is it a Gold Open Access? If yes please provide the processing fees (in €)
Prediction of antimicrobial resistance in clinical <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> isolates from whole-genome sequencing data 10.1007/s10096-020-04043-y https://zenodo.org/record/4249355#.X6UnVWhKjcc	YES		3825 €

Additional output

The code that is being developed is available on github as described in the DMP. As the code is work in progress it will be continuously updated.

Outcomes

With BeONE we are building a platform where the goal is to enable data sharing between different institutes. Furthermore, we are testing different pipelines used for analysing foodborne bacteria at the different partner institutes to gain insight of how comparable the methods are. We are also testing different clustering strategies. All these will help the community to be able to work together across institutions and countries more easily than currently possible.

5. *Contacts and cooperation with national or international projects, organizations, networks, or national ministries*

BeONE is in contact with EFSA on streamlining cgMLST implementation, exploring if/how the BeONE implementation can be in accordance with the joint EFSA/ECDC database. For our 2nd annual meeting we had Mirko Rossi (EFSA) as a keynote speaker on the EFSA/ECDC data sharing system.

There is close cooperation between BeONE (particularly WP4) and the SOFI project. The SOFI project is a collaboration on a multi-actor data sharing platform between the Danish Food Authorities (Fødevarestyrelsen, not an OH-EJP partner), DTU and SSI.

6. *List of critical risks*

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	Yes
Delay in work plan execution	Yes
Conflicts within the consortium	No
Lack of commitment of partners	No
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	Yes
Poor intra-project relationship	No
Potential entry/exit of partners	Yes
Other risks (please describe)	?